

Country-specific Study Project

(Vol. 3)

Studies on China

Editor

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PREFACE

In 2013, Foreign Policy Research Centre (FPRC) launched a country-specific studies project. These countries hold a prominent position in the world and India is particularly sensitive about maintaining good relations with them so as to concentrate on development.

Each study seeks to highlight India's relationship in bilateral and international perspectives. The initiative began with Iran and has been followed by Studies on Pakistan.

The China project, the third in the series, is a timely initiative as China and India make an "Asian century". And in our venture, we have the support of national and international scholars who have agreed to come under the umbrella of FPRC to disseminate knowledge on China. We express our sincere gratitude to them for their cooperation in bringing this project to a successful culmination. They have always been a source of strength to us.

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Country-Specific Studies- CHINA

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CSS China
Contents

RESPONSES (pp.26- 57)

Articles :

(A) China's foreign policy in 21st Century

1. **China's Foreign Policy in the 21st Century**
Amb.Nihal Rodrigo (pp.58-64)
2. **China's Regional Diplomacy in Asia**
Dr. Xiaoyu Pu (pp.65-76)
3. **Chinese Sphere of Influence in the Asian Region**
Dr.Abanti Bhattacharya (pp.77-85)
4. **China's strategic objectives in Asia**
Balaji Chandramohan (pp.86-96)
5. **China's Quest for 'Ozeanraum'**
Rear Admiral Dr. S Kulshrestha (retd.) (pp.97-108)
6. **Is India A Key To Resolve China's Security Predicament In IOR?**
Brig Narendra Kumar (pp.109-115)
7. **China in the Indian Ocean: Strategic interests and policies**
Amrita Jash (pp.116-128)
8. **Competing for Influence:
Revival of China's Maritime Silk Road and India's Project Mausam**
Sylvia Mishra (pp.129-135)
9. **Learning To Be Loved:
An Initial Assessment of China's Soft Power Promotion since 2000**
Dr.Zhiqun Zhu (pp.136-150)
10. **Vietnam Overseas Students in China and
China's Soft Power in Vietnam**
-the Case Study of Vietnam Oversea Students in Yunnan China
Liu Peng (pp.151-174)

(B) China and Regional Groupings

1. **Whither the Shanghai Cooperation Organization?**
Stephen Blank (pp.175-188)
2. **China and SCO:
An Overview of The Emerging Geostrategic Dynamics**
Dr.Bawa Singh
Mohamad ArifMir (pp.189-207)

3. China and ASEAN

Carlyle A. Thayer, Emeritus Professor (pp.208-215)

4. Asean's Relations with China

Jatswan S. Sidhu, Ph.D. (pp.216-219)

5. Sino-Japanese relationship

and their interests towards ASEAN

Marc Pinol (pp.220-227)

(C) International Perspective on CHINA

1. Sino-Russian relations in the new period

SHI Ze (pp.228-233)

**2. China's Four-R Strategy toward the United States:
Resisting, Reducing, Replacing and Reordering**

Dr. Fei-Ling Wang (pp.234-250)

3. China and the US Hegemony in the Asia-Pacific Region

Dr. José Guerra-Vio (pp.251-255)

**4. Identity Discourse and China's Relations
with the United States and Japan**

Dr Rex Li (pp.256-273)

**5. Xi Jinping Facing North Korea under Kim Jong-Un:
Policy Transformation with New Assumptions**

Shi Yinhong (pp.274-286)

6. SOUTH KOREAN PERSPECTIVE ON CHINA

Nitya Iyer (pp.287-295)

(D) China and INDIA

1. China and India: Time for Resetting the Relationship

Dr. Kerry Brown (pp.296-300)

2. INDO-CHINA RELATIONSHIP: A PRISMATIC VIEW

Dr. Manas Chakrabarty

&

Miss Sumita Saha (pp.301-324)

3. Sino-Indian Relations – trajectory they should take

Lt Gen PC Katoch (pp.325-333)

4. India and China: A "Pair" in the Making

Dr. Richard Rousseau (pp.334-342)

5. India: Mountains/Rivers in Perils and Eco-politics

Dr. ZHOU Lei (pp.343-351)

**6. Climate Change and the Quest for Hydrocarbons:
Indian and Chinese Energy Security Imperatives**

Dhanasree Jayaram (pp.352-366)

7. India-China Relations : The United States Factor

- Chaarvi Modi (pp.367-373)
8. **The Great Power relationships in East Asia :
Indian and Chinese perspectives**
Dr. Mahendra Gaur (pp.374-391)

(E) China's engagement with various Regions

1. **China's footprint in South Asia**
Amb. Harun ur Rashid (pp.392-400)
2. **Regional conflicts in South Asia: Role of China**
Dr. Bawa Singh
Mohamad Arif Mir (pp.401-421)
3. **China's Increasing Footprint in South Asia:
Implications for India**
Dr. Sanjay Kumar
& Dr. Mohammad Samir Hussain (pp.422-431)
4. **COURTING THE DRAGON:
Relations between the SouthEast Asian States and CHINA**
Jatswan S. Sidhu (Ph.D.) (pp.432-446)
5. **China's Venezuela Challenge**
Margaret Myers (pp.447-450)
6. **Kazakh - Chinese cooperation
in energy sector: geopolitical aspect**
Dr. Malik Augan (pp.451-460)
7. **China's Economic Engagement in Central Asia: An Assessment**
Dr. Gatikrushna Mahanta (pp.461-483)
8. **New Silk Road Economic Belt
and China's Central Asia Policy**
Dr. MA Bin (pp.484-487)
9. **The impact of the Middle East revolutions
on the Communist party in China**
Dr. Nadia Helmy (pp.488-505)
10. **Arab States Stances towards the unrest
in Xinjiang Province**
Hanan Kamal Abu Sekin (pp.506-518)
11. **The EU and China trade relations**
Moritz Rudolf (pp.519-523)
12. **The 'Re-Emergence' of China
in the Context of East Asian Regionalism**
Dr. José Guerra-Vio (pp.524-531)

(F) China's Domestic and Foreign Policies

1. **Rebalancing China's Economy**
Prof. Paul Armstrong-Taylor (pp.532-543)
2. **China's Foreign Currency Reserves
and its Sovereign Wealth Fund**
Dr. Richard Rousseau (pp.544-549)
3. **China's Successful Economic Statecraft:
Strategic Motives for Trade Liberalization**
Dr. José Guerra-Vio (pp.550-556)
4. **GOVERNANCE IN CHINA**

- Dr. Ritu Agarwal (pp.557-561)
5. **How China's Traditional Harmony Thought Affects Chinese Foreign Policies**
Professor Zhang Lihua (pp.562-568)
6. **China's Internal Dynamics and Great Power Compulsions in a Changing World Order**
Francis A. Kornegay, Jr. (pp.569-576)
7. **Xinjiang Unrest: Need for a New Look**
Arabinda Acharya (pp.577-585)
8. **"Factionalism and Succession in the CCP: Power Struggles at the Apex"**
Dr. José Guerra Vio (pp.586-606)
9. **China's Domestic and Foreign Policies**
Dr. Parasaran Rangarajan (pp.607-638)
10. **Nontraditional Security Threats and China**
Imran Ali Sandano (pp.639-650)
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(**Tan Chung**, born in 1929, was christened 'Asoka' by Rabindranath Tagore at Santiniketan when he was two months old. He attended Jiaotong University, Shanghai, obtained MA & Ph.D in History (Delhi University), D.Litt. honaris causa (Visva-Bharati). He retired in 1994 from Jawaharlal Nehru University as Professor of Chinese Language. From 1971 to 2004, he served at various times as Head of the Department of Chinese and Japanese Studies of Delhi University, Chairman of the Centre for Afro-Asian Languages and Chairman of the Centre for East Asian Languages of Jawaharlal Nehru University, Professor-consultant and Head of East Asia Research in the Indira Gandhi National Centre for the Arts, New Delhi. He was the founder Co-Chairman of Institute of Chinese Studies, Delhi (1990-2003). He has written and edited 20 books in English and Chinese. He received the Indian civil award of Padma Bhushan and the China-India Friendship Award in 2010. He is the fourth Chinese (after Zhou Enlai, Tan Yun-shan and Wu Baihui) to be awarded 'Deshikottama' (the highest honorary degree) from Tagore's Visva-Bharati University in 2013. He is also an Honorary Academician of Yunnan Academy of Social Sciences, Kunming, China.)

Interview

1. How do you visualize China's Role in the Emerging World Order in the wake of Asia's Rise and the West's Decline

I think in the next quarter of a century there will be only a relatively stronger Asian economy vis-à-vis a fairly stable Europe and United States which will shrink in size, of course, not decline. China may emerge as the largest economy quantitatively, but not the strongest economy qualitatively. Her per capita income will still lag behind scores of other countries. There will be two great bottlenecks in the Chinese development. First, the scarcity of resources will persist especially in oil, natural gas and water. Over dependence on external supply of energy and

overseas market for manufacturing goods will not be a perfect permanent solution. Second, the problem of an ageing population will constrict development. The dismal example of Japan is already a warning. Much will depend on how well China can transform the entire space of her territory into a comfortable supporting base for her huge ageing population with increasing demands of higher living standards.

We live in two worlds, as described by the famous *New York Times* columnist, Thomas Friedman: one of order, and another of disorder. A developing, universally moderately prosperous China will greatly stabilize the *world of order*, so will be a developing, universally moderately prosperous India. The stable and smooth development of China will, for a long time to come, face serious challenges from internal and external quarters which would wish chaos to return to the country that had been ravaged by Western imperialism for a century and has enjoyed half a century of peace and development.

The world is at a cross road, we see no clear “Emerging World Order” in the immediate future. In all the three arenas of global tension China finds herself difficult to play a proactive role. She is avoiding any involvement in the *cool war* between the US and Russia. She is watching the US-sponsored *World war on terror* with keen interest as hundreds of Chinese citizens (the Uighurs of Xinjiang) have joined the camps of the Al Qaeda and ISIS. However, a direct involvement in this US-led world war on terror may be detrimental to China’s own cause of multiracial unity and harmony. There is the ambivalent Obama move of *pivoting to Asia*, with Washington trying to encourage Asian nations and Australia to counterbalance the emerging Chinese giant on one hand, and busying in US-China dialogues and befriending Beijing on the other. China has determined to strengthen her naval forces and consolidate her influence over the maritime region which had been the “South China Sea” for many centuries until China became a victim of the Western “gunboat diplomacy” from mid-19th century onwards. As China steadily increases her maritime power, the US will have to loosen her encirclement around China and the current antagonistic sentiments against China on the part of Vietnam and the Philippines will weaken consequentially.

2. According to Joseph S. Nye, “[In today’s age] success depends not only on whose army wins, but also on whose story wins”. This comment remains especially pertinent, with China attempting to ‘improve its story’ to the rest of the world – primarily through the use of soft power. How have these initiatives played out? Have they contributed towards a more positive global image of the PRC?

China has been hypnotized by Joseph Nye’s theories on “soft power” and led to the garden path. Whereas Nye and other scholars have made it crystal clear that “soft power” is different from self-strengthening force

and is aggressive in nature, the Chinese have persistently mis-translated “soft power” as “*ruanshili*软实力/soft strength”, not calling a spade a spade as “*ruanqiangli*软权力/soft power”. As a result, the Chinese Communist Party document defines culture as “soft power” and Chinese government thinks it a good way to export Chinese culture to rescue China from her current dilemma of constantly being misinterpreted, even demonized, in the international forums. In my opinion, China is objectively lowering her status of a *civilization state* to play the power game of nation states which will not only not succeed, but ultimately weaken her civilizational standing in the world. The earlier China frees herself from the misleading influence of Joseph Nye the better for her to emerge as a great civilization state of the 21st century.

3. “Building A New Type of Major Power Relationship between India and China”. (similar to a framework for U.S.-China relations that, since last year’s meeting between Presidents Obama and Xi) has been the refrain in recent times. Chinese emphasis now is on the use of words like Asian nations,Asian culture,friends,neighbours, historical and civilisationalties,partners in economic development,interdependence of relationship.Is it a change of heart or a part of a strategy to wean India away from US ?

I understand the question but don’t like the way it is framed. Yes, the Chinese leader, Xi Jinping, has advocated a “New Type of Major Power Relationship” between China and USA while the Obama administration is responding only half-heartedly. The essence of this equation is China’s quest for China-US parity and harmony which is handicapped by the “American triumphalism” in international affairs.

Incidentally, in his opening remarks in the India-China summit talks in New Delhi on September 18, 2014, Indian Prime Minister, NarendraModireiterated “a climate of mutual trust and confidence; respect for each other’s sensitivities and concerns; and, peace and stability in our relations and along our borders”. These words, in a way, truly reflect what China has wished Sino-US equations to become. There is a feeling in China that the US attitude towards China falls short of a respect for China’s sensitivities. Perhaps, there is similar feeling in India about the Chinese attitude towards India. There is the Confucian adage of “*jisuobuyuwushiyuren*己所不欲勿施于人” (do not do unto others what you don’t want done to you). I am sure if China were aware of what we are discussing she would definitely respond to what Prime Minister Modi had wished, viz., respect for India’s sensitivities and concerns as she is keenly wishing the US to do the same to her.

As India never consciously or unwittingly leans towards the US in an antagonistic equation vis-à-vis China, there is no question of China’s wanting to *wean India away from the US*.

China's highlighting the "Asian" identity is not a recent phenomenon. When Deng Xiaoping talked to Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi in Beijing in 1988, he highlighted the importance of China and India to make an "Asian century". What people generally don't realize is China's most prominent position in the world of having 14 land neighbours. The present Chinese leadership is particularly sensitive about maintaining good neighbourliness which is vital for China to concentrate on economic development. There is a popular Chinese saying of "*yuānqīnbùrújīnlín*远亲不如近邻" (The close neighbour is more important than one's dear and near staying afar). Maintaining good neighbourliness has been the permanent rule of China's foreign policy.

All what I have said just now is not the crux of China-India relationship. I have a whole theory of China and India being the civilization twins of the "Himalaya Sphere" having established their affinity even before the inventions of the identities of "China" and "India". We can use a famous Chinese Chan/Zen/Dhyana adage "*Nizhong you wo, wo zhong you ni*你中有我，我中有你" (you in me and I in you) to summarize the millennial interconnectivity between China and India. I think we need to educate the policy-makers and ruling elites of both the countries about this. I am glad to see that an increasing awareness of this relationship is reflected in the recent visit to India by the Chinese Chairman Xi Jinping.

4. China is a great power and wants to grow greater and greater. But China has "Few Friends but More Rivals." It is quite surprising that in East and South East Asia, almost all countries in the region have problems with their relations with China. With some of them, it has serious territorial disputes over small patches of land. How can China assure its peaceful rise ?

Again, the formulation of this question has reflected insufficient understanding of China and her environment. While I have partially answered this question already, let me make two points. First, within the present Chinese territory there are two of the earth's five greatest rivers (the third greatest river, Yangtze, and the fifth greatest river, Huanghe/Yellow River) and all the ten greatest rivers on earth are international waters except these two possessed by China alone. Moreover, these two great rivers have originated from the same place, flowed apart for thousands of miles and finally got reunited along the sea coast. They drew the contours of a huge sphere on earth for the innumerable tribes and communities living in the two river valleys to establish a super state, and this is the story of how China was created.

What does this mean? It means that from its inception, humanity has done far better on the land of China than anywhere else in living together and uniting together, in creating friendship and harmony between humans and humans. According to historians like Angus Maddison and

others, during the last two thousand years, the super state of China has embraced from 1/6 to 1/3 of humanity in various historical periods.

Second, as the world history shows, neighbours fighting each other and destroying each other has been a normal international behaviour, but what has happened in China is constant invasion of neighbours into China, not vice versa, and the foreign invaders have ultimately become Chinese to make China grow bigger and stronger. If you bear in mind these two realities, you would not have asked the question in the way you have asked.

I do not agree that China has *few friends and many rivals/enemies*. Is Vietnam China's "rival/enemy"? If you go to China and meet the Vietnamese there, or if you go to Vietnam and meet the Chinese there you will find this question irrelevant. Similarly, those who trumpet China and India as "rivals/enemies" have to visit India and China to see how the two peoples have warmly loved each other. Why is it surprising that China's neighbours in East Asia and Southeast Asia, even South Asia, Central Asia, and Russia, have problems in their relations with China? When there is friendship, contacts increase; when contacts increase, problems crop up. If there is no love between husband and wife, they maintain a cold peace and a *problem-free* relationship which is not desirable, certainly not ideal. If they love each other intensely, they shower affection towards each other, but also quarrel not infrequently. China's having problems with her neighbours is a reflection of her having a close relationship with them.

You mention the territorial dispute which is an issue I feel very strongly. Ideally, every country should behave like a "civilization state" which expands vertically without coming in conflict with neighbouring states. But, in our so-called *modern* and *civilized* world, almost every country behaves as a "nation state" which knows only horizontal expansion, clashing with neighbours and scrambling for spatiality. As each territorial dispute has its specific background and circumstances, we should not generalize. But, we can take up the China-India "territorial dispute" for discussion.

It is common knowledge that if you have not *governed* a piece of land you cannot claim it your "territory". Now, the keen constants of China-India border dispute are the two young governments: the People's Republic of China born only in 1949, and the Republic of India born only in 1950. They are claiming those remote Himalayan peaks more than 5,000 metres above sea level where life cannot sustain – even a blade of grass does not grow, and they have never governed those peaks. Anyone with common sense will agree with me that such territorial disputes are imaginary and bogus, and unworthy of pursuing by any great civilization – certainly not China and India. If you have no right to claim the territory, then where is

the territorial dispute? If there is no territorial dispute between the People's Republic of China and the Republic of India, the border problem is not a problem. The fact is there has never been any border between China and India. According to me, there is no need of any demarcated border between China and India. China and India have been living trouble-free without a border for thousands of years. If a "border" is a necessity in modern politics, let us conceive one, more in our minds than on the land (particularly not on the snow-capped peaks where no blade of grass grows). The most uncouth and unwise thing for China and India to do is to waste precious resources and sacrifice human lives to survey that forbidden height and demarcate it, let alone fighting for it and occupying it.

5. "A few years ago, China was driven in the past by intent. Today it is driven by capability." Do you agree with this statement?

I am sorry for my ignorance to such a sophisticated, superficially clever and actually meaningless observation. I don't know the cutoff point here, and what is meant by "a few years ago" – five, ten, or twenty? About China, especially China's development, I would like to make a few general observations. First, one hundred years ago, both China and India were societies of "lotus-eaters", and the Chinese ethos was dominated by the Indian spirit of "jivananda" (in Chinese, "*letian* 乐天/Heaven makes me happy"). It was the insult, invasion, repression and exploitation of the Western powers that have provoked China to become a "dragon" or "awakened lion", whatever you may like to describe. Today, the posterity of Rudyard Kipling is largely at ease, but China has carried forward Kipling's "white man's burden" in vengeance. It looks that China is now in the Victorian Era while Europe is in the Song Dynasty. Another topsy-turvy phenomenon is that China is the most ardent disciple of the German philosopher, Karl Marx, and China is breaking world record as the longest living Communist (not Confucian) state of the world. Those who think of "Communist China" as the spectre of our world must first put the blame on the 19th century Europe.

Second, it is perhaps easier to understand the Chinese society by comparing it with Japan and India. Japan is a model of societal civility, stability and harmony, but diversity and idiosyncrasy are wanting. India is thriving with diversity and idiosyncrasy but there are problems about her societal civility, stability and harmony. China is on the whole stable and united with atmospheric harmony while social tension is also high. There is a unique combination of unity of national will and political consensus on the one hand and thriving diversity and idiosyncrasy on the other.

Third, it is the Eastern perception that the government is the guardian, protector, patron and benefactor in sharp contrast to the American

notion that the government is the problem, not the solution. Government plays a dominant role in the development of Japan, India, and China, while the Chinese government role is especially dominant, providing an extra input in achieving an advantage in international competition from manufacturing goods to sports. It has become a Chinese culture that can be reproached but not replicated by other societies.

Fourth, I do think China enjoys the civilizational bonus of millennial sedimentation of wisdom and global social behaviour which has enabled her to emulate and catch up with the advancement of the times. Like Japan, China is good in imitation. Unlike Japan, China is not contented with aping, but maintains a strong quest for a newer and newer status and capability.

6. Even China is facing the menace of terrorism and the two countries should collaborate and root out terrorism. What steps should be taken to accelerate cooperation between the two countries to fight this menace?

There is consensus in China and India to root out terrorism, and no effort should be spared in a joint China-India fight against it. There are technical details I am not familiar with, but the experts of the two countries can sort them out. I think two things are essential for China-India collaboration in this front. First, both countries should jointly declare their zero tolerance for terror, especially “jihadist” terror. The large Muslim communities in both countries should champion it. Second, as millennial civilizations with profound wisdom and experience in promoting universal love, not hate, harmony, not conflict, China and India can join hands in making themselves the ideal land of sharing prosperity among all ethnic and religious communities. Till today, the Muslim communities of China and India are the least poisoned by “jihadist” fundamentalism and fanaticism. The two great civilizations should jointly develop a new civilization in which the word “clash” is taboo. A vigorous cultivation of the Chinese ideal of “*tianxiadatong*天下大同/grand harmony all under Heaven” and the Indian ideal of “*vasudhaivakutumbakam*/the world is one family” can help create such a new world.

7. The cultural intercourse between India and China was more than 2,000 years old. And the two great civilizations have contributed immensely to each other’s fund of goodwill and knowledge in various fields.How this legacy can be carried forward?

I have written many books and articles on this topic. Much as I want to answer your question as exhaustively as I wish, you will not have enough space for me to do so.

Let me just say one thing which does not answer the question fully, but is an important point. On April 26, 1924, the Indian poet, Rabindranath Tagore, visited the Fayuan Monastery of Beijing and enjoyed the performance of song and dance by Chinese youths in welcoming him. Tagore was in high mood. When he was asked to address the welcoming gathering he said (my translation from Chinese press report cited in the book by Professor Sun Yixue 孙宜学 of Tongji University, titled "*Taige'er: Zhongguozhiliu* 泰戈尔：中国之旅 / Tagore: A trip to China", Beijing: Central Compilation and Translation Press, 2013, pp. 63-4) :

"It is beyond my expectation that today I have discovered the China of my dream. The venue where I am in just now is especially the place that I have longed to visit. I have written lots of poems and essays that have not been very useful. Only today, when I am in China, have I found them valuable. Why? I have long wanted to complete the uncompleted tasks of the Indian masters who had come to China. I must share this responsibility with the Chinese youths. I also want to bring something back to India, something that is the fruit of the Buddhist influence in the past in China. The Indian gifts for China were Love and Peace, totally different from the political commodities of the West. The fruit of the Indian gifts for China in the past is also different. It is the quintessence of the Eastern culture."

I have two explanations for this Tagore quotation. First, these are not Tagore's original words, but my English translation of the Chinese translation of what Tagore had said in 1924. But, I think the ideas are truly Tagore's. I am glad that I have contributed my mite in restoring a part of history that Tagore had expressed such ideas in China which has not been included in the collections of Tagore's speeches and writings. This should be included. Second, for the last many decades till date I have seen Indian intellectuals wasting time on the controversy that Tagore was an "unwelcome guest" in China in 1924, some Indians even adding fuel to the fire of the controversy that has been kindled by Western scholars. It is a pity that no one has cared to go to China to dig out this reportage of Tagore's 1924 China visit (as well as many other reports) which demonstrates the real feelings of Tagore about his China visit.

My providing this Tagore quotation is not to criticize anyone, but to show the huge knowledge gap between what has happened in the cultural interactions between China and India and those who only observe from a distance yet thinking that they know everything. What I am saying is that much has happened between India and China for more than two thousand years but precious little have been done in inquiring and understanding this history and drawing the right conclusions, especially avoiding being misled by certain malignant Western scholarship that would not like to see India and China coming together.

Let me mention another example. There are nearly 500 caves at the Mogao grottoes at Dunhuang in Gansu Province which is now a famous international tourist spot. Inside these caves there have been frescoes painted and preserved for more than fifteen centuries some of which might disappear after a few decades. The total size of these thousands of wall paintings exceeds 45,000 square meters. The paintings are exquisite and rich narratives of ancient Indian legends. I have visited the site half a dozen times since it was open to public view in the early 1980s. I have found the cultural contents of these paintings not properly studied with virtually no Indian scholarly input. I think this is ridiculous. I would suggest a joint China-India endeavour in seriously studying this cultural treasure which, I am sure, will not only carry forward millennial India-China cultural affinity and friendship, but also enhance the contemporary Indian knowledge and understanding of India's own cultural past as well.

2. Xiaoming Zhang

Professor of international relations

at School of International Studies, Peking University, Beijing

(Zhang Xiaoming is a professor of international relations at School of International Studies, Peking University, Beijing, China, where he has taught since 1988. He was educated at Peking University (BA in 1985, MA in 1988 and Ph.D. in 1993). He has been working on Cold War history, China's relations with its neighboring countries, US-East Asia relations, and theory of international relations. He is the author of the following books in Chinese: *George F. Kennan's Containment* (1994), *Cold War and Its Legacy* (1998), *China's Relations with Its Neighbors* (2003), *English School of International Relations: History, Theory, and View on China* (2010), *An Introduction to the History of US-East Asia Relations* (2011). He was a fellow of Cold War International History Project at Woodrow Wilson Center (1994), fellow of Korea Foundation at Korea University (1998), Fulbright research scholar at Harvard University (1999-2000), guest researcher at Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (2000), visiting

professor at Chuo University, Japan (2005), and visiting senior scholar at London School of Economics (LSE) (2007-2008).

He is also Associate Editor ,The Journal of International Studies.)

Response to Questionnaire

1. How do you visualize China's Role in the Emerging World Order in the wake of Asia's Rise and the West's Decline.?

A: One of the rising non-Western powers in the international society.

2. According to Joseph S. Nye, "[In today's age] success depends not only on whose army wins, but also on whose story wins". This comment remains especially pertinent, with China attempting to 'improve its story' to the rest of the world – primarily through the use of soft power. How have these initiatives played out? Have they contributed towards a more positive global image of the PRC?

A: China has not much soft power in the world.

3. Beijing has expressed concerns that Washington is either encouraging its allies in the Asia-Pacific region to pursue maritime territorial claims against China or, at the very least, profiting from the sharply increased regional tensions that these disputes have generated. Do you subscribe to this view point?

A: Yes, that is true.

4. China is a great power and wants to grow greater and greater. But China has "Few Friends but More Rivals." It is quite surprising that in East and South East Asia, almost all countries in the region have problems with their relations with China. With some of them, it has serious territorial disputes over small patches of land. How can China assure its peaceful rise ?

A: That is too oversimplified. China has problems with some, not almost all of the countries in the region. China is only one party of those disputes and it is unfair to blame it for all the disputes.

5. "A few years ago, China was driven in the past by intent. Today it is driven by capability." Do you agree with this statement?

A: Partly true, and partly wrong.

6. A consensus is evolving in India that unlike other major global powers, China does not recognise India as a global power and does not show sensitivity to its core security concerns. As a consequence, China has replaced Pakistan as the nation's primary

security concern. Is it fair to say that both China and Pakistan embraced each other in order to contain and constrain India?

A. That is not true, China has been trying its best to balance its relations with the two countries.

7. . “Building A New Type of Major Power Relationship between India and China” . (similar to a framework for U.S.-China relations that, since last year’s meeting between Presidents Obama and Xi) has been the refrain in recent times. Chinese emphasis now is on the use of words like Asian nations,Asian culture,friends,neighbours, historical and civilisationalties,partners in economic development,interdependence of relationship.Is it a part of a strategy to wean India away from US ?

A. No.

8.How could Beijing, which expects the world to accept the “One-China” doctrine, be insensitive to New Delhi’s “One- India” policy?

A. Is there a "Two-India" policy? I have never heard of it.

3.ZhiyongXiong

Professor of China Foreign Affairs University

Beijing, China

The major publications:

The Contemporary Diplomatic History of China (co-author)

The Modern History of China’s Diplomacy

The 60-years Sino-American Relations

Questionnaire

1. How do you visualize China’s Role in the Emerging World Order in the wake of Asia’s Rise and the West’s Decline.?

Xiong: Personally I don’t agree with the concept of the west’s decline. At least the US continues to grow. China is still the largest developing country with many internal problems to be solved. Meanwhile, China should and is able to work closely with other nations to keep the world peaceful and stable, to make international rules fair and to promote economic growth.

2. According to Joseph S. Nye, “[In today’s age] success depends not only on whose army wins, but also on whose story wins”. This comment remains especially pertinent, with China attempting to ‘improve its story’ to the rest of the world – primarily through the use of soft power. How have these initiatives played out? Have they contributed towards a more positive global image of the PRC?

Xiong: The positive image of China is contributed mainly to the story of the quick economic growth and poverty reduction in China. In fact, its policy of promotion of her soft power doesn’t work well. She shouldn’t “improve its story” but should improve the channels for other peoples to reach a real China.

3. Beijing has expressed concerns that Washington is either encouraging its allies in the Asia-Pacific region to pursue maritime territorial claims against China or, at the very least, profiting from the sharply increased regional tensions that these disputes have generated. Do you subscribe to this view point?

Xiong: I don’t regard the American policy toward this area as an encouragement of the maritime disputes because any conflicts will not favor her general interests. But the US may like to take advantage of a limited tension in order to balance China’s growing influence because it has still been afraid that China will challenge her hegemony position in the world.

4. China is a great power and wants to grow greater and greater. But China has “Few Friends but More Rivals.” It is quite surprising that in East and South East Asia, almost all countries in the region have problems with their relations with China. With some of them, it has serious territorial disputes over small patches of land. How can China assure its peaceful rise ?

Xiong: China is a big country but not a great power yet though it is her target. That comment on the relationship between China and countries in East and Southeast Asia is a kind of distortion which can be corrected by a simple calculation of countries. The peaceful rise means that China doesn’t want to achieve a hegemony position as other hegemony powers did through wars in history and doesn’t expect any arguments and disputes with other countries to be solved by force either. But China never says that she will not use soldiers whenever her basic interests are damaged by force.

5. "A few years ago, China was driven in the past by intent. Today it is driven by capability." Do you agree with this statement?

Xiong: No. As I said that the Chinese leaders are fully realized of our capability, which is exaggerated by foreign media or institutions sometimes. In fact, China is driven by her will to solve her headaches.

6. A consensus is evolving in India that unlike other major global powers, China does not recognise India as a global power and does not show sensitivity to its core security concerns. As a consequence, China has replaced Pakistan as the nation's primary security concern. Is it fair to say that both China and Pakistan embraced each other in order to contain and constrain India?

Xiong: India is a global power without doubt. We work together as BRICS partners. As I said, China is very sensitive to the territorial dispute with India but China doesn't want to be involved in India's disputes with others. As the same, China doesn't expect India to be involved in China's disputes with others. This is decided by Chinese philosophy. As to the relationship between China and Pakistan, we share many common interests and positions. We have cooperation in many fields but never try to make joint efforts to damage interests of the third country. It is a pity that India has territorial disputes with these two countries because of the British colonial rule in history. We don't expect Pakistan to be involved in our disputes with India while we keep distance from their dispute with India.

7. . "Building A New Type of Major Power Relationship between India and China". (similar to a framework for U.S.-China relations that, since last year's meeting between Presidents Obama and Xi) has been the refrain in recent times. Chinese emphasis now is on the use of words like Asian nations, Asian culture, friends, neighbours, historical and civilisational ties, partners in economic development, interdependence of relationship. Is it a part of a strategy to wean India away from US ?

Xiong: When President Xi suggested this concept when he met President Obama, a new type of relations between powers means in his mind the special relationship between the hegemony power and a growing power because these two kinds of powers often fought a hot or a cold war to gain dominant position in history. In the current

world, there is only one hegemony country: the United States. Later on this term was used occasionally to cover improperly all the relations among powers. Its original meaning is lost. None of India or China is hegemony. It is not good to define our relationship by this term.

8. How could Beijing, which expects the world to accept the “One-China” doctrine, be insensitive to New Delhi’s “One-India” policy?

Xiong : These two policies are essentially different. “One-China” is focused on the Taiwan independence movement though the constitutions of both the mainland China and Taiwan insist on one China. It is mainly an internal problem of China and foreign countries are not expected to be involved in it. “One-India” is focused on the territorial disputes between China and India. This is a bilateral problem with China as a party. In fact, this issue is so sensitive in both India and China that it is better to be solved properly between them.

4. Commodore R Seshadri Vasan, Indian Navy (Retd)

**Director Chennai Centre for China Studies,
Head, Strategy and Security Studies, Centre for Asia Studies, India
Director, Asian Secretariat World Boderpol**

(An alumnus of the Defence Services Staff College and the College of Naval Warfare, India, Commodore (Ret'd) Vasan has a distinguished career spanning over 34 years. His wide ranging appointments both at sea and ashore include Command of warships, appointment in carrier borne wing of INS Vikrant, command of long range Maritime Reconnaissance/ASW squadron, member examiner of the Aircrew Categorisation and Standardisation Board (AIRCATS), Chief Staff Officer (Operations) at Southern Naval Command and a Director at the Naval Aviation Staff at NHQ in charge of Air Ops and Training. He commissioned a major naval air station close to the east coast of India and commanded another air station on the west coast. He was on the faculty for over two years at the prestigious College of Naval Warfare that trains senior level officers from all the three services.

He was on deputation to the Indian Coast Guard from 2000 to 2003 as the Eastern Regional Commander with maritime jurisdiction in the Bay of Bengal including the Indo Bangladesh maritime border and the Indo Sri Lanka maritime boundary. He was charged with the task of I4SR, EEZ surveillance, anti-piracy, Search and Rescue, anti-poaching and marine pollution prevention.

Since his retirement he has been writing regularly for various magazines, newspapers and websites.. He has been conducting workshops and delivering talks for International delegates in many parts of the world on maritime issues,

strategy, security and aviation issues. He was selected for an International Visitor Leadership Programme on 'National Security and Media' in US for three weeks in Aug-Sep 2009. He presented a paper at Chatham house in October 2012 and also interacted in the British Parliament with the All Party Parliamentary group on Transatlantic and Asian Security. He was on a security panel at a Harvard University programme Taipei. He has interacted with international audience and presented papers at Sydney, Melbourne, London, Kiel, Taipei, Seoul, Kunming, Colombo, Johannesburg, Rome, Lisbon, Marseilles and other places also in India.

In addition to being the Additional Director Projects and Development, he steered the Maritime Security Programme at the Observer Research Foundation, a major think tank in India. After three successful years in ORF, he joined the Center for Asia Studies as Head, Strategy and Security Studies in October 2008. Besides being the Director of the Asian Secretariat of the World Borderpol(WBO) and served as President, Navy Foundation Chennai chapter for three years. He was also the Chairman of the Aeronautical Society of India, Chennai charter for two years. He is on the Board of Advisory Group at the Madras University and Stella Maris College; a visiting faculty at the Indian Maritime University, HIET, AMET the first private maritime university in India and the Great Lakes Institute of Management.

*After having served as an Executive committee member of the C3S, since inception, he has recently taken over as the Director of the **Chennai Center for China Studies** a think tank that specializes in China affairs.)*

Response to Questionnaire

1. A consensus is evolving in India that unlike other major global powers, China does not recognise India as a global power and does not show sensitivity to its core security concerns. As a consequence, China has replaced Pakistan as the nation's primary security concern. Is it fair to say that both China and Pakistan embraced each other in order to contain and constrain India?

The answer to this question cannot be in black and white. There are many shades of grey in Sino Indian relations which includes the Pakistan factor. From all the indications including the recent visit of Xi Jinping, during which there were major border incursions, it is clear that China wants India to have bilateral relations on its terms mostly on economic terms by holding other issues hostage to economic engagement.

There has been hardly any transparency in sharing of China's perceptions on border issues while India has shared its perceptions. This is being seen as a hindrance at any efforts towards CBMs. Pakistan considers China as an all-weather ally as this friendship has stood the test of time for decades with military, economic and political relations being nurtured well by the leaders of both the countries. From the point of view of Pakistan, it needed friends to contain its bigger brother India. A willing China which was looking to engage India's neighbours has obliged

Pakistan by its unconditional support. This action by China conforms to the diktats of Chankya's ArthaShastra which advocates befriending the neighbours of one's adversary in a big way by all means.

So in the scheme of things, Pakistan, Maldives, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Bangladesh fall in the category of the immediate maritime neighbourhood of India which needs to be brought under China's influence.

It was former Defence Minister George Fernandez who publicly said that China is the No 1 enemy. While this was undiplomatic, there is a lot of truth in China being the No 1 adversary for India. The alliance of China and Pakistan appears to be always at work against the interests of India.

2. Lou Chunhao, a strategic affairs expert said "Now, China under [President] Xi Jinping is paying more attention to 'going west', and as India 'looks east', there will be more interaction [in the Indian and Pacific Oceans]."

One hopes that this is indeed the case. Yes, both the countries are not interested in going to war and are concentrating on the economic development. However, China is at least two decades ahead of India in terms of its overall national prowess. It is not today that China is eyeing the rich energy and other resources in Africa, Middle East and other countries near and far. Where ever there are resources and opportunities, China has ensured that its long term strategic interests are pursued by pulling out all stops. India on its part though has a declared Look East policy for the last two decades plus, has not really matched the capability of China or intent in protecting its interests.

In fact it is perhaps the failure of China or the discontent in the countries of investment (as in Myanmar) that makes these countries look at India and not the system in India that is yet to deliver. Despite the soft power and also the kind of governance; east or west, India has not been assertive in its foreign policy aspirations to serve its long term strategic interests. With the change in the Central Government post May 2014, there appears to be some semblance of effort to change all that and make India relevant in the global comity of nations. It all depends on how the present Government persists with its policies and gives a new dimension to its foreign policy objectives.

3. *With China's maritime presence in the Indian Ocean set to expand along with its economic interests, the question for India — and its strategic community — was how to engage with this new reality?*

The major manifestation of China's look west policy was in the form of Maritime Silk Routes through which China wants to revisit the past and also build strategic alliances through the commercial route. This would compliment the economic engagements which are already on a high in Africa, Middle East and other Indian Ocean countries. India has likewise initiated the project Mausam which is a similar effort to revisit the maritime glorious past from the days of the spice route that enabled trade, commerce, spread of religion and exchanges in the countries that were connected by the trade winds during North East and South West monsoons. All these initiatives are being viewed as efforts by China as well as India to gain strong foot hold in the Indian Ocean. As of now there are no prizes for guessing who will win the race unless India changes the ways it deals with both its internal and external policies.

China is banking on its economic prowess and flexibility that puts it ahead of India in being able to invest at will in any part of the world. This economic leverages in the long run would provide the strategic dividend including basing/turn round facilities in many of the ports that would serve PLA-Navy's forward posturing and presence in the IOR. The recent example of the conventional submarines berthing in Colombo on the eve of the visit of the Chinese President Xi Jinping is indicative of the grand design and the shape of things to come.

As for as India's responses are concerned, it will be a big challenge to match China's ability. However, India enjoys a great geographic advantage in the Indian Ocean and has the strongest Navy in the IOR. China and India are both well aware of the soft belly of China which is in the Sea Lines of Communication as the energy and trade flow from and to China virtually passes under the watchful eyes of the Indian Maritime Forces. The Andaman and Nicobar which houses the Tri Services Command provides advantage of a well-equipped forward post and a C4ISR hub that can monitor all that which passes from any of the straits on the east including Malacca, Sunda and Lombok Straits. The options for India therefore are obviously to work on its strengths to address the weakness of China in the Indian Ocean. This has to be done while economic engagements are not hindered. It is all about being prepared for a contingency by drawing up those plans and rehearsing them.

4. A stray remark by Indian PM Modi on a recent visit to Japan about some countries' expansionist inclinations, which was widely read as a criticism of China, has led to speculations. Can "Sino-Indian ties in any way be counterbalanced by the Japan-India friendship" ?

At one end of the scale, this can be viewed as 'Games nations play' as nations vie for influence and try to achieve a strategic balance while pursuing national interests. The visit of Prime Minister Modi to Japan comes in this category and was a calculated one. While with his visit to Nepal and Bhutan, he wanted to gain the trust of India's Himalayan neighbours who share border with China, the visit to a Pacific power Japan which is reinventing itself has long term implications. The intention was also to tell the rest of the world, (including China specifically,) that India does not hesitate to get in to those alliances which will help India even in economic investments as Japan looks to diversify its investments. So on one hand it is to ensure that there is diversification of the economic investments without depending on just China and on the other, it is also again as if India was conforming to the prescriptions of Arthashastra which prescribed friendship with the neighbours of one's adversary.

With the traditional mutual mistrust between India and China and the perception that most of the economic relations are in China's favour, both India and Japan have a lot to gain in terms of long term dividends. China would be uncomfortable with the expanding nature of India's relations with Japan and USA and has always held that these alliances are orchestrated to stale mate China in the Indo Pacific area. So the future of this delicate balancing as India looks east depends largely on how well planned these manouvres are at the strategic, political and economic fronts.

5. "Building A New Type of Major Power Relationship between India and China" . (Similar to a framework for U.S.-China relations that, since last year's meeting between Presidents Obama and Xi) has been the refrain in recent times. Chinese emphasis now is on the use of words like Asian nations, Asian culture, friends, neighbours, historical and civilisational ties, partners in economic development, interdependence of relationship. Change of heart or a part of a strategy to wean India away from US ?

There can hardly be any doubt that this contributes to the stated philosophy of China for a peaceful periphery albeit on its terms. (including by use of force). How else does one explain the border intrusions during the visit of Xi Jinping to India?

Mere statements or assertions about an Asian identity are unlikely to find any audience unless it is matched with concrete actions on the ground that brings about greater confidence. None of the maritime neighbours in South China Sea and the East China Sea are comfortable with the aggressive posturing of China. India is uncomfortable with the unresolved land borders for decades and China has no inclination to come to an agreement soon. On the contrary, it continues to keep testing India by stapled visas, border incursions, and new claims every now and then.

While it is true that both China and India are great civilisations from the past, the fact is that the Chinese approach to work on its terms on its own schedule of calendar is a discomfiting one. The recent visit despite a lot of publicity and hype did not bring about any confidence in the Indian public about the true intentions of China. Even the economic investments did not even match the Japanese investments in the country. Unless, China matches its rhetoric with action on the ground for CBMs, the loud proclamations will continue to sound hollow and countries which have any kind of dispute with China will not buy its sales pitch. All this can change if China and India are able to resolve the only issue of border dispute that the two nations have not been able to resolve despite a war in 1962 and about 18 meetings since.

6. *Relations with China retain elements of both “cooperation and competition.” As prime minister, Modi says he will vigorously resist China’s “mindset of expansion.” He has also made clear that India under his leadership will do business with China, given the development imperative. Will Modi be able to balance a growing security dilemma vis-a-vis China against the magnetic appeal of its market as a spur to domestic economic growth?*

The Indian experience with China as far as economic engagement is concerned is that it is one sided and totally loaded in favour of China. India has come to realise that it has lost more by allowing China to enter Indian markets in a big way.

The unethical practices of Chinese businessmen in collusion with Indian counterparts have resulted in a big drain in the economic dividends. The recent report of the Chinese crackers flooding the market through the

back door has spelt doom for the indigenous industry sustained for centuries. The case is similar when it comes to mining of raw materials. It is evident that India has to change the rules of the game with China by diversifying its investments in to other countries willing to do business and also opening up its markets with due checks and balances. India should not fight shy of being branded a protectionist economy at least when it comes to dealings with China.

7. *Border remains central to Sino-Indian relationship. Unless and until the prickly boundary issue is resolved amicably between the two nations, no substantial progress can be achieved on any other bilateral front. Do you agree with the viewpoint?*

It is evident from some of the detailed responses above, that this indeed is the case. China and India both recognise that this is the core issue that brings in impediments in otherwise possible excellent relations. However, the reluctance of China to work on achieving a resolution has only increased the suspicion of India which feels that there would be new claims and China will keep the pot on the boil. It is puzzling as to why China continues with this unproductive approach that has only negative fall outs for both sides.

The reasons for Chinese claims on Arunachal Pradesh and certain other border areas and frequent border incursions citing difference in perceptions does not bring any credit to a country that aspires to be number one by replacing USA one day.

8. *Could Beijing, which expects the world to accept the “One-China” doctrine, be insensitive to New Delhi’s “One-India” policy?*

We have come a long way from the days when China was accused of supporting secessionist activities. At least as of now there is belief that China does not indulge in this anymore nor is there any evidence to support this charge. As India has gone out of its way to accept Tibet as an integral autonomous part of China and has no intentions to interfere in the internal affairs of China, the same is expected from China. To be fair to China, it is unlikely to meddle in the internal affairs of India nor is it likely to engage in such activities for balkanisation of India. Whether it would work with Pakistan on such an agenda is doubtful.

9. *Is it correct to assume that India’s orientation toward China will be influenced in part by the role of the United States? It is said: If US policy toward China is wobbly, or if America is simply less present in Asia than it used to be as the Obama administration*

steers the ship of state without a strategic rudder, Indian calculations naturally will be affected.

This has to be seen at many levels. In the short term may be even up to two decades, USA will continue to be a dominant power and will remain relevant in global affairs. Yes, there is a reduction in the emphasis with which US rushed to a trouble spots and tried to take charge. This is not just a story of lack of leadership but more a realisation of the pitfalls of undesired intervention that is trying for the public and wasteful in terms of national expenditure.

The recent phase at which it is trying to intervene in Syria and Iraq can best be described as the actions of a nation on decline which is circumspect of its own power and influence.

Every nation needs to work on how it wants to achieve its national interest and India is no exception. With the new leadership in place, there appears to be some method in the ways of the new government. The actions are lack of them cannot be totally dependent on the course of action pursued by USA which is on decline. India would need to follow what suits it best. So by not being a party to sending its forces to Syria/Iraq/Afghanistan etc., it has steered clear of such adventurism. With the third largest Muslim population that is well integrated in the concept of a nation called India, there is hardly a need to antagonise this section of Indians by participating in misadventures of the west. The choice of rebuilding the war ravaged Afghanistan or Iraq by using its skilled and unskilled man power is the right one.

10. How do you visualize China's Role in the Emerging World Order in the wake of Asia's Rise and the West's Decline?

With the economic prowess, political system, a growing military, there can be hardly any doubt that China will start increasing its engagement in different spheres around the world. The current focus is on economy and protecting its core interests. The climate for China to be a relevant world power is just right provided that China builds on its ability to read signals without mistakes. However, it is the receptivity of the comity of nations to such a thought that at the moment is hardly encouraging. China is still viewed by a large number of nations with suspicion. The description of China as an "Expansionist State" does not behove of a responsible global power which wants to lead.

The leadership in China is indeed strong and the system has a reputation for delivering. It is these strengths that China needs to work

towards to remove the perceived and real obstacles. This is not beyond the leadership of China and can be achieved by some deep introspection. With great power comes great responsibility and China is in a position to understand this dimension of power play. However, there are no doubts that China will continue to be a super power of relevance in the coming decades and will play a dominant role in steering the global affairs.

(5) Dr. Gregory J. Moore

Associate Professor of International Relations in the Political Science Department at the School of Public Affairs at Zhejiang University in Hangzhou, China

(Gregory J. Moore is currently an Associate Professor of International Relations in the Political Science Department at the School of Public Affairs at Zhejiang University in Hangzhou, China. His research interests include international relations (IR), IR theory, Chinese foreign policy, Sino-American Relations, East Asian IR/security, foreign policy analysis, and the North Korean nuclear issue. He is a member of the (U.S.) National Committee on United States-China Relations.

Prior to his coming to Zhejiang University, he taught at Eckerd College, the University of Denver, Metropolitan State University of Denver, Renmin University of China, and a number of other Chinese universities. He also served for two years as Assistant Director of the Center for China-United States Relations at the University of Denver. He did his doctorate at the University of Denver's Josef Korbel School of International Studies, formerly the Graduate School of International Studies (international politics, comparative politics, China/East Asia), his master's degree at the University of Virginia in Charlottesville, Virginia (foreign affairs), and his bachelor's degree at Concordia College in Moorhead, Minnesota (art).

At Zhejiang University he teaches graduate and undergraduate courses including: "International Relations Theory," "Research Methods," "International Relations History and the Causes of War," "Foreign Policy Analysis," and "American Politics and Foreign Policy." At Eckerd College he taught, "East Asian International Relations;" "Political Science Research Methods;" "Government and Politics of China;" "Japan: Government, Politics, Foreign Policy;" "Introduction to Comparative Politics;" "East Asian Comparative Politics;" "The Pacific Century" (or the Political Economy of East Asia and India), "The Struggle for Modern Tibet;" "International Relations Senior Comprehensive Exam," etc.

He is currently working on a book on Sino-American relations, and just completed an edited volume titled, North Korean Nuclear Operationality: Regional Security and the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Regime (Johns Hopkins University Press, 2014) with Graham Allison, David Kang, Andrei Lankov and others, and a book on the international relations thought of Reinhold Niebuhr, which is under review. His work has appeared in journals such as International Studies Review, Foreign

Policy Analysis, International Relations of the Asia-Pacific, the Journal of Contemporary China, Asian Perspective, the Journal of Chinese Political Science, the Journal of Asian Studies, Human Rights Working Papers, Issues and Studies, etc.)

Response to Questionnaire

1. How do you visualize China's Role in the Emerging World Order in the wake of Asia's Rise and the West's Decline.?

First, I am not sure the west is declining (unless you mean in relative terms). The US has a decent growth rate, and Western Europe is not going to disappear. Having said that, China's role is not clear at the moment. As Jeffrey Legro has argued, it will largely depend on what China will want, and what kind of a power China will become. We don't know that yet. It will also depend on how China is treated, which will depend on politics and trends in the established powers, as well as on China's own behavior.

2. According to Joseph S. Nye, "[In today's age] success depends not only on whose army wins, but also on whose story wins". This comment remains especially pertinent, with China attempting to 'improve its story' to the rest of the world – primarily through the use of soft power. How have these initiatives played out? Have they contributed towards a more positive global image of the PRC?

I agree with this statement. China has tried hard to improve its image with Confucius Institutes. There is no conclusive data that "proves" this has worked or not, but in the long run it will probably have a nominally positive impact. Overall, China does not have much soft power. It was doing much better in the eyes of the world from 2003 to 2009 or so, but its image in the world has gone down since 2010 when it turned to a more robust (aggressive) foreign policy in the Asia-Pacific. I believe its shift to a more robust foreign policy since 2010 has undone whatever good its soft power initiatives have done.

3. Beijing has expressed concerns that Washington is either encouraging its allies in the Asia-Pacific region to pursue maritime territorial claims against China or, at the very least, profiting from the sharply increased regional tensions that these disputes have generated. Do you subscribe to this view point?

I do not subscribe to this point of view. The US and its allies are responding to China's more robust/assertive foreign policy claims in the region. Is the US profiting from the tension? Yes and no. Yes, in that China's moves strengthen US alliances and make the US a more attractive partner for almost everyone in the region. No, from the perspective that this is going to cost the US and its friends much more in defense in coming years, and may have a deleterious effect on economic growth in the region if this arms racing and tension gets out of hand.

4. China is a great power and wants to grow greater and greater. But China has "Few Friends but More Rivals." It is quite surprising that in East and South East Asia, almost all countries in the region have problems with their relations with China. With some of them, it has serious territorial disputes over small patches of land. How can China assure its peaceful rise ?

It should go back to its foreign policy that it pursued in the two decades prior to 2010. Reassure its neighbors, dispense with the 9-Dash Line, make a border deal with India, soften its position on the Diaoyu Islands, redo the electoral laws in Hong Kong's 2017 elections to give people there a real choice of candidates, give up its claim to Huangyandao (so close to Philippines' shores), and negotiate a peace with Vietnam over the Spratleys, where it does have legitimate claims. It won't do most of these things, but if it did, it would find a much more peaceful neighborhood, and it might even woo Taiwan to return to the Mainland (the events in Hong Kong have had a bad impact on Taiwan's views of China).

5. "A few years ago, China was driven in the past by intent. Today it is driven by capability." Do you agree with this statement?

I don't find that statement really helpful. If it just means China has more capabilities, well yes. But key then and now are its intentions, as I said above (what will China want?).

6. A consensus is evolving in India that unlike other major global powers, China does not recognise India as a global power and does not show sensitivity to its core security concerns. As a consequence, China has replaced Pakistan as the nation's primary security concern. Is it fair to say that both China and Pakistan embraced each other in order to contain and constrain India?

I think that is fair to say.

7. . “Building A New Type of Major Power Relationship between India and China” . (similar to a framework for U.S.-China relations that, since last year’s meeting between Presidents Obama and Xi) has been the refrain in recent times. Chinese emphasis now is on the use of words like Asian nations,Asianculture,friends,neighbours, historical and civilisationalties,partners in economic development,interdependence of relationship.Is it a part of a strategy to wean India away from US ?

I think so. China doesn’t want to give up its border claims against India, and yet it worries that its security environment has worsened in recent years and that now India too has joined the US orbit. It hopes it might coax India to be on China’s side, or at least not go against China.

8.LouChunhao, a strategic affairs expert said “Now, China under [President] Xi Jinping is paying more attention to ‘going west’, and as India ‘looks east’, there will be more interaction [in the Indian and Pacific Oceans].”

With China’s maritime presence in the Indian Ocean set to expand along with its economic interests, the question for India — and others — was how to engage with this new reality?

I think that India, along with the US and China’s other neighbors, should continue a policy of engaging with China, and yet work hard to persuade China that it should return to its pre-2010 good neighbor policy, that the present policy is bound to only worsen China’s security environment and strengthen the resolve of China’s neighbors to work together to stand firm against any Chinese advances. This is not in China’s interest. China may not be persuaded, as it sees anti-Chinese conspiracies at every turn. In this case, India should work together more closely with Japan, the US and others who believe holding China accountable and encouraging China to be a responsible stakeholder in the international system is best for China, the region and the world. I am not talking about an anti-China alliance, as that would only make things worse. But China claims to want a peaceful rise. My suggestion is to take China at its word. Its actions will reveal its intentions and unless its actions violate its stated goal of a peaceful rise, India and other powers should do all they can to help China facilitate a peaceful rise.

9. How do you view Chinese perspective on North Korea's nuclear proliferation?

I believe China's position is not so different from that of the US. China does not want to see a nuclear North Korea and has done much to thwart North Korea in its attempt to go nuclear. China is very unhappy with Pyongyang, though it does not desire to let its true feelings be known for a number of reasons. One interest China has that the US and other powers are not as concerned about is the problems a collapsed NK would have for China. China is just as concerned about a collapsed NK as a nuclear NK, so it has to balance these two interests. Still (and I have a couple of articles and a book on this issue), I am certain China is 100% opposed to an operationally nuclear NK, and on NK nuclear proliferation. It is a threat to China for many reasons, including the fact that it could start an arms race in East Asia that might push South Korean, Japan and even Taiwan to go nuclear.

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Response to Questionnaire

1. How do you visualize China's Role in the Emerging World Order in the wake of Asia's Rise and the West's Decline.?

We should interpret China's evolving role in world affairs by looking inside China first. Domestic order and stability is a prominent feature of Chinese strategic thinking, with perpetuation of Chinese Communist Party (CCP) rule the primary prerogative.

Chinese strategic thinking sees developments take shape over long time horizons. One of the key lessons from China's four-millennia long dynastic cycle is that China as a unified political entity tends to break apart when politically unstable. Modern Chinese history is replete with examples that continue to influence contemporary Chinese strategic culture: the decline of the Qing Dynasty from the Opium Wars, through the Taiping and Boxer Rebellions to the Wuchang Uprising and Xinhai Revolution of 1911; the tumult of the Republic period from Yuan Shikai and the warlord era to the Japanese occupation and the civil war; and the upheaval of the Mao Zedong era where Mao's attempts at national governance based on the principles of guerrilla warfare and permanent revolution led to the misery of the Great Leap Forward and the chaos of the Cultural Revolution.

The structural changes to the Chinese economy initiated by Deng Xiaoping through the 1980s moved the CCP away from the orthodoxy of Mao Zedong thought and implicitly established a new social bargain with the Chinese people that has become the legitimising foundation of CCP rule: the people will enjoy increasing standards of living in exchange for their continued acquiescence to one-party rule. Economic growth in the range of 7-10% per annum is pivotal to this grand bargain. Political instability, whether internal or external, is a threat to economic growth and by extension the perpetuation of CCP rule itself.

There are several schools of thought as to what this implies for China's future global role. There is the benign rise theory, which argues that China is likely to be a status quo power given that its economic miracle has depended upon its participation within the American hegemonic order. There is an intermediate position which suggests that China is engaged in "soft balancing" against the United States through subtle moves to check the expansion of American power in regions adjacent to China's frontiers, in cooperation with Russia. Finally, there is the aggressive rise theory, which argues that China's interests have outgrown the current hegemonic order and thus China will seek to change the rules of the game.

China's more assertive foreign policy behaviour since the global financial crisis of 2007-08 suggests that it is indeed beginning to challenge American hegemony. We have seen China establish what is euphemistically called the "Beijing Consensus", through which it has established a series of priority access resource procurement deals with countries around the world. The Beijing Consensus offers developing countries an alternative to the structural adjustment conditionalities inherent to development assistance from the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund. In contrast, Chinese resource procurement deals promise no intervention in the domestic politics of partner states, sweetened by infrastructure contracts, in exchange for direct Chinese access to desired commodities outside of US dollar denominated international markets.

This strategy makes sense in light of growing and/or predicted scarcities in key resource feed stocks, locking in more stable price and supply arrangements without having to compete on volatile international markets with other players. It also creates a dynamic that is critical to hegemonic transition: a challenge to the hegemony of the US dollar as global reserve currency. Because global trade has for the most part been denominated in US dollars, countries have previously had to acquire holdings of US dollars in order to participate. The global demand for US dollars as a fiat currency has allowed the US to finance its global military commitments through deficit spending to a degree that no other state can match. Nowhere is this more evident than in the impact of petrodollar recycling in international energy markets.

The Beijing Consensus presents a direct challenge to the US dollar as global reserve currency by removing trade interactions from dollar denominated markets and thus decreasing the necessity of participants to acquire US dollars, thus undermining the capacity of the US government to undertake deficit spending. The establishment of a BRICS development bank as a competitor to the World Bank, as articulated in the *Fortaleza Declaration* from the July 2014 BRICS summit in Brazil, and China's deepening bilateral trade partnership with Russia are important developments that are illustrative of this growing challenge to the rules of the game.

2. According to Joseph S. Nye, “[In today’s age] success depends not only on whose army wins, but also on whose story wins”. This comment remains especially pertinent, with China attempting to ‘improve its story’ to the rest of the world – primarily through the use of soft power. How have these initiatives played out? Have they contributed towards a more positive global image of the PRC?

If we look back on the beginning of the American global hegemony immediately following World War Two, its soft power message of liberal freedoms and democratic governance held tremendous appeal in a number of areas across the world. Ho Chi Minh even argued that the constitution of a Vietnamese state independent from France should be modelled on the US constitution.

It is not clear that China has a similarly compelling positive soft power vision to sell, beyond offering an alternative to American hegemony through the Beijing Consensus. What we do see is a model of South-South cooperation on offer, articulated in Hu Jintao's “Harmonious World” doctrine that privileges, at least rhetorically, non-intervention in domestic politics and mutually beneficial economic outcomes. Rather than offering an explicit prescription for governance and the good society based on capitalism and liberal democracy, as does the American soft power vision, China's soft power hook appears to be its distinction from what is perceived in many places to be overly aggressive US foreign policy

behaviour in the War on Terror era, coupled with resentment over economic austerity regimes instituted through structural adjustment conditions associated with loans from the Bretton Woods institutions.

We are seeing a renaissance in official interest in China's dynastic history as a source of ideational inspiration, particularly in the revival of Confucianism in official discourses and the proliferation of government-funded Confucius Institutes in countries around the world. Indeed there is much to admire about Chinese history and culture, however the CCP's complicated relationship with this cultural legacy, particularly in relation to Mao Zedong thought and the attack on traditional social structures during the Cultural Revolution, makes it difficult for the Chinese government to draw too heavily on this as a source of soft power appeal.

What this highlights is the difficult task faced by the CCP in melding together a coherent legitimising paradigm from the often contradictory influences of China's dynastic historical traditions, its Mao-era legacy and globalised capitalism.

3. Beijing has expressed concerns that Washington is either encouraging its allies in the Asia-Pacific region to pursue maritime territorial claims against China or, at the very least, profiting from the sharply increased regional tensions that these disputes have generated. Do you subscribe to this view point?

Regional states have different ideas about how to resolve the region's maritime disputes. The United States favours multilateral dialogue as its preferred vehicle for dispute resolution, using existing multilateral forums as a trap to pressure the Chinese from multiple sides. It should not be surprising that we see balancing behaviour against China by Southeast Asian maritime states, as they can maximise their leverage against China through multilateral engagement and court American naval assistance, as the United States is the only power that can credibly defend their claims against Chinese incursions.

By contrast, the Chinese preference is to resolve disputed claims bilaterally with rival claimants, a strategy that maximises Beijing's leverage and attempts to freeze the US out of the process. Hence the importance of the Sino-American competition over dominant regional integration initiatives; the regional architecture that comes to predominate in the medium term may go some way toward defining a possible outcome to maritime disputes.

4. China is a great power and wants to grow greater and greater. But China has "Few Friends but More Rivals." It is quite surprising that in East and South East Asia, almost all countries in the region have problems with their relations with China. With some of them, it has serious territorial disputes over small patches of land. How can China assure its peaceful rise ?

Hu Jintao's "Harmonious World" doctrine was an attempt to assure neighbouring states of China's benign intent, however, as my response to question one articulates, it may now be more difficult for China to present a credible defence of itself as a benign power. This is not just a question of the Chinese government's intent, but an unavoidable feature of the international politics of hegemonic transition.

5. "A few years ago, China was driven in the past by intent. Today it is driven by capability." Do you agree with this statement?

Eventually a rising power with global economic interests needs a military with the force projection capability to defend those interests. We are witnessing the beginning of this process in China's naval modernisation. China's area denial strategy for protecting its Pacific Ocean maritime flank simultaneously challenges the United States' position as maritime hegemon in East Asia and has allowed Beijing to adopt an increasingly assertive approach to substantiating its claims in the South China Sea and East China Sea.

One could argue that the Chinese national project post-Deng Xiaoping has been driven, in part, by a desire to make up for China's "century of shame" and return the country to its traditional position of prominence in world affairs. This project culminated in the 2008 Beijing Olympic Games, which was the "new" China's coming out party. Now, as argued above, China appears to be positioning itself to challenge the rules of the game, so to that extent, I can agree with the statement.

6. How do you view Chinese perspective on North Korea's nuclear proliferation?

There are diverse views on North Korea from among the actors within China's foreign policy elite. Traditionally, North Korea has been viewed as a strategic buffer zone between US forces positioned in South Korea and the China-DPRK frontier along the Yalu and Tumen Rivers. Indeed China entered the Korean War when that frontier was encroached upon by UN forces. The buffer zone concept extends much further back into history than the Korean War, as the Korean Peninsula has historically been the primary invasion pathway for belligerent armies from Japan. There is also a view that North Korea soaks up the attention of a segment of US forces in East Asia that would otherwise be mobilised directly against China. The strongest argument for supporting North Korea is to prevent a collapse of the Kim regime and the North Korean state, which could precipitate a large refugee exodus from the DPRK into China's northeastern provinces in Jilin and Liaoning. Such an influx could jeopardise social stability and economic development in these regions, which are not as prosperous as China's eastern coastal provinces. From this perspective, the DPRK could be seen as a net strategic asset.

Opinions have begun to diverge from this view in light of North Korea's 2009 and 2013 nuclear tests, which have prompted some within the Chinese foreign policy elite to suggest that the DPRK has become a net strategic liability to China. According to this argument, North Korea's nuclear gambit raises the risk of regional conflict, which would be a disaster for China's goal of 7-10% annual economic growth and the CCP's grand social bargain with the Chinese people. In addition, political instability associated with the North Korean nuclear problem creates investment uncertainty that has slowed the development of China's northeastern provinces. There is also a perception that North Korea has caused the Chinese government to lose face through some its recent provocations in 2013, which Pyongyang proceeded with in spite of warnings from Beijing.

China and North Korea enjoy a symbiotic relationship. North Korea is heavily reliant on China as the foundation of its economic development and conduit to the global economy. American protestations about Chinese leverage over the DPRK notwithstanding, North Korea does occupy an important strategic space that the Chinese government cannot take for granted. The two countries maintain an ongoing alliance relationship, however they are no longer "as close as lips and teeth" as Mao Zedong once proclaimed, and the Chinese security guarantee for North Korea is far from iron-clad.

7. What is China's role in international politics of climate change?

China is a significant actor in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) conference of parties, where it has been the historic leader of the Group of 77 negotiating bloc representing the interests of the Global South. In the UNFCCC China has consistently held a position based on the doctrine of "common but differentiated responsibility," whereby the countries of the developed world, who are responsible for the overwhelming proportion of greenhouse gases already emitted into the atmosphere through industrial processes, should take the lead in reducing their emissions and assist developing countries with the cost of greening their economies. In the meantime, they argue that newly industrialising countries should be allowed to raise their greenhouse gas emissions in order to reach a higher stage of development, before all countries of the world begin reducing their emissions together from a position of greater developmental equality. The United States and other developed countries have argued against this position, claiming that their economies will lose competitiveness if they are subjected to emissions reduction obligations that their competitors in the developing world are not. This negotiating deadlock within the UNFCCC is not immune from the broader politics of the Sino-American rivalry and the machinations of hegemonic transition that I described above, which will make it difficult for the negotiating parties to reach agreement on binding emissions reduction targets for all states by the pivotal twenty-first conference of parties meeting in Paris next year.

This does not mean that China is a recalcitrant actor on climate change. Becoming “green” is in China’s self-interest. China has significant problems with environmental degradation and is acutely vulnerable to climate change impacts, both of which threaten the country’s economic vitality and thus its political stability. Indeed addressing climate change may be an existential challenge for the CCP, given the link between economic growth, raising living standards and the state of the environment in China. The Chinese government’s challenge is to maintain high economic growth rates while greening the economy, a task which has been a key focus in the government’s current *12th Five Year Plan* for the national economy. China’s impending roll-out of a national carbon price mechanism, models for which are currently being trialled across six different provinces, could be a game-changer in terms of the flow-on pressure it exerts on China’s trading partners to establish their own carbon pricing schemes.

8.How do you look at Geopolitics Of China-Russia Energy Relations?

Sino-Russian energy relations are becoming closer due to energy security considerations and a mutual convergence of interests in resisting American pressure. In terms of energy security, China is a net energy importer and by buying oil and gas from Russia it can reduce its vulnerability to fluctuations in the American-dominated maritime oil trade and to disruptions to maritime deliveries which arrive en route through several vulnerable sea lines of communication from the Middle East. In turn, Russia gets to diversify its customer base away from reliance on European buyers, which is timely given the current geopolitical complications with NATO involving Ukraine. American pressure on Russia itself is driving Russia closer to China. American economic sanctions against Russia provide an incentive for Russia to sell its energy resources to customers through bilateral deals denominated in currencies other than the US dollar. Here Russia and China can collude in eroding the power of the US petro-dollar, thus undermining the economic foundation of American power.

Articles

(A) China's foreign policy in 21st Century

1. China's Foreign Policy in the 21st Century

Amb. Nihal Rodrigo

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China's Security Policies

China's current security policies are influenced by aspects which reach deep into the past, as well as evolving contemporary developments in the complex global situation.

In September 2014, Chinese President Xi Jinping visited India, Sri Lanka and Maldives in South Asia. A scheduled visit to Pakistan was postponed. The discussions he held, gave some indication of China's security concerns and its emerging policies.

Current events within the extensive territory of the Peoples Republic of China are, of course, very much part of its security concerns as well. Security policies within its own territory require considerable care as any use of armed force against the PRC's own widely-spread citizens has to be very much a last resort. Excessive local military action would also

negate PRC unity within its diversity and even precipitate foreign intervention.

Developments within China's own borders are in a state of flux with some ethno-religious complexities as in areas such as the Xinjiang Uighur Autonomous Region, and to a lesser extent, in the Tibetan Autonomous Region. China perceives that Uighur complexities in Xinjiang derive to an extent from external sources.

Current demonstrations in the Special Administrative Region of Hong Kong, have been termed as "Occupy Central with Love and Peace" and were earlier seen as less of an external threat and one requiring "home-grown remedies". The continuity of the protests and the high youth engagement in it has now however shown potentially more dangerous security complications as well. China's official "Peoples Daily" newspaper has described them as "linked to foreign and anti-Chinese forces". The Chinese "Global Times" reacted to foreign media criticisms of excessively violent State control of the young demonstrators by reporting that the Western press was seeking to "stir up extremism in Hong Kong society", to break unity, and even separate the Region from China. China has strong opposition to what it describes as the threat of "the Three Evils of Extremism, Terrorism and Separatism". This was demonstrated in the assistance it rendered to Sri Lanka when the island was threatened by the deadly extremist ethno-centric, separatism terrorism of the Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam.

Use of water cannon and tear-gas against the demonstrators has reduced the number of participating youth blocking access to vital areas of Hong Kong's corporate and state activity but may not yet signify a complete end to the demonstrations. Diverse major leaders active in the demonstrations include Joshua Wong, a 17 year old leader of the student group, *Scholarism*, and a half-century old Law Professor at the University of Hong Kong Tai Yiu-ting.

The origins of the demarche could be traced back to August, when the official Standing Committee of the PRC's National People's Congress (NPC) and Hong Kong's Chief Executive, Leung Chun Ying declared intent not to accept nominees directly proposed by the people to serve as candidates for the Hong Kong Chief Executive's elections due in 2017. This was despite Hong Kong's Basic Law which indicates that nominees should be picked by "a broadly representative Nominating Committee, in accordance with democratic principles". Some

discussions have taken place with groups of protesters but with out acceptable conclusions.

At the time of writing, the protests have not ceased, although the numbers participating have dwindled. The Hong Kong security forces have had little alternative but to remove, what one writer described as “the resident demonstrators” and their obstruction of roads, to ensure safe access to vital economic areas including Hong Kong’s administrative areas and popular lucrative shopping and tourist centres. China’s newspaper, the People’s Daily concludes in a Report, that “while Hong Kong bears the brunt of the negative impact of the city’s street politics”, given its role “as a bridge between the mainland and the external world”, the PRC would also be affected.

China and Great Power Politics

In the so-called Cold War years , Great Power politics was linked very much with the rivalry between the two contrasting politico-economic systems of Capitalism and Communism. The United States of America and the Soviet Union were, respectively, the two dominant exponents of the systems, each with a significant number of supportive states. Many British, French and Spanish colonies were tied into the Capitalist system too. A dramatic demonstration of the systemic division then was Germany. It was divided into the German Democratic Republic (GDR) under Communism; and the Federal Republic of Germany (FDR) under capitalism. I had my first diplomatic assignment in the Sri Lanka Embassy in Bonn, then capital of the Federal Republic. The Great Power politics of the time and its system had dramatically then even led to the division of Germany’s capital Berlin, by the extensive Great Wall constructed separating East and West Berlin.

Then China, what is now the Peoples Republic of China (PRC), was also divided by aspects of the systemic differences between the Communist Peoples Republic and the territories of Hong Kong (then under British colonial rule), Macao (under Portuguese colonial rule) and Taiwan. Today, Hong Kong is part of the PRC as a ”Special Administrative Region”. Macao, a former Portuguese colony, is also part of the PRC on the same basis.

Following the end of World War II, and the gradual independence of colonial territories around the world, the United Nations Organisation with currently 193 independent States as members represents the current global situation. Five among the current members states are still being recognised as “Great Powers”, having Permanent Membership of

the Security Council and endowed with even power to veto and sabotage any decisions being taken in the Council. The 5 are China, Russia and the United States (the former lead states, respectively, of global Communism and Democracy) and colonial powers France and Great Britain . Japan and Germany were not seen fit, even following the end of World War II, as “defeated” states, to qualify for permanent UN Security Council membership and veto powers.

Military might is still considered a vital asset of the so-called Great Powers. Yet increasingly, the term Great Powers is used, largely if not universally, in terms of the economic impact and other subtle powers (inclusive of military might) they can utilize to influence other states and indeed world affairs. The military aspects do remain as well, but now in the background. There is no unanimity or any formality in assessments relating to Great Power politics. However, fancied generally as being among today’s most influential states, with economic clout, are also the United States, China, Japan, and to a lesser level, Russia, Britain and France.

China’s ascending economic strength has now been playing a major role in its rising influence and relations in Great Power Politics. In fact, China’s major economic partners are now the non-Communist United States and the European Union. Differing economic ideologies do not now constitute a bar to China’s cooperation with them, though some alarm bells may be ringing particularly with regards to matters of cyber connectivity, including the impact of the Chinese corporate group, Ali Baba on Western web-sites.

Economic aspects today are therefore the major factor in power and influence even though military strength still remains an influential factor as well. Religious movements now also do use military strength to establish their edicts but these are being resisted. Economic benefits now work at a bilateral level although here too exploitation of the weaker partners is not absent. General Motors, the mega US vehicle manufacturer, will be investing around \$ 15 billion in China to increase sales (and its own profits) in the world market, partly as it is cheaper to produce them in China.

In August 2012, the Asian Development Bank (ADB), had presented its rather prophetic (some Western economists even called it “ominous”) Report, “ Asia 2050: Realizing the Asian Century” at a Forum in Japan. Introducing the Report, the ADB President, speaking of the rising Asian Century indicated that it could not be one of development confined to

countries such as China, India, and Japan alone, but clearly “a century of **shared global** prosperity”. He had stressed also that building Asia’s regional development would also need “collective leadership, recognizing a concept of balance of power among all of Asia’s major powers” as well as also powers beyond the region as well.

The United States National Intelligence Council (USNIC) also presents regular Reports of forthcoming global trends. The Reports are based on a wide consultative process engaging academics, defence experts, economists and think-tanks. The USNIC report of last year entitled: “Global Trends 2030: Alternate Worlds” frankly indicated that “by 2030, China will probably have the largest economy, surpassing that of the United States a few years before 2030”. Meanwhile, China has, of course, already overtaken Japan, to be the second largest economy following the United States. China’s economic might, plus its reach and connectivity, are major factors in its progression in current Great Power Politics.

China’s Sphere of Influence in the Asian Region

Given the major significance and virtual credibility now being given, however grudgingly, to the so-called Asian Century, China’s traditional economic, political, cultural, even religious links in its neighborhood of Asia constitute a major foundation and a stage for its own rising spheres of influence and cooperation in the continent. China, at the same time, does have certain contentious bilateral issues in its immediate neighborhood. The bilateral benefits of cooperation with such countries need to be balanced as well. China has territorial disputes with South East Asian countries including Japan, Philippines, and Vietnam which, despite claims made, have been kept under control. However these do erupt strongly as they did over the establishment of Chinese oil rigs in seas under dispute with Japan; and in other issues such as the visits by Japanese Prime Minister Abe to war memorials which honour Japanese military personnel including those who were held to be responsible for many human rights violations during World War II.

Chinese President Xi Jinping paid visits to India, Maldives and Sri Lanka, all countries bordering on the Indian Ocean. Bilateral visits to each of these countries are vital for the implementation of current Chinese policies of securing spheres of influence in the Asian region. The 21st Century Maritime Silk Road initiative, recently launched, reinvigorates and expands, in the current context, benefits that China had been long securing from economic links across the Indian Ocean Region (IOR).

Such contacts can be traced even as far back as to the 15th century when the Chinese Muslim navigator, Zheng He and his huge fleets were moving across the IOR. In fact, Zheng He is reputed to have even touched the east coast of America well before Christopher Columbus and his much smaller fleet, according to the Australian researcher, Gavin Menzies.

President Xi Jinping wrote in a newspaper that the Maldives was also “an important stop of the ancient silk route” and that China “welcomes the Maldives to get actively involved in building the 21st Century Silk Road”.

In Sri Lanka, China has been collaborating in developing the port of Hambantota on the island’s southern coast which has been a major stop-over for vessels crossing the Indian Ocean. Sri Lankan ports and warehouses have also been major points for providing “break-bulk” facilities as well. Chinese assistance is being extended also for the establishment of Sri Lanka’s capital, Colombo, as a Port City. China’s current investment in the project is estimated to be at about \$ 1.5 billion.

China and Sri Lanka have announced establishment of a Joint Committee on Coastal and Marine Cooperation to explore feasibility and means of closer cooperation on essential ocean observation, ecosystem protection, marine and coastal zone management, marine security, combatting piracy and smuggling, and search and rescue operations.

Certain Western think-tanks, such as Booz-Allen-Hamilton have issued not too sober assessments of the Asian region and the Indian Ocean. Ed Snowden was also once a member of the think-tank. The development of a chain of ports across the Indian Ocean region, including Gwadar (Pakistan), Hambantota (Sri Lanka), Chittagong (Bangladesh) and Sitwe (Myanmar) in cooperation with China was described by the think-tank as a “string of pearls” to throttle India. Later, it came to be projected as “a necklace of thorns”. General J.J. Singh, a former Indian Army Chief has ridiculed the string of pearls theory. As Sri Lanka’s Defence Secretary, Gotabaya Rajapaksa has also pointed out, “throughout history, the Indian Ocean has been a major conduit of international exploration, migration and commerce” and that, currently, “the overall security and stability of the entire Indian Ocean Region is critical for the global economy”.

China’s Space Aspirations

The Office of the Chinese State Council, at the end of 2011, released a White Paper on China’s space aspirations outlining major objectives for

the period 2012 to 2017. It counted among its achievements the exploration of the surface of the moon's surface and satellite flights deep into space sending back signals to earth from millions of miles away.

The Report calls for efforts "to work wisely and skillfully" with its neighbours and others including the United States through bilateral and multilateral exchanges. Former Chinese President Hu Jintao, following his meeting with US President Barak Obama, in their Joint Statement in 2011 dealt with the need for deeper dialogue and interaction in outer space activities rather than clashes and disputes.

However, later that year, the Chairman of the US House Appropriations Sub-Committee which oversees funding and other aspects of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), apparently inserted 2 sentences into the document on funding legislation that prohibits joint scientific activity between the United States and China involving NASA. That legislation is reported to be enduring. The Chairman's rationale for the ban has included the following points: the US need not give China opportunity to take advantage of US technology; the US gains nothing in return from dealing with China on technology; and includes a question: Would the US have (had) a bilateral programme with (Russia's) Stalin?

In June this year, the US National Research Council (NRC) had released a report, "Pathways to Exploration - Rationale and Approaches for a US Program of Human Space Exploration". It had advocated the inclusion of China in international space collaboration. Zhao Weibin, a Researcher at the Academy of Military Science of the Chinese People's Liberation Army, in a July 2014 Report states that "reaching for the stars is one of China's dreams to realize the rejuvenation of the Chinese nation ". He regretted that unfortunately, there is competition between China and the United States at the legal, military and diplomatic levels . He therefore calls for "a new model of major power relations" between the two States in the face of "the common space security threats" they face and to "overwhelm the impulse of confrontation by the impetus of cooperation".

The concept of a new model of major power relations is being applied by China, as a major aspect now relating to many global issues which cannot be satisfactorily resolved unless some compromises are made for Consensus between China and the other major power rising, or risen.

2. China's Regional Diplomacy in Asia

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From October 24 to October 25, 2013, Beijing held a major conference on China's regional diplomacy in Asia. The meeting laid out some long-term goals of China's regional diplomacy. President Xi Jinping's speech catalogued the tools of economic aid, trade, security, and public diplomacy for China's regional strategy. According to Xi, China must strive to make its neighbors friendlier in politics and more cooperative in economy and security.ⁱ

While China continues to seek a benign leadership role in regional diplomacy, China's recent "assertive" diplomacy has generated wide speculations and debate in the international community.ⁱⁱ Because of the heightened tensions of territorial disputes, China seems to damage its cooperative relations with some regional countries. How do we understand China's regional diplomacy? Is China's assertive diplomacy unprecedented? What are the driving factors of the recent "assertive turn" in China's regional diplomacy?

China's Regional Diplomacy

In recent years China has implemented a “differentiated strategy” in regional diplomacy: for some regional countries, China wants to demonstrate its benign image as a regional leader; for other regional audiences, China might want to be feared rather than be liked. While reassuring some regional countries about its peaceful intention, China is also striving to maintain its credibility of coercion. During Hu Jintao's era, China formulated a diplomatic approach that stated: “big powers are the key; neighbors are paramount; developing countries are the foundation; and multilateralism is an important stage.”ⁱⁱⁱ This indicates that China considers great powers, neighboring countries, developing countries as three major international audiences.

China has been a predominant power in East Asia for thousands of years, and some Chinese regard China's leading status in the region as being natural instead of challenging the status quo.^{iv} The power asymmetry had shaped the relationship between China and the regional countries. In the historical tribute system, the neighboring countries demonstrated their respect to the Chinese empire, while China provided security and material rewards. The historical legacy of China as a regional leader has shaped contemporary debates on Chinese foreign policy. While China's official discourse always emphasizes China's benign intentions, some Western strategists have deep suspicions about China's long-term intentions. In his famous book *The Tragedy of Great Power Politics*, John Mearsheimer boldly declared, “A wealthy China would not be a *status quo* power but an aggressive state determined to achieve

regional hegemony.”^vOther scholars regard the power asymmetry between China and its neighbors as a key factor that have helped maintain a peaceful and hierarchical order in East Asia.^{vi} Chinese officials often emphasize “China does not seek a sphere of influence” and “The country does not intend to build an exclusive regional order and is not capable of doing so.”^{vii}

Today’s China is different from the historical Chinese empire as geopolitics in Asia has become more complicated. The United States, as a non-East Asian power, has become the dominant power in East Asian after World War II. As a leading power in the Asia-pacific region since World War II, the United States does not want to be pushed out of Asia by an exclusionary bloc. When China seeks an active regional role in Asia, it must handle its relationship with the United States carefully.

China’s Charm Offensive and Benign Leadership

China has been trying to create favorable international conditions for continuing China’s domestic growth while reducing the risk that other countries will see a rising China as a threat.^{viii} China has tried to reassure its neighbors that China is not an emergent threat but an opportunity. Some scholars conceptualize China’s policy toward Asian neighbors as that of “charm offensive” diplomacy.^{ix} The first wave of the charm offensive was launched in 1997 when Beijing declared during the Asian financial crisis that it would not devalue the Renminbi (RMB) and was reinforced a few years later when China proposed a China-ASEAN

free trade agreement. Xi Jiping's proactive regional diplomacy could be viewed as the second wave of charm offensive.^x

In 1998, China took an active and responsible role by maintaining the value of Renminbi (RMB), and China also voluntarily provided assistance to rescue its Asian neighbors. China's response to the Asian financial crisis was widely praised by the international community. Asian financial crisis was a transformative moment in China's foreign policy. After the Asian financial crisis, China started to be actively involved in regional diplomacy and to participate in many regional institutions. Initially the Chinese government was not seriously concerned about the Asian financial crisis until the Hong Kong dollar came under speculative attack in October 1997.^{xi}The Chinese government refused to devalue the Chinese currency.^{xii}During this crisis, China made a significant contribution in the number of US\$ 1 billion to the Thai support package. While economic interest was certainly an important driving factor for China's decision in response to the Asian crisis, the projection of a "responsible power" image was important in shaping the way China dealt with the crisis. According to the then Chinese Premier Li Peng, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) asked China to provide assistance to Thailand through IMF's medium, but the Chinese leadership insisted that China would deal with Thailand directly and provided assistance accordingly.^{xiii} China wanted to deal with Thailand directly because this might provide a good opportunity for China to improve its own image.

China's response to the Asian financial crisis was a "transformative moment" in Chinese foreign policy. Since the late 1990s China has changed its earlier position and has pursued a proactive policy toward regional integration. China now actively participates in most of the regional institutions in Asia-Pacific regions, such as ASEAN+1 (ASEAN and China), ASEAN+3 (ASEAN, China, Japan, and South Korea) and APEC. It has even initiated some new institutions in the region. After the Asia financial crisis, the Chinese elites started to think more about China's role in Asian community.

The trend of charm offensive continues during Xi Jinping's new administration. Xi's regional diplomacy is referred as China's "second wave" of charm offensive. At the October 2013 work forum, Xi Jinping identified a four-part philosophy to guide diplomacy toward such nations, centering on efforts to convey or realize *amity, sincerity, mutual benefit, and inclusiveness*. These are all positive features generally resonate with earlier approaches to nearby states. Regarding economic diplomacy, China proposes to build *One Belt and One Road* (yidaiyilu), which refers to the "Silk Road Economic Belt" and "21st Century Maritime Silk Road." These concepts were put forward by President Xi Jinping during his visit to Central Asia and Southeast Asia respectively in 2013.^{xiv} Regarding security order, speaking at a summit of the Conference on Confidence-Building Measures in Asia (CICA), Xi outlined his thoughts on the future of security in Asia. Xi's comments served a purpose as strategic reassurance. Chinese officials have identified CICA

as a key platform from which to broadcast a reassuring message for a regional audience. Xi's CICA address fits into an attempt by Beijing to re-energize its regional diplomacy over the past year.^{xv}

China's proactive diplomacy has generated a dilemma for many of China's neighbors. In economy and trade, China's neighbors increasingly expect their future relations to be tied to China. In terms of security, many countries continue to expect to rely on American alliance protection.

China's Coercive Diplomacy

China has tried hard to project a benign image in the region. However, many observers have argued that China has become more assertive. As a stronger China seeks to defend what it views as its territorial and maritime interests, it might increase the insecurity of its neighbors, who grow increasingly wary of China's long-term intentions.^{xvi}

We should not overestimate the degree of change in China's "assertive" turn. China's coercive diplomacy has a long history, and its coercive image is not new. While China wants to build an overall positive image, China might also want to maintain coercive credibility to defend its claims.

In history, China has used coercive diplomacy to achieve its goals in several cases. In many instances, Beijing implemented a calculus of signals. China would first deter an adversary from taking actions contrary to Chinese interests by threatening the use of military force; if

deterrence failed, China justified its use of military force as being defensive. This deterrence pattern was applied in each of the major instances in which Beijing has resorted to military force, including the Korea war in 1950, the Sino-Indian border dispute in 1961–1962, the Sino-Soviet border dispute in 1968–1969, and in China-Vietnam war in 1979.^{xvii} Beijing follows a pattern of incremental escalation: Beijing typically uses a variety of official protests to signal its resolve. If the crisis persists and Beijing perceives its interests are not satisfactorily taken into account, Beijing would escalate its statements to include increasingly explicit warnings of possible use military force. This approach has been employed consistently despite the sweeping changes in China's international and domestic environment.^{xviii}

In recent cases, China has used various statements to signal its resolve; China also has taken some low-risk behaviors to defend its claims. Most of China's current assertive behavior could be viewed as defensive assertiveness instead of offensive assertiveness. China has not changed its policy on those issues. China has more capabilities to defend its existing sovereign claims when challenged by its neighbors. That said, defensive assertiveness is still challenging for regional order.

China's official statements have often emphasized that China should safeguard its sovereignty and territorial integrity. At the CCP meeting in 2013, Xi Jinping mentioned the need for China to safeguard "national sovereignty, security, and development interests" as part of periphery diplomacy.^{xix} Foreign Minister Wang Yi stated in March 2014, "We will

never bully smaller countries, yet we will never accept unreasonable demands from smaller countries.”^{xx}

Strongest assertions of the need to defend China’s maritime sovereignty are often found in military sources. Recently Chinese military leaders and their US counterparts exchange tough talk openly.^{xxi} The tough talk of Chinese military leaders aims to clarify China’s resolve and interests.

China also takes concrete actions to defend its territorial and maritime claims. Chinese recent behaviors in maritime disputes are conceptualized as “salami slicing.”^{xxii} Beijing is attempting to strengthen its claims incrementally, without making a move dramatic enough to justify a major response by others. For instance, in territorial disputes such as the South China Sea or the Diaoyu/Senkaku islands, China has strengthened its maritime capabilities and has sent more ships and airplanes into those regions. China does not change its policy regarding the disputed territories. China appears to be more assertive largely because China has more resources to defend its claims.

The international factor alone could not fully explain China’s “assertive” face. Domestic audience has also largely explained the emergence of China’s tough image. Some domestic factors are driving China into an assertive direction, especially the Chinese nationalism. China’s assertiveness could be a result of a mix of confidence on the international stage and insecurity at home. While China’s nationalism has been a major factor in Chinese foreign policy, the Chinese government often made effective efforts to control popular nationalism

before 2008. The situation has changed in recent years, and the Chinese nationalism has turned a strident turn. Enjoying an inflated sense of empowerment after global financial crisis, and terrified of an uncertain future due to social tensions at home, the CCP has become more willing to play to the popular nationalist card.^{xxiii} To maintain long-term regime legitimacy and social stability, Chinese leaders sometimes take a tougher stand in foreign policy to boost CCP's domestic prestige.

Conclusion

China is increasingly sending contradictory signals in regional diplomacy. On the one hand, China tries to reassure its regional countries about its peaceful intention so that a rising China will not face a balancing coalition from regional countries. On the other hand, China wants to maintain its credibility of coercion so that it will not lose bargaining leverage in territorial disputes.

China's "assertive" turn of China's regional diplomacy is intentional rather than the hazard result of increasing domestic fragmentation. China is no longer simply responding but acting on its own initiative. Unlike his predecessor Hu Jintao, who had a highly institutionalized process for foreign policy making, Xi Jinping has strengthened the coordination among foreign and security agencies, and he plays a dominant role in the execution of foreign policy. We are witnessing much more concerted coordination at every level in the Chinese government.

China is always projecting two faces in regional diplomacy. For the diplomacy of any great power, deterrence and reassurance might be the two sides of the same coin. Beijing's proactive economic diplomacy might be largely regarded as part of the charm offensive diplomacy; however, there is a hidden "coercive" element in economic statecraft. From China's perspective, deep interdependence could bind its neighbors in a web of incentives that increase their reliance on China. On the other hand, while the "coercive" aspect of China's diplomacy appears to be threatening, it should be noted that coercive diplomacy could help clarify China's resolve. In some cases, China's "tough" image might be good for peace and crisis management. As two American strategists James Steinberg and Michael O'Hanlon emphasize recently, "The key to stable U.S.-Chinese relations over the long term is for each side to be clear about its true redlines...it involves demonstrating both the will and the capability to make good on threats."^{xxiv}

Combining the shifting balance of power and complicated domestic factors, the emergence of an assertive China seems to be inevitable. It is important to differentiate different types of assertive behaviors. The world should have legitimate reasons to worry about the emergence of China's offensive assertiveness. However, we see little evidence of China already taking an offensive assertive approach. Furthermore, while China's assertiveness is a reality, the serious challenge is not just China's new assertive nationalism, but competing versions of nationalism from all relevant countries in Asia.^{xxv}

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3. Chinese Sphere of Influence in the Asian Region

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Notionally, sphere of influence is associated with the 19th century competition for colonial possessions in Asia and Africa among the European powers of Britain, France, Germany and others. In the scramble for power, China was then divided into sphere of influences, referred in history as cutting of the Chinese melon. But sphere of influence was not solely a 19th century Western phenomenon. In historical past, China was at the centre of the East Asian order and its cultural, economic and political influence spread to Japan, Korea and Vietnam. This Chinese centered order has been referred to in history as the Chinese tributary system. Although there was no tributary system in reality and was merely an explanatory term used by the Western scholars to refer to China's place in the East Asian order, China was the dominant hegemonic power in the Sinic world by virtue of its rich culture, advanced political institutions, vibrant economy and strong military. However, Western and Japanese imperialistic onslaught in the 19th century disintegrated the Chinese tributary order and eroded its sphere of influence and eventually China got the epithet of the Sick Man of Asia. Consequent to the disintegration of the Chinese tributary order there emerged a nationalist outcry for salvation and national rejuvenation to obliterate the scourge of the century of humiliation inflicted upon it by the West. The central crux of this rejuvenation had been the restoration of Chinese glorious past. This national rejuvenation encompasses the Chinese sense of nationalism today and informs the current Chinese

foreign policy perceptions. It finds a strong resonance with the current leadership of Xi Jinping and shapes China's domestic and foreign policy goals.

Arguably, China's notion of the sphere of influence is not same as that of the 19th century notion of imperialistic possessions. Rather it should be understood in the context of the Chinese past and thus is associated with the notion of territoriality that specifically consisted of two zones, a zone of direct Chinese rule and a zone of indirect rule or loose rein (*jimi*). The loose rein zone underscored the sphere of influence and prevailed at the frontiers of the Chinese imperial state. The frontiers were not static zones but mobile zones whose influence ebbed and flowed with waning and waxing of imperial power at the centre. The frontiers were also not meant to be hostile zones but that which supported and enhanced the imperial core. Further, the frontier zones were strategic areas that encompassed the Chinese sense of territoriality. These were not directly administered areas, nonetheless comprised the Sinic zone where China's culture and civilization spread. Since these were the areas where Chinese culture prevailed, the imperial state regarded these as Chinese spheres of influence but not as imperialistic possessions with the right to extraction and exploitation. Further, the zonal configuration while indicated the Chinese sphere of influence, also indicated the degree of imperial control. The proximity of the zones to the centre meant enhanced degree of bureaucratic control and those lying away from the centre enjoyed greater autonomy. Thus, spatially the Sinic zone resembled concentric zones with imperial centre at the core, followed by the directly controlled provincial zones, followed by the minority non-Han areas, followed by the tribute paying countries and finally by trading countries that did not pay tribute to the celestial emperor. This was the tributary system that essentially represented the Chinese notions of territoriality. The defeat of China in the First Opium War of 1842 caused the appearance of the first cracks of disintegration of the tributary order and the final collapse came with China's defeat against the Japanese in the 1895 Sino-Japanese War. The War did not simply mean disintegration of the imperial order but more significantly meant decentering of the Chinese power. From the throes of this loss of centrality emerged the nationalist cry to avenge the national humiliation and salvage the glorious past. This salvation, therefore, meant retrieving the historical notion of territoriality that involved both building a strong and prosperous state and reclaiming the lost lands and lost spheres of influence. This twin goal of restoration laced the Chinese narrative of nationalism and imbued the Chinese foreign policy perceptions right from Mao Zedong to Xi Jinping. In other

words, there is an essential continuity in Chinese foreign policy from the post-1949 to till today.

Continuity and Shifts in Chinese Foreign Policy

Under Mao Zedong, the strategy of reclaiming the glorious past was sought through undertaking the Wars of liberation as was evident in the case of Tibet and Beijing's support to the Communist revolution worldwide as well as armed insurgencies in the neighbouring countries, of India's Northeast and Myanmar. In the post-Mao era, while the goal of restoration remained firm, there was a shift in the strategy from politics in command to economics in command. With de-radicalisation and prioritization of economic development came the new foreign policy formulation of lying low strategy underscored in Deng Xiaoping's 'Sixteen Character' strategy. The essential element of this strategy was to buy peace to develop the economy. But, not to forget, while peace and development defined the core of Deng Xiaoping's sixteen-character strategy, the strategy of 'striving to make accomplishments' remained the long term goal.

Chinese leadership has, however, incrementally moved away from Deng's low-lie strategy from Jiang Zemin's era onwards. Jiang Zemin while retaining Deng's fundamental reform strategy of 'peace and development' embarked upon 'great power diplomacy' and focussed on the fourth modernization programme that of defence modernization. While Deng emphasised on self-restraint, Jiang favoured conforming to the international order but demanding equality and respect. Also, he formulated the 'New Security Concept' that sought to offer a win-win strategy as against the Western zero sum game. Hu Jintao moved a step further. His foreign policy was symptomatic of the rise of a confident China that was clearly visible after the successful hosting of the Beijing Olympics. No more the century of humiliation occupied a central focus, instead China under Hu shifted to a more proactive foreign policy. Quite inevitably, Hu's term coincided with the 2010 eruption of the South China Sea dispute which evidently demonstrated, as a Chinese scholar, Yuan Peng contended, "Shedding of 'self-restraint' and opting for 'modest operations'" in foreign policy. In other words, Hu focussed on Deng's latter part of the sixteen character strategy, that is, instead of focusing on 'hiding capabilities and biding time', it harped upon 'striving to make achievements'. Therefore, in 2010, China started flexing muscle in the South China Sea and was willing to confront the US in the region. Hu's leadership also saw a further refinement of Jiang Zemin's formulation of a counter-hegemonic strategy to contain the US unilateralism. He

emphasised on harmonious development philosophy that underscored Chinese vision of global governance. Such a vision entailed not Jiang's policy of simply conforming to the international system but also to reshape the international order to better reflect its national interest. Pro-activism, thus, became hallmark of Hu's foreign policy. Commensurate with this shift in strategy, a renewed debate on *tianxia* or Chinese world view began to resonate in the academic discussions. Questions like whether China has its own international relations theory and how such a theory would provide an alternate view of world politics emerged as a new area of study. Incipient in these developments were however, the reverberations of the old quests of rejuvenation and restoration of the glorious Chinese past.

Continuing with the goal of restoration, the current leadership under Xi Jinping also has embarked upon the dream of rejuvenation. His belligerence in the East China Sea and South China Sea is not a deviation in Chinese foreign policy. It is a decisive attempt to de-centre the US and reclaim China's centrality in the East Asian order, thereby fulfilling the 'Chinese dream'.

The Clash of Competing Orders in Asia

After the Sino-Japanese War of 1895, when China was de-centered, it was Japan that usurped China's position and attempted to dominate the East Asian order with the creation of the Greater East Asia Co-Prosperty Sphere. The experiment, however, fizzled out with the Japanese defeat in the Second World War. But soon after the end of the War, the East Asian region saw the rise and dominance of a new extra-regional power that of the United States that established the so called hub and spokes model to govern its relations in the region. Notably, the hub and spokes liberal institutional order was created by the US in East Asia to essentially contain the Soviet Communist expansion. The spokes or the allied partners- Japan, South Korea, Philippines, Thailand, Australia and Taiwan were tied down in a tight bilateral-hegemonic system so that none could challenge each other and disrupt the order. Further, the power of the militarist Japan was clipped and turned into a pacifist nation, while the US maintained military bases in the allied countries for its operations against the Communist bloc. In effect, the hub and spokes system enabled the US to not only establish its preponderance in East Asia but as John Ikenberry has contended also engendered the "single most important anchor for regional stability" in East Asia. Significantly,

the hub and spokes system echoed a variant of the Chinese tributary order albeit under a non-resident power of the US in Asia.

It is important to note that the hub and spokes system was essentially a Cold War liberal institutional architecture which continued to prevail despite the disintegration of the Soviet power and the demise of the Cold War rivalry. In fact, in the post-Cold War era, the US reinvigorated its alliance with Japan and more recently it has rebalanced its interest in East Asia by its 'pivot' policy. America's reaching out to its erstwhile adversaries, Myanmar and Vietnam, is integral to this pivoting strategy. This US rebalancing has, in turn, led the Chinese to retaliate with its declaration of the Air Defence Identification Zone (ADIZ) in the East China Sea and posed threats of expanding it to the South China Seas. Arguably, the ADIZ is the manifestation of China's incremental re-creation of the Chinese centered order where the countries in the region are required to comply with the Chinese rules on the Seas. The ADIZ is clearly seen as a Chinese challenge to the US hub and spokes system. In fact, China believes that the US power is in relative decline. Therefore, ADIZ is aimed to test the efficacy of the US hub and spokes system in East Asia and pave the way for China to step in as security guarantor of the region.

Decentering the US

Indeed the ADIZ is axiomatic of the recreation of the Chinese preponderance in East Asia by decentering the US from the region. But this decentering of the US is traceable to the post Cold War era itself when China after being rebuffed by the West due to the Tiananmen massacre turned towards its southeastern periphery and wooed the Southeast Asian nations into accepting China as a benign power and a country of opportunity. This underscored Jiang Zemin's periphery strategy when the doors of Western investment and trade were closed to China while it urgently required foreign investments to sustain its economic reform strategy. Thus, China under Jiang embarked upon mending ties with the countries in its Southeast Asian periphery.

The 1997 East Asian financial crisis provided the opportune moment for China to intervene as a savior in the region and provided economic aid to some of the collapsing economies of Southeast Asia. While the US and Japan failed to come forward to dole out the Southeast Asian economies from the worst economic crisis, it was China that took the leadership role and emerged as responsible power, thus earning goodwill in the region. In effect, the absence of the US in the region paved the path for China's

supremacy in the region and this trend got further bolstered with the US preoccupation with the War on Terror following the 9/11 terror attacks. China took the opportunity to deepen its relations with the Southeast Asian countries by creating the FTA and binding the region in a thick web of economic interdependencies. Clearly, China has emerged to be a strong economic contender in the region not just proving an alternative to the US but increasingly replacing the US in terms of economic opportunity in East Asia.

The 2008 global financial downturn was yet another critical factor that propelled the Chinese power in the region and demonstrated the US in a relative decline. Coupled with the success of the 2008 Beijing Olympics, the Chinese power was certainly buoyed to the extent that for the first time it shed all the inhibitions of a peaceful rise and adopted distinct belligerence in the South China Sea dispute and claimed the disputed territories of the South China Sea as sovereign territories of China. In effect, China sought to expand its sphere of influence. The earlier strategy under Jiang Zemin was to economically entice the Southeast Asian countries and wean them away from the US orbit and thereby create more allies in the region. Under Hu Jintao while economic enticement has continued to prevail, it is coupled with challenging the US and adopting a more proactive role in the region. In other words, if earlier Chinese foreign policy was aimed at conforming to the international system, the foreign policy under Hu and Xi is to reshape the international system to reflect the current reality of changed power configuration.

The Silk Route Strategy and the Emerging Chinese Sphere of Influence

Under Xi Jinping, while economic enticement of East Asia has continued to gain traction, a major fillip has been given to the periphery strategy. This strategy which is rooted in Chinese historical past and which had seen a renewal under Jiang Zemin's leadership has currently acquired a preeminent foreign policy initiative under Xi. In fact, Xi Jinping's October 2013 Speech at the Conference of Diplomatic Work toward Surrounding Countries has been hailed in China as the highest level conference on diplomatic work since 1949. This priori attention on the periphery has certainly come up with the US rebalancing strategy in Asia. But more than that, as Qinghua professor Yan Xuetong has argued, the periphery strategy has gained a new dimension owing to two significant shifts in Chinese foreign policy. First, from the earlier foreign policy strategy of ascribing top priority to China's relations with the United States, the new

strategy emphasises on giving first priority to China's relations with the neighbouring relations. Second, from the earlier emphasis on Deng Xiaoping's *Tao Guang Yang Hui* (keeping a low profile), China under Xi Jinping has now been talking about *Fen Fa You Wei* (striving for achievement).

Under this new foreign policy strategy, China's periphery has gathered preeminent focus. China, has thus, called for reviving the three Silk Routes- Silk Road Economic Belt in Central Asia, Maritime Silk Road in Southeast Asia and the China-India-Myanmar-Bangladesh economic corridor in South Asia. This Silk Route Economic belts is part of China's sub-regional integration mechanism that is focussed on not only economic cooperation with the neighbouring regions but more specifically integrating the neighbouring regions. Based on the revival of the ancient silk route, it promises to "form a channel of cooperation, development and prosperity" across regions of Central Asia, South Asia and Southeast Asia. It also claims to be inclusive strategy. As Chinese ambassador to India, Wei Wei writes, "The "Belt" and "Road" initiatives are inclusive because they are a banner of unity among nations and a commitment to cooperation."

However, Silk Route strategy is a decisive assertion of Chinese power and a step towards recreation of a Chinese sphere of influence in Asia opposed to the US hub and spokes model. One of its central principles states that it aims at building a 'Community of Common Destiny'. Some Western experts have aptly argued that China's Community of Common Destiny sounds similar to Japan's Greater East Asia Co-Prosperity Sphere in the inter-war period. Yan Xuetong himself asserts that "Many people, especially Chinese scholars, are reluctant to talk about this issue, because they know that the core of such a community is military cooperation. A community of common destiny will not exist without military cooperation...Eventually this may even extend to providing security guarantees to select countries."

Yan Xuetong has in fact, located Xi's Silk Road strategy in the context of the US-China relations and argued about what China's role would be in the global arena where its influence is growing but where it still has to confront the US. In an article written on January 28, 2014, he says, "Under Xi, China will begin to treat friends and enemies differently...For more than twenty years, even those nations that were generally supportive of China could not count on China to be a friend in times of need because China would make no commitments of alliance. In the future, China will decisively favor those who side with it with economic

benefits and even security protections. On the contrary, those who are hostile to China will face much more sustained policies of sanctions and isolation. Nations in these regions should expect to see much increased willingness by China to underwrite substantive economic, security, and other benefits in exchange for political support for China's regional objectives." Clearly, China's Silk Route strategy is not a mere regional integration strategy but a robust attempt to reshape the regional order on a hegemonic principle.

This is all the more true as regionalism and sub-regionalism have failed to evolve as regional security architecture owing to competing nationalism and territorial sovereignty issues afflicting Asia. The 2010 South China Sea dispute has clearly shown that sovereignty issues have triumphed over cooperative peace. Since regionalism has failed in Asia, China has turned to power politics to reshape the region in opposition to the US.

Inference

A glance at the evolution of Chinese foreign policy post 1949 evidently suggests that China has always remained steadfast in its goal of national rejuvenation. While the goal has remained firm, the strategy to achieve it has changed over the years. The shift in strategy has been prompted by the change in the global configuration of power; China's ever expanding national interest and the need for robust foreign policy to match the Chinese growing power. Under the present dispensation of Xi Jinping China has distinctly grown as a world power. It has emerged to be the second largest economy in nominal GDP and largest economy in purchasing power parity terms. This robust economic growth is reminiscent of China in the 18th century when it was the world's manufacturing hub and accounted for about one-third of world's GDP. Quite naturally, it is now demanding to reshape the global institutions to reflect this changed global reality of power configuration. More recently, it has floated its own institutions like the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB) to rival the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank.

At the moment, however, the question is whether the US would be able to contain China's emergence as an alternative power centre. Also, equally there are questions if other great powers and middle powers are amenable to join Chinese sphere of influence. Further, if China was the centre of the Sinic order in history, India was equally the centre of the Indic order. Given the rise of India, a repetition of a bipolar order

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comprising the US and China is unlikely. Further, domestic turmoil could well derail China's rise and would remain a long-time factor inhibiting China's preponderance in Asia.

4. China's strategic objectives in Asia

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As the geo-political shift has taken place with the start of the 21st century with the rise of China, as like other Great Powers have done in the past and as was done during the earlier Chinese empires, it wishes to expand in its periphery with its security interest secured in its mainland Asia.

It's understood that as with being an Asian country, China wishes to first expand itself by economic and military means by setting up its Sphere of Influence in many parts of Asia such as in South-East Asia, Central Asia and Middle-East which will enable its stature in the International Arena and so will act as a check for any of the Great Powers from Asia or outside to have any sort of influence in the region.¹

Chinese expansion in Asia was warranted by the two major factors. First, with the end of the Soviet Union, it was understood that China will play the major role in Asia one played by Soviet Union. Second, with the first pre-eminent power in the world United States having military commitments apart from Asia, China has decided to expand its Sphere of Influence in the continent.

China has decided to have a 'free go' throughout the world. This 'free go' has necessitated the establishment of a firm Chinese foothold in the Asia-Pacific region, from which it can broaden its sphere of strategic influence even to Africa, Latin America and Europe. India acts as a distinct challenger in this respect. With a population of more than one billion people, a growing economy and supple latent power, India is a clear leader in the affairs of South Asia which is challenged by increased Chinese economic and military influence.

For example, China's President Xi Jinping became the first Chinese head of state to visit Sri Lanka in three decades, underlining Beijing's renewed push to deepen its existing strategic presence in the Indian Ocean.

The Chinese leader will become the first President to visit Sri Lanka since former leader Li Xiannian in 1986. His visit assumes significance in the

context of strengthening ties between the two countries, with China investing heavily in the island nation.

A \$500 million- built port built by the Chinese was inaugurated in Colombo last year giving Beijing a strong foothold in one of the busiest international shipping routes in the world. With heavy investment in infrastructure, including in a massive port it helped build in Hambantota along Sri Lanka's southern coast, China is said to have surpassed Japan and India as the biggest contributor to investments in the island nation.

China's strategic objective in Asia

China is an ancient continental land power in Asia with a ever expanding maritime orientation in the Asia-Pacific region. With the transformation of China's grand strategy from landward security to seaward security following the end of the Cold War, maritime security interests have gradually become the essential element in China's strategic approach. Undoubtedly, the quest for sea power and sea rights has become Beijing's main maritime strategic issue.

As China's maritime politico-economic-military leverage in the Asia-Pacific region escalates, so too does its desire to become a leading global sea power which will help in develop its position in the as an influential actor both in economic and military terms in the Asian region. This objective demands that it expand its maritime capabilities by developing its navy preparing for armed confrontation if challenged in a regional war in the Asian region.

From China's perspective, its security environment is changing. The traditional territorial scramble is shifting from an emphasis on control of land to control of territorial waters, of maritime strategic resources and of critical sea-lanes. As a result, maritime economic competition has become a key focus for many nations. Given this, China's maritime shift from a coastal to a high seas focus is understandable.

As a part of Chinese maritime strategy is the island hopping strategy. The Chinese "island hopping" strategy defies historical precedent and differs from the strategies of other and past great powers in that they were usually explicit about their intentions. China apparently believes that concealing its motives best serves its interests.

An increased Chinese presence across the Indian Ocean poses a challenge to India as it is trying to project itself as a great power beyond South Asia. The two Asian giants are vying for economic opportunities

and international recognition. Renewed American engagement, which is likely to follow military withdrawals from Afghanistan and Iraq, could prove an obstacle to China's designs and cause it to intensify its efforts now.

China is seeking to contain India by forging alliances with island nations including the Maldives, Mauritius and the Seychelles and building a "string of pearls" of military bases from East Africa to Pakistan.

The strategy is designed to curtail Indian influence in the region so China, with the Americans distracted in the Middle East, can have a free run in other parts of Asia and across the Pacific Ocean but also to encroach upon African countries that welcome its yuan diplomacy — developmental and industrial support with no strings attached.

Chinese maritime strategy thought started to be pursued actively in the 21st century was first enunciated by Admiral Liu Huaqing in 1988 and is encapsulated in the "three island chain" approach. By 2010 China seeks to establish a permanent blue water presence in the first island "chain" arrayed on a Japan-Taiwan-Philippines axis, to include the South China Sea. By 2025 it proposes to establish a permanent blue water presence in the second island "chain" stretching from the Aleutians through the Mariana Islands to the East Coast of Papua New Guinea, and which includes the Malaccan Straits. By 2050 the reach will extend to the third island "chain" starting in the Aleutians and ending in Antarctica, to include waters offshore of New Zealand and Australia

Apart from India, another Great Power in Asia which is likely to challenge Chinese influence is Indonesia both in terms of continental and maritime expansion . Indonesia is nonetheless aware of China's interest in the Natuna Islands and in developing the ability to project military power beyond the "Second Island Chain" (the arc extending from Japan through Guam, Northern Australia and Indonesia).²

The Chinese Navy has already conducted an exercise in the Lombok Strait, the narrow strip of water linking the Java Sea with the Indian Ocean. The drills have been seen by analysts as underlining China's expanding ability to carry out operations in waters far beyond its borders. A three-ship flotilla of the South China Sea Fleet conducted ten exercises, including anti-piracy, search and rescue, and damage control drills, over a five-day period from 29 January 2014. It involved the Changbaishan, China's largest amphibious landing craft, which is equipped with advanced weapons systems, plus the destroyers Wuhan and Haikou.

This was the first drill of this nature held in the Lombok Strait and it also marked the first time the People's Liberation Army Navy (PLAN) had, in its drills, used a new route from the South China Sea to the Indian Ocean. In earlier drills, ships sailed up the much-traversed Malacca Strait, the crucial link between the Indian Ocean and East Asia.

Hainan Island is a critical element in the "Second Island Chain" strategy, as it would provide bases for combat aircraft operating around the Indonesian archipelago, the Australian "Sea-Air Gap" and the southern approaches to Guam. Hainan Island has six airfields, three of which are semi-hardened/hardened fighter bases. The other three are dual-use civil airports, two of which have 11,000 foot runways capable of accommodating long range aircraft. Burma/Myanmar, with four runways exceeding 11,000 feet in length, supplements Hainan Island by covering the western arc out of south-east Asia through the Andaman Islands.

A further potential irritant to China-Indonesia relations is China's interest in helping Timor-Leste to build a naval base for Chinese-made patrol boats. This has raised concerns in Jakarta (and Canberra) about Beijing's military influence in Timor-Leste. Plans to develop a naval base at Betano, in the south of the country, were announced in 2009 by East Timorese Secretary of State for Defence, Julio Pinto, but little appears to have come of it so far.

In an effort to curb China's more far-reaching ambitions in the South China Sea, Indonesia has also started to court Japan as a strategic partner. Japan has much more immediate and strategic reasons for helping any South-East Asian country to counterbalance China. The recently declared Chinese Air Defence Identification Zone (ADIZ) in the East China Sea and the dispute over the Diaoyu/Senkaku Islands have made Japan extremely sensitive about Chinese assertiveness. Japan – like China – is also nervous about the security of its energy trade routes through the South and East China Seas, but Japan's pacifist constitution does not allow its Self-Defence Forces to do anything beyond protecting its own territory.

That, therefore, leaves the US besides India as the only other country that Indonesia could ally itself with in the short-term that could substantially influence Chinese behavior in the South China Sea and pose challenge to Beijing's Sphere of Influence ambition.

China's Rise and systematic re-alignment for Sphere of Influence in the International Arena

Power in the international system is relative and ever-shifting. Over the

past three decades, China has demonstrated tremendous ability to plan and mobilize national resources to implement goal-oriented, timely action strategies in economic, diplomatic, and military arenas.

No rising power is ever a status quo power. Rising powers tend to be both risk-takers, impatient, and paranoid powers. They flex their muscles and test the resolve of old, established powers. They seek to benefit from the weakness in resolve — not capabilities — of the established powers by employing asymmetric strategies to chip away at their hegemony. For, China — the biggest beneficiary of the post-World War II order — no longer sees US primacy as serving its interests. Beijing dubs US alliances ‘relics of the Cold War’ which must be dismantled to restore what it calls ‘natural power balance in the region’ (translation: a Sino-centric hierarchical order of pre-modern Asia). It is not in China’s DNA to play second fiddle to any other power. Moscow learnt the hard way in the 1950s. Now it is the turn of those Americans who have long dreamt of co-opting China as a junior partner. Moreover, regimes that do not share power or abide by the rule of law in domestic politics do not abide by the rule of law in international politics or share power in world politics.

China’s Asia strategy is to undermine the United States’ credibility as regional security guarantor. Beijing’s diplomatic rhetoric notwithstanding, the ‘New Type of Great Power Relations’ seeks US recognition of China’s primacy in Asia in a geopolitical deal that limits Washington’s regional role and presence, and relegates traditional US allies (especially Japan) to the sidelines. This push and shove will continue for decades because the Chinese believe that ‘the US is in irreversible decline, and growing weaker as China grows stronger.’ From Beijing’s perspective, the main issue is how to manage, and profit from, America’s decline. The challenge, from Washington’s perspective, is how to manage China’s rise within the US-led order without diluting American role and presence. Who emerges at the top in this poker game will ultimately determine the future of world order. It is against this backdrop that the Obama Administration officials have been visiting Asian capitals to reassure US friends and allies about security commitments, and reaffirm Washington’s determination to rebalancing to Asia.

Significantly, China is not rising in a vacuum. Under Shinzo Abe’s leadership, Japan is keen to become a ‘normal nation.’ India has been economically and strategically rebalancing towards the Asia-Pacific for nearly two decades under its ‘Look East’ policy. With the victory of Narendra Modi-led BJP government in May 2014 elections, India may

well be back in the reckoning. Since Beijing will not abandon its policy of engaging India economically while strangulating it geopolitically, a revitalized India will form the southern anchor of an Asian balance of power and frustrate efforts to establish Chinese supremacy. Small and middle powers (Singapore, South Korea, Indonesia, Vietnam, the Philippines, and Australia) are also maneuvering for balance and advantage. Indonesia and Vietnam, in particular, are upgrading their naval power, as territorial disputes in the South China Sea escalate. For its part, Russia is using its vast energy resources to stage a comeback on the world stage. Though it pre-dates the Ukraine crisis, the Russian pivot to Asia is set to deepen given Western isolation under sanctions, Gazprom's 30-year gas deal worth \$400 billion with China, and growing demand for Russian weaponry and energy by China's neighbours. Russia is unlikely to slide into the role of 'China's Canada' without resistance. It is indeed a very complex and crowded geopolitical space out there.

These Asia-Pacific powers are today where Germany, France, Britain, and Italy were at the beginning of the 20th century or in the 19th century when the concept of the "Concert of Asia" was played out. They are looking outward globally in search of markets, resources and bases, jockeying for power and influence, outmaneuvering and outbidding each other in different parts of the world, and forming natural resources-based partnerships characterized by hedging strategies. The major power competition is between China and the United States, but in the maritime and continental domains, it is between China and Japan and between China and India. The logic of geopolitics — i.e., Japan's and India's worries about their place in a Sino-centric Asia — will forge a closer bond under the Abe-Modi leadership. It will intensify Beijing's strategic competition with both Tokyo and New Delhi.

Much like Europe in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the Asia-Pacific of the early 21st century is thus home to several rising, contending powers and some fragile or failing states. As new powers rise in Asia, new strategic balances are emerging as partnerships and alliances among states shift. Simply put, the Asia-Pacific of the early 21st century bears more resemblance to Europe of the late 19th and early 20th centuries. The rise of nationalist leaders in Japan, the Philippines and India is in part because of their predecessors' failure to deal strongly with Chinese transgressions.

China's geo-strategic challenge in Asia

This is the decade of power transitions in Asia. For small and weak

states in China's neighborhood, this is the decade of living dangerously. Among regional countries, China arouses unease because of its size, history, proximity, power, and, more importantly, because the memories of 'the Middle Kingdom syndrome' or tributary state system have not dimmed. Historically, there has never been a time when China has coexisted on equal terms with another power of similar or lesser stature. As in the past, a rich and powerful China demands obeisance and deference from other countries. What has changed is that Beijing's economic interests have now displaced the ideological fervor of the past. In Asian capitals, there are hardly any takers of 'China's peaceful rise' or of 'non-interference in internal affairs' rhetoric (ask North Korea, Cambodia, Laos, Malaysia, Indonesia, Myanmar, Nepal or Sri Lanka).

The growing economic ties between China and its Asian neighbors have created a sense of dependency and despondency. While China's neighbors do not oppose China's power and prosperity, they do not welcome their own loss of strategic autonomy in foreign policy-making. With the exception of a few (notably Pakistan), most Asian countries (including North Korea) show little or no desire to live in a China-led or China-dominated Asia. Instead, they seek to preserve existing security alliances and pursue sophisticated diplomatic and hedging strategies designed to give them more freedom of action.

Territorial integrity is the core interest of all nations – weak or strong, big or small. The mounting tensions between China and its neighbors from India to Japan over land and maritime disputes have geopolitical implications. China's unresolved land and maritime disputes and the 'Middle Kingdom syndrome' work to Beijing's disadvantage, and to Washington's advantage.

Beijing's aggressive posturing since 2007 on land and maritime disputes all along its periphery has driven China's neighbors into Washington's embrace. Examples include Canberra-Tokyo, Manila-Hanoi, Manila-Tokyo, Tokyo-Hanoi, Hanoi-New Delhi and Tokyo-New Delhi strategic partnerships. The target of everyone's balancing in Asia is China, not Russia or the United States. In fact, those balancing China (India, Vietnam, the Philippines, and Indonesia to name a few) are being armed by both Russian and American weaponry.

Historically, the rise of a continental power has always led to the formation of a coalition of maritime powers to counterbalance it. This is particularly so if that continental power happens to have an authoritarian regime nursing historical grievances with active territorial

disputes and/or happens to be a polarizing power. China is no exception to this rule. Being a distant hegemony, the United States remains the balancing power of choice for most countries on China's periphery. All want to benefit from economic ties with China, but none want the region dominated by Beijing or their policy options constrained by China. Put simply, there is no desire to replace the fading American hegemony with Chinese hegemony.

Much as Beijing would like to restore China's primacy that prevailed in pre-modern Asia, structural changes in Asian geopolitics over the last 200 years rule out a return to the Sino-centric hierarchical tributary state system of the past. Since geography defines a country's role and power, there is no turning back the clock. A major reason the United States is a global superpower is its unique geography. China does not have Canada and Mexico on its borders, but large powerful states – Russia, Japan, Vietnam, Indonesia, Australia, and India – that will do everything to counterbalance China's growing power for historical, civilization, geopolitical and geo-economic reasons. This gap or disconnect between China's ambitions in Asia and the changed geopolitics which works against the restoration of Chinese supremacy is what the Chinese ruefully call the 'containment of China.' Objectively speaking, this is China's 'geopolitical discomfort,' not 'containment.'³

Landward or Maritime Dilemma in China's Asian outlook

Asia's geopolitical centre of gravity is shifting inland, with implications for maritime powers. Mahan matters but so do Mackinder, Spykman, Kautilya and SunZi. Notwithstanding the focus on maritime rivalries, new economic hubs, institutions, transport corridors, high-speed railways, expressways and pipelines networks are changing the geopolitics of Eurasia. During the Cold War, much of the economic growth took place within the US hub-and-spokes alliance network in maritime Asia. Post-Cold War, economic growth has taken place in China, India, and continental Southeast Asia, outside of the US Pacific alliance network.

China, much like Britain and Russia in the past, is now employing modern transportation technology, high-speed railways, expressways, pipeline networks to re-draw the geopolitical map of Eurasia. As part of its 'Go West' strategy, Beijing is spending hundreds of billions to create its 'economic hub-and-spokes system' in continental Asia via pipelines, highways, railway networks linking China with Central, Southwest and Southeast Asia. These spokes or arteries will bring in raw materials and

energy resources and export Chinese manufactured goods to those regions and beyond. However, not enough attention is being paid to Eurasia because three centuries of Anglo-American maritime dominance seem to have caused a certain degree of 'land-blindness' among policymakers

These strategic trends will shape the future of Asian geopolitics, in particular the interactions among the United States, China, Russia, Japan, and India. Power asymmetry among major powers means that each will form flexible ad hoc partnerships with the others where their interests converge, mobilize the support of one against the other when their interests collide, and checkmate the other two from forming an alignment against it as they compete, coalesce and collude with each other when their objectives coincide. China is, of course, the most important piece of the geopolitical puzzle. No country threatens China today as it is presently constituted. As the largest (in terms of territory) and the most powerful (economically and militarily) country in Asia, should Beijing agree to freeze and accept territorial status quo all along its land and maritime boundaries, it could unravel the Cold War-era US alliances and undermine the *raison d'être* of US forward presence.

Since the prospects of the PLA accepting the territorial status quo are nil, the question then facing the United States and its friends is how to sustain a robust balance of power that deters intimidation and aggression and reassures friends and allies faced with an increasingly confident and powerful China, determined to establish its dominance on the Asian continent and its adjoining waters. Peace and stability will prevail if major powers work for a multipolar Asia with inclusive multilateral institutions and dispute resolution mechanisms. However, competition, rivalry, and even conflict will result should bipolarity re-emerge or should Beijing seek to re-establish a unipolar Sino-centric hierarchical order wherein the Middle Kingdom behaves in a hegemonic manner, expecting obeisance and tribute from its neighbors⁴.

Last but not the least; nothing is inevitable in life and politics — domestic or world. The Soviet Union and Japan show that nothing is inevitable about the rise of China. Historically, rising powers, expecting too much too soon, have often shown an uncanny knack for being their own worst enemies. Contrary to what International Relations textbooks teach us, a country's foreign policy is not a cold calculation of costs and benefits or pros and cons alone. It's a mix of five 'Ps': passion, power, profit, pride and prejudice. That is what makes the task of predicting China's future or the future of world politics so difficult. The risk of

miscalculation lies in China overestimating its strength, and the rest of the world underestimating China's ambitions, power and purpose.

Ever since China emerged as a regional power in Asia, it has been increasingly assertive to further its territorial claim in the SCS, and has announced the nine-dash line shown on the Chinese maps over which it claims sovereignty. China has bolstered its presence in the area by increasing naval patrols and imposing restrictions on foreign fishing activities.

These actions by China can be seen as showcasing power to strengthen claims in the SCS, which has potentially threatened regional security. The Philippines initially opted for the bilateral route to settle the claims against China and proceeded for a multilateral resolution under the aegis of the ASEAN. However, these negotiations did not resolve the dispute, which compelled the Philippines to take recourse to international arbitration, and it filed case before the ITLOS under Article 3- Annex VII Part XV of UNCLOS against China on January 2013. The Philippines also sought invalidation of China's nine dash line claim and cessation of incursions into the Philippine Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). In response, China rejected the arbitration proceedings, asserting its indisputable sovereignty over the disputed maritime area with Philippines.

The SCS dispute is marked by complex political factors, both international as well as domestic. Even though there are established rules laid down by the international law, countries in true sense behave according to their core values, domestic policies as well as their national interests. These factors sometimes over ride the set norms of international law as is exemplified by China's claim in SCS.

But as responsible international players, countries usually abide by the rules set by the international community like India did in the India-Bangladesh case. If China does not accept the international law it will be falling short in playing its part as a responsible power which might lead to diplomatic repercussions.

China and the Philippines could well emulate this example in East Asia and take their cases for arbitration even at the risk of an unfavorable outcome. The India-Bangladesh judgment showcases political will to be an overriding factor in resolving these disputes amicably, and can be seen as a pathway for China and the Philippines to resolve theirs.

While comparing the two cases, the most prominent feature which stands out is the failure of bilateral talks between the parties. Despite China's opposition, if the UNCLOS based arbitration moves forward, it would have an impact on the other claimants leading to a positive domino effect in the region. China would do anything to avoid a situation where it is pitted against the collective stand of other claimants for an international arbitration. The arbitration filed by the Philippines is considered as a useful first step by the other claimants of Southeast Asia to counter China's claims in the region.

States as international players have to abide and adhere to certain norms of international law. The absence of international law governing maritime delimitations would lead to countries behaving according to their own national interests, which could lead to a state of anarchy.

If China, by virtue of its size or military capacity, is free to ignore the international law, then the entire global institution risks being discredited. And no nation, China included, would find its security and prosperity better served in an anarchic environment.

In conclusion,

As China being primarily an Asian power wishes to expand its range and scope of economic and military presence in continents such as Europe, Africa, Latin America and off shore continents such as Australasia, it wishes to first consolidate and expand its presence in the Asian region both in terms of continental and maritime direction by having its Sphere of Influence which is something challenged by countries such as India, Australia, Indonesia and the external power players in the Asia region such as the United States. Whether Beijing will be able to ward off the challenge is something worth to be watched or meanwhile, we will have the privilege of watching a "Concert of Asia" in the 21st century.

Notes

- 1) <http://www.worldaffairsjournal.org/article/nervous-neighbors-china-finds-sphere-influence>
- 2) See more at: <http://www.futuredirections.org.au/publications/indian-ocean/1677-indonesia-s-evolving-grand-strategy-foreign-powers.html#sthash.obzhNaN3.dpuf>
- 3) <http://www.diplomatist.com/articles/article010.html>
- 4) http://www.idsa.in/idsacomments/PLAAssertsasModi-XiJinpingTalk_gkanwal_220914.html
www.nzia.org.nz/new-zealand-international-review.aspx

5. China's Quest for 'Ozeanraum'

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We have beheld in the ocean huge waves like mountains rising sky-high, and we have set eyes on barbarian regions hidden away beyond a blue of light vapours, while our sails, loftily unfurled, day and night continued their course like that of a star, traversing the savage waves as if we were treading a public thoroughfare.

Zheng He, "Admiral of the Western Seas"¹

The economic march of the Chinese juggernaut makes it easy for it to become a target of unbridled anxiety of the neighbours as well as other powers in the region. The term 'String of Pearls'² coined by defence contractor Booz Allen Hamilton in 2005, has let the imagination run riot deflecting the discussion from reality. The fact is that China or for that matter, any aspiring naval power like China would be distressed to be in the current position if the spotlight is shifted seawards. China has been late in realising the importance of sea power since it had a land focus, however If one looks from Chinese land mass towards the East and the South China seas, which are its gateways to the oceans, what one would see is Japan with its vast island territories, South Korea, Taiwan, Philippines with its island chain, Vietnam, Indonesia and the US base Guam (Map 1). In fact in a somewhat geographically distorted simile the Chinese land mass seems akin to a giant crab whose claws do not belong to it!

Map-1: Depicts the Seaward Encirclement of China.

The geographical situation that China unfortunately finds it in is not conducive for unhindered, unobserved and unrestricted naval operations. Further the sea lines of communications (SLOCs) most essential for China can be encumbered easily by its sea neighbours. The Chinese navy is rapidly evolving from a primarily coastal defence force to green water navy with blue water ambitions. This is borne out by the fact it has started on a path to work up the aircraft carrier and would eventually like to project power across the oceans. A bird's eye view of the access to the oceans depicted in Map-2, between China and India would put in perspective the anxieties of China on this account.

Map 2: Depicting Relative Ease of Access to the Indian Ocean by Indian Navy as Compared to the Pacific Ocean by Chinese Navy. *(The maps are not to scale; the Indian Ocean map has been rotated by 90 deg left for better appreciation)*

The aim of this article is to therefore, look at the traditional maritime anxieties/perceived threats faced by China across its shores, for developing a balanced perspective in to the modernisation program of the Chinese Navy and its quest for unhindered access to open seas.

South Korea and Japan. Korea occupies an envious position by virtue of the fact that it oversees Chinese SLOCs. The South Korean island of Cheju sits astride the intersection of the East China Sea (ECS), the Yellow Sea and the Tsushima Strait. **The access to and from the major Chinese ports of Dalian, Tianjin and Qingdao can be easily controlled by the US forces based in South Korea.** The Chinese North Sea Fleet is based at Qingdao and a naval base is located at Lushun near Dalian.

Japan poses a major obstacle to the seaward expansion of the Chinese Navy in the North Pacific. **Japan, with its long chain of islands, covers the entire eastern flank of China and Russia.** Japan blocks the shortest route beyond the first island chain. Its southern tip is just 80 km from Taiwan. Japan can easily monitor the movements of the Chinese North and East Sea fleets. Further Japan has a vast maritime domain; with a coastline of ~17000 miles with thousands of islands and believes in guarding it fiercely.

Source: <http://www.infoplease.com/atlas/country/japan.html>

Map-3: Korea and Japan

Taiwan. It can effectively choke the Chinese SLOCs as it is located across the Chinese mainland. Taiwan overlooks the SLOCs to South China Sea (SCS) from the Malacca strait and the Western Pacific shipping lane outside the first island chain. **Taiwan presents the biggest hindrance to Chinese Navy from projecting power seawards.** However, Taiwan integral to China, would reap tremendous advantages for the Chinese Navy.

(Source: <http://www.chinatouristmaps.com/assets/images/chinamaps/topography-of-jiangxi-fujian-taiwan.jpg>)

Map-4: Taiwan

Vietnam. Parcel Islands are claimed by both Vietnam and China but are under control of China. A dispute over the installation of a large Chinese oilrig in waters near the Parcel Islands in the South China Sea in the recent past escalated into a confrontation between the ships of China and Vietnam.

Philippines. There are territorial disputes between Philippines and China over certain islands and reefs of Nansha Islands. Philippines lays claim to nearly 65,000 km of waters adjacent to Nansha islands by bringing it under its Kalyaan Island group. In April 2012, a Philippine warship reportedly harassed Chinese fishing boats and fishermen. In addition Reed Bank, submerged atoll near Spratly Islands, is claimed by China and Philippines.

Multinational Maritime Disputes. Apart from the above-mentioned issues, China is embroiled in a number of maritime multinational territorial disputes namely:-

East China Sea (ECS) - Senkaku Islands are claimed by China, Japan, and Taiwan.

South China Sea (SCS)-

-Scarborough Shoal is claimed by China, Taiwan and Philippines.

-Spratly Islands are claimed in entirety by China, Taiwan and Vietnam and partly by Malaysia, Brunei and Philippines

-Macclesfield Bank, which is a group of submerged shoals and reefs between Scarborough shoal and Paracel islands, is claimed by China, Philippines and Taiwan.

EEZ Claims. The situation in respect of EEZ claims in the area can at best be stated as highly disputed due to multinational sovereignty claims over various islands and atolls.

Forces Inimical to China in the Region.

China has always perceived the United States as its main adversary. It is also clear to China that smaller states look up to the United States to support them in case bigger states in the region try to bully them in their territorial disputes or their EEZ claims. The US has strong allies and bases in the region, namely Japan, South Korea, Philippines, Australia, Thailand and Singapore. Map 5 depicts the open source information about US bases and force strength (> 40,000 troops) in the region. Coupled with this is the announcement of the Asia Pacific shift of the US Navy, which has been taken by China as an added measure aimed at containing the rise of China.

Source: http://news.antiwar.com/wp-content/uploads/2012/06/56779433_us_pacific_bases_46411.gif

Map 5: US Bases and Force Strength in the region

Further out of the total US Naval strength depicted below, 60% would be deployed in the Pacific by 2020 and the remaining in the Atlantic, needless to state that in comparison, strength of the Chinese naval forces is nowhere near:-

Overall U.S. Navy Inventory (2013)

Deployable Battle Force Ships	283
Aircraft (Operational)	3700
Aircraft Carriers	10
Amphibious Assault Ships	9
Amphibious Transport Docks	8
Dock Landing Ships	12
Cruisers	22

Destroyers	62
Frigates	17
Submarines	71
Littoral Combat Ships	3

Source: "Status of the Navy," *U.S. Navy*, last modified 2013,

The strength of PLAN is far less and is depicted in the table:-

Military Power of the People's Republic of China	
Type	Yr 2010
Nuclear Attack Submarines	6
Diesel Electric Submarines	54
Destroyers	25
Frigates	49
Tank Landing Ships	27
Medium Landing Ships	28
Coastal Patrol (Missile)	85
Aircraft Carrier	1

(source: <http://www.globalsecurity.org/military/world/china/plan-mod.htm>)

Quest for 'Ozeanraum'

It would be worthwhile to glance at some of the persuasive actions listed below, which have been taken by China in the last decade to ensure its access to the Oceans-

-Development of DongFeng 21 D Carrier killer missile having a range of +2000 km. This missile has driven a wedge of fear in carrier operations, the aircraft carriers would think twice before coming in kissing range of

this potent missile. This would ensure deterring the expedient force from roaming with impunity at just beyond the territorial waters, which it normally can, under right of innocent passage at sea.

-Claiming of an extended maritime boundary (depicted in Map-6) for itself, this in turn would lead to complete control over its 'near seas'. China has categorically stated in the UN "China has indisputable sovereignty over the islands in the South China Sea and the adjacent waters, and enjoys sovereign rights and jurisdiction over the relevant waters as well as the seabed and subsoil thereof"³

Source:

http://www.theodora.com/maps/new9/china_claimed_maritime_border.jpg

Map-6: Claimed Maritime Boundary by China

- China has been aggressively pursuing the policy of resolving maritime disputes with nations bilaterally, assuaging and addressing concerns of individual nations to avoid internationalising the issue.

-Building of artificial islands for military use by reclamation has been reported on disputed Johnson South Reef, as well as on Gaven and Cuarteron reefs. It is said that China is building airstrips on them for better monitoring of the area. This is seen as extending its reach substantially since these reefs are about 1500 miles from Chinese mainland.

-Rapid all around modernization of Chinese Naval Forces and rushing to operationalize the lone aircraft carrier while building the next one indigenously. The US has addressed the issue of modernisation of the Chinese Navy in a document “China Naval Modernization: Implications for U.S. Navy Capabilities—Background and Issues for Congress”⁴It is brought out in this document that the near term objective of modernisation of Chinese forces (including the PLAN) is Taiwan centric. In case of a developing military situation in Taiwan, the aim being to deter or at least affect a delay in intervention by US forces. The PLAN modernisation is with the long-term aim of matching US naval strength in Asia Pacific. China has concentrated on defence of its coastal areas up to the first island chain by rapidly strengthening its conventional submarine fleet and building up its nuclear submarine fleet in a calibrated manner. It also implies that China in near future does not aspire for true blue water capabilities but aims to acquire them over the next 15/20 years, when it starts operating and mastering its carriers along with its fleet ships.

-A spurt of maritime incidents asserting China’s right in disputed areas of South China Sea. For e.g. China’s announcement on November 23, 2013, of an air defense identification zone (ADIZ) for the ECS that includes airspace over the Senkaku Islands; and the implementation of fishing regulations administered by China’s Hainan province applicable to waters constituting more than half of the SCS;

- A major contentious issue, which has erupted between China and the United States of America, is the Chinese view of regulating activities of the foreign military forces within its EEZ. The US contention is that it has right of innocent passage through a country’s EEZ, and that a country can regulate only economic activities within the EEZ and does not have the right to regulate foreign military activity beyond the 12 nautical mile zone of its territorial waters.

-Forays in Indian Ocean by Chinese submarines and warships. With Chinese Naval expansion, being fundamentally Taiwan centric it can be surmised that its move to acquire influence in the Indian Ocean is of relatively of lesser importance than what is portrayed in media. In case China does use the string of pearls for positioning its naval ships (though there are no such indications) it would definitely factor, that in case of hostilities with India, many of the ports/bases would fall within the range of Agni missiles, Indian strike aircraft, ship launched Brahmos missiles and carrier based aircraft. However, such a scenario at sea appears a bit farfetched at present because China has never operated

naval bases abroad, it has no contentious maritime territorial issues with India, and its concern over SLOCs in Indian Ocean is as legitimate as the Indian concern. With China gearing up its military to tackle the United States of America at a faceoff involving Taiwan, there appears no immediate threat at sea to Indian assets/ territories.

Conclusion

It is a general view that as China accrues more economic influence and military power it will tend to be more belligerent and aggressive. An interesting study has been carried out by Alastair Johnston⁵ titled "China's Militarized Interstate Dispute Behaviour 1949-1992: A First Cut at the Data". The author has utilised conflict data from 1949 to 1992 to study the patterns in Chinese conflict behaviour and crisis management. The study does not imply that in future China will behave as per the findings of the study, but it does provide indicators to mitigating conflicts and reducing violence by engaging China meaningfully.

The study concludes that during the cold war period China got involved in more disputes except for the US, and that it was inclined to use higher levels of violence than others would. The disputes have largely involved territorial issues and consolidation of long-standing territorial claims, *the growth of China itself has not led to increase in number of disputes*. The increasing stature of China amongst nations has led China to avoid conflicts. The frequency of Militarised Interstate Disputes has not increased even with increasing economic and military power of China. The study concludes that China is more likely to use force and higher levels of force, when disputes involve territory and when the gap between the desired and ascribed status is large. ***In other words, a more powerful China does not imply a more aggressive China; in fact, it may be less likely to get involved in disputes as long as its territory is not under threat and as long as it is accorded an appropriate international status.*** However once a dispute is militarised China will escalate it to higher levels of force.

The term 'Ozeanraum' has been coined from the term 'Lebensraum' that has been used since the WW II to describe a nation's need for expansion of territories physically or metaphorically. The discussion of various issues above, related to geographical realities, conditions prevailing in the near seas of China and aspirations aptly fits China's quest for ease of access to the oceans. The title of this article "China's Quest for Ozeanraum" would stand justified in this context.

“China’s political and economic focus lies on the coastal areas... For the present and a fairly long period to come, China’s strategic focus will be in the direction of the sea.” ---**Lieutenant General Mi Zhenyu**

1. Louise Levathes, *When China Ruled the Seas, The Treasure Fleet of the Dragon Throne, 1405-1433*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1996, p. 75
2. The phrase “String of Pearls” was first used to describe China’s emerging maritime strategy in a report titled “Energy Futures in Asia” by defense contractor, Booz-Allen-Hamilton. This report was commissioned in 2005 by the U.S. Department of Defense’s Office of Net Assessment.
3. Communication from China to the United Nations dated May 7, 2009, at http://www.un.org/Depts/los/clcs_new/submissions_files/submission_vnm_37_2009.htm.
4. China Naval Modernization: Implications for U.S. Navy Capabilities—Background and Issues for Congress, 17 Oct 2012, RL33153. www.crs.gov
5. Johnston, Alastair Lain. *China's Militarized Interstate Dispute Behaviour 1949-1992: A First Cut at the Data*. The China Quarterly, 1998.

6. Is India A Key To Resolve China's Security Predicament In IOR?

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You can make your own history, But you have to live with your geography,

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Note:- The views expressed in the article by Brigadier Narender Kumar are his personal and in no way reflect the opinion of the organisation he is currently serving with.

Abstract. China's aggressive brinkmanship and desire to control the territory and strategic space in the subcontinent is a step fraught with pitfalls. Geo-strategic disposition of India in IOR is an advantage as well as a vulnerability for China if a policy of animosity or aggression is displayed. India dominates one of the busiest SLOCs in the world and has the potential to be a net security provider to the allies and strategic partner. China stands to gain if it considers India as an equal partner, but will be at a loss if it views India as a competitor. India today cannot be bullied or subdued by aggression or hegemonic stance. The time has come when China must look at India with a different prism, more as an enabler and less as an adversary.

Key Words. Indian Ocean Region (IOR), Tibet, Pivot, Hegemony, Strategic, Asia Pacific.

Introduction

China and India, the two largest developing countries in the world, have a commonality of history, culture, economic and social characteristics,

and profiles of development.¹ Yet both nations have drifted away. Geographical logic, suggests that India and China complement each other in their Geo-strategic disposition, regional security construct, energy and maritime security. China's failure to see the strategic wisdom in building bridges with India is in fact baffling. On the other hand aggressive and hegemonic posture of China is forcing India to align itself with the US, Japan and rim nations of South China Sea. In the long term China is losing an opportunity to eliminate the vulnerabilities, which it has in terms of security of SLOC, strategic posturing in IOR and uninterrupted access to the Indian Ocean Region. Normalisation of diplomatic and strategic relationship with India is definitely a win win situation for China.

India A Maritime Fulcrum in Northern Indian Ocean. China is aware that India derives its Geo-strategic importance principally from its geographical location.² Encirclement or containment of China in Asia Pacific or IOR is incomplete without the participation of India. It is a foregone conclusion that India is willy nilly one stop solution to China's insecurities in IOR and TAR. But if China wants to develop strategic ties with Pakistan instead of India it is indeed a retrograde step and lack of wisdom. India does not need China as much as China need India as a consumer market, source of industrial raw material, security of SLOC in IOR and stability in the Tibet Autonomous Region (TAR). India may not have the oil and gas reserves, but SLOC in IOR and Karakoram Highway definitely pass through the shadow of strategic influence of India. China must recognize that India moving closer to the US and Asia Pacific nations will create challenges to it.

Is Pakistan Factor Blinding Geographical Logic. During a visit of Premier Wen Jiabao to India, he went so far as to compare cooperation between India and China and stated, "two pagodas, one hardware and one software; combined, we can take the leadership position in the world."³ Yet it is perplexing why China has failed to see the geographical logic and rather neglected the Sino Indian relations in the light of the increasing footprint of the extra regional powers in IOR and Asia Pacific Region. India has the potential to be a net security provider in the Indian

¹ Zhang Guihong, U.S-India Security Relations Implications for China, accessed from <http://www.satp.org/satporgtp/publication/faultlines/volume14/article2.htm> 24 Oct 2014

² Narender Kumar, Challenges in the Indian Ocean Region Response Options, Knowledge World publishers, 2011, p 1.

³ See Jon Sigurdson, Regional Innovation System (RIS) in China, Working Paper, 2004; and Ministry of Science and Technology of the PRC and OECD: OECD Reviews of Innovation Policies, China, Paris, OECD, 2007.

Ocean Region especially the SLOC passing through 6 and 9 channels. Pakistan offers China a sea port and access to the Indian Ocean through Gwadar Port and Karakoram Highway, but given the turbulence in Pakistan, especially Balochistan and NW Frontiers, uninterrupted flow of traffic along Karakoram Highway is un-realistic. Pakistan does not have the potential to replace India as far as trade, security in IOR and availability of raw material is concerned. Banking upon Pakistan is a deal fraught with uncertainty and insecurity.

Generation of Instability a Recipe for Turbulence. Inherent resources and geography is never adequate to propel a nation to be a regional or global superpower. It needs allies, strategic partners and neutral nations to eliminate the vulnerabilities and insecurities. So far China has reposed faith in rogue nations with dubious history. That is not adequate to fill the power vacuum or to guarantee protection of core interests in a geographical area. Soviet Union did create a chain of allies, but failed to keep them with it, as a result not only Soviet Union disappeared but its allies also stood fragmented. Similarly, China has failed to create allies and secure environment in the area of its strategic influence. China's hegemony in the region is rooted in the past that is probably forcing it to pursue the policy of fragmented neighbourhood. This is a huge security deficit and failure to identify the strategic fulcrums of its rise.

What Went Wrong? It is not a complex question to answer that which country is more important for China, India or Pakistan? The answer is simple, India has greater economic opportunities, greater influence in IOR, a major power with clear development prospects, while Pakistan is a regionally important country facing an uncertain economic future.⁴ As long as core interest areas do not get compromised, strategic wisdom is in building bridges to be partners rather than being adversary and competitors. But China's aggressive and hegemonic stance is polarizing the region and friction is pushing India and other Asia Pacific nations to drift away. In the bargain, extra regional powers will have increased foot prints in IOR and South China Sea. There is a power vacuum in the region and China is rushing to fill the vacuum, but the approach adopted by China is flawed. A nation which claims that it is pursuing peaceful rise/ development should act rationally and cannot be aggressive and insensitive to the aspiration of regional countries. The bigger question is that has China miscalculated and adopted a wrong trajectory for peaceful rise / development or there is a flaw in the grand strategy? It is

⁴ Mu Chunshan, China's Choice: India or Pakistan? Which South Asian country is more important for China's future? *The Diplomat*, September 27, 2014.

beyond the realm of reality to assume that a nation can afford to survive or rise in isolation, even US need partners to remain a relevant global superpower.

Causes of Friction Between India and China. Major irritants and causes of friction have been attached to the national pride of India and China. Some of the major bottlenecks or irritants are as under:-

- **Territorial Dispute.** Both nations have attached national pride and this subject has become a sentimental issue and a no go situation. China is in occupation of 36000 square km area in Ladakh and Chinese claim over entire Arunachal Pradesh is illogical and hegemonic. Whether China is using it as a leverage against India to force India to be a subordinate power in the region or it has the intent to of forceful integration. Both aspects are irrational in nature and indeed disturbing. Until or unless both nations agree to a common acceptable LAC the high voltage drama along the borders will continue to give sleepless nights to the security establishments and the diplomatic corps.
- **Tibet Government in Exile.** China has never appreciated the idea of political asylum to the Dalai Lama and his followers in India. The crisis will deepen post Dalai Lama. If China is in a position to install its nominee as the next Dalai Lama, in that case the present Tibetan Government in exile will lose relevance. At the same time uprising in Tibet on religious or political reasons on account of imposition of the next Dalai Lama or a movement for self determination will be attributed to India, which may be far from reality, but it will be difficult to change the perception of Chinese political leadership and its establishments. China has viewed presence of Dalai Lama and Tibet government in exile as a threat to integrity of China, which is far from reality India's Tibet stand is more on humanitarian ground and not a political and diplomatic blackmail.
- **Security of SLOC.** There is a trust deficit between India and China. China considers that maritime capabilities of India are aimed at to build capabilities to establish naval blockade at a point in time. Where as India's capabilities are primarily focussed on protection of maritime boundaries and the exclusive economic zone. China should consider India's geo- strategic location as a net security provider rather than considering it as a tool to disrupt the SLOC.
- **Access to Indian Ocean Region.** China is wary of India's dominant geographical location and rising influence in South Asia. Should India and US form partnership it can literally shut the door for China. That is the biggest predicament to China since 80% volume of trade passes through the SLOC of Indian Ocean.
- **India's Foray in South China Sea.** China has not appreciated India's foray and involvement in South China Sea and Asia Pacific

region. China is averse to India standing alongside rim nations of the South China Sea, the US and Asia Pacific nations. It is deemed as a red flag to China's authoritarian claim on the South China Sea and Asia Pacific region. But China has forgotten that India is as much sensitive to China's activities in POK as she is to South China Sea. Policy of I am always right is not going to be reconciliatory in nature.

India a Strategic Pivot

India and China shares same set of predicaments and stance on strategic national issues. To play such a role, the partner should be economically strong with some clout in international politics.⁵ Competition is bound to happen when two nations are rising in a same strategic space. Both aspire to occupy the dominant regional power status in an environment where the flux of power exists. Besides Russia, India is the natural choice to complement China for mutual security and stability in the region. A Sino-Indian partnership can help China achieve its national interests more quickly and easily.⁶ Coming together of India and China, though may cause turbulence in a global power balance, but in long term perspective, it will reduce friction between two nuclear powers and bring stability to the regions. As long as Sino-India friction remains, US can afford to let the Northern Indian Ocean be handled by India.

India as a Pivot for Realignment of Power Balance in Asia. West is comfortable with India since India does not challenge the present system of global pr balance. The convergence of interests makes India a natural ally of US led western power block. Dr Tellis assess US and Indian interests with respect to China as fundamentally parallel in goals, parallel in strategy and parallel in complexities. Where as the same cannot be said about China.⁷ China's policy of aggressive and expansionist stance is causing turbulence, but serving the interests of the US and its allies by creating an environment of insecurity. US is anxious and will even go the extra mile to prevent India, China and even Russia coming together as a strategic partner.

India a Balancing Factor in Security Architect of IOR.

- China has failed to acknowledge that Russia, US and even the Asia Pacific nations stand to gain from Sino- Indian competition.

⁵Ibid.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Alyass Ayres, Power Realignment in Asia: China India and The United States, in a book edited by Alyssa Ayres, C Raja Mohan, SAGE Publications Pvt. Ltd, 2009, p 17.

US would like India to act as leverage in IOR and supplement their efforts to maintain balance in the Northern Indian Ocean Region. Similarly, as long as the rivalry remains between China and India, Russian and US weapons will continue to find a market. Similarly, Japan and Asia Pacific nations will find an ally to work out a hedging strategy against China. In the backdrop of these geo-strategic realities, China should be able to decipher what is larger good for both nations. Unfortunately China seems to be carrying the baggage of history and refuse to narrow the trust deficit in the larger good of both nations.

- Security architect of IOR is unimaginable without India as a dominant partner. No matter how many bases or places China acquire in Indian Ocean Region or so called string of pearls, India will continue to maintain dominant presence. China and extra regional powers have to acknowledge this fact and should get used to of working with India rather than against India. Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) lacks geographic significance without India. SCO has the potential to upset the balance of power in Asia provided India is part of this group. More than the trade and commerce it will assist Russia and China to have secured SLOC and uninterrupted access, provided China resolve long pending border disputes with India and acknowledge India's dominant geographical location in the IOR. In the true sense rise of Eurasian Heartland can be a reality with India as a strategic partner.

More Flexible and More Responsive Stance a Way Ahead. No nation has benefited from rigid and unresponsive posture. China has to display flexibility and more responsibility in dealing with its neighbours. It must learn to accommodate and accept the territorial autonomy of regional and neighbouring nations for collective growth. India's right to exercise sovereign autonomy of its territory is legitimate and China must accept this fact with grace and without any ambiguity. China must refrain to call right a wrong and wrong a right which it has done often when it comes to the territorial claim over the sovereign territory of India.

Conclusion

Conflict and confrontation are generally unpleasant affairs that churn up unpleasant emotions.⁸ China stands to gain from developing a strategic partnership with India more than any other nation in the region. China must look at India as a net security provider in IOR rather than as a competitor or an adversary. A relationship based on pragmatism is the best that can emerge from this loaded and complex

⁸ Robert Greene, *The 36 Strategies of War*, Viva Books, 2006, p 279.

heritage and its three decades of “freeze.”⁹China has to climb down from its stated position and acknowledge the reality and the right of a nation to maintain sovereign control over its territory. If China does not accept the geographical logic and the long term impact of continued friction with India, it will lose an opportunity to secure its vital interests in the IOR. India as a rising economic and regional power that can neither be ignored nor can be subdued for long. If China allows India to drift to a point of no return, China will be at a loss. “The dream to make China rich and strong”¹⁰ will remain incomplete if China refuses to acknowledge the significance of India as a regional power and partner. China needs to realise that, “Geography has made us neighbours. History has made us friends. Economics has made us partners, and necessity will make us allies”.

⁹Jean-François Huchet, *Between Geostrategic Rivalry and Economic Competition, Emergence of a Pragmatic India-China Relationship*, China perspectives, 2008/3 (2008).

¹⁰ Timothy Cheek, *Beyond Exceptionalism: China’s Intellectuals from Tragic Heroes to US Allies*, in Timothy B. Weston, Lionel M. Jensen (ed) *China Beyond The Headlines*, Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, 2000, P 128.

7. China in the Indian Ocean: Strategic interests and policies

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Abstract:

The Indian Ocean has become the key strategic arena in global politics due to its increasing importance in the area of global economic trade and global security. With a booming economy and aspiring great power status, China seems to enter the Indian Ocean by becoming an active player in the region. This shows the strategic shift in China's maritime focus from the long standing focus on the Pacific to that of looking into the Indian Ocean. China has increased its military activities in the region, expanding the range of its navy westward. This strategic approach is mainly attributed to the growing energy demands and geopolitical considerations vis-à-vis the U.S. and India in the region. In this light, China's unfolding Indian Ocean strategy is often perceived as an alternative to avoid the Malacca Dilemma'. Thereby, with this context, the present paper attempts to focus on the strategic value of the Indian Ocean in international politics. The

objective of the paper is to trace China's changing maritime perception towards the Indian Ocean, analysing its emerging strategic security interests in the region and the policies adopted- which is a key element in China's national security.

Keywords: China, Indian Ocean, Malacca Dilemma, Maritime security, Strategic interests.

I. Introduction: Indian Ocean in 21st Century Global Politics

Oceans have always been an important factor in great power politics, owing to their significance in the survival and economic development of nation-states. In the twenty-first century, oceans have become the new theatre of international politics. With this view, the Indian Ocean, third largest ocean in the world tactically placed between the Arabian Sea and the Bay of Bengal, surpassed the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans and has become the most important strategically significant trade corridor.

Owing to its geopolitical landscape, it has become the key strategic maritime corridor for global economy and security. In this context, the strategic importance of Indian Ocean can be best assessed in the prophetic words of maritime strategist Rear Admiral Alfred Thayer Mahan, who famously stated: "Whoever attains maritime supremacy in the Indian Ocean would be a prominent player on the international scene. Whoever controls the Indian Ocean dominates Asia. This Ocean is the key to the seven seas in the twenty-first century, the destiny of the world will be decided in these waters." It is viewed as an 'active ocean', which many perceive as the emerging centre of gravity in the strategic world.

In assessing the importance of the Indian Ocean, Robert Kaplan argued that "the Indian Ocean-- the world's third largest body of water-- forms centre stage for the challenges of the twenty-first century"¹, the place where global struggles would be played out, in addition to, conflicts over

energy security, clashes between Islam and the West and rivalry between a rising China and India. This assessment holds true as having a strategic geography, Indian Ocean has served as the main route thoroughfare for trade between Asia and Europe and with the turn of the century, has significantly emerged as the world's principal source of energy and the highway over which that energy is transported to the rest of the world.² Thus, being a critical waterway, Indian Ocean is the new hotspot of global politics serving as a key route for both global economic trade and security, and hence, the central ground of power politics of the twenty-first century.

II. China and the Indian Ocean: *Why is the Indian Ocean important?*

Indian Ocean has become the new pivot of international politics. What makes Indian Ocean the centre of gravity is its unusual geography which imparts vulnerability to the most significant trade corridor. The vulnerability lies in the fact that it is "home to important SLCOs (Sea Lanes of Communications) and maritime choke points"³, which are narrow entry and exit points to and from adjacent waters. These include the Strait of Hormuz which joins the Indian Ocean with the Persian Gulf and the Strait of Malacca, which is the primary exit/entrance between the Indian and the Pacific oceans. While the other vital chokepoints include the Bab el-Mandab, the narrow strait that links the Indian Ocean with the Red Sea and the Mediterranean, and the Mozambique Channel/Cape of Good Hope, which is the gateway between the Indian and South Atlantic oceans- which form the vital routes for trade and energy (oil and gas) supplies.⁴ Together these carry over 50 per cent of the world's container traffic and over 80 per cent of the world's seaborne oil trade travels through this maritime corridor of the Indian Ocean.

Among these bottlenecks, the two most significant chokepoints that forms the nodal to the trade are⁵: first, the Strait of Hormuz, located at the head of the Persian Gulf between Iran and Oman, is the world's most

important oil chokepoint- moving around 35 per cent of the world's seaborne trade in oil, largely destined for Asia, Europe and the United States. And, the second major chokepoint is the Strait of Malacca, between Indonesia and Malaysia, which is the major trading route between the Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean. This trade route carries almost one-third of global trade with energy supplies, transported from the Middle East to East Asia. Thereby, any disruption to the sea lanes calls for severe security implications for the littoral states, which hinders their economic development. As for instance, a blockade at the Malacca Straits would cause almost half of world's shipping fleet to reroute through the Sunda or Lombok Straits- through the Indonesian Archipelago which are themselves vulnerable to blockade.

Keeping this context, although the People's Republic of China's (PRC) primary strategic focus have been on the Pacific but it seems that it is shifting its maritime domain and looking the 'Mahanian Way' into the Indian Ocean. It is the rising power of China and its important thirst for energy and resources that has led to the strategic shift towards the Indian Ocean. Although India enjoys a certain degree of supremacy in the Indian Ocean over China's weak posture, but it would be a folly to ignore China's gradually unfolding ambitions which are indicative of a robust maritime and naval presence.

In this changing nature of strategic landscape of the Indian Ocean, it can be rightly said that Beijing's forward-leaning posture in the Indian Ocean arena, of becoming a major nautical player is deemed to change the strategic geometry of the region. It is because Indian Ocean has become a priority for China based on its maritime and security interests as it serves as a focal point in China's calculative security interests related to its overseas energy and trade shipments. More than 70 percent of China's imported energy supplies are transported through shipping lanes in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR), with major strategic checkpoints at the Malacca Strait.

To secure its national interests China is expanding its military posture and naval modernisation in the Indian Ocean.⁶The exemplary to China's unfolding Indian Ocean strategy is its recent January 2014 naval drill conducted by a three-ship Chinese navy squadron- where the largest amphibious Chinese landing ship – *Changbaishan* - along with two destroyers - *Wuhan* and *Haikou* took part.⁷The choice of Lombok Strait near Indonesia as the drill location has been a strategic choice- which demonstrates to the Indo-Pacific region that China's combat reach now extends to the eastern Indian Ocean.⁸ Srikanth Kondapalli notes that with this "China could be testing the waters in the eastern Indian Ocean, including its ability to operate some distance away from its bases in the region".⁹Above all, the principle driver behind China's strategic gaze into the Indian Ocean can be understood in its aspiration for great power status fuelled by a booming economy which is primarily guided by the quest for economic and energy security. It is therefore, important to assess China's strategic interests and policies of being a potential maritime player in the Indian Ocean.

III. China in the Indian Ocean: *What are the Strategic Interests and Security Concerns?*

Historically, China has been a continental power. Since 2000, China's maritime strategy is debated as a way to pursue peaceful development in the light of its exponential rise to global power. Though China's primary focus lies in the Pacific and is not an Indian Ocean country, but the new international dynamics has prompted China's maritime shift to the Indian Ocean- making it one of the pillars of China's maritime strategy in the formation of a new strategy. The rationale behind this can be understood in the determinant power of the seas to predict the fate of the nations, where in the era of emerging markets, trade and international cooperation and the SLOCs- seas have become the ultimate highways for nations to interact and communicate in the new century. Like other countries, China is now interdependent in a globalized market and

involved with a growing number of international agenda such as global warming, energy security, nation-building, nuclear proliferation and global financial system.¹⁰ Thereby, to fulfil these national security objectives, China needs to have access to all strategic resources and protecting the critical sea lanes transporting energy supplies from abroad, in the overall interest of its development. This maritime interest is well coded in China's latest Defence White Paper (2013) on "protecting national maritime rights and interests" and "armed forces providing reliable support for China's interests overseas." It is clear that the PRC intends to expand the capabilities of its navy, especially to operate abroad- shifting the policy from conducting coastal defence activities to offshore defence and ultimately to far sea defence.¹¹

China's initial interest into the Indian Ocean was primarily drawn as a reaction to the increasing US and Soviet presence, but with the rising tensions over the territorial sovereignty of the South China Sea, China directed its focus in consolidating its access to the Indian Ocean through the Karakoram Highway and Karachi, through the China-Burma road to Burmese ports and through the Malacca Straits.¹² This external influence to China's Indian Ocean seems apparent in the official statements and observations of authoritative scholars, including the remarks in the 'Blue Book of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences' published in 2013, which confirm China's dominant thinking on the Indian Ocean- which is majorly driven by the presence of two dominant powers, the US and India¹³

But since the onset of the 21st century, marked by China's sudden economic boost to becoming a world economy and a top trading nation, the focus in the Indian Ocean has been primarily shaped by the concerns of the freedom and safety of navigation in international trade waterway. Since the Indian Ocean is an important waterway of international trade, it's natural that the increase of interest will result in the increase of security demand, and the increase of security demand will result in the

promotion of security strategy.¹⁴ Thus, as China continues to grow steadily, it needs energy resources to meet the increasing needs of its rising population, whereby majority of China's oil imports passes through the Indian Ocean, especially through the Strait of Malacca. While Indian Ocean due to its geographical proximity and historical linkages, has been traditionally influenced by India. In the realist assumption, China's pragmatic approach lies in increasing its own presence in the region as an imperative to preserve its national interests.¹⁵

In this framework of analysis, China's strategic interests in the Indian Ocean seems to be driven by two major factors. First, Energy Security, which is a paramount concern, which Maharaja Krishna Rasgotra, a former Indian Foreign Secretary views as "to safeguard the supplies of much-needed energy and material sources from Middle East and Africa".¹⁶ Here, the concern lies over securing the SLOC that spreads from the Persian Gulf to the South China Sea. As to pursue a 'well-off society', a rapidly increasing energy supply is fundamental to China's future.

The exponential economic growth and demand for energy led China to become a net importer of crude oil in 1993 from being a net exporter, being the world's sixth largest oil producer. This is a result of China's heightened energy use which has doubled in the past two decades. Projections suggest that the import production gap will continue to grow through 2020 and beyond. Currently, importing 48 per cent of its oil, China perceives heavy energy shortages from a constricted global market as one of its gravest threat.¹⁷ Here, since 80 per cent of China's petroleum imports pass through the Malacca Strait, which is referred to as the 'lifeline' of China's economic development.¹⁸ To avoid any threat to energy supply, China is diversifying suppliers and developing other transit routes, including overland pipelines as an alternate means of transporting its energy needs- whereby Indian Ocean offers an

alternative to its 'Malacca dilemma'- where China fears a lack of control of sea lanes. Thus, the increasing energy needs have compelled Beijing to "cast anxious eyes on the Sea Lines of Communication" whereby the "security of the waterways stretching from China's coastlines to the Indian Ocean has taken on special policy importance for Beijing".¹⁹ And in this regard, to avoid any Thereby, to avoid any inherent risks of energy imports and transport bottlenecks, China has adopted strategies such as- pursuing equity stakes in overseas upstream energy projects, building overland or underwater pipelines, investing in pariah states such as Iran, Myanmar, Sudan and others and by establishing Strategic Petroleum Reserves (SPRs)²⁰, to secure its energy needs.

Second, geopolitical considerations driven by the ambition in building an ocean capacity to become an 'active actor' to further promote China's rise in the global scope.²¹ To which, Rasgotra views as motivated "to project power in the Indian Ocean in rivalry not only with India but primarily with the U.S."²² Here, U.S. and India are two countries which are most important for China's freedom of navigation in the Indian Ocean.²³ With U.S., China's strategic thinking in the Indian Ocean is guided by fear of US containment of PRC-"by roping in Indian Ocean littorals within an 'Indo-Pacific' framework"²⁴ and of America's prowess in holding of China's sea-dependent economy hostage in times of crisis, mainly the Malacca Straits.²⁵ This is because the geostrategic position of China is vulnerable along with the requirement of the heavy use of the Malacca-Strait in the south-east Asia- which is a significant strategic choke points which SLOCs travel through.²⁶

Apart from the worries on US dominance, China's strategic thinking in Indian Ocean is also majorly guided by India's supreme presence in the region. China increasingly views India's rise, especially its rapidly strengthening and modernising navy- as a potential challenge to its interests in the IOR. As for China, India dominates the Indian Ocean by virtue of its geographic location and, given its potential to be a great

power together with its aspirations in that regard, could compete with China for strategic and hegemonic space in the future. Furthermore, China recognises India's requirement for energy security, which it anticipates as another challenge to its own energy procurement.²⁷

Since both India and China are rising powers, thereby, China's strategic thinking is guided by the policy to counter-weight India's balance of power. China has projected its sphere of influence on the littoral states, by building closer ties with Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Pakistan, Bangladesh and others, which is commonly perceived as China's "String of Pearls Strategy" to encircle India with commercial and military facilities.

Therefore, the strategic interests of China in the Indian Ocean is clearly reflected in the PLA Navy's growing operations in the Indian Ocean which reflect China's desire to improve its ability to combat perceived threats to sea routes vital to its economic development- to "break through" the First Island Chain to operate in China's "distant seas".²⁸ As it is argued by the PLA strategists and academics that the United States uses the First Island Chain to "encircle" or "contain" China and prevent the PLA Navy from operating freely beyond China's immediate periphery.²⁹ China's maritime interests are an offshoot of impressive economic growth and the attendant appetite for energy resources. Hence, China's interest is to safeguard the expanding national interests- trade and energy, by securing an uninhibited access to the high seas as there is an inherent paranoia of 'Malacca Dilemma'.³⁰

IV. China's Indian Ocean Strategy: Access through Myanmar, String of Pearls and the Maritime Silk Road

With these motivations, China is involved in flexing its military muscle in the Indian Ocean, which is reflective of its unequivocal desire to improve their ability to combat any kind of perceived threat to the critical sea lanes- which directly pose a challenge to its economic development. With such hawkish behaviour, China's national security strategy aims to forge

a link to the Indian Ocean in order to have an unimpeded market access, more direct energy supply lines, and the option of bypassing the dangerous bottleneck of the Strait of Malacca.³¹To accomplish this national interest, China's Indian Ocean strategy can thus, be best assessed in the following three strategic policies.

First, Access through Myanmar-to reduce its dependence on the strait for supplies of oil and other commodities, China is using Myanmar as a gateway to secure access to the Indian Ocean.³² Whereby, it is establishing a strategic network of road, rail and air transport from Yunnan Province in the southwest through Myanmar to the Indian Ocean, as Myanmar acts as the most convenient 'land bridge'³³ to the Indian Ocean both for its acquisition of trade routes as well as security. China intends to connect to Myanmar by constructing oil, gas and water pipelines- such as, a natural gas pipeline have been laid at a seabed of a gas field called "Shwe" off to the Rakhine State, while a deep-sea port is under construction in Madaya island near Kyaukpyu- which is said to transport crude oil from Middle East and Africa to Myanmar through a pipeline to the Yunnan province in China.

Second, String of Pearls Strategy, which is establishment of naval bases coupled with diplomatic presence strategically located at points in the IOR- acts as a means to project China's maritime power into the Indian Ocean and beyond to the Middle East. It is reported that this policy is mainly centered around reported fears of an oil blockade of one or more key choke points for shipping at the straits of Hormuz, Malacca, Luzon and Taiwan.³⁴ As the Chinese fear a US naval blockade at the strategic chokepoints, especially Hormuz and Malacca, preventing oil tankers from reaching China.

China's this Indian Ocean policy, which can be called 'Look West', is primarily aimed at encircling India. This strategy as argued is seen as an attempt of Beijing to establish a series of naval outposts in the Indian

Ocean, with the presumed aim of keeping the Indian Navy from consolidating its influence over its own strategic backyard (to use the same logic that Beijing applies to the South China Sea).³⁵ The pearls are: Gwadar (Pakistan), the Hambantota port (Sri Lanka), Chittagong (Bangladesh) and Sittwe and Coco Island (Myanmar).

Third, Maritime Silk Road Plan, proposed by President Xi Jinping in October 2013. Under this plan, China announced 10 billion Yuan (\$1.6bn) fund to build ports and to boost maritime connectivity with Southeast Asian and Indian Ocean littoral countries, in support of infrastructure projects under the 'silk road plan'. In the Indian Ocean, China is cooperating with littoral states in building the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor and China- India-Myanmar-Bangladesh Economic Corridor. With these mega-projects and heavy investment, China intends to mitigate the security concerns in the Maritime Silk Road, ranging from territorial disputes in the South China Sea to transnational threats such as piracy, armed robbery and terrorism.³⁶

Hence, China's quest to gain prominence in the Indian Ocean is being regulated by the above three policies in order to safeguard its national interests.

V. Conclusion:

In the concluding remarks, it can therefore, be stated that China is indeed looking the 'Mahanian Way' in its attempt to gain influence in the Indian Ocean vis-à-vis the other stakeholders- U.S. and India. It is a strategic move on China's part which is aimed to avert the 'Malacca Dilemma' and secure its 'peaceful rise' by safeguarding the national strategy of economic development. And this national objective can only be achieved by securing the Sea Lanes of Communications which are vital for trade and energy security. Till now, China has been a relatively weaker and dormant actor in the Indian Ocean but how it evolves into an active player and through what means is the test of time. Therefore, Indian Ocean is already on its way to become the new 'great game' between the major powers.

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**8. Competing for Influence:
Revival of China's Maritime Silk Road
and India's Project Mausam**

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As China celebrated its 65th anniversary on September 30, 2014, President Xi Jinping stated that China would continue to *give priority to development, adhere to reform and innovation and remain committed to the path of peaceful development.*¹ The Chinese economy has been growing at an impressive pace since the early 1980s, and many experts expect it to continue expanding at a similar rate over the next few decades. If so, China, with its huge population and enormous wealth will eventually have the wherewithal to build a formidable military. There is and has been continuous debate, discussions and speculations whether China would rise peacefully or will China flex its military muscle. While there is no single structural realist answer to these questions, some realist theorists predict that China's ascent will lead to serious instability. Others provide reasons to think that a powerful China can have relatively peaceful relations with its neighbours as well as the major powers. Borrowing from the defensive realist strand of thought, in spite of the scramble for security competition, it is likely that the international system would create a strong incentive for China to be able to co-exist with neighbours peacefully.² The unchanging nature of geographical proximity that mandates two countries always inhabit a contested space would continue to be confronted with competition from each other. With China's forays in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR) which India considers its own strategic backyard, IOR has become one such contested space which has become a theatre of both competition for influence and power projection between India and China.

China's Revival of Maritime Silk Road

China's recent policies showcase that Peoples Republic of China (PRC) is trying to enhance cooperation with its Central and Southeast Asia border-states in what is called "New Silk Road diplomacy". Behind this approach there are mostly domestic motivations to preserve stability at

the borders on the Western part of China, secure export markets and energy supply routes and also to lessen the development gaps between the eastern and the western provinces of China. Central to President Xi's strategy has been the extension of the Silk Road concept that has been largely discussed in relation to China's policy towards Central and Inner Asian regions to the maritime domain. On September 7, 2013, President Xi in a speech at Kazakhstan's Nazarbayev University announced a new foreign policy initiative called "Silk Road Economic Belt" to intensify international cooperation and undertake joint development through Eurasia. Elaborating on this new foreign policy directive, he stated that China with overall regional cooperation would strengthen economic collaboration, improve road connectivity, promote trade and investment, facilitate currency conversion and bolster people-to-people exchanges.³ Following the enunciation of China's Silk Road Economic Belt, Chinese President in a speech addressing Indonesia's Parliament extended the Silk Road policy to the maritime domain. He called for a re-establishment of the old sea networks to create a "Maritime Silk Road" to foster international connectivity, scientific and environmental research and fishery activities.⁴ The idea of a maritime silk road has evolved into a foreign and security policy of China as the country envisions constructing a maritime silk road that connects the waters of the Pacific and the Indian Ocean Region through a route of inter-state commercial activities. The Maritime Silk Road is aimed at connecting China in the east to Iran and the Mediterranean in the West and is expected to strengthen maritime economy, environment, technical and scientific cooperation.

The Asian security complexion is undergoing a flux and China's assertive stance in the South and East China Seas has been met with apprehensions from neighbours including Japan, Vietnam, the Philippines and Singapore. Chinese designs of Maritime Silk Road which aims to connect the waters of the Pacific and the Indian Ocean have been accompanied by a profound shift in Chinese naval power's presence in the Indian Ocean Region. As India gravitates towards being a net security provider in the region, it is likely that Indian and the Chinese navy may come in contestation with each other. Admiral Alfred Thayer Mahan's seminal work, *The Influence of Sea Power upon History 1660-1783*, "Whoever controls the Indian Ocean dominates Asia. Mahan writes;

The history of Sea Power is largely, though by no means solely, a narrative of contests between nations, of mutual rivalries, of violence frequently culminating in war. The profound influence of sea commerce upon the wealth and strength of countries was clearly seen long before the true

*principles which governed its growth and prosperity were detected. To secure to one's own people a disproportionate share of such benefits, every effort was made to exclude others, either by the peaceful legislative methods of monopoly or prohibitory regulations, or, when these failed, by direct violence. The clash of interests, the angry feelings roused by conflicting attempts thus to appropriate the larger share, if not the whole, of the advantages of commerce, and of distant unsettled commercial regions, led to wars. On the other hand, wars arising from other causes have been greatly modified in their conduct and issue by the control of the sea.*⁵

Central to Mahan's thesis is a narrative of contests between nations to gain influence of sea commerce, culminating into mutual rivalries and clash of interests. Borrowing from Mahan's premise to take a stock of developments in the IOR provides ground of analysis that expansion of Chinese footprints in the IOR is likely to clash with Indian interests. Although, China has invited India to join its Maritime Silk Road initiative, India with reservations finds its neighbours Sri Lanka and Maldives within Beijing's Maritime Silk Road calculus. Reports of Sri Lanka allowing Chinese submarines *Changzheng-2* and warship *Chang Xing Dao*, docking at its port has further failed to assuage Indian concerns regarding Chinese naval presence in India's southern part.⁶ Responding to the event of Chinese submarines docked at Lankan port, an official from Chinese Defence Ministry told news agency Xinhua, "It is an international common practice for a navy submarine to stop for refueling and crew refreshment at an overseas port". Indian strategic studies expert, C. Raja Mohan has been quick to respond stating that an explanation often is worse than the presumed offence as statements from Colombo and Beijing on the frequent appearance of Chinese submarines and ships at Sri Lankan ports are likely to worsen New Delhi's concerns rather than blunt them.⁷China has been building ports facilities across South Asia in Pakistan, Bangladesh and Myanmar. While many security experts worry about Chinese presence in IOR, some see no reason for alarm. They point out that ports cannot be quickly converted into naval facilities. Expert Bharat Karnad has noted that rising Chinese naval profile in the IOR is more of a shadow play. He offers reasons that during war time, no port in the Indian Ocean is going to be available to the Chinese navy because none of these countries can afford to alienate India. All of India's neighbours have relied heavily substantively on Indian security for their protection both in the past and the present.⁸

Indian Initiatives to Restore Strategic Balance

The present government's agenda has been focused on improvising economic and security ties with the neighbourhood. India is also bolstering its maritime cooperation with countries creating credible network of partnership to respond to China's growing naval profile. India is the founding member of the Contact Group on Piracy and also of the Indian Ocean Naval Symposium (IONS) – a voluntary initiative that seeks to increase maritime co-operation among navies of the littoral states of the Indian Ocean Region by providing an open and inclusive forum for discussion of regionally relevant maritime issues. In the process, it endeavours to generate a flow of information between naval professionals that would lead to common understanding and possibly cooperative solutions on the way ahead.⁹ India has close defence ties with almost all important countries in the region, particularly Mauritius, Maldives, Seychelles, Sri Lanka, Singapore, Vietnam and Malaysia. India started Maritime Security Cooperation in October 2011 with Sri Lanka and Maldives to intensify trilateral cooperation on maritime security which included initiatives to enhance Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA), training and capacity building in the areas of MDA and joint activities including trilateral exercises.¹⁰ India cannot prevent Maldives and Sri Lanka from joining Xi's Silk Road, however it could take another look at the existing cooperation agenda and improvise on short to long term agenda for the three countries in the IOR. Recently, India's External Affairs Minister, Sushma Swaraj traveled to two key neighbours in the IOR, Mauritius, where three ships from the Western Fleet of the Indian Navy namely, INS Mumbai, INS Deepak and INS Talwar were docked, and Maldives, to enhance and deepen security ties. This underscored the importance of India's bilateral ties aimed at multi-faceted cooperation in ensuring peace, stability and maritime security with these countries.¹¹ Along with regional neighbours, India has sought to deepen military ties with Vietnam. India has offered a \$100 million concessional credit line to Vietnam for purchasing patrol boats and is focusing on enhancing naval cooperation through joint naval exercises and working on issues of maritime security.¹² Successive Indian governments have attempted to respond to the changing geopolitics of the IOR by adjusting its foreign policy to a new backdrop of maritime security imperatives. On the multi-lateral front, one of the key initiatives launched by the present government to retain Indian influence in the IOR is 'Project Mausam'.

Project Mausam: The Ministry of External Affairs has enunciated a new foreign policy initiative 'Project Mausam'. "Mausam" which is Arabic for "Mawsin" refers to the season in ancient times when ships could sail

safely. Project Mausam launched by India is a multi-disciplinary, trans-national project which would endeavor to position itself at two levels: at the macro level it would reconnect and re-establish communications between countries of the Indian Ocean while at the micro level, the focus would be to understand national cultures in their regional maritime milieu. Project Mausam would link cultural route and maritime landscape across the multi-faceted Indian Ocean “world” — extending from East Africa, the Arabian Peninsula, the Indian subcontinent and Sri Lanka to the Southeast Asian archipelago coastal centres to their hinterland. The aim of this project is to enhance and multiply the movement of people, goods and ideas across the Indian Ocean enabling multi-cultural and multi-ethnic interaction and exchange. Of particular interest is the undertaking of joint collaborative research studies on the knowledge and manipulation of the monsoon wind which impacted ancient and historical trades, local economies, politics and cultural identities. Thus, along with rekindling long lost ties across the Indian Ocean Littoral and forging new avenues of cooperation and exchanges between India and states of the Indian Ocean, Project Mausam would also contribute to the dissemination of culture and civilization along the IOR.¹³

A report submitted by Pentagon in June 2014 to the US Congress notes that China is steadily expanding operational deployment in the IOR with Chinese Navy being equipped with advanced nuclear submarines, destroyers and frigates.¹⁴ China’s expansion of operational deployments of submarines with added nuclear-strike capability alters the strategic balance in the IOR. Another recent report by the Wall Street Journal notes that a Chinese attack submarine known as the hunter-killer, designed to destroy enemy vessels slipped through the Strait of Malacca above water and disappeared only to resurface near Sri Lanka and then in the Persian Gulf. Reportedly this successful voyage of Chinese submarine hunter-killer has fulfilled China’s four-decade quest of joining the elite club of countries with nuclear subs that can ply the high seas.¹⁵ Drawing from the realist tradition, balance of power is considered to be a function of tangible assets- such as armored divisions and nuclear weapons that each power controls. A Chinese nuclear submarine like hunter-killer is only creating security dilemma in the Indian Ocean. The essence of security dilemma is that - the measures a state takes to increase its own security¹⁶; in the case of China- a claim to bolster economic interests through Maritime Silk Road decreases the level of security of other states. In spite of rhetoric of China’s ‘peaceful rise’, a competing narrative of unilateral action as seen when the Ministry of

National Defence of the PRC announced the establishment of an Air Defence Identification (ADIZ) in the East China Sea. These unilateral actions have only added to uncertainty about intentions and have now rather become unavoidable due to Chinese forays in the Indian Ocean. Hence, states in the Indian Ocean can only be hopeful about China's claim to 'peaceful rise' and adjust to the changing geopolitics of the region through bilateral and multilateral partnerships.

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**9. Learning To Be Loved:
An Initial Assessment of China's Soft Power Promotion since
2000**

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Professor Zhu has received several research fellowships, including two POSCO fellowships at the East-West Center in Hawaii, a Korea Foundation/Freeman Foundation fellowship to do research in Korea, and two visiting fellowships at the East Asian Institute of National University of Singapore. In the early 1990s, he was the senior assistant to the Public Affairs Officer at the American Consulate General in Shanghai, China)

After more than 30 years of rapid development, China has become a powerful and arguably an indispensable player in the world today. Since the early 2000s Beijing has been consciously cultivating a positive international image. Most people in China are wealthier and China's modern infrastructure has awed the world. Chinese officials assume that since China has contributed positively to global development, people outside China ought to view it favorably. Yet one of the frustrations that

China faces is that despite its remarkable progress, its international image remains unsatisfactory in many parts of the world, especially in the West. According to the BBC polls, a puzzling trend is that over the last decade, negative ratings of China have gone up dramatically from 32 percent in 2005 to 42 percent in 2014, while the proportion of people who view China positively has dropped from 48 percent to 42 percent. Countries in developing regions tend to view China's development more positively, while developed countries tend to be more negative. Surveys by other organizations such as the Pew Research Center and the Chicago Council on Global Affairs reveal similar results.

China does not seem to enjoy a good image that is commensurate with its standing in today's global economy. While many Chinese have expressed high personal satisfaction, displayed strong patriotism and are some of the most optimistic people, the outside world does not seem to have such a bright view of China. This discrepancy is perplexing and worth studying.

Strategies to Boost Overseas Image

In order to soften its image around the world, the Chinese government has resorted to several major strategies since the early 2000s:

- 1) Highest-level diplomacy

High-level engagements are symbolic in international politics and are often viewed as a barometer of how serious a country's leaders view

its foreign relations. Top Chinese leaders from Hu Jintao and Wen Jiabao to Xi Jinping and Li Keqiang have been busy global-trotters, travelling to every corner of the world to promote trade, seek energy, expand investment, and enhance China's soft power.¹ Everywhere they go, Chinese leaders will emphasize how China's development has contributed positively to global peace and prosperity.

Since assuming the party leadership and presidency in late 2012 and early 2013, Xi Jinping has displayed a new diplomatic style. For example, his visits abroad are typically accompanied by his glamorous wife Peng Liyuan, making full use of the "first lady diplomacy" to reach out to and generate goodwill from a wider audience. President Xi has also revived the "panda diplomacy" by sending a pair of pandas to South Korea during his visit to Seoul in July 2014.

Chinese leaders seem to understand the significance of "soft power" in its foreign relations and have reached out to the ordinary people during their trips abroad. In February 2012, then Vice President Xi Jinping, on his official tour in the United States, went to Muscatine, Iowa to see his "old friends" who he met during the 1980s when he first visited the small town as a county official from Hebei province.

In October 2013, Xi Jinping visited Southeast Asia and attended the APEC and East Asian Summit as the new president of China. In contrast, due to the federal government shutdown President Barack Obama cancelled (the 3rd time) his Asia trip, prompting many to question

how committed the United States is to its strategic rebalancing towards the Asia Pacific. Though President Obama did return to Asia in April 2014, doubt about America's commitment to Asia lingers. The United States still dwarfs China in global influence, but China has tried very hard to catch up.

2) Strengthened official *duiwai xuanchuan* (overseas publicity)

To be more transparent, China has established a multi-layered news briefing system. At the central government level, the Information Office of the State Council regularly holds news conferences. Major ministries such as Ministries of Foreign Affairs, Defense, Public Security, Commerce, and Taiwan Affairs Office have set up their own spokesperson system.

All major Chinese media, especially the “Big Four”—*Xinhua*, *China Central Television (CCTV)*, *China Daily*, and *Radio China International*—have strengthened their overseas operations since 2000. For a long time, *China Daily*, which was launched in 1981, had been the only English-language source of daily news and information from China. That has completely changed. The Chinese government reportedly gave *Xinhua* and *People's Daily* cash injections of 15 billion yuan each to pursue the projects.² The English language *Global Times* was launched in April 2009 as “a new reliable channel for Chinese people and the rest of the world to understand one another,” according to its website. An affiliate of *People's Daily*—the Communist Party's mouthpiece, the Chinese version of *Global Times* has long been popular

among nationalists, but it is the newly launched English version that has often strayed into realms once thought taboo. For example, in 2009, it was the only Chinese paper to report on the anniversary of the Tiananmen Square protests and their suppression in 1989.

China is learning to take control of “*hua yu quan*” (discourse power) in international affairs. By October 2009, CCTV had already set up 6 channels to broadcast news globally in English, French, Spanish, Arabic, Russian and Chinese around the clock to counter the perceived “distorted reporting” of China by foreign media. It increased the number of foreign news bureaus from 19 to 56 between 2010 and 2013. CCTV-America and CCTV-Africa began broadcasting in 2012 and have hired a number of veteran foreign journalists and anchors to make their programs appear more international and objective. The Chinese media are moving toward more instant reporting and transparency, with live coverage of major events and interviews and dialogues with international commentators. These government efforts to enhance China’s *duiwai xuanchuan* are described by some as “a Great Leap Outward” for Chinese media.³

To help the public understand China’s policies on key issues, the Chinese government has started to publish a series of white papers. Since the early 2000s, the State Council Information Office has published, among others, Ecological Improvement and Environmental Protection in Tibet (2003), Progress in China’s Human Rights Cause (2003), China’s Peaceful Development Road (2005), China’s National

Defense (yearly), Progress in China's Human Rights (2009), China's Peaceful Development (2011), The White Paper on Diaoyu Islands (2012), etc.

3) Active global participation and skillful diplomats

China's increasing involvement in regional and international affairs helps alter people's views of China. The hosting of the Six-Party talks, the dispatch of anti-piracy warships to the Gulf of Aden, appointment of special envoys on Sudan and the Middle East, and emphasis on soft power by establishing Confucius Institutes globally are just some of China's more active diplomatic efforts. In 2014, China became the first major power to restore its embassy in Somalia after the African country became more stable following decades of civil wars. Due to its active and more sophisticated diplomacy, China has secured a firm foothold in much of the developing world.

A new generation of Chinese diplomats are filling key positions of Chinese foreign service. These diplomats tend to be young, fluent in foreign languages, well versed in foreign culture and history, and have an international perspective. Different from the traditional stern face and Marxist rhetoric of Chinese officialdom, these diplomats are good at appealing to foreign governments and publics directly, using the language the latter can understand. The current foreign minister, Wang Yi, is an urbane and skillful diplomat, having accumulated experience from his previous positions as a vice foreign minister, ambassador to Japan, and head of the State Council's Taiwan Affairs Office. His

remarks about China's foreign policy, while vigorously defending China's long-standing principles and practices, sound rational, conciliatory, and pragmatic, as evidenced by his speech at the UN in September 2013.

After Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe's visit to the controversial Yasukuni Shrine in December 2013, Chinese diplomats took the offensive by writing commentaries and speaking at conferences condemning Abe's perceived efforts to reinterpret Japan's war history. Most notably, in his attempt to appeal to the British public, Chinese ambassador Liu Xiaoming wrote in the *Daily Telegraph*: "In the Harry Potter story, the dark wizard Voldemort dies because the seven horcruxes, which contain parts of his soul, have been destroyed. If militarism is like the haunting Voldemort of Japan, the Yasukuni Shrine in Tokyo is a kind of horcrux, representing the darkest parts of that nation's soul." Liu also squared off on TV with the Japanese ambassador in London to defend China's position. Liu's command of British English and his forceful style made the Japanese ambassador pale by comparison.

4) Public diplomacy

Public diplomacy deals not only with governments but primarily with individuals and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The Chinese government has learned to speak directly to foreign audiences. For example, the September 28, 2012 edition of *New York Times* and *Washington Post* published two-page advertisement to defend China's claim over Diaoyu/Senkaku islands. The Chinese government also

purchased broadcast time for displaying news and other programs on the giant screens in New York City's Times Square. Chinese scholars and diplomats are writing commentaries and op-ed pieces for major news outlets.

Over the years other players such as academics, think tanks, NGOs, and individuals have become important actors in China's diplomacy. Many individuals have been involved in "Track II diplomacy", which is different from the state-dominated formal diplomacy. Growing exchanges in culture, education, sports, tourism, and business improve relations at the societal level and supplement what formal diplomacy can achieve.

Chinese scholars and think-tanks have been actively engaged in policy debates in recent years, directly or indirectly affecting China's foreign policy. Prominent scholars and retired officials have been actively involved in policy discussions and conferences with their foreign counterparts. Meanwhile, research on public diplomacy has gained more scholarly attention in China. In 2010 a Public Diplomacy Research Center was set up at the Beijing Foreign Studies University. Understanding the negative connotation of the word "propaganda", the Chinese government changed the English name of the former "Propaganda Department" to "Department of Publicity" in 1998. Meanwhile, the Foreign Ministry established a new office: Office of Public Diplomacy.

Promoting Legitimacy and Soft Power by an Authoritarian Regime

Legitimacy of a regime is largely a domestic issue. Though there is no strong and organized challenge to the CCP rule now, China's poor image abroad will affect its effective control of the country. There seems to be a need to take a two-pronged approach: continue to promote domestic growth and actively project a benign image overseas.

Since the collapse of communism in the Soviet Union and Eastern Europe in the late 1980s, the CCP has focused on promoting economic growth as the major means to stay in power. To a large extent, this has worked well. However, the Chinese society has become more plural and volatile, with hundreds of protests taking place every day across the country. Economic performance-based legitimacy is inherently fragile and vulnerable to economic downswings. Realizing this, the Chinese government has applied other means to enhance its image. For example, with the passage of the Organic Law of Village Committees in 1987, village elections were introduced in most Chinese villages. After a trial implementation in the late 1980s and early 1990s the Organic Law was fully adopted in 1998 by the National People's Congress (NPC). Despite reported problems in some villages such as vote-buying, village elections have been hailed as democracy in action at the grass-roots, and many have hoped that a bottom-up democratic movement may take shape in China. Unfortunately, there has been only debate but no real progress in escalating the election to township and other higher-levels of government.

China established the first Confucius Institute abroad in 2004. By mid-2014, over 440 Confucius Institutes have been set up globally. The headquarters in Beijing, the Office of Chinese Language Council International or *Hanban*, offers financial and teaching support to these institutions abroad.

The Chinese government-backed Confucius Institutes have faced criticisms in recent years. For example, in June 2014, the American Association of University Professors (AAUP) called on universities to uphold principles of academic freedom by either terminating or renegotiating the agreements that have brought nearly 100 Confucius Institutes to campuses across the United States and Canada. The AAUP claimed that colleges and universities in the United States had sacrificed the independence and integrity of their institutions and staff by allowing the Chinese government to set guidelines for the recruitment and supervision of academic staff, the design of the curriculum and boundaries on debate within the Confucius Institutes. “Confucius Institutes function as an arm of the Chinese state and are allowed to ignore academic freedom,” the AAUP statement said.⁴ Such concerns highlight the difficulty for a non-democratic regime to promote soft power abroad.

Inconsistency between domestic and foreign policies

As Joseph Nye pointed out, China does not seem to appreciate that using culture and narrative to create soft power abroad is not easy

when they are inconsistent with domestic realities.⁵ Indeed, such inconsistency of policies is a fundamental reason why China's soft-power promotion is so challenging. For example, the 2008 Olympics were a success, but shortly afterwards, China's domestic crackdown in Tibet and Xinjiang undercut its soft power gains. The Shanghai Expo in 2010 also went well, but was followed by the jailing of the Nobel peace laureate Liu Xiaobo and the activist Ai Weiwei. China's soft power promotion is often torpedoed by its continued tight control on the Internet and jailing of human rights activists.

China has few true friends in international affairs. Its more aggressive behaviors in the disputed territories in East Asia since 2010 and souring relations with several of its neighbors have created an image of China as a regional bully. Chinese officials sometimes call the Dalai Lama "the devil in sheep's clothing". Such Cultural Revolution-style repulsive language will do China no good for its image abroad.

Perceptual Gap and Media Bias

While the Chinese government tends to emphasize the progress China has achieved using vertical comparison—comparing China today with China 30 or 60 years ago, many individuals and Western media tend to find problems in China by looking at China horizontally—comparing China with other countries now. Such perceptual differences contribute to much of the negative reporting of China by Western media.

Western media have the tendency to highlight China's problems just as they like to exaggerate China's power. For example, although both the Chinese and US governments considered President Barack Obama's first state visit to China in November 2009 a success, and the Chinese media and public were largely positive in their views of the American president, much of the US media coverage was strongly negative, accusing Obama of failing to gain concessions on key issues such as Iran's nuclear program and climate change, as well as being weak on human rights.

No "public sphere"

China is a country full of contradictions, one of which is the contrast between a strong central government and a small and weak civil society. When major events occur, all news media in China will report in a uniform way approved by the government. One can barely hear alternative coverage. Despite the government's efforts to project soft power abroad and its improved public diplomacy, domestically there is little "public sphere" where sensitive political, economic, and social issues can be debated and discussed.

A country's soft power comes from within, where a dynamic civil society can prosper. To build a more positive global image, the Chinese government must encourage freedom of speech, without using the official *Xinhua* news agency to monopolize news reporting. Weighty voices from highly respected businesspeople, artists, activists and intellectuals who

are independent of the government and who are not considered as the government's mouthpieces should be heard. If these people speak up and point out Western media's biased reporting of China, Westerners are more likely to listen.

Partial socialization

Socialization is a lifelong process of inheriting and disseminating norms, customs and ideologies, providing an individual with the skills and habits necessary for participating within his or her own society. It's been over 35 years since Deng Xiaoping opened China to Western influence again. China has become a member in almost all international political and economic institutions and many Chinese consider the Western-originated values such as human rights as universal. Yet everything happens in China is with Chinese characteristics, an euphemism for not fully embracing Western ideas.

Domestic debate is inconclusive regarding China's proper role: Is it still a developing nation or should it flex its muscles now as the second largest economy? While China has been slow and perhaps reluctant to completely accept the universal norms and values, the external world is also unready to treat China as a full-blown great power. Some countries particularly China's neighbors and the United States are struggling to adjust to the changed political and economic landscape of Asia as a result of China's rapid reemergence. Both China and the rest of the world

need to re-socialize and re-connect with the changing global politics and economics now.

Conclusion

A nation's foreign image largely depends on how its domestic affairs are conducted. Not a democracy in which a social contract exists between the public and the elected officials, China has been trying hard to churn out impressive economic growth and strengthen diplomatic efforts to improve its international image. However, it is not easy for an authoritarian regime to be loved than feared.

China scholar David M. Lampton remarked, people tend to be anxious about big, rapidly changing, and nontransparent things—China is all three.⁶ While China has become an economic and military power, it has stagnated on political democratization, which has clearly hampered its international image. It is not difficult for a wealthy China to invest massively on programs such as the Confucius Institute, but money alone cannot buy credibility in the international community.

The purpose of the “going out” strategy should not be just enhancing China's influence, but also learning from others and embracing universal values. The Chinese government and the CCP need to pay more attention to its overall governance, not just economic growth. Political freedom and civil society must be promoted to consolidate legitimacy and enhance soft power in the absence of democracy.

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**10. Vietnam Overseas Students in China and
China's Soft Power in Vietnam
-the Case Study of Vietnam Oversea Students in Yunnan China**

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Abstract: Soft power theory has become an important paradigm for international studies. Vietnam is China's neighbor and China, US, Japan and India has taken a lot of new foreign policy moves in Vietnam in recent years, yet little research has been done on Soft Power Comparison between China, US, Japan and India in Vietnam and none has been done from the perspective of Vietnam foreign students. This paper, taking the method of questionnaire survey and conducting empirical analysis on Soft Power Comparison between China, US, Japan and India in Vietnam and find out US and Japan still in the lead in soft power even though many reports and analysis on the increasing China's soft power in Vietnam. China's soft power is in the third place in the terms of economic, culture and foreign policy soft power. This paper also put forwards a few suggestions on how to improve China's soft power in Vietnam.

Key Words: China, US, Japan and India; Soft power; Vietnam Foreign Students

Soft power theory has been given widespread concerns in academic circles since the end of 20th century, and many scholars at home and abroad have discussed from different views such as soft power composition, influence and the relationship with foreign policy, making a series of achievements.

The foreign student community has always been the most important carrier for our country to enhance international prestige and expand the soft power. In 2010, there were 265,090 foreign students, from 194 countries and regions, in various disciplines of learning to study in China in 620 universities, including 22,390 students who were granted Chinese Government Scholarships, accounting for 8.45% of the total number of the foreign students studying in China. ^[1]

Vietnam is an important neighbor of China and China has been its biggest trading partner since 2005 with the bilateral trade volume up to \$30,094 million in 2010; also in 2010, Vietnam became China's fifth largest national origin of foreign students with 13,000 students studying in China, accounting for 5.26% of the total number of foreign students in China ^[2]. Still, there have been fluctuations in the relationship between China and Vietnam in recent years under the effect of diplomacy moves of US, Japan, and India. In order to maintain a long-term and stable relation between China and Vietnam, the research of China's soft power in Vietnam is especially necessary. To study China's soft power and compare with US, Japan and India on this point by taking the method of questionnaire survey and conducting empirical analysis, after all, is an important perspective.

I. Definition and evaluation of soft power

The concept of soft power has been attended unprecedented since it was introduced to China, and it has gradually been "generalized" and "China characterized". According to Joseph Nye, the soft power is derived from the ability to shape preferences of others ^[3], by which attain one's desires through attraction rather than by force or by buying. The main sources of a country's soft power include culture, political values and diplomacy and international institutions ^[4].

For the reason that the soft power focuses on attractive power, how to quantify and evaluate the soft power is a big problem. Currently, the works in foreign countries analyze the soft power mainly from the soft power strategy, education, economy, popular culture and other aspects ^[5]. Men Honghua, a Chinese scholar has evaluated the China's soft power from the five aspects of culture, attitudes, development patterns, international institutions and international images, while a series of reports submitted by the Chicago Committee to the United States Congress on soft power made empirical studies on soft power of all nations in the world from four aspects of economy, culture, diplomacy and institutions. In the field of international studies, the core factor of

the focus soft power refers to the attractive power for other countries' individuals and groups and the ability to shape preferences of other countries' individuals and groups, therefore, taking the method of questionnaire survey or other approaches to know evaluation and recognition made by individuals and groups of one country on another country is a feasible method to quantify the soft power. This study conducts an evaluation on soft powers of China, US, Japan and India from four aspects of economy, culture, diplomacy and political & institutional by combining the research methods both at home and abroad with reference to the evaluation method of the soft power of the US Chicago Committee.

II. About respondents

The Vietnamese students studying in China are the important group for studying China's soft power in Vietnam. Foreign students will have an important influence after back to the countries where they come from, meanwhile, they are forceful communicators for the soft power of the countries where they have studied as foreign students. To compare the soft power between China, US, Japan and India in Vietnam by investigating Vietnamese foreign students is an important perspective, which will help us know the four countries' separate influence among those highly-educated young Vietnamese. But there is no denying the fact that taking this method to measure the four countries' soft powers in Vietnam is of great limitation, and the results of survey also can only partially reflect these four countries' soft powers among the foreign students.

The objects of this survey conducted in the period from September to December in 2011 are mainly the Vietnamese students in Yunnan, selected from four universities with the largest number of Vietnamese students which are Yunnan Normal University, Yunnan University, Yunnan University of Finance and Economics and Yunnan Nationalities University. Altogether 800 questionnaires are put out, and 608 effective ones are taken back, accounting for 76% of the total. This survey is conducted by using self-administered and delivered questionnaires. Samples are chosen by simple random sample. The number of investigated students accounts for about 1/3 of the total Vietnamese students in each university. According to the survey results, 88% of the respondents are at the ages of 20-25, and the major ethnic group among Vietnamese students studying in Yunnan is of Jing nationality, accounting for 90%. The main group of the investigated Vietnamese students are undergraduates, accounting for 91%, while postgraduates

accounting for 9%; most of the respondents have been studying in China for 1-3 years, with 46% in China for 2-3 years and 23% for 1-2 years (see Table 1). Most of the respondents have had a better understanding of China.

Table 1 About the respondents

(Unit: %, proportion of the completed samples)

Age	Proportion	Nationality	Proportion	Grade	Percentage	Time in China	Percentage
20-25	88	Jing	90	Undergraduate	91	2-3 years	46
15-20	8	Dai	6	Postgraduate	9	1-2 years	23
Over 25	4	Other	4			Over 4 years	17

Date source: Data compilation based on the questionnaires (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

III. Analysis on evaluation of soft powers of China, US, Japan and India among Vietnamese students in Yunnan

This questionnaire survey involves a total of 4 aspects, including economic, cultural, diplomatic and political & institutional soft power, corresponding to the four major sources of the soft power.

(I) Economic soft power

In recent years, the economic relationship between China and Vietnam is becoming closer and closer, since 2005, China has been Vietnam’s number one trading nation with bilateral trade volume in 2010 up to \$25.4 billion. The trade with China accounted for 16.54% Vietnam’s total volume of foreign trade [6]. In the first 8 months in 2011, The investments of Mainland China’s enterprises in Vietnam reached \$460 million, ranking the fourth, only behind Hong Kong (China), Singapore and Japan [7]. But according to the feedback of the respondents, it seems that China’s soft power in Vietnam is not improved along with the promotion of the bilateral economic relationship and the growth of China’s importance in Vietnam’s economic development.

The questionnaire about economic soft power includes four major parts which are economic influence, product reputation, corporate image and economic aid. There are a total of 11 specific questions around the four parts in the questionnaire, and the scores of economic soft power of the four countries are obtained by assigning the rankings in the question scores of China, US, Japan and India. According to the survey of the Vietnamese students in Yunnan, China ranks third in the economic soft power in Vietnam (2.25 points), lower than US (3.58 points) and Japan (3.00) but higher than India (see Table 2).

Table 2 Evaluation of soft powers of China, US, Japan and India in Vietnam^①

Item \ Country	US	Japan	China	India
Economic soft power	3.58	3.00	2.25	1.17
Cultural soft power	3.33	2.78	2.44	1.33
Democratic soft power	3.89	2.78	2.00	1.67
Political & institutional soft power	3.50	3.00	2.50	1.00
Comprehensive soft power	3.58	2.89	2.30	1.29

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

As for the economic influence (see Table 3), respondents think that US, China and Japan have a great economic influence in Southeast Asia, and the US has the strongest influence with the average score up to 7.14 (0 indicates no influence while 10 represents a significant influence), China scores 7.08 in the economic influence in Southeast Asia, ranking second only to the US. The average score of Japan is 6.41 and India 4.94. The survey results of China, US, Japan and India about the influence on the world economy are roughly the same as the results of the previous survey. The US gets the highest average score of 6.86 in the influence on the world economy, while China, Japan and India get 6.48, 6.26 and 4.94 respectively, ranking from the second to the fourth.

Table 3 Economic influence of China, US, Japan and India

	US	China	Japan	India
Average score of economic influence in Southeast Asia	7.14	7.08	6.41	4.94
Average score of influence on the world economy	6.86	6.48	6.26	4.94

Note: 0 indicates no influence while 10 represents a significant influence

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

As for the influence of China, US, Japan and India on Vietnam’s economic development in trade, investment and other economic cooperation fields, the respondents think that American trade and investment is the most important to the economic development of Vietnam. The US gets the average score of 7.14 points, China follows with 7.12 points, India and Japan get 6.17 and 5.45 respectively. Although China and Japan have exceeded US in trade and investment in Vietnam, the respondents still think that American trade and investment are more important.

Good quality and reputation of Japan’s products have greatly promoted the economic soft power of Japan in Vietnam. In the survey, Japan holds the first place among four countries in the scores of this question (see Table 4). The survey shows that the when the product is known to be made in Japan, the desire to buy will be greatly increased. On this question, Japan gets the average score of 6.71, ranking the first; in the evaluation of the product quality among the four countries, Japan is also the highest scored countries (the average score is 6.47). The US holds the second place in these two questions, while China’s product quality and reputation have been widely questioned in the survey with the scores of 5.09 and 5.28 respectively, ranking the fourth and the third. 66.04% of the respondents think the quality of Japan’s products is excellent or comparatively good, while only 37.74% of the respondents hold the same view to the Chinese product quality.

Table 4 Scores of related indicators in soft powers of China, US, Japan and India

Questions	US	China	Japan	India
Will your desire to buy be affected if you know that a product is made in a country of the following?	6.38	5.09	6.71	5.16
How do you think of the quality of the produces made in the following countries?	6.41	5.28	6.47	5.11
How do you think of the economic competitiveness of the following countries in the world?	7.14	5.95	6.60	5.52
Do you think the following countries' companies have the outstanding entrepreneurial spirit?	6.16	6.23	6.72	5.64
How do you think of the development level of science and technology in the following countries?	6.59	5.85	6.9	6.04
Do you think the economic development of the following countries is helpful to the economic development of Vietnam?	7.41	6.48	6.67	5.68
Do you think that there are world's leading multi-national companies in the following countries?	7.12	6.38	6.64	5.64
Do you think that the following countries can provide humanitarian assistance and economic assistance for the poor areas/countries?	6.52	6.11	5.97	4.7
Which country's TV programs do you think are more attractive to you?	7.02	6.52	6.45	5.57
Manners and politeness of Chinese, American, Japanese and Indian	6.38	5.8	6.76	5.85

CSS CHINA

residents					
Educational qualifications of Chinese, American, Japanese and Indian residents	6.74	6.17	6.93	5.4	
Do you think the following countries have rich cultural meanings and the historical and cultural resources?	Proportion of the respondents granting 7 points or above	58.49	67.92	62.26	50.94
	The average score	6.17	6.21	6.17	5.59
Do you think the following countries have a leading role in the international organizations?	Proportion of the respondents granting 7 points or above	75.47	54.72	64.15	49.06
	The average score	6.95	6.12	6.5	5.63
Do you think the foreign policy of the following countries respects the sovereignty of other countries enough?	Proportion of the respondents granting 7 points or above	71.70	67.92	66.04	52.83
	The average score	6.81	6.19	6.69	6.24
By watching news, diplomatic activities of the following countries do you think are more friendly?	Proportion of the respondents granting 7 points or above	64.15	50.94	69.81	60.38
	The average score	6.72	5.99	6.72	6.5
Do you think the following countries	Proportion of the	56.60	45.28	64.15	54.72

are promoting the trust in Asia and mutual cooperation?	respondents granting 7 points or above				
	The average score	6.43	5.99	6.11	5.92

Note: The table is subject to 10-point system where 0 indicates the lowest evaluation while 10 represents the highest evaluation. The proportion of the respondents granting 7 points or above refers to percentage of the number of the respondents grant 7 points or above in completing the questionnaire samples in the whole samples under the unit of %.

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

American enterprises have a positive public image in Vietnam. 50.94% of Vietnamese foreign students think American enterprises have made positive contributions to Vietnam, followed by Japan (26.42%), China (24.53%) and India (11.32%) (see Table 5). It is the same, the international competitiveness of America enterprises has also been widely recognized. According to the survey of the four countries' international competitiveness of the economy, 81.31% of the respondents think the international competitiveness of American economy is comparatively strong or very strong with the average score of 7.14, ranking the first; and 67.92% of the respondents hold the same view to Japanese economy with the average score of 6.6, ranking the second, followed by China and India (see Table 4).

Table 5 Contributions of the companies (enterprises) of China, US, Japan and India to Vietnam

(Unit: %, proportion of the completed samples)

Country	Very Positive	A Bit Positive	Total	A Bit Negative	Very Negative	Not Positive Nor Negative	Unknown
US	50.94%	30.19%	81.13%	9.43%	5.66%	1.89%	1.89%
China	24.53	32.08	56.60	26.42	7.55%	3.77%	5.66%

	%	%	%	%			
Japan	26.42 %	32.08 %	58.49 %	18.87 %	18.87 %	0.00%	3.77%
India	11.32 %	39.62 %	50.94 %	9.43%	28.30 %	9.43%	1.89%

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

Japan’s entrepreneurship and scientific and technological level have been widely accepted in Vietnam (see Table 4). According to the survey of the corporate image of the four countries, 66.04% of the respondents think the Japanese enterprises have a very outstanding entrepreneurship, granting an average score of 6.72, ranking the first. While the proportions of those believing the US, China and India have an outstanding entrepreneurial spirit are 62.26%, 58.49% and 47.17% respectively, granting the average scores of 6.16, 6.23 and 5.64. 81.13% of the respondents think that Japan’s scientific and technological development level is comparatively high or very high, granting an average score of 6.90, while 69.81% of the respondents hold the same view to American scientific and technological development level, granting the score of 6.59. The scores granted by the respondents grant to China and India in scientific and technological development are 6.04 and 5.85 respectively.

The US ranks the first among the four countries in the helpfulness of the economic development to Vietnam, owning leading multi-national corporations and economic assistance. 84.91% of the respondents think that American economic development is comparatively or very helpful to Vietnam’s economic development, granting the average score up to 7.41. Japan gets a slightly lower score of 6.67, while China and India are scored 6.48 and 5.68 respectively. Respondents think that the US has comparatively many or very many world’s leading multi-national corporations, granting an average score of 7.12, followed by Japan (6.64), China (6.38) and India (5.64).

As for the aspect in providing humanitarian aid and economic assistance for poor regions, the US is also scored the highest. 69.81% of the respondents think that the US can provide humanitarian aid and economic assistance for poor countries and regions, granting an average score of 6.52, followed by China (6.11), Japan (5.97) and India (4.7) (see Table 4).

(II) Cultural soft power

In term of the cultural soft power, the questionnaire survey is carried out from four angles of languages, higher education, popular culture and citizen quality. The scores of cultural soft powers of the four countries are obtained by assigning the rankings in the question scores of China, US, Japan and India in these four aspects. According to the results of the survey, the cultural soft power of the US is strongest among the four countries, followed by Japan, China and India. (see Table 2)

The language and higher education advantages as well as the popular culture of the US have a wide and deep influence on Vietnam, which have been proved again. In the parts of the survey involving the items above, the American influence ranks the first among the four countries. 81.13% of the respondents think that to learn English is most important for himself/herself or his/her children to be successful in the future, and 22.64% of the respondents think to learn Japanese is the most important for the future success. While those who think Chinese and Hindi the most important for the future success account for 7.55% respectively.

In the aspect of higher education, the US also has an absolute advantage. 68% of the respondents want themselves or their children to receive higher education in the US, while 9% of the respondents want to receive higher education in China, and the people wanting to receive higher education in Japan and India account for 6% respectively.

Fig. 1 Selection of destinations for higher education

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

The survey shows that American popular culture including movies, TV shows and music are higher than those of China, Japan and India in attraction and acceptance frequency. At this point, the US ranks the first among the four countries. 50.94% of the respondents enjoy American movies, music or TV shows every day, while those enjoying movies, music or TV shows of China, Japan and India every day account for 18.87%, 13.21% and 7.55% respectively. In addition, American TV shows are more attractive to the Vietnamese foreign students with the average score of 7.02, while the TV shows of China, Japan and India are scored averagely 6.52, 6.45 and 5.57 respectively (see Table 4). Moreover, the Vietnamese foreign students also have a positive evaluation on American popular culture. 41.51% of the Vietnamese foreign students think that American popular culture has a very positive role in the development of Vietnam, while 22.64% hold the same view to Chinese popular culture, with 11.32% and 13.21% to Japan and India respectively (see Table 6).

Table 6 Influence of popular culture (such as movies, animation, music, clothing and food, etc.) of China, US, Japan and India on the development of Vietnam

(Unit: %, proportion of the completed samples)

Country	Very Positive	A Bit Positive	A Bit Negative	Very Negative	No Effects	Not Sure
US	41.51%	18.87%	3.77%	9.43%	3.77%	22.64%
China	22.64%	35.85%	22.64%	1.89%	9.43%	7.55%
Japan	11.32%	35.85%	22.64%	11.32%	5.66%	13.21%
India	13.21%	28.30%	16.98%	15.09%	15.09%	11.32%

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

Japan has a good performance in politeness and education of its residents and tourism attraction with a score ranking the first among the four countries (see Table 4). According to the survey of the residents' politeness of the four countries, 67.92% of the respondents think that Japanese residents are more polite and grant the highest score of 6.76. The average scores of the politeness of American, Indian and Chinese

residents are respectively 6.38, 5.85 and 5.8. China gets the lowest score in this item. In education, Japan gets 6.93, which is also the country scored highest. While the US, China and India get the average scores of 6.74, 6.17 and 5.4 respectively in higher education of the residents. Tourism attraction is another important aspect of the cultural soft power. 41.51% of the respondents have no experience of traveling to Japan and India and want to go there for tourism, while 32.08% of the respondents have no experience to the US and want to go there for tourism.

China's rich cultural connotation and the historical and cultural resources have also been recognized in the survey. 67.92% of the respondents think that China has very rich cultural resources and historical and cultural connotation, granting an average score of 6.21, ranking the first, while Japan, US and India get the average scores of 6.17, 6.17 and 5.59 respectively in this item (see Table 4).

(III) Diplomatic soft power

Neighboring diplomacy has always been one of the focuses of China's diplomatic affairs, and a great progress has been made in the relationship between China and Vietnam in recent years. However, according to the survey, China ranks the third in the diplomatic soft power following the US and Japan (see Table 2). In the 14 questions related to the diplomatic soft power, China does not get any score that ranks the first. To achieve the goal of being "good four" of the relationship between China and Vietnam among the people seems to have a long way to go.

In the questions concerning the leadership in Asia, providing effective solutions to international disputes, and the leading role in international organizations, the US has been widely recognized with a score ranking the first. In answering the question that which country you would accept as the leader of the Asia among the following countries, 43.4% of the Vietnamese students can fully accept the US as the leader of Asia, while those can accept Japan, China and India to be the leader of Asia account for 39.62%, 26.42% and 22.64% respectively (see Table 7). 47.17% of the respondents think that the US provides very effective solutions to international disputes and 75.47% of the respondents think that the US plays a leading role in international organizations, grant an average score of 6.95. Those think that Japan, China and India have a leading role in the international organizations account for 64.15% (6.5), 54.72% (6.12) and 39.62% (5.63) respectively (see Table 4).

Table 7 Acceptability of the leadership role of China, US, Japan and India in Asia among the Vietnamese students

(Unit: %, proportion of the completed samples)

Country	Fully Acceptable	A Bit Acceptable	Little Acceptable	Fully Unacceptable	Unkown
US	43.40%	16.98%	24.53%	9.43%	5.66%
China	26.42%	26.42%	20.75%	11.32%	15.09%
Japan	39.62%	24.53%	18.87%	11.32%	5.66%
India	22.64%	11.32%	28.30%	28.30%	9.43%

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

Respecting other country’s sovereignty is one of the five principles of peaceful coexistence Chinese has pursued, and also is one of the important sources of the international legitimacy of China. However, according to the results of this survey, the respondents seem not to accept that. 71.7% of the Vietnamese students think that American foreign policies are comparatively respectful or very respectful for the sovereignty of other countries, granting a score of 6.81, ranking the first; 67.92% of the respondents hold the same view to China granting a score of 6.19, ranking the third; while 66.04% and 52.83% of the respondents hold the same view to Japan the average scores of 6.69 and India respectively (see Table 4). By watching news reports, 69.18% of the Vietnamese students think that the diplomatic behaviors of Japan are comparatively friendly or very friendly, Japan and America share the average score of 6.72, ranking the first equally, while those hold the same view to India and China account for respectively 60.38% and 50.94%, granting the average scores of 6.5 and 5.99. China gets the lowest score. (see Table 4).

The questions of how the Vietnamese foreign students in Yunnan regard the roles of China, US, Japan and India in Southeast Asia, and what roles they expect for China, US, Japan and India Japan and India to play in Southeast Asia are also involved in this survey. 64.15% of the respondents think Japan has played an important role in promoting the Asia Trust and mutual cooperation, granting an average score of 6.11; and the US is scored 6.43 in this item, ranking the first, while China and

India get the average scores of 5.92 and 5.99 respectively (see Table 4). 67.92% of the Vietnamese students think that the US can develop a closer relationship with ASEAN countries and they give the US an average score of 6.43, ranking the first; while China, Japan and India get the scores of 6.42, 6.29 and 5.76 respectively, where China ranking the second. Those expect the US, India, Japan and China to play a greater role in Southeast Asia account for 60.38%, 41.51%, 30.19% and 15.09% respectively; those expect China, Japan, India and the US to maintain their roles in Southeast Asia account for 47.17%, 26.42%, 24.53% and 16.98% respectively, and those expect China to play a greater role only account for 15.09%, the lowest among the four countries (see Table 8).

Table 8 Expectations for the future roles of China, US, Japan and India in Southeast Asia among the Vietnamese foreign students

(Unit: %, proportion of the completed samples)

Country	Playing a Greater Role	Remaining Unchanged	Playing a Less Role	Unknown
US	60.38%	16.98%	13.21%	9.43%
China	15.09%	47.17%	22.64%	15.09%
Japan	30.19%	26.42%	30.19%	13.21%
India	41.51%	24.53%	5.66%	28.30%

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

Overall, the respondents think that China has played a positive role in Asia. 38% of the Vietnamese students think China played a very positive role in Asia, and 46% of the respondents think China has played a positive role in Asia (see Figure 2). As for China’s harmonious world diplomatic idea, which has a limited influence among the Vietnamese foreign students, only 17% of the respondents have heard of such Chinese diplomatic idea about harmonious world (see Figure 3). In the face of Chinese rise, 8% of the respondents think that the rise of China has a very positive influence on Southeast Asia, and 50% think the influence is a bit positive (see Figure 4). As for the relationship between China, US and Vietnam, the policy supporting Vietnam not to attach to China nor the US seems to be more widely recognized. 21% of the

respondents support Vietnam to follow the US to contain China, while 54% of the respondents oppose this approach.

Figure 2 China’s influence in Asia

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

Figure 3 Chinese diplomatic idea about harmonious world

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

Figure 4 Influence of Chinese rise on Southeast Asia

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

(IV) Political & institutional soft power

The study on the political soft power mainly covers the human rights, government evaluation, the future order and overseas Chinese. According to the survey, there seems to be a certain gap of the cognition on human rights between the respondents and the West, in the standard of evaluation of the human rights from 0 to 10 points, the respondents give Japan, US, China and India the average scores of 6.96, 6.95, 6.28 and 5.8 respectively. Japan ranks the first and China ranks the third.

In the evaluation on the national service of government agencies, the Vietnamese students give the average scores of 6.84 (US, ranking the first), 6.72 (China, ranking the second), 6.55 (Japan, ranking the third), 5.56 (India, ranking the fourth). Their evaluation of Chinese government is better than our expectations.

In view of the prospects for China becoming the world leader in the future, the survey respondents hold a pessimistic view. 19% of the respondents think that China will become the future leader of the world, while 47% don't think so (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 Possibilities for China to become the world leader in the future

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

The community of overseas Chinese is an important source of China’s soft power and also one of the carriers to expand China’s soft power. In the questions involving the overseas Chinese, 8% of the Vietnamese students think the overseas Chinese are very important to the development of Vietnam and 51% think comparatively important. (see Figure 6) At the same time, 43% of the Vietnamese foreign students approve the Chinese Vietnamese’s strengthening the relationship with China, while 32% of the Vietnamese foreign students hold opposite opinions. Thus it can be seen that there are wide differences between the roles of Chinese Vietnamese and the relationship between the Chinese Vietnamese and China among Vietnamese foreign students.

Figure 6 Roles of Chinese in Vietnam

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

IV. Evaluation results of the soft powers of China, US, Japan and India among Vietnam foreign students in Yunnan

The four countries' soft powers can be obtained by taking a weighted average of the four soft powers of economy, culture, diplomacy and politics of China, US, Japan and India. Based on the above, we can see that, Vietnamese foreign students think that the US has the strongest soft power among China, US, Japan and India (see Table 2). The US gets an average score of 3.58 (out of 4), ranking the first in all the four aspects of have scored in the four aspects of economy, culture, diplomacy and politics & institutions. Japan ranks the second with the total score of 2.89 in soft power in Vietnam, with all separate soft powers of the four aspects above ranking the second. China, scored 2.30, ranks the third in soft power in Vietnam, with all separate soft powers ranking the third. India ranks the fourth.

There are some surprising results of this survey: (1) the US is far ahead in soft power in Vietnam, 23.88% higher than Japan, ranking the second, and 55.65% higher than China, ranking the third. In the 51 questions in this questionnaire, the US is scored the highest in approximately 80% of the questions. In view of the war lasting more than a decade from 1960s between the US and Vietnam, the result is a surprise. (2) The respondents of this survey are the Vietnamese foreign students in Yunnan, considering the fact that these students choose to study in China and 69% of the them have received education in China for more than one year, it's reasonable to expect that they would give a higher evaluation and recognition on China's soft power, but according to the results of the survey, China's soft power is ranking the third, significantly lower than that of the US and Japan. (3) In contrast to what foreign experts have noted or the media coverage, the soft powers of the US and Japan in Vietnam have not declined, and China's soft power in Vietnam has not exceeded that of the US and Japan.

Overall, the Vietnamese foreign students in Yunnan have a better comprehensive impression on the US. When answering the question "Do you think Vietnam has the similar culture and lifestyles with China, US, Japan or India", 38% of the respondents think the Vietnam and the US share similar culture and lifestyles to a great extent, while 23% hold the same view for China and 17% for Japan. Those think the Vietnam and

the US share similar culture and lifestyles a great extent account for 5% (see Table 9).

Table 9 Similarity in lifestyles of Vietnam with those of China, US, Japan and India

(Unit: %, proportion of the completed samples)

Country	Greatly	Partly	Little	No
US	38	35	25	2
China	23	42	29	6
Japan	17	35	42	6
India	5	22	36	37

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

In addition, according to the survey of the Vietnamese foreign students in Yunnan, this community has a very positive feeling for the US; those have very positive feelings feel and have a bit positive feelings for the US respectively account for 39% and 23%; those have the same feelings for China respectively account for 28% and 25%, while those who have somewhat negative feelings for China account for 33%, up to 1/3 of the respondents at the highest proportion among China, US, Japan and India. (see Table 3)

Table 10 Feelings of the Vietnam foreign students in Yunnan for China, US, Japan and India

(Unit: %, proportion of the completed samples)

Country	Very Positive	A Bit Positive	A Bit Negative	Very Negative	Not Sure
US	39	23	15	8	15
China	28	25	33	8	6
Japan	28	25	21	15	11
India	15	28	25	15	17

Data source: Calculation based on the results of the survey questionnaire. (Conducted from September to December in 2011)

V. Implications and Suggestions

Vietnam is one of China's neighbors and the diplomatic frontier, in addition, it has been China's fifth largest source of foreign students. The Vietnamese foreign students in China should have played a role in perceiving China and expanding China's soft power in Vietnam. In recent years, Chinese government has adopted some measures including improving the government scholarship amount and proportion to attract foreign students to study in China, hoping to dissolve the fears of other countries about China by flexible means and improving the soft power of China. The survey results will have implications for China's soft power diplomacy, China-Vietnam relationship and education of foreign students to some extent.

(I) The Vietnam foreign students in Yunnan have a higher recognition on the soft powers of US and Japan in Vietnam.

After a long period of operation, the US has a strong soft power in Vietnam. With the implementation of American government's policy of "pivot back to Asia", the US will continue to maintain its strong "hard power" (such as a military presence) and soft power in Asia in the foreseeable future. Depending on the advanced technologies, excellent higher education and humanistic quality, as well as the developed industrial production, Japan will still have a strong soft power in Vietnam, coupled with the recent increase in aid and investment in Vietnam, its soft power is expected to continue to maintain. The presence of the US in Southeast Asia is recognized and welcomed by Vietnamese foreign students, believing the American military presence will contribute to the stabilization of Southeast Asia.

(II) There are still great concerns among Vietnamese to China.

Nearly 1/3 of the respondents in the Vietnamese foreign students have negative feelings for China in general. The fact that China gets a lower score than US and Japan in soft powers in Vietnam indicates that there are still great concerns among Vietnamese to China. How to enhance the recognition among Vietnamese people to China still needs further discussion.

(III) The development of Chinese economy makes Chinese economic influence improve in Vietnam, but with big flaws.

The survey shows that the development of Chinese economy makes Chinese economic influence recognized in Vietnam and Southeast Asia, but the quality of Chinese products, product reputation and Chinese enterprise images put much trouble onto Chinese economic soft power, in such aspects China is scored much lower than Japan and the US. In addition, the entrepreneurial spirit of Chinese enterprises, the level of technology and the lack of the world's leading multi-national corporations also bring negative influence on China's economic soft power. The improvement of Chinese economic attractiveness will depend on the improvement of the product quality and the entrepreneurial spirit.

(IV) There is still a big space to improve the education and teaching content for foreign students in China.

This survey is aimed at the Vietnamese foreign students in Yunnan. With the experience in studying and living in China, these students should have given a higher evaluation on China when assessing the soft powers of China, US, Japan and India, but the fact is that the soft power of China is lower than that of the US and Japan, which shows that there are still many problems in promoting foreign students' recognition to China in the education for the foreign students. How to take the method of "silent influence" to improve the intimacy to China of the foreign students studying in China is the effort direction of the education of foreign students.

(V) In the education of foreign students and Chinese cultural transmission, face the "present" besides emphasizing the history.

According to the survey, the Vietnamese foreign students in Yunnan have given the highest evaluation on Chinese traditional culture, the score is the highest among the four countries, but in the survey questions concerning the present, China is scored not high in general. In the current education of foreign students, Chinese traditional culture, such as history, folk customs, calligraphy, martial arts, painting often get an in-depth publicity, but the discussion and analysis on the current Chinese culture, actualities, and other realistic questions are obviously insufficient. China's current education of foreign students should highlight the rich traditional culture of China and the long history on one side, on the other side, the education should stress on the education advancement, improvement of the human environment and colorful popular culture of contemporary China. In this survey, China is scored first in cultural connotation and historical and cultural resources, but it is not satisfying in higher education, popular culture, and politeness of

residents, schooling and tourism attraction. Kung Fu, Beijing operas and dragon boat culture should be promoted, in addition, Chinese modern literature, movies and music should be also publicized. Only by this way, can Chinese culture step down and go into the real life.

(VI) The foundation of China-Vietnam trust is weak.

Even the principle of respecting the sovereignty of other countries that China is proud of fails to be recognized among the Vietnamese foreign students believing that China is less respectful for other countries' sovereignty than the US and Japan, and thinking China is more unfriendly in diplomatic affairs compared with the US and Japan. Those expecting China to play a greater role in Southeast Asia account for only 15%, far lower than 60% of the US, 41% of Japan and 30% of India. At the same time, the Vietnamese students think that there is a high possibility of a conflict between China and Vietnam in the next ten years, the possibility is the highest among the four countries, indicating there is still a great space for improving the construction of mutual trust between China and Vietnam.

(VII) Official activities should be reduced with promotion in non-official sectors for the improvement of the soft power under the silent influence.

According the survey, we have discovered that although China have taken a lot of official measures in improving the soft power, the positive effect of these activities are not obvious among the Vietnamese foreign students in Yunnan. Whether the aggressive activities of "Year of Chinese Culture", government's high interest-free loans, development assistance or expanding Confucius Colleges, these are conducted with official efforts. To improve the soft power with the "thinking of campaign mode" is very easy to cause the rebound of other countries, especially the countries with deep concerns to China, such as Vietnam. Therefore, for these countries, to improve the soft power of China, the government should fade into the background and encourage non-official institutions and commercial organizations to carry out related activities. Except Confucius Colleges, commercial Chinese language training institutions can also achieve the purpose for Chinese promotion; except the official "Year of Chinese Culture", commercial movies, TV shows and music can also increase the Chinese cultural influence; except the official development assistance, public activities of NGO may be easier to set up a good image of China.

Notes :

[1] Sheng Jianxue: *Address in “Development Seminar of the Five Northwestern Provinces on the Education of Foreign Students in China”*, *Research on Foreign Student Affairs*, No. 4, 2011.

[2] International Cooperation and Communication Department, MOE: *Summary of foreign students in China 2011*, Page 7.

[3] Nye, Joseph S. Jr., *Soft Power the Means To Success in World Politics* , New York: Public Affairs, 2004.p.5.

[4] Nye, Joseph S. Jr., *Soft Power the Means To Success in World Politics* , New York: Public Affairs, 2004.p.11.

[5] See Joshua Kurlantzick ,*Charm Offensive: How China's Soft Power Is Transforming the World* ,Yale University Press.

[6] Zheng Guofu: *Empirical Study on the Development of Bilateral Trade Since the Normalization of China-Vietnam Relationship*, *Southeast Asia*, No. 4, 2011 , Page 7.

[7] See the economic & commercial counselor's website of Chinese embassy in Vietnam, <http://vn.mofcom.gov.cn/static/column/zxhz/tjsj.html/1>

(B) China and Regional Groupings

1. Whither the Shanghai Cooperation Organization?

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During 2014 China has launched a major new initiative regarding Central and South Asia that fundamentally departs from its previous policies and points in new and hitherto unforeseen directions. China has reversed its traditional opposition to Indian participation as a full member in major Asian security institutions and invited India to join or participate in the following agencies, many of which are Chinese-sponsored institutions: the Chinese-sponsored Asian infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB), ambitious Chinese-initiated maritime silk road projects through Southeast Asia, the Asia-Pacific Economic Community (APEC) whose annual meeting China is hosting in November, and the

Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). Iran, Pakistan, and Mongolia will also receive invitations to the SCO.¹ And, China and India are both founding members of the forthcoming BRICS bank.² This is an amazing turnabout for Beijing since most analysts perceive the Indo-Chinese relationship to be fundamentally rivalrous.³ While space precludes a full investigation of China's motives for these invitations; we focus on trends within the SCO for there is no doubt that India, Iran, Pakistan, and Mongolia will all become members.

India has long sought membership in the SCO and the Modi government's newly enhanced engagement with China and India's pre-existing "Connect Central Asia policy" suggest it will actively participate in the SCO.⁴ Analysts have already discerned two potential benefits for China by expanding the SCO in this fashion.

As noted by former (Indian) Ambassador M.K. Bhadrakumar, the timing of this investigation is quite relevant. The United States' recent relations with China and Russia have been strained at best; India joining the SCO does not bode well for the pro-India lobby in the United States, which had been trying to cultivate it as a strategic ally (potentially against China) in the region. While an SCO that lists Iran, Pakistan, and India amongst its members would by no means constitute an NATO of the East, it would effectively block Washington's ability to dictate terms to Kabul or Islamabad.⁵

An expanded SCO works to curtail US influence in both South and Central Asia that could block expanded Chinese influence in both regions. We already see in Central Asia considerable Sino-Russian cooperation particularly against the US. One might visualize the SCO as a joint effort to restrict Washington's presence there and prevent Central Asia's alignment with either Moscow or Beijing against the other.⁶ But

from Moscow's standpoint the SCO is undoubtedly a way to moderate or channel China's rising Central Asian profile within an institution where Russia has an equal voice and can assert itself. Expanding the membership is a calculated Chinese risk to dilute Russia's voice, obstruct India's gravitation to either Moscow or Washington, and enhance its own influence through Pakistan's adhesion.

Beijing has consistently envisioned the SCO as a template of multilateral cooperation for a new, essentially anti-American, and alternative system of Asian and international relations generally. The SCO thus represents the embryonic form of a future anti-American system in Asia where China plays a major role and leverages its membership as a means of influencing these organizations in its direction. It has always emphasized that the SCO embodies China's vision of a future world, or at least Asiatic, order from which American military power and calls for democratization would either be excluded or at least restricted to a minimum. Thus Beijing simultaneously pursues multilateral initiatives like the East Asian Summit that it has tried to guide in order to engender the exclusion of America throughout Asia as a whole. Many commonalities exist between China's efforts to guide the SCO and its promotion of multilateralism in Southeast Asia.

One of the results of China's diplomatic efforts has been to marginalize the United States. Washington is not a party to any of the regional institutions that China promotes and which are now setting the future Asian agenda. To be sure, the United States does not have to belong to every institutional organization, but China is defining multilateralism for the region in ways that specifically exclude the United States.⁷

In this respect the SCO is the opposite of America's Asian alliance system. China's policies toward Central Asia, particularly the development of the SCO, exemplify the process by which China intends first to build a prosperous neighborhood under its auspices and then shelter its economic development from both internal and foreign threats. Beijing also hopes to reshape Asian security agendas to attenuate U.S. alliances and replace them with relationships that are ideologically and politically more congenial to China's insistence on its unfettered sovereignty and freedom to maneuver in world affairs.

Step one for the SCO was to build the group, the first multilateral group China had started on its own. Step two: expand it to discussions of trade, economics and energy. Step three: begin discussions on more substantive security partnerships. The SCO has gone so far as to conduct its own joint military maneuvers, in China's Xinjiang Autonomous Region. This approach of deepening regional multi-level ties will likely be repeated in other forums, such as ASEAN+ 3 grouping (ASEAN plus Japan, Korea, and China).⁸

Ultimately this also makes the SCO the arena for Russo-Chinese competition in Central Asia.. While both governments support suppressing Central Asian reform and repressing any threats to the status quo; they clearly compete against each other in the SCO and Central Asia. Thus those governments have previously differed on membership issues in the SCO.⁹ A 2008 Senate Foreign Relations Committee study observed that,

Some observers have viewed the creation of the SCO as reflecting the common goal of Russia and China to encourage the Central Asian states to combat regime opponents (in their own countries-author) of the two major powers. While cooperating on this broad goal, Russia and China have appeared to differ on

other goals of the SCO and to vie for dominance within the organization. Russia has viewed the SCO mainly as a means to further military cooperation and to limit China's influence in Central Asia, while China in recent years has viewed the SCO not only as enhancing regional security but also as an instrument to increase trade and access to oil and gas.¹⁰

Since 2008 we have seen numerous examples of Sino-Russian competition in Central Asia and Russia's mounting but ultimately unsuccessful efforts to hedge against China's growing influence there. China frustrated Russia's attempts to dominate the region's energy industry and force it into a single Russian channel.¹¹ China has also become the primary money and foreign capital market for Central Asia.¹² Similarly China's commercial penetration of Central Asia compared with the visible signs of Russia's inability to compete commercially or as an investor in Central Asia has triggered increasing Russian anxiety and moves to restrict Central Asian trade with China like the new Eurasian Union. and accompanying Customs Union ¹³ These trade diverting organizations are already diverting Central Asian trade from China to Russia.¹⁴ A study of the impact of that Customs Union on Kyrgyzstan concluded that,

The main conclusion of this section of the study is the need to modify Kyrgyz trade policy, which has been based on trade flows going from China to the CU countries through Kyrgyzstan. All stages of the supply chain from importation to exportation must be changed. According to the opinions of local experts, changes in the trade flows from China to CIS countries could be expected as a result of the CU formation. Such changes would likely increase trade flows via Central Asia rather than the Far East region of the Russian Federation, due to lesser costs. At the same time, "shadow" re-export flows could be replaced by products produced in Chinese factories newly located in Kyrgyzstan. ¹⁵

Kazakh analyses also highlight Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan's inability to compete with Chinese goods and conclude that the Customs Union will reduce China's penetration of their domestic markets.¹⁶

This bilateral rivalry over energy, economics and each government's political influence in Central Asia is visible, robust, and growing despite both sides' understandable efforts to conceal it. Russian analysts already claim that "the interaction with China within SCO only weakens Russia's position in the long run."¹⁷ Maria Teploukhova writes that,

Beijing is one of the major foreign policy partners of Moscow, bilateral dialogue is well set, and the SCO cannot be regarded as a priority for further development or interaction. Even for military exercises both parties do not need the SCO – they can simply continue them in the bilateral format, as they do now. Meanwhile attempts to compete with China within the SCO are also doomed to failure, since for China the SCO is a matter of foreign strategy and for Russia it is a matter of prestige. Therefore, Moscow either has to agree to the position of second player (as it does now), or to spend much of its resources on real rivalry. Cooperation between the SCO and the Collective Security Treaty Organization helps to improve the position of Russia, but again the overall context implies that the structure is more oriented towards Central Asia than the Russian Far East.¹⁸

Indeed, China's economic power grew so much in 2009 that Russia had to accept China's investments in Central Asia as a positive phenomena. Deputy Foreign Minister Sergei Ryabkov actually praised Chinese investment in Central Asia for its "transparency."¹⁹ Ryabkov further claimed that,

We believe that our friends and partners in Central Asia are appropriately meeting the situation and solving the task facing them in the sphere of economic and social development using the opportunities that present themselves as a result of cooperation with China. Hence this can only be welcomed.²⁰

Given Moscow's consistent paranoia regarding any gain by China, or America, in Central Asia this represented a profound change in rhetoric if not policy and a major concession to China. As a 2007 report of the Russian-Chinese Business Council observed,

Being a member of the SCO, China views other members of the organization as promising markets. It is China that wishes to be the engine behind the trade and economic cooperation within the framework of the SCO --- China's intentions to form [a] so-called economic space within the SCO are well known. Owing to that fact, experts have been speaking about greater Chinese economic expansion in various parts of the world, including Central Asia. -- Beijing has activated ties with all Central Asian countries and strives to comprehensively strengthen economic relations and the dependency of these countries on its market.²¹

By 2007 China was already Russia's commercial rival there, bypassing Russian efforts to monopolize Central Asian energy trade against China.²² And now China has become the leading outlet for Central Asian and especially Turkmen gas. It will soon get up to 65BCM annually from Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and Kazakhstan, more than they send to Russia.²³ Nevertheless, Russia will not admit that China is its rival and only acts indirectly or covertly against China there. As Dmitri Trenin and Alexei Malahenko wrote,

The rise of China has challenged Russia's position in Central Asia even more massively, fundamentally, and permanently than America's insertion into the region. However, Moscow while traditionally allergic to military expansionism, is relatively tolerant toward the projection of economic influence, which distinguishes the Chinese practice in Central Asia from the American. Russia still regards the United States -- not China -- as its principal competitor.²⁴

For Russia China remains the "threat that dare not speak its name" in Central Asia as elsewhere.²⁵ And there are still more examples

of this rivalry. China joined other SCO members in 2008 to block support for Abkhazia and South Ossetia 's independence from Georgia. China then collaborated with Uzbekistan to thwart Russian efforts to intervene in Kyrgyzstan's domestic crises in 2010.²⁶ China prevented Russia from obtaining a precedent using Article 51 of the UN charter and the right to protect ethnic kinsmen abroad from being applied to Central Asia. That precedent could be used to devastating effect against both Central Asian and the Chinese governments and could have been used in Ukraine but thi precedent apparently blocked that gam bit. While principles defending states' territorial integrity are enshrined in the SCO charter, Russia clearly does not take them seriously. This alone drives other members' to look to China. Should future crises erupt within one or more member states or between any two of them, it will be an important test for the SCO. Ukraine suggests it could fail that test. and that the gap between the SCO's formal by-laws and its effective functioning will probably grow over time

Zhao Huasheng, the Director, Center for Russia and Central Asia Studies, Center for Shanghai Cooperation Organization Studies, at Shanghai's Fudan University, wrote in 2004 that issues like terrorism, drugs, and the links between drug running and the Taliban were problems beyond Russia's effective unilateral ability to cope with either in the short or long-term perspective. Moreover, other regional organizations could not fight these challenges either. Only the SCO could combat terrorists, extremists, separatists, and drug trafficking. Zhao embellished upon the idea of China's free riding, explaining that China

concedes to Russia a leadership position in Central Asia, as long as Russia recognizes that it needs China's influence to exercise legitimate authority here.

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, Russia has continued to influence this area but its ability to control Central Asia is waning. To varying extents, the countries of Central Asia wish to be independent from Russia. In the long run, Russia's control over Central Asia is worrisome. The Shanghai Cooperation Organization links the Central Asian countries and remains attractive for this reason. Therefore, the SCO may be conducive to the exertion of Russian influence and domination. In particular, Russia may cement its broad and general existence in this region with the help of China's influence and the Central Asia's confidence in China. The newly-born SCO has the potential to develop into the most influential regional organization of this part of the world. Joining the SCO is an important way for Russia to take part in Asian affairs, otherwise Russia's potential is greatly diminished.²⁷

If he accurately captured China's thinking and Russia's reality, then the SCO could well resemble Asian security organizations even more than it presently does. That is not a positive outcome for Russia or India. For example, in the Asian Regional Forum (ARF) and ASEAN open rivalries and strong differences may be publicly voiced but little practical result ensues. Unless Russia learns to compete economically with China, it may ultimately function as the gendarme of Eurasian autocracy and of China's investments.

More recently it appears that Russia has essentially given up competing against China's silk road project for Central Asia. Xi Jinping has announced two "silk roads" one through Central Asia and a maritime

one through South and Southeast Asia and launched enormous railroad, infrastructure, telecommunications, and pipeline projects to realize this vision. This vision contradicts and could eclipse Russia's rival vision of a transcontinental "iron silk road" from Europe to Asia through the Trans-Siberian Railroad and a North-South corridor to India, Iran, and Central Asia. And by inviting India into the maritime if not overland silk road China also destroys the essentially rhetorical US silk road project while also coopting India into its grand design. China already is and will remain the most consequential and preeminent foreign actor in Central Asia.²⁸

Recognizing Russian suspicions, Xi Jinping magnanimously offered to link the Trans-Siberian railroad to the Chinese Silk Road. Putin welcomed that offer.²⁹ Sergei Ivanov, Putin's Chief of Staff may claim that the silk road will link to Russia's Baikal-Amur and Trans-Siberian railroads and have a great potential if they do so by connecting East and Southeast Asia with Europe.³⁰ Nevertheless this magnanimity displays China's victory over Russia and Russia's inability to compete with China. Russia now is merely a "junior brother" in such endeavors. Typically China graciously but decisively punctured Russia's grandiloquent Eurasian and great power pretensions. Given the expansive geostrategic benefits that China will obtain as it realizes its silk road vision, the evolving bilateral relationship on this issue portends a massive and decisive Russian strategic defeat in Eurasia rendering it here, as in energy, China's raw materials appendage.³¹

Finally China's recent invitation to India, Iran, Pakistan, and

Mongolia to join the SCO opens a new chapter in the SCO. This may be partly a gesture to Russia which has long supported Indian entry into the SCO in return for the visible warming of Russo-Pakistani relations or it may be part of an altogether new page in Sino-Russian rivalry of the SCO in South and Central Asia. Only time will tell. But this move certainly comports with the Russo-Chinese desire to create new international organizations that exclude the US and transform the Asian and international economic-political order. But it is unlikely that this move will improve amity within the SCO formal rhetoric to the contrary notwithstanding. Despite the professed Russo-Chinese identity of outlooks, at the 2012 Beijing summit of the SCO, Russian diplomats openly took the credit for successfully torpedoing China's major initiatives.³² Thus the Kazakh analyst Adil Kaukenov writes,

It is difficult to understand how an efficient and reliable organization can be established if the second largest participant is set on doing all it can to prevent major projects from working. And there is an explanation for this; it is obvious that one of the reasons for Russia's accession to the SCO was to prevent China's uncontrolled penetration into Central Asia. At the beginning of the 2000s, it became clear that China's entry into the region was inevitable, so Moscow gave the green light, as long as it was involved too. This was also advantageous to Beijing, since Moscow's participation in the organization gave the SCO, which also meant China's entry into the region, a significant reserve of legitimacy. So Moscow occupied the position of an active pessimist in the SCO, making generous offers, allotting funding, but in the end doing everything to ensure that the SCO does not go beyond the framework of a dialog platform. Russia's attempts to make the SCO more global by means of an enlargement or active efforts on the global scale are being opposed both by Beijing, for which the SCO is an entirely specific mechanism, so it is worried about its erosion, and by the Central Asian countries, which are worried they will be drawn into a new standoff between Russia and the West.³³

While he thinks Xi Jinping's new policies towards Russia and

emphasis on finding larger areas of agreement with Russia might change this situation; this rivalry remains the primary impediment to the SCO's effectiveness.³⁴ Furthermore China is consolidating its advantage by building a gas pipeline from Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan to China even though Gazprom took over Kyrgyzstan's energy company and China could buy cheaper gas using the existing Kazakhsan-Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan pipeline. As Kyrgyz expert Adjar Kurtov argues, China aims to create,

A system for the region's dependence on interests of China. Its aim is to create conditions so that in the future China might become a moderator of [the] majority of key processes in the west of its borders. And China consistently will implement this aim step by step which will be facilitated by China's financial mightiness and international reserves which are the biggest in the world in terms of volumes.³⁵

Thus India may join the SCO but it might yet recoil from what it finds there.

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**2. China and SCO:
An Overview of The Emerging Geostrategic Dynamics**

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Abstract

Shanghai Cooperation organisation got worldwide attention since its inception in the world politics. The organisation portrayed positive growth at all levels due to the cooperation of its member countries. It's a group of China, Russia, and Central Asian states, originally founded to address common threats and concerns, especially in the security realm. It has evolved as an organization institutionally and has taken on greater importance in fostering economic cooperation and trade. China has certainly been the driving force behind the SCO's emergence. SCO members are highly infested by terrorism, fundamentalism, secessionism, drug trafficking, small arms proliferation etc. Though, Ukraine crisis is not directly involved but it has spill over effects in the region. During the 2013 Summit, foreign policy makers of the SCO have strongly advocated for concerted efforts to step up cooperation to root out terrorism, extremism and separatism, as well as transnational crime, drug-trafficking, illegal arms trade and other subversive activities. Moreover, the evolving the new strategic environment in post 2014 Afghanistan, would pose serious security concerns for members of the SCO. China being a major potential power of the region, has the responsibility to seek the cooperation of SCO members to engage the members to help in sorting out the Afghanistan imbroglio. The organisation attracted both major and regional powers because of having members of Central Asian Countries which are strategically as well as economically significant. The main focus of this paper is to analyse the geostrategic challenges being faced by the regions; how China can play role in security architecture of SCO to check these problems?

Key Words: SCO; China; Central Asia; Russia; Geostrategic challenges; Imperatives

Introduction

The Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), has all important players of the region within its fold. It started with a limited scope. But in

the wake of fast paced globalization and a number of regional and global developments in the political, economic and security environment, the organization has extended its purview. SCO is getting important place in the Chinese foreign policy. It is showing its positive and constructive willingness to get engaged positively and constructively with SCO that is being reflected in its participation in all SCO summit meetings. The SCO is an enduring association which was originally brought together by the short-term border security interests of its first five members. Russia is also playing a leading role in the SCO; in fact, however, the organization is and has always been driven by China, and Moscow's role is vital but secondary. The Central Asian states with no history of modern statehood or governance, are not equal partners but their geostrategic location and, in some cases, natural resources make them potentially valuable allies for the China and other major powers.

Seeing its standing in the global politics, some of the regional actor such as India, Pakistan etc are trying to get its membership. But geopolitics will decide its geopolitical expansion which is unlikely to take place. Though, many countries such as India or Pakistan are trying to get entry in the SCO. However, any enlargement of the organization could be fraught with difficulties. It is mainly because of conflicting interest between China and Russia. The members expressed fear that some new candidates are potential international liabilities and may create further conflict within the organization. Recent announcements that the SCO will improve its multidirectional cooperation do not seem to be supported by specific planning or political determination. Only unforeseen and extraordinary world events could make the SCO member states move closer towards real political, economic, or military integration, with all the long-term strategic implications that would entail. While the SCO as an organization does not mount any direct challenge to U.S. interests, its political role as a coalition of anti-U.S. sentiment is likely to develop further in the future. Bilateral security cooperation with the Central Asian members of the SCO is ripe for development, but this will require

careful and tactful management of their balance of interests between the United States, China, and Russia.

Geostrategic Saliency of the SCO

Iranian writer, Hamid Golpira, expressed the saliency of this region through the opinion of the former national security adviser Zbigniew Brzezinski. Brzezinski said, "Control of the Eurasian landmass is the key to global domination and control of Central Asia is the key to control of the Eurasian landmass....Russia and China have been paying attention to Brzezinski's theory, since they formed the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation in 2001, ostensibly to curb extremism in the region and enhance border security, but most probably with the real objective of counterbalancing the activities of the United States and NATO in Central Asia."¹

Geo-strategically, some of the members are sharing long borders with unstable countries such as Afghanistan, Iran, and Pakistan. Thus, this region is facing many serious security problems which include Islamic extremism, secessionist movements, drug trafficking, narcotic flows, terrorism, and the region's importance in energy resources, influence of major powers create strategic challenges (Boland, 2011: 29). Being closer to these political and strategically unstable countries are also under the spell of these problems. These challenges now not only include Central Asia, but also SCO's permanent members China and Russia plus observers and dialogue partners.

Russia and China as the prime movers of the SCO can be said as two major nuclear powers that on the global stage are contending powers with the United States (Hu, 2014). Nevertheless, China took the lead role by devising the mechanism to combat three evils- separatism, extremism and terrorism waged by the radicalized elements, while promoting economic ties (Boland, 2011: 8). This development gave a new dimension to the organisation towards multilateralism; meant for tackling security

issues especially in Xinjiang. This arrangement has also addressed the concerns of CARs regarding the territorial integrity and committed to concerted efforts against the perceived common threats from the extremist forces especially to curb nationalist sentiments among Turkish speaking Uyghurs. The sole motive behind this move was to negate the establishment of East Turkistan (Zhao 2004, 116-125).

Central Asia is very rich in energy sources whereas China is deficient in energy sources. The former one is facing serious problems regarding the availability of capital and again China is in surplus in capital. Likewise, there are many areas where the convergence of interests is taking place. SCO provided China an opportunity to make ingress in the Central Asian region to meet her ever growing energy needs and to dominate Central Asian markets through extensive commercial activities. Russia, on the other hand, conceived SCO as an opportunity for preserving its strategic interests in CARs and to maintain her traditional influence over the near abroad (Dmitry, 2003: 72-82.) As far as the Central Asians are concerned, security vulnerability was one of their areas of concern, hence, the leadership of CARs felt strengthened by associating themselves with this organisation. Under the purview of SCO, however, it is a viable forum to prevent interstate conflict among member states and to make CBMs (Yuan, 2010: 861).

Similarly with permanent members of the organisation, other observer members and dialogue partners are also facing similar geostrategic challenges. Some of the observers including India are being at the crossroad of Central Asia, South-West Asia and South Asia. These observer countries are keenly monitoring the SCO and conceived it as an opportunity to play a responsible, constructive and positive role. India is the most affected country and suffered a lot from terrorism and extremism. Since SCO is particularly concerned about these problems and in view of this, India wanted to join the SCO in any capacity considering the converging interests (Roy, 2012: 547). Like India,

Pakistan, Iran are also facing similar geo strategic challenges within their respective territories either exists within their territories or flowing from neighbouring countries

Genesis of SCO

The Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) is an international organisation which includes Russia, China, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan. The SCO was founded on the basis of agreements on strengthening the strategic cooperation and trust in order to check the security concerns. The Shanghai Five agreed upon for mutual reductions of armed forces in border areas, by signing agreements in 1996 and 1997. The creation of the SCO was formally announced in Shanghai (China) on 15 June 2001 after the joining of Uzbekistan at a meeting of the heads of six governments. At a Summit Meeting in St Petersburg (Russia), the SCO Charter was adopted. This charter is the basic document which defines the roles, aims and principles of the organisation, its structure and main areas of activity. As per the SCO's charter adopted in 2002, its main objectives are to strengthen mutual trust, good neighbourliness, develop effective cooperation in political affairs, economy, trade, science & technology, transport & environmental protection, and maintain regional peace, security and stability. Since December 2004, the SCO has had the status of an observer at the United Nations General Assembly. In 2004 and 2005 Mongolia, India, Pakistan and Iran became observers and Belarus, Turkey and Sri Lanka are dialogue partners at the SCO.

Initially, the SCO dealt with security issues only; however, presently economic issues have also become an important part of SCO's agenda. The SCO is a wide-ranging cooperation organisation, covering issues such as regional security and countering trans-national security threats. This activity is coordinated, in accordance with the decision of the Tashkent SCO Summit in 2004, by means of regular meetings of the secretaries of the national security councils of the member states of the

organisation and meetings of the heads of security departments. In order to coordinate the activities of security forces in countering international terrorism, a Regional SCO Anti-terrorist Organisation was set up in 2004 with its headquarters in Tashkent (Uzbekistan). This headquarters is manned by representatives from the security departments of Russia, the Central Asian countries and China. The Council of this organisation meets twice a year to take decisions of a mandatory type concerning all aspects of its activity.

China: Dominant Player in SCO

The evolution of SCO in 2001 from Shanghai Five, which was established in 1996, was solely an initiative of China to exhibit its leadership role in the region for future socio-economic development – including energy security and internal social stability (Norling and Swanstrom, 2007: 430). China is also wanted to heighten its influence over the growing radicalized elements in Central Asia as a result of the improvised financial condition, poverty and unstable politico-economic condition. Many western analysts and policy makers regard SCO as anti-US, anti-western bloc, or as a Russian and Chinese anti-Western vehicle to have some check on the emerging great power's row in the region over the strategic-cum-economic gains. (Aris, 2009: 1321-1344). This argument was strengthened when SCO during the Astana Summit (2005), called for US to vacate its bases in Central Asia and rejected the US-sponsored Colour Revolutions in the region. This grouping provided an opportunity to the resource-rich neighbouring states of Central Asia-Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan and Russia to chalk out mutually beneficial policies (Roy, 2014:)

The fundamental role played by China in the institutionalisation of the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation in 2001 is notable. This initiative demonstrates a historical turning-point in China's foreign policy: an unprecedented active engagement of Beijing in establishing a regional organisation. In fact, China's role was crucial to CA's regional

security development. China sees the SCO as an instrument for its regional recognition and as a tool to improve its image of a responsible power. As the SCO has been the first organisation inspired and built by Beijing, its good development is considered to be a test for the Chinese leadership proving that China can do what other great powers have done before it. It is also the evidence that a 'new kind of organisation' - as China describes it - can be created by developing countries, which reproduces China's foreign policy guidelines. The so-called 'Shanghai Spirit' of mutual trust, benefit, equality, consultations, respect for diversity of cultures and aspiration for joint development, is constantly put forward by the Communist Party of China (CPC) as a new pattern shaping non-Western regional integration.

China has played a key role within the SCO, to establish the 'Group of Five'. First, the dissolution of the USSR left Central Asia vagrant of the stabilising security function provided by Moscow. This was a factor of great concern for the Chinese leadership as they fear to face a similar destiny. In particular, growing insecurity in CARs could have destabilised China's Xinjiang. With around one third of the entire Chinese territory, this autonomous region of Muslim minority (Uyghur) is a sort of bridge between CA and China. Rich in oil and other natural resources, it faces secessionist movements (East Turkestan Independence Movement). Hence, China's main interest for CA has always been driven by major security concern, a matter of national priority the need to safeguard its territory and avoid separatism forces to destabilise the PRC. For instance, not only the independence of the former Soviet Republics in CA but also the radicalising of the Taliban in Afghanistan was empowering separatist movements in Xinjiang. Through the Shanghai Five Beijing's aimed to improve trust among its members and to set their frontier disputes. Later, the SCO represented a further step for China since its chart listed three-evil forces to be fought: separatism, extremism and terrorism.

The Chinese interest and its eager advocacy of SCO should be considered in the form of its immediate security needs. Through SCO, it wants to show that it has an alternative worldview, has the will to lead and is ready to assume leadership role. Thus, it uses SCO to convey its message not only to Central Asia but also to the rest of the world. It tries to convince the international community, particularly its regional neighbours, about its capabilities and concerned intentions. Through SCO China projects a great power image and behaviour. The fact is that SCO is the only international organisation in establishment of which China has played an instrumental role and is setting rules of the competition. China makes every effort to draw attention of the international community towards its participation in SCO to prove its credentials of being a responsible great power. China's push for the creation of SCO corresponds with the increased terrorist violence in its western province of Xinjiang, the Central Asian states and the Russian province of Chechnya. Secondly, Central Asian energy sources, located in China's immediate vicinity, have seen attracting international players like the US and regional powers like India and Turkey. The overall strategic scenario was critical in its formation.

China takes solemn examine of the ingress of various superpowers and regional powers in Central Asia for its implications on security of the Xinjiang in the long run. Thus, China considers SCO as an instrument that could provide a determined standing for China in Central Asia and help it in consolidating its western periphery. Moreover, China's preference for multilateral engagement in Central Asia also arises out of its necessity of making itself more acceptable in Central Asia. China expects Russia to stay in Central Asia and engage it there, because China knows the objective ground reality of Russia wielding considerable influence in the Central Asian states. In this context, SCO can become a powerful link between China and Russia. In fact, SCO can be considered as 'an outgrowth of the Sino-Russian cooperation'. The future of SCO depends very much on this cooperation. Central Asia is the backyard of Russia and any problem with Russia could land China in

problematic environment. Thus, China wants mutual accommodation and engagements with Russia in Central Asia in order to pursue its energy related goals in Central Asia. China also wants to seek the Russian strategic help in checking and curbing the Uighur separatism. Russian help in its military modernization is having the utmost importance for China. China has entered a "strategic partnership" with Russia and concluded a bilateral "Treaty of Good Neighbourly Friendship and Cooperation" in July, 2001 in Moscow.²

Chinese Stakes in the SCO

China aims to achieve short term, medium term and long term goals through SCO. Long-term goals are what. China planned to build a peaceful buffer in the region between itself and the agitated Afghanistan and West Asia. SCO can help in this direction as all of its three Central Asian neighbours are the members of SCO. Its active participation in SCO reflects and confirms its strategy to ensure peace and national development. As part of its security strategy, it aims to fetch the weak Central Asian states onto a common platform where it can promise and encourage them about the benefits of its astoundingly rising economy. To build faith for itself in the Central Asian states is one of the main objectives of China's policy towards SCO.

Short term goals, from the immediate security perspective, are containing three evils - terrorism, separatism and extremism, border security and energy security. Medium term goals are constituted by other concerns and problems of transnational nature, which do not need urgent attention in comparison to immediate security issues. The immediate security threat that China intends to contain is Uighur separatist movement in Xinjiang, which is part of larger problem of separatist demand of the Eastern Turkistan. This separatist movement affects many former republics. The situation worsened after Afghanistan fell into the hands of Taliban. American presence in the Central Asian region evokes apprehension and nervousness in the Chinese mind that this presence may fuel and add to instability in its Xinjiang province.

Xinjiang creates a sense of vulnerability in the national psyche of China. The separatists, if succeeded, will snatch one-sixth of China's territory away, cut off its connectivity with Central Asia, strip it off its nuclear testing grounds and the oil reserves in Tarim basin.

The US presence in the Central Asia creates a sense of caution in China for Xinjiang. The situation in Xinjiang can have a destabilizing impact on China's northwest provinces of Gansu and Qinghai and autonomous regions of Ningxia and Tibet. The separatist demand for Eastern Turkistan is just one of the many separatist and extremist problems of the region, which share common ideological bonding and networking. Farghana valley, located in the Tian Shan mountain ranges of Central Asia which lies commonly in Eastern Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, is supposed to be the breeding ground of international terrorism. Since the Chinese western region has to share the burden of every problem that originates in Central Asia, China intends to stabilize its north-western periphery by stabilizing Central Asian region so that it will have no snowball effect on the Taiwan issue and the territorial disputes of the South China Sea. China's emphasis on mutual economic cooperation and development through SCO helps its strategy to develop its western provinces in order to make public move away from insurgency and to lessen the influence of the separatist forces. SCO also provides China a platform where it can explore its energy needs. Medium term goals cover issues and concerns of transnational nature. Basically, primary focus of these goals is to curb internationally banned crimes like narco-trafficking, smuggling of small arms, illicit business, local mafia gangs that operate trans-border, illegal migration and human-trafficking.

Geostrategic Contours: Emerging Regional Challenges

The SCO region as a whole faces diverse challenges and threats. These include both traditional and non-traditional internal and external threats. These challenges cannot be seen in isolation since in the globalized world of today, there are global actors like the United States which exercise sway in the region. The challenges such as religious

intolerance, violence, extremism, separatism, militancy and terrorism have become major concerns for the all SCO members. The conflicts among the states of Eurasian region are utmost worry to the members of SCO as well as to India.

The SCO, being apparently a security organization, and some of its members are all pretty close to Afghanistan, would seem to emerge one of the major problems for the organization. After the signing of Bilateral Security Agreement, it has become crystal clear that the ISAF is going to withdraw by late 2014. Afghanistan can be called as the 'Heart of Asia'. China is the only country in the region that has direct geographical access to Afghanistan. Similarly, though India is not sharing direct border with Afghanistan, but the existing geostrategic and geopolitical environment have direct impact on Indian interests. Thus, China and SCO have lot of stakes in the political stability and security of Afghanistan. China and Russia are the major powers. Both the countries could play a very significant role in the post 2014 Afghanistan. Bilateral relations between China and Afghanistan have been remained mostly warm and friendly during most of the 20th century. But after the invasion of Soviet Union in 1979, these bilateral relations severely deteriorated until the fall of the Taliban regime. Soon after the United States intervention in 2001, relations between China and Afghanistan had greatly improved and were re-established. In December 2001, China sent a working team of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to Afghanistan, which attended the Afghan Interim Administration's foundation ceremony and sent a message of congratulations to President Hamid Karzai.

During a recent visit to the Afghanistan, Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi highlighted the salience of domestic stability in Afghanistan for the internal stability of China's western province of Xinjiang. As there is anticipation of the re-emergence of the Taliban and radical groups and in view of this, there is the possibility of Afghanistan turning into a heaven for insurgents and terrorists. China is very sensitive to this anathema as its restless Xinjiang is very close to Afghanistan. However, Afghanistan

has reassured China that it, “would never allow the East Turkestan Islamic Movement (ETIM) to take advantage of the Afghan territory to engage in activities endangering China, and will continuously deepen security cooperation with the Chinese side.”

The some of the important members of SCO are sharing border with SCO and some of them are sharing proximity with Afghanistan. Till date no tangible steps have been taken by SCO in this regards. China has lot of geostrategic and geo-economics interest, but so far it has not involved itself in the Afghan imbroglio. Similarly, SCO’s decisions on economic cooperation, anti-terrorist efforts, related to Afghanistan have been remained on paper. Theoretically, countless plans and projects are on table but there is no information provided how these projects have specifically been carried out.

The most prominent geostrategic issue which is bothering the SCO is post 2014 Afghanistan. Very recently, Bilateral Security Agreement has been signed and it has become crustal clear that ISAF will leave Afghanistan by the late 2014 Most of the strategic commentators are of the opinion that there is a possibility of the re-emergence of the Taliban and other terrorist’s outfits. India, China and SCO members are highly infested by terrorists’ outfits. Keeping Xinajiang, Jammu and Kashmir in perspective, post-2014 Afghanistan would be a serious concern for SCO as well as for India. India, through the SCO forum could engage with the member countries to jointly work for stability in Afghanistan. India’s perception about SCO’s role in Afghanistan is well laid out in the statement made during the SCO meeting at Bishkek; SCO “provides a promising alternative regional platform to discuss and reflect upon the changing security situation in Afghanistan”.³ What happens in Afghanistan post 2014 is uncertain. The situation being highly dynamic, it is difficult to make accurate projections. Most calculations are disconsolate, and expect political instability, a worsening security situation, a weak economy and violence. However, this pessimistic

scenario need not materialise if post 2014 security mechanisms, economic assistance, and a stable political system are put in place.

The situation in Afghanistan after the withdrawal of ISAF is viewed differently by different experts of the respective countries according to their interests. Afghanistan's six immediate neighbours (China, Iran, Pakistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan) and its close neighbours (Russia, India, and Saudi Arabia) all have a stake in Afghanistan's future when the US withdraws. However, it is the USA and its allies who currently exercise influence over the finances, military power, and other governance and economic reform efforts that will likely dictate strategic success or failure. Additionally, it is increasingly apparent that the US and its allies must rely on Afghanistan's neighbours to at least avoid derailing the progress made, and ideally, to continue to support progress when the US withdraws. This requires a deliberate effort to resolve regional issues that preclude effective cooperation between those stakeholders.

Ukraine crisis is one of the serious concerns for the global politics as in this conflict the major powers of the world such as Russia, USA and European Union (EU) are involved in this crisis. Although the confrontation between Russia and Western powers over the Ukraine crisis is not directly related to the SCO but it has spill over effect for the SCO. However, Sun Zhuangzhi, secretary general of the SCO Research Center expressed opinion that Ukraine crisis unlikely trigger a "New Cold War", reason being the national interests of most of the countries are intertwined. This crisis could break the geopolitical balance in Eurasia. Geographically, Ukraine is unrelated to the SCO, but it is a member of the Commonwealth of the Independent State (CIS), in which Russia and some Central Asian countries such as Kazakhstan, whose diplomatic policies can directly affect the development of the SCO.⁴ Despite Russia is directly involved in the Ukraine crisis and has been attaching greater importance to cooperation with China and Central Asian countries after the outbreak of the Ukraine crisis, but the SCO neither wanted to get

involved in Ukraine, nor wanted to go with Moscow against the West. Instead, the SCO prefers to help resolve the Ukraine issue through diplomatic and political channels, and prevent the crisis from having "spillover effects" on Ukraine's neighbours.⁵

Although China enjoys a substantial influence in the region, it has relatively receded its interests Afghanistan, but it also needs to be continuously monitored to gauge a change in its interest. While external stakeholders may influence the internal dynamics of the Afghan operational environment, the success or failure of the US strategy will likely depend on its ability to influence internal factors while simultaneously preventing external stakeholders from disrupting those efforts. Given the geographical location of the Organisation, there are enormous expectations from SCO for sharing greater responsibility to stabilise Afghanistan, especially in the post 2014 period. If SCO has to establish itself as an effective regional body, it cannot afford to sit on the side-lines with regard to the Afghan evolving situation.

SCO strategy and options for the Strategic Concerns

Terrorism and secessionism are the major problems of SCO. The Xinjiang conflict is an ongoing separatist struggle is the one of the major problems in the People's Republic of China (PRC) far-west province of Xinjiang. Uyghur separatists are claiming that the Xinjiang is not part of China and according them it is East Turkestan. Asia is also emerging the focal point of the Islamic radicalization and extremism. The Ferghana Valley is a fertile land and it is densely populated region. It comprised of mainly Uzbek territory divided politically between Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan where the "Islamic sentiment has already expressed itself [since] the early 1990s."⁶ Almost all countries have been affected by the terrorism. Uzbekistan and Tajikistan have been the most terrorist affected countries. The notorious Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan (IMU), the Islamic Jihad Union (IJU) and the Islamic Movement of Turkestan (IMT) are the major terrorist outfits are operating in the Central Asia.

Regional conflicts such as Afghanistan and Ukraine crisis are having the spill over effect for China and SCO. Along with these problems, drug smuggling, small arms proliferation are also posing the serious security concern for the SCO.

In order to check these strategic challenges, there is need of strengthened cooperation among the member states including observers as well as dialogue partners aims at boosting mutual trust, maintaining regional stability, promoting the economic development of the region and member states, and building a new international economic and political order that is fair and rational. Over the passage of time, China and Russia realized the convergence of their priorities to complement each other's national interests. Joint military exercises under the supervision of SCO pointed out that their mutual concerns related security issues are bothering all the SCO members. In order to step up strategic cooperation, these SCO members are coming on the one platform. Since the last decade, ten joint military exercises have been conducted with different code names such as "Collaboration-2001, 2006" , "Union-2003" , "Peace Mission-2003, 2007, 2009, 2010, 2012"; Tianshan-I, 2. On the other hand, India at the bilateral level has been addressing this issue with CARs and Russia. It has expressed its desire to deepen security related cooperation with the SCO in general and with the Regional Anti-Terrorism Structure, in particular. During the SCO Summit 2013, Shanghai, India external Affairs said, "New Delhi is also looking forward to the signing of the Model Protocol of Intent in the near future as demonstration of its commitment and willingness."⁷ The threat emanating from the Af-Pak region and increasing violence in Afghanistan is an area of concern for India and all the SCO member-states.

The approach of the SCO member-states has been that given the size and nature of these challenges, multilateral cooperation is the only way to address these threats. It has been argued that the integrated approach is required to deal with these challenges. It was also pointed out that it would not be possible to deal with the problems of terrorism

unless the root causes of the problem are addressed. It was emphasized that there is a need to build new models of security cooperation among small and big countries within the SCO mechanism to address the challenges of terrorism. However, the seriousness of the problem in Afghanistan and their impact for the entire region after the withdrawal of US led NATO force has drawn much more attention in among SCO member plus observer as well as dialogue members. The member-states are of the view that in the light of US withdrawal from Afghanistan SCO needs to play a greater role in Afghanistan. From the regional perspective on Afghanistan an expert from the Centre of Strategic Studies, argued that there is a need to involve India, Iran, Pakistan, Russia, China and Central Asian Republics to solve the Afghan quagmire. The need for cooperation between SCO, SAARC and CSTO has been suggested.⁸

Besides India and China, no other country in the region is in a position to be considered as stabilizing force in Afghanistan. Some of the scholars are of the opinion that though Russia has always considered Afghanistan is part of its influence but it is unlikely that Russia may get involved in Afghanistan. Geopolitical equations are changing in the region. China, Russia and Pakistan are coming closer whereas on the other hand democratic quadrant-US, India, Japan and Australia are coming on the one platform. Russian leadership is considering that Pakistanis having influence in Afghanistan. In view of this, it is enhancing its relationship with Pakistan to get involved it in Afghanistan, expecting that it will persuade the Taliban not to interfere into the areas of Russia's influence. Of course, Russia is interested to look after the problem of Afghanistan only under the China-led SCO framework.

Conclusion

From the inauguration of SCO, to its existing phase, China has played a significant and strategic role. Besides, China has been using SCO to advance its national, regional and global interests. This trend will continue in the near future. In the long term what is to be seen is how

China play a critical role in the evolving strategic environment as by late 2014, ISAF is going to be withdrawn from Afghanistan. Most of the SCO Members are highly infested by terrorism, fundamentalism and secessionism. In order to check these fundamental problems, some strategic sort of steps have been taken by SCO in which China being a potential power has been playing major role. But it seems that the new evolving strategic environment out of post- 2014 Afghanistan, Ukraine Crisis, conventional and unconventional strategic problems, SCO is unprepared, though lot of frameworks have been put in place. It is, therefore, highly recommended that China through SCO must step up with efforts with the regional countries then only some serious kind of strategic problems can be sorted out.

¹.Tehran Times, November 20, 2008.

². Wilson, Jeanne L: Colour Revolutions: The View From Moscow and Beijing. Accessed from- http://www.ceelbas.ac.uk/workshops/Jeanne_Wilson_paper.pdf, 29 October, 2014.

³.Statement by Mr. Sanjay Singh, Secretary (East) at the SCO Heads of Government Meeting in Bishkek, 5 December, 2013.Extracted from, the MEA of GOI, <http://www.mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/20907/Statement+by+Mr+Sanjay+Singh+Secretary+East+at+the+SCO+Heads+of+Government+Meeting+in+Bishkek>, 29 October, 2014.

⁴.Zhuangzhi, Sun: SCO outshines NATO in valuing cooperation, TheChina Daily, 11 September, 2014.

⁵.Ibid.,

⁶.Cornell, Svante E. & Spector, Regine A: Central Asia: More than Islamic Extremists, The Washington Quarterly,25(1), 2002, p. 199.

⁷.Statement by the External Affairs Minister at the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) Heads of State Summit 2013 in Bishkek, at <http://www.mea.gov.in/in-focusarticle.htm?22197/Statement+by+External+Affairs+Minister+at+the+Shanghai+Cooperation+Organisation+SCO+Heads+of+State+Summit+2013+in+Bishkek> accessed on August 14, 2014.

⁸. Views expressed by the Afghan Participant in the International Conference on “10 Years by the way of Security and Cooperation: Successful Experience for Countering Challenges and Threats on SCO Areas”, Almaty, February 22-23, 2011

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3. China and ASEAN

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Introduction

When the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) was founded in Bangkok in August 1967 it was viewed by China as a club of pro-western anti-communist states. Chinese media and Chinese commentators derisively referred to ASEAN as “the son of SEATO.”¹ It took China nearly two and a half decades before it decided to engage with ASEAN. China was initially motivated by economic and political-diplomatic interests but it was not long before security interests came to the fore.

ASEAN promotes regional autonomy as a means of buffering itself from outside pressures by the major powers. ASEAN also seeks to be “in the driver’s seat” with respect to Southeast Asia’s economic and political-security multilateral architecture such as the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF), ASEAN Defence Ministers’ Meeting Plus (ADMM Plus), Expanded ASEAN Maritime Forum and East Asia Summit (EAS).

This paper is divided into five parts and a conclusion. Part one provides an overview of ASEAN-China relations; it is followed by sections covering economic and strategic relations. Part four discusses the South China Sea as an irritant in ASEAN-China relations, while Part five reviews ASEAN’s efforts to maintain regional autonomy in the face of pressures from external powers.

Overview of China-ASEAN Relations

China’s first formal contact with ASEAN took place in July 1991 when China’s Foreign Minister Qian Qichen attended the 24th ASEAN Ministerial Meeting (AMM) in Kuala Lumpur as a guest of the Malaysian government. Qian expressed China’s interest in developing cooperation with ASEAN and ASEAN responded positively. In July 1994, ASEAN and China reached agreement to establish two joint committees — one on economic and trade cooperation and the other on science and technology

cooperation. China and ASEAN also agreed to open consultations on political and security issues at the senior official level.

In April 1995, ASEAN and China held the first meeting of senior officials on political-security issues in Hangzhou, southern China. The following year China was accorded official dialogue partner status by ASEAN. As an ASEAN dialogue partner, China regularly participates in the annual ASEAN Post-Ministerial Conference consultation process. This takes the form of a meeting between ASEAN and its ten dialogue partners (ASEAN 10 Plus 10), and a separate meeting between ASEAN members and each of its dialogue partners (ASEAN 10 Plus 1).

In February 1997, ASEAN and China formalized their growing cooperation by establishing the ASEAN-China Joint Cooperation Committee (JCC). The JCC first met in Beijing where it was agreed that it would “act as the coordinator for all the ASEAN-China mechanisms at the working level.”² Since 1997 ASEAN and China have held annual summit meetings. As a ASEAN dialogue partner China became an inaugural member of the EAS and ADMM Plus in 2005 and 2010 respectively.

China-ASEAN Economic Relations

A major turning point in ASEAN-China economic relations was reached following the Asian Financial Crisis of 1997-98 that impacted severely on Southeast Asia’s economies. The International Monetary Fund, supported by the United States, imposed harsh conditions on loans to affected states. In contrast, China contributed to regional bail out packages and also refrained from devaluing its currency. As a result ASEAN members perceived China as Southeast Asia’s indispensable – but not only - economic partner.³

In November 2002, China and ASEAN adopted the Framework Agreement on Comprehensive Economic Cooperation. Two years later China inaugurated an annual China-ASEAN Expo in Nanning to promote trade. The Expo regularly attracts ASEAN government leaders as well as representatives from the private sector.

The 2002 Framework Agreement led to the signing of agreements on trade in goods (2004), trade in services (2007) and investment (2009). These agreements formed the building blocks of the ASEAN-China Free Trade Agreement (ACFTA)⁴ that came into force in January 2010 for six ASEAN states (Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand and Brunei). China granted special concessions to ASEAN’s developing members – Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar and Vietnam – and they were given until 2015 to comply with tariff reductions. ASEAN and China also established a Joint Committee to oversee the ACFTA. This committee met for the first time in April 2012 in Nanning, China.

In 2009 China established the China-ASEAN Fund on Investment Cooperation capitalized at US \$10 billion with an additional US \$15 billion in credit to support infrastructure development projects.

China's economic rise has altered Southeast Asia's political economy and absorbed regional states in a production network feeding into China's export-orientated manufacturing industries. China not only buys primary commodities and natural resources, particularly oil and gas, but also electronic parts and components from Southeast Asia. China's economic rise also has resulted in the displacement of the United States as the major trading partner for most Southeast Asian states. In 2009 China emerged as ASEAN largest trading partner while ASEAN became China's third largest trading partner. Two-way trade reached US \$318.6 billion in 2012 with a goal of US \$500 billion by 2015.

In October 2013, at the 16th ASEAN-China Summit, ASEAN leaders agreed to a Chinese proposal to upgrade the ACFTA to further economic integration. The Summit also agreed to speed up ASEAN's Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) first approved in 2012. RCEP is an initiative to create a free trade area comprising ASEAN's ten members and six countries that have free trade agreements with ASEAN – Australia, China, India, Japan, New Zealand and South Korea. At the Summit China offered its support for ASEAN's Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity and later made available a US \$10 billion line of credit to support this initiative.

The Obama Administration has backed a competing trade arrangement known as the Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP) that is viewed as a first step towards a free trade area of the Asia-Pacific. Currently twelve countries are negotiating the TPP, including four ASEAN states: Australia, Brunei, Canada, Chile, Japan, Malaysia Mexico, New Zealand, Peru, Singapore, the United States and Vietnam.

China's economic initiatives are aimed at challenging U.S. and Japanese dominance of the World Bank and Asian Development Bank. On October 24, 2004, China launched the Asian Infrastructure and Investment Bank (AIIB). Representatives from twenty-one countries attended the launch including nine ASEAN states. The BIIA will be capitalized at US \$50 billion and will fund trade-related infrastructure across Asia. The United States is opposed to this bank and heavily lobbied Indonesia, South Korea, and Australia not to join.

Most recently, at the 11th China-ASEAN Expo in October 2014, China proposed to ASEAN the establishment of a Maritime Silk Road to boost regional economic integration.

ASEAN-China Strategic Relations

In October 2003, China acceded to the ASEAN Treaty of Amity and Cooperation (TAC), and undertook in writing "faithfully to perform and carry out all the stipulations therein contained."⁵ The TAC commits signatories not to use or threaten the use of force in their relations. At the same time, ASEAN and China issued a joint declaration establishing a Strategic Partnership for Peace and Prosperity. The joint declaration was the first formal agreement of this type between China and a regional

organization, as well as a first for ASEAN itself. The joint declaration was wide-ranging and included a provision for the initiation of a new security dialogue as well as general cooperation in political matters.⁶ China was also the first nuclear weapon state and ASEAN dialogue partner to offer to accede to the Protocol of the 1995 South East Asia Nations Nuclear Weapon Free Zone Treaty.

In late 2004, China and ASEAN drafted a five-year Plan of Action (2005-2010) to implement the new strategic partnership. This plan included, *inter alia*, a joint commitment to increase regular high-level bilateral visits, cooperation in the field of non-traditional security, security dialogue and military exchanges and cooperation.⁷ Later an Action Plan for 2011-2015 was adopted for eleven priority areas: agriculture, information and communication technology, human resource development, investment, Mekong Basin Development, transportation, energy, culture, tourism, public health and environment.

In 2006 ASEAN and China further institutionalized their relationship by raising their Strategic Partnership to an Enhanced Strategic Partnership.⁸ In July 2006, China-ASEAN held their first workshop on regional security in Beijing between their respective defence departments. China and ASEAN currently conduct annual consultations on strategic and political security cooperation by defence officials, an annual conference by foreign ministers, and an annual summit meeting of government leaders.

South China Sea

In the early 1990s ASEAN concerns focused on the manner in which China pursued its territorial and maritime claims in the South China Sea. In 1992 China adopted the Law on Territorial Sea and Contiguous Zones; and China's oil exploration activities soon brought it into conflict with Vietnam. China's actions raised alarm bells among ASEAN members that viewed China's actions a claim to the entire South China Sea. ASEAN concerns were heightened by the U.S military withdrawal from the Philippines at this time.

In 1992, ASEAN responded to China-Vietnam tensions by issuing a Declaration of Concern urging unnamed parties to resolve the matter peacefully. Southeast Asian anxieties about Chinese assertiveness were aroused again in 1995 when China occupied Mischief Reef claimed by the Philippines. ASEAN issued another public declaration calling for restraint and the peaceful settlement of disputes.

In an attempt to resolve this matter ASEAN and China embarked on seven years of fruitless negotiations to secure a legally binding Code of Conduct in the South China Sea (COC). In November 2002 all the two sides could come up with was a non-binding political statement known as the Declaration on Conduct of Parties in the South China Sea (DOC). The DOC laid out a series of cooperative activities and confidence building measures. It was not until December 2004, however, that China

and ASEAN agreed on the terms of reference for a Joint Working Group to implement the DOC. Another seven years passed before the Guidelines to Implement the DOC were finally adopted in July 2011.

Since the adoption of the Guidelines to Implement the DOC ASEAN leaders have pressed their Chinese counterparts to fully and effectively implement the DOC. There were further delays until 2013 when China announced it was willing to enter into consultations on the COC with ASEAN members but only under the framework of the Joint Working Group to Implement the DOC and on the basis of consensus. On September 13, 2013, China and ASEAN held their first consultations on the COC at a meeting of senior officials in Suzhou, China. Consultations are continuing with the most recent meeting, the eighth ASEAN-China Senior Officials Meeting, held in Thailand in October 2014.

During the period from 1995 to the present China has aggressively asserted its sovereignty claims over the South China Sea. China has expanded construction on Mischief Reef. In May 2009 China officially tabled its u-shaped nine-dash line map to the UN Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf. China's claims the South China Sea on the basis of "historic rights" but at the same time China refuses to clarify what it means by that expression or what it is claiming within the nine-dash lines on its map. It appears that China is claiming sovereignty over every island and rock in the South China Sea and "their adjacent waters."

China's nine-dash lines overlap the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ) of Vietnam, the Philippines, Malaysia, and Brunei. China's nine-dash lines also cut across the continental shelf claimed by Indonesia around Natuna Island. China's aggressive assertion of sovereignty against the Philippines have led China's virtual annexation of Scarborough Shoal and interference with efforts by the Philippines to resupply a small garrison of marines based at Second Thomas Shoal. In May-July 2014, China precipitated a major crisis in its relations with Vietnam when it deployed a mega oil drilling platform accompanied by an armada of navy and civilian ships in Vietnam's EEZ. At the same time China has initiated massive land reclamation projects on five of the features that it occupies in the Spratly archipelago.

Territorial and sovereignty disputes in the South China Sea have exposed rifts in ASEAN. The most notable example was Cambodia's action as ASEAN Chair in 2012 to block all mention of these disputes in the customary joint communiqué than normally follows the foreign ministers' AMM. China has played on internal ASEAN differences by deliberately protracting the consultation process on implementing the DOC and adopting a legally binding COC.

China's stonewalling tactics have led the Philippines to take its maritime dispute with China to an Arbitral Tribunal and to beef up its alliance with the United States. Vietnam has opted to pursue a multilateral strategy among the major powers by encouraging the United States,

Japan and India to balance China, by securing Russian and Indian support for the modernisation of its naval and air forces, while at the same time attempting to manage friction in its bilateral relations with China. ASEAN itself has doggedly pursued a political-diplomatic strategy with China to secure a binding COC.

East Asia Exclusivism versus Southeast Asia Autonomy

During the first half of the 1990s, ASEAN members viewed China both as a security threat and an economic challenge. China's assertive behavior towards Vietnam (not yet an ASEAN member) and the Philippines (an ASEAN founding member) in the South China Sea was a major source of concern. Southeast Asian states initially feared that China's economic rise would be at their expense because it would result in the diversion of trade and investment. ASEAN states also feared being pulled into China's orbit in a dependent relationship as supplier of raw materials.

Three key developments proved pivotal in shifting ASEAN perspectives from "the China threat" to "China as an opportunity," thus facilitating China's rapid engagement with ASEAN. First, China itself changed its views and began to see the benefits of multilateralism. In the aftermath of the Cold War ASEAN was no longer viewed as a pro-western anti-communist club. China sought to engage with ASEAN and ASEAN-centric multilateral institutions. Second, China's positive response during the Asian Financial Crisis in the late 1990s went down well with ASEAN states. China was viewed as an indispensable economic partner. Third, the 2002 ASEAN-China agreement on the DOC temporarily assuaged regional concerns about China's overly assertive South China Sea policy.

ASEAN welcomed and encouraged engagement with China. But at the same time ASEAN has resisted being pulled into China's political-security orbit. For example, in 1997 China advanced a "new concept of security" to promote cooperative security within the ARF with a heavy emphasis on non-traditional security. This approach was welcomed by ASEAN members because it addressed issues they held to be important. But China's repeated criticism of Cold War era alliances and their focus on traditional security issues drew a less enthusiastic response from members that welcomed a continuing U.S. presence in the region. China's "new security concept" failed to gain traction.

In 2003, China renewed its efforts to promote its "new concept of security" by successfully proposing the creation of a Security Policy Conference comprised of senior military and security officials drawn from all ARF members. In late 2004, when China hosted the first ARF Security Policy Conference it used this forum to push for a security treaty to promote "peace, stability and prosperity" in the region. Chinese officials argued that the new treaty would give equal attention to the concerns of all ARF members and guarantee security through united action rather than seeking "absolute security for oneself and threaten[ing] other parties' security."⁹ Due to reservations by ASEAN members China's

proposal was left on the table. China's motivation in proposing the Security Policy Conference was viewed in some quarters as designed to create an alternative to the western dominated Shangri-La Dialogue initiated in 2002.¹⁰

As a response to the Asian Financial Crisis in the late 1990s China took the initiative in setting up an annual summit meeting including ASEAN, Japan and South Korea. This became known as ASEAN Plus Three or APT. China strongly advocated a focus on non-traditional security issues and later pushed for defence ties among APT members. China's support for the ASEAN Plus Three was clearly aimed at consolidating its position in the region through East Asian exclusivist arrangements omitting the United States. ASEAN responded by demonstrating its concern to maintain autonomy and remain in the driver's seat. In 2005 ASEAN established the East Asia Summit by initially including India, Australia and New Zealand along with the APT members, and later included Russia and the United States.¹¹

In 2013 President Xi Jinping toured Southeast Asia as part of his attendance at the East Asia Summit. Xi proposed a treaty on good-neighbourliness and friendly cooperation between China and ASEAN. Thus proposal was made after Indonesia had floated a proposed a treaty of friendship and cooperation embracing the wider Indo-Pacific Region. Once again ASEAN chose to maintain regional autonomy by noting "with appreciation" - but taking no action on - both proposals.¹²

Conclusion

In summary, ASEAN has fended off pressures and inducements to align with China by actively encouraging engagement with the other major powers and by placing priority on ensuring Southeast Asia's regional autonomy. ASEAN generally has welcomed the Obama Administration's rebalance towards the Asia-Pacific and its support for ASEAN and ASEAN-centric multilateral institutions. Although the Obama Administration's policy of rebalancing has provided ASEAN with some leverage in its relations with China U.S. rebalancing has also resulted in renewed Chinese efforts to counter U.S. influence. This was illustrated in 2013 when the U.S. proposed hosting an inaugural informal meeting with ASEAN defence ministers; China quickly countered with a similar offer.¹³

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4. Asean's Relations with China

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The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) was formed on 8 August 1967 through the Bangkok Declaration. The founding members of ASEAN were Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore and Thailand – all being non-communist states. While explicitly it was established to foster good relations between its members, implicitly, however, it was aimed at creating a unified front against the expansion of communism. Therefore, in its initial years, the communist states in the region, namely Vietnam, Laos and Cambodia, were excluded from this regional organization. However, with the end of the Cold War in 1991, ASEAN began witnessing an era of expansion. On 8 January 1984, Brunei became ASEAN's sixth member, and on 28 July 1995, Vietnam was admitted as its seventh member. Further, on 23 July 1997, both Laos and Myanmar (Burma) joined ASEAN, and on 30 April 1999, Cambodia became the organization's tenth member. As a regional organization, ASEAN not only promotes cordial relations between its member states, but even promotes good relations with extra-regional major players. These amongst others, include the United States, Japan, India and China.

With China, ASEAN engages the country through a number of means. The genesis of ASEAN's engagement with China began in 1991, when a dialogue was initiated between both at the request of China. Further, these relations were taken to a higher level when in July 1996, China was accorded the status of a full dialogue partner by

ASEAN. In 1997, the dialogue with key Northeast Asian states namely China, Japan and South Korea, was institutionalized to become the ASEAN Plus Three (ASEAN+3). It was also in the same year that ASEAN and China entered into what is known as the 21st century-oriented partnership, which in 2003, was upgraded to become a strategic partnership. Since its inception in 1997 and later institutionalization in 1999, the ASEAN Plus Three (ASEAN+3) mechanism promotes dialogue between ASEAN and China, Japan as well as South Korea. Apart from the ASEAN+3 that is annually held during the ASEAN summits, there is also the ASEAN-China Summit which began in 1997. In addition, China is also a member of the East Asia Summit (EAS) that is comprised the ASEAN member states (AMS), Australia, China, India, Japan, New Zealand, Russia and the United States. The EAS is primarily a Malaysian initiative and was inaugurated on 14 December 2005 in Kuala Lumpur where its first meeting was held.

Apart from that, there is also the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF), a loose but broad-based security framework that was created by ASEAN on 25 July 1994. The ARF currently comprises of 27 members from across the Asia-Pacific and is aimed at discussing issues pertaining to peace and security in the region. As a major power, China's presence is considered extremely vital especially in terms of ensuring peace and stability in the Asia-Pacific. What more, China is also a claimant in the disputed Paracel and Spratly islands which is also claimed by a few ASEAN states, namely Malaysia, Philippines and Vietnam.

Over the years, trade between ASEAN and China has also significantly grown partly due to the signing of bilateral free trade agreements between China and the Southeast Asian states. For example, while trade between both stood at US\$59.6 billion in 2003, by 2008, it was already valued at US\$192.5 billion.¹ In fact, trade between both had markedly increased since the creation of the ASEAN-China Free Trade Area (ACFTA) which came into effect on 1 January 2010. The idea to create a free trade area between both was first mooted by China in November 2000. Further, on 4 November 2002, an initial framework was signed in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, which eventually led to the establishment of the ACFTA. With a population of 1.9 billion and combined GDP of around US\$6 trillion, the ACFTA is currently the largest free trade area in the world. As a result of its creation, tariff on more than 7,000 products has been reduced to zero and all these items account for some 90 percent of the current trade volume. While this arrangement on tariff reduction currently only includes Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore and Thailand, the other ASEAN states, namely Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar and Vietnam (CLMV), are to follow suit by 2015. As of 2013, trade between ASEAN and China was valued at US\$443.6 billion. Of this, ASEAN's imports from China were at US\$244.1 billion while its exports stood at US\$199.5 billion. As a whole, while China is ASEAN's largest trading partner, ASEAN on the other hand, is China's third largest trading partner. In the

area of investment, while ASEAN's investments into China were valued at US\$8.35 billion in 2013, Chinese investments in the ASEAN region for the same year were at US\$5.74 billion.² Apart from providing both parties with greater access to each other's markets, the ACFTA is also viewed by some as China's attempts to entrench itself economically in the Southeast Asian region.

Although trade, commerce and investments from both sides have significantly increased, the issue of disputed territorial claims in the Paracels and Spratly remains a thorny issue in the relations between both parties. While China claims both the groups of islands in its entirety, not all ASEAN states are claimants to these islands. In the case of the Paracels, Vietnam is the only Southeast Asian country that has laid a claim on these islands, while in the case of the Spratly, only three ASEAN countries are claimants, namely Malaysia, Philippines and Vietnam. In connection, on 4 November 2002, all the ten ASEAN member states and China signed the ASEAN Declaration on the Conduct (DOC) of Parties in the South China Sea in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, aimed creating a Code of Conduct in the South China Sea. At the moment, both parties are negotiating towards the eventual implementation of the DOC and reaching an agreement on the COC. However, ASEAN hardly has a united stand when it comes to dealing with China in the South China Sea. One such example was in 2012 when Cambodia, the host of the ASEAN Summit, strongly resisted attempts by the other ASEAN member states to press China on the issue. In fact, the failure of ASEAN member states to reach a unified stand on the said issue even prompted the ASEAN Secretary-General, SurinPitsuwan, to comment that such a dereliction was indeed "unprecedented" in the more than four decades of the regional organization's history. He even remarked that "ASEAN will need to learn how to consolidate and coordinate its positions if it wants to take on the global community."³

Nevertheless, taking into account increased Chinese military presence and activities in the South China Sea, most, if not all, ASEAN member states remain wary and suspicious of Chinese ambitions in the region. For some, China is obviously trying to turn the South China Sea into a Chinese lake. More so, when China's nine-dotted (or nine-dash line) is taken into account as it overlaps with the exclusive economic zones of most ASEAN member states. For example, while Indonesia is not a claimant to the Spratly, however, its exclusive economic zone north of the Natuna Island overlaps with the said line, which in turn, has created some problems between Indonesia and China. One such incident was in March 2013 when an Indonesian patrol boat was coerced by a Chinese naval ship to release Chinese fishermen caught in Indonesia's EEZ.⁴

On the whole, recognizing that China is a key player in the Asia-Pacific region, ASEAN has over the years increased its engagement with the former through a variety of means, channels and levels. All the same, the rise of China as a major economic power has also afforded the

ASEAN member states with the opportunity to diversify its economic relations. While till the late 1980s, the economic relations of most ASEAN member states were either with major Western key players or Japan, the rise of China in the 1990s, has afforded these states with an added opportunity to expand their trade, commerce and investments. However, it is equally important to note that despite all these positive economic developments, most if not all, ASEAN member states remain wary of Chinese ambitions in the South China Sea – a sea that is considered of vital importance to almost all ASEAN member states. As such, any attempt by China to take full control of the South China Sea would surely be resisted strongly by most ASEAN member states. It therefore safe to conclude that the future direction of ASEAN-China relations would be shaped in the South China Sea rather than by trade, commerce and investment. In other words, the South China Sea might eventually become the theatre where the direction of relations between the ASEAN states and China would be decided.

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5. Sino-Japanese relationship and their interests towards ASEAN

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Abstract

This paper analyses the importance of ASEAN for China and Japan; that stands as a relevant topic provided that the Sino-Japanese relationship is tough and ASEAN has emerged as a key role player. This paper analyses, first, the Sino-Japanese relationship emphasising the current tensions. Second, it looks at the links they both have with ASEAN in order to find out the expectations of such relationship. It concludes that both parts want to impose their own rule and counterbalance each other's power; China is mainly concerned about security issues, as well as economic links, while Japan is focused on political-economic links. What needs to be seen is how ASEAN will evolve in the future and how powerful it will be by itself, hence the implications for the Pacific Rim.

Introduction

At the time being, no one doubts that in terms of security, economy and politics, China and Japan stand as the two crucial forces in the Pacific Rim. Historically, they have a long record of episodes of mutual cooperation, but also disputes: from a period of cultural and political exchange and enhancement, witnessing afterwards the outbreak of the First Sino-Japanese War in 1894, to the current situation in which each one is trying to defend their respective geopolitical roles and position themselves in East Asia while redefining their power¹.

Despite the power exerted by Beijing and Tokyo, they are not solo regional role players: the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) is nowadays the focal point. This cohort of nation-states has become highly relevant in terms of stability among the great powers in East Asia. China's views on ASEAN are mostly on security ², while Japan is trying to reinforce its condition of ASEAN's legitimate economic partner, therefore making the region more stable at the expense of China's rise of power³. Such visions are not unique, though. What is clear is that whoever may see ASEAN turning into a battleground for China and Japan might not be entirely wrong, while ASEAN member states have to keep an eye on trying not leaning too much towards one of the sides if regional stability wants to be preserved ⁴.

Sino-Japanese relationships

Relationships between China and Japan are anything but easy. They are normally highly complex, and the author Burns, K. perfectly identifies five stages: **1)** before 1894; **2)** between 1894 (First Sino-Japanese War) and 1945; **3)** during the Cold War; **4)** between 1972 and 1978 (when Japan re-emerged and tried to normalize the relations); and **5)** 1979 onwards⁵.

Sino-Japanese relationships enjoyed of centuries of prosperity: ties between them were tight between the 5th and 10th centuries, when Japan accumulated endless amount of knowledge from the Chinese – they adopted their writing system, Buddhism and Confucianism or political institutions based on the Chinese ones⁶. Moving forward on time, the end of the First Sino-Japanese War in 1895 over control of Korea meant a shift of power in favour of Japan and a decadence of the Qing Dynasty in China.

Contemporarily, such relationship is witnessing an episode never seen before, therefore inspiring uncertainty: the emerging China and the re-emerged Japan are two major forces face-to-face in East Asia, and the view of Tokyo taking the regional lead since the Sino-Japanese War may have come to an end ⁷.

More recently, between 2006 and 2012, the relationship improved when Shinzo Abe became PM to the expenses of Junichiro Koizumi; Abe made an effort to improve diplomatic relationships and establish certain normalcy between the two nations⁸, and his counterpart positively responded with his “warm-up trips” to China. After President Xi Jinping took office in 2012, though, relationship deteriorated again. The broken

equilibrium may easily be linked to nationalistic issues: on one hand, Xi's predecessor Hu Jintao did not enjoy of a strong control of the domestic politics as to make them prosperous – something that changed with Xi's presidency in 2012. All in all, the post Koizumi improved relationship was no longer valid⁹. On the Japanese side, certain nationalistic actions did not help at all, either – think of Tokyo Mayor Ishihara Shintaro announcing that Japan would purchase and nationalise Senkaku Islands¹⁰.

Currently, the raise of nationalism is not an issue that will contribute positively to regional progress. Each other's perceptions are far from being encouraging: in 2014, only 3% of the Japanese declared seeing China as a positive influence, while vice versa was the 7%¹¹.

The Association of Southeast Nations (ASEAN)

In 1967, The Bangkok Declaration gave birth to ASEAN, whose aim was clear and simple: creating a contention block against the establishment of the communist forces in the recently decolonized Southeast Asia, within an international structure that was clearly bipolar – ASEAN prioritized very much not to be seen as an organization exclusive focused on military and security purposes, as regionalism involves much more than that¹².

Since its foundation, ASEAN has witnessed great improvements among its members (which reveal sharp differences among them in terms of culture, economy, development, religion, etc) and ASEAN is nowadays a cluster of nation-states with over 600 million people¹³. What makes, then, ASEAN be a key global player? And more importantly: why will ASEAN remain as a priority for China and Japan? Reasons may be countless, but economically speaking, ASEAN is now an investment hub due to the stabilization of domestic politics of a number of its members; socially speaking, its youth will represent a new wave of workforce¹⁴; finally, in terms of security, ASEAN went from a modest sub-regional organization to dealing with multi-lateral processes all over East Asia. That is especially valid considering the creation of several intra-governmental organizations such ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) and ASEAN Plus Three (APT), which have built up and shaped constructive multi-lateral relationships in the triangle ASEAN-China-Japan¹⁵, which also means that each part will try to make its own priorities resilient.

ASEAN and China

The relationship China-ASEAN has witnessed a number of changes since the Cold War era: while China had satisfactory bilateral relationships

with some countries like Indonesia or North Vietnam, another number of states perceived China as a threat; a threat called communism, which made some countries gather around the Southeast Asian Treaty Organization until 1977 – backed by the United States. Diplomatic state-to-state relations were delayed till the late 70's, and progressed during the 80's with the communist insurgent movements in the region. The first China-ASEAN contact dates back to 1991, when China was invited to the 24th ASEAN Foreign Ministers' Meeting. Besides that, the Chinese charm offensive also consisted in establishing bilateral relationships with ASEAN nations, thus making ASEAN looking towards the East to develop a solid relationship with China¹⁶.

The FTA between China and ASEAN (ACFTA), signed in 2002, was a turning point¹⁷: that meant the creation of the biggest FTA in Asia, but above all it projected the Chinese stunning economic offensive over ASEAN and how not only military growth seemed to matter: it guarantees China access to raw materials and less barriers for exports. Besides trade, China is playing the card of assistance, especially to the Mekong Sub-region; thanks to such support to development, China can benefit from creating trade partnerships¹⁸.

In terms of security, there is one particular issue that clearly remarks the importance of such field for China: the South China Sea (SCS) dispute. Such dispute goes beyond a mere geographical term involving Spratly and Paracel Islands; what are really focusing the attention of China are the hydrocarbons in the area, in particular natural gas, which are believed to be abundant¹⁹. Among the non-OECD countries, China will lead the increase of natural gas consumption in Asia – which is growing 3.9% annually and will represent the 19% world gas consumption in 2035, according to the U.S Energy Information Administration (EIA), and also estimates that around 11 billion barrels of oil could be extracted, along with the 190 trillion cubic feet of natural gas²⁰. Besides the conflict itself, the fact that the claimant is not ASEAN as a whole, but each individual state, is not making the dispute easy to solve.

The geographic importance of the region encompassed between the Malacca and Taiwan straits responds to global trade, too: the Strait of Malacca, one of the gateways to the SCS, sees how more than half of the annual merchant fleet tonnage sails across it (Malacca, Sunda and Lombok), and most of it continues – or comes from –to the SCS. On top of that, it also represents one of the world's busiest maritime routes for crude oil and liquefied natural gas (LNG)²¹.

ASEAN and Japan

The relationship ASEAN-Japan established its first link over forty years ago. At a first sight, Japan is sharply concentrated on economic issues and investment. But, on the other hand, political issues are also relevant – rise of tensions due to the dispute of Senkaku Islands.

Economic interests are existent since Japan was “rebuilt” after the Second World War, but mainly rooted in the 1990’s decade that witnessed a deep economic stagnancy: Japan had need to target other economies in Asia where they could invest in and relaunch its economy²⁵. The fact that Japan is recently looking towards ASEAN in terms of investment is double edged: ASEAN offers low production costs, and those of China are on the rise. In terms of Nippon investment, China reached its peak during the second half of 2011, but from that moment on, Japanese investment moved towards ASEAN – more specifically, towards Thailand, Indonesia and Vietnam – as the production costs were more competitive. Japan not only found out that infrastructure and industrial complexes were notably developed, but also that the nominal GDP in cities like Bangkok was at a par with that of China, which could make the Thai capital become a consumption hub of Japanese firms and products²³.

In terms of security, Japan’s influence over ASEAN is certainly limited because of its post Second World War security alliance with the United States. But even with such cornerstone, Japan still plays a role in political-security cooperation. There is no doubt that such an issue is highly complex; even if ASEAN comes as a single block, each state presents its own domestic policies, some leaning more towards China – like Cambodia – and some others more towards the U.S – the case of the Philippines – which is clearly making hard to establish how far ASEAN should go with Japan in terms of security²⁴. For Japan, of course, the political influence exerted over ASEAN should serve as a rebalancing tool against China²⁵.

What is clear is that even if Japan sees itself certainly limited while being under the American security umbrella, is that the PM Abe has not been losing his time and has made very clear his pro-ASEAN policies visiting all members since 2013, plus the Minister of Foreign Affairs Kishida Fumido is paying regular visits to ASEAN members in a clear declaration of strengthening bilateral relationships²⁶.

Discussion

Sino-Japanese relationships might be an example of two roosters in the same coop. The biggest uncertainty is where such a tense relationship and new type of great power relations between the second and third world economies will bring them to – plus the role of the U.S as pivoting agent.

Despite the recent raise of tensions, open conflict remains unlikely: in such scenario, they both are well aware that mutual damages would way overpass the benefits. What seems apparent is that both China and Japan now differentiate politics from economics: China shows its assertiveness on the Senkaku Islands dispute – trying to establish an Air Defence Identification Zone (ADIZ) – but at the same time, Japan remains as China's top trading partner. Economically, they are interdependent; prove of that is Abe's (renewed) cabinet and its willing to improve the relationship, not only with China, but also with South Korea – intention that was also expressed by Yuko Obuchi, precisely the Japanese Minister of Trade and Industry.

The Sino-ASEAN conflict over the SCS is shaping their relations; it is not only downgrading the diplomatic relationships, but also the economic ties. That is especially going against China; Beijing's government strategy appears to be focused on a military offensive, but an economic offensive is clear, too – and maybe even more important – which may be the only means to fuel the military offensive, too. As mentioned, China should not expect an open conflict with Japan, but the military and economic offensive may well respond to a China's concern on a potential Asian NATO-like alliance that could put Beijing at a disadvantage in the new regional architecture. Therefore, ASEAN stands as a priority for Beijing – probably not to intentionally form a large security alliance in the Pacific, which seems unlikely to happen, but at least to avoid ASEAN leaning towards Japan which, in turn, would also involve the US.

Politically, though, differences seem far from being settled; on one hand, China has been taking unilateral actions like the establishment of the ADIZ or new fishing regulations over exclusive economic zones and is only willing to set bilateral relationships with the ASEAN members, rather than bilaterally with ASEAN. A big hurdle may come from ASEAN's lack of unity, as not all ten members are claimants and each one has domestic issues that directly define its position. The direct consequence of that is a delay in the establishment of solid and binding measures to ease tensions. ASEAN should be worried, of course, of China assertiveness, but both parts need to think of the economic

opportunities they are losing due to such tensions; economic goals are there, but may be damaged if no progress is made.

The Japan-ASEAN relationships have traditionally been longer compared to those of China. Such links are especially political and economic, and will not be likely change in the future; it can be observed through domestic politics and the so-called *Abenomics* – aggressive fiscal policies implemented by the PM Abe. Japan is interested in fostering good relationship with ASEAN: on one hand, because of ASEAN Economic Community that will be a reality by the end of 2015, therefore for interest in building-up confidence by means of aid to narrow down the development gap in Southeast Asia. On the other hand, Japan will have to take a role in East Asia in order to counterbalance the influence of China.

Japanese military power is limited, so the future will greatly depend on Abe's efforts to reinterpret the Article 9, along with the Article 51 of the UNO Charter – which allows displaying self-defence measures if attacked, and the will to keep America in.

Is then correct stating that ASEAN is the new battleground for China and Japan? To a certain extent, there is nothing wrong in such statement. Both China and Japan are using their strategies to become more influential over ASEAN, hence over the Pacific Rim. Concurrently, their efforts to enhance their relevance respond basically to domestic strategies to counterbalance each other's influence.

It should not be forgotten that the triangle China-Japan-ASEAN is being analyzed, which is why it will be fundamental to see how ASEAN evolves: the effectiveness of the AEC, the developmental gap, domestic politics of its nations, etc., all in all, the ASEAN centrality. The logic path for ASEAN to have a stronger voice would be a better cohesion among its members, which would also relationships with other actors harsher but more gratifying if achieved.

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(C) International Perspective on CHINA

1. Sino-Russian relations in the new period

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In recent years, Sino-Russian relations at a high level the track continues to deepen, maintained a strong momentum of development. Sino-Russian relations have maintained sustainable development is no accident, with intrinsic motivation and reasons. First, the lessons of history to become Russia two big neighboring countries by hostility to the good-neighborly friendship precious heritage. Practice has proved that the two sides establish a non-confrontational, non-aligned, is not directed against third countries, non-intervention in internal affairs, respect each other's choice principle is correct, full of vitality. Russia established diplomatic relations 20 years ago, in the midst of the international environment, relations between the two countries through a variety of tests, always upward along the track of development. Can be described as easy, two big countries and Russia for decades and stable development of bilateral relations in the relations between big powers in rare. From the establishment of partnerships between the two countries, the strategic cooperative partnership to a comprehensive strategic partnership, one step forward solid tie. Most importantly, in 2001 the two sides signed the historic "good-neighborly friendship and cooperation treaty." Second Sino-Russian friendship is a stage of development in which the two countries as well as the historical task facing the decision. The two adjacent geographical features, especially the more than 4300 km long common border, determine the stability of a good surrounding environment has become an important prerequisite for the two sides to each other to preserve the sovereignty and development. Both countries are currently focused on the revitalization of the national economy, to solve domestic problems, have an urgent need for a long-term and stable surrounding environment. In this context, handle the relationship with the greatest neighbors apparently have become the two most important foreign policy. For many years Russia has clearly recognized politicians handle the weight of the bilateral relations, both viscerally willing to maintain long-term good-neighborly and friendly relations between the two countries, have sincerely hope the two countries will always be good neighbors, good friends, good partners such a firm clear political will to

guide the healthy development of bilateral relations is very important. Third Sino-Russian friendship is by the two countries in which the geopolitical and strategic security environment of the decision, the two countries faced with some common or similar problems, such as the threat of separatism, terrorism, extremism, Chechnya, Taiwan, Xinjiang issues, etc., need to support each other, coordinated response. After the Cold War, the evolution of the world situation, determine the Sino-Russian strategic rely on each other, the two sides back to back, mutual aid, which is conducive to maintain their strategic initiative. Of course, this strategic cooperation is not directed against any third country. Moreover, decades of efforts by both sides, the dispute may lead to the history of bilateral relations disputes gradually be properly addressed. The two sides solve the historical legacy of the border to the problem, which is the relationship between the two countries in a very significant achievement. We can say that now no longer exist in bilateral relations major sensitive source, there is no longer a major problem can not be resolved through friendly consultations. But also that both sides erase ideological interference factors, more attention to be pragmatic cooperation with each other.

If the Sino-Russian relations compared with other big-power relations, we can see a very important track, bilateral cooperation in the international arena is a masterstroke. In the post-Cold War international environment, China and Russia are more valued geopolitical position and role of the other, that is to balance the role of the United States. This external or international factors are the main driving force to promote the further development of Sino-Russian relations. Looking back at history can be seen more clearly. American bombing of Yugoslavia, NATO enlargement, missile defense in Europe, to intervene in the internal affairs of the Taiwan issue and the CIS countries have become closer to the opportunity and motivation. This phenomenon is the history of a particular environmental decisions. Sino-Russian cooperation in the international arena to safeguard their own interests, to safeguard world balance of power, to resist the hegemony of the West, the role is very prominent. But we can see that the short-term co-operation and emergency coordination and more, while relatively few strategic initiatives and long-term cooperation. Since more attention to each other's geopolitical role, coupled with the challenge to resist external pressures to bear the brunt of this situation determines the pragmatic cooperation between the two sides is not always at the center position, and thus the size and quality of economic cooperation are at a lower level in the objective. Here it should be emphasized that the low level of economic and trade cooperation has its objective reasons. After the

Soviet Union collapsed, Russia political chaos, the long-term economic malaise, limiting the potential of economic cooperation. Bilateral trade volume has been hovering at the level of a few hundred billion dollars. If the lateral comparison will be more clear, the annual trade volume between China and the United States reached \$ 500 billion, with the EU even more than this figure, 300 billion with Japan, and South Korea have reached \$ 210 billion.

Changes in the international situation even more highlights to enhance economic and trade relations between the two countries urgency. Practice has proved that promote the development of bilateral relations important impetus - trade and economic cooperation over the years has always been short board. For a long time the two sides are not each other's key trading partners. Cause political heat the cold, the heat under the cold. If the changes in the political and economic development of the situation is not synchronized, before the financial crisis is not urgent, then the current will become more prominent. Economic foundation of bilateral relations is not strong, of course, there are concepts, institutional, structural problem. Although great progress in recent years, is still difficult to adapt to the rapid development of bilateral relations. To be fair, highlighting the problems of economic and trade cooperation between the two countries is that trade structure is irrational. Russian exports of resources and energy, China's exports of light industrial products, machinery and electrical products. This is Russia's industrial structure decisions. You can say that Russia is a historical issue export resources. There inevitability of its formation. Anthropogenic changes in the economic history of the formation of structure is not easy. I remember when the 65-year reign of Prime Minister Kosygin proposed changes in the economic structure, but so far without success, and have actually become increasingly serious. Resources and energy exports accounted for 65-70% of national income, 85-90% of foreign exchange. Over time the development of Russia will indeed have serious consequences.

The changing situation in the world today to further promote China-Russia relations and the conditions are different from the past. Impetus to the development of bilateral relations of unity must be changed. Both sides need to explore new momentum to stimulate development of bilateral relations. I think the breaking point is that economic cooperation through bilateral cooperation to promote economic development in their respective countries to pull Russia relations. After the financial crisis has given us this opportunity. The following reasons: First, after the crisis, United States and Europe as a whole recession,

which are dependent on external factors driving Russia's economy is a new challenge. China and Russia have a long-term economic development by stimulating trade, dependence on overseas market is large. United States and Europe are recession shrinking demand for commodities in China. China's development will be restricted. Russia's main export resources market in the European Union, now Russia's demand is also reduced. Post-crisis economic and development issues in both countries are very prominent. Each other on both sides need each other more economically. Especially in the United States and Russia gradually achieve energy independence a big impact. United States dependence on Middle Eastern oil imports decreased, the Middle East oil sources has set its sight on China and Europe, the Russian market is facing challenges of shrinking. Russia's huge Chinese market more attractive. Can not miss opportunities. The second is to change the Chinese characters. Sino-Russian economic and trade cooperation in the past, just export commodities trading partner role China plays, while Russia was in urgent need of investment to revitalize the economy, eyes stare only Western countries. With the sustainable development of China's economy, China already has a strong foreign investment capacity. Has evolved from a trading partner for investment partners, greatly increased the attractiveness of Russia. The current leg to stand on Western countries, Russia has been unable to rely on Western funding. This is starting to focus on the premise Russian Foreign Asia-Pacific region. After Russia's accession to the WTO will open a major trend, the opportunity for bilateral cooperation will also increase. Fourth, the two countries with economies in transition As regard the important position for both sides have become an urgent task. China advocates the scientific concept of development, improve the economic structure of Russia in the pursuit of modernization, promote scientific and technological innovation, both mutual and complementary in economy, easier to release the huge potential for economic cooperation.

Politically speaking, Sino-Russian relations of strategic and political significance. Prerequisite for the development of economic cooperation is persistent relationships, lack of this will never be good prospects for cooperation. Only short-term behavior. We have every reason to be optimistic future bilateral relations position. But in the new high-level starting point, to be given a more solid foundation for Sino-Russian relations. The current international strategic situation is complicated. United States in the Asia-Pacific and European regions offensive aggressive, deeply involved in Syria, Iran, Iraq, Afghanistan, South China Sea and other hot issues. In countries around the trouble, the two countries still need to continue to strengthen coordination and

cooperation in the international arena. But under the new situation alone can not support the building of a wheel of bilateral relations. Need wheel drive or wheel drive. Prominent position in economic cooperation together. Good political relationship requires a solid economic foundation for the job. Future economic cooperation relations between the two countries will play a strong reinforcement effect. For China's sustainable economic cooperation with Russia can not leave. Russia's economic revival in the United States and the West can not abandon China squeezed. Future of Sino-Russian relations will be more focused on economic and political, security, cultural, and other multi-wheel drive strategic cooperation, the two sides will bring tangible results. In particular, the two sides should seize the opportunities of economic cooperation, economic cooperation and effectively make a real masterpiece, deepen cooperation in the fields of investment, regional cooperation, energy, transportation, science and technology, thereby enabling the bilateral relations to a new higher level to continue to benefit the two peoples, for the world to contribute to the prosperity and stability.

2. China's Four-R Strategy toward the United States: Resisting, Reducing, Replacing and Reordering

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Abstract

An epic question the world faces today is what will happen between the United States and China. The current international order and world peace especially the regional stability and security in Asia are at stake. Contrary to the conventional wisdom and despite the notoriously opaque nature of Chinese politics, Beijing's basic strategy towards the United States is rather unambiguous: Essentially, China eyes the top position of global power and leadership currently occupied by the United States with great amount of complex feelings of antipathy, dread, and envy. The deeply-rooted ideational path and the historical logic of Chinese polity determine that, without a sea change of sociopolitical institutions and values at home, the PRC is destined to be a lasting rival and challenger to the United States. The PRC is now forcefully molding the diverse Chinese views and preferences into a statist patriotism of the "China dream" of rejuvenating China's power and glory in the past. Beijing is trying everything to resist, reduce, and replace the American power and leadership, first in the neighborhood and then wherever and whenever possible, to eventually reorder the world for its regime survival. This four-R (resisting, reducing, replacing, and reordering) strategy in steps is likely to constrain significantly international and regional cooperation, providing some financial opportunities to neighbors while forcing them to take sides. It also has great implications about the future of world order and global governance.

To observers of international relations, a profound question of our time is what will happen between the world's two largest economies that have drastically different political systems. More specifically, will the United States and China be colluding even co-hegemons or deadly rivals for world leadership? One of the two, the People's Republic of China (PRC), is growing and evolving rapidly now pursuing a grand new "China dream" that mainly calls for rejuvenating China's past power and glory,¹ thus makes the question ever more pressing and challenging. Various speculations are already abundant ranging from the so-called Beijing-Washington "G-2" idea or "Chinamerica" of a new world order, a new Chinese rule of the world, a fierce geopolitical struggle between the USA and the PRC first in the region of Asia-Pacific, to a coming realization of the two-decade old prophecies of global clashes between the Western and the Eastern civilizations.² Whatever the eventual outcome, the current international order and world peace especially the regional stability and security in Asia are clearly at stake.

The epic enormity, uncertain dynamics, and ever changing factors in the Sino-American relations demand extensive yet nuanced analyses to ascertain the future of this crucial relationship. Central to that effort is the need to understand the strategic visions, values and norms, and policy preferences that guide the two great powers. While the American strategic preferences and value system are relatively stable and transparent, the most common aphorism used to describe Chinese strategic intentions remains the word "uncertainty."³

Contrary to some of the conventional wisdom and despite the notoriously arcane and opaque nature of Chinese politics, Beijing's basic strategy towards the United States is in fact rather unambiguous: Essentially, China eyes the top position of global power and leadership currently occupied by the United States with great amount of complex feelings of antipathy, dread, and envy. The deeply-rooted ideational path and the historical logic of Chinese polity determine that, without a sea change of sociopolitical institutions and values at home, the PRC is destined to be a lasting rival and challenger to the United States and Beijing is trying everything to resist, reduce, and replace the American power and leadership so to reorder the world, first in the neighborhood and then wherever and whenever possible. To China's neighbors and the world at large, Beijing's Four-R strategy of resisting, reducing, replacing, and reordering is likely to constrain significantly international cooperation.⁴ It will increasingly force the nations especially in Asia to choose side, voluntarily or involuntarily, and to settle past scores and current and future issues with growing deference to Chinese demands and preferences.

China's four-R strategy is deeply rooted in a peculiar Chinese traditional and ideational foundation for the making of Chinese foreign policy. It is also necessitated by the current Chinese politics. Essentially, it is for the rising China to counter the American power so to safeguard Beijing's core interest of political survival and regime security.

The PRC and the USA: Tradition and Ideation

The Chinese traditional and ideational path, on which today's Chinese foreign policy is moving forward, can be summarized as a thick heritage and a long political experience of an empire-world order and a state-constructed *tianxia* (all under the heaven) worldview. Historically and geographically, the Chinese ruling elite held the belief that the whole world should be united under one ruler at the center. Outsiders are mostly different, often inferior and must be subjugated or assimilated or kept at bay.⁵ This *tianxia* ideal mandates Chinese rulers to seek, or at least pretend to seek, a political unification of the whole known world under one single ruler, the Son of Heaven, who provides legitimacy for political order and governance for all.

After many dynasty cycles, the last Chinese *tianxia* world order collapsed under the superior force of foreign powers towards the end of the 19th century. Unlike in the past, non-Chinese influence has affected just about every aspect of Chinese life. All political forces and groups were under foreign influences and often directly financed by foreign sponsors. The United States in particular has been a key, later the most important, foreign factor shaping Chinese foreign policy, internal politics and even the Chinese mind. It was the American doctrine of "open-door" first proposed in 1899 by the then U.S. Secretary of State John Hay, arguable a mostly self-serving move by Washington, that led to the aversion of a Chinese repeat of the fate of India and Africa.⁶

The *Kuomintang* (KMT or Nationalist Party) and the ROC (Republic of China, 1912-) have had deep and extensive relations with the United States, as amply documented already by the historians. The ROC was also profoundly influenced by its exhausting struggles against the Japanese invasion and the Soviet subversion. Foreign induced and imposed institutional and ideational changes nudged and pushed the ROC to overcome its “natural” inclination and move away from the traditional Chinese path towards *tianxia* and “joined the right side twice” during both world wars to finally enter the post-World War II Westphalia system led by the United States as one of the Big Five.⁷

Mao Zedong and the CCP (Chinese Communist Party) were once also openly professed fans of American ideals, institutions, policies, and leaders.⁸ But they were more the combination of a Chinese nationalist movement and a tool of subversion created by the Soviet Union.⁹ It grew strong during World War II, with significant American help, to successfully replace the ROC with a “New China” (the PRC, 1949-) through a rather classic peasant rebellion. Then Mao took side with Moscow to be at both cold and hot wars with the United States. The PRC took a leap backward and Mao become a new “son-of-heaven,”¹⁰ who, like the Chinese emperors before, instinctively knew the need to work towards a *tianxia* world order to preserve and govern his new empire. Politically and ideologically, the United States became logically enemy number one to Beijing. Mao dreamed big for a worldwide anti-American

communist revolution to create a new *tianxia* order under the banner of communism or simply “the East Wind.”

However, the new Chinese emperor had little new ideas and only limited resources. His theatric maneuvers to capture the whole “socialist camp” failed with a costly Sino-Soviet split ten years after he signed alliance treaty with Moscow. With a burning desire, Mao harshly and utterly incompetently micromanaged the economy to “catch up with the West” through the mad campaign of Great Leap Forward. Its collapse created the worst peacetime loss of human lives in world history (over 30 million death in three years). His absurd push for a speedy world revolution and world leadership soon led his regime and country into the very dangerous position of opposing both superpowers by the late-1960s.

Interestingly, the United States came to the rescue of Mao’s empire. Thanks to American geopolitical realists chiefly Richard Nixon and Henry Kissinger, who were eager to get out of the quagmire of Vietnam and gain an upper hand in the Cold War against Moscow, Mao and his successors survived their *tianxia*-building blunders and acquired a membership in the international community of sovereign states. The U.S. shielding and the access to Western technology, capital, and market, at the expenses of forcing Beijing to abandon its ideological and treaty comrades all over the world, saved and enriched the PRC.

After the Tiananmen uprising in 1989 and the ending of the Cold War in 1991, Beijing managed to continue its crucial access to world

market despite the sharpened political difference with the U.S.. The CCP retreated further. Not only did Beijing give up any pretention of world revolution against the United States, it deliberately went low-key to follow Deng Xiaoping's order of *taoguang yanghui* (laying low hiding and biding for the time).¹¹ China made greater efforts to open more but selectively to the outside, culminating in joining the World Trade Organization in 2001.

In short, for the past four decades, the U.S. has been the chief source of security, technology and capital to China and China's largest export market. Much of China's impressive new wealth is generated by its highly lucrative trade with the United States.¹² The PRC ran basically trade deficit with much of the world while it continued and even enlarged its massive trade surplus with the United States to finance its massive domestic and international endeavors.

Beijing's Strategic Views and Preferences

Decades-long opening to the outside has given China growing vested interest in the U.S.-led world order. Great amount of complex flows of people and information have also brought new perspectives to China.¹³ There is, however, a fairly consistent Chinese take of the United States, increasingly influenced by the rising Chinese strength and statist nationalism.

On the one end of that spectrum of ideas, Chinese liberals want to embrace fully the norms and values of the U.S.-led current world

system such as globalization and other “universal values” or “world perspectives.” They think the problems and mistrust between Beijing and Washington are mostly rooted in China’s “problem of the Chinese autocratic political power” and “the only way to avoid China becoming the ‘Yellow Peril’ to the world in the future is to change China’s autocratic political power.”¹⁴ Not surprisingly, Beijing has taken a hardline to harass, marginalize, exile, and jail those politically “dangerous” thinkers and writers such as China’s first Nobel Peace Prize winner (2010) Liu Xiaobo, who was sentenced to jail for 11 years in 2009.

Moderate views see China as “quasi status quo country” that can work peacefully with the United States.¹⁵ China should join, rather than confront, the United States but seek a bigger role to modify even reconstruct the current world system to best address China’s core interests peacefully.¹⁶ Retired senior official Zheng Bijian asserts that China and the U.S. can sustain a win-win “convergence and community of shared interests.”¹⁷

Realist thinking of hegemonic power struggle now deeply colors China’s strategic thinking today. Viewing the preservation of its autocratic polity as its number one core interest, Beijing should treat the U.S. as the leading competitor and the main external threat. In order to resist the American influence and pressure, China must play its international power games better so to reduce the American power and to replace Washington’s leadership so to eventually reorder the world, one step at a time. And to enrich and empower itself through a mercantilist

international competition is deemed as the key route. A two-pronged strategy is in practice: China pushes for economic globalization for its vital needs of foreign markets, resources, and technology. Beijing also works hard and creatively to resist and replace American power wherever and whenever there is a chance under the general slogan of promoting multipolarity.¹⁸ China could successfully rise up to win its inevitable “zero-sum game” against the United States by utilizing Western ideas and technology as a new kind superpower and to create a new world order.¹⁹ The current world leadership of the United States is to be grabbed by the patient, better, and stronger PRC in due time.

The powerful tradition of Chinese politics and the deeply harbored *tianxia* worldview are also rising, often disguised as realism and patriotism, to provide the blueprints for the possible Chinese reordering of the world. Distasting the development of a spectrum of diverse ideas that tend to undermine the CCP’s one-party authoritarian regime, Beijing has been working hard in recent years to re-strengthen its traditional control of the Chinese mind, in the name of rejuvenating Chinese civilization and upholding Chinese characters. China’s strategy toward the U.S. is now increasingly influenced and even defined by a statist dichotomy of “the universal world” versus “the special China.”²⁰ China will usher in a new, better, harmonious, and rational world order to reorganize and transform the whole world from a “bad world” to a “good world.”²¹ The revitalized *tianxia* idea of reordering the world has already started to affect China’s strategy towards the United States by justifying

Beijing's efforts of resisting, reducing, and replacing Washington. Not only the American leadership but also the overall organizing principle of the current world order are questioned and challenged by the *tianxia* "alternative," a "better vision for the world."²² China ought "to establish a new clean world modeled after Chinese ways and laws" that are the (superior and invincible) "way of the heaven versus the West's acting out of the (disastrous and undesirable) way of humans."²³ Many in China are pretentiously repackaging the Chinese world order before the 19th century as China's alternative to the Westphalia system.²⁴

Chinese Policies: Four-Rs in Steps

Essentially, the PRC has a core interest of tenaciously protecting its political system of a non-hereditary autocracy that is fundamentally at odds with the dominant political values and norms represented by the current international leader. It is truly ironic that the U.S.-led post-Cold War liberal world order has enabled China to be secure and prosperous as a nation; yet it constantly makes the PRC rulers fundamentally insecure and discontent because the institutional and normative incompatibilities created by the tradition and ideation of Chinese politics. From the same imperial playbook, Beijing has to keep away, confront, and challenge the American leadership in today's world and, ultimately, seek to replace Washington so to reorder the world.²⁵

Therefore, the PRC has refused to be a full-fledged member of the post-Cold War world community by subscribing fully its values and rules

and by shouldering proper shares of obligations. The fearful yet wealthy Chinese leaders are rule-of-force rulers, so they continuously seek refuge in more power through extensive state monopolies, aggressive mercantilist policies, and steady military expansions. Chinese leaders openly stated the goal of China's development is to have a "Rich Country and Strong Army,"²⁶ similar to the official purpose of the pre-World War II Japan, so to safeguard the CCP rule as China's top core interest, resist and deny American power, and replace American leadership, one step at a time.²⁷ Accordingly, the PLA (People's Liberation Army) is already growing at a pace even faster than the red-hot Chinese economy for over two decades, with many expensive and blue-water capable and far-reaching military capabilities (such as anti-satellite ability, submarines, long distance missiles, and airplane carriers) being actively developed.

In fact, Beijing sometimes pretends that there is already a *tianxia* system centered in the PRC by working creatively to create a "Chinese world" first through strikingly isolationist measures including propaganda wars and information control.²⁸ Even the supposedly integrated cyber space has been walled off along the Chinese borders by a mighty PRC Great Fire Wall. Beijing has also gone offensive ideologically by promoting a "Beijing Consensus" or "Chinese Model" as opposing the "Washington Consensus."²⁹ The reducing and replacing efforts are observable in far away places of Africa, where Chinese money and influence have already confronted American power and leadership, however costly and ineffectively so far.³⁰ *The Economist* already reported

that China is now an external player, equal to if not more important than the United States, in the Sudan versus South Sudan conflict.³¹

Nourished by the surging calls of the PRC statist nationalism or patriotism, the rising Chinese power is already seen exercising a “new” leadership in East Asia as part of the overall strategic game with the United States. One example is the highly patronizing tone in PRC President’s letter of congratulation to Kim Jong-En’s succession in Pyongyang in 2012. The heated up Chinese disputes with Southeast Asian nations over the islets in the South China Sea and with Japan and Korea over the rights in the Yellow Sea and East China Sea are also moves in the direction of reducing and replacing the American power in the region through acquiring deference and submission based on fear, to be generated by achieving a power parity even superiority in the region versus the United States. This is powered by the “important decision of build China into a great maritime power” made by the CCP leadership—an unspecified but grand new plan for the expansion of Chinese maritime presence and power.³² An outspoken spokesman of the PLA opened declared that the PRC must build up its military power as fast as it can so to “make foes suffer and give friends goodies” and “only when we are not afraid of the United States anymore, other nations will then be afraid of us.”³³

For its neighbors, China’s four-R strategy and the related policies towards the United States offers short-term opportunities but spells long-term trouble. Beijing’s “united front” effort of resisting and reducing

American power and influence creates windfalls for regional nations in terms of preferential trade terms, direct financial gains and overall friendly accommodation. China has bent over, for example, to appease and court South Korea for that strategic purpose.³⁴ Beijing's effort in this regard has seen some clear successes such as in the 2012 foreign ministers meeting of the ASEAN, where the Southeast Asian nations for the first time ever in 45 years, failed to agree on a joint-communiqué due to the disagreement between Cambodia and other members (the Philippines and Vietnam) about whether to mention the territorial disputes with China about the South China Sea.³⁵

As speculated by many, in the long run especially, China's imperialist tradition in the region is likely to re-manifests itself.³⁶ And indeed Beijing has become increasingly assertive and demanding, felt most acutely by its neighboring nations.³⁷ As some have already observed, Beijing is having its own version of Monroe Doctrine.³⁸ The expected further tensions in the U.S.-China rivalry is likely to force East Asian nations to take sides more explicitly and expensively down the road. One interesting and yet largely overlooked development is perhaps the success of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) that China has helped to create and has been very active in.

Conclusion

With a deep historical tradition and a very live ideation of *tianxia* (all under the heaven) worldview, China pursues a strategy of four-Rs in

steps to resist the United States effectively and creatively and to reduce and replace the American power whenever and wherever possible so to eventually reorder the world. The diverse strategic thoughts and world views identifiable in the PRC are being forcefully controlled and molded into a Sino-centric statist patriotism ideology in the name of rejuvenating the past Chinese power and glory. The new Chinese worldviews powerfully justify Beijing's high-stake four-R strategy towards the United States as it is believed by the CCP leadership to be essential to its political survival.

The four-R strategy is perhaps a natural consequence associated with the rise of a new great power, as predicted by the power-transition theory and realist thinkers. The Sino-American rivalry may, hopefully, be kept as measured and largely virtuous competition between the world's two largest economies. However, given China's reviving tradition of preferring a different "new" world order and after some critical steps of the four-R pursuit, determined by mostly Beijing's internal political logic and dynamics, as some Chinese intellectuals have already warned, Beijing's statist foreign policy could easily go grossly wrong, leading the Chinese nation and the whole region, if not the whole world, into catastrophes just like what the Militarist Japan did before.³⁹ China's neighbors are increasingly forced to take side expensively already. Only history will tell if this time the world can wisely avoid a repeat of the past.

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**3. China and the US Hegemony
in the Asia-Pacific Region**

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International Politics are determined and characterized by the distribution and transition of power within the international system, where power is nowadays intimately related to economics. Power transition theory describes a hierarchical system and most if not all nations recognize the presence of this hierarchy and understand their relative position within this power terrain. The distribution of power is uneven and concentrated in the hands of a few. A dominant nation, that controls the largest proportion of resources within the system, sits at the top. For the past six decades or so this position was unquestionably occupied by the United States.

Today, however, a more nuanced picture is emerging, which has been one of the most debated and analyzed topics in recent international relations scholarly work. There are many old and new great regional powers like China, Japan, Germany or the EU as a whole, or revanchist Russia assuming its recovery, and even India; which are gaining more influence and want to have a more decisive voice in world affairs. Most of these great powers are satisfied with the regime's rules, their share in the allocation of resources and they actually help to maintain the international system. Occasionally, though, great powers are dissatisfied, such as China or Russia today, and are not fully integrated into the dominant power's regime, but they act more against it, trying to accommodate whenever possible, while opposing to the hegemony's supremacy.

In such cases, as we are increasingly seeing in the international stage, these great powers that are dissatisfied with the status quo are constantly trying to enhance or further its sway within the international community. In theory, as Jacek Kugler emphasizes, on certain occasions a challenger to this hierarchy arises: "challengers are defined as nations that have 80% or more of the dominant country's power. China today is the strongest potential challenger to the United States. In the future India could also play this role. The EU is satisfied and thus not a

potential challenger. Dissatisfied challengers and their supporters can be the initiators of war unless economic and political means are applied to alter their course” (Kugler, 1999: 2). However, although those economic or political means the challenger can enhance and extend its sphere of influence while buying its time.

For half a century, since the end of the World War II, the Asia-Pacific order, in particular, has been built around the mutual strategic embrace of America and its Asian partners. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, international politics turned into a unipolar system. Today, the region is characterized by the US hegemonic position which is fixed with the American-led system of bilateral security arrangements and alliances based on the San Francisco accords.

However, in recent years the most powerful nation in the world has begun to feel the presence of a new influential competitor in the trans-pacific affairs. The traditional American supremacy in the region is now challenged, especially in economic terms. The recent global financial breakdown started in the US; the huge trade deficit it maintains with China and the assertive new role Beijing is playing regarding economic arrangements along the Pacific Rim could be taken as proofs of this new situation. America's shown of concern over losing its supremacy in the Asia-Pacific is signaled by its new Asia Pivot strategy and its push for a Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP); both designed to counter-balance China's moves in military as well as economic aspects, and to bring calm to Beijing's worried neighbors and US allies in the region. The two world's giants on both sides of the most dynamic ocean in terms of trade are inevitably colliding in this region. Each one of these two powers is indeed trying to guarantee a more influential position in the region, and while US remains unparalleled when it comes its military presence in Asia, the economic integration processes being carried out throughout the region give China a good terrain for increasing its clout.

On the one hand, as East Asia's economic strength keeps growing, its economies have become increasingly intertwined with that of the United States. The Americans trade more with the Asia-Pacific region than with any other region. In this context the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation forum has become “the architecture” used by Washington to facilitate a kind of relationship that would keep the US involved in Asia in a post Cold War world. The US Government has remained committed to APEC, which views as the logical focus for economic cooperation, and it has made regional trade liberalization as its ultimate goal regarding economic policies for the region, this is why the TPP has been

consistently framed within the context of APEC. More importantly, for the Americans, a regional regime such as APEC offered a forum in which China could learn multilateralism.

On the other hand, the fact is that American military power has remained as the paramount security umbrella setting deterrence and providing stability in Asia-Pacific. However, in the last decade the US uncontested leadership in the Pacific has encountered some obstacles, especially regarding the economic field, and China has a lot to do with this. As David Shambaugh explains, Beijing new confidence, its distinctive diplomatic voice and increased involvement in regional and multilateral affairs have helped China to earn praise around its neighbors, in detriment of US image. "As China's influence continues to grow, many of these countries are looking to Beijing for regional leadership or, at a minimum, are increasingly taking into account China's interest and concerns in their decision making," which has become the principal catalyst in shaping a new order in Asia and the Pacific (Shambaugh, 2004/05: 65). This new emerging order is also characterized by a changing role for the United States, because China's allure is tremendous in terms of economic gains, and partly due to the several developments occurred in East-Asia within the last two decades, especially after the Asian Financial Crisis of 1997-98, and the more recent global financial crisis.

But is really the American hegemony in the Asia-Pacific being challenged by this "re-emergence of China"? Here the notion of *hegemony* proposed by Gramsci is the one taken into consideration. This author's approach to the world is anchored firmly in Marxism. He recognized that ideas interact with material forces and that the ideal and the material are both necessary in creating hegemony and securing the structural integration of a social formation. Hegemony then involves "consensus armoured by coercion" and is materialized in a "historic bloc" that reflects a historically constituted correspondence between the economic base and its ethico-political superstructure. Cox and other neo-Gramscian scholars have transferred Gramsci's account of hegemony and the historic bloc from national states to international relations. Thus, Cox (1987) is more concerned with the nature and dynamic of 'world orders' and tend to allocate a subordinate position to most nation-states in this regard.

In pure realist terms, considering just material implications of power, many authors and even Chinese officials have agreed that for China it is still impossible to compete against the US as the world's

strongest military power. The disparities existent among China and the US make it difficult to foresee a direct power struggle in the region within the near term, and both powers realized that is not in their best interests. However, as it has been noted, in the economic field, the PRC has presented huge advancements, and this is what could mean a setback for Washington's influential position in the region. In the meantime, however, the United States remains far ahead of China in the key determinants of national power. The so called 'peace and development' strategy proposed as the main pillar for Chinese foreign policy towards the region basically has been built in accordance to this fact. It is a policy towards the US that avoids confrontation and seeks to maintain healthy economic and technical exchange, in other words, a policy of accommodation to US hegemony at least in the short run, while at the same time China is increasingly more confident to show its strength and military muscles at a more regional level, becoming more assertive in its territorial disputes with its neighbors to the East and the South China seas, and also using its huge economic clout to threat and influence other states in the region.

But the Chinese are also quite aware of China's weaknesses, and many analysts assure the PRC has neither the capability not the intention to challenge America's commanding position in the Pacific in the short term. That might be for now, while China needs the stable security umbrella provided by American hegemony to continue its path towards development; but there are indicators that Beijing is quietly preparing the ground for a future era in which Chinese international leadership takes precedence over American leadership. To begin within its backyard - namely, the Asia-Pacific region - seems to be the obvious course of action for this strategy. Will China, as a rising power, try to alter the current order by redrafting the rules in an attempt to consolidate its own regional hegemony, or will it just respect the existing situation. Basically, will it behave more as a revisionist or '*status quo*' power?

Considering the PRC's high level of involvement in regional and global organizations, so far it can be said that it has become more or less socialized in the current state of affairs within the International Community. However, China is no more hiding its dissatisfaction with the US dominated global order. "A rising, dissatisfied China presents a fundamental challenge to the international order established and preferred by the United States" (Johnston, 2003: 8), therefore the Chinese intentions on building new regional blocs as a long term strategy. The creation of new regional and global organizations led by

China, like the BRICS, the Chiang Mai Initiative, or the Shanghai Cooperation Organization; and China's constant demand for reform of global institutions like the IMF or World Bank are clear examples of the need of its aspirations as a global superpower. If the latest economic developments in the world are also taken here into consideration, empiric proofs of the partial shift in the balance of global power are indeed well founded. But although things are changing fast, at this point the PRC still follows the rules of the game and it does not seem to have an urgent intention of taking over it, considering all the responsibilities that would entail. After all, China's domestic concerns and the continuity of its economic development that gives legitimacy to the CCP are usually more pressing issues for the leadership in Beijing.

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4. Identity Discourse and China's Relations with the United States and Japan

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International relations in East Asia have long been driven and dominated by great power politics. Despite the growing significance of smaller nations and regional organizations in East Asian affairs, the great powers remain the key actors in shaping the regional security environment. Arguably, China, the United States, and Japan are the most influential powers in shaping the security dynamics and future direction of the region. Until recently, the three major powers were able to maintain relatively stable relationships despite their differences on various issues. Since 2009, however, there has been rising tension in US-China relations and Sino-Japanese relations. Meanwhile, regional flashpoints such as the territorial disputes in the South and East China Seas and the North Korean nuclear issue have become more prominent.

Some scholars have suggested that a new Cold War may be emerging in the region.¹ To consider whether a Sino-US and/or Sino-Japanese conflict is on the horizon, this paper focuses on the analysis of the national identity dimension of China's relations with the US and Japan. In particular, it considers how the national identities of these major actors are defined and constructed, and how their changing identity discourses are linked to their foreign policies and security strategies. The paper argues that whether China could have a stable and co-operative relationship with the United States and Japan will to a significant extent depend on how serious the great power identity tensions are and to what extent they may be reduced.

National Identity, Foreign Policy, and Identity Conflict

To understand the role of national identity in shaping Sino-US and Sino-Japanese relations, it is important to define the concept of identity in relation to foreign and security policy. National identity is a form of collective identity, whereby the identity of a group of people is defined and shaped by its internal cohesion and external relationship with other groups of people. Anthony Smith believes that it is "perhaps the most fundamental and inclusive" collective identity which provides "a powerful means of defining and locating individual self in the world through the prism of the collective personality and its distinctive culture."²

According to social identity theory, the identity of the "self" is intimately linked to its perception of and interaction with the "other."³ The scholarly insights into personal identity can be usefully applied to the analysis of national identity and international relations.⁴ "In a state-centric world, the substantive content of national identity is the state, which defines itself as what it is as well as what it does."⁵ National identity does not emerge naturally. Rather, it has to be forged through education and sometimes inculcation. Thus, national identity "should be understood...as an ongoing process or journey rather than a fixed set of boundaries, a relationship rather than a free-standing entity or attribute."⁶ This is particularly relevant to our analysis of the process of national identity formation in China and Japan.⁷

Why does national identity matter in foreign policy and international relations? National identity matters because it "provides a cognitive framework for shaping its [a state's] interests, preferences, world view and consequent foreign policy actions."⁸ As Alexander Wendt has rightly pointed out, "without interests identities have no motivational forces, without identities interests have no direction."⁹ A state (the self) forms its identity in relation to how it evaluates the perception of other states (the other) and their actions. As constructivists argue, change in a state's identity can cause considerable changes in its interests, which shapes national security policy. Alternatively, a state may develop interests during the process of forging or maintaining a specific identity,¹⁰ often relying on a "discourse of danger" to construct its identity, in the sense

that it needs to create a threatening “other” in order to construct a universalized “self.” The process of “othering” can be very powerful in asserting national identity, as seen in its construction in China, Japan and the United States.¹¹

The Global Financial Crisis and Changing Discourse on China’s Great Power Identity

The conception of China’s national identity is closely related to its historical legacy. As a political entity, China was established on the basis of dynasty and culture rather than the nation-state. The Asian order was essentially a Sino-centric order with China occupying a central role in a hierarchical system. But the Chinese empire began to crumble in the nineteenth century when it was challenged by Western powers and Japan. Most Chinese elites are proud of their civilization and historical pre-eminence but also shamed by the “century of national humiliation” (*bainianguochi*). Since the founding of the PRC, the primary goals of Chinese leaders have been to build a prosperous and strong (*fuqiang*) China, and to regain what they perceive as their country’s rightful place in the world. Throughout the Cold War, China’s foreign policy was seriously constrained by its strategic relations with the United States and the Soviet Union. As Gilbert Rozman observes, “A great power’s identity focuses on the country’s past, present, and future in international relations, concentrating on its capacity to project power in comparison to other countries with their own ambitions.”¹² Seen from this angle, the foreign policy and security strategy of other great powers are connected to China’s identity formation, assisting or hindering its pursuit of a great power status.¹³

Between 1989 when the Cold War ended and 2008, Chinese scholars and policy elites engaged in a rigorous debate on what path China should follow in pursuing its great power status. While many analysts were apprehensive of the security intentions of the United States and Japan, their discourse on China’s position in the international system in relation to other major powers was rather subdued. Many recommended a non-confrontational approach to handling great power relations and territorial disputes with other Asian countries. However, this identity discourse changed in 2008 when the global financial crisis seriously undermined the economic strengths of many of the dominant players in the world economy.

While the United States and other Western powers were still struggling to revive their economies in 2009, China had recovered, partly due to the introduction of a large economic stimulus package, including a four trillion yuan investment package, tax cuts, and consumer subsidies. Making its economic development less dependent on Western consumers, China grew rapidly, boosting confidence and leading to a reassessment of the global strategic environment. America’s weakened position and China’s continued rise were a clear indication of the changing global

balance of power, perhaps explaining the way China has recently handled territorial disputes in the South China Sea and East China Sea.

Many Chinese scholars and think-tank specialists have argued for the adoption of a more proactive and assertive strategy. While controversy over following Deng Xiaoping's advice on "hiding our capabilities and biding our time" (*taoguang yang hui*) has proceeded, there is agreement that China should be more active in "accomplishing something" (*you suo zuo wei*). Some argue that the trend of multipolarization (*duojihua*) has strengthened. Others go further in implying that this term is no longer the guiding principle. At the same time, the "China model" (*Zhongguomoshi*) has attracted considerable attention.¹⁴ China should take advantage of the current strategic environment (*zhanlue huanjing*) and historic opportunity (*lishijiyu*) to hasten its development as a great power, one reads. Instead of merely following the trends of "peace and development," China needs to create an environment (*moushi*) for fulfilling its great power aspirations. As the biggest winner (*yingjia*) of the financial crisis,¹⁵ some Chinese writers argue China "must not waste the opportunity that has emerged from the crisis."¹⁶ Others are critical of the American/Western economic system, which is said to be responsible for causing the global financial crisis,¹⁷ and they are more certain that the Chinese model has proven itself to be successful. The financial crisis has proved, one analyst asserts, the "failure of market fundamentalism."¹⁸

Meanwhile, more Chinese analysts have advocated that China should develop itself as a maritime power since the mid-2000s. They contend that China has no option but to become a maritime power because its trade and economic activities depend heavily on external resources. As a Chinese scholar puts it, 90 per cent of China's imported oil passes through the Strait of Malacca, which is in effect the lifeline of the country.¹⁹ If this strategic sea lane is controlled by the United States and Japan, China's economic development and national security are under serious threat. Without naval power to dominate the water adjacent to China, another Chinese scholar concurs, the future of China will be in jeopardy. According to Ni Lexiong, the experiences of the two world wars show categorically that maritime states have a distinct advantage over continental states in terms of their ability to mobilize the necessary resources in times of war. He concludes that China would suffer a miserable defeat, as Germany did, if it were to be afraid of developing its sea power.²⁰ In the words of one security analyst, "without a powerful navy China will certainly not have a great future."²¹ To some Chinese elites, especially the military analysts, the development of China as a maritime power is an important part of constructing China's great power identity. Both Presidents Hu Jintao and Xi Jinping have advocated the building of China as a maritime power in the 21st century.²² China's maritime policy is driven by what Robert Ross calls "naval nationalism," a "manifestation of 'prestige strategies' pursued by governments seeking greater domestic legitimacy."²³ The link between nationalism and

geopolitical discourse is identified by Christopher Hughes as “geopolitik nationalism.”²⁴ Indeed, the ‘dream of a powerful military’ (强军梦) is presented as a vital and inseparable part of the ‘dream of a powerful nation’ (强国梦) or the ‘China dream’ (中国梦) under the current leadership of Xi Jinping.²⁵

Perceived American decline and China’s rise have led to both official encouragement of a confident response by foreign policy analysts and intellectuals on how China should respond to the changing international environment and to an exuberant reaction from the general public. The publication of popular nationalistic books such as *Unhappy China* and *China Dream* has fuelled anti-Western and anti-American sentiments and shaped the identity discourse in the PRC.²⁶ Many argue that China is suppressed and condemned by the West despite its economic progress, and that a Sino-American confrontation is inevitable as China has been identified by the US as its rival. They advocate development of a robust Chinese military capability and adoption of a tougher policy toward Western powers. A common theme running through these books is that China must actively seek to play a more prominent political and economic role on the world stage.

This unprecedented level of confidence explains why PRC leaders felt that they were able to pursue a more assertive policy toward the United States. Much recent discourse indicates that the United States is a major hindrance to China’s efforts to achieve great power status. To many Chinese elites, America is determined to preserve its unipolar position despite a major economic crisis, the Obama administration is pursuing “hegemonic ambition” and global dominance in the name of freedom and democracy, and Washington is attempting to dominate the Asia-Pacific through the US-Japan security alliance and other bilateral security arrangements. They assert that Obama has become more proactive and assertive in shaping the Asia-Pacific security environment to serve US interests. PRC analysts are convinced that Washington is using its “pivot” to Asia or rebalancing strategy to perpetuate US dominance in the Asia-Pacific with a specific objective of containing China.²⁷

The perception of US “strategic encirclement” is widely evident, as many write that China has become the main target of America’s “offshore balance,” not believing that hegemony can be benign. Rather, they associate it with domination, control, and subjugation, using the term “hegemonism” (*baquazhuyi*) with very negative connotations to describe US policy. This is contrasted with the culture of “harmony” (*hexie*) and the Confucius concept of “benevolent rule” (*wangdao*) in Chinese foreign policy.²⁸

Many PRC writers are critical of “democratic peace theory,” which, it is argued, underpins Obama’s foreign policy. This is said to have provided the ideological justification to criticize or undermine countries whose

political systems the United States disapproves. Behind the facade of democracy promotion, Chinese contend, is the ambition of global dominance.²⁹ They argue for an alternative political system based on the Chinese conception of “good governance” (*liangzheng*), which emphasizes policy “contents” and “results” rather than the “Western preoccupation of correct procedures.” In Chinese political culture, a regime’s legitimacy is thought to derive from the “minds and hearts of the people” (*minxin*) rather than public opinion (*minyì*) associated with regular elections and multiparty politics. This type of system, one scholar maintains, is superior to the Western system.³⁰

Japan’s desire to construct the identity of a “normal nation” has been a continuous concern for Chinese policy analysts, who believe that by 2003 a consensus had been reached by political forces that Japan should take this path in quest of the status of a political power (*zhengzhidaguo*). From Japan’s perspective, to become a political power it is necessary to develop military capabilities accordingly, which is thought to be the rationale behind Japan’s active involvement in the US-led “war on terrorism” and other activities. Japan’s “UN diplomacy” is deemed to be an integral part of its attempts to reach the status of a political power and revise its pacifist constitution.

The Chinese have expressed concern that the progressives in Japan are no longer in a position to constrain the right-wingers. Most of the “new generation politicians” (*xinshengdaizhengzhijia*) are said to have strong conservative tendencies. Many advocate revision of the constitution, unafraid of putting forward their views on sensitive issues or restrained by traditional party or factional allegiance. As they have little wartime experience, say the Chinese, they do not have a guilty conscience towards other Asian countries that suffered from Japanese imperialism. This is illustrated by the growing number of incidents in recent years where Japanese politicians have attempted to justify Japan’s actions during the Second World War.³¹ Without an historical burden, they subscribe to the view that Japan should assume more responsibility in world affairs and make a full contribution to the international community.

China’s view is that the conservative tendency has become stronger in the past few years, particularly under the leadership of Abe Shinzo, who is regarded as a staunch supporter of Japan’s UN Security Council membership, revision of the Japanese Constitution, expansion of the role of the armed forces, and strengthening of the US-Japan security alliance. The prevalent view among many Chinese is that Japan’s efforts to alter its national identity in the direction of a “normal” power is tied to its militarist past, and that its desire to seek a stronger voice at regional and global levels is driven by motives similar to those in the pre-war era. They also believe that Japan is exploiting its close defence relationship with America to challenge China’s attempt to develop its great power identity.³² The emphasis on the “common values” of democracy and

freedom in Abe's foreign policy is perceived as a strategy of undermining China's moral authority. As China's economic power grows, it is argued, Japan has treated China as its major rival and has done everything it can to contain China in the region. The Abe administration, accordingly, is willing to confront China over the Diaoyu/Senkaku dispute at the cost of a reduction in Sino-Japanese trade.³³

The clash of identities between China on the one hand, and the United States and Japan, on the other, has been exacerbated over the past few years at a time when all three great powers are undergoing a process of redefining their national identities. This creates fertile soil for a divide reminiscent of the Cold War.

US National Identity and Leadership in a Liberal International Order

National identity plays an important part in underpinning America's foreign policy and security strategy. Despite differences on specific policies, successive US governments have been fully committed to such values as democracy, liberty, freedom, and the free market. All are regarded by leaders and policy elites as significant symbols of their national identity. In a long-running debate on the direction of US foreign policy, some favor an isolationist or neo-isolationist policy, arguing that America's military should be limited because the country is thought to be sufficiently secure due to its geographical location, military strength, and economic power. It is, therefore, unnecessary to define the national interest to include the protection of the security and freedom of all its friends and allies. This view is contested by others who believe that it is vitally important to play a global leadership role in order to maintain a liberal democratic international order. In their view, national interest and security can be enhanced immensely in a rule-based international system, where economic and security issues are resolved through multilateral institutions and international organizations and America promotes democracy around the world. This view draws on the theory of democratic peace, which postulates that democracies do not fight democracies. Related to this is the idea that war can be prevented by trade interaction and economic interdependence among democratic nations. Many believe that the preeminent US position in the world is best preserved by maintaining military superiority, preventing rising powers such as China from challenging US preponderance. This means supporting multilateralism while preparing to act unilaterally for the protection of American interests.

An analysis of Obama's foreign policy shows that it is influenced heavily by liberal internationalism.³⁴ As his predecessors, Obama is keen to promote democratization in the world, but given the legacy of the Bush era, he is less inclined to get involved directly in military conflicts. It is clear that Obama's conception of America's national identity is underpinned by the political values of liberalism in that it should play a leading role in promoting liberal democratic ideas and governance.³⁵

What distinguishes Obama from other US presidents is that he is more willing to involve other countries, including emerging great powers, in the exercise of American leadership. This is evidenced by the proposal of building a multi-partner world presented by Secretary of State Hillary Clinton in 2009.³⁶ Obama is also prepared to accept different paths to democracy while promoting what is central to US national identity.

Similarly, the construction of America's national identity on the basis of its political values is prevalent among US elites in the past few years. A prime example of this is the publication of a report prepared by a bipartisan task force of foreign policy and national security experts, entitled *Setting Priorities for American Leadership: A New National Security Strategy for the United States*. The report argues that America's global role should be based on the belief that "the advancement of an open, rules-based international order that promotes universal values of liberty, democracy, human dignity, and economic freedom is essential to the security and economic vitality of the United States."³⁷ According to a recent survey, the majority of respondents to the question "What does it mean to you to be an American?" emphasized freedom, including freedom of speech, movement, and religion, freedom from fear and tyranny, political freedom, and freedom to own property.³⁸ This indicates that the perception of American leaders and elites on the centrality of freedom and democracy to America's national identity is widely shared by its citizens.

It appears that Obama is seeking to maintain a liberal unipolar system or what G. John Ikenberry has called a "one-hub" international system with America at the centre. This system is based on a liberal order that is best seen as "an organizational complex in which the United States is the organisational hub."³⁹ In this sense, unipolarity is established on the basis of not only US economic and military power but an American-led open and rule-based global system, which can be joined by other great powers. This type of global leadership reflects a conception of US identity as a benign hegemon that builds a liberal international order with the cooperation of other countries. Such an international order is welcomed by many US friends and allies, including those in East Asia. Obama's "pivot" to Asia can be seen as an important step in exercising American leadership in building a liberal order in the Asia-Pacific.⁴⁰ Yet, such discourse in the past few years and its manifestation in US foreign policy have caused considerable concern in China. While China has benefited substantially from the existing international economic order, it is concerned about the political and ideological challenge of American unipolarity. Indeed, Obama's decision to fortify American relations with other democratic countries in the Asia-Pacific, such as India, Japan, South Korea, and Australia, on the basis of common values could be seen as a move to deny China's moral authority as a regional leader.

Indeed, during her first official visit to the country in February 2009, Secretary of State Clinton raised the issue of human rights with Chinese

leaders.⁴¹ China's human rights practices have been regularly criticized by American officials and in the US Department of State's annual human rights reports.⁴² By criticizing China's lack of political freedom and poor human rights record, the Obama administration is, in effect, questioning the moral basis on which China's identity as a respectable great power is constructed. Like his predecessors, the Obama administration has raised serious concerns about the implications of China's military developments and lack of transparency in its defense budget.⁴³ This can be seen as questioning the sincerity of the rhetoric of "peaceful rise" that underpins China's great power identity. The US is particularly concerned about China's recent military activities relating to its territorial disputes with other Asian countries in the South and East China Seas. While America's position on these disputes is neutral, Washington has indicated that it has treaty obligations to support regional allies such as Japan and the Philippines.

China's political system and ideology are fundamentally different from those of the United States.⁴⁴ The values that America cherishes are precisely the values that are contested by the Chinese authorities. While US identity is built on such values as freedom, democracy, and liberty and the notion of American exceptionalism, the construction of China's identity is closely associated with the revival of the Chinese nation and regime survival. The differences in their identity discourses have become much more conspicuous in the past few years. They have different conceptions of and preferences for the world order. China is increasingly assertive in articulating its conception of a future order based on Chinese civilization and philosophy. For example, the idea of building a "harmonious world" (*hexieshijie*) has been widely advocated. In constructing and spreading China's cultural values, it is suggested, Chinese socialist theory should also be integrated with traditional Chinese culture.⁴⁵ Their perception of each other's national identity is to some degree shaped by a "discourse of danger."⁴⁶ In ideological and structural terms, both the United States and China see the other side as a threatening "other." This perception has, in turn, contributed to the formation of their national identities.

A major challenge for both countries is how to manage the process and consequences of the "power transition" in the international system in an increasingly interdependent world. They are aware of the danger of treating each other as enemies. Their economies are inextricably linked and they are facing a wide range of common challenges. The United States needs China's cooperation to tackle a variety of traditional and non-conventional security issues, such as the North Korean nuclear issue, climate change, and global terrorism. They understand that to discredit the other country's national identity completely would have profound implications. The Obama administration has said that the United States welcomes the rise of a stable and prosperous China.⁴⁷ Recently, Chinese leaders have proposed the idea of establishing "a new type of great power relationship" (*xinxingdaguoguanxi*).⁴⁸ Yet, we can

discern heightened identity tension, or what Gilbert Rozman calls an “identity gap,”⁴⁹ between the United States and China. This has already led to some difficulties in managing their relations. China’s more assertive foreign policy and defense posture are undoubtedly linked to its more assertive identity discourse since 2009. Chinese analysts have often used “cold war mentality” to describe the thinking behind US policy. Washington is said to be using cold war measures to contain China.⁵⁰ Should the US-China identity tension increase, it may well lead to a new cold war in East Asia.

Japan: Constructing the National Identity of a “Normal” Global Power

Ever since the end of the Second World War, Japan has been struggling to find an identity that reflects not only its own self-identity in the light of its defeat in the war but also its changing relations with the outside world. It was not an exaggeration to say that Japan faced an identity crisis after the war. As a defeated country its national pride was seriously damaged and its room of manoeuvre limited. The rebuilding of the Japanese nation was influenced considerably by America’s political and strategic agenda. It was clear to Japanese political leaders and elites that the path toward the building of a ‘normal’ power would be turbulent. On the one hand, they had to come to terms with what had happened before the war. On the other, they needed to recover from the tragedy and rebuild their nation. In the light of all the domestic and external constraints Japan chose to follow a path of economic development, focusing on the development of Japan’s economic strength. This led to an enormously successful outcome with the Japanese economy being expanded immensely. Within a short period of time Japan was on its way toward the status of an economic superpower. This was of course due largely to a national economic strategy supported by the Japanese state. Japan’s economic developmental model was so successful that it became the role model for other newly industrializing countries in East Asia. However, throughout the years of Japan’s economic success there was a sense of uncertainty among Japanese elites about their national identity. Japan’s post-war developments led many analysts to believe that Japan had abandoned its military aspirations in favor of a national identity that is based purely on economic pursuit.⁵¹ This is, of course, at odds with the realist view that an economically powerful country would inevitably utilize its resources to develop military capabilities. That is why Kenneth Waltz refers to Japan as a “structural anomaly.”⁵² To many observers, Japan clearly opted for a pacifist national identity, developing norms of anti-militarism originated from the Yoshida doctrine. However, Japan was a close security ally of the United States, which had gradually developed its defense capability, although constrained by Article 9 of the Constitution. Japan’s defense budget was not supposed to exceed one percent of its GDP, but given the size of the economy, Japan was able to develop its military power with a budget climbing to third in the world. This is not to say that Japan harboured the furtive ambition of augmenting its military power while presenting a pacifist image to the

world. But it does reflect the intrinsic tension in Japan's post-war identity formation. Even in the Cold War era, there were voices arguing for a more active role in international affairs.

The end of the Cold War forced every country to reconsider its position in the international system. Japan, like other great powers, has been trying to advance its status in the hierarchy of the emerging structure. During the period of 1975-1990, according to Takashi Inoguchi, Japan was a systemic supporter.⁵³ But from 1990-2005 Japan, along with Germany, was said to become a global civilian power, joining in a range of activities such as peace-keeping, international rescue and relief, and economic reconstruction. As these activities were related to human security concerns, Japan was able to maintain its pacifist national identity. Since 2005, Inoguchi believes, Japan has chosen the emerging role of a global power. This signifies a transformation of identity from an economic superpower to an "ordinary power." Japan is now able to deploy its Self-Defense Forces beyond its borders in support of America's counter-terrorist activities. The momentum for constitutional revision is building, against the background of growing nationalism. Clearly, both the elites and the people are involved in a process of redefining Japan's national identity in a changing world.

The construction of the identity of a "normal" international actor is a challenging task for Japan due to the contentious interpretations of its actions in the Second World War. The problem of war memories is inseparable from Japan's efforts to construct an identity in a new era. The controversies over history textbooks, apologies for war crimes, and politicians' visits to the Yasukuni Shrine have caused considerable divisions among the Japanese and strong reactions from other East Asian countries like China and South Korea. As Stephanie Lawson and Seiko Tannaka have rightly pointed out, 'war memories are particularly powerful forces in the construction of national self-imagery and in policy legitimization'.⁵⁴ This is certainly the case for Japan.

Despite the difficulties in confronting its past, Japan has gradually augmented the scope of its contribution to regional and global security, particularly in the last decade. The expansion of Japan's security policy is explained by Bhubhindar Singh as a shift in security identity from a peace-state to an international-state.⁵⁵ Clearly, there is a direct link between Japan's security practice and its national identity. In many ways, Japan's security activities have been seriously constrained by a complex process of identity construction.⁵⁶ This is why Japanese leaders have been assiduously seeking to construct the identity of the country in such a way that would enable it to engage actively and proactively in security affairs in East Asia and beyond. As Linus Hagström has argued persuasively, "how 'Japan' is inter-subjectively constructed on a scale between 'normal' and 'abnormal' has material consequences. The importance of this discourse has to be understood both in terms of how it enables and constrains Japanese action and through the signals that it

transmits to other states about what actions are acceptable and unacceptable".⁵⁷ By declaring that "Japan is back," Abe Shinzo clearly indicates that Japan intends to play a more prominent and active role in global affairs. Under Prime Minister Abe, it is likely that Japan will take a more assertive approach to handling its relations with China.⁵⁸

With Chinese leaders and elites concerned about Japan's aspirations to become a normal power and its security implications for China and Japan's apprehensiveness about China's dismissal of Japan's right to be a political great power or to acquire a sense of being a "normal" state, the gap between the two states appears to be irreconcilable. The growing confidence in China's identity discourse in relation to its role in the international system and its relations with the United States and Japan has led to much anxiety in Japan. The Japanese fear that China will become more assertive and demanding in dealing with its Asian neighbours including Japan, as its power grows.⁵⁹ Despite China's reassurance that its rise to a great power status will be peaceful, the Japanese are unconvinced that this is the case. China's more assertive posture in its recent territorial disputes with Southeast Asian countries in the South China Sea and its dispute over the sovereignty of the Diaoyu/Senkaku islands with Japan has exacerbated Tokyo's concerns. Meanwhile, Japan's identity as an economic superpower has been challenged by China, which has overtaken it as the second largest economy in the world.⁶⁰

While Japan has normally refrained from criticizing China's domestic political system and human rights record, there has been a greater emphasis on strengthening Japan's security relations with other democratic countries in Asia. This is reflected in Abe's 'value diplomacy', which advocates a closer cooperation between Japan and other countries on the basis of their common values such as freedom, democracy and human rights. In a way, the focus of Japan's 'value diplomacy' could be construed as an indirect way of highlighting China's lack of commitments to the norms and values of the global community, thus undermining its moral authority as a great power. All this seems to indicate an emerging identity conflict between the two East Asian powers.

Conclusion

The analysis of the identity discourse of China, the US and Japan in this paper indicates that there is a growing identity tension between China and the other two East Asian powers. While this tension is rooted in their historical relations and ideological differences, it has become much more prominent in the past few years. There is ample evidence indicating that the gap between their identities has been widening following the global financial crisis. The three East Asian powers have become more critical and less tolerant of each other's national identity.

Recent events also show that some of their responses to the other's policies are a result of a re-evaluation of self-identity and the identity of their perceived rivals. This is particularly the case for China, which has emerged as a more powerful actor after the global economic crisis. The United States and Japan have both responded to Beijing's more assertive posture in an equally robust manner. Again, the reactions are based largely on an evaluation of China's changing identity as a rising power and their own national identities in the light of domestic demands and external circumstances. Since 2009, China and the United States have become increasingly critical of each other's national identity and ideology. They have also been more willing to deny the other's moral authority in the international community.

If we look at China's bilateral relations with the United States and Japan from the perspective of identity discourse, there are some early signs of an emerging cold war. If the current tension in identities continues to grow, the chances of a military confrontation will rise as a result not necessarily of strategic miscalculations, but of predispositions to perceive the other side in a more negative light. Clearly, the formation of national identity is a complicated process that is influenced by history, culture and politics. It is notoriously difficult to change a country's self-identity and its perception of the identity of other actors. States play an important role in constructing and cultivating national identity, as seen in the experience of identity formation of all three great powers. Indeed, the identity discourse in China over the past few years has to a large extent been driven by the Chinese government, although the growing influence of popular nationalism should not be ignored. Similarly, the Japanese government has been actively promoting national identity discourse that reflects its political and security agenda. As to the United States, its foreign policy is underpinned by the national identity that America should seek to play the role of a global leader on the basis of its liberal values.

The current situation reminds us of the US-Soviet rivalry in the Cold War years, when a deep ideological division existed between the two superpowers despite their efforts to improve diplomatic relations. The circumstances today are of course very different but the intensity of China's identity clash with the United States and Japan is a cause of serious concern. Some Chinese writings indicate that China is increasingly assertive in contesting the merits of the US-led international liberal order and advocating an alternative conception of the world order based on Chinese civilization and values. This is viewed as a competition for the dominant discourse (*huayuquan*) in the international community, which has long been monopolized by the West.⁶¹ Some have even declared "the end of a monolithic Western discourse."⁶² A conscious effort has been made by PRC leaders and elites to develop China's soft power and cultural influence in order to advance its global position. Meanwhile, Japan's active pursuit of a "normal power" status, combined with its

support for universal values, has resulted in an intense identity clash with China. Chinese reactions to perceived US-Japan collaboration to prevent China from achieving its national rejuvenation (*minzufuxing*) and great power aspirations may well lead to a cold war divide over national identity.

However, a military confrontation between China and the US and Japan is not inevitable. If identity is a product of social construction, it can be altered through various channels. Given that state plays a significant part in identity formation, it has a responsibility to make a positive contribution to this process. To be sure, it is not easy to change some deep-seated nationalistic sentiments and historical animosities among nations such as China and Japan. But precisely because of this, a greater effort to reduce identity tension is required. To avoid an armed conflict, the political leaders and policy elites in China, Japan and the United States must try and shape the process of their national identity construction in a positive way that would reduce the concern of their competitors. This would contribute to the de-escalation of their tensions.

It is understandable that both China and the other two East Asian powers have their national interests to safeguard. However, it is important not to allow their national identity sentiment and/or ideological position to dictate their policy toward each other. Already, some efforts of rapprochement have been made by their leaders such as the Obama-Xi Jinping meeting in America in 2013. But a lot more needs to be done. They should also be more realistic in resolving their territorial disputes rather than being dictated by their identity politics.⁶³ If peace were to be maintained in the region, the three East Asian powers have to work out a way to accommodate each other's great power aspirations and identities. No doubt, this is a formidable task facing the new leaderships in all three countries.⁶⁴ But for the sake of economic prosperity and regional security, they have to take on the challenge. China, Japan and the United States are great powers, and great powers have greater responsibilities.

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**5. Xi Jinping Facing North Korea under Kim Jong-Un:
Policy Transformation with New Assumptions**

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On Kim Jong-Un's side there would always be no lack of drama, and then soon on China's, which has been proved to be really extraordinary

and even drastically surprising in consideration of the previous general record of China's policy toward North Korea over a decade. Three months after Jang Song-Thaek's visit to Beijing in August 2012, the Chinese Communist Party held its 18th National Congress and produced a new leadership headed (soon all-powerfully) by Xi Jinping, a top-leader remarkably different from his two predecessors because of his *noblesse* Communist revolutionary family background, stronger sense of mission for the Party with stronger self-confidence, sharper strategic style reinforced by much greater risk-taking inclination, and more intensive aspiration for China's national greatness.

In the foreign policy area, an objectively welcomed major testing-ground for almost all of these came so soon after Xi Jinping's taking-over of power, from the adventurous green youngster Kim Jong-Un. What was the basic meaning of the major political events had happened up to then within North Korea throughout a year since his father's death? Among several fundamental orientations or policies of North Korea, whether dynastic dictatorship, "military first" (*Songun*), nuclear armament and longer-range missile development, or intensive hostility against ROK, and the unique posture toward China featured by dependence, hostility, and manipulation in tandem, only "military first" began to be substantially degraded by the Kim Jong-Un for both the superior power interest of the dynastic dictatorial regime and its financial requirements, which had been threatened by the rampage of the military developed during his father's years.¹¹

¹ Cf. Choe Sang-hun, "North Korea Removes Its Army Chief from All His Post," *The New York Times*, July 16, 2012. "It is likely that Ri Yong-ho was sacked while resisting the party's attempt to control the military," said Cheong Seong-chang, an analyst at Sejong Institute....Although Mr. Kim officially stuck to his father's "military-first" policy, the party's growing control of the army and the fall of Vice Marshal Ri, a hard-liner, may soften North Korea's external policy, said Mr. Lee, the analyst. *Ibid.* Of course, that softening has totally have not happened. Cf. also Choe Sang-hun, "North Korea Said to Remove Military's Lucrative Export Privilege," *The New York Times*, July 20, 2012. "The military has developed a taste for money," the Web site ("the HYPERLINK "<http://eng.nksis.com/>"North Korea Strategic Information Service Center", one of a group of Internet sites that rely on defectors and their sources within North Korea) quoted Mr. Kim (Jong-Un) as saying. "From now on, the party and the state will provide bullets and guns for the military, and the military should just focus on how best it can fight." *Ibid.* See also "N. Korea Shuts Down Military-controlled Investment Firm," *Chosun Ilbo*, August 6, 2012. "The Asahi Shimbun reported last Thursday that Kim ordered

However, the principle and practices of dynastic dictatorship (including brutal purge, court conspiracy, and highly suppressive politics) have not only been kept intact by Kim Jong-Un, but even further aggravated. This was most strongly and drastically shown by the sudden and extremely brutal execution of Uncle Jang Song-Thaek, an event regarded very plausibly by an American expert as "what seems clear....is that 'Chinese-style reform' has become increasingly unlikely for North Korea. Jang had long been seen as its number one advocate",² and also an event with its strong anti-Chinese implication which was publicly declared by Pyongyang itself and which has plunged China-DPRK relations to its perhaps lowest point in history.³

The world has found a more volatile, violent, and provocative dictator over North Korea than Kim Jong-Il, except in a degree in terms of "military first". Kim Jong-Un's regime formally incorporated in April 2012 DPRK's self-identification as a "nuclear state" into the foreword of the revised Constitution,⁴ and in the same month as mentioned above launched a satellite (which violated U.N. Security Council's sanction resolutions against North Korea and was surely in fact a testing of intercontinental ballistic missile technology), against persuasion and

the military not to meddle in efforts to attract foreign capital, and also shut down an organization known as Room 39, which managed former North Korean leader Kim Jong-il's slush funds and directed businesses earning foreign currency through 17 overseas offices and 100 trade firms under its roof." Ibid.

² Ralph A. Cossa, "North Korea Regime Change," PacNet #90, Monday, December 16, 2013.

³ "North Korea Officially Declared Charges against Jang Song-Thaek" (in Chinese), New China Network, September 9, 2013. Among those included his action of "betraying the country through selling off cheaply its valuable natural resources". Ibid. This, all the world know, refers viciously to China. Since then up to now, the Chinese party and government has never in any official occasion publicly referred to Kim Jong-Un's name, an extraordinary practice unquestionably indicated China's (and of course Xi Jinping's) angry and disdain toward him.

⁴ "North Charter Proclaims Nuke Status," JoongAng Ilbo, May 31, 2012. HYPERLINK

"<http://koreajoongangdaily.joinsmsn.com/news/article/article.aspx?aid=2953705>."

<http://koreajoongangdaily.joinsmsn.com/news/article/article.aspx?aid=2953705>."

Demanding denuclearization of North Korea is now demanding it change its constitution....It means that they don't want you to talk about it anymore." "Observers said the move was an outright rejection of several agreements to denuclearize the North has made with the international community, including the Sept. 19, 2005 agreement during the six-party talks, the Joint Declaration with South Korea in 1991, and an agreement with the U.S. in Geneva in 2000." Ibid.

warning of both China and the United States,⁵ followed by a six-month round of North Korea's extraordinarily wild sabre rattling that began with a successful launching of a long-range rocket on December 12, 2012, which was regarded as "a giant step forward in its quest to develop the technology to deliver a nuclear warhead", and reflected Kim Jong-Un's self-confidence that he could ignore the "hollow warnings" of the international community. He, as a South Korean professor on international relations commented, "couldn't care less....what the Chinese position is".⁶

Moreover, on February 12, 2013, North Korea conducted its third nuclear test, a major action as both a substantial technological step to develop nuclear armament and a diplomatic sabre rattling to retaliate a new U.N. Security Council's sanction resolution passed on three weeks ago for the first time for punishing its longer-range rocket launching. According to *Cholsun Ilbo*, one of South Korea's biggest newspaper, this nuclear test was made in despite of the summoning of DPRK ambassador and minister in Beijing three times by China's Foreign Affairs Ministry toward the end of January to strongly ask North Korea not to conduct the threatened test.⁷

Kim Jong-Un went to wildness. On one hand, his regime through its supreme organ National Defence Commission publicly condemned China

⁵ In early April, a few days before North Korea launched the long-range rocket with satellite and a little more than a month after the aborted U.S.-DPRK February 29 agreement, an U.S. team headed by Joseph DeTrani, then in charge of the National Counter Proliferation Center in the Office of the Director of National Intelligence, made a secret visit to Pyongyang for trying to persuade the regime there not to implement the launching and "encouraging the new leadership to moderate its foreign policy". "I was initially guardedly optimistic that [Kim Jong Un] was moving in the right direction," DeTrani said later. "With the launches and the test, he's reversed that." Ken Dilanian and Barbara Demick, "Secret U.S.-North Korea Diplomatic Trips Reported," Los Angeles Times, February 23, 2013.

⁶ Calum MacLeod, "North Korea Experts See Repercussions in Rocket's Success," USA Today, December 12, 2012. "This time, just like previous times, all international pressure on North Korea, including Chinese, is ineffective. They are themselves, and they love their rocket, missile and nuclear programs," said this author in a telephone interview. Ibid.

⁷ "South Korean Media Said that China Summoned North Korean Diplomatic Envoys Three Times but Failed to Dissuaded Nuclear Test" (in Chinese), Sina.com.cn, February 8, 2013. HYPERLINK
"<http://news.sina.com.cn/w/sd/2013-02-08/121826240284.shtml>."
<http://news.sina.com.cn/w/sd/2013-02-08/121826240284.shtml>. The DPRK ambassador was said to retort during the summoning that "Conducting nuclear test is North Korea's independent right, against which China have no right to interfere." Ibid.

(though without calling name) "submitted to the peremptoriness and might of the United States, confounded to the degree of abandoning the minimum principle",⁸ and, according to Reuters, formally informed China that it would within the year conduct one or two nuclear tests and launch again long-range missile flying over Japan.⁹ On the other, the Supreme Command of the North Korea's armed forces declared on March 5, 2013 that the Korean Armistice would become "completely null and void" within a week, and one month later its General Staff "formally declared to the White House" that "the final preparation of the revolutionary warfare has been completed", among which including "very advanced means of nuclear strike for destructing ruthlessly American hostile policy toward North Korea".¹⁰ While, DPRK's Foreign Affairs Ministry "suggested" foreign embassies and international institutions in Pyongyang to consider their withdrawal from North Korea because "at the present the issue is not whether there will be a war outbreak in the Peninsular, but when this war will erupt."¹¹ About the same time, Kim Jong-Un even signed operation plan of "attacking Continental U.S. and the bases of American aggressive forces as Hawaii and Guam, etc.", while North Korea's longer-range missiles was reported to having moved to a launching position targeting on Guam.¹²

"This is one of the most dangerous moments since 1953," *Los Angeles Times* quoted this author then with an assessment of the Peninsular

⁸ "North Korea Swore to Conduct Nuclear Test, Saying Some Major Power just Like Puppet, Confounded to Abandon Principle" (in Chinese), news.ifeng.com, January 25, 2013.

http://news.ifeng.com/world/detail_2013_01/25/21599250_0.shtml.

⁹ "Foreign Media Reported that North Korea Had Formally Informed China the Forthcoming One or Two Nuclear Tests and Missile Launching This Year" (in Chinese), new ifeng.com, February 16, 2013.

http://news.ifeng.com/world/special/chaoxiansanheshi/content-3/detail_2013_02/16/22159257_0.shtml.

¹⁰ "North Korea's Military Declared Non-recognition of the Korean Armistice since March 11" (in Chinese), People.com, March 5, 2013. HYPERLINK

"<http://politics.people.com.cn/n/2013/0306/c70731-20688438.html>."

<http://politics.people.com.cn/n/2013/0306/c70731-20688438.html>. "North Korea Formally Informed the U.S. That It Had Been Ready for the Final Fight" (in Chinese), Yonhap News, April 4, 2013.

<http://chinese.yonhapnews.co.kr/international/2013/04/04/030100000ACK20130404000600881.HTML>.

¹¹ "DPRK Foreign Affairs Ministry Suggested Foreign Embassies to Withdraw" (in Chinese), Xinhua News Agency, April 5, 2013.

http://news.xinhuanet.com/video/2013-04/07/c_124546516.htm.

¹² "North Korea Moved Missiles to East Sea and Targeted against Guam" (in Chinese), JoongAng Ilbo, April 5, 2013.

http://chinese.joins.com/gb/article.do?art_id=102091&method=detail.

situation held at large by most of the observers.¹³ Peace, China's perennial No.1 vital interest about the Peninsular had been severely threatened, a situation the new Chinese top leader Xi Jinping could not tolerate. All compatible with his inner belief, sense of national honour, political personality, and strategic style, Xi launched a policy determinedly toward North Korea's dangerous and hostile behaviour, which made one remember Deng Xiaoping as to guts, resolution, and directness.

Dramatic policy transformation was on the way. On January 23, 2013, with China's final agreement negotiated over about one month, the U.N. Security Council passed its extraordinary third sanction resolution against North Korea, the first one punishing the latter's longer-range rocket (missile) launching rather than nuclear test. In some sense, this is a revolution of China's pattern of behaviour in the Security Council about North Korea, what contributing to that was also Xi's hope for a closer relationship with the United States in general and his requirement in particular in the extraordinary intensive confrontation with Japan over Diaoyu Isles.¹⁴

Soon, shortly after North Korea's third nuclear test and a series of other sabre rattling, South Korean media found something they never found previously: China's unilateral or national sanction against North Korea, along with China's participation in the U.N. collective sanctions already over years since 2006. China "has not only (severely) restricted ordinary shipping to North Korea, but also suspended some projects of infrastructure building relating to North Korea," along with suspension of some import of its fishing products, all of which was not required by the

¹³ Jung-yoon Choi, "North Korea Analysis: 'One of the Most Dangerous Moments,'" Los Angeles Times, April 2, 2013.

¹⁴ As to the latter cause, Agence France-Presse quoted this author as follows : Mr Shi said China's backing for the resolution - it has a veto at the Security Council - was a signal it wants closer ties to Washington as it seeks a rapprochement amid a simmering territorial row with Japan. Last week the US secretary of state, Hillary Clinton, issued a veiled warning to Beijing not to challenge Japan's control of the East China Sea islands that Tokyo calls Senkaku, but which are known as Diaoyu in China. "China wants to show a major concession to the US over North Korea, to influence US actions with regards to Sino-Japanese confrontation," Mr Shi said. "Otherwise you cannot explain why China suddenly changed its previous behaviour. It wants to influence the American position over Diaoyu." "China urges patience as North Korea threatens US with third nuclear test", Agence France-Presse, January 25, 2013.

Security Council sanction resolutions.¹⁵ This is really another revolution happened in China policy toward North Korea, one had never happened until then since 2003 and therefore the febleness and ineffectiveness of Beijing's dealing with Pyongyang over the past decade.

What is even more significant and having more "lethality" is that in one strike China strictly prohibited all the illegal banking activities in China of all North Korean banks, among them perhaps only one had been listed in the U.N. Security Council's sanction resolutions. And soon after that it was reported that all major Chinese state banks had perhaps suspended banking transaction with North Korea's Foreign Trade Bank.¹⁶ On April 6, obviously under President Xi's personal instruction and probably in his very words, China's Foreign Affairs Minister Wang Yi declared on the Peninsular situation that China did not permit anyone "make disturbance at China's doorstep".¹⁷ This of course should be understood as primarily a blunt warning to Kim Jong-Un. In one's memory, there has never been until then China's public warning against North Korea in this way.

Revolution in China's Korean policy was stunning, to the arrogant and wild youngster Kim Jong-Un. Along with firm deterrence from the United States and ROK, China's harsh words and extraordinarily hard "physical pressure" almost suddenly made him bow his head in submission, though reluctantly and partially. On May 22, 2013, shortly after announcement by Beijing and Washington that President Xi and President Obama would meet each other in California, Vice Marshall Choe Ryong Hae, then second to none under Kim Jong-Un in North Korean military, was sent to Beijing as Kim's envoy. He paid now restored lip-service to China-DPRK friendship, showing apparent respect

¹⁵ "North Korea Began to meet China's Unilateral Sanctions," DWnews, March 12, 2013. <http://global.dwnews.com/big5/news/2013-03-12/59154947.html>.

¹⁶ 31 "China Strictly Prohibits North Korean Banks' Illegal Banking Activities in China" (in Chinese), Yonhap News, March 19, 2013. HYPERLINK "http://chinese.yonhapnews.co.kr/n_international/2013/03/19/8000000000ACK20130319002300881.HTML." http://chinese.yonhapnews.co.kr/n_international/2013/03/19/8000000000ACK20130319002300881.HTML.

"China's Four Major Banks May Have Suspended Transactions with North Korea's Foreign Trade Bank" (in Chinese), Yonhap News, May 10, 2013. http://chinese.yonhapnews.co.kr/n_international/2013/05/10/8000000000ACK20130510002300881.HTML.

¹⁷ "Wang Yi Talks about Korean Situation, Making Disturbance at China's Doorstep Not Permitted" (in Chinese), China News, April 6, 2013, <http://www.chinanews.com/gj/2013/04-06/4705490.shtml>.

to China that was abandoned totally in the past six months, while refused to commit in any degree to denuclearization of his country. After a few days of uncertainties and observers' speculation, President Xi personally received him. The fact that Xi gave a personal audience to Kim's envoy was something of a surprise given months of North Korean snubs toward China.

However, this is anyway Kim's bowing head, under China harsh warning and hard sanction. Moreover, China's triumph, which almost consistently lacked in the past decade with a sort of appeasing policy, was more in substance in terms of peace and peninsular stability: Since then, there has been as yet no North Korean nuclear long-range missile test, and no major military sabre rattling on the part of Pyongyang. North Korea under Kim Jong-Un is still nuclear armed, refusing to discuss its own denuclearization, keeping its strong hostility toward ROK, and unreformed in both domestic and foreign policy. But it has been at least temporarily tamed in the above aspects, tamed due to perhaps first of all Xi Jinping's new policy posture. Moreover, Xi would surely much value it as a major positive experience that must be very significant, significant to the future of China's policy toward North Korea.

Ongoing Limitation with New Assumptions:

China Facing North Korea in the Predictable Future

There is no breaking revolution of China's policy toward North Korea, even a North Korea under Kim Jong-Un, whose hostility toward China and violent political feature has proved even much worse than his father. As always previously, China's Korean policy is primarily conditioned by Pyongyang's behaviour, and Kim Jong-Un's tactic turning in the sense of improving his apparent attitude toward China and suspending his wild threat to peace, which happened roughly at the same time of Choe Ryong Hae's visit to Beijing, was sufficient to make China's posture changed again, in a somewhat reversed direction. Though North Korea still much stucked to its nuclear and longer-range missile program and refused any negotiation with its commitment to denuclearization as precondition or even final purpose, Xi Jinping still sent Vice President Li Yuanchao to Pyongyang in late July, 2013 to urge Kim Jong-Un rejoin the Six-Party Talks, denuclearize, and commit to peace ("The message was one North Korea's state-run media refused to pass on to their own people"), and to hear from him much rhetoric about China-DPRK friendship, even giving

him a hug "in a sign of just how repaired the relations are".¹⁸ Moreover, the inertia of traditional policy or discourse is still strong in China's unchangeable repeat of its appeal over so many years to reopening (unconditionally) of the Six-Party Talks, in despite of the fact shown again and again that "the Six-Party Talks have already run their course....North Korea will not take part in Six-Party Talks that presuppose denuclearization" as their primary and original No.1 purpose.¹⁹

More profoundly, China still has a vital interest perceived by so many in keeping, at least in a minimum form, its historically and geographically shaped "strategic relationship" with DPRK in the complicated and far from benign regional security environment in which China has had a much growing China-U.S. strategic rivalry, an intensive confrontation with Japan, and still complicated political relationships respectively with ROK and Taiwan area. China at least prefers not to have a very hostile DPRK at its border. Though seemingly less than previous times, Beijing still would like to prevent the denuclearization process too seriously damaging relations with Pyongyang through too much alienation from the regime there. Moreover, China still concerns with the possible collapse or severe disability of the Pyongyang regime and the ensuing chaos, resulted partly from perceivable great pressure from China. This would force China to deal with a number of dangerous and complex strategic/diplomatic/refugee problems. In summary, to Beijing, the best solution is peaceful denuclearization in such a way as to avoid losing its relationship with the DPRK or creating a chaotic neighbour across the Yalu, though how to realize this is a very different question.²⁰

So, there will be no breaking revolution of China's policy toward North Korea in the predictable future. However, after the above-mentioned

¹⁸ "Chinese VP Meets with, Hugs Kim Jong-Un," Shanghaiist, July 27, 2013.

HYPERLINK

"http://shanghaiist.com/2013/07/27/chinese_vp_meets_with_kim_jong_un.php.

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http://apdforum.com/en_GB/article/rmiap/articles/online/features/2013/08/13/china-korea-nukes.

¹⁹ Seong Yeon-cheol, "Chinese Professor Says Six Party Talks on NK

Denuclearization Have Run Their Course," The Hankyoreh, February 20, 2013.

http://www.hani.co.kr/arti/english_edition/e_northkorea/574744.html.

²⁰ Cf. Shi Yinhong, "China and the North Korea Issue: Competing Interests and Persistent Policy Dilemmas," The Korean Journal of Defense Analysis, V. 21, No. 1 (March 2009), pp. 34-35.

dramatic policy transformation under the leadership of Xi Jinping, especially in the first half of 2013, the possibility that Beijing might return to the "old track" in its Korean policy will surely be quite small. Rather, the Chinese government will probably keep a large (or even the larger) part of the newly established hard measures against North Korea unless Pyongyang regime would substantially reform its general foreign policy in a positive direction--a prospect no one in the world at the present could realistically expect. Moreover, as noted before, the brutal execution of Jang Song-Thaek its strong anti-Chinese implication has much further damaged China-DPRK relations, plunging them to a very chilly state. In these context, besides the quite positive feedback (and therefore the potential reinforcing effect) Xi Jinping's blunt pressure on Pyongyang has brought to China's Korean policy,²¹ Beijing's much tougher stance can be expected to last quite long in its essence.

This prospect is primarily based on a paramount fact, a rapidly developing one: China's Korean policy now has some new assumptions emerged from intensive policy practices under the leadership of Xi Jinping, with the benefits of keen learning from the past painful lessons of China's dealing with North Korea. These new assumptions still need further consolidation, in consideration of their new-born status and the lasting residue influence of what are opposite to them among bureaucrats, academicians, and public, let alone the "interference" by the dynamic (sometimes even volatile) situation which might impose some partial reverse as what is indicated in the beginning of this section, but they are already there to dominate the current mainstream of policies backed by the paramount authority of Xi Jinping himself.

The first new assumption is that, along with prohibiting severe and imminent threat raised by North Korea to the fundamental peace in the Peninsular and beyond, as what Kim Jong-Un did during the first half of 2013 and his father did in attacking a South Korean Yeonpyeong island on November 23, 2010,²² North Korea's general attitude toward China should be the No.1 determinant in deciding China's posture and policies

²¹ See the last paragraph of the last section "Drastic Policy Transformation: China Facing North Korea with Xi Jinping Addressing Kim Jong-Un".

²² That attack by firing dozens of shells killed two South Korean soldiers and setting off an exchange of fire "in one of the most serious clashes between the two sides in decades." Quoted from Mark McDonald, "'Crisis Status' in South Korea After North Shells Island," *The New York Times*, November 23, 2010. As to China's response to the event and the related complications in China-U.S. and China-DPRK relations, Cf. Shi Yinhong, "New Games in Tightly Fixed Structures: North Korea's Volatile Desperation and China's Cornered Strategy," *The Korean Journal of Defense Analysis*, Vol. 23, No. 3 (September 2011), pp. 361-362.

toward it. One can convince that China's general posture toward North Korea under Xi Jinping's leadership has been decided according to this new assumption, which is compatible with what this author advocated emphatically in mid-2009: "Some previous (Chinese) practice in dealing with North Korea's actions damaging East Asian stability should be changed...China's assistance and leniency alone are unable to bring about in exchange North Korea's amicability to China"; "Generally speaking, in deciding China's attitude and policy toward any country, the primary element or at least one of the major considerations should be latter's attitude toward China, while China's policy toward it should aim at, among other purposes, its adopting a sort of attitude compatible with China's fundamental interest and dignity. To this common sense rule in international relations, North Korea should not be an exception."²³ In fact, this is the essence of what "China-DPRK relations is normal ones between states" means, and it is going to be realized at large under Xi Jinping's leadership.

The second new assumption similarly emerging under Xi Jinping is still to be consolidated but has been increasingly establishing since Madam Park Geun-hye, who "got the most media coverage in China" and was liked by the Chinese people during the South Korean presidential campaign,²⁴ was elected in late December 2012. This new assumption is: China's efforts at "parallel friendship" with both Koreas since the establishment of diplomatic relations with South Korea under Deng Xiaoping in 1992 should become tilting toward Seoul rather than Pyongyang. In fact, this long overdue assumption has been imposed upon China by North Korea itself, through more than a decade's off-rampant hostility, humiliation, and actions damaging China's major interests and honour. With South Korea, China has not only actively developed economic relations (it has already become the ROK's biggest trade partner), but also tried to control with occasional political tensions and endeavored to mitigate controversies over history and a few small territorial disputes. Moreover, China in recent years has actively promoted political relations with the ROK, including the May 2008 elevation of bilateral relations to "a partnership of strategic cooperation."²⁵ All of these has been in general responded positively by the ROK government, with its more than occasional initiatives.

²³ Shi Yinhong, "How should China Deal with North Korea?" (in Chinese), *China Newsweek*, June 24, 2009.

²⁴ Sunny Lee, "New Policy Needed for Beijing," *The Korea Times*, December 24, 2012.

²⁵ Shi Yinhong, "China and the North Korea Issue: Competing Interests and Persistent Policy Dilemmas," p. 44.

Now under Administrations of Xi Jinping and Park Geun-hye with quite successful summits between them, China-ROK relations have undoubtedly entered into their best period in history. The ROK-U.S. military alliance has been regarded by many in both China and South Korea as a major obstacle to the development of a much better long-term relationship, but without much evidence and real plausibility. Generally speaking, that military alliance in fact has no longer damage (at least directly) the fundamental relations between Beijing and Seoul, and no doubt the ROK government will not likely in any predictable future to permit it to target against China.²⁶ In short, the basic difficulty of China-DPRK relations and the essential advantage for China-ROK ones are both structural, and Beijing's tilting toward Seoul and alienation from Pyongyang will continue without its "abandonment of North Korea".

The third new assumption of China's policy under Xi Jinping toward North Korea is more firmness and emphasis on the denuclearization of that country. Accompanying with Pyongyang's step-by-step progress in possessing nuclear armed capability and round-after-round strategic tensions with diplomatic headaches brought about by its nuclear and longer-missile tests, all has directly or indirectly damaged China's strategic security and international prestige, Beijing's sense of the involvement of China's vital interests in the denuclearization of North Korea²⁷ has become keener to a degree that the repeatedly declared commitment to that by the government under Xi's leadership has had a tune remarkably more convincing and serious than ever before. Though as previously "China will not break ties with North Korea just because of the nuclear issue,"²⁸ but its commitment to denuclearization of that country has become unreserved in words²⁹ and deeds, deeds in the nature of above-mentioned extraordinary sanctions taken both in and

²⁶ It should be noted in this connection that no one in the world has referred to ROK-U.S. military alliance seriously whenever the U.S. strategic "re-balance" with its China theme is discussed.

²⁷ Cf. Shi Yinhong, "How to Understand and Treat the Nuclear Crisis of DPRK" (in Chinese), Takunpao, January 12, 2003. This is the first publicized voice from a Chinese observer to point out and emphasize China's vital interests in the denuclearization of North Korea, and even more importantly, to advocate employing China's economic leverage when necessary to oppose against Pyongyang's nuclear program.

²⁸ Quoted from this author, in Bill Smith, "Consequences of A Nuclear Test," Oman Daily Observer, February 13, 2013.

²⁹ For example, Xi Jinping himself told Kim's envoy Choe Ryong Hae in late May 2013 that "China's position is very clear: However the situation changes, all concerned parties must insist on the objective of denuclearization of the Korean Peninsular". "Xi Jinping Received Kim Jong-Un's Envoy", Xinhuanet, May 24, 2013. http://www.hb.xinhuanet.com/2013-05/25/c_115907289.htm.

outside the framework of the United Nations. The pursuit of a "new typed great power relationship" with the U.S. boosted further that posture, as the limited fruits of Xi-Obama summit held at Sunnyland, California demonstrated.³⁰

The fourth new assumption needs hardly to be pointed out again, after having been already noted and emphasized so much in this article. That is: when necessary, China must employ its substantial economic leverage against North Korea's provocative and dangerous behaviour, a leverage so often the only effective means to deal with it. In fact, this is the primary painful lesson Beijing finally learnt after so many frustrations over a decade, a too long learning process until Xi Jinping taking over the bridle of policy-making. What still required here is to make its novelty more prominent through quoting a related faulty prediction made by a first-rate expert on China's policy toward North Korea, made as late as in mid-February 2013: "North Korea's leaders are betting that China needs them more than they need the Chinese...They hold their nose and continue to support North Korea from a strategic position despite eroding public and elite support for that approach".³¹ Experts used to be with largely constant "appeasing" and "eating humble pie" pattern of Beijing's behaviour toward Pyongyang, and they need Xi to remind them that everything could be changed in this world, sometimes drastically. This half-sentence, a common-sense human experience, can be taken as an appropriate concluding note for the present exploration of China facing North Korea over the past decade. It can be a ray of guiding light for the future, however ambiguous and abstract it seems to be.

³⁰ "American officials came away from the Obama-Xi summit believing that China is ready to work more closely with the United States on North Korea than it has in the past....White House national security adviser Tom Donilon told reporters that Obama and Xi 'agreed that North Korea has to denuclearize, that neither country will accept North Korea as a nuclear-armed state and that we would work together to deepen cooperation and dialogue to achieve denuclearization.' Chinese State Councillor Yang Jiechi told a separate news conference that Xi had told Obama that China and the United States were 'the same in their positions and objectives' on the North Korean nuclear issue." "Obama and Xi Agree on North Korea, Discuss Cybersecurity at Summit," Reuters, June 9, 2013.

³¹ David Pierson and Ken Dilanian, "North Korea Nuclear Test Irks Ally China," *Los Angeles Times*, February 12, 2013. This sort of prediction then was definitely not exceptional: "China is frustrated by its lack of influence with North Korea, but....he (another quite experienced observer) doesn't expect the new leadership to fundamentally change its support for Pyongyang. However, Beijing might agree to more stringent sanctions to show North Korea it can get tough, he said." *Ibid.*

6. SOUTH KOREAN PERSPECTIVE ON CHINA

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Introduction:

President Park Guen-hye has completed one year in office on 25th February, 2014. Upon taking office, the Park administration outlined her foreign policy in 3 forms. A) **'Trust building'** process on Korean peninsula-a response to North Korean provocations. B) The **'Northeast Asia Peace and Cooperation Initiative' (NAPCI)**-envisagesto develop cordial bilateral and multilateral relations with the nations concerned. C) **'Middle power diplomacy'**-aims to build upon South Korea's middle power status to engage in important international issues. South Korea dreams of playing a global role in the region, contributing to global peace, improvement of human rights, strengthening cooperation with the rest of the world on global security and economic issues. With the change in global order, the most crucial task till date is to bring its economic partner-China and its sole security guarantor-the United States on same page.

As far as trust-building and NAPCI are concerned, it garnered support from the two giants-the United States and China. Park administration was successful in re-opening of the Kaesong Industrial Complex, family re-unions, and the Najin-Hasan Railway. But, there are many issues where the two super powers are weary of each other. However, President Park has advocated the importance of a trilateral cooperation between South Korea, the United States and China. The United States seems to think that the Park administration is moving closer to China. Whereas, China believes that in-spite of maintaining amicable relationship for

economic benefit, South Korea will definitely give priority to US. Thus, it will become very difficult for Korea to find a strategic balance between the two countries. Similarly, when it comes to opt between North Korea and South Korea, China will prioritize North Korea. Given North Korea's strategic value as a 'Cordon Sanitaire' Beijing's primary objective will be the survival of its backward and fragile regime, over which China can consolidate its unique and dominant influence.

Since taking charge as President, her first overseas visit was understandably to the United States. She gave a surprise to the world by opting China as her second destination, which proves the level of importance the administration attaches in building amicable relations with China unlike her predecessor. Here it is worth mentioning that she skipped Japan. Her choice seems to reflect growing South Korean resentment of Japan, where the Abe government denies Japan's war crimes and the Japanese right seems bent on reviving Japanese militarism.

To what extent the Park administration is successful in managing the 3 outlined policies will be studied in the following sections along with the scope of a trilateral cooperation and its limitations.

Summit Meetings 2013-2014

The diplomatic relations between South Korea and China were established in 1992. Since then, the bilateral ties have undergone positive and upward development. Xi's Seoul tour could be seen as reciprocation for President Park's state visit to China in June 2013. Park's China trip last year put an end to Seoul's annual diplomatic routine of visiting Tokyo ahead of Beijing. The two heads of state held talks in Beijing, and pledged to boost cooperation and issued a joint statement along with an action plan to enhance their Strategic Partnership. During the visit, the Mandarin-fluent Park said while speaking at Tsinghua University on June 29, 2013, "During my most difficult time, it was China's famous scholar Feng Youlan's History of Chinese Philosophy that served as the beacon of my life and helped me regain my inner calm." The reason of choosing to deliver the speech at Tsinghua is because; the university is President Xi's alma mater. It proves the importance South Korea attaches with China. Park also visited Xi'an, where, in addition to many South Korean enterprises already operating, a massive \$7 billion Samsung Electronics plant is under construction - the single biggest investment in China by a South Korean firm⁽¹⁾

China is now South Korea's largest trading partner, largest market for exports, largest source of imports, and largest destination for overseas investment. South Korea, in turn, was China's third-largest trading partner and fifth-largest source of foreign investment in 2013. Statistics from China's General Administration of Customs show that China's two-way trade with South Korea totalled \$274.25 billion last year, indicating an annual increase of 7 percent. The figure is more than the combined trade volume of South Korea with the United States and Japan.

Graphical representation of Trade Volume between South Korea and:

(2)*KORUS FTA Trade Figures-US Korea Connect
*China's General Administration of Custom
*KITA

The FTA negotiation is said to be one of the major negotiations this year which will determine whether bilateral trade will reach the promised \$300 billion next year. The FTA, when finalized, is expected to help the two countries improve the mutual complementarities of their markets and strengthen the foundation for regional economic integration. China, Japan and South Korea had agreed to set up a trilateral FTA, but due to certain issues—mainly concerning Japan—the trilateral FTA came to a deadlock.

Regional Security:

The below mentioned chart will help in understanding the complexities in the relations between China, South Korea, North Korea, Japan and the United States in ensuring the regional security.

During Xi Jinping's visit to Seoul, the two leaders carved out the importance of maintaining peace in the Korean Peninsula, facilitating the resumption of six-party talks. As Beijing and Seoul draw closer, Pyongyang became more active in negotiations with Tokyo over the issue of its past abductions of Japanese nationals. The two sides had a

meeting in Beijing on July 1. On July 3, Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe announced that Japan would partially lift its sanctions imposed on Pyongyang.

China and South Korea are two major victims of Japan's war crimes. The commonly shared history brought them together against a common enemy-Japan. Apart from the issue pertaining to history, island claims by Japan-Senkaku/Diayou and Dokdo irks both China and South Korea. Dokdo issue is one of the most crucial matter involving the South Korea and Japan. Due to the rightward shift in Japanese politics, its attitude toward its war past has drawn severe criticism from both the countries. Most recently, despite pronounced international concern, Abe has gutted Japan's pacifist Constitution in order to allow Japanese forces to fight abroad. Given Abe's unrepentant historical attitude, the move poses a grave menace to regional stability. During their meeting, Xi and Park expressed worries about Japan's continued historical revisionism and its attempt to expand the right to self-defence. Korea-Japan relations deteriorated even further following Prime Minister Shinzo Abe's visit on December 26, 2013 to the Yasukuni Shrine. The visit set off a tidal wave of indignation in South Korea and China. President Park and Mr. Abe came into their respective offices at nearly same time, and the relationship immediately got off on the wrong foot. President Park holds a deep mistrust of her Japanese counterpart, and declared that a summit would not take place unless there were fresh apologies for Japan's past atrocities. China's announcement of ADIZ also drew international concern and criticism.

The role of United States in the affairs of Northeast Asia dates back to World War-II time. It constructed the post-war regional order and has been largely content since then to view the matter settled, even though issues of territory, compensation, and historical justice were left unresolved. Now it ensures security in the region by conducting Joint Military drills with South Korea which irks China, concerned about North Korean nuclear programmes and tries to sort impending issues between Japan and South Korea. The best solution would be to leave the affairs of Northeast Asian nations in to the hands of nations concerned.

Korean Perspective on China, Japan and the United States:

For convenience and clearer understanding, the section has been divided into different sub-headings- The views are based on the public poll conducted by the Asan Institute for Policy Studies ⁽³⁾.

- A. **China-** Xi's affirmation of China's position on the denuclearization of the Korean peninsula was a disappointment. The Summit did not bring what Koreans wished for. According to the survey, Korean public demonstrate that it will not lean toward China unless there is a meaningful step forward by China on North Korea's nuclear program. The data also suggests that warm South Korea-China ties may not necessarily translate into substantial security cooperation, as China's reluctance to condemn North Korea's sinking of the South Korean corvette, Cheonan, and shelling of Yeonpyeong Island in 2010 are not too distant memories for South Koreans. Although political and economic ties between the two are warm, but the decision maker in Seoul must remain cognizant of Beijing's strategic goals in the region that are inherently antithetical to South Korea's security interests. China has approached Korea about working together to address shared historical grievances with Japan. This is a smart move by China as many Koreans support the idea of cooperation with China on these issues. This could be damaging for the United States.
- B. **Japan-** Despite the negative views for the country and of Prime Minister Abe, the Korean public is not opposed to the idea of improving relations. The most obvious sign of improving relations would be a summit between the respective leaders. Another would be the enactment of GSOMIA (General Security of Military Information Agreement). All parties involved agree that passing GSOMIA would serve as a platform to enhance security of both Korea and Japan. The agreement was nearly signed under President Lee Myung-Bak, but was withdrawn due to public backlash. The Japanese government should clearly understand that the dispute over Dokdo is the single most important issue to the Korean public. It is the United States that is most frustrated by the turmoil in Northeast Asia.
- C. **The United States-** Public polls conducted from March 2014 indicate that 70.4% of South Koreans state that Korea should strengthen the alliance with the United States to check China. At the same time, there is a negative perception about United States in Korea because it strongly backed Japan's efforts to expand its collected Self Defence Forces and it could not do much about Abe's visit to Yasukuni Shrine.
- China's rise puts South Korea in a strategic dilemma between the United States and China. Due to China's consistent rise, market growth, and size, however, South Korea is increasingly dependent

on China's economy. Consequently, South Korea has to dually manage its security, which is grounded in the ROK-U.S. alliance, and its economic well-being, which is dependent on the ROK-China strategic cooperative partnership. The South Korean public tends to favour the diplomatic strategy of managing both bilateral relationships harmoniously. However, sustaining friendly relations with both powers has proven difficult. Former presidents Roh Moon-hyun and Lee Myung-bak struggled to manage these two bilateral relationships and failed in their search for an ideal balance. The world is looking at President Park on her balancing policy. (4)

Limitations to Sino-Korean relations:

- A) The North-East Project:** Launched in 2002, the project is run by the Chinese Academy of Social Sciences (CASS) aims to confirm that northeastern China including early Korean kingdoms, has always been under the Middle Kingdom's control. China claims Koguryo-one of the ancient Three Kingdoms of Korea as its part. The project met fierce resistance from Korea. Beijing applied to the UNESCO to register Koguryo tombs in Chinese Manchuria as a World Heritage Site by conspicuously scrubbing its website of references to pre-modern Korean history. In the face of strong protests from the Korean government and civic groups, Beijing decided to back off from its claims. However, China has continued on with the project. While the Northeast Project appears to be a pretext for expanding China's borders, academics say "China isn't making the claims just for historical reasons but for political reasons to claim dominion over North Korea in case of a changing political situation in the region," says Prof. Song Ki-ho of Seoul National University.(5)
- B) South Korea-US cooperation:** China's efforts to stifle South Korea's cooperation with the US- which is the sole security guarantor of the latter for over 60 years highlight the limits of the South Korea-China relationship. For example: in response to US-ROK joint military drills intended to increase deterrence against North Korea. Furthermore, at a speech during a dinner ahead of the fourth Conference on Interaction and Confidence Building Measures in Asia (CICA) summit, in Shanghai May 20, 2014, President Xi warned against the strengthening of alliances in the region, and while he did not mention the US, but it was clear that he was in part referring to U.S. efforts to improve trilateral cooperation with Japan and South Korea. He said, "To beef up and

entrench a military alliance targeted at a third party is not conducive to maintaining common security.” (6)

- C) China’s Air Defence Identification Zone:**The leaders of Korea and China have come to an agreement on certain crucial issues as evidenced by the joint statement issued in June 2013. However, despite the talks, Park administration could neither prevent nor mediate the surprise expansion of China’s Air Defence Identification Zone (ADIZ). Similar limitation arose with regard to North Korean nuclear issues, which are the key items on the security agendas between the two countries.
- D)** The sinking of the Cheonan and the Yeonpyeong Island bombardment in 2010-Chinese reluctance.

Analyzing the possibilities of a Trilateral-US-China-South Korea Cooperation:

Recently concluded sixth joint meeting of the U.S.-China Strategic and Economic Dialogue (S&ED) in Beijing from July 8-10 hold great significance. The US desperately needs Chinese help to dampen North Korean ambitions, particularly when it comes to their missile and nuclear programmes. The U.S. watched with some satisfaction when Xi visited Seoul. Similarly, the US needs Chinese cooperation in the UN Security Council, in climate change negotiations, as also with regard to Syria, Iraq and Iran’s nuclear file (P5+1 Talks). Last year about one and a half million Chinese tourists visited the US, and, according to a report by the National Association of Realtors (NAR), the Chinese are the largest foreign buyers of US real estate, spending nearly US \$ 22 billion. (7)

The question for America is whether it is prepared to share power with China? It is clear from the inputs provided that the United States wishes to bring China to a similar platform, but is the requirement mutual? Does China require the help of the United States in bringing global change or in maintaining regional security? To an extent, the answer is yes, but, not at the cost of its sphere of influence. Being a political spectator it seems that the major objective of this charm offensive has been to upgrade the Sino-South Korean relationship as a means to spread China’s influence vis-à-vis the United States. The regional order is changing rapidly. South Korea and the United States were once indispensable partners, but, gradually, China has taken the chunk of cake in its kitty by making South Korea economically dependent. China played smartly by bringing the issue of Japanese wartime aggression and acting sympathetic to South Korea in shared history. Given South Korea’s dependence on China in securing further economic development

and managing North Korean affairs, however, a certain level of Chinese influence may have already taken root among Koreans, but a strategic sense of common purpose and shared common interest between the two countries remains lacking. As a result, while a stronger China-South Korea relationship may serve mutual interests on some issues, there remain clear limits on the development of the political and strategic relationship between the two countries. The United States has urged the South Korean government to sort out differences with Japan, but of no concrete result.

Though the decision maker of South Korea wants a balanced approach in managing the economic benefits from China and security from the United States but, a more balanced and strategic approach would be to leave the politics of Northeast Asia among the nations concerned. For that, the regions concerned should sort out intraregional rivalries and diverging interests. The United States should 'abandon its pivot to East Asia'. Over-dependence on the United States is creating further disorder in the already distorted region. The current situation is such that the United States could do nothing to control the rise of China. It could do nothing about China's Air Defence Identification Zone. Moreover, it failed to make North Korea a non-nuclear nation. Obama's policy of pivot has failed most of the tests. China is as serious about changing the status quo in Asia as America is about preserving it.

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Views expressed are personal and do not represent the views of the organization.

(D) China and INDIA

1. China and India: Time for Resetting the Relationship

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The relationship between India and China is one of the most globally important of the modern era, and yet one of the lowest in profile and the most neglected. With the election of a new populist Indian Prime Minister, Modi, and the creation of a major new development bank for the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) announced in mid-July in Brazil by the five national leaders, are we about to see a reset and reenergisation of the relationship or are their potential rocky moments ahead.

Let's start on the trade. India and China are home to the world's largest and second largest populations respectively. Their combined populations come to about 40 per cent of the people currently living in the world. Most predictions would say that the consumption of this vast shared market will be one of the main sources of growth in the coming decades.

Consumption as a proportion of GDP in China is currently around 36 per cent and will have to rise as the whole economy is restructured and continues to modernise. In India, too, there is an emerging Middle Class, though far more extensive and entrenched levels of poverty than in China. For the rest of the world, finding ways to sell and reach these development and expanding markets will be critical pathways to growth.

Despite this, China and India's bilateral trade is unbalanced. There is no Free Trade Agreement between both sides, and a current merchandise trade deficit in China's favour of about USD40 billion. In 2012, India exported largely resources and raw materials to China, up to a value of USD20 billion. It imported machinery and other consumer goods of USD60 billion. The Indian economy is only a third the size of the Chinese one, despite starting at about the same level three decades ago. India lacks the infrastructure of China, and despite having an extensive stock market network fails to attract as much direct investment as its neighbour. In terms of investment between each country, again there is imbalance. In 2012, India had cumulative investment of USD470 million into China, and China about USD half a billion in India. An outsider looking at this would simply say that both sides could do better. Their current trade relationship is underwhelming, and despite having a Strategic and Economic Dialogue set up in 2010 which has already met several times, India only ranks as China's 15th largest trade partners, and China is India's seventh largest. In a world where something like 120 countries, from Australia to Germany count China as their largest trading partner that two such close and large emerging economies don't trade more with each other is a huge anomaly.

The geopolitics don't help. India and China share a vast border over some of the world's most inhospitable terrain. But that doesn't stop them from still arguing over two large segments of this border. While China has settled land border disputes with Russia, Vietnam and many other neighbours since 1949, the only two outstanding issues remain with India. Despite many discussions in the last few years, there has been little progress. For India, memories die hard. The devastating defeat in 1962 might be over half a century ago, but it left a terrible stain on India's pride and confidence, with a comprehensive Chinese victory. Since then, while there have been skirmishes, one in 1987, there have been no reengagements in combat. This is a good thing. But despite this, the two sides lack a strong political vision of the relationship with each other, and that means they remain vulnerable to fallings out and arguments.

For China, there is no doubt that its western land borders are critically important. Robbie Barnett, Professor of Tibet Studies at Columbia University in the US stated in a recent speech in Sydney that in the last century, of all the global wars, 96 per cent had been over land borders. It is land borders where countries seek security and certainty. So the lack of solid political understanding and common ground between India and China is worrying. As a source of resources, of water, of geopolitical security, the Tibetan plateau is of immense importance to China. It is unclear at the moment how Modi might bring fresh thinking to this issue, but despite his immense mandate in the recent elections that brought him to power, he has shown a strong nationalist streak, restoring the use of Hindi language in government communication, and speaking about strengthening India's national image. This might mean that he has the confidence to address the land border issues in a new way and offering interesting initiatives. But it might also mean he feels emboldened to stand firm and make no concessions or moves at all.

For Modi, the core issue, like his counterpart in China President Xi Jinping, is to maintain growth. Growth in India in the last few years has been from 3 to 4 per cent. In this context, a richer economic relationship with China would make sense. It is close, it has a vast market, and it already buys some of India's high technology goods. A more diverse and freer economic relationship would make sense to India, and be a source of dynamism and growth. For Chinese investors, too, with rising labour costs in China, India offers some potential. But surveys of entrepreneurs show that so far, they see bureaucracy, poor infrastructure and a less educated work force as impediments.

India has looked at the development model China has used to lift so many hundreds of millions of people out of poverty. In a study of India by Nobel Prize winner Amartya Sen and economic Jean Dreze published in 2013, 'An Uncertain Glory: India and its Contradictions', they show how the country remains full of potential, and how some of its separate have managed to pursue successful poverty reduction and education policies. Health has improved, gender equality in some areas has risen, and education and literacy rates have gone up. But as with China there are big differences across provinces. And as Sen and Dreze make clear, the fundamental issue is that on a per capita basis, amongst the BRICS India remains the poorest, with a level half that of China, a third that of Brazil, and a quarter of Russia. Poverty remains its greatest inhibitor, and it is as a campaigner against poverty that Modi must succeed. Where the relationship with China assists in this, then there will be harmony. This will be the most solid basis for their sustainable, stable relationship.

Like Xi Jinping, one of Modi's initial moves has been to pursue a more plain, less wasteful government service image. According to some reports, he has walked around the government buildings in New Delhi commenting on the wastage and bureaucracy and demanding that things be improved. This down to earth image was one of his great assets in his campaign. He is an anti-elitist figure, ranged against his largest opposition, the Indian National Congress Party, the candidate of whom in the last election was from the Gandhi clan. While not yet launching the sort of anti-corruption campaign seen in the last few months in China, corruption has been a target of some of Modi's public language. As with China, corruption creates immense public anger, and is seen as a drag on more efficient growth.

There is plenty of room in the international sphere for India and China to do better, but there is also potential for tension, beyond their border argument. Pakistan remains one of China's most steadfast allies, but has historically very troubled relations with India. Modi's inauguration ceremony saw the attendance by Pakistan's prime minister, which bodes a more tranquil future. But this is a relationship that can never be taken for granted.

India's relations with the US too under its newly elected leader will be of core concern to China. Back in the later period of George W Bush' presidency, around 2006 to 2007, there were signs that the US was drawing closer to India in what seemed to some analysts to be a game of triangulation. Economist journalist at the time Bill Emmett wrote a book, 'Rivals', which described the three way dynamics between Japan, China and India and the way that they would shape the future of Asia. For him, India's liaison with the US created a perfect stranglehold, containing China along its Western border, while the US's alliances with Japan and South Korea also managed its Eastern sea borders. The US and India underwent a number of top level visits over this period, with President Bush visiting in 2006 perhaps being the most significant. Part of this diplomacy was in recognition of India's having become a nuclear power and needing extra attention. But it also acknowledged India's core strategic role in what is sometimes seen as a great geopolitical game around China's borders. The economic crisis in 2008, and the change in presidency to Obama in 2009 took the intensity out of this, but under Modi there might be increased closeness again. Modi is due to visit the US for the first time as leader later this year, and has stated publicly that as the world's largest and second largest democracies, there is huge potential for their relationship to grow. The outcome of this visit will be closely watched in Beijing.

With the creation of a BRICS development fund however, there is a new dynamic to India China relations, and the possibility under Modi of a more nuanced relationship, and one with a greater sense of how to work together more as developing economies who have a lot to offer each other which they have yet to devise good ways to best share. India and China have many different dialogues and have signed a number of governmental memorandum's of understanding. The main issue now is to give their relationship, under two relatively new leaders, a fresher and more suitable larger framework. There will be risks here. Distrust and cultural misunderstandings on either side are still large. There is a surprising lack of mutual understanding between two such large neighbours. But with a bit of attention, and some more official infrastructure, things could change rapidly. A key state in this process will be the planned state visit by President Xi to India later this year. This will be the opportunity to announce something broader within which to develop the relationship. Prime Minister Modi and President Xi will both see the value in upgrading relations, and they know of the ultimate importance they have for each other. The issue now after many years of dialogue and talks is how to achieve this upgrading, how to define what they both see as their expectations and goals towards each other, and what key outputs they want. This is a touch challenge, but one that neither can walk away from.

**2. INDO-CHINA RELATIONSHIP :
A PRISMATIC VIEW**

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INDO-CHINA RELATIONSHIP:

A PRISMATIC VIEW

INTRODUCTION

Relationship refers to the bonds of dependent or reciprocal relations. (Martin Pierre Marie-1986). If we come to International Politics, like all politics, it is a struggle for power. Whatever may be the ultimate aims of international politics, the power is always the immediate aim. ((Morgenthau, Hans J., 1985) On the other hand, International Relations include the study of all human interactions across national borders and factors that affect those interactions. (Pearson F.S. & J.M. Rochester. 1988).

In the present day world, International Relationship is of great significance. It is so because it includes a great variety of transitional relationships. (Palmer Norman D and Perkins Howard C. 2011). It is an agreed fact the relations of states are comprehensible against a context, as the relations of individuals are comprehensible against a context (Bajpai Kanti P. & Harish C. Shukul 1995). We should also keep in mind that there exists a context which gives meaning to and channels the behaviour of states in their relations with other states and other external entities. (Bajpai Kanti P. & Harish C. Shukul- 1995). It should be taken into deep consideration that this context is by no means inscribed forever, nor is there full agreement with all its elements and characteristics. (Bajpai Kanti P. & Harish C. Shukul, 1995).

Relationship between two countries carries significance to a great extent not only in the matter of the two countries concerned in a particular situation or at a particular time but also for the whole world. It has rightly been said that the present day world is a global village. Again, a man who can live without other beings is either a God or a beast. (Malhotra, V.K. – 2001). In modern times, we can safely say that no nation or country can live in isolation. Coexistence of the nations is the order of the day. (Malhotra, V.K. - 2001). It can therefore be said that international relations is of prime importance in the world society from any aspect that is taken for analysis or consideration. It is all the more important because global politics is in the midst of dramatic and accelerating change. (Mansbach R.W. & Kirsten L. Taylor. 2012)

In our present era, international relations have assumed all the more great significance. In the twenty first century, we live in a world that is both fascinating and terrifying -one that exhibits deep contradictions and yet manifest high hopes. (Duncan W. Raymond et al. – 2002). Further, the terrorist attacks on the World Trade Centre and the Pentagon, demonstrated just how complex international relations have become in the past decade. (Wenger, A. & Doron Zimmermann. 2004). It should be stated that the relationship of nations emits a great mark of implications not only in the relationship status of two or more countries but also exerts a tremendous influence all over the region and the world. Therefore, inter-national relationship is significant from all dimensions. (Chakrabarty Manas in Mishra Sylvia(Ed) 2014). This definitely shapes the pattern and dimension of international relations at large.

As already said, international relations are therefore very significant from all respects. It is more important when the matter is related with two neighbouring countries, and the relationship between the two countries is always significant not only from the regional politics but also from the point of view of world politics at large. It is very natural to state that if the relationship of the countries, particularly, the neighbouring countries, is friendly, the atmosphere of the region remains filled with

good oxygen which produces peace but if it is reverse, the entire environment becomes smoky and poisonous .(Chakrabarty Manas in Mishra Sylvia(Ed) 2014). It greatly affects the international scenario. We should always be concerned with the aspect that the immediate threat to any country arises from its neighborhood. That is why the maintenance of peace, stability and friendship with neighbouring states are considered basic to a nation's foreign policy. India's relations with its neighbours therefore constitute a critical component of its foreign policy.

Accordingly, the foreign policy of a nation becomes all the more important because it determines the nature of relationship either between two countries or a large number of countries. As per international norms, foreign policies are the central objective to preserve the liberty of states and to maintain the balance of power. Again, a special care should be devoted for understanding international relationship because there has been a paradigm shift in its content. In fact, the disciplinary dimensions of international politics have witnessed quantitative expansion as well as qualitative complexities since 1945. (Jaitly, Anam- 1986). It is also significant to note that a cursory look at the expanded scope of international relations and politics unambiguously indicate that these have reached the farthest corner of human creativity and as such deeply influence mankind. (Jaitly, Anam- 1986). . The traditional conceptual categories are no longer sufficient for comprehending the dynamics of international politics. (Jaitly, Anam- 1986).

The foreign policy or so to say, that of foreign relations is the systematic activities evolved by communities for changing the behavior of other states and for adjusting their own activities to the international environment. (Archana- 2011) In fact, all states have some kind of relation with one another and in their behavior, they have a particular manner of self pattern. (Archana - 2011) In the present day international society, one of the utmost significant dimensions is that of relation between nations. It should be kept in mind that the relationship is

dynamic in character. It is never permanent. With the passage of time and depending on a particular situation or any specific interest, the relationship is affected and undergoes change. Like human relations, international relations between and among countries become significant particularly when the world is being referred as a global village. (Chakrabarty, Manas- in Mishra Sylvia(Ed) 2014). It is also an important fact that there is no reason that a state should live in isolation. In such a case, it not only deprives the country concerned from multifaceted development but also to exchange ideas on different matters that may be conducive for development of a particular state. It is therefore, perhaps a necessity that no nation should live in isolation. If it remains aloof or away from the dynamic international social order, it shall be deprived from the advancements, developments and particularly, the move towards betterment, will remain unknown and secondly and more importantly, it is foolish to be away from the international social dynamics which can take a nation in a far advanced position. Under the circumstances, it is essential to remain within the purview of international relations and it becomes sine qua non and of prime necessity for a modern state. In today's world we cannot think of remaining isolation. It is foolish and also not possible at the same time. In the present day society, man is social, not by choice but by necessity. (Chakraborty R. - 1970). Therefore, there is no necessity to point out the importance of international relationship.

INDIA-CHINA RELATIONSHIP

BACKDROP

When we speak of bilateral relationship between two countries, it should be kept in mind that every nation's problems and prospects are significantly determined by history, heritage and its location on the globe. (Rowland John- 1967.)

From the geographical point of view, China and India are separated by the formidable geographical obstacles of the mighty Himalayas. So far as

geographical boundary is concerned, China and India today share a border along the Himalayas with Nepal and Bhutan acting as buffer states. China and India also dispute most of Arunachal Pradesh at the far eastern end of the Himalayas. Notwithstanding their fundamental clash of interests rooted in history, strategic culture and geo politics, the rapprochement process between the two countries had begun in the late 1980's. (Y.Yagama Reddy - 2012.)

At the outset it should be stated that India's relations with no other country have fluctuated as widely as have those with china. (C.V. Ranganathan/Vinod C. Khanna - 2000.) To a student of international relations, Indo-China relationship is of great significance because India and china are two giants of Asia. (Iqbal Khanam- in Kaythwal 1999) No doubt, China and India have lots in common: long histories, ancient civilizations, unique cultures, vast land mass, huge populations and significant natural resources. (Swaran Singh. 2005.)

If we move our attention to interactions between India and China during the colonial era, we find that more than fifty years after the establishment of formal diplomatic relations between the Republic of India and the People's Republic of China, tangible relations between the two Asian giants are not as predictable, solid and stable as many in both countries might consider desirable. (Surjit Mansing- in. Madhavi Thampi(ed), 2005.)

Indo-China relations, refers to the bilateral relationship between the People's Republic of China (PRC) and the Republic of India. Historical facts reveal that India and China have a prolonged relationship for more than 2,000 years. From the international perspective, the growth in China and India's international diplomatic and economic influence has significantly increased the significance of the bilateral relationship between India and China. The relations between China and India during the first ten years of existence of the People's Republic of China which came into existence on 1 October 1949 were amicable. (Adel D.S. 1984).

It is commonly acknowledged that the relationship between India and China in recent times has not been free from 'the problems left over from history'. Relations between the great neighbouring civilizations of India and China date back to the ancient times, but the nature of their relationship was to be greatly transformed as both came under colonial and imperialistic domination. (Thampi Madhavi - 2005.). It is important to note that if we move our attention from interactions between India and China during the colonial era to those of the post colonial era, we find that more than fifty years after the establishment of formal India's relations with no other country have fluctuated so widely as have those with China. (C.V. Ranganathan and Vinod C. Khanna- 2000)

It is now fairly commonplace to hear that the coming years will be led by India and China. Economists, Political Scientists and Journalists are almost equally divided on who has the upper hand in this race to the top. Yet, surely the more pertinent question to ask the two is not who but how this race will be won. (Ira Pande 2009-Spring 2010.) Like another difficult neighbor, China has a long and complex history with India, for it spans centuries rather than sixty odd years. From the early years of trade and commerce along the Silk Route to the present global age, both India and China have redefined their relationship with the world and each other but certain ambiguities still remain unaddressed. It should be kept in mind that we live in a fast changing world that reminds us of the Chinese saying 'First three decades of the glory on the east of the river, then three decades of the glory on the west of the river. India and China were fairly and lowly in the international standing until recent years. They have suddenly ascended the centre stage of the world in the twenty first century- a new epoch, in which china is supposed to lead. (Tan Chung- 2010.)

BOUNDARY AND BORDER DISPUTES

Geographically, India and China share a substantially long border

beginning from the extreme end of Ladakh in the north west to the borders of Myanmar in the east. Altogether, both the countries share about 4000 km long border. (Srivastava C.B.P. - 2001).China-India border disputes are one of the most prominent factors embedded in Sino-Indian relations, as they began influencing the relationship between the two Asian powers since the end of the Second World War. From the geographical point of view, boundaries are the lines of political zones. (M.L.Sali- 1998.) Boundary issues have always occupied a central focus in the relations between India and China. (Noorani A.G. – 2011.)

It is discernible that the relations between contemporary China and India have been characterised by border disputes. This resulted in three major military conflicts :

- (i) the Sino-Indian War of 1962,
- (ii) the Chola incident in 1967, and
- (iii) the 1987 Sino-Indian skirmish.
- (iv) But in spite these conflicts, since the late 1980s, both countries have successfully attempted to revamp diplomatic and economic ties with each other. Further, in 2008, China emerged as India's largest trading partner. Both the countries also attempted to extend their strategic and military relations.

It can be definitely said that there has been considerable growth of economic and strategic ties. But in spite of that there are several hurdles for India and the PRC to overcome in order to establish favourable relations with each other.

In modern times, as per records of history, India's relationship with China dates back to 1950. Amongst the non-socialist countries, India tied the knot of diplomatic relationship with China on 1 April, 1950. Prime Minister Nehru visited China in the month of October, 1954. Although the cloud of tension between the two countries engulfed the

diplomatic sky in 1962 in view of the Indo-China border conflict. The year 1988 may be regarded as a major land mark in the Indo-China bilateral relationship. The visit of the then Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi in 1988 helped substantially to melt the ice and helped to usher into a new improved era in bilateral relationship between India and China. The signing of the Agreement on the Maintenance of Peace and Tranquility along the Line of Actual Control (LAC) on the India-China Border Areas during the visit of Prime Minister Narasimha Rao in 1993 greatly helped to make the bilateral relationship like a soft cake. It helped to put the bilateral relationship on the stable foundation considerably. Relationship between the two countries moved from good to better with the visit and counter visit of summit leaders of both the countries. The visit of Prime Minister Vajpayee in 2003, the visit of Premier Wen Jiabao to India in 2005, President Hu Jintao's visit in 2006, Prime Minister Manmohan Singh's visit in 2008 and Premier Wen Jiabao's visit in 2010 definitely paved the way for cementing the bond of relationship between India and China.

Incidentally the outcomes of the visits and counter visits may be traced. During the visit of Prime Minister Vajpayee in 2003, the two countries signed a **Declaration on Principles for Relations and Comprehensive Cooperation**. It was also decided to mutually appoint Special Representatives (SRs) who would try to find out solution measures regarding boundary settlement.

During the visit of Premier Wen Jiabao in the month of April 2005, India and China established a **Strategic and Cooperative Partnership for Peace and Prosperity**,

Further, during the visit of the Chinese President Hu Jintao to India in the month of November 2006, the two countries issued a Joint Declaration containing a ten-pronged strategy to intensify cooperation. Another important milestone in the bilateral relationship between India and China was the visit of the Indian Prime Minister Dr. Manmohan

Singh to China in January 2008. During his visit, a joint document titled "**A Shared Vision for the 21st Century**" was issued. It is pertinent to note that during the visit of the Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao to India in December 2010, the two sides jointly set a bilateral trade target of US\$ 100 billion for 2015. In the series of developments in the bilateral relationship between India and China, another important milestone was the visit of the Chinese President Hu Jintao in the month of March 2012. His visit was in connection with the BRICS Summit. The External Affairs Minister visited China twice during the year. Further, the Chinese Foreign Minister Yang Jiechi visited India in February. Further, the Chinese Defence and Commerce Ministers also visited India. All these visits considerably improved the status of bilateral relationship between the two countries. Bilateral consultations on regional issues pertaining to West Asia and Africa were also held during the year. With respect to defence exchanges, the fifth round of the Annual Defence Dialogue concluded in Beijing on 14 January 2013.

COMMERCIAL AND ECONOMIC RELATIONS

Trade and commercial relationship plays a key role in any bilateral relationship. There has been a rapid progress in this field during the last few years. As per record, in the year 2000, trade between India and China was less than US\$ 3 billion. By the end of 2012, it was US\$ 66 billion. The two countries have set a target of US\$ 100 billion by 2015 for bilateral trade. China-India trade and commerce relationship is a matter of significant importance. It started with an extremely slow pace with an annual turnover of only a few million dollars. It stayed on the margins for much of the decade of 1980s. In fact, their trade has gradually come to occupy the centre stage of their interaction. In the short-run, their current institutional arrangements and enthusiasm augurs very well for their continued trade boom, which can contribute a great deal to their growing confidence on the one hand and on the other hand, their evolving long-term strategic partnership between the two countries. It is important to note that China's foreign trade stood at US\$851 billion in

2003 and exceeded US\$1 trillion in 2004. On the other hand, India's foreign trade could reach only about US\$180 billion for 2004. It is discernible that the positive trends in the bilateral trade between India and China have been particularly shaped by the economic reforms on both sides and the consequent search for new business partners. As a result of this, their complicated politico-strategic equations, that had continued to slow down the rising enthusiasm, have come to be underplayed and marginalised. It had definitely left a great impact on the bilateral relationship.

It is important to note that India and China officially resumed trade in the year of 1978. A land mark in the Indo-china trade and commerce relationship was definitely the MFN. In 1984, the two sides signed the Most Favoured Nation (MFN) Agreement. Its impact was readily visible. It may be stated again that the India-China bilateral trade record was as low as US\$ 2.92 billion in 2000 which catapulted to US\$ 51.8 billion in 2008. There was a down ward trend by the end of 2009, as a result of the world economic downturn. As a result of this, bilateral trade between India and China had dropped to US\$ 43.27 billion which shows a decline of 16.54%. But in the year of 2010 bilateral trade could rise up to US\$ 61.74 billion. It marked a growth of 43%. As per record, India-China total trade in goods during the year 2012 stood at US\$ 66.57 billion which recorded a decline of almost 10%.

Due to fast growth of trade and commerce, both China and India have emerged as the fastest growing economies. If we consider from the global perspective, China and India have already gained their place as two unique new players in the international arena. An analysis in the politico-strategic dimension shows that their recent economic success has led both the countries to occupy an expanded space in the regional as well as international decision-making space. It has definitely been a matter for worldwide concern for all the countries. It is a matter of recent development that the political initiatives on both the sides have helped in the process of confidence-building and it has definitely contributed to expand their areas of mutual co-operation. It is based on their new

mantra of mutual accommodation and mutual benefit. In this regard, the bilateral trade has come to be recognised as the most reliable as also the most agreeable instrument of China-India rapprochement. There is no denying the fact that this China-India economic partnership remains an essential prerequisite for the success of their regional and global political initiatives at a very important scale.

There is no doubt that the China-India bilateral trade as well as regional and global—has undergone a radical metamorphosis and has been changing rapidly. At the bilateral level, this is a proved fact that their partnership has provided a great boost to their ongoing political confidence-building measures. It must be said that the Indo-China bilateral trade has faced many ups and downs and in view of India's nuclear tests of May 1998, the bilateral trade was the first to bounce back to its normal pace. Several factors and measures have significantly contributed for trade and commerce development between the two countries. The opening of a third border trade route through Sikkim in June 2003, and the discussions for evolving a China-India Free Trade Area (FTA) is definitely conducive for enhancement of Indo-China trade relationship.

FRAMEWORK/SPRING BOARD OF INDO-CHINA TRADE RELATIONSHIP.

JOINT ECONOMIC GROUP

In order to build and develop Indo-China trade and commercial relations, several frames and mechanisms have been evolved. One of the most important tools in this regard is definitely the **JOINT ECONOMIC GROUP** which was evolved during the visit of the then Prime Minister of India, Mr. Rajiv Gandhi to China in 1988. India-China Joint **Economic Group** on Economic Relations and Trade, Science and Technology is definitely very significant. The JEG is a ministerial-level dialogue mechanism established in 1988 as already said, during the visit of the former Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi to China. The Joint Economic

Group may be regarded as a mechanism which helped to strengthen the Indo-China bilateral relationship in the sphere of trade and commerce.

Further step in this regard was a Joint Study Group (JSG) which was set up after the visit of the former Prime Minister Sri A.B.Vajpayee to China in the month of June 2003 in order to examine the potential complementarities between the two countries in the field of trade and economic cooperation. As per recommendation of the JSG, a Joint Task Force (JTF) was set up to study the feasibility of an India-China Regional Trading Arrangement. The Report of JTF was completed in the month of October 2007. The Joint Economic Group may be regarded as a mechanism which helped to strengthen the Indo-China bilateral relationship in the sphere of trade and commerce. The working group on the trade and economic cooperation is mandated to prepare an action oriented work plan for improving India's trade imbalance with China. In the last JEG meeting with China on August 27, 2012 in New Delhi, Sharma had handed over to the Chinese Minister of Commerce the roadmap for enhanced cooperation between India and China in IT& ITeS and the pharmaceuticals sector.

So far the JEG has met nine times.

First Session	New Delhi	Sep 18-20,1989
Second Session	Beijing	Feb 06, 1991
Third Session	New Delhi	Dec 09, 1991
Fourth Session	Beijing	Jan 04, 1993
Fifth Session	New Delhi	Jun 13, 1994
Sixth Session	Beijing	Feb 19-20,2000
Seventh Session	New Delhi	Mar 16, 2006
Eighth Session	Beijing	Jan 29, 2010
Ninth Session	New Delhi	Aug 27, 2012

The 9th JEG was jointly chaired by Indian Commerce & Industry Minister Shri Anand Sharma and the Commerce Minister of P.R.C., Mr. Chen Deming.

STRATEGIC AND ECONOMIC DIALOGUE

Further, during Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao's visit to India in December 2010, India and China agreed to set up the **STRATEGIC AND ECONOMIC DIALOGUE** mechanism. The SED served as a forum for both sides to discuss strategic macro-economic issues impacting both nations as a result of the changing international economic and financial landscape. It was further designed to share their individual best practices and in handling challenging domestic economic issues. Further, it attempted to identify specific fields for enhancing cooperation, learning and experience sharing. The first SED took place in Beijing on 26th September, 2011.

FIRST SED MEETING-

The first India-China SED Meeting took place in Beijing from September 26-27, 2011. Among the most important issues that were discussed during the first SED include d:

1. To finalise the 12th plan priorities of the two countries.
2. A discussion on each country's monetary and fiscal policies.
3. Investment policies of the two countries.
4. Policies on energy conservation and environment protection etc.
5. The two sides decided to constitute five Working Groups on policy coordination, infrastructure, energy, environment protection and high-technology.

SECOND SED MEETING- The second meeting of the SED took place on November 26, 2012 in New Delhi.

The most important issues that were discussed during the second SED included:

1. The two sides discussed a wide range of topics including greater cooperation at the global level which might strengthen the communication.
2. Expanding trade and investment and promoting bilateral cooperation in the financial and infrastructure sectors.
3. The two sides agreed that in the current global economic situation, it was important to raise the level of economic engagement between India and China.
4. The two sides also signed a total of 4 Government-to-Government and 7 business MoUs during the 2nd SED.

THIRD SED MEETING

The third SED (Strategic Economic Dialogue) between India-China was scheduled to be held in Beijing in 2013 but the event was postponed. The tensions arising out of People's Liberation Army's (PLA) incursion in Ladakh in the India-China border region and Xi Jinping and Li Keqiang's assumption of power in China as new leaders may have been the reasons for this postponement. The third round of the SED was held in Beijing during 17-18 March 2014. The Dialogue was co-chaired by Dr. Montek Singh Ahluwalia, Deputy Chairman, Planning Commission of India and Mr. Xu Shaoshi, Chairman, National Development and Reform Commission of China.

An extensive and in-depth discussion on bilateral trade, investment, and economic cooperation and on the regional and global economic situation was the main areas of discussion. The major attention was given on enhancing macro-economic policy coordination and to join hands to address issues and challenges. Further, bilateral cooperation in sectors like railway infrastructure, information technology, energy, and finance was also emphasized. Again, the two sides agreed to continue deepening bilateral coordination and engagement in multilateral frameworks like the United Nations, G-20 and the BRICS. Memoranda of Understanding on (i) Sustainable Urbanization and on (ii) Cooperation in Information and Communications Technology were signed at the Dialogue. Action

Plans on joint studies in sustainable urbanization and energy planning were also signed for completion before the next round of the Dialogue.

It should be stated that the India-China SED needs to discuss seriously the issue of reforming the global financial bodies. On discussion table both the countries have tried to advocate their reform measures, but unfortunately, common and decisive joint perspective is still missing in the arena. Again, a solid understanding between the two is required for improving voting rights and quota in the IMF. It is necessary to point out that the three rounds of SED have, no doubt, built a strong momentum in the India-China institutional engagement, but it is a major challenge that how to upgrade the level of dialogue, bring maturity to the interaction and make it a distinct and regular affair without making it just another talk shop. The India-China SED has not really matured as a trusted bilateral mechanism to discuss the regional and global complexities of economic and strategic substance yet. In fact, there is a great lack in understanding the basic problems of the two giants.

CULTURAL RELATIONS

Cultural relation and cultural exchange programmes are regarded as a stepping stone for better bilateral relationship. Both India and China has considerably depended on this important area and have gained substantial result in this arena. India and China may be reckoned easily to have different cultures in the true sociological sense. China is basically a temperate climate against largely torrid climate of India, implying different constraints for agricultural development, plenitude of natural resources of China against the paucity of the same valuable resources in India. There is no social divide in China as it exists in India. But, there are some similar divides. The Soldier is rated low in China while in India he is only no 2 to the priest. But, unlike in India, where castes are endogamous, in China, all Chinese are of equal marital acceptability.

It is from the time of the establishment of the diplomatic relations between China and India as early as in 1950, both India and China have kept frequent contacts in cultural exchanges and personnel visits by the personnel belonging to the cultural domain. Several cultural activities like **art** exhibitions and film weeks have been arranged by both the countries. A significant land mark could be reached in the year of 1988 when China and India signed the **CULTURAL COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT**. It was decided that Executive Programme of the Cultural Agreement between two governments would be signed every triennium. During the Indian Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi's visit to China in 1988, the Executive Programme of the Cultural Agreement for 1988-1990 was signed between China and India. Again, in 1992 and in 1994 respectively, both China and India successively arranged large-scale art festivals in both the countries. As a result, it was possible to take the cultural exchanges between the two countries at a very high pitch. It is seen that with the restoration and development of the bilateral relations ever since 1999, the cultural exchanges between China and India have become increasingly frequent and regular. It has definitely contributed a lot for better bilateral relationship between India and China.

It is very significant to note that most importantly, these two giants of Asia are unique 21st Century examples of unbroken civilizations which cover a period over 3000 years. It should be stated that contiguous territorially, and with significant mutual influence in areas like religion and ordinarily Cultural symbols like art, literature etc. the Indo China cultural relationship is greatly significant.

It is important to note that Rabindra Nath Tagore's visit to China raised a lot of hopes for literary euphoria amongst the Chinese just coming out of the initially literary and more importantly, political, May 4 th Movement, some of whose progenitors initially glorified Tagore's visit but later recanted, may be, due to ideological reasons – Zhen du Xiu, "Mao Dun" etc. It was left to Guo MoRo, and few others who came to realize Tagore's

down to earth concerns for the poor farmers, and that Tagore was not a spiritualist only, talking high and dry religious philosophy. Tagore got a Chinese name-Zhu Zhendan (Zhu stands for ancient name for India (there is still a village near Beijing airport called TIAN ZHU – standing for INDIA) and ZHENDAN stands for transliteration for Sanskrit CHANDAN for SANDALWOOD)

A great development that took place after his visit was the setting up of the India China Cultural Society, with Tan Yunshan as the major actor in it. And Tan YunShan himself became part of Vishva Bharati; a Cheena Bhavan was established there under him. One can speak more about Tagore's visit and the pro-Tagore winds and counter winds. It is therefore clear that the visit of Rabindra Nath Tagore had exerted a tremendous influence in the cultural domain of China.

In the year of 2010, with a purpose to commemorate the 60th Anniversary of the establishment of the diplomatic relations between India and China, **FESTIVAL OF INDIA** was celebrated across more than 45 cities in China. In December 2010, the two countries signed a Cultural Exchange Programme (CEP). The major aim of this exchange programme was to provide a greater people to people cooperation in various fields. During the visit of President Hu Jintao to India in the month of March, 2012 the important decision to celebrate 2012 as **'The Year of Friendship and Co-operation'** was undertaken and was celebrated.

CONCLUDING OBSERVATION

At the concluding part, it must be stated that the foreign policy of China has shown higher degree of fluidity. Therefore, it has always changed its stance so far as border dispute is concerned. In the present context, when China has also shown keen interest to develop cordial relations with India, it is expected that some solution on border dispute between the two countries would come in future. (Srivastava, C.B.P.-2001) It is

seen that since 2007, Indo-China relationship has not moved on a plain road. Many attempts to resolve the border dispute have been stalled and Chinese activity on the northern side of Pakistan occupied Kashmir has substantially gone high. The relationship between the two countries received a big jolt in view of the Chinese military buildup and other activities which are not conducive to India.

The India-China relationship status at the end of 2013 had reflected more positive than negative tone and temper. It is observed that the new leaders of China reflects definitely a positive direction towards India which was conspicuously absent for quite a long time. The exchange of visits by leaders of both the countries clearly proves that both have taken the aspect of relationship as very important and put the same on priority list. It is really significant that Premier Li decided to land at India as his first overseas stop. It can definitely be said that this was a deliberate choice on the part of the Chinese Premier in order to mend and repair the status of bilateral relationship between India and China and open a new vista of relationship.

Further, a very significant aspect is definitely to undertake greater efforts to resolve long standing boundary issues. In spite of sincere attempts, both the countries have failed to resolve their long-standing border dispute. There has always been imposition of aspersion on each other regarding border dispute, military infiltration etc.

As President Xi said, the Chinese and Indian “dreams” are interconnected and mutually compatible. The Indian leadership also expressed sufficiently positive tone for a greater cooperation and open new chapters of relationship that will brightly reflect ‘good will’ on both sides. A clear message that could be seen that the era of confronting and containing each other is over and a closed chapter and a new era has dawned to look afresh to the problems and make sincere attempt to usher into a new era in the bilateral relationship between the two countries. Under the given new improved situation, it would definitely be

an easy task on the part of the Indian leaders to build a new superstructure of relationship in 2014.

But it should be kept in mind that there are lingering differences over boundary dispute that may continue to threaten India-China relationship status. There is no denying the fact that the challenge in 2014 on the part of the leaders, both in China and India, would be to find out avenues that will lead to a mutually acceptable boundary settlement which has haunted the bilateral relationship for quite a substantive period. Both on the boundary and trans-border river issues, there could be an out-of-the-box thinking available should be explored. (**P. Stobdan**, 2013).

To be sure, commerce will continue to drive the engine of relationship, but challenge before the next leadership is to resolve trade imbalance \$40 billion against India. Significantly, India has overcome past apprehensions and is getting more receptive to the Chinese proposals. The Border Defence pact is a case in point. The prospects of a Regional Trade Agreement (RTA), Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP), setting up industrial zones and aligning the (BCIM) Economic Corridor are being positively looked into. Importantly, new Indian leadership will do well learning from China's experience of spurring internal economic development with regional and global linkages. (**P. Stobdan**, 2013)

It can be definitely said that there has been considerable growth of economic and strategic ties between the two countries. But in spite of that there are several hurdles for India and the PRC to overcome all these problems in order to establish favourable relation with each other. The year 2012 may be said to be an important milestone in the history of international relations because in June 2012, China categorically clarified its position with the statement "Sino-Indian ties" could be the most "important bilateral partnership of the century". However, it must be said that the emergence of India and China in the new global order as

strong power houses has been a sensational story. (Apala De- in Y.Yagama Reddy – 2012). It is a significant point to note that there is no doubt that India and China are emerging powers which had made a significant mark in the recent decades, in various fields of human activity. (A. Chandrasekharan and P. Govinda Reddy - 2012).

The situation as it reflects today, both China and India are more politically and economically engaged than it has been discernible in the recent past. Bilateral trade between India and China has expanded sixty-seven-fold from 1998 to 2012. One more significant aspect is that the Chinese and Indian armies held their first-ever joint military exercise in 2007, which was followed by two more in the year of 2008 and in 2013. It was possible on the part of both the countries to find common agenda and programme of action on global issues of mutual interest which include world trade talks, climate-change negotiations, the primacy of state sovereignty, and the need to reform global-governance institutions. A major break in the Indo-china bilateral relationship is definitely the meet of Ms. Sushma Swaraj, the Indian Minister of External Affairs with the Foreign Minister of China, Wang Yi, who met on the sidelines of the series of Foreign Ministers' Meetings on East Asia competition in Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar. (News From China, 2014). The statement of Wang Yi is very significant when he said: China and India, the two biggest developing countries who are neighbours, if join hands in cooperation, will make the world more balanced, secure and stable. The bilateral relationship also got a major revamp with the meet of the President Xi Jinping and the Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi who had a successful meeting at Brazil. They identified their commitment to a more closely knit partnership and the goal of achieving peaceful, cooperative and inclusive development. In fact, the successful meeting between Prime

Minister Modi and President Xi Jinping, in particular, serves as a strong boost to bilateral relations.

(News From China, 2014). As said by Sushma Swaraj, the Indian side warmly welcomes President Xi Jinping's visit to India, stands ready to vigorously enhance cooperation with China in the fields of trade, investment, culture and people-to-people exchanges, so as to bring bilateral relationships to a new height. (News From China, 2014). Mention should also be made regarding President Xi Jinping's latest three day visit to India which began on 17th September, 2014. Three agreements between India and China were signed in the presence of the dignitaries of the two countries. (The Statesman, 18th September, 2014). Two of the three MoUs signed are about developing sister province state tie up between China's Guangdong province and Gujrat State and a similar relationship between Guangzhou city and Ahmedabad. The third MoU signed between the China Development Bank Corporation and Indext-B (Industrial Extension Bureau) of the Gujrat Government is for extending Chinese support to develop an industrial park project in Gujrat. (The Statesman, 18th September, 2014).

These are some of the important areas where both the countries could come together. The major aspect that should be highlighted is that cooperation and competition coexist in this relationship. There is no doubt that the cooperative temper is working very well and has been accelerating since the turn of the century, but at the same time the strategic competition has also kept pace, and in some arenas competition has overturned the dimension of cooperation. However, at the end it must be said that if the bilateral relationship between the two countries move on a smooth plane, it would definitely be conducive for

both and would help to minimize tension which is one of the 'curse' factors in international relations and lead towards development.

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**3. Sino-Indian Relations
-trajectory they should take**

Lt Gen PC Katoch

PVSM, UYSM, AVSM, SC

(Lt Gen PC Katoch, PVSM, UYSM, AVSM, SC superannuated as DG Information Systems of Indian Army in 2009. A Special Forces officer, he fought in the 1971 India-Pakistan War, commanded a Special Forces battalion under the Indian Peace Keeping Force in Sri Lanka, a Brigade on Siachen Glacier, a Division in Ladakh and a Strike Corps in South Western Theatre. He was part of the Indian contingent to an international sky-diving competition held in USSR during 1976 and has served as Defence Attaché in Japan and Republic of Korea. MSc in Defence Studies, he graduate of National Defence College. Post retirement, he has authored over 500 articles on international affairs, geopolitics, military, security, technical and topical issues. He is an elected Council Member of United Services Institution of India, is active in seminars at international and national levels and has presented papers in USA, China, Taiwan, South Korea and Maldives. He has authored books titled 'India's Special Forces' and 'Indian Military and Network Centric Warfare'.)

Ancient Links and beyond

That India and China have had ancient historic linkages is a fact well known. To the younger generation, this was reinforced when Prime Minister Narendra Modi referred to memoirs of the 7th Century Chinese Scholar Hiuen Tsang in his conversation with Chinese Premier Li Keqiang to underline the importance of ties between the two countries. Incidentally, a memorial to Huen Tsang stands in Bihar even today:

It does not matter that China has no such memorial for Dr Kotnis but Mr Modi told Mr Li that Hiuen Tsang had even visited his village Vadnagar in Gujarat, as mentioned in memoirs of Hiuen Tsang post travelling pan India for some 15 years. Premier Li had rung up PM Modi to congratulate him, being the first foreign head of state to do so. Having established personal contact with heads of SAARC countries coinciding with his swearing in, Mr Modi told Mr Li that China was always a priority in India's foreign policy. PM Li conveyed his government's desire to establish robust partnership with the new Indian government. PM Modi underlined India's resolve to optimize potential of the 'India-China Strategic and Cooperative Partnership', resolve outstanding issues and develop greater economic engagement. It is also a historic fact that Buddhism from India travelled to SE Asia through China. It was a blind Chinese Buddhist monk who travelled to Japan by sea and established the first Buddhist temple in the ancient city of Nara; a magnificent wooden structure with the tallest bronze statue of Buddha in the world (60 feet high) with Sanskrit *shlokas* engraved on the back of the statue:

With the stupendous win of PM Modi and development and industrialization being top priorities of his majority government, energizing the India-China dialogue is well on the cards, indications of which have already emerged. Mr Modi's victory was well received in Beijing because the Chinese leadership already shared good rapport with him. As Chief Minister of Gujarat, Mr Modi visited China four times, as a result of which much of China's US\$ 900 million investments in India have been made in Gujarat. Earlier this year, Chinese President Xi Jinping had expressed the desire to visit India later this year and PM

Modi had extended an invitation to President Xi Jinping through Premier Li.

In March this year, Qin Gang, China's Foreign Ministry spokesman had said, "The signal we have sent to our friendly neighbour India is peace and win-win cooperation." During the same period, an editorial in China Daily also said, "As long as we do not interfere in others' domestic affairs, as long as we do not covet others' territories, as long as we commit our military capabilities to safeguarding peace, as long as we can afford it, we have the right to spend as much as necessary." Here, two issues mentioned in the China Daily editorial differ from the ground situation. First, is the issue of interfering in the domestic affairs of other countries, which China denies. China may deny being the source of weapons and equipment to insurgents in India, these being available in the global market, but can China deny giving refuge to Indian insurgents on its soil. It is an established fact that the ULFA hierarchy led by Paresh Barua is based at Ruli in China. Then, China has armed the United State Wa Army (USWA) of Myanmar lethally and that too openly. China has been providing tacit support to Pakistan's anti-India jihad. Second, is the issue that China does not covet other's territory? The fact remains that it is only in the past decade that China dug out claims by the erstwhile Kuomintang (that she overthrew in 1949) and started claiming "Other's Territories" as Chinese territory.

More significantly, claim to entire Arunachal Pradesh was put forwarded only in 2006, while earlier China only claimed the Tawang Plateau in this sector on grounds that Tibetans come to pray at the ancient Tawang monastery but then what about the enclaves of Minsar (Men ser), near Lake Mansarovar (Ma pham) which are for annual pilgrimage for all Indians and Bhutanese enclave of Tconsists of Darchen (Dar chen) Labrang etc near Mount Kailash (Gangs rin po che, Ti se) again used by Bhutanese and Indians for periodic pilgrimage – both these enclaves being under Chinese occupation? Incidentally, Mount Kailash is the abode of Lord Shiva, part of the Trinity so sacred to Indians. As to the claim to Arunachal (referred to as South Tibet by China, China cannot go back in history same way as Mongols and Tibetans can't claim large parts of China based on old history and India cannot lay claims to Maurya and Chola Empires and conquests by Maharaja Ranjit Singh; Indian territories then included region right up to Hindukush Mountains, Sri Lanka, Maldives, Bangladesh, parts of Burma, Malaysia, and Indonesia and portions of Tibet - not many would be aware of the captured Chinese flag brought by Maharaja Ranjit Singh that adorns the officer's mess of an infantry battalion of the Indian Army and that Indian

troops of British India were posted at Yatung in the Chumbi Valley of Tibet.

In October 2013, the joint India-China statement had outlined the vision for developing an 'India-China Strategic and Cooperative Partnership for Peace and Prosperity', main features of the vision being: *one*, exploring prospects of a bilateral Regional Trade Arrangement (RTA), review negotiations on the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) and expedite framework agreement for establishing industrial zones to provide platforms of cluster type development for enterprises of both countries; *three*, review progress of the India-China Study Group on the BCIM (Bangladesh, China, India and Myanmar) Economic Corridor and further discussions on concepts and alignment of the economic corridor; *four*, Special Representatives exploring framework of settlement of the India-China boundary question to continue efforts in that direction; *five*, recognition of peace and tranquility on the India-China border as an important guarantor for the development and continued growth of bilateral relations – the Border Defence Cooperation Agreement (BDCA) strengthening maintenance of stability on the border; *six*, defence exchanges and military exercises being important in building greater trust and confidence to continue as agreed to mutually; *seven*, appreciation of signing MoU on Strengthening Cooperation on Trans-border Rivers, plus agreement to exchange flood-season hydrological data and emergency management etc; *eight*, facilitating greater people-to-people contacts and exchanges, supported by sister-city relationships that have been concluded initially on a pilot basis; *nine*, in addition to marking 2014 as a Year of Friendly Exchanges, India and China to discuss with Myanmar commemoration of 60th anniversary of the Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence (Panchsheel); *ten*, coordination and cooperation in multilateral forums including Russia-India-China, BRICS, and G-20 to jointly tackle global issues such as climate change, international terrorism, food and energy security, and to establish a fair and equitable international political and economic system.

Post the Indian elections in India, Wei Wei, the then Chinese Ambassador at New Delhi wrote an Op-ed in the *Economic Times* titled 'India's Economic Takeoff' outlining China's hopes for economic cooperation and common development. More specifically, he wrote about: *one*, increased Chinese investments in manufacturing sector with 'Made in China' global tag and China possessing plenty resources and experience; *two*, encourage Chinese investors develop Chinese-style industrial parks in India like China has done in ASEAN countries like Cambodia, Indonesia and Vietnam, and since such industrial parks help

increase trade balance; *three*, partnership in developing infrastructure especially efficient transportation between inland cities and ports with railway transportation (increase speed and loading capacity and upgradation of railway stations) since this will improve efficiency of freight transportation, easing energy shortage in India, accelerate production and improve competitiveness of Indian products; *four*, combining China's "Open to the West" with India's "Look East Policy" to achieve better connectivity with a Sino-Indian railway apart from the BCIM economic corridor and since China has commenced constructing the Trans-Asian High-Speed Railway connecting southwestern China to East Asian countries.

On the defence cooperation front, the BDCA has been operationalized, a high level Chinese military delegation held talks in New Delhi recently and China is participating in the Fourth India-China Joint Training Exercise (JTE) scheduled in India during November 2014. Premiers Modi and Li had agreed to continue exchange of high level delegations and communications. A number of delegations have been exchanged between India and China over the past three years under aegis of the India China Economic and Cultural Council aimed at learning and experiencing how to boost livelihood opportunities with increased income in rural population through means to develop rural support infrastructure, marketing systems, government policy initiatives and various other interventions. Interaction meetings between business delegations were organized to further strengthen the understanding of the service outsourcing industry and learn to understand international service outsourcing experience in order to promote the service outsourcing enterprise to develop the outsourcing market. A high level delegation from China Electronics Corporation too visited India. Study tours from India have visited both China and Hong Kong. Several such trade and investment delegations from various industry verticals and Indian states to China in coming months have been planned. A 60-member Indian services sector delegation participated in the 3rd China International Fair for Trade in Services (CIFTIS) in May-June 2014, showcasing IT and services sector. This was one of the largest services sector delegation to visit China in recent years represented by verticals of healthcare, media, entertainment, IT and tourism, all being priority sectors for cooperation identified by the inter-governmental Joint Working Group on Trade in Services by Commerce Ministries of both sides. Services Sector is one of the key areas that India is pressing China to open up its markets, especially IT products, to address the trade deficit stretching to US\$ 35 billion in China's favour. China sponsored a visit by a group of Indian journalists to China from 29 June to 5th July 2014, which interacted

with Chinese Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Defence Ministry, China institution of international Studies, All-China Journalists Association, China Daily and few military units and institutions:

Visit of President Xi

There was great euphoria in India prior to the Visit by President Xi Jinping but then came the Chinese intrusions. That China has been resorting to such intrusions even earlier during high level visits is not the point. This time it was certainly not expected with PM Modi's personal rapport with the Chinese leadership? In his meeting with Prime Minister Narendra Modi in Brazil during July 2014, President Xi Jinping had said that as the two biggest developing countries and emerging markets, both China and India are in a great historical process of realizing national rejuvenation; thus, what the two countries value most is peace and development, and the ideals and goals of the two countries are linked closely. Later Xi Jinping went on record to say, "When India and China speak in one voice, the world will pay attention --The combination of the world's factory and the world's back office will produce the most competitive production base."

Chinese companies have already invested US\$396 million in India, while Chinese companies had executed infrastructure contracts in India worth \$24.7 billion till 2011, cumulative contractual value of these projects

being US\$53.46 billion as per CII estimates. Chinese companies have also been investing in the power sector. Indian markets are flooded with Chinese goods - toys, gaming, sports equipment alone amounting to US\$36.7 million during 2013-2014. It is no secret that China has been eyeing India markets in major way. Just before President Xi Jinping's visit, media talked of a US\$100 billion investment package being brought by him, overshadowing Japan's US\$35 billion investment. But then came a sudden damper to Xi Jinping's visit; some 300 so called Chinese nomads transported by PLA trucks intruding and pitching tents across the LAC in the Depsang Plain a day prior to Xi's arrival in India, and; some thousand odd soldiers of a Chinese Border Regiment (Border Divisions of China are directly under command the PLA) intruding 5-6 kms inside Indian Territory in area of Chumar. That this is part of the archaic CPC standing operating procedure during / close to high level visits is well known: Chinese troops intruded six kms into India in February 1997 following President Jiang Zemin's visit to India preceding December; Chinese intrusion in Arunachal in June 2003 during Vajpayee's visit to PRC; Chinese intrusion in Arunachal in May 2005 in aftermath of PM Wen Jibao's visit to India; just prior to President Hu Jintao's visit in November 2006, Chinese Ambassador Sun Yuxi announced entire Arunachal belonged to Chian, and; prolonged Chinese intrusion in Depsang Plains prior to and during PM Li Keqiang's visit to India in May 2013. It is well known that all these intrusions are orchestrated by the CCP to show their claims in congruence with Mao's dream, as reiterated by Deng Xiaoping, that Tibet is the palm of China while Ladakh, Sikkim, Bhutan, Nepal and NEFA (read Arunachal) are its fingers. However, in this particular instance, two-timing the Depsang-Chumar intrusions with Xi's visit damaged relations more because of the following: BDCA signed between India and China and promise not to disturb border peace; China's reiteration that border population should not be disturbed - why then 300 so called Chinese nomads being transported in PLA trucks deep into Depsang Plains; relationship that PM Narendra Modi enjoyed with China CM Gujarat; bonhomie shown by President Xi when he met PM Narendra Modi in Brazil, and; no-nonsense PM Narendra Modi heading a majority government in India and his belief for partnership and peace with all for development and prosperity of all, boosting the Asian Century.

Prime Minister Narendra Modi was explicit in saying that a "climate of mutual trust and confidence; respect for each other's sensitivities and concerns; and, peace and stability in our (India and China) relations and along our borders are essential for us to realize the enormous potential in our relations". Xi's planned US\$100 billion investment in India over

five years already appeared doomed from the beginning with Beijing's refusal to accept the 'one-India' policy while wanting continued Indian commitment to 'one-China', besides other obduracy like stapled visas for residents of Arunachal Pradesh etc. So, in the bargain, what Xi achieved was just a US\$20 billion investment in India over five years, far below contemporary Japan. There is no doubt that President Xi's visit upgraded India-China relations and resulted in the following specifics: Chinese commitment to invest \$20 billion in infrastructure over next five years; invitation to China to invest in manufacturing sector; two Chinese industrial parks will be built in India; new road to Kailash Mansarovar via Nathu La; Mumbai and Shanghai to be twin cities, as also Ahmedabad and Guangzhou; commitment by China to address bilateral trade deficit; facilitation of visit of 10,000 pupils from both countries; Chinese agreement to hold friendly discussions to resolve border issues, and; invitation to PM Modi to visit China next year. Prime Minister Modi raised the issue of the Chinese intrusions in Ladakh and said, there should be peace in Indo-China relations at the borders. If this happens the two nations can realize true potential". Xi did say that "China and India are two key nations in the multi-polar world. The two nations share similar developing goals". However, the atmosphere was marred by the Chinese intrusions. On balance, it appears that a historic opportunity perhaps has been missed.

Way Forward

The world is watching with interest the changes that would come about in the world's largest democracy, together with India's foreign policy and international relations, particularly India-China relations and its resultant effect on the course that Asia would take. But if Prime Minister Narendra Modi is taking India out of its time wrap, it will be contingent upon President Xi Jinping to do likewise and take a call on the CCP changing the old mode of seeking more territory and weigh it against the gains that can accrue by focusing on the issues mentioned herein; territorial mindset despite the euphoria of economic might and military muscle versus strategic gains from a stronger India-China relationship. China has been making every effort to get to the warm waters of the Indian Ocean through Myanmar and difficult and turbulent regions of Pakistan. India is directly South and access to Indian ports should be lucrative enough compared to expanding territorial ambitions. Amicable resolution of border can enable Russia-China-India energy and transportation corridors linking China to Indian ports via Nepal, Sikkim (Nathu La on the already agreed alternative route to Kailash-Mansarovar) and other mutually agreed routes. India is a sub-continental power and

will certainly not subjugate its national security interests in favor of any other country. Mutual understanding of the population of the two ancient civilizations also needs to be worked upon. China with its fully state controlled media is better poised to educate her masses yet only 23 percent Chinese have a positive view of India whereas 36 percent Indians view China positively, according to a BBC World Service Poll conducted in 2013.

True powering of India-China relations can happen with closer cooperation between India and China, political resolution of the border mutually acceptable to both, which in turn would unleash infinite scope for cooperation benefiting population of both countries. Today the bilateral trade itself today is lopsided, India's trade deficit vis-a-vis China having peaked to US\$ 35 billion, which must be corrected. Dumping of Chinese goods into the Indian market has shut down many small-scale industries, increasing unemployment. However, the prospects in industrialization in both countries are gigantic, as is the scope of Chinese investments in infrastructure in India. Following the visit and aftermath of President Xi's visit, the ball is actually in China's court. While reflection, discussion and resolution must be focused upon to actually kick start the new phase of strategic cooperation, Prime Minister Modi's visit to China (perhaps next year) would provide another golden opportunity to elevate the relationship, benefiting both countries. Year 2014 is being observed by both countries as the 'Year of Friendly Exchanges' to step up engagement on various fronts. India has launched its biggest year long cultural festival in China called 'Glimpses of India' this year. The prospects in industrialization in both countries are gigantic, as is the scope of Chinese investments in infrastructure in India. Time has arrived to resolve outstanding issues and kick start a new phase of strategic cooperation, which would mutually benefit both countries immensely, ushering a new chapter in Asian history.

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4. India and China: A “Pair” in the Making

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India and China, the two most populous countries, are perhaps condemned to understand each other and live together, i.e., overcoming their traditional military rivalry (which is thought to have peaked in the border war of 1962). It is now a mutual necessity for them to peacefully resolve their territorial disputes and develop deeper economic ties.

Two key factors have contributed to the improved understanding between these countries. First, there is a growing convergence between their foreign policies and strategic interests, as we have seen in recent years in forums such as the G20 and the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) economic grouping. India and China are both advocates of multilateralism and multipolarity as keys to regional and global stability and both have prioritized the need to combat poverty and raise their per capita income levels. Second, there is an economic complementarity between the two countries which is expected to significantly increase in the future. This article argues that this complementarity is important and ever growing, to the degree that one can speak of a “Chindia” in the making.

Trade In Goods

The first striking fact is that bilateral trade in goods between India and China has grown considerably in recent years, which in itself is a sign of growing complementarity and division of labor. It grew from just \$3 billion in 2000 to \$63 billion in 2010, and further improved to \$73.9 billion in 2011. Both countries have set a trade target of \$100 billion in 2015, which appears reachable barring some catastrophe or a drop in the level of trust. This trade has been, is and will probably remain based upon a “vertical” type of transnational division of labor, i.e., China exchanges manufactured goods for India’s raw materials. We cannot totally rule out the possibility that India will also begin exporting a

significant quantity of manufactured products to China one day, though, and this trade would be of an inter-industry rather than an intra-industry nature.

According to UN Comtrade Database, exports from India to China and India's imports from China are substantially different in nature. India's main exports to its eastern neighbor are mainly iron ore, nonferrous metals and textile fibers (especially cotton). In contrast, its imports from China are mainly telecommunication equipment, electrical and industrial machinery and equipment needed to generate electricity.

Between 2007 and 2011 the value of India's exports to China increased from \$14.6 billion to \$23.4 billion, but that of imports from China grew even faster, from \$24 billion to \$50.5 billion, according to data from Comtrade. Therefore, in 2011 India ran a \$27.1 billion deficit in its trade with China.¹

Indian official statistics differ in part from those provided by Comtrade Database. According to the DGCIS, the official Indian source of trade information, India's deficit with China has grown from \$16,270 billion in 2007-08 to \$39,650 billion in 2011-12, equivalent to 2% of GDP. India's bilateral trade deficit with China is an important factor driving India's effort to change the traditional structure of its exports to China, which includes rice, medicines, automobiles, services and Information and Communications Technology (ICT). On the import side, there have been cases of Indian protectionism in recent years, such as anti-dumping measures and the higher tariffs imposed on electrical machinery purchases from China.

The reason for India's concern however is not so much the deficit with China as its total trade deficit, which has increased from \$13 billion in 2000 to \$150 billion (6% of GDP) in 2011, despite strong growth in exports (by 19.3% on average between 2000 and 2011, almost as great as the 20.1% average in China during that period). The deficit with China accounts for less than 20% of the total deficit, while the energy import component covers no less than 65%. However, if we exclude energy, the deficit with China is equivalent to more than half of the total deficit.

Bilateral Trade in Services

As is well known, India has an advantage over China in the export of ICT. Although in 2012 China's total service exports (\$190 billion) were higher than India's (\$148 billion), ICT exports accounted for 49% of total exports in China, while 70% in India.²

The risk faced by India is an excessive concentration of its exports in the ICT sector. It is not advisable to rely exclusively on this sector to absorb the problem of surplus agricultural labor. India, therefore, must develop its industrial sector to balance its labor market.³

In the computer software and services sector, India occupies a larger share (8%) of the world market than China (6%), despite the important gap in GDP per capita between the two countries. Not surprisingly, the leaders in this sector are the United States (39%), Europe (34%) and Japan (12%). With regards to computer software and services exports, the main difference between India and China is that the U.S. is the main buyer of Indian products (accounting for 52% of its ICT exports in 2011-12), followed by the UK (21%), Canada (4%) and Germany (2%). In contrast, China's main customers were very similar to those who bought Chinese manufactured goods (the EU, U.S. and ASEAN)⁴

Foreign Direct Investment

The volume of cross-border investments is extremely small, considering the size of the two countries' GDP and FDI. It is estimated that in 2011 Chinese FDI stock in India was only \$580 million (only 0.14% of the total FDI inflow) while Indian FDI stock in China was significantly less, at \$460 million.⁵ China was only India's 30th largest investor between April 2000 and June 2013. Only 10 Chinese companies have built, or are building, factories in India and approximately 100 have offices with representatives. These figures pale when compared to the total inward FDI in China (\$366 billion) and India (\$111 billion) in 2011. Countries like the United Kingdom, with \$22 billion in foreign direct investment in India, Japan with \$17 billion, The Netherlands with \$13 billion, and even debt-stricken Spain, with \$1.9 billion, are much more active than China in the Indian market. Most of the inward FDI in China comes from other Asian countries and is concentrated in the manufacturing sector, while the bulk of India's inward FDI originates from the U.S. and Europe and is concentrated in services.

During his three-day visit to India in September 2014 President Xi Jinping pledged to try to remedy this imbalance. The Chinese President promised that China will make \$100 billion in investments over the next five years, essentially to build industrial parks and bullet trains. This is reflective of India's growing appetite for everything Chinese, from phones to machinery.⁶

Will There Be Complementarity?

Many analysts estimate that manufactured products will soon form the

bulk of India's exports, a change that could adversely affect China's industrial sector given the difference in wages between the two countries. In 2011, the monthly average salary in each country was estimated to be \$656 in China and \$295 in India. Some analysts also believe that China could soon replicate its extraordinary success in exporting finished goods overseas in the ICT sector, thereby coming into direct competition with Indian ICT exports. This thesis suggests that China and India will progressively compete with one another – in domestic and foreign markets – at a much higher level than currently.

However, despite some forays into manufactured goods exports (for example in the automotive industry), India is not likely to compete with China in the manufacturing sector any time soon. The causes of this are many, but the primary one is that China's industrial sector is much more competitive than India's, as competitiveness is not only related to wage levels but also productivity levels. This comparative advantage is likely to remain, as China has made considerable progress in recent years in establishing a transport and communications infrastructure in the countryside. The jump in Chinese salaries, currently happening in the coastal industrial regions, will not necessarily translate into a relocation of foreign businesses from China since there are already cheaper places to produce industrial goods, such as Vietnam, Cambodia, Malaysia or Indonesia.

On the other hand, a major growth in China's ICT exports is unlikely. China has several disadvantages in this sector compared with India: it lacks qualified engineers and programmers, staff with good English proficiency are a rarity, there are not enough dynamic private ICT enterprises such as India's Wipro, Infosys, TCS, etc., and the fast-growing domestic market, the result of higher purchasing power and the refocusing of Beijing's economic policy towards domestic demand, has had the effect of boosting domestic consumption rather than exports.

With respect to FDI, India and China are competing to attract it and likely to remain doing so for some time. FDI in China is much higher than in India (\$127 billion in China and \$28 billion India in 2013, according to UNCTAD).⁷ The source countries/regions of FDI in both China and India are very diverse. India's main investors, not excluding tax haven countries, are Singapore, the United Kingdom, Japan, the United States, the Netherlands, Cyprus, Germany, France and the UAE. For its part, China receives most of its investments from other Asian countries. Hong Kong, Singapore and Japan are top of the list, followed by the United States, South Korea, Taiwan, the Netherlands, France and

Germany. Finally, foreign investors have different sectoral preferences: they invest in the industrial sector in the case of China, while focusing more on the service sector (software and telecommunications) in India.

Political Collaboration

In September 2014, Chinese President Xi Jinping promised Prime Minister Narendra Modi and the Indian people to take Sino-Indian relations to a “new level”. In March 2012, Hu Jintao and Prime Minister Manmohan Singh declared that year to be the “Year of India-China Friendship and Cooperation” in order to strengthen their bilateral relationship. Hu presented a five-point plan to improve this relationship: more high-level contacts, enhanced cooperation, promotion of cultural and people-to-people (P2P) relations, ironing out differences to ensure more peaceful and stable relations and more coordination in international affairs and forums. The latter objective has been in large part achieved, since India and China collaborate meaningfully in forums such as the G20 and the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa).⁸

But in September 2014 Prime Minister Modi was more reticent towards the Chinese offer to intensify bilateral cooperation. Three issues are of great concern to the Indian government: increasing Chinese investment in India, especially in infrastructure projects; agreements to enhance Indian export to China and in this way reduce India’s trade deficit with the “Middle Kingdom”; and the urgent resolution of the longstanding border dispute dating back to 1962. The latter issue cast a shadow over Xi’s visit, as Modi’s government claimed that the Chinese army had made incursion near Chumar in the disputed Ladakh/Aksai Chin region just a few days before Xi’s arrival.

One of Xi’s objectives in visiting India was to counter Washington’s and Tokyo’s efforts to strategically isolate China in South and East Asia. The U.S. and Japan have hasten their anti-China agenda since Modi’s election in May 2014. At the end of August of the same year Modi went on a five-day tour of Japan during which New Delhi and Tokyo elevated their relationship to a “Special Strategic Global Partnership”. A week later, Modi was in Washington where he received an enthusiastic welcome from the Obama Administration. For the past decade, U.S. administrations have aggressively curried favor with India, Japan and Australia in order to contain the economic and military expansion of China. Military assistance has been offered to India to boost its presence in the Indian Ocean, Southeast Asia, the South China Sea and Central Asia. In the months leading up to Modi’s trip to Washington, American

officials sought to convince New Delhi to agree on the integration of the two countries' militaries through the joint development and production of advanced weapons systems.

Aware of U.S.-Japanese political and military maneuvers in India, Beijing is making every effort to thwart them. The Chinese President repeated to his Indian counterpart that India should see only benefits from closer commercial ties with China. He pledged to invest \$20 billion in India's infrastructure, especially railways and industrial parks, over the next five years. China is now India's largest external trade partner, but in 2013 India's current account balance with China ran a deficit of \$30 billion. Xi promised to taken steps to tackle this trade problem by removing obstacles to imports from India, particularly of agricultural products and pharmaceuticals, an industry in which India is a world leader.

A \$20 billion investment in infrastructure would certainly bring Sino-Indian economic ties to another level. However huge, this sum of money, some analysts in the Indian media complained, is still less than the \$35 billion Japan promised in August 2014.

Since 2000, Chinese companies' total investments in India have reached only \$400 million. Indian officials, because of security concerns, have repeatedly put up obstacles to Chinese investment, particularly in infrastructure projects. The Modi government promises to quickly implement governance reforms and that should facilitate Chinese investment. However, it is unlikely that New Delhi and Beijing will reach an agreement similar to one with Japan, according to which "two Japanese officials will be appointed to a special branch of Modi's Prime Minister's Office devoted to expediting Japanese investments".⁹

In September 2014 Xi invited India to work with China on the "Maritime Silk Road" project. This project consists of building port facilities and road and rail transport networks in South and Southeast Asia with the objective of gaining access to fossil energy and other raw materials together with boosting trade. But Modi did not react favorably to this invitation. American officials speculate that the "Maritime Silk Road", which they had previously dubbed the "String of Pearls," aims at building facilities to increase China's military presence in the Indian Ocean region. India's military-security establishment concurs with the American claims and that can explain New Delhi's reluctance to participate in the Maritime Silk Road project.

The Chinese are also interested in establishing a stronger partnership with the Indian on the world stage, particularly in international forums

like the IMF and the G20. “Both China and India are influential countries in the world. When our two nations speak with one voice, the whole world will listen attentively,”¹⁰ declared Xi in one of his speeches. Xi demonstrated his good intentions with a pledge to support India’s full membership in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), a regional alliance led by China and Russia and established to counter the U.S.’s expanding influence in Central and South Asia. Currently, India has only observer status in the SCO.

Despite these laudable statements of good intent, there are striking deficiencies and idiosyncrasies in India-China relations. For instance, there are no direct flights between Mumbai and Beijing or Shanghai, in part because tourism is almost nonexistent between the two countries – only about half a million people pass from one country to the other every year. Also, given the low level of bilateral trade, it makes little sense that India has approved restrictions on imports from China, such as anti-dumping measures and higher tariffs on telecommunications products and electrical machinery. Even more questionable is India’s decision to restrict rice sales to China, justified by the inadequate internal supply of this commodity, which tends to be only occasional (dependent on monsoon rain). More generally, Indians have an excessive fear of an invasion of low-priced Chinese manufactured goods, which could interrupt the development of the infant Indian industrial sector; despite all indications that the era of cheap Chinese exports may be drawing to a close. But according to the Indian elite, equally threatening, for national security reasons, are Chinese direct investments.

Tendencies

Nevertheless, there remains an intrinsic complementarity between the two economies. The most optimistic Indian analysts estimate that India could soon develop a powerful industrial export sector, especially since China is on the verge of transforming its economy from a labor-intensive and low-technology one to a capital-intensive, high value-added and high-technology-based one. They also believe that China’s massive investments in health care and education will require the purchasing of considerable amounts of medical products, equipment and pharmaceutical products. This situation suits India well, as it has a comparative advantage in these areas. India has a knowledge-based economy, and therefore China will also be ready to access some of the hundreds of millions of English training manuals it produces. In addition, India is able to provide legal consulting services and has global

level marketing and advertising expertise. According to that analysis, India could greatly benefit from the continuing boom in China.

While the massive export of Indian health care and pharmaceutical products is a plausible scenario, India, however, has still a long way to go before it can massively produce and export the labor-intensive and low-technology products China also requires. The countries with the greatest capacity to benefit from growth in this sector of Chinese demand are Vietnam, Indonesia, Bangladesh and Myanmar, not India. For instance, the manufacturing sector accounts for 27% of Indonesia's GDP, 20% of Vietnam's and 18% of Bangladesh's, while in India this indicator is only 15%.¹¹ In addition, although the decline in labor-intensive and low-technology Chinese coastal industries is becoming more apparent, it is still possible that these industries will move to the interior of the country where a huge unskilled population is still to be tapped.

The view that India is a future China in the making and that China will soon become the main international ICT supplier is not supported by evidence. On the other hand, the booming bilateral trade in goods (\$73.9 billion in 2011 to \$100 billion in 2015), the expanding trade in capital goods (iron, nonferrous metals and fiber versus machinery, tools, buildings and other capital goods), and India's determination to reduce the bilateral deficit (through the sale of more rice, medicines, automobiles, and ICT services) are signs that point towards a process of gradually increasing complementarity and division of labor between India and China. Within a decade or two the world economy could be characterized as one economy called "Chindia" rather than "Chinamerica".

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5. India: Mountains/Rivers in Perils and Eco-politics

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“Both China and India all have a rather profound knowledge about ourselves, our nature and human future, but slowly and pitifully slide into oblivion.”

Rationale of Study

Based on academic conferences participated by the author during 2009-2013, this paper intends to pontificate some cognitive schemata shared by anthropological conference-attenders, as represented by their presentations, conference interval talks, after-conference mingling and conferences literatures; all vividly narrate a “Traidhatu” (The three realms in Tibetan language, which means desire realm, the form realm, and the formless realm) they trying to negotiate and a socio-cultural inertia propels jarringly different trajectories amid East Asian countries with cultural similarities.

The crisis of Asia and discrepancies of East Asia Anthropology, in this sense, is the crisis of “subject”, as people differ at their id, ego, and super-ego levels -- all corresponding to the aforementioned three different realms in spiritual sphere.

These conferences were held in Japan, Singapore, Thailand, India, China, Hong Kong, Korea, Vietnam and Nepal, all participated, partly or entirely, by anthropologists; the author will use some fieldwork data generated from Thailand, India and Myanmar to corroborate the reflections based on conference ethnographies.

To dub this narration and analysis as “Chrono-logical-ly”, is the author’s intents of referring some evidences generated from conferences taking place at different locales that have been superseded, transposed, and

dislocated; these materials have been reproduced according to the logical clues of ethnographic data gleaned at different stage of fieldwork.

State of Ecology of The Tibetan Plateau

Scientists, technical experts, experienced diplomats and senior administrators from India, China, the Tibetan Plateau and neighbouring countries met in Delhi in private roundtable over three days to consider the prospects of consensus on problems affecting the ecology of the Tibetan Plateau, and future policy directions on transboundary issues. Such transboundary gatherings are unfortunately rare.

The 50 hand picked roundtable participants gathered at the invitation of the Foundation for Nonviolent Alternatives (FNVA), for intensive consideration of the bigger picture, transcending the narrow concerns of separate states.

A common language, and common understanding emerged, in which the Himalayas and Tibet, rather than dividing India and China, unite them. On a wide range of issues, from rural livelihoods to the sharing of the waters originating in Tibet, and drunk daily by 1.4 billion people; from the dynamics of development to the militarization of the high mountains, commonalities emerged.

This FNVA roundtable, from 28 to 30 March, 2014, expressed its deep concern that a realm of traditional land management, indigenous knowledge, light touch nomadic mobility, respect for nature and a last frontier of pristine landscapes, is rapidly becoming, on all sides, the object of national development strategies aiming at intensive resource extraction, water impoundment and channeling, exclusion zones nullifying viable customary livelihoods, irreversible biodiversity loss and the redefinition of the whole Himalayan/Tibetan Plateau region to serve the needs of distant downstream communities, chiefly for water, electricity and raw materials.

The prospects for greater official participation, and contributions from governments of the region were discussed. In the absence of established multilateral forums in the region, semi-official forums could achieve much. The many scientists involved have immediate opportunity to build not only data sharing but also collaborative projects.

Drawing on the professional experience of participants able to balance short term gain with longer term consequences, this FNVA roundtable drew to the attention of all regional governments the following specific concerns(to be omitted for brevity).

- Attenders were primarily anthropologists, glacier specialists, natural scientists, environmentalists, governmental officials, strategists and religion practitioners

The gist of this conference, as its manifesto evoked, is mainly the discussion the dire future confronting all the people connected by international mountain ridges and watersheds, and contemplating possible ways to break the current barriers which make cooperation, exploration, communication and collaboration hard to achieve.

Tibetan refugees delegates were also invited to this conference, sharing their understanding of sacred mountains and deities reside in the mountain ridges and along these international watersheds.

Like many other international conferences with an aim to influence or inform the potential policy makers, this conference has gradually been morphed into different knowledge clusters and opinion groups. Once clusters, groups and modules have been formed, each participants, discussants and presenters have to follow an invisible structure, while pinging information into the dark box of knowledge clusters and academic blocs.

Within this occasion and in my presentation, a Mundellian “development trilemma” is proposed as a globalization conundrum and an impossible trinity, in order to describe the deeply entrenched water crisis in Asia settings and three elements of “development” running afoul with each other erstwhile deteriorated into a vicious circle (a triangle of impossible trinity).

The three elements of impossible trinity can be summarized as following:

A: development based on infinite growth and material abundance presupposition -- a free flow of “modernity” and a “civilized juggernaut”.

B: prosperity accessible to all (fantasy) and one “fluid” development/modernity paradigm fits all – “development by the people, for the people and of the people”; an ever-lasting exchange process between nature resources and artificial knowledge concoctions.

C: nature conservancy and continuity of cultural heritage -- a “stateless” global village where miscellaneous cultures converge and intermingle versus a myriad of “sovereign tribes” where culture “fossilized” and encrusted by incremental development sugar coats.

In order to use network analysis, anthropological method and holistic approaches to unravel the *imponderabilia* of global interconnectedness and liquid modernity, this research intends to analyze the development failure in SW China through a few concepts stemmed from Chinese contexts.

In macroeconomic management, policy makers must face a trade-off of simultaneously choosing two, not all, of the three policy choices: monetary independence, exchange rate stability, and financial openness. This famous hypothesis in international finance is a fundamental

contribution of the Mundell-Fleming framework, which is better known as ‘impossible trinity’, or the ‘Trilemma’.

As it could be problematic when we move around concepts from one sphere to another, disassociating/disembedding them from the intertwined and jargons-specific contexts; this paper intends to be more vigilant on the concepts’ expansion of ‘trilemma’, (rather than) in a strict economic sense, focuses more on using this Mundellian triangulation method to re-examine some ethnographic phenomenon collected from Southwest China.

We are witnessing in Asian contexts – including many other geographical locales – people start to use an unorthodox approach to address their problems which I entitle it as “ignolledge”. Take China as an example, ignolledge is one kind of power that cannot be dissociated from decision-making and control over the political agenda, and can be used to address contestations between different countries or interest groups within countries. Moreover, it is oriented towards an effort to revive a past prosperity, to erase a historical stigma and to usher in a socialist renaissance in a comprehensive way, and all current and potential issues, and overt and latent conflicts, may be addressed through this packaged ‘knowledge’. In the end, the use of ignolledge realizes many goals, these being:

- (i) the domination of power and its manipulation over resources,
- (ii) the capability to harness organizational and physical power to its own ends,
- (iii) the compliance of previously discordant voices from the non-governmental sphere, and (iv) the production of power.

According to Foucault, when compared to repression, “production” is positive in the sense that it “traverses and produces things, it induces pleasure, forms knowledge, produces discourse and more specifically, it produces ‘subjects’, forging their character and normalizing them.” The transfer of water from the Three Parallel Rivers area (Nu River, Jinsha River and Lancang River) might eventually be conducive to the expansion of Kunming and the ‘Dian civilization’, strengthening their influence within the Greater Kunming region and realizing the seafaring dreams of Zheng He and his journeys across the Kunyang Ocean (Dianchi Lake) and beyond, a mentality which lives within local people and local political ambitions. In ‘The Anthropology of Power’, Angela Cheater summarizes the inconsistency of Foucault’s descriptions of power, by drawing-upon another definition of power given by Foucault; “Power in the substantive sense, le pouvoir, doesn’t exist...power means...a more-or-less organized, hierarchical, co-ordinated cluster of relations.”

By creating the new phrases and concept of political other shore, I can describe the large amount of scientific and endemic knowledge being incorporated into a final theoretical structure, that which constitutes the essential fiber of ignoledge. In addition, the construction of political other shore allows for, at least superficially, community participation, peer review, empowerment, and a “people-focused approach...listening to the voices of the poor”, as described in *Empowering Ambiguities* by Wendy James¹, who points out that “on the evidence of the Oxford English Dictionary (1971), ‘empower’ as a verb is, in itself, not new, but well established, having, since the seventeenth century, meant ‘to invest legally or formally with power or authority; to authorize, license’, or ‘to impart or bestow power to an end or for a purpose; to enable, permit’.”² The political other shore, in this circumstance, is also used to empower the public, to justify the ignoledge and to facilitate the textual governance; it imparts or bestows power to ignoledge and enables textual governance. Those suspicious of ignoledge are particularly alarmed by the “hazards versus providentiality” situation, as defined by Ulrich Beck in *Risk Society and the Provident State*, hazards resulting from the decisions made (in a residual risk society).³

The most problematic part of ignoledge is the fact that it is not self-critical, but self-worshiping and self-reverential. Political other shore strengthens ignoledge as a power through moral and aesthetical justification, and the “scientific” aspects of textual governance merely reinforce ignoledge through technocratic and theoretical calculation.

Out of these liquid ‘trilemma’, the ignoledge should be treated as darkening light and concealed alētheia when memory persists and time melts, turning lithe, supple and fluid-like: as powerfully captured by Salvador Dali in his *La persistencia de la memoria*.

Discussions

Based on my fieldwork experience from 2007-2013 and para-ethnographic data presented above, when we discuss the so called East Asian Anthropology Community or any regional commons in Asian settings, I think some basic concepts such as East Asia, Southeast Asia, South Asia have all changed, re-oriented and reproduced.

It becomes extremely difficult to construe us belonging to one group that is based on geographical modules and ensembles; when we are culturally, spiritually and idea-topologically disoriented, it’ll be difficult for us to apply traditional topos-specific concepts to define us and orient us toward a common cause.

To be more specific, the English word “compass” is literally addressed as “South Pointing Needle” in Chinese, it’ll be difficult for the Physical and

geographical “South Pointing Needle” to keep pointing us a fixated direction, when our hermeneutical magnetic field changed.

In reality, occasioned in international conferences and many political consultation situations, we often find the old South Pointing Compass, which based on traditional destiny bindings and *zuqun* (tribes, moieties, ethnic groups) coils can no longer give us a correct answer.

Like the examples that I have given, although we (Asian people) share many resemblances physiologically and physiognomically, the myriad and variegated “mini-selves” – in cognitive, psychological and cultural perception senses – reside in Southeast Asian people have been repackaged and “trans-genetically” reproduced.

According to my shallow understanding of linguistics, “Compass” in English, derived from old French, which means, “make a circuit of, to surround and encircle”; obviously, this gadget or concept is closely related to the prototypical ideas of boundary, cartography and ownership.

Imagining yourself to have a conversation with an ambitious ancient Chinese emperor, if you ask what your majesty intends to conquer, he will cursorily tell you: The South (The West, The East or The North) or I relish the self-effacing allegiance from The South. However, it’ll be really “negotiable” where the Furthest or Truly South (boundary, line, border, territory) is.

To finish this with one caveat in historical setting, during Yuan Dynasty (1271 AD.-1368 AD.), according to Mongolian’s rigid classification system, all the Han Chinese who has forsaken their “hereditary and deity-given boundaries” for allegiance toward “barbarian Mongols”, being entirely put into one category, entitled as Nanren (People from The South).

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**6. Climate Change and the Quest for Hydrocarbons:
Indian and Chinese Energy Security Imperatives**

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Introduction

The Asian continent increasingly is being regarded as the centre of geopolitical, geostrategic and geoeconomic developments. At the turn of the twenty-first century, global attention shifted to two countries – China and India – as they began to assert themselves in more than one arena. However, the way forward is not a cakewalk for both countries. Both countries face immense challenges due to threats emanating from energy (in)security and climate change among others. On the one hand, the growing water requirements of the manufacturing sector, urbanisation, climate change, ground water extraction, deforestation, pollution, over-exploitation of land and many other environmental concerns could derail the growth stories of the two countries in future. On the other, energy management has gained salience in both India and China in the current scenario as the energy requirements of both countries have been rising rapidly. Their energy consumption is expected to grow further in the years to come taking into consideration the growing population and the expected growth in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Any growing economy can sustain its growth only if it has a reliable supply of energy, usually in the form of electricity, gas and petroleum products. Limited domestic reserves of fossil fuels has forced the two countries to explore and acquire resources from abroad. These fossil fuels emit large amount of greenhouse gases (GHGs) that are touted as the single biggest cause for global warming and climate change. Thus, the urge to adopt cleaner and efficient fuels and technologies is strengthening year after year. Yet, the drive for acquiring hydrocarbon resources has not ceased.

As India and China take more steps towards mitigating the effects of climate change by investing in renewable energy technologies, the very same effects of this phenomenon have direct implications for hydrocarbon availability, exploration and security. Climate change could open up new reserves of hydrocarbons (mainly oil and natural gas) as well as change the geophysical features of resource-rich regions – both of which could have political ramifications. This could potentially spark fresh conflict between nation states that have historically fought wars over resources. Second order impacts of climate change include alterations of maritime boundaries including exclusive economic zones (EEZ) that could affect nation states' claims to resource-rich regions in the seas. This paper makes a modest attempt at analysing the behavioural patterns of China and India with respect to their requirement of hydrocarbons, especially in the Arctic and the disputed South China Sea. Discovery of resources in the Arctic due to climate change (melting of ice and thawing of the permafrost), and the question

of sovereignty over the disputed islands of the South China Sea dictated by the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) that could well be altered with the disappearance of some of the islands caused by sea-level rise, are worth revisiting.

Energy Trends of China and India

Like any other country, China's high energy requirements are inextricably linked to its growth rate (8-10 per cent). Since 2000, China's requirement for oil has been increasing at the rate of 10 per cent per annum.¹ Since 1990, its energy requirements have risen manifold, forcing it to import energy resources to meet them. It became the second largest consumer of oil by 2003 after the US,² and the second largest importer of oil, overtaking Japan by 2009.³ Currently, nearly half of the oil which China consumes is imported as China's current domestic supplies are nowhere near its demands. It has only 16 billion barrels of proven domestic oil reserves, which is only 1.2 per cent of the world's proven reserves. Along with importing oil for short term requirements, Chinese companies have been investing in foreign oil firms which would ensure oil supplies in the long run.⁴ Future projections suggest a rise in oil imports up to 73 per cent by 2025, which equals almost that of Europe, even though China has committed itself to limit the import of oil at 60 per cent.⁵ Estimates also reveal that it could overtake the US to become the world's largest oil consumer by 2030.⁶ This has driven China into adopting a multi-pronged strategy. First, China has established channels of hydrocarbon diplomacy with resource-rich regions; it has started to look beyond the resource-rich West Asia that is in the middle of a geopolitical turmoil. Second, China has shifted its attention to the goal of diversifying its energy mix by investing heavily in nuclear and renewable energy. Third, China has and is still focussing on implementation of policies to slow oil consumption growth such as increasing taxes on transport fuels, energy efficiency as well as population control (One-child policy).

As far as India is concerned, according to the US Energy Information Administration (EIA), coal/peat accounts for 41 per cent of India's total energy consumption; solid biomass and waste, 23 per cent; petroleum, 23 per cent; natural gas, 8 per cent; nuclear and renewables, 5 per cent. It has now become the fourth largest energy consumer in the world after the US, China and Russia.⁷ While talking about India's energy policy, besides the energy mix, it is equally important to emphasise its heavy dependence on imports to meet its energy demands. India's growth is theoretically and practically, determined by factors such

as international markets, availability of global energy reserves, production capacities and geopolitics. For example, the major oil and natural gas rich region of Persian Gulf/West Asia is currently highly politically unstable in the light of the civil war in Syria and the escalating threat of the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria in Iraq and the rest of the region, leading to a surge in crude prices. These factors could potentially choke energy supply to India. India imports 79 per cent of its oil requirements while China, roughly 40 per cent.⁸ The chief suppliers of oil for India are Saudi Arabia, Iran, Nigeria, Iraq, Kuwait, United Arab Emirates, Malaysia and Yemen. In the natural gas sector, India imports about 15 per cent of its total requirements. India's natural gas imports are on the rise with the Petroleum Ministry estimating that in 2014-15, imports (115 mmscmd) will exceed domestic production (113 mmscmd).⁹ India also imports coal from countries such as Australia, Indonesia, South Africa and the US. The Planning Commission has projected the imports to touch 185 MT by 2017 as compared to 137 MT by the end of the Eleventh Five Year Plan (2007-12).¹⁰

A study of the International Energy Agency (IEA) reveals three important projections: first, India's primary energy demand will be more than double by 2030, growing an average 3.6 per cent every year; second, India will become the third largest net importer of oil before 2025 after the US and China; and third, net oil imports will rise to 6 million barrels per day in 2030.¹¹ The Hydrocarbon Vision 2025 lays out an investment strategy that entails around \$40 billion to \$50 billion across the value chain, which would result in a jump in the contribution of natural gas in total energy consumption from 8-20 per cent by 2025. The increase in India's oil production has been negligible – from 0.7 million barrels per day in 1990 to about 1 million barrels per day in 2009. Although, the discovery of oil in KG basin by reliance and in Rajasthan by Cairn energy could add appreciably to the domestic production, India would still be heavily dependent on oil imports.¹²

Implications of Climate Change for Hydrocarbon-related Energy Security

As India and China set out to acquire resources from different parts of the world to meet its burgeoning energy requirements, one factor, namely climate change is expected to play an important role in its global hydrocarbon policy. Seldom do researchers do look into the impact of climate change on hydrocarbon security of nation states as the focus is mostly on mitigation of climate change by shifting from carbon-intensive fossil fuels to cleaner sources of energy such as renewables and nuclear.

However, the interconnectedness between environmental security, climate change and energy security does not stop at this. The international security environment is so fluid and complex that very minute changes in the geophysical features of the earth could have far-reaching geopolitical and geoeconomic ramifications. Climate change is not only realigning but also opening up new paths of exploring and extracting hydrocarbons that have dictated world politics for long.

The South China Sea

Sovereignty over the South China Sea is a bone of contention between the littoral states and will remain so in the coming years, especially due to the presence of unproven deposits of oil and natural gas in the region. According to the US Energy Information Administration, nearly 28 billion barrels of oil and 25 trillion cubic metres of natural gas are present in the South China Sea.¹³ China's historical claim (based on the 'nine dotted lines') over more than 80 per cent of the region has been met with criticism and opposition from the other countries such as Vietnam, the Philippines, Brunei, Taiwan and Malaysia. More than two dozen military clashes have occurred in this region since 1974 when the Paracel Islands were seized by China from Vietnam.¹⁴ The South China Sea is now being projected by Beijing as a "core interest," alongside Taiwan, Tibet and Xinjiang. Beijing has been issuing strict warnings against any party that ventures into the region for exploring and extracting the resources. In 2014, a standoff between the Chinese and Vietnamese sides on account of Chinese move to drill in the contested waters (Vietnam's waters according to the UNCLOS but claimed by China) got averted when the Chinese leadership decided to move the drilling rig away from the location.¹⁵

Indian interests in the region are also at stake. China has warned India against undertaking oil and natural gas exploration projects in the South China Sea, alluding to the activities of the ONGC Videsh Limited (OVL) at the offshore Vietnamese hydrocarbon blocks.¹⁶ The OVL has one producing block and one exploration block off the coast of Vietnam. When tensions between the littoral countries were at the peak, the OVL had earlier decided to relinquish its exploration activities in one of the blocks, citing techno-commercial considerations as the block was located at a water depth of more than 400 metres and it found it difficult to anchor the rig on hard sea bottom. However, India and Vietnam have inked an agreement for joint oil and gas exploration, development and production with the latter asserting that the former has the right to pursue such activities in the South China Sea as the assigned blocks lie

in the Vietnamese Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ).¹⁷ The OVL has in fact agreed to start its exploration activities in two to three blocks out of the five offered by Vietnam in the South China Sea, that lie in the area outside the purview of Chinese claims.¹⁸

In 1988, a Chinese article said, “In order to make sure that the descendants of the Chinese nation can survive, develop, prosper and flourish in the world in the future, we should vigorously develop and use the oceans. To protect and defend the rights and interests of the reefs and islands within Chinese waters is a sacred mission....The [Spratly] Islands not only occupy an important strategic position, but every reef and island is connected to a large area of territorial water and an exclusive economic zone that is priceless.”¹⁹ China is a signatory to the United Nations Convention on Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) but its claims go much beyond the 200 nautical mile Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) recognised by the treaty. China has elected 45 legislators to govern the 1,100 people living on the island groups of the Spratlys, the Paracels and the Macclesfield bank as well as approved military deployment to guard islands claimed by India and Vietnam.²⁰

The South China Sea is constituted by atolls, islands and banks that lie only a few inches or feet above sea level at high tide. Sea level rise caused by polar ice melt and expansion of the oceans could lead to the submergence of some of these geographical entities as well as recession of coastlines. According to the UNCLOS, “the default baseline is the normal low water mark, designated in official maps, but the law allows states to set baselines using other mechanisms, such as drawing straight baselines or fixing maritime limits.”²¹ The baseline is the point from which the territorial sea is measured. Boundaries are calculated solely on the basis of land that is above sea-level all the time. As the coastline retreats or as islands disappear, the low water mark retreats. The law does not specify the course of action to be taken in case islands disappear or coastlines retreat except providing the option for arbitration. Thus, it does not take climate change into account.

Figure 1: The United Nations Convention on Law of the Sea

Source: <http://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=File:Zonmar-en.svg&page=1>

Hong Kong's Government has found that the sea level has risen 2.8 mm per year since 1954.²² This implies that climate change has the potential to either end the dispute as the islands that have become a source of tension would no longer exist; or it could complicate existing claims as the boundaries would have to be redefined and fresh

negotiations would have to begin for this purpose. The chances of resolution of the current claims are grim at least in the coming few years. Countries (especially China based on the nine-dotted lines) might choose to freeze their political maritime boundary irrespective of these factors as a pre-emptive measure, which could add fuel to the existing disputes. India, in response might try to build closer ties with Vietnam, which has historically been unfriendly to China as well as other littoral states to gain access to the resources available in the region to add to its energy basket.

The Arctic

The Arctic accounts for about 13 per cent of the world's undiscovered oil, 30 per cent of undiscovered natural gas and 20 per cent of the undiscovered natural gas liquids in the world. Together, they account for almost a quarter of the world's hydrocarbon energy reserves.²³ And with the opening of two major sea routes (due to climate change – rising temperature, thawing of the permafrost, melting of ice and so on) in the Arctic – the North West Passage (NWP) adjacent to the northern coastline of North America and the Northern Sea Route (NSR) along the northern coastline of Eurasia, and primarily controlled by Russia, the voyage from Europe to East Asia would get shortened by one third as compared to the route through the Suez Canal; and the journey from the American East Coast to East Asia by one-fourth as compared to the route through the Panama Canal. The NWP consists of a series of routes meandering through the spaces between the islands of Northern Canada which are more difficult to traverse in comparison to the NSR; this route may not be used in the near future unless the ice retreats to dismal levels or completely.²⁴

China has been working towards its ambitions to explore the Arctic for oil and natural gas. It has been very active in terms of expanding its exploration activities in the region especially since 1995 (when a group of Chinese scientists and journalists undertook an expedition to the North Pole by foot to conduct scientific research).²⁵ Since then, China led four scientific expeditions to the region – in 1999, 2003, 2008 in the Bering and Chukchi seas²⁶ and in 2010, they went as far as 120 nautical miles short of the North Pole by ship. In July 2004, China established an exploration base, the Huanghe research station at Ny-Alesund in the Spitzbergen Island. Chinese Polar experts have participated in the International Polar year programme from March 2007 to March 2009.²⁷ China has planned three research expeditions to the Arctic from 2011 to 2015.²⁸ It possesses an ice-breaker – Xue Long (Snow

Dragon) that became the first Chinese vessel to pass through the NSR via the North Pole and has commissioned another one. It has announced that it would make its first commercial transit of the NSR in 2014.²⁹ China along with several other Asian nations has been inducted as 'permanent observers' in the Arctic Council in 2013.

Another facet of China's policy on the Arctic can be discerned through a statement made by Rear Admiral Yin Zhin, who at the third session of the 11th Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference on March 5, 2010 opined that the UNCLOS, the North Pole and surrounding area are the common wealth of the world's people and do not belong to any one country, and that China must play an indispensable role in Arctic exploration as it has one-fifth of the world's population.³⁰ It calls itself a "near Arctic-state" and an "Arctic stakeholder". It has signed a free trade agreement with Iceland and is building the largest embassy in Greenland, a country known to be extremely rich in rare earths. China National Offshore Oil Corporation has struck a deal with Iceland's Eykon Energy firm to explore off Iceland's Southeast coast. China came to Iceland's rescue when its banking sector was on the verge of an imminent collapse and the European Union was reluctant to support it. Sino-Russian cooperation in the Arctic has taken giant leaps over the years, especially in the energy sector besides the shipping lanes. China has signed deals with Russia's Gazprom and Rosneft to explore oil and gas fields in the Arctic.³¹

India's policy towards the Arctic is not as aggressive as that of China although it has also been anointed as a 'permanent observer' in the Arctic Council. India's interests in the Arctic do not lie in the Northern passages, as it does not stand to benefit as much from them, unlike China, due to its geographic location. India's Arctic observatory – "Himadri" – is located in New Aalesund, Spitsbergen and is the largest research station in Norway's Svalbard archipelago. What India could capitalise in the region is its wealth of resources. India's former Minister of External Affairs, Salman Khurshid is the first minister from the new members of the Arctic Council to visit the Arctic region. India is planning to acquire an icebreaker worth Rs. 800 crore for undertaking scientific and business expeditions in the Polar Regions.³² The OVL has been showing keen interest in acquiring stakes in Russia's Arctic region and in 2013, Russia's Rosneft offered the OVL a stake in two exploration blocks in the northern part of the Sea of Okhotsk in eastern Russia.³³

India's expertise in oil exploration and extraction activities could be used to acquire part of the stakes in hydrocarbon fields, especially the

ones in Russia which Moscow has found difficult to develop due to insufficient experience so far. Moreover, India already has experience in collaborating with the Russians in Siberia, such as in the Sakhalin energy field. This presents India with a unique opportunity to pursue close energy ties with Russia as an alternative to China in the joint exploration of the Arctic oil and gas fields. India could also make inroads into Russia by utilising its expertise in the safe extraction of gas hydrates from the offshore deposits that could become unstable as the oceans warm.³⁴

Conclusion

In the South China Sea, the latter has a major stake while the former's stake is dependent on its relations with the Southeast Asian nations, particularly Vietnam. As far as the Arctic is concerned, both agree that the region is a 'global common' but their outlook towards this concept is diametrically opposite. While India largely maintains that like Antarctica, the Arctic should not be used for any activity except scientific expeditions due to its environmental vulnerabilities, China contends that the resources of the Arctic region belong to the entire world and not just the littoral countries. One could argue that the resources in these regions are plentiful for both countries to get hold of without competing against other each other. However, the conflict over a region with altered territorial waters and exclusive economic zones will be even more complicated for the littoral countries to resolve.

In the case of the South China Sea, which is yet to have a regional arrangement like the Arctic Council, China will have to negotiate with countries like the Philippines, Vietnam and Malaysia among others to get undisputed access to the available resources; India has to deal with an increasingly aggressive China in the region through its diplomatic efforts. In another scenario, a South China Sea Council could be formed by the littoral countries to manage environmental problems such as marine pollution, rescue and shipping. In fact, the genesis of the Arctic Council (1996) could be traced back to the signing of the Arctic Environmental Protection Strategy in 1991.³⁵ In such a scenario, India's chances of acquiring resources in the region would depend on grant of an observer's status to it in the Council among other conditions – both political and legal. Like the Arctic Council, it has to overcome maritime territorial disputes to maintain peace. It should undertake scientific expeditions to study the impacts of climate change in the region, especially on the islands, as well as carry out joint exploration of resources in which India could also participate.

In the case of the Arctic, China has been closely cooperating with the Arctic and India is not far behind when it comes to forging ties with Russia in this regard. Russia is one of the pivotal players in the Arctic region and it is set to benefit most from the opening up of the Arctic sea lanes and resources. Russia-India-China trilateral cooperation (ongoing and prospective) could be a platform for joint exploration of the Arctic for resources. India and China should exploit Russian companies' (Gazprom and Rosneft) "lack of experience of offshore projects at senior level, poor environmental, health and safety track records"³⁶ (in drilling in the Russian Arctic). Russia's resources could fulfil the requirements of energy-deficient India and China. The two countries will continue to compete with each other for better relations with the littoral countries such as Russia and the Nordic countries. Differences with Norway over the Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam (LTTE) issue in Sri Lanka when Norway was a mediator between the LTTE and the Sri Lankan Government and diplomatic fissures with Denmark over the latter's refusal to extradite Kim Davy, the main accused in the 1995 Purulia arms drop case are yet to be fully ironed out by the Indian administration.³⁷ China's relations with Greenland (Denmark) and Iceland are extremely good at this point in time as specified earlier. After three years of estranged relations between China and Norway over the award of the Nobel Peace Prize to Liu Xiaobo (a Chinese "dissident") in 2010 by the Norwegian Nobel Committee, the two countries are close to signing a free trade agreement as well.³⁸ There is also news of possible cooperation between the two in exploring oil in Iceland.³⁹ In short, China has a clear-cut edge over India in the region.

Geopolitically, ties between China and India have been tense. Tensions along the border have now extended to the Indian Ocean over China's growing relations with the countries in the region and even to the South China Sea over India's ambitions to explore oil and gas in the region. In this analysis, China seems to be in a better position than India with its long-term strategic moves to forge strong interdependent ties with countries around the world. At the same time, India is yet to use some of its inherent strengths to enhance its national interest that has energy security as one of its pillars. However, there are ample opportunities for the two Asian giants to come together as well to secure their energy needs. Although the main focus of the policy community should be on mitigating climate change, the second order security impacts of climate change are bound to create prospects for conflict and cooperation that the international community has to take into consideration while shaping climate and energy policies at all levels.

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7. India-China Relations : The United States Factor

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India, the United States of America, and the People's Republic of China; as different as they are, what can we pinpoint as similarities between the three? Geographically and demographically, all three are among the largest countries by landmass and the top three most populated countries of the world. Economically, put together their GDPs combined and they result into the world's biggest economies. With all the geography, demographics, and money in the right place, and an invincible trilateral relationship that could take the world over, the three countries can emerged to be, at least on paper, one of the most powerful groupings on the international scene. Setting all political tensions aside those exist internally among the trio, if the three come together to cooperate, the outcome is a shrewd, well thought-out, tactful relation of strategic importance that could change power dynamics in the world.

But how exactly can this volatile relationship sustain? Too many internal differences mark the scene. India and China are constantly up against each other with India running to match up every advance China makes. The competition is so furious that the two are among the principal spenders on defence merchandise as the neighbours feel constant threat from each other. China with its economy that runs in several trillion US dollars and over billions of people being affected by its development every single day, the Indians are still a good distance from bolstering their efforts enough to match the zenith the Red Dragon has set. However this

does not stop them from making their own advances and taking things in their stride.

This brings in another important factor. As already predicted for 2050, India and China are forecasted to be the largest manufacturing economies. The two also compete for strong economic and political relations with the world's biggest superpower- the United States of America. America and China can obviously be seen as eyeing each other's every move closely as China vies for economic and political hegemony in the world with its large investments in all sectors. With its growing energy investment in Asia and Africa, its 30-year gas deal with the Russian Federation, which happens to be India's Big Brother and U.S.' historic rival since the Cold War days, the People's Republic is surely ruffling some feathers.

India – China Tensions

It is no secret that Asian mega-power neighbours China and India have serious border issues. Minor skirmishes at the border are a regular feature. In fact, the wounds of the issue are so deep that the two even went on a month long war over it in 1962 sending the 1954 '*Panchsheel*' (Five Principles of Peaceful Co-existence) for a toss. The war ended with the predictable victory of the well-armed People's Liberation Army (PLA) capturing all claimed territories. Post the settlement of the war, the PLA did recede to the de facto border but the bitterness remained and India cut off diplomatic ties with China for a few good years.

It was only after the then External Affairs Minister- Atal Bihari Vajpayee's February 1979 visit to Beijing that high level political contacts were re-established. The war was a serious setback to their bilateral relations. Prima facie, both have remained cordial to each other since it is in their mutual interest to pursue healthy relationships in other sectors of trade and business.

The Joint Working Group that exists today to come to a mutually acceptable solution for the border predicament is the brainchild of former Indian Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi's visit to China in December 1988 wherein it was also agreed upon to expand bilateral relations in all sectors.¹ As economies of the two grew multi-fold since, the two have diplomatically maintained that they are not rivals but competitors.

India – United States Bilateral Relationship

Even though today the United States of America and India seem to be cooperating bilaterally in all possible sectors of cooperation, for example

defence, space, science and technology, energy and trade etc., the two have not had the best of relations throughout India's independent history either. India's non-signatory status to the 1968 Nuclear Non-proliferation Treaty (NPT), the world's largest arms control treaty (189 signatories)² which entails to stem the spread of nuclear weapons through legally binding commitments to boost international cooperation, as well as India's open declaration of possessing nuclear weaponry, has long irked the United States.

However at a historic moment in September 2008, the US requested the 48-member (2014 estimate)³Nuclear Suppliers Group (NSG) to grant a 'unique' waiver to India so that it could collaborate with India in nuclear trade, ergo bringing to closure a thirty-four year long embargo which was put in place after India's successful 1974 tests. The waiver which now permits India to legally trade in civilian nuclear fuel and technology was granted on consensus but not without the eruption of diplomatic tension between Beijing and New Delhi. China walked out of the meeting which was pacified only later by U.S. President George W. Bush called the Chinese President Hu Jintao.⁴

The waiver granted India a thriving relationship with Washington and a step towards greater world power. This was a cause of annoyance to the Chinese as India justifies its nuclear weapons programme as a "strategic deterrence" aimed evidently at China. The waiver was perceived as India legally joining the elite group of recognized nuclear weapon states which was previously only restricted to China, United States, France, United Kingdom, and Russia.

Despite this, the India-USA relationship has not been so smooth continually. In 2013, diplomatic tiff between India and USA erupted after the then Indian Deputy Consul General, Devyani Khobragade, was arrested on charges of visa fraud and perjury in the United States. In retaliation, India downgraded privileges of a certain category of US diplomats among other steps.⁵ Things on the diplomatic front have been cooled down ever since but the tiff caused immense awkwardness in their bilateral relations for a considerable period of time in modern history.

United States – China Rapport

The world's largest superpower and the world's fastest rising power share today a relationship that was unimaginable a few decades ago. United States views India to have an ameliorating effect on rising Chinese dominance in the region and the world.⁶ U.S. and China have been

getting close through the U.S. – China People-to-People Exchange (CPE). This exchange was based on culture, education, sports, women, and science & technology.

The CPE is also helping in spreading awareness regarding some key issues for example breast cancer, which is considered to be a taboo subject in China. In July 2014 the latest session of CPE was conducted to enhance cooperation.⁷

However tension exists as China has unilaterally declared that foreign countries will require Chinese permission to fish in the waters of the South China Sea. It has also established an Air Defence Identification Zone (ADIZ) over the hotly disputed Senkaku/Diayou islands in East China which are administered by Japan and claimed by China on the basis of “historic claims”. Japan, a well known fact, is protected under the United States’ nuclear umbrella. China’s influence in the region will require the removal of the strategically placed U.S. naval vessels and military bases.⁸ Also the fact that the U.S. is militarily backing two other claimants in the maritime dispute- Vietnam and the Philippines, the issue has been made a lot of bad blood and the bilateral relations are said to be the worst since President Nixon’s visit to Mao’s China.⁹

This year, the U.S. has also achieved the 100,000 mark set in 2010 which aimed at sending 100,000 American students to China to pursue their education. This was considered an essential stem to boosting bilateral relations.¹⁰

To counter China’s growing dominance, the one way India has to stand up against the dragon is by allying with the U.S. the U.S. also finds allying with India a smart way to control Chinese dominance but China is too big a power to ignore and giving China a complete cold shoulder would be ill-advised.

India’s importance came to international light in the second half of 2010 when world leaders of the permanent members of the Security Council travelled to India. Also, India’s quick recovery from the Global Recession of 2008-09 brought to light the chances of business collaboration opportunities in India.¹¹

It is also a well known fact that India is among one of the claimants to a permanent seat in the expanded United Nations Security Council (UNSC) alongside Brazil, Germany and Japan. But only one UNSC member’s absolute veto power stands in way of achieving that goal: China’s. The United States has declared openly that it backs India’s claim to a

permanent seat in the expanded UNSC. Ever since the Bush administration, relations with India have been warmed. However the election of President Obama put India under the looming fear that Obama's foreign policy will favour the administration at Islamabad over New Delhi to continue to sustain America's mission in Afghanistan due to the availability of warm water ports at Karachi. To India's disadvantage, Pakistan, another neighbour India has deep rooted troubles with, also happens to be China's "all weather ally".

In 2009, the United States struck the wrong chord with India after it issued a joint statement with China about how the two would work to stabilise South Asia. The joint statement by the two clearly mentioned:

*"The United States reiterated that it welcomes a strong, prosperous, and successful China that plays a greater role in world affairs. China welcomes the United States as an Asia-Pacific nation that contributes to peace, stability and prosperity in the region. Working together, both leaders support efforts to build a more stable, peaceful, and prosperous Asia-Pacific region for the 21st century."*¹²

This was on the top of the agenda on then Indian Prime Minister's meeting with Barack Obama in Washington a few weeks post his return from China. Singh was appeased that India was "an indispensable power" and "leader in South Asia". Obama was also quick to act as in the preceding year he initiated a strategic dialogue with India, thus calming India's concerns regarding China.

The Chinese have been suspicious about U.S.-India relations and believe they might be trying to "contain" China, which is clearly not the case. On the other hand, the Chinese have been "containing" India through its "string of pearls" by developing ports – commercial and military- around the Indian subcontinent. The largest of the ports- in Pakistan (Gwadar) and Sri Lanka (Hambantota) have already been developed to do so though they are commercial ports. Why it is alarming to India is because these Chinese-controlled facilities are right off the Indian coast plus they look like Pakistan and China- its hardest rivals- have bolstered security together to threaten India's national security.

There lies however an area where both India and China could cooperate - Afghanistan. With the United States troops due to gradually return home from the war torn country, India and China have a common concern of rampant terrorism rising as soon as the American troops depart. For China it is important so that the volatile province of Xinjiang is not affected by insurgents in West Asia. For India as well, keeping the

Taliban at bay is of utmost importance no matter how many new arenas of business interests Afghanistan open up.¹³

Conclusion

How the trilateral relationship takes off now is the tricky part as China unabashedly puts up competition against the United States for global dominance, China and India compete for hegemony in Asia, and India competes for a concrete relationship with the United States while boosting its economy. With such dynamic forces headed towards the same goal, it will be interesting to see how situations develop.

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8. The Great Power relationships in East Asia : Indian and Chinese perspectives

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Key Words

India, Asia, Look East policy, India-U.S., India-China, India-Japan, India-ASEAN,

East Asia under global focus

Asia, the world's fastest growing region today, contributes 40 percent of the world's annual growth. By 2050, economic growth projections suggest that Asia should account for over half of global GDP—a meteoric rise considering that it accounted for perhaps only 10 percent of world GDP in 1950. And yet, this bright future is not assured, for the region still confronts many challenges and potential pitfalls.

The post-Cold War unipolarity is transiting towards an East Asian multipolarity and the East Asian region is under global focus.¹ East Asia's ascent is represented by the rise of the entire region. Consequently, its overall weight in global affairs is also increasing significantly, and hence developments here will have major implications for the rest of the world. Today India is an indispensable part of East Asia and its role and interests are steadily expanding within the region. East Asia occupies a vital place in India's national security priorities as one-third of India's trade is with East Asia and regional security issues have long-term consequences for her. As part of its "Look East Policy," New Delhi is hoping to quench its growing thirst for energy by fostering closer relations with Southeast Asian countries, particularly Vietnam, and helping to develop their hydrocarbon resources.²

East Asia – economic prosperity vs geopolitical tensions

On the one hand, it has become a center of global attention due to the growing significance of the region to the global economy with the center of gravity of global politics shifting to East Asia; on the other hand, ongoing diplomatic tensions and political spats over a number of territorial issues point to a worrying future for peace and stability in the region. For a region that hasn't seen a real shooting war in almost 40 years, East Asia is surprisingly tense. Threats abound, generating anxiety and bad feeling. China continues to flex its economic and military muscles. Chinese military purchases and expenditures have increased by 170 percent since 2010 alone. This puts it second only to the US, whose USD640 billion splurge in 2013 was still more than the next 10 countries in the world put together and who still accounts for 37

percent of total global arms spending. The fact that Asian countries are now boosting their arsenals is worrying given the geopolitical tensions simmering beneath the veneer of peace and stability in the region.³ Indeed, territorial disputes in East Asia have begun to emerge as a serious flash point, raising regional concerns about the future of East Asia as a whole. In other words, as peace in East Asia remains precarious; prosperity cannot be taken for granted.

India's "Look East"

East Asia has come to assume an important place in Indian foreign policy priorities. Even before Independence Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru travelled to the East Asia and connected her fate with that of the people of Asia. Under his leadership as India's first prime minister, India reengaged with East Asia. The Asian Relations Conference held in New Delhi on April 2, 1947 served as one of the earliest attempts to form a pan-Asian identity. But during the cold war era India's preoccupations with security forced her attention on immediate periphery. India in the early 1990s had initiated a "Look East Policy" not merely as a dimension of its external economic policy but as recognition of the strategic shift of global focus to Asia and India's capacity to partner the processes in this part of the world. The policy itself was widely accepted by most interest groups in India, and persisted despite new political parties coming to power, and has come to stay as one of the corner stone of India's foreign policy.⁴ Varied interpretations of the 'Look East' Policy have come up. Some say it was a very major change in policy, while others view it as more in the nature of focusing upon a region which had until then not received the attention it deserved.

The expanded scope of Look East policy

When entering the 21st century, India is even more ambitious to look beyond the South Asian region, While after more than 20 years of evolution, LEP has been very well developed both in content and extension, and has evolved itself into one of the most successful external policies in India. In near future, it may be even more enriched and restructured to cover a much wider region - the Asia-Pacific region in whole and the region around the Pacific in particular. Together with new initiatives on cooperation with the countries in Asia-Pacific region, India may announce the third phase of LEP in near future. ⁵

Great powers - key actors in the East Asian security environment

Despite the growing significance of smaller nations and regional organizations in East Asian affairs, the great powers remain the key actors in shaping the regional security environment. Arguably, China, the United States, and Japan are the most influential powers in shaping the security dynamics and future direction of the region. Until recently, these three were able to maintain relatively stable relationships despite

differences on various issues. Since 2009, however, there has been rising tension in US-China relations and Sino-Japanese relations. ⁶

East Asian security will indubitably hinge upon the nature of the US-China relations in coming years. The US allies have found in China a constructive economic partner, but they continue to rely upon Washington's security commitments. China realises the importance of economic cooperation with the US to sustain its economic growth, but it has issues with the US hegemony in Asia. Currently, "the US consternation that China may surface as an Asian hegemon, and the Chinese angst that the US intends to restrict the growth of the Chinese power," will shape strategic landscape in Asia in coming years. ⁷ The observers caution that "pivot to Asia" might very well precipitate the very cold war with China it is supposed to prevent. The U.S. needs to find a way to live with Chinese power – unless the U.S. is prepared to seriously confront China in a major armed conflict, something one highly doubt U.S. public opinion would support. ⁸

The on-going experiments to forge a new East Asian architecture or community should be understood in the context of major power relationships. Competition and cooperation are different facets of a single new reality. Asian countries understand that regional stability is the prerequisite to continued economic growth. Hence, various regional groupings and dialogue mechanisms have been established in recent decades to manage these multi-faceted relationships, facilitate regional integration and defuse potential flashpoints. While varied in their composition and specific focuses, all these groupings have as their fundamental *raison d'être* the objective of managing the increasingly complex interactions among major powers.

(A) Visions of regional order in Asia ⁹

US vision - 'The Open Door'

The essential aspects of this US vision include a trans-Pacific geographical dimension that links the US to Asia; open markets free of government regulation that impede business; freedom of navigation guaranteed by US naval power; and the promotion of democracy and human rights.

Chinese vision - 'Community of Common Destiny'

China under Xi Jinping's leadership has inaugurated a programmatic effort to construct a so-called "Community of Common Destiny" in Asia. It comes in response to what China sees as new historical moment, i.e., the ending of America's post cold war "unipolar moment" and the transition back to structural bipolarity in the international system. With China's surrounding Asian neighbours ever more dependent on China's

trade, capital, and GDP growth –not to mention China’s strategic behaviour-China is crafting a China-centric initiative in regional construction that differs markedly from existing approaches to Asian regionalism.

Japanese vision –‘The Flying Geese’

Flying Geese refers to a Japanese vision of Asian development popularised in the 1980s by the noted economist and statesman, Saburo Okita. It rests on the notion of a group of interdependent Asian nations at different stages of industrialisation moving forward through the process of export-oriented industrial development as a group. Movement of the group and its individual members would be smoothed by development policies enacted by each government, and overall leadership would be provided by Japan. The role of the US was not emphasized, but the Flying Geese model of Asian development could not work without the US absorbing Asian exports and providing regional security.

Indian Vision –‘Look East’

Ever since beginning its “ Look East” effort, India has sought to strengthen economic and cultural linkages with ASEAN and the Asia-Pacific to complement India’s own turn toward economic liberalization and the active pursuit of foreign trade and investment linkages. The key diplomatic axis has been India-ASEAN relations. India-China relations have constituted a parallel look east diplomatic axis.

USA and East Asia :

Pivot, Rebalance, or Reinvigorate?

"Rebalance" was the original name of this U.S. strategy toward the region. But there were some in the administration, not in the White House, who wanted to call it a "pivot"—jazzier, sharper (In late 2011). The third term that's been used and one that, according to Lieberthal, actually should have been used from the start and really describes what we were seeking to do was to "reinvigorate." ‘We never left Asia. We've had huge interests out there. We haven't neglected them, but we've put so much attention elsewhere that reinvigorating the effort to Asia would have put us in the right position’ ¹⁰

US trying to contain China?

In late April 2014, President Barack Obama paid his fifth official visit to Asia—a tour of four nations intended to reassure nervous allies of America’s commitment to them, to send signals to China that the United States was standing fast in its regional presence and commitments, and

to provide tangible proof of Washington's "pivot" (or "rebalancing") policy towards the region. Was this a "China containment tour" ? At virtually every press conference along the way, the president's stock responses included the following phrases:

- "We want to continue to encourage the peaceful rise of China" (Tokyo, April 24);
- "My hope is that China will continue to engage with us and other countries in the region (Tokyo, April 24);
- "China's participation in pushing the DPRK [North Korea] in a different direction is critically important as well" (Tokyo, April 24);
- "We're not interested in containing China; we're interested in China's peaceful rise and it being a responsible and powerful proponent of the rule of law and an international system." (Seoul, April 25).
- "We want to see a peaceful rise for China, because we think it can and should contribute to the stability and prosperity that we all seek" (Kuala Lumpur, April 27);
- "We have a constructive relationship with China... So our goal is not to counter China. Our goal is not to contain China" (Manila, April 28);
- "It's inevitable that China is going to be a dominant power in this region just by sheer size. Nobody, I think, denies that. The question is whether other countries in the region are also able to succeed and prosper on their own terms and tend to the various interests and needs that they and their people have as well. And that's what we support" (Manila, April 28). ¹¹

Chinese are skeptical of U.S. rebalancing policy:

- The U.S. grand strategy of the rebalance, and especially American efforts to reassure allies, were really about the "construction of threats," designed to make China into the enemy. the Obama administration's "Return to Asia" was responsible for promoting regional instability, especially by backing allies, thereby creating instability and a demand among allies for greater security measures. President Obama's promise in April to defend the Senkakus was a primary case in point. ¹²
- The economic component of the U.S. rebalancing strategy through establishment of the Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP) drew an equally skeptical analysis. The U.S. design is to create an unstable atmosphere in Asia so that Asian countries continue to accept a U.S. presence in the region.

The questions that agitate the Chinese public about the U.S. rebalancing:

1.What kind of equilibrium situation would the U.S. want to achieve though its rebalancing to Asia and Pacific? Which nations' engaging power does the U.S. want to balance?

2.We never heard of any Chinese experts talking about any balancing strategy to North America, to keep the needed equilibrium among

Canada, America, and Mexico. Why is the U.S. dominance in the North America accepted by China like this, while China's strength advantage in Asia cannot be accepted by the U.S.? Why does the U.S. regard China's regional upper hand as something needing to be balanced?

3. What does the U.S. think about the Japanese military force development in its strategy of rebalancing Asia and Pacific? Does America consider the Chinese public's worry about Japan strengthening its self-defense forces?

4. Most of the Chinese public dislike so many American military bases existing close to their nation. They think that the United States never allows its rivals' military bases—such as Cuba's—near its territory but puts so many bases around China¹³

But there are others who believe that the broader Chinese psychology associated with its rise has moved well past Hu Jintao's focus on "peaceful development" to a mindset in which, as part of Xi Jinping's "Chinese dream," China's ability to exert its own sphere of influence in Asia is regarded as an expected benefit that will naturally accrue, regardless of the impact on the neighborhood. And this is why, regardless of what it is called, the United States must make the task of preserving East Asian stability a top priority not only for the Obama administration, but also for the long-term. ¹⁴.

JAPAN and East Asia :

The evolving Sino-Japanese relationship should be considered against the background of a "rising" China and "stagnant" Japan. Due attention should be paid to both the complexity of Sino-Japanese interactions and Japan's role in shaping regional dynamics, which are often overlooked as analysts focus on the supposed power transition between the United States and China. Strategic militarized rivalry coupled with national identity clashes will likely worsen Sino-Japanese conflict, although economic interdependence (perhaps including growing tripartite institutionalization with South Korea) and Japan's geopolitical position through its alliance with the United States serve as constraining factors. ¹⁵ The United States as an offshore balancer is a key determinant of the nature of Sino-Japanese ties as being neither too hot nor too cold. Therefore, what is needed is a cohesive US-Japan alliance that remains the bedrock of geopolitical stability in the region by providing a united front to deter China and restrain Japan. ¹⁶

Enhancing or destabilising regional stability :

Japan's decision, on 1 July 2014, to reinterpret its pacific constitution to allow the right to collective defence has angered China. It is crafting a more active role in security and defence in response to rising instability in Northeast Asia. ¹⁷

These Japanese actions should not be perceived, it is argued, as deliberate attempts to destabilise the regional security environment. They are a reaction to the rising levels of perceived threats from North Korea and China and a response to growing American criticism of Japan as a 'free rider' benefitting from the umbrella provided by US defence expenditure. North Korea's continued development of its nuclear and ballistic missile capabilities worries Japan. Defence planners are pre-occupied with responding to a nuclear warhead on a missile targeted at Japan.

China's strategic rise is another long-term concern for Japan.

The rapid increase and lack of transparency in Chinese defence expenditure is an immediate source of anxiety. Although still a distant second to the US (which spends four-and-a-half times more than China), Chinese defence expenditure dwarfs the Japanese defence budget of \$48.6 billion. Global military expenditure was \$1747 billion in 2013. Military expenditure in Asia and Oceania rose by 3.6 per cent in 2013, reaching \$407 billion. The increase is mostly accounted for by a 7.4 per cent increase by China, whose spending reached an estimated \$188 billion. 'Japan's concerns over China's growing military power, combined with the Japanese Government's own nationalist policies, have led to Japan ending its long, gradual decline in military spending. ¹⁸

Fierce and continuing confrontation between China and Japan really makes one wonder ,why and how on earth it has become possible that the two countries with an expectation that they live in peace after their establishment of diplomatic relations in 1972,just 40 years later, stand on the verge of a physical clash which might even develop to a new war.

Some Japanese now have begun to seriously wonder that Zhou Enlai and Deng Xiaoping's readiness for reconciliation might just have been a "leaning low" profile not to stir the world while China's power was weak ,and now that it became strong , it began to able rattle to the extent of reaching a dangerous point of war,ignoring entirely Japanese sense of humility for the past ,the complete peaceful development for 70 years after its defeat.China is rapidly depleting the whole asset of its positive image accumulated in the post-WW II years in Japan,it is argued.¹⁹ It's therefore not surprising that Japan being China's fourth largest trading partner and China being Japan's largest trading partner in imports and exports, there has been no strong political initiative in either country to form a bilateral FTA.

On the other hand, China points out that the stubborn and illegal announcement act of the nationalisation of D/S Islands insisted by

Japan, and Japan's adoption of confrontational diplomatic and defence policy to China have resulted in the fiercest Sino-US rivalry after world war II ²⁰ What also needs to be noted is that Shinzo Abe's administration hypes "China Provocative Theory" and "China Threat Theory" on almost all important East Asian multilateral governmental conferences. This year's Shangri-La Dialogue took place in the background of increasing maritime disputes in Asia-Pacific as a result of growing unilateral action by the disputing nations.²¹

CHINA and East Asia :

China's own rebalancing act

It seems that China and the US sees itself as the "insider", while the other as the "outsider". This is the fundamental strategic doubt and fear between China and the US on East Asian regional multilateralism. The US is not the only global power rebalancing. China, the object of much discussion in relation to the US pivot, has also been actively balancing the rest of the globe in its favour. China has long used the term 'rebalancing' largely referring to (although not exclusively) economic reforms. There lies the significance and global reach of China's own rebalancing act as China's economic and commercial interests square away Beijing's influence in strategically important corners of Africa, Asia and the Pacific.

Chinese moves in the region to secure sea lanes, oil blocks, potential mineral beds and maritime territories through proxies bring to mind a quasi-pincer movement which indirectly contains not only regional powers but has the potential to isolate and diminish the regional influence of traditional United States allies such as Australia, New Zealand and strategic partnerships with evolving friends such as Indonesia and Singapore from the US pivot. The Chinese approach is multi-pronged with diplomatic, economic and increasingly maritime fronts which may prove to divide and contain the Asia Pacific despite US late efforts towards rebalancing China's balance of power in the region.²²

Unlike his predecessors, Xi is making foreign policy with the mindset of a great power, increasingly probing U.S. commitments to its allies in the region and exploiting opportunities to change the status quo. China's recent rhetoric and actions show a move from a defensive, reactive, and image-conscious policy to a proactive approach designed to further China's vital interests. Xi's new slogan is the "Chinese dream," a vision for the national rejuvenation of the Chinese people. And in the U.S.-China relationship, U.S. diplomats used to frame the debate with terms such as "responsible stakeholder" in the global system. But China has

now put forth its own catch phrase: a "new type of great power relations," in which the U.S. recognizes China's core interests and respects it as an equal. ²³

Nevertheless, China's rise instead of promoting confidence and pride in its neighborhood has increased apprehensions among its neighbors. Territorial disputes with them have become more tensed. Maybe China is misunderstood, but it is China's responsibility to ensure and assure its neighbors about its peaceful rise and no heavy handedness against its neighbors. ²⁴

(B) India and great power relationships in East Asia

(i) India-China :

Both are ancient civilisations with deep cultural memories and great ambitions. Although each side continues to view the other through lens coloured by some unhappy experiences, this has not stopped cooperation. Both sides are adopting a pragmatic approach in their dealings with each other and are learning to manage their differences while seeking cooperation in areas where there is mutual benefit. Their bilateral trade, for example, continues to expand rapidly. The current bilateral trade touched USD 65.47 billion (from US\$15 billion in 2005) hoping that bilateral trade would reach the official target of USD 100 billion by 2015, already making China India's largest trading partner.²⁵ The bilateral trade has seen a downward trend since 2011, with 2013 registering a 1.5% decline. The current trade deficit with China stands at \$ 31.42bn The unfavourable balance of trade, however, remains the worrying factor for India ²⁶

The competition between these two growing giants for resources such as energy and raw materials is likely to intensify, there are encouraging signs that both sides want to avoid conflict and focus on economic development.

India's 'Look East' policy a failure : China

India's Look East Policy "was born out of failure - the failure of India's Cold War strategy of playing both ends against the middle" "...today, India is harping on the same string but should wisely skip the out-of-tune piece ...implying that India's assumed and presumed China containment efforts will fail." ²⁷

China's perspective on India's LEP is explained as follows : China knows that in the long term India is the only country that could possibly challenge its ascendancy and potential hegemony in Asia. "All this cannot but make China somewhat wary of a Rising India too". The central fact is that the two countries have competing visions: India wants a multi-polar Asia and a multi-polar world, whereas China seems to

prefer a uni-polar Asia and at best a bi-polar world.” “Now China seems to feel threatened in her own backyard by the success of India’s look east policy.” “China regarded India's Look East policy with suspicion that India may not limit itself only to economic benefits of trade and investment in Asia, that New Delhi might seek, with U.S. assistance, in blocking China's rising influence in the region. “Generally speaking Chinese analysts do not take India too seriously as a rising power due to differential growth rates in their economy and defense spending. However, recently the military cooperation component of the Look East policy has provoked some concern” ²⁸

India-China relations post-2014

That China is ready to work with India's new government to push their cooperation to a new high was indicated during the first high-level interaction with the new dispensation in India. For three long hours. Chinese foreign minister Wang Yi , who is special envoy of Chinese President Xi Jinping, on 8 June 2014, held talks with his Indian counterpart Sushma Swaraj and discussed ways to strengthen cooperation in key areas including trade and investment. Next day, he met India's new prime minister, Narendra Modi, who said that "India and China share strong civilizational contacts" and should work to "expand our partnership." The Chinese foreign ministry put a positive spin on the two days of meetings, saying the two nations' foreign ministers reached a consensus on four points, among them "to appropriately handle border issues." ²⁹ Similar sentiments were expressed by Chinese President Xi Jinping, during his meeting with Indian Vice President Mohammad Hamid Ansari on June 30 at the sidelines of celebration of 60th anniversary of signing Panchsheel agreement. He said India is an important partner for China, that the relationship is a priority in China's diplomacy, Reciprocating the sentiments, Ansari said the good-neighborly relationship between India and China is in the fundamental interests of the two countries and peoples. Earlier, on June 28 at a high-profile meeting to mark the 60th anniversary of the Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence at the Great Hall of the People. President Xi reiterated : **China will never seek hegemony, no matter how strong it becomes.** ³⁰ China's gestures toward India are of particular interest in light of recent overtures by the Japanese government to bolster ties with New Delhi. India is seen as a part of a multi-polar Asian counter-weight to rising China. Yet, for India to inch towards global-power status, it has to first resolve problems with China

(ii) India-U.S. :

US interest in working more closely with India in the East Asia

(1) "US would like to encourage as many countries as possible to have policies which are friendly to the preservation and protection of US regional interests." India has its own vital interests in the region and to the extent that they are compatible, multi-dimensional cooperation between the two is desirable, inevitable and perfectly understandable.

(2) "US and India share a convergence of interests; so do US and China as well as China and India. Diplomacy in Asia is a constant and complex dance, with the sole aim of promoting a constellation that favours you. India has no intention to bring into Asia a new cold war."

(3) It is in the U.S. interest to strengthen India's obligations and ties with the region and offer India support to checkmate China.

(4) "From Washington's perspective, India is a status quo power. They acknowledge that it would certainly like to have a greater voice in regional decision-making, but New Delhi is not interested in disrupting or overturning the existing regional order that has helped facilitate stability and economic prosperity in Asia for decades."

But analysts have a word of caution for India "to plow her own independent furrow, with self-confidence, than to get involved with the USA or the Western countries, which may only lead India to grief." ³¹

India 'Looking East' to 'Look West' towards US

India's growing engagement with the US is across the globe and across an all embracing spectrum of activities. India does not have to look east to look west to the US. LEP's scope may or may not have increased, but the Western powers are certainly seeing benefit in it for themselves. During the last decade, with changes in the geopolitical scenario, smaller south-east Asian states have also looked towards India to increase its regional profile and engagement as a balancer. India's LEP can be now said to have been upgraded to version 2. Starting with development of trade and investment linkages with the ASEAN region, the focus is now on deeper economic ties and more consultation on security issues. India has also moved into wider East Asia (Pacific Asia) and Pacific Basin (southern Pacific) settings. In fact, with the American plans to reduce its obligations in the region, very largely for economic reasons, Washington would be happy if India picks up some of the responsibility with potential for checking excessive power in China's hands. In 2003 "phase II" of Look East was launched to encompass the broader Asia-Pacific region and expand the scope of India's relations from strictly economic to embrace political and strategic ties as well. As a major Pacific power, increased engagement with the U.S. in Asia has naturally resulted from India's eastward focus.

To what extent New Delhi will do Washington's bidding at the cost of its relations with Beijing was yet to be seen. New Delhi's consternation, for instance, was obvious when American Defense Secretary Leon Panetta claimed during a visit to Delhi that India was the linchpin of America's 'rebalancing strategy' in East Asia, for it might result in compromising the 'strategic autonomy' that it always cherished. Moreover, "India

generally shuns security groupings,” and “feels uncomfortable with something directed against another country as such.”³²

US refuses to talk China with India

It makes strategic sense for the U.S. and India to join hands, especially because there is no clash of interest between the two once the nuclear issue has been removed from the equation. But recent developments relating to US "strategic inattention" are likely to be watched carefully in India. US has refused to hold the East Asia dialogue with India for the past year. Through the East Asia dialogue, the US and India discussed issues relating to China and beyond, while India and South Asia are the subjects of discussion with China in the South Asia dialogue. From mid-2013, sources said the US has been stalling all attempts to hold the East Asia dialogue. Indian officials have even offered to meet in a third country but the new assistant secretary of state Daniel Russell, who took over from Kurt Campbell, met them with stony silence. Many in the Indian system describe this as "strategic inattention" by the Obama administration. It is most strongly manifested in the lack of engagement about Asia. The US and India still have a trilateral discussion going with Japan. That too would have sunk were it not for the efforts of Japan and India to keep it afloat. "Some in the US, looking for a way to kick-start relations with India, have toyed with the idea of a trilateral dialogue with China. But Beijing, it is believed, has torpedoed it, deeming it unworthy. But Beijing has not been averse to holding a trilateral with India and Russia on Afghanistan." ³³

(iii) India-Japan :

The most promising region for India's external relations remains the redefined Asia which lies between India and Japan. The potential for developing relations between India and Japan into a defining partnership for an "Asian Century" is enormous. The Japanese partnership with India is of particular significance regarding the construction of an East Asian Community. This nascent relationship between "the most developed and the largest Asian democracies", grounded on a rich historical legacy of contributions toward East Asian regionalism, has the ambition to play a central role in the current regional construction. ³⁴

The interplay of global trends and events, major power strategic relations, the rise of China, and complementary economic interests drive India and Japan toward closer partnership. There is steadily expanding political engagement, Economic complementarity and Security cooperation. A security alliance between India and Japan against China or any other country is out of question. "Containing China is not the point".³⁵ This "mutually beneficial" relationship may be significant for this new wave of Asian regionalism, which seems to shift from an "Asia-Pacific" to a "broader East Asia" focus.

India's strategic partnerships with the US and Japan have been strengthened and transformed though some misplaced confusion over the meaning of "strategic autonomy" has resurfaced. India needs to forge strong ties with the world's leading powers to bolster its emergence as an independent pillar of the global community. But it cannot create "a new and alternative universality" or "nonalignment 2.0" in isolation and must be prepared to shoulder greater responsibilities in the international system.

The United States and Japan also have a robust trilateral dialogue with India on a wide range of regional and global issues, including, in particular, cooperation in the area of maritime security in the Indian Ocean and Western Pacific, the development of an Indo-Pacific economic connectivity corridor among the countries in the region to enhance regional connectivity, and humanitarian assistance and disaster relief. But New Delhi should be careful not to allow its ties with Japan to get unnecessarily entangled in a regional race for power, just as so-called China factor must not be allowed to derail India's relations with other countries in the region.

India's strategic engagement with East Asia

Managing the current transition and creating a new East Asian security order is critical and that is where India's role is pivotal. Most countries expect major Indian contribution in meeting the security challenges, especially maritime related, and in building a stable balance of power. India's security role in regional affairs acquires significance at a time when all the great powers are rebalancing their strategies toward East Asia. Of course, the high-profile U.S. pivot is well known but equally notable are Japan's new rebalancing strategy under Shinzo Abe and China's ambitions of becoming the pre-eminent power in the region. On the other hand, having remained on the margins, India's too has its own pivot strongly anchored to East Asia. It has now becoming a key player in regional affairs. This is evident in the vast security cooperation arrangements it has crafted with most countries in the region.

India's strategic engagement with East Asia is both *multilateral and bilateral*. Relations at the bilateral level are extensive. India has forged defence and strategic links of one kind or another with countries of the entire East Asian region-North Korea being the sole exception. The security related multilateral frameworks, such as the ARF and Six-Party Talks, have been a disappointment so far because of lack of mutual confidence. A more credible security framework is the need of the hour. And India's role in the emerging balance of power in East Asia is going to be very significant. For India, the guiding principles on which a regional security framework could be charted are: No Containment, No Hegemony, No Condominium. And 'Yes' to everything that promotes dialogue as the principal instrument of foreign policy.

India's role in Eastern Asian power equations

Over the past two decades, India's Eastern policies have been deeply analysed and widely commented upon by scholars. They believe New Delhi has undertaken a concerted effort to direct its foreign, economic, and military policies eastward. India can play an extensive role as an 'external balancer'; 'enabling power'; 'engaged power'; a pluralistic power and as a "stabilising power. India, however, has made it abundantly clear that her "foreign policy posture needs to be "inclusive, comprising all powers — regional and extra-regional — relevant to the practice of Asia's security." But India's sudden withdrawal from joint oil exploration with Vietnam in the South China Sea, after previously boldly asserting its legal claims there, has certainly raised questions about the credibility and sustainability of her role as a major balancing power in the area.

India's options;

To some India's involvement with East Asia is 'more rhetoric than reality.' Its limited diplomatic presence rendered it unable to capitalize on the significant good will enjoyed by India. To achieve real power and influence, India would need to grow its foreign policy apparatus, prioritize its East Asian relationships, and commit real resources rather than continuing to do "too much with too little." Even if India only develops its overall strategic capabilities fitfully, its engagement in Asia can only grow because its vital interests are now engaged there. ³⁶

Others struck a different tone arguing that, in contrast to the picture 20 years ago, India's engagement of East Asia and a large number of institutions indicated India's desire to play a larger role internationally, leading to greater multilateral involvement and contributions over time, particularly as Indian trade with East Asia accelerated. India's efforts to play "catch up" due to its historically limited role in East Asia need support by regional actors, However, with China determined to keep India out of East Asian organizations, it is suspected "India cannot play a real regional counterweight to China and will likely remain on the margins." As economic and military gaps with China widen, India has to depend on its partnerships with the US, Japan to preserve the strategic balance and secure its interests. ³⁷

Road forward for India in East Asian scenario

Against the backdrop of the oft-chanted plaint that India is a reluctant and diffident power. it is stressed that "India has been very economical in its foreign entanglements but not engagements." "We have so far resisted siren calls for us to do what others want us to, in the name of being "responsible" or "stepping up to the plate. This shows an acute awareness on our part, but not others, of the extent and limits of India's power and its potential uses, and a clear prioritisation between our interests and between our goals." "Others tell us that the articulation of

our policies is normative, moralistic and academic, even in explaining acts of realpolitik. We have even been called 'preachy'! The key to understanding India's foreign policy practice so far is the Indian understanding of the uses, limits and nature of power." ³⁸ Fourteen major accidents involving submarines and warships in just 10 months could possibly paralyze Indian naval capabilities. The ambitions of becoming a strategic blue-water power, India is expending its naval crew with Russian assistance. But that seems impossible given the submarines and warships have completed 75% operational lives. India can play a role in the region only to the extent that countries of the region and countries that exercise influence in the region perceive that India's involvement in or with the region is relevant to their needs and concerns. Therefore, these 'challenges' materially circumscribe the scope of India's ability to take initiatives; it is much more up to countries of the region and countries playing roles in the region to involve India. Through the 'Look East' Policy, India signaled its interest and desire in reengaging with the region. Since then, more of the initiative was taken by the countries of the region to build the current superstructure on the foundations that India expressing its interest in being engaged represented. The China factor has certainly played a significant role in the emergence of these new ground realities in South and Southeast Asia but it has been a far more important motivating factor for countries of the region than it has been for India ³⁹

The history of Indian foreign policy and Sino-Indian relations suggests that India will not concede to live under Chinese dominion in a unipolar Asia. The success of national revitalization policies by Narendra Modi in India and Abe Shinzo in Japan, it is pointed out, will do much to determine the degree of multipolarity in 21st century Asia. However, the decisive variable will not be the trajectories of India and Japan, but the future role of the United States as the region's (offshore) primary power. Yet, acknowledging the important potential roles to be played by South Korea, Russia, and Southeast Asia, within Asia, we should recognize that the triangular relationship among the region's three leading states will do most to determine the constellation of power and the nature of regional order.

While the United States has a natural alignment of interests with India, that does not include pushing it into a hostile relationship with China. Its own equities vis-a-vis Beijing are enormous and complicated enough already. At the same time, Americans are less worried about the development of any kind of India-China bloc given the disparity of interests and values between these rising powers, which is only magnified by their geographic proximity. ⁴⁰

Conclusion

In conclusion, it may be stated that India remains committed to further

intensifying its relations with this region. The pursuit of regional economic integration, emphasis on South-South cooperation, promotion of societal links through cultural cooperation and educational exchanges, as well as an increased focus on security cooperation and countering threats to national security will remain important pillars of India's engagement with East-Asia.

For historical, cultural, political as well as for substantial economic reasons India belongs to the East Asian table. One of the key opportunities is to revive and build on India's historical and cultural legacy in Asia without appearing to be seeking hegemony or trumpeting a chauvinist vision. But it needs to resolve some difficult challenges so as to ensure that its influence on the global stage will be commensurate with its strategic potential. There are no easy solutions but India has to draw up policies to deal with them.

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(E) China's engagement with various Regions

1. China's footprint in South Asia

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China is the planet's most populous country and second largest by land mass. China has become one of the globe's fastest-growing post-industrial economies since reforms were put into place in 1978 by Deng Xiaoping and its rapid industry growth since then has led to competition with the United States and Europe.

China's standing has changed faster than any nation in history and is perhaps the most dynamic part of a new international order. The replacement of G-8 by G-20 in global politics did not come about by accident but by realizing that without China, global issues cannot be adequately addressed.

China's expanding economic, military and diplomatic influence has contributed to its image as a formidable world power. It is reported that by 2028 China will be the world's largest economy, putting the economy of the US into the second position.

Economic, political, military and strategic influence is moving to Asia. China may eventually turn the 21st century as 'Asia's Century' with India, Indonesia, Japan and South Korea.

Given the above context, it is natural that China's footprint is gradually getting larger in South Asia and in the Indian Ocean.

China's past "ping-pong diplomacy" is replaced by current "cheque-book diplomacy". China is attracted to investment in South Asia in sectors which would generate good returns to China and it is reported that in the next five years, China is to provide \$30 billion investment and \$20 billion loans in South Asia.

In October 2013, China has proposed to form a bank, Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, with an estimate approved capital of \$100 billion. The Bank will mainly focus on infrastructure construction in Asia to promote regional connectivity and economic cooperation. Bangladesh, India and Nepal reportedly expressed their interest to join as members of the Bank. The Bank will be complementing the work of other

entities, like the Asian Development Bank (controlled by Japan and the US).

China has proposed two silk routes -one maritime silk route for trade for littoral states of the Indian Ocean and the other is economic corridor through land territory connecting Bangladesh, China, India and Myanmar (BCIM).

In December 18, 2013 officials from four countries attended the two-day meeting of the joint working group of the BCIM corridor at Kunming and underscored the need to implement the plan at the meeting. The meeting at the official level from BCIM countries demonstrates that plan of the BCIM corridor has the approval in principle by the four countries.

China's maritime silk route of the 21st century for littoral countries of the Indian Ocean has reportedly received strong support from the Maldives, Sri Lanka and Singapore in addition to many African countries. All these countries perceive that the maritime silk route could act as a catalyst for development of trade and investment.

Following is the brief account of Chinese growing influence in South Asia:

Bangladesh:

Bangladesh is a nation of strategic importance not only to South Asian region but to the larger geo-political dynamics of Asia as a whole. The country constitutes a bridge between South Asia and South East Asia. This provides an opportunity for interaction with Bangladesh by South East Asian nations and China. Bangladesh's access to the Indian Ocean is commercially and strategically important.

Bangladesh and China has maintained close and cooperative relations. Many politicians and academics believe that friendly relations with China will act as a counter-weight to Bangladesh's relations to India and Bangladesh will have more negotiating power with India.

The policy "Look to the East" has ushered in a new phase of Bangladesh foreign policy under the current government. Bangladesh Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina visited China in early June of this year and received commitment of financial support and investment from China in a big way, reportedly \$ 7 billion for about 14 infrastructure projects.

The more investment Bangladesh receives from China, its goal of becoming a middle income country by 2021 will be quicker. The two nations have everything to gain from developing this investment relationship. The governments and the peoples interact closely in the case of investment and the relationship with the investor-country is deep and lasting.

India's offer of \$1 billion loan to Bangladesh in 2010 also prompted China to think how it could play a greater role in Bangladesh. China's financial support for Bangladesh during the last three years surged significantly. China has gone to the global scene including in South Asia as an investor and not as trader only. . China has already built six bridges across the rivers in the country which contributed to the accelerated socio-economic growth of the country, facilitating the movement of people and goods within the country.

Over the past few years, China has replaced India as Bangladesh's biggest import destination with bilateral trade between the two nations as of 2013-2014 standing at US\$8 billion , though heavily skewed in favour of Beijing.. To remove the trade imbalance between the two countries, China offered in 2010 duty-free access to some 5,000 Bangladeshi products in a "goodwill gesture". The products include medicinal materials, plastic appliances, leather, timber, textile, readymade garments and poultry products.

It is reported that government has decided that Padma Multi-purpose bridge, the country's largest-ever infrastructure project, is to be built by China Major Bridge Engineering Company (CMBEC). The CMBEC will get the \$1.55 billion job against a revised estimated cost of \$1.77 billion.

China has shown its interest in constructing a deep sea port at Sonadia, near Chittagong with \$5 billion, the gateway to the Bay of Bengal. It is reported that the total cost of the deep sea port with its three phases would cost about \$9 billion. Bangladesh however is reportedly considering a consortium of countries to build the deep sea port with India, China, Denmark, Netherlands, UAE and the US.. Some observers say that Bangladesh does not want to give to China alone to build the sea port to avoid upsetting India.

It is noted that China is an important supplier of arms and weapons to Bangladesh. Reportedly Bangladesh and China signed an agreement in December 2013 to buy two "Ming" class submarines at the cost \$230 million to protect its maritime areas in the Bay of Bengal. Since 2010, the government has taken firm steps in gradually building Bangladesh Navy as a deterrent force and the acquisition of submarines is a part of

the plan to defend its off-shore areas in the Bay of Bengal.(more than 1, 18,000 square km.)

Nepal:

China has continued to assist in various sectors of the economy in Nepal. Nepal views the Tibet autonomous region as a gateway to the markets of inland China and the wider world, according to a senior Nepalese diplomat in Lhasa as reported in the media."The Chinese and Nepalese people are expecting great things from each other," he told China Daily in an exclusive interview in 2013. He said Nepal and Tibet have had strong religious, cultural, business and interpersonal ties throughout history, ever since they first began trading food for salt, gold and wool.

"Trade nowadays is more dynamic and multifaceted between the two sides. Goods from China are very much loved by Nepalese people, according to their income capacity and the durability of the goods," the diplomat said. "We are working to develop trade hubs for bilateral and international trade."

The overall trade volume stood at Rs 380.04 billion, an increment of 14.2 percent compared to the same period a year ago in the first half of current fiscal year 2014. .During this period, Nepal's trade deficit expanded to Rs 289.62 billion. Nepal imported goods worth Rs 334.83 billion in the six-month period, while exports stood at Rs 45.21 billion, according to the latest statistics of the Trade and Export Promotion Centre (TEPC).

Beijing is funding a 60-megawatt power plant on the Trishuli river in Nepal, already under construction, and a \$1.6 billion, 750-megawatt joint venture on the Seti river, due to be completed by December 2019. For the first time, China's investment in Nepal has surpassed India's. China has also been wooing Bhutan with tempting investment proposals.

To reduce the trade deficit, Nepal and China in 2010 signed an accord that will allow zero-tariff entry facility to 4,721 Nepali exportable items in the Chinese market. The list of commodities enjoying the facility covers some 60 percent of total products that Nepal exports to China.

The proposal of running China-Nepal Direct Cargo Service by the Chinese Railway Company would further help to develop the economic relations of our two countries. Moreover, it would also help the Nepalese businessmen to export their goods to the third countries using this service.

The two sides also agreed to construct and manage dry ports along the six Nepal-China border points in a bid to facilitate bilateral trade and movement of people. China agreed to allow citizens of Nepal residing within 30 km of the international border to use the pasture and graze their livestock on the other side of the border.

The two governments have agreed to develop international-standard dry ports and cargo terminals in Yari-Pulam, Rasuwa-Jilong and Kodari (Tatopani)-Zangmu (Khasha) customs. China further agreed to expedite the implementation of Tatopani Dry Port and upgrading and expansion of the existing Ring Road in the Kathmandu Valley.

Nepal also requested China to extend railway line that it was building up since 2008 to the bordering town Khasa to Kathmandu and also up to Lumbini. The Chinese premier in 2012 during his visit to Nepal said such an extension was highly possible.

"Despite geographic proximity, cultural intimacy, economic interdependence and shared political values, India has stumbled in Nepal," wrote C. Raja Mohan, columnist for The Indian Express. Citing a growing perception in Nepal that "India promises, China delivers", he wrote that "India's record of project implementation in Nepal is awful".

Maldives & Sri Lanka:

The Chinese President who paid a visit to Maldives and Sri Lanka in the middle of September of this year before visiting India is significant.

The Maldives which straddles major international shipping lanes in the Indian Ocean is both commercially and strategically important to big powers. During the visit of the Chinese President, trade and security issues were reportedly discussed. In a joint statement, the two countries said they agreed to cooperate on security issues -- a potentially sensitive issue in a region traditionally dominated by India.

The Maldives also secured Chinese support for an ambitious project to build a road bridge between central Male island and nearby Hululle island, where the international airport is located.

It is noted that Chinese investment there has grown significantly as Beijing tries to secure vital trade routes. "The Maldives welcomes and supports the proposal put forward by China to build the 21st Century Maritime Silk Road, and is prepared to actively participate in relevant cooperation," the statement said.

After the Maldives, Chinese President Xi Jinping arrived on 16th September for the first state visit to Sri Lanka by a Chinese head of state in decades.

Xi said upon his arrival reportedly stated that the two countries are "good brothers sharing weal and woe, good partners seeking common development and good friends with close relationship," "I hope the visit will promote the profound friendship between the two peoples and that the ship of China-Sri Lanka friendship will brave the wind and waves along the magnificent 21st Century Maritime Silk Road," Xi said.

China is the biggest investor in the post-war island, building motorways, a power station and an airport. China has become Sri Lanka's second largest trade partner and second largest source of imports. In 2013, China became Sri Lanka's largest investor and bilateral trade reached \$3.62 billion U.S. dollars.

Pakistan:

Pakistan is a long-time ally of China. No other country has ever backed and armed another Asian country as China has backed and armed Pakistan more than last fifty years in such a consistent manner.

Prime Minister Nawaz Sharif visited China in July 2013. During the visit he reportedly said at the Great Hall of the People in the Chinese capital, his welcome "reminds me of the saying, our friendship is higher than the Himalayas and deeper than the deepest sea in the world, and sweeter than honey".

Beijing has been involved with the upgrade of the Karakoram Highway as part of a proposed economic corridor between the two countries. During the visit of the Chinese Premier Li Keqiang to Pakistan in May 2014, the two sides reached an agreement on building a China-Pakistan economic corridor starting from the Arabian Sea

On bilateral relationship, China's *Global Times* writes: "China and Pakistan enjoy the best of bilateral relations, and their relationship has no parallel in modern international relations. This relationship could be a role model for other states. For Pakistan, China is and will remain the keystone of its foreign policy."

Xi Jinping would have discussed the Maritime Silk Route with Pakistan too but Beijing had to postpone the visit to Islamabad in September of this year due to prevailing political situation in the country.

Li Mingjiang, a professor at the S. Rajaratnam School of International Studies at Singapore-based Nanyang Technological University, told the Global Times that the goal is to consolidate China's long-term strategic influence in the region.

Wang Xiaopeng, an expert on maritime and border studies at the Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, said that the initiative could help China and other claimants build strategic trust and manage disputes through breakthroughs in the economic sphere. "Politicians in those countries will have to get bilateral ties back on track, because they can't afford the consequences of missing out on opportunities provided by China's growth," Wang added.

String of pearls:

Observers argue China has been gradually encircling India by the so-called "String of Pearls". The term "pearls" meant naval facilities China reportedly has been developing in Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Thailand and Cambodia and possibly in Bangladesh.

Gwadar port in Pakistan , being built in Baluchistan coast, will be run by China. India thinks that both Pakistan and China may interdict Indian tankers, if necessary.

China moved into India's backyard when it signed an agreement with Sri Lanka in March 2007 to develop Hambantota Development Zone, which includes a container port, an airport and other facilities. China is said to be financing more than 85% of the project t of \$1 billion.. The entire project is scheduled to be completed by 2015. China is also involved in modernization of the Colombo port.

The Chinese role is not just about influence in Sri Lanka, it is about China's presence close to Indian shores, which has implications for India's security. .

Indian Ocean & China:

Access to the ocean is commercially and strategically important. However from its western point such as Somalia to the monarchies of the Persian Gulf to Iran and Pakistan along the shores of the Arabian Sea, lies the arc of instability.

Indian Ocean also has choke points and flash points, such as the Red Sea, the Strait of Hormuz, the Persian Gulf (Arab Gulf), the pirate-infested water off the Horn of Africa (Somalia), the Malacca and Sunda

Straits, through which passes 40% of the world's seaborne oil, including a third of China's supply, 70% of Japan's and 90% of India's.

A growing dependence on seaborne imports represents a potentially vulnerability in Chinese eyes. Beijing has responded in two ways: first by beginning to build up its own naval power, and second by seeking alternative supply routes that are less susceptible to interdiction by the United States or other hostile powers. Included among these are overland pipelines to contiguous energy sources in Central Asia and a variety of ambitious engineering projects (including a new port at Gwadar in Pakistan, pipelines from ports of Myanmar, to China and a possible canal across the isthmus of Thailand) that could shorten the maritime route to China..

In his "Monsoon" (2010) , US author Robert D. Kaplan argues that, it is in the Indian Ocean that the interests and influence of India, China and the United States are beginning to overlap and intersect. It is here, Kaplan says, that the 21st century's "global power dynamics will be revealed." Kaplan is at his best when he describes the "new Great Game" that is now unfolding across the Indian Ocean.

China perceives US as hostile:

The footprint of China in South Asia is possibly necessitated by the fact that China has a perception that the US is determined to contain Chinese influence across the world on the belief that if China rises, the US falls.. China perceives that the US has deployed its military all round its periphery. The US Taiwan Relations Act 1979 which required the US to "maintain (its) capacity...to resist any resort to force and other forms of coercion that would jeopardize its security...of the people of Taiwan" The deterrent intention of the US law is clear.

Furthermore, dissidents in Tibet and Xinjiang receive moral and diplomatic support and sometimes material assistance from ethnic diasporas and sympathetic Western governments. Furthermore, China has 14 adjacent countries. Except Russia, none of China's neighbours share their core national interests with those of China.

Conclusion:

Some strategists believe that the US must come to terms with the fact that China's rise is not simply a result of its failure of policy but is rather one of those great and highly infrequent historical shifts that governments can do relatively little to prevent.

Henry Kissinger in his book "On China"(2012), argues for an accommodation between the US and China. , Kissinger insists that the

common interests the two powers should make possible a “co-evolution” to “a more comprehensive framework.” He envisions wise leaders creating a “Pacific community” comparable to the Atlantic community that America has achieved with Europe. All Asian nations would then participate in a system perceived as a joint endeavour rather than a contest of rival Chinese and American blocs.

2. Regional conflicts in South Asia: Role of China

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ABSTRACT

South Asia a home to one-fifth of humanity is a region that by virtue of its geo-strategic location and population, for many years has been a central area of the Great Power struggle for influence. The politico-strategic environment in South Asia has been seriously hindered by internal or intra-state conflicts. The region is one of the most ethnically, culturally and linguistically diverse. It is host to deeply entrenched ethnic hostility, communal violence and numerous wars, both inter and intra-state. Some of these conflicts, such as those in Kashmir and Sri Lanka, are well documented, while many others receive minimal attention. Diverse political experiences, ideologies, ethnic identities and economic conditions across and within the states pose serious challenges for the security of the region. Extra regional powers particularly China for its own vested interest influenced the region by whetting up rivalry between the two major powers India and Pakistan as well as in some other ways to small powers such as Sri Lanka, Nepal, Bangladesh. However, the main focus of this paper will be analytical study which includes the overall geostrategic and geopolitical environments of South Asia along with the genesis of problem and the roots of mistrust between the two countries. The main focus of this paper will also examine the role of China in South Asia.

A GENERAL OVERVIEW OF SOUTH ASIA

South Asia is an expanse in which three adversary nations-India, Pakistan and China¹ share disputed borders (Dhanda 2010: 3). They are ragged by deep rooted animosities and countenance each other with nuclear and missile capabilities. On the one hand, Conflicts in the South Asia are having various forms (Ahmed, Bhatnagar 2008: 7-8) such as territorial disputes between India-Pakistan over the deadlock on issues of Kashmir, Siachen Glacier and Sir Creek. Border dispute between Afghanistan-Pakistan is also lingering. Sri Lankan ethnic conflict is a serious concern for the regional security. Cross border terrorism for the last three decades has been seriously threatening the region. India-Pakistan on several occasions has been blaming each other for carrying out terrorist activities or supporting such acts in their respective

countries. Conflict over natural resources is also figuring in the changing dynamics of security matrices. Baghliar Dam being built over River Chenab in Indian administered Kashmir is opposed by Pakistan. India-Bangladesh relations have been disturbed by many bilateral issues such as Farrakha Barrage and Moore Island. Bilateral relations between India and Sri Lanka have been affected by the unresolved Sri Lankan ethnic conflict and highly aggravated by the Indian intervention. Although India shares cordial relations with its neighbourhood but it lacks intensity and substance in its relations whereas Pakistan is sharing up to some extent good relations with South Asia countries except India.

It is considered that despite many other conflicts in the region, controversial issues between India and Pakistan attracted more attention. The continuing conflict between India and Pakistan has led to ever-increasing investments in arms and ammunitions to counter each other's military capability. Both states continue to invest huge amounts of their financial resources in buying weapons from the USA, China, Russia, Israel, Canada, Sweden and France. The complex security challenges confronted by South Asia have assumed an ominous dimension with India and Pakistan, two nuclear capable states, always remaining in a confrontational mode. No other region in the world today is as volatile and unstable as South Asia with its longstanding India-Pakistan hostility and conflict and its crucial role.²

The history of Indo-Pak relation is a narrative of two hostile neighbours, having different religious ideologies, different socio-economic bases and conflicting national interest. Its reality can be best described as a dichotomous model where the two countries are seen as locked in a zero-sum conflict *i.e.*, the gain for one is seen as the loss of the other (Khan 2009: 62). Unfortunately, the relationship between India and Pakistan since independence has been turbulent and hostile marked by wholesale communal massacres at the time of the partition of British India. Soon after their independence, relationship between both the

states witnessed deficit of trust (Rizvi 2012: 1-38). Three wars (1947-48, 1965, and 1971) were fought between both the countries. At least four occasions (1987,1990, 1999 and 2002) they were at the brink of a major armed conflict. Thus relationship between both the states remained most of time volatile except for brief periods (Tashkent³ and Shimla Agreements⁴). However, this was an exception rather than a normal practice in their bilateral relations. The motive, which impelled both India and Pakistan towards hostility and rivalry “are embedded in history and politics of the subcontinent(Nazir 2004: 21). The hostile relationship between these two countries has not only posed economic, political and security challenges but has also severely affected the security environment of the region (Marwah 2003).

On the other hand, many efforts have been made by both the countries to normalize bilateral relations but peace remained as a distant dream. Soon after independence, Jammu and Kashmir has become a bone of contention, over which both the countries fought two wars in 1948 and 1965. The 1971 year proved a very catastrophic over the issue of Bengali refugees and both the countries met with an another destructive war which led to the liberation of East Pakistan (Bangladesh) out of partition of Pakistan (Sanskar, Shrivastava 2011).However, by Shimla Agreement (1972), both the countries agreed to resolve their differences through peaceful means mutually agreed upon between them but the civil and military leadership of Pakistan could not forget this insult(Dixit 2002: 210).To take revenge of 1971, Pakistan started aiding and abetting cross border terrorism in India. At the same time, South Asia region has also been remained as the playground of Cold War politics. Many external powers such as USA, USSR and China intervened in the bilateral issues of both the countries and whetted up the animosity for their geopolitical and geostrategic interests in the region. These powers started assisting both the countries militarily and economically. Also, to contain Indian influence in South Asia, China supported Pakistan with nuclear technology. Changing security

environment and Sino-Pak nexus compelled India to develop nuclear capability.

On account of security concern perceptions, both the countries India and Pakistan, conducted their nuclear tests in 1998 to display their nuclear technology. In 1999, Kargil war started in Kashmir. As a result of this misadventure, both nations had suffered considerable losses in term of man and material. Instead of bringing peace and prosperity to their majority of population deprived of basic needs, people of both the countries felt threatened and insecure by such misadventures. The Indo-Pak rivalry remains one of the most enduring⁵ and unresolved conflict since their independence. (Paul and Hogg 2005: 253). Paul who is expert in this area contended that there is no sign of a permanent settlement is in the vicinity in near future despite occasional normalcy being witnessed by these countries. During 1990's, the acquisition of nuclear weapon and introduction of terrorist tactics into the conflict heightened the possibility of breaking out a catastrophic war in South Asia with unimaginable consequences (Paul 2005: 3).

The rivalry between the two countries further intensified when India began to assert its role as a hegemonic power in the region. Pakistan, though accepted India as a significant player in the region, sought to resist its attempts for domination. Consequently, Pakistan's foreign policy towards India has been remained as reactive (Paul 2005: 4). In many incidents such as the Kargil crises (1999), the terrorist attacks on the Indian parliament (December 13, 2001), Indian railways in Mumbai (August 2006); Taj and Oberoi Trident hotels (November 26, 2008) etc. further intensified bilateral animosity.

The Indo-Pak relations remained one of the most hyperbolic and unresolved conflict since their independence. In such milieu, the relations are once again became tensed and poised and does not need more than a few hours to enter into a conflict situation because of the

recent terrorist activities. Despite Pakistan's rejections of all imputations of involvement in the terrorist attacks, Indian government is pointing its finger at Pakistan. Thus, the South Asian security dynamics revolve basically around the rivalry and antagonism between India and Pakistan.

The external powers particularly USA and China had played a critical role in India and Pakistan relations. These two powers openly supported Pakistan for their geo-political influence. SisirGupta, an expert of the strategic affairs, outlined America's and China's anti-India approach in the following words:

“Although China and USA shared the belief that India could be kept under check through Pakistan. The reasons for their doing so might have been different.

In the case of America, the underlying assumption behind its foreign policy postures was in its supreme confidence in itself. There was consequently a broad western stance of siding with the so called weaker powers in regional contests, for example, Malaysia against Indonesia, Pakistan against India, and Israel against the Arabs.

In the case of China, its geopolitical stakes in preventing India from becoming a major power were so high that it began to perceive a great deal of interest in the ability of Pakistan to act as a check on India” (Gupta 2008: 145-52).

The purpose of this paper is to understand the issues of rivalries between India and Pakistan. It is an attempt to know the causes of persistency of this rivalry even when some other long-running conflicts in different parts of the world have come to an end. This paper also analyses the role of external powers in whetting up the conflicting issues rather than helping to resolve them.

ISSUES OF RIVALRY BETWEEN INDIA AND PAKISTAN

The disputes between India and Pakistan, though regional in nature, were exploited by the Great Powers. The root of the Indo-Pak confrontation stemmed from the communal antagonism which was deep-rooted in the demographic distribution of their territories. There are a number of reasons behind the Indo-Pak persistent enmity, of which, the most important are discussed below;

KASHMIR ISSUE: A STUMBLING BLOCK TO PEACE

“When the media covers Kashmir, it inevitably focuses on the possibility of war between India and Pakistan”. **Izzat Jarudi**

Kashmir, a 222,236sq km area in the north-western Indian subcontinent, is bordered by the Indian states of Himachal Pradesh and Punjab in the South, Pakistan in the west, China in the northeast and Afghanistan in the northwest. The area has been baptized a "disputed territory" between India and Pakistan since independence. India-Pakistan relations have revolved mainly around the issue of Kashmir. This issue has been a major bone of contention on which they have fought two wars (1947, 1965) against each other. First Kashmir War was fought from 1947 to 1948. It was the first of four wars fought between the two newly independent nations. The results of the war affected the geopolitics of both the countries. While the struggle for attaining the right of self-determination which was being carried out peacefully in the political arena, has been transformed into an armed resistance movement for the last three decades. Tension between the two countries is unlikely to diminish without an amicable resolution of the conflict.

The Kashmir dispute kept India and Pakistan divided and has largely influenced the international outlook of the two countries. It has been a major cause of the armed conflicts between India and Pakistan. In fact, this dispute has hampered all the efforts on part of both states to normalize their relations. Until this dispute is settled, the threat of war is bound to persist (Gupta 2011). Their relations have been affected by this

issue very seriously and most of the scholars hold this issue responsible for the failure to reach an agreement on any other major issues and weakened the pace of any normalization process between the two countries. Both nations have unfortunately continued to look at the issue in an emotional rather than a rational and realistic manner.

Pakistan has consistently maintained that Kashmir is the 'core' problem between the two countries and until this issue is resolved, all the attempts to bring normalcy in their relations will be fruitless. Both the parties have remained largely inflexible in their positions. Even, mediatory efforts by some friendly countries have not been fructified. However, both the countries made many efforts to resolve this dispute, but due to stubborn attitude from both the sides, this issue is lingering since independence of both the countries. India has tried a variety of strategies to keep Kashmir in its fold such as Article 370 of the Indian constitution.⁶

However, from the mid-1960s onwards, India sought to integrate Jammu and Kashmir more tightly into the mainstream. These efforts might have provoked Pakistan in 1965, causing the outbreak of a second war between the two countries (Paul 2005: 215). Despite the failure of the earlier bilateral efforts, many more were made by Pakistan to resolve the dispute through bilateral negotiations that were all frustrated by Indian intransigence. In fact, the two Indo-Pak wars 1948, 1965 and a mini war the 'Kargil Conflict 1999' have been fought over this conflict and the energies of the two countries have been greatly consumed over the tension generated by this issue. Noor-ulHaq argued in one of his articles that people of Kashmir have been fighting for freedom for the last sixty years which was referred by India as an "insurgency"; later, as "militancy" and now it is referred to as "terrorism". All these terms are used to mislead international opinion and to disguise the fact of the continued forcible Indian occupation of Kashmir (Haq 2003: 29).

Kashmir is very important for both the countries on account of its strategic location and major source of water. Strategically, it borders with

Afghanistan, Tajikistan, Sinkiang and Tibet. Kashmir was conceived as a gateway to Central Asia and a stronghold of defence. It also holds a key of both countries economy being origin of rivers flowing in India and Pakistan. The Indus River originated and flows in Tibet, Kashmir and Pakistan. It provides water resources for the economy of Pakistan - especially the breadbasket of Punjab and Sindh which account for most of the nation's agricultural production. The control of this river system is critical to the survival of people living in northern Pakistan. If India were to place a dam on the river and divert the water to their side of the border, to the dry regions of the south, Pakistan could suffer a water shortage in the northern part of the country.

SIACHEN GLACIER

The Siachen glacier is the highest battlefield in the world, having witnessed military skirmishes between India and Pakistan for approximately three decades. This glacier is 70 km long and flows from an altitude of 5750 meters. Considered uninhabitable, it was left undemarcated. The line of control between India and Pakistan in Jammu and Kashmir terminated at the Salto range in the northeast at the point named NJ9842 (Koithara 2004: 36). Both India and Pakistan claim sovereignty over the entire Siachen region. Prior to 1984, neither India nor Pakistan had any permanent presence in the area. When Pakistan gave permission to a Japanese expedition team to scale the important Rimo peak in 1984, it provoked India to take measures in order to secure the glacier.

The peak, located east of Siachen, and if it comes under Pakistan, it weakens the Indian claim over eastern areas of the Aksai Chin. The Indian military believed that such an expedition would provide a link for the western and eastern routes — the trade route leading to Karakoram Pass and China and eventually provide a tactical, if not strategic advantage to Pakistan and China. In 1984, India launched a successful military operation (Meghdoot). Against Indian operation Pakistan launches operation -Ababeel. (Joshi, 2012), but India succeeded in

maintaining control over the Siachen Glacier and its two passes Sia La and Bilafond La (*The Tribune*, April 14, 2012). The areas north and east of this point had been under India's control. Shimla Accord (1972) forbade unilateral territorial alteration by positioning troops in the Salto range. Pakistan accuses India with the charges of control over the area while India's position is that the areas were under her control before the Shimla Accord. India's occupation of the Siachin Glacier was viewed by Pakistan as a stab in the back. The ensuing crisis nearly brought the two countries to come to blows in 1984. Further attempts to reclaim positions were launched by Pakistan in 1990, 1995, 1996 and even in early 1999, just prior to the Lahore Summit.⁷ Political constraints on the Indian government, however, compelled it to pull out of negotiations and the dispute has continued ever since. However, Ashutosh Mishra, an expert on this issue has argued that both the countries close to resolution of this problem since late 1980s. (Mishra 2010: 118). This conflict puts an enormous drain on the national exchequer on both sides. India suggested a comprehensive cease-fire in the region, while Pakistan wants redeployment. (Joshua 2012).

In order to sort out this crisis, both the countries made many efforts in this direction. Till date, 12 rounds of talks held but could not make any breakthrough. Both sides were sticking to their respective positions and still viewing the dispute as a zero sum game. During the latest talk between the defense secretaries of both the countries, on Siachen in June 11-12, 2012, advocated the early resolve of dispute. The Siachen talks were held when both the sides strongly raising demand for the demilitarization of the glacier after a destructive avalanche took place on April 7, 2012 in the Gayari region. Unfortunately, no major headway was achieved during the talks as both the countries are sticking to maintain the status quo.

SIR CREEK

The dispute over Sir Creek is related to the maritime boundary between the Kutch and the Sindh region of respective countries. This is a

96 km marshy strip in the Rann of Kutch area lying between the southern tips of Pakistan's Sindh province and Indian state of Gujarat, opening in the Arabian Sea. Pakistan claimed over this region as per paras 9 and 10 of the Bombay Government Resolution of 1914 signed between the then Government of Sindh and Rao Maharaj, the ruler of the princely state of Kutch, according to which Creek was included in Sindh region. This dispute became reason for Indo-Pak War of 1965.

The British Prime Minister Harold Wilson successfully persuaded both countries to end hostilities and set up a tribunal to resolve the dispute in the same year. This case referred it to India-Pakistan Western Boundary Case Tribunal, presided by Swedish Judge Gunnar Lagergren. It awarded a solution in February 1968 that was accepted by both contestants. The International Tribunal that settled the Kutch dispute left untouched the Creek, saying it is out of the purview of tribunal (Mishra 2010: 32). A consensus was reached and boundary was fixed in 1968 which saw Pakistan getting 10% of its claim of 3,500 sq. miles. But what complicates the issue is that the Creek is a fluctuating tidal channel that from time to time shifts its course. India's case is based on a 1914 map, which shows the land extremities of the estuary, which should be extended on -normal nautical principles- to the maritime boundary. Pakistan contends that the outer limits of Sir Creek have been altered considerably over the years due to tidal interference, which shifted it outward, and the Sea space should be equally divided irrespective of the claims based on India's long coast lines (Mishra 2010: 32-33).

The Indian Air Force fighter plane MiG-21 shot down a Pakistani Navy BreguetAtlantique surveillance aircraft over the Sir Creek on August 10, 1999, killing all the 16 crews on board. This incident surcharged the strategic environment on both sides and armed forces again deployed on both sides of the LOC. India claimed that the plane had strayed into its airspace which was disputed by the Pakistani navy.⁸

Given the mutual possibility of the loss of territory and potential economic dividends, both sides trying to find out the solution of this problem through dialogue and the latest two-day talks on Sir Creek issue was held on 18-19 June 2012 in New Delhi.⁹The two sides discussed the land boundary in the Sir Creek area and also delimitation of International Maritime Boundary between both the countries. Both sides reiterated their desire to find an amicable solution of the Sir Creek issue through sustained and result-oriented dialogue. Both sides agreed to hold the next round of the talks on Sir Creek issue in Pakistan at mutually convenient dates to be determined through diplomatic channels.

**TULBUL NAVIGATION PROJECT / WULAR BARRAGE AND STORAGE
PROJECT DISPUTE**

The project itself in nomenclature displays dispute. India refers to it as Tulbul navigation project whereas Pakistan calls it Wular barrage. The basic dispute concerns a barrage being constructed by India in 1984 on the Jhelum River just below Wular Lake, about fifteen miles north of Srinagar and 5,180 feet above sea level. Pakistan protested claiming it was a violation of 1960 Indus Water Treaty (The Times of India, July 29, 2004). Under the Indus Water Treaty (IWT) of 1960 unlimited use of the eastern river water of the Indus system i.e., Beas, Ravi, Satluj are assigned to India while the western water i.e., Chenab, Indus, Jhelum belong to Pakistan (Mishra 2010: 32). The treaty allowed Pakistan to construct a system of replacement canals to convey water from the western rivers into those areas in West Pakistan which had previously depended for their irrigation supplies on water from the eastern rivers (Bhatnagar 1986: 230-31). Pakistan has built the Mangla and Tarbela dams and several other similar facilities on the waters of Indus, Jhelum and Chenab. Similarly India has been building various dams and barrages on the Ravi, Sutlej and Beas. Disputes over the shared waters have been cropping up from time to time, most notably over the Baglihar dam which India has constructed on Chenab River (Vaid and Maini 2012: 6). Pakistan took this case to Indus Waters Commission

(International Arbitral Court) in 1986. India suspended construction work until some agreement could be reached. Due to geo-economic importance and geostrategic location, it has become a politically sensitive issue for both sides (Mishra 2010: 32-33). More than ten rounds of talks have been held to resolve the issue. Recently in March 27-28, 2012, both the countries resumed dialogue. Delegations of the two countries tried to resolve this issue.¹⁰

TERRORISM

Terrorism is a major problem of the South Asia region. The terrorists are playing havoc with the man and material. Both the countries are charging each other for this problem in their areas. With the intervention of the external powers for their vested interests, this problem was further heightened. When Soviet Union withdrew from Afghanistan in 1989 and the United States followed suit, a civil war broke out among Afghan ethnic warlords. Though, in the beginning, Northern Alliance was successful but the Taliban comprising mainly Pakhtuns of southern Afghanistan ousted them in 1996. This Taliban regime received support and recognition from Pakistan. Pakistani defence strategists had always worried about Pakistan's lack of 'strategic depth' vis-à-vis India began to entertain ambitions of creating an Islamic super-state or confederation comprising Pakistan, Afghanistan and Indian administered Kashmir. Many of the Pakistani Mujahideen from the Afghan theatre had already shifted their activity to the Indian-administered Kashmir. Within Pakistan militant fundamentalist organizations were openly active in recruiting volunteers to fight in Kashmir. The Harkat-ul-Mujahideen (HUM), Jaish-e-Muhammad (JUM) and the Laskar-e-Tayyaba (LeT) were the major concerns from Indian security perspective. The Mujahideen perpetually crossing into the India and carried out armed attacks against what they perceived were Indian occupation forces. These organizations were patronized by ISI of Pakistan as well as by the Pakistan military (Ahmed 2012: 77).

This problem haunting India during the last 30 years but terrorist attacks have been increased exponentially in the first decade of the 21st century. On December 13, 2001 an attack by Pakistan based militants on the Indian Parliament drove the two countries near to war as both sides deployed soldiers on the both sides of LOC. It was international diplomacy which calmed tempers on both sides and a major war between two neighbouring nuclear-weapon states averted. However, on November 26, 2008 a terrorist attack carried out by the LeT cadres in Taj and Oberai hotels and consequently 170 innocent people including more than 50 Indian Muslims died in this incident. Once again the prospects of an all-out war became imminent. Good sense prevailed and averted the war through the international diplomacy. On the other hand, Pakistan has persistently alleged that India is behind the on-going armed insurgency in Balochistan.

In the post 9/11, Pakistan joined George W Bush's war on terror and consequently the Pakistani Taliban turned their guns on the Pakistani power elite while simultaneously wreaking havoc on completely innocent men, women and children through a spate of indiscriminate suicide bombings. During 2001-2011 at least 35 thousand Pakistanis including 5000 military personnel lost their lives because of the terrorism carried out by the Taliban in Pakistan.¹¹ Such activities had devastating impact on the Pakistan economy as foreign investors fled and Pakistan gained the unenviable reputation of the epicentre of international terrorism and much worse. India is always expressed its fear regarding the Pakistan's nuclear may go into the hands of extremists. Various efforts have been made between the two countries in order to bring normalcy, but all these proved fruitless. In recently a joint statement was signed between the foreign secretaries of India and Pakistan on July 5, 2012, New Delhi.

ROLE OF CHINA IN INDO-PAKISTAN RELATIONS

Since end of the colonialism, South Asia has been remained as a battle field for external powers. These powers did not want to leave this

region for one or the other reasons. When the question comes of Indo-Pak relations, external powers involvement became more perceptible. With the beginning of the Cold War, Indo-Pak relations have been hijacked by the Cold War politics. These two countries instigated to fight against each other by these external powers. Both USA and China helped Pakistan militarily and economically. To check communism and kept its hold on these regions, USA led security alliances were formed. Pakistan joined these security alliances like SEATO, CENTO etc. whereas India on account of its Nonalignment policy kept itself at bay from these security alliances. In this way, these countries remained in the opposite groups.

In order to achieve their vested interests, attempts have been made by these great powers to maintain asymmetries in the distribution of military and economic power. This has been amply manifested in USA's dual containment policy in respect of Pakistan and India (Zafar 2001: 3). In the same, Pakistan has been given pivotal place in the Chinese foreign policy. On the one hand, it consistently created pressure on India by interfering in the Kashmir issue and on the other hand supported Pakistan during the Indo-Pak war by providing strategic support. India's major concern come into play when China being itself nuclear power, started helping in the modernization its military built up as well aiding in the development in its nuclear programme.

Although, geographically China is not considered the part of South Asia but it is an important factor in geo-strategic landscape of South Asia. The uncertain triangular among India-Pakistan-China is also contributing to the tensions between India and Pakistan. Zafar argued in one of his papers that the legacy of the distrust and conflict, the unresolved border issues and the plurality of perceptions and options of the decision-makers in each country heightened tension and complexity in this region (Zafar 2001: 1). In the views of perceptible scholar that structured tension between India and Pakistan is the brainchild of China, to maintain its superiority in this region. Though the roots of India-Pakistan animosity are deep-seated in religion, history, and the

politics of revenge and thus predate Sino-India hostility. China's strategists recognized the enduring nature of the India-Pakistan enmity and exploiting it to Beijing's advantage. In fact, Beijing has long been the most important player in the India-Pakistan-China triangular relationship. Since the Indo-China border war of 1962, China has aligned itself with Pakistan and made heavy strategic and economic investments in that country to keep the common enemy, India under strategic pressure (Malik 2003: 35-50). In 1963, Pakistan ceded to China the Trans-Karakoram Tract, also known as Shaksam Valley, of the disputed territory of Kashmir. The area subsequently became part of the land bridge linking Pakistan to China's Xinjiang along the Karakoram Highway. China sided with Pakistan during the 1965 and 1971 wars against India (Chawla 2012: 50) during which China put its own forces along the Indian border on high alert, in order to put pressure on India from two frontier sides. Since then, China has proved one of the most reliable partners to Pakistan. China has provided military equipments and economic aid whereas its other friends such as the United States started cutting off military aid. China always come forward to support Pakistan when it was isolated by the international comity due to various reasons like its nuclear proliferation, the antidemocratic coup d'état in 1999 and its support of the Taliban regime in neighbouring Afghanistan. China has not only remained reliable partner but it helped Pakistan to develop its nuclear programme. According to Chinese Strategic analysts, in South Asia, Pakistan is the only country that counters India's dominance. It was in a position to be helpful in fulfilling the objective of China's South Asia policy. The Chinese believed that as long as India is engaged with Pakistan on its western frontier, it will not be a danger on the Tibetan border. A secure and stable India at peace with Pakistan would, on the other hand, make it free from pressure to focus on China and East Asia. John Garver has succinctly summed up China's Pakistan policy:

“China's overriding strategic interest is to keep Pakistan independent, powerful, and confident enough to present India

with a standing two-front threat... Were India able to dissolve this two-front threat by subordinating Pakistan, its position against China would be much stronger ...[This would amount to] conceding South Asia as an Indian sphere of nuance. Such a move would spell the virtual end to Chinese aspirations of being the leading Asian power and would greatly weaken China's position against Indian power" (Garver 2008: 80-85).

Through Pakistan, China wants to create the threat perception which saps India's military power. It was the provision of the Chinese nuclear and missile shield to Pakistan during the late 1980s and 1990s (at the height of China-India rapprochement) that encourages Islamabad to wage a proxy war in Kashmir (Malik, M.J. 2004: 135). A reliable ally such as Pakistan also provides China with a secure access to naval bases (Karachi and Ormara) in Arabian Sea. China's concerns about separatist Islamic influence in its Xinjiang also kept China's engaged with Pakistan (Malik, M.J. 2004: 135). China has been actively assisting Pakistan with its nuclear program in many aspects of nuclear programme. Late 1980s onward it has provided with ready-to-launch M-9, M-11, and Dong Feng 21 ballistic missiles, thus helping it to bridge the military capability gap with respect to its arch rival India (Rehman 2012: 65-66). It is widely accepted that China transferred equipment and technology and provided scientific expertise to Pakistan's nuclear weapons. Ballistic missile programs of Pakistan throughout the 1980s and 1990s was also not left untouched which got optimum assistance from China and enhanced Pakistan's strength in the South Asian strategic balance. The most significant development in Chinese-Pakistani military cooperation occurred in 1992, when China supplied Pakistan with 34 short-range ballistic M-11 missiles. Beijing also built a turn-key ballistic missile manufacturing facility near Rawalpindi, and helped Pakistan develop the 750-km-range solid-fueled Shaheen-1 ballistic missile (Curtis, Lisa and Scissors, Derek. (2012).

In the triangular power balance game, the South Asian military balance of power is neither pro-India nor pro-Pakistan; it has always been pro-China.¹² Beijing will take all possible means including war to ensure that the regional power balance does not tilt in either India or Pakistan favour. Even in the absence of war, Pakistan hopes to continue to reap significant military and economic payoffs not only from the intensifying Sino-Indian geopolitical rivalry in Southern Asia but also from confrontation between China and the United States, which will further increase the significance of China's strategic ties with Pakistan.

Apart from China, there are many other external powers which are/were playing important role in relations between India and Pakistan since their independence. The Cold War politics has also played the mischievous role to make them fight against each other and accelerated the pace of nuclearisation in South Asia. The international security system of alliances and counter alliances heightened security concerns in South Asia. Oftenly, attempts have been made by the major powers to maintain asymmetries in the distribution of military and economic powers and to create technological and legal condominiums to enshrine the rights of great powers. This has been amply manifested in USA's dual containment policy in respect of Pakistan and India.

CONCLUSION

The politico-strategic environment in South Asia remained 'tensed', throughout the last sixty seven years on account of regional disputes. However, many efforts have been made to normalize this environment but no considerable impacts are visible. Along with the regional disputes, some external power intervention in this region further intensified animosities among the countries of this region. Also, they made fight against each other in order to create balance of power in their favour.

India and Pakistan are deeply immersed in these conflicts. The present conflict between India and Pakistan is not a new phenomenon, but it is the legacy of the past. From the very beginning, the relations between the two countries are marked by conflict, discord, mutual

distrust and suspicions. There were some brief periods when these relations could be described as normal and cordial. However, this was an exception rather than a normal practice in these bilateral relations. Both states have followed a “swing” model of relationship, where the pendulum of the relationships swings from one end to the other. The peace, security and stability of South Asia primarily depends on the status of relations between the two antagonists being the two powerful states of the region. This hostile relationship has immensely affected the security environment in the region. Due to a qualitative change from conventional to nuclear, economic sanctions and embargoes, the perimeters of competition between the two rivals could result in domestic destabilization, and hardships in both states, economic as well as political and security challenges. Analysts believe that conflict between the two states is of a protracted nature, leaving behind little opportunities for peaceful coexistence. Perceptible scholars of the region realized that the Kashmir issue is one of main reasons for the nuclearisation. In addition to this, it is also perceived by Pakistan that the military imbalance is the major threats from India. In order to come at par with India, its efforts have been supported by external powers in general and China in particular.

Notes :

1. Though China is not a part of South Asia but it has serious implications for South Asian security. The South Asian security equation cannot be realistically assessed without taking China into account. China sees itself as an emerging military, economic and political superpower, with real and expanding interests in South and Southeast Asia. Thus China challenges India's pre-eminence and their relationship has settled into a protracted rivalry. Since the mid 1960s, China has lent its political support and transferred arms to Pakistan to create a counter weight to India position. Above all, India believes that the balance of power in South Asia is affected by China being a nuclear power.
2. The former president of Pakistan, General Pervez Musharraf, has been quoted by a newspaper in the United States as having called South Asia “one of the most volatile regions in the world”. He called on the US government “to address the root causes of problems in the region and force Pakistan and India to resolve their political differences”. He said the region faced three major challenges: terrorism and extremism, the acrimonious relationship between India and Pakistan, and poverty and

- underdevelopment. He said, “Pakistan faces all facets of extremism, including Al Qaeda and the Taliban, and...groups [that propagate them] must be stopped from spreading in the society...this is a battle for hearts and minds”. See also, Editorial (2009). South Asia: the most volatile region. Reported in, The Daily Times of Pakistan.
3. The Tashkent Declaration of 10 January 1966 was a peace agreement between India and Pakistan after the 1965 war. Peace had been achieved by the intervention of the great powers those convinced the two nations for cease-fire. A meeting was held in Tashkent in the USSR (now in Uzbekistan) beginning on 4 January 1966 to try to create a more permanent settlement. The Soviets, represented by Premier Kosygin moderated between Indian Prime Minister LalBahadurShastri and Pakistani President Muhammad Ayub Khan. See also, Brig. Shakti Gurung.(2008). Strategy to resolve the Jammu and Kashmir dispute, pp. 10-12. Asian Security Scenario, NDC, Papers.
 4. The Simla Treaty, popularly known as the Simla Pact or the Simla Agreement, was signed between India and Pakistan on 2 July 1972 following the 1971 India- Pakistan War. The treaty was signed in Simla, by Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto, the President of Pakistan, and Indira Gandhi, the Prime Minister of India. The agreement laid down the principles that should govern their future relations. It also conceived steps to be taken for further normalization of mutual relations. It is significant that the Cease-Fire Line was changed to the LC during this summit. This was not merely a change of nomenclature but a consequence of an agreement, seeking to adhere to the status quo by all means. The treaty has been the basis of all subsequent bilateral talks between India and Pakistan, though it has not prevented the relationship between the two countries from deteriorating to the point of armed conflict. See also, Brig. Shakti Gurung.(2008). Strategy to resolve the Jammu and Kashmir dispute, pp. 10-12. Asian Security Scenario, NDC, Papers.
 5. The Kashmir conflict is one of the most controversial in nature. Although it can be argued that six decades of conflict is rather modest in an historical perspective, the conflict is frequently portrayed in terms of ‘enduring’ and ‘protracted’. Defined by Paul as a; “*persistent, fundamental, and long term incapability of goals between India and Pakistan. For full detail see, T.V.Paul, 2005.*
 6. Article 370, gave the state of Jammu and Kashmir a “special status” with greater autonomy over other Indian states. It contains ‘temporary provisions’ with respect to the State of Jammu and Kashmir. For more detail see, D.D. Basu(2012). *Introduction to the Constitution of India*. 20TH edition. Lexisnexis: New Delhi.
 7. The Lahore Declaration was a bilateral agreement between India and Pakistan signed in February 21, 1999, by the then-Prime Minister of India Atal Bihari Vajpayee and the then-Prime Minister of Pakistan Nawaz Sharif in Lahore, Pakistan. It signalled a major breakthrough in overcoming the historically strained bilateral relations between the two nations in the aftermath of the nuclear tests carried out by both nations in May 1998. But did not show any positive result due to the Kargil

- misadventure on the part of Pakistan. For more details see Ministry of External Relations, Republic of India., Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Islamic Republic of Pakistan.
8. MacKinnon, Ian. (August 11, 1999). 16 dead as India shoots down Pakistani naval plane, *The Independent* (London). Also can see in <http://indiancurrentaffairs.wordpress.com>
 9. Extracted from the joint statement -on India-Pakistan Talks on Sir Creek June 19, 2012. The Indian delegation was led by Surveyor General of India Swarna Subba Rao and the Pakistani side was led by Additional Secretary in the Ministry of Defence Rear Admiral Farrokh Ahmad. For this see, <http://www.mea.gov.in/mystar.php?id=530519646> Accessed on November 5, 2012.
 10. During this dialogue the Indian delegation was led by Mr. Dhruv Vijai Singh, Secretary, Ministry of Water Resources (GOI), and the Pakistan delegation was led by Mr. Imtiaz Kazi, Secretary Ministry of Water and Power. Pakistan delegation also met to Vincent H. Pala, Minister of state for Water Resources, (GOI). Both sides committed to bilateral engagement in a spirit of constructive cooperation.
 11. Terror In Pakistan Since 9/11 available on www.truthr.org. Accessed 2012 September, 28.
 12. For full discussion refer to Trenin, Dmitri. 2012: True Partners? How Russia and China see each other, Centre for European Reform (CER), Great College Street, London.

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3. China's Increasing Footprint in South Asia: Implications for India

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Introduction

The present paper seeks to analyse the expanding footprint of China in South Asia and its implications for India. China and India, the two Asian giant remain strategic rivals competing for regional influence and engage in contradictory and counterproductive acts. Both the nations have the requisite potential for robust economic growth, independently as well as conjointly. However, China's GDP is four times larger than that of India.

The core of China's policy is to enhance its economic and strategic interests by keeping a peaceful and stable environment particularly along

its strategic periphery. Under this policy, China is seeking to enhance its security around the periphery through trade and transportation corridors and maintain stability around it by creating new regional institutions in order to deal with post Cold War security challenges.¹

A renowned expert on China, Mohan Malik has noted that “South Asia ranks third in importance after the North East and South East Asian regions in China’s Asia policy”. The region of South Asia has of late become an important aspect in China’s foreign policy. Beijing perceives that the lasting stability and development in the region holds the key to security of China in various ways. Any sort of instability in the region would have serious implications for China. And as such China shares common borders with Afghanistan, Bhutan, India, Nepal and Pakistan.²

China’s expanding footprint in South Asia is in consonance with its growing economic and military power. Beijing is putting a lot of energy and making huge investment to expand its cooperation with India’s South Asian neighbours in its favour. From the strategic and economic point of view, China in a bid to serve its national interests is expanding its reach in South Asia in which India is a major player. China’s increasing presence in South Asia and its consequent attempts to gain access to the Indian Ocean posed major challenges to India requiring necessary moves to be undertaken to address it.³

Geo-Strategic Significance of South Asia

The South Asian region comprises of seven nations such as India, Pakistan, Srilanka, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Nepal, and Maldives. South Asia as a region occupies an important place among the regions of the world due in part to the presence of two nuclear power countries, India and Pakistan. The region is not only located in a critical position but is identified as one of the poorest areas of the globe. Besides, the region covers a vast area equivalent to the whole of Europe and is home to one-fifth of the global population.⁴

The region assumes immense significance by virtue of its geo-strategic location and the availability of natural wealth. It is located in close proximity to the Persian Gulf as well as Central Asia which is known for the presence of huge reserves of oil and natural gas. From the economic and strategic perspective, South Asia offers huge market and a tremendous scope for investment. Most nations of this region have growing large markets of millions of middle-class citizens with huge buying capacity, high-caliber skilled and cheap labor forces, rich natural resources, democratic frameworks, reliable legal systems as well as economic liberalization policies. This has without any doubt evoked much interest from the major powers of the world including the United States, Japan, China, etc.⁵

India's Predominant Position in South Asia and Beyond

India enjoys strong cultural, linguistic and ethnic connections with the neighbouring countries. Among the South Asian countries, India is the largest which accounts for 70 per cent of population, nearly 80 per cent of the GDP and about 75 per cent of the regional economic output. India shares boundary with all the South Asian neighbours. Should India play a crucial role on the global stage then it becomes imperative to maintain stability in its relations with its neighbours.⁶ From the Geo-strategically and geo-politically point of view, India's relations with the South Asian neighbours have been guided by – first, its desire to protect the sub-continent from the adverse external forces that might destabilise India's security environment and secondly, its desire to ensure that geographically proximity and ethno-religious affinities do not lead to instability on or near its border, particularly as they inevitably may affect its domestic, ethnic, religious and political relationships. This could even give rise to secessionist demands within the country.⁷

India enjoys a predominant position in South Asia and beyond owing to its large size, economic capabilities, military prowess and geographical standing. India has a huge stake in not only playing a pivotal role in the region but also keeping it free from external powers' presence and interference.⁸ According to Stephen Blank, a well known expert who has written extensively on Asian security is of the view that India is definitely an extra-regional power. The U.S. Quadrennial Review published in 2010 has described India as a net provider of security in the Indian Ocean and beyond.⁹ Bhabani Sen Gupta has argued in favour of India playing a crucial role in the region when he said that, "The Indian elephant cannot transform itself into a mouse. If South Asia is to get itself out of the crippling binds of conflicts and cleavages, the six will have to accept the bigness of the seventh. And the seventh, that is India, will have to prove to the six that big can indeed be beautiful." India shares a land border with Pakistan, Nepal, Bhutan and Bangladesh and a maritime border with Srilanka and Maldives. India accounts for 72 percent of the land surface in South Asia. The economic potential and military capabilities of India have made the country a primary regional force in South Asia to be reckoned with. India is being referred to as the 'key to the development and progress of SAARC'. India's responsibility in shaping and directing the cooperation drive was recognized by extra-regional powers. The size and position of India give it a special role of leadership in South Asian and world affairs. They confer on it at the same time the special responsibility for accommodation and restraint that strength entails.¹⁰

Chinese Strategic Interests in South Asia

China has developed keen long-term strategic and economic interests in South Asia in consonant with the changing scenario in the region. It seeks to maintain its long-term presence in the region thereby allowing it to play a bigger role in the region. By expanding closer relations with the smaller nations of South Asia, China not only seeks to serve, economic,

security and energy interests but at the same time limit Indian regional power status in the region. Zhao Gancheng, Director of South Asia Studies at the Shanghai Institute for International Studies has made a comments on how Beijing looks at South Asia that,

“A strategically more autonomous South Asia would ... lead to less reliance of South Asia on foreign forces ... From the angle of long-term interests ... China should adopt a dialectic approach and follow a long term South Asia policy ... As the construction of a new South Asian regional order progresses, it would be necessary for China to play a permanent role in establishing equilibrium and stability in South Asia.”¹¹

China's Anti-Indian Move in South Asia

China is playing a dirty game against India. On the one side, it seeks to engage close economic and strategic relations with India. But on the other side it is supplying arms and equipment to India's neighbouring countries. A large per cent of China's arms sales goes to India's neighbouring countries. However, China has time and again justified its military relations with Indian neighbours as legitimate and normal state-to-state relations well within the premises of the Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence.¹² Mohan Malik, a renowned expert on India-China relations is of the view that, China is following a policy of strategy of encirclement, envelopment and entanglement towards India. *Encirclement* is a kind of strengthened Chinese strategic presence (encircling India) in Tibet, Pakistan, Nepal, Srilanka, Bangladesh, Myanmar and in the Indian Ocean island states. *Envelopment* is essentially integrating all of India's neighbours into the Chinese economy. And *Entanglement* seeks to exploit India's domestic contradictions and multiple security concerns. This strategy is aimed at maintaining Beijing's weight in South Asia thereby thwarting India's strategic role as a regional power in the South Asian region.¹³ Beijing is increasingly making an effort to influence India's neighborhood for its long-term benefits through trade, infrastructural concessions and investments. The purpose for this is to checkmate India's growing economic and political influence together with its ambition to play a big power role and to gain strategic presence in the Indian Ocean.

China's strategic inroads into Nepal and Bhutan are a cause of security concern for India. One of the renowned Chinese academicians, Professor Wang Hongwei of the Chinese Academy of Social Sciences has made a comment that, 'China knows very well India's desire to turn Nepal into a second Bhutan or Sikkim. But China must not let this situation to occur. China will always support to keep Nepal sovereign, free and united.'¹⁴ It has in recent times taken initiatives for the development of the Gwadar Port off the Baluchistan coast, closer military ties with Myanmar and also its developmental projects in Bangladesh. These are viewed with suspicion in India.¹⁵ India is strategically concerned about the '*String of Pearls*' strategy employed by China to extending its areas of influence

very close to India's border. One of the key objectives of this strategy is to size up with its adversaries establishing its footprint in the region with deployment capabilities to challenge and decisively achieve military objectives against adversaries in a conflict/war situation. China also seeks to reinforce sea-based nuclear deterrence against India and other powers through forward deployment and patrol of its nuclear attack and fleet ballistic missile submarines in the region.¹⁶

India's inimical relations with both China and Pakistan have given way to the closer cooperation between the latter two countries. Also their common interests of not wanting to see India become a major power have played a significant part. Pakistan got maximum benefit out of this. India is seriously concerned about China providing arms and equipments needs to Pakistan that has nothing to do with Islamabad security concerns. Beijing has transferred to Pakistan weapons designs and nuclear fissile material. China's policy of equipping Pakistan serves dual purposes- one is that it helps Pakistan to maintain balance with arch rival India, thereby challenging India's conventional military strength and secondly, it pressurises India from taking any such steps that is not in favor of China. This way arms supply relationship between China and Pakistan has serious negative implications to India. These developments have compelled many strategic analysts in India to view that Beijing has a continuous and an uninterrupted support to Pakistan as a policy of encirclement of India. Also it seeks to ensure that Beijing successfully proceeds with its efforts to achieve its objective and delay India's ability to challenge China. India's suspicions were further aggravated when China developed a naval base in Gwadar in Karachi. Given this posture, Chinese claim of India-U.S. defence cooperation directing towards them is not justified. The recent Chinese expansion should not become an offshoot to the growing India-U.S. defence and security ties that holds the key to international peace and security. But the Chinese move would only destabilise the Asian security rather than bringing stability to the region¹⁷ and gain more and more weights in the international system.

China's anti-Indian stand is very well reflected in the recently concluded nuclear deal with Pakistan. Under the deal, China would be lending Pakistan with \$207 million to buy two more reactors- Chasma-3 and Chasma-4. This deal is directed toward the successful conclusion of India-U.S. civil nuclear deal to show that if United States can offer nuclear deal to India then why cannot we offer to our close ally, no matter whether it goes against the wish of the international community and in particular to India. When United States under the leadership of former President Mr. George W. Bush has out rightly rejected Pakistan demand for a nuclear deal, China has come out in support of its long time close allies Pakistan for establishing two more reactors at the Chasma atomic complex in Punjab. This step is aimed at maintaining a nuclear parity between India and Pakistan and also to ensure that India is engaged in a tussle with Pakistan that would restrict New Delhi from moving ahead and shift its focus from China.¹⁸

However, India is most unlikely to adopt a confrontationist stand against its Asian giants, China owing to the fact that it would keep the options alive of closely engaging with all the major powers of the world, which it perceives is the key to it becoming a major power in the world. Table 2 shows economic and trade relations between China and South Asian nations for the period from 1999 to 2006. On the trade and investment front, China's has become an important partner for South Asian nations by providing development assistance for building infrastructure and enabling reconstruction. China has been extending help to Pakistan in areas such as energy, infrastructure, and mining projects under the Pakistan-China Joint Five Year Economic and Trade Cooperation Plan. Its development assistance has increased by 50 percent from US\$14 million in 2005 to US\$21 million in 2009. Besides, it is also providing assistance to Nepal focusing on the development of hydro power, roads, and tourism sectors.¹⁹ From the table given below, it can be observed that Pakistan and Bangladesh is the second and third largest trading partner for China in South Asia.

Table 1: China's Bilateral Trade Relations with South Asian Nations
(Millions of US \$)

Countries	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
Bangladesh	715	919	975	110	1368	1963	2483	3189
Bhutan	1	2	2	1	2	-	-	0.16
India	198	291	360	494	7595	1360	1871	2486
Maldives	5	1	3	7		4	7	1
Nepal	1	1	2	3	3	8	17	16
Pakistan	215	204	154	110	127	171	196	268
Srilanka	971	116	130	180	2430	3061	4256	5250
Total	6	5	7	0	9	5	7	5

Source: Elmie Konwar Rengma, "Soft Power Game: A Study of China, India and South Asian Association for regional Cooperation (SAARC) Tripartite", pp. 22-23, available at <<http://indiachinainstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2010/03/Elmie-Soft-Power-Game-A-Study-of-China-India-and-SAARC-Tripartite.pdf>>.

Why China is Reluctant to Resolve the Border Dispute with India?

Both sides have claimed each other for not succeeding to resolve the border dispute. But, it was the lack of consistent Chinese stand on the issue. They keep on shifting its position from time to time which had only aggravated the chances of breakthrough. The efforts that has been made since the cold war end in general and by the dawn of the twenty-first century in particular has been thwarted by the new Chinese claim to the

Indian state of Arunachal Pradesh repeatedly in 2006, 2007 and 2008. The first such claim was made during the Chinese President Hu Jintao's visit to India in 2006. Before this, China had never claimed the whole of Arunachal Pradesh to be part of their territory. The only part they were claiming was the Tawang area. This sends out a wrong impression to India that they are not in a hurry to resolve the dispute. This way the Indian officials were not very clear about the Chinese intentions. Their claim of Arunachal Pradesh is not reasonable. India will only stick to the McMahon line that has been offered to it in April 1960.

Beijing is taking more time to resolve the border issue for its own benefit. Another factor that has also worsened the possibility of resolving the issue is the Chinese linking of the border settlement with the Tibet issue. They perceive that the early border settlement will have its implications on the status of the Tibet. So, they are waiting for the Tibet issue to be resolved first. This will only delay the process of border dispute settlement. Unless they show any seriousness, India should not step forward to resolving the border dispute because, resolving the dispute should be in the interests of both countries.²⁰

Indian strategic affairs analyst Brahma Chellaney was quite right when he argued that, "keeping India engaged in endless and fruitless border talks is a key Chinese objective so that Beijing, in the meantime, can change the Himalayan balance decisively in its favor through accumulation of military power and greater infrastructure development."²¹ Therefore, it becomes very clear that resolution of the ongoing border dispute in future can take place if and only if both sides are ready to make some changes in its stand on the dispute. And also the lack of political commitment is only delaying to provide result.

Implications for India

China's gaining strategic weight in South Asia would definitely pose serious economic and security implications for India. India face a tough challenge from China on every front while maintaining its foreign relation and securing its national interests with its immediate neighbours such as Bangladesh, Nepal, Myanmar, Srilanka and Afghanistan. Among the many relations China enjoy at present with the countries of South Asia, India is seriously concerned by China's growing connectivity with Pakistan by means of linkages through the occupied territory of the Indian state of Jammu and Kashmir. The 2008-09 Annual Report of the Ministry of Defence has stated that, "Enhancing connectivity with Pakistan through the territory of Jammu and Kashmir, illegally occupied by China and Pakistan, will have direct military implications for India."²²

China's multi-faceted strategic engagement with India's South Asian neighbours has deep-rooted security implications for the regional peace and security at large and India in particular. This type of cooperation would bring China's military force close to India's border which in itself poses a serious threat to the peace and security of our country. China's

anti-Indian policy in South Asia without addressing the regional issues sends a strong message to the world that China is not really concerned about ensuring lasting peace, security and stability in Asia and South Asia in particular. The growing engagement between China and South Asia countries excluding India is aimed at Beijing's desires to strengthen its influence into South Asia thereby blocking New Delhi from enjoying regional preeminence in the region. Such cooperation has every potential to threaten India's ambitions of becoming a global power by not allowing it to work freely for the development within the country. Such a Chinese move would no doubt widen the power gap between New Delhi and its South Asian neighbours and undermine New Delhi's strategic advantage in the region.²³

Indian Responses

How should India respond to the emerging challenges posed by China's ever expanding footprint in South Asia? According to Baladas Ghoshal, India's response to China's diplomatic and economic strategies has often been "desultory, characterized by ad hoc policies and more often reactive, rather than proactive and failed to leverage its available resources and comparative advantage to gain economic and diplomatic benefits."²⁴ In view of the challenges raised above, India cannot remain silent. While continuing to engage closely with China on different sectors, India will need to take all necessary measures to protect its national security, territorial integrity, and sovereignty. It must also strengthen its border security measures in the light of Chinese increasing influence close to India's borders. India will need to strengthen its relationship with China's traditional adversaries, including Japan, Vietnam and the United States.

Former Chief of naval staff, Admiral Sureesh Mehta, in his address at the India Habitat Centre has stated that, 'militarily our strategy to deal with China must include reducing the military gap and countering the growing Chinese footprint in the Indian Ocean region. The traditional or 'attrition' approach of matching 'Division for Division' must give way to harnessing modern technology for developing high situational awareness and creating a reliable stand-off deterrent.'²⁵

In the backdrop of the rising Chinese economic and investment profile in the South Asian region, India has also taken significant steps to engage closely with neighbouring countries so that it is within its grips and to ensure that it does not come under the influence of other competing nations. To offset Chinese investment in the smaller countries of the region, India has granted US\$ 361 million for development of transportation links in Nepal's Terai region and US\$ 1 billion development assistance to Bangladesh. Besides, India has also extended US\$ 20 million for development purposes to Myanmar.²⁶

Conclusion

Having already gained a strong foothold in India's close neighbours, China will continue to take initiative to increase its strategic clout

enormously by broadening economic and security linkages with virtually every South Asian nation. From the Indian perspective, a rise of China in India's neighbourhood presents both a threat and an opportunity. To appease them China has in recent times made significant investment in South Asia's smaller economies. China's current trade volume with all South Asian nations approaches US\$ 20 billion a year. This effort has transformed the region from India's near abroad into China's own backyard. Besides, there emerged a paradigm shift in the perception among the countries of South Asia excluding India from a China threat to China opportunity.²⁷ China is emerging as a major supplier of arms to India's neighbours thereby expanding its politico-strategic influence in the South Asian and Southeast Asian region. Limiting China's strategic influence in this region becomes a serious challenge for India in the coming years.

The key to dealing with such challenges lies in India's ability to sustain close bilateral ties with the South Asian neighbours. Effort must be made by India to deepen the multi-faceted ties with the countries of South Asia for the mutual benefit. Besides, India has to balance out between regional peace, its own strategic interests and that of long-term peace, security and development in the region. This way India can become a close partner for the South Asian neighbours thereby reducing the pressure of China's presence in the region.²⁸

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**4. COURTING THE DRAGON:
Relations between the SouthEast Asian States and CHINA**

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INTRODUCTION

Due to the proximity between East and Southeast Asia, China is no stranger to the Southeast Asian world as relations between China and the Southeast Asian polities have indeed existed for centuries. In fact, in the pre-modern era, Chinese presence and ambitions in the region have had a deep direct cultural impact on most, if not all, Southeast Asian polities. Apart from viewing the region as part of its imperial aggrandizement ambitions, most Southeast Asian polities also maintained tributary relations with China. This was mainly done as means of securing Chinese protection as well as tapping into the Chinese trade network.

However, in modern times, the story has been rather different. While most, if not all, Southeast Asian states shunned China when the country turned communist in October 1949, however, present-day relations have been marked by a hype of economic activity between both sides. It can be said that at least until the 1970s, many Southeast Asia states did not have relations with China which only improved after the United States normalized its relations with the latter in 1972. Nevertheless, since the introduction of economic reforms in China in the late 1980s which witnessed its eventual rise as an economic powerhouse, relations between the latter and Southeast Asian countries have dramatically improved such that China is in fact a major key economic player in the region. While it is true China's relations with the region

predates back to centuries, nonetheless the focus of this paper is to highlight China's relations with Southeast Asian states in the post-independent era. As such, the purpose of the paper is to provide a broad overview of China's relations with all the eleven Southeast Asian countries.

BRUNEI

While relations between Brunei and China go back to some 2,000 years ago, in modern times however, relations between both are relatively recent and were only established after 1 January 1984 when Brunei gained independence from Great Britain. Official relations between Brunei and China were established on 30 September 1991, some eight years after the former gained its independence. Further to this, in 1993, an Annual Bilateral Joint Consultative Meeting (JCM) was created between both, aimed at overseeing and enhancing bilateral cooperation. In fact, it can be said that since 1993, China has begun showing greater interest towards Brunei which is reflected in the dramatic increase in the number of high-level visits from both sides, in addition to a number of bilateral agreements on trade, commerce and investment.

For China, greater interest in Brunei is very much related to its quest for energy security. The testimony of this was when in 2000, Brunei Shell Petroleum signed an agreement with China International United Petroleum and Chemicals Company (UNIPEC) to supply the latter with 10,000 barrels of oil per day, which was later in 2004, increased to 40,000 barrels a day.¹ As far trade is concerned, it was reported in 2013 that bilateral trade between Brunei and China had increased 80-fold since the establishment of relations between both in 1991 and was at the level of US\$1.6 billion.²

For Brunei improved relations with China are aimed at diversifying its economy that is too dependent on the natural gas and oil sector. As far as trade is concerned, bilateral trade between both witnessed a dramatic increase by 2011 when it reached the level of US\$1.3 billion, a fourfold increase when compared with its level in 2008.³ Cooperation between both was also taken to greater heights when on 5 April 2013 both parties formed the 'Brunei-China Strategic Cooperative Relationship', aimed broadening and deepening cooperation between both countries. It is noteworthy to mention that China's nine-dash line also overlaps with Brunei's exclusive economic zone. Generally speaking, relations between Brunei and China can be considered rather low key when compared with relations of other Southeast Asian states with China.

CAMBODIA

China's relations with Cambodia, especially during the Cold War and even till the present, are best understood as how the latter serves as

pivot for China to counterweigh Vietnamese influence in mainland Southeast Asia. Official relations were established in 1958 with China continually maintaining close and personalized links with King Norodom Sihanouk, the Cambodian head of state and government at that time. However, all the same, between 1975 and 1978, China also provided support for the Khmer Rouge, with the former continuing to support the latter even after its ouster from power in early 1979. In fact, when Cambodia was invaded by Vietnam in 1978, China continued providing both military and political support for the Khmer Rouge, mainly aimed at ousting Vietnam from Cambodia.⁴

Since the 1993 United Nations-sponsored elections in Cambodia that saw the return of stability to the country, relations between China and Cambodia has markedly improved. China has not only increased its trade with Cambodia but even its investments in the country. Between 2006 and 2011, China was ranked the top foreign investor in Cambodia, with its total investments for the said period amounting to some US\$8.8 billion. In terms of bilateral trade, between 2007 and 2010, China served as Cambodia second most important export destination with its total exports to the country for the said period valued at some US\$2.5 billion. Similarly and for the same period, China was also Cambodia's second most important import source with total imports valued at US\$4.2 billion. On another note, between 1992 till 2011, Cambodia also received some US\$863 million in foreign assistance from China.⁵

One area where China is heavily investing in Cambodia is in the construction of hydro-dams which are mainly built by Chinese companies. In addition, China has also invested significantly in the construction of roads and the number of Chinese companies operating in Cambodia has markedly increased. In 2013, it was also reported that China was building a fully funded military academy for Cambodia and that the latter was also purchasing military hardware from the former. In fact, the same source noted that from 1994 till 2013, China had invested some US\$9.1 billion in Cambodia.⁶ Another source reveals that Chinese companies have been the biggest concessionaires of land in Cambodia since 1994 with some 4.6 million hectares of land granted to them, mainly for mining, agriculture and hydropower development. This in fact amounts to some 50 percent of all the land concessions granted since 1994 by the Cambodian government to foreign concessionaires.⁷

For Cambodia, good relations with China are considered extremely important especially for its economic development. By investing in the textile industry in Cambodia, China has created employment for thousands of Cambodians while its investments in hydropower development have also helped the country to alleviate its shortage of energy. On the same note, for China, Cambodia offers access to abundant mineral resources what more cheap labor and markets for its manufactured goods.⁸

INDONESIA

Relations between Indonesia and China can be best described as being rather bumpy as it did witness a period of suspension of relations between both. Indonesia was in fact the first Southeast Asian country to recognize China when official diplomatic relations between both were established on 13 April 1950. However, on 30 October 1967, Indonesia severed its relations with China which remained in the cold until 1990 when it was normalized. While relations between both took off well initially and became extremely cordial during the Sukarno era, however, during much of Suharto's tenure and at least till the late 1980s, it remained in the cold. This was mainly due to Beijing's support for the Communist Party of Indonesia (CPI) as well as its alleged involvement in the 30 September 1965 events in Indonesia. Nonetheless, in December 1989, both parties began talks aimed at normalizing relations which was realized on 8 August 1990 when the two sides signed a Memorandum of Understanding on the Resumption of Diplomatic Relations.

Present-day relations between both are rather solid with a marked increase in trade, commerce and investments. China is currently Indonesia's second largest trading partner with bilateral trade between both valued at US\$66.2 billion in 2012 – marking a fourfold increase since 2005. In 2013, both parties also pledged to take this trade to the level of US\$80 billion by 2015.⁹ While Indonesian exports to China in 2013 accounted for some 12.4 percent of its total exports, its imports from China during the same period accounted for some 16 percent of its total imports.¹⁰

One another note, while Indonesia is not a party to Spratly islands dispute and has all along remained rather silent on Chinese activities in the area, a recent report however suggest otherwise. A recent statement by the head of Indonesia's Sea Security Coordinating Agency noted that China's increased military activities in the South China Sea, especially in the disputed Spratly islands, were in fact a "real threat".¹¹ Such a view clearly suggests that while relations between Jakarta and Beijing may be cordial, however, Indonesia remains wary of Chinese activities and ambitions in the South China Sea.

LAOS

Laos, a landlocked country which shares a 505-kilometer border with China, established official relations with the latter on 25 April 1961. However, due to the Vietnam War, relations between both were rather unsteady until 1989 when it was normalized. While relations between both during the Cold War period were turbulent and hostile, nevertheless since 1989, these have improved tremendously such that Chinese presence in the country is today highly visible.¹² For Laos, relations with China are important as the latter is not only the country's major source

of foreign aid but is even extremely important where trade is concerned. More importantly, taking into account Laos' status as an underdeveloped country, China provides the country with the opportunity for development, both in terms of finance and technical know-how. On a similar note, for China, Laos is viewed as a major supplier of cheap mineral resources and other raw materials.

To break the ice, in 1989, Laotian Prime Minister, Kaysone Phomvihane, paid a state visit to China while in November 2000, President Jiang Zemin became the first Chinese head of state to visit Laos. By 2011, it was also reported that China had invested some US\$3.3 billion in the country. China is currently not only Laos' largest trading partner but even its biggest provider of external assistance thus making the latter China's closest ally in the Southeast Asian region. Laos currently supplies minerals to China and is also the latter's major source of timber, with its timber exports to China in 2011 alone standing at 80,000 cubic meters of logs. It is projected that by 2020, Laos would be supplying China with some 5 million tons of minerals resources annually.¹³

To facilitate and increase trade and the flow of resources from Laos to China, the latter is also currently helping Laos to construct a 421-kilometer railway track linking Vientiane with Boten, in northern Laos. This railway track, costing some US\$7 billion, is currently funded by a loan from the China Export-Import Bank.¹⁴ As of 2013, Laos was the second largest recipient of Chinese investments, after Singapore, with Chinese investments to the country amounting to some US\$800 million.¹⁵

MALAYSIA

Malaysia officially recognized China in 1974, two years after President Nixon's visit, and became the first non-communist Southeast Asian country to do so. Upon achieving independence from Great Britain 1957, Malaysia embarked on a foreign policy posture that was overtly pro-West and anti-communist. This was mainly due to Beijing's support to the Malayan Communist Party (MCP) that had started armed rebellion against the government even before independence was achieved and one that lasted decades beyond independence. It is important to note that the insurgency by the MCP lasted for some 41 years from 1948 till 1989. However, due to the changing dynamics of the Cold War and the rapprochement between China and the United States, Malaysia began toning down its pro-Western stance and hence embarked on a review of its foreign policy priorities which eventually resulted in the opening-up of relations with China in 1974.

In terms of trade, Malaysia continues to be China's largest trading partner within the Southeast Asian region, with bilateral trade in 2013 valued at US\$106.7 billion. Of this, Malaysia's exports to China

accounted for some US\$60.14 billion while its imports from China were valued at US\$45.93 billion– showing a marked increase of 11.9 percent when compared to 2012. Based on the trade figures, it is clear the trade balance is indeed in favor of Malaysia. In addition to trade, in 2013 alone, Malaysia invested some US\$280 million in China, thus making it China's third largest investor from the Southeast Asian region – with Singapore and Thailand taking the first and second place respectively.¹⁶

Apart from trade, commerce and investments, Malaysia is also amongst the favorite destination in the Southeast Asian region for tourists from China. In 2011, some 1.25 million Chinese tourists visited Malaysia¹⁷, while from January to September 2013 alone, the figure was at 1.45 million – showing a marked increase of 32.6 percent when compared with 2012.¹⁸ However, due to the 8 March 2014 incident which saw the disappearance of the Malaysian airliner MH370, there has been a decrease in Chinese tourist arrivals in Malaysia since.¹⁹

On another front, Malaysia is also one of the claimants in the Spratly islands dispute, where it claims a small number of islands/reefs as these fall within the country's exclusive economic zone (EEZ) of 200 nautical miles as defined by the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS). These, amongst others, include the Swallow Reef, Ardasier Reef and Mariveles Reef. In March 2013, when China conducted a major naval exercise close to the James Shoal, just some 80 kilometers from Malaysia, the latter chose to ignore the issue with a muted reaction.²⁰ This is in fact very much different when compared to strong protests from Vietnam and the Philippines whenever China encroaches into their respective territorial claims and EEZ.

MYANMAR

Myanmar (or formerly Burma) established official relations with China on 8 June 1950 and was amongst the first non-communist countries to do so. However, relations began to turn sour soon after due to at least two major reasons. The first was China's support to the Communist Party of Burma (CPB) and the other was Chinese incursions into Myanmar's territory in pursuit of the Koumintang (KMT) that was waging an insurgency against the Chinese government close to the China-Myanmar border. However, with the onset of military rule in Myanmar, coupled with the introduction of Burmese Way to Socialism, relations began improving, especially in the 1970s. By the 1980s, relations between the countries further progressed, especially when China withdrew its support to the CPB, which eventually saw the disbandment of the latter.

When major Western states began imposing economic sanctions against Myanmar after the 1988 brutal backlash against the democracy movement, China, on the other hand, seized the opportunity to entrench its position in the country. China not only became the largest investor in Myanmar but was even the latter's largest supplier of military hardware.

It is not an overstatement to suggest that the military regime in Myanmar managed to cultivate extremely close relations with China after 1988 mainly as a means for regime survival. This relationship, frequently labeled as *'pauk-phaw'* (fraternal or kinsfolk ties)²¹, lasted for at least more than two decades until 2011, when a nominally civilian government took the reins of power in Myanmar. In fact, during the height of these relations Myanmar was at times labelled as a Chinese client state.²² Not only did China emerge as Myanmar's largest foreign investor but was even its second largest trading partner, after Thailand.

From 1988 and until July 2013, Myanmar received some US\$42.95 billion in total contracted foreign investments. Of this, investments from China alone amounted to some US\$14.2 billion or 48 percent of the said total – thus making the latter the largest single investor in the country. In fact, around 50 percent of Chinese investments in Myanmar have been solely for the development of some 30 hydropower dams in the country. In addition to hydropower development, Chinese investments in Myanmar are also largely concentrated in the oil and gas sector where China is a major player.²³

However, since the inauguration of a new government in Myanmar in 2011, the latter has been diversifying its source of foreign investment such that Chinese investments have witnessed a decline. For example, while China's investments in Myanmar in 2011 totaled to some US\$8.5 billion, however, it had dropped to US\$1.02 billion during the first eleven months of 2012.²⁴

PHILIPPINES

Relations between the Philippines and China were established on 9 June 1975 when the leaders of both countries signed a joint communiqué. The move by the Philippines to recognize China was done almost three years after the United States normalized its relations with the latter. It is noteworthy to mention that the Philippines was the United States staunchest ally in the region during the Cold War years and even housed American military bases. Generally speaking, although on the whole relations between both have grown since 1975, however claims by both parties into the disputed Spratly islands continue to factor significantly in these relations at present.

Since 1975, relations between both have been also marked by a number of high-level visits from both sides as well as an increase in trade and investments. While on the one hand relations between the Philippines and China have improved over the years, on other hand, the Philippines continue to maintain extremely close relations with the United States as well. The testimony of this is the Mutual Defense Treaty between the Philippines and the United States, signed in 1951, and in effect till today. In fact, shortly before President Barack Obama's visit to the Philippines in 2014, both countries entered into a new security pact

known as the Enhanced Defense Cooperation Agreement (EDCA) that allows the United States troops rotational access into the Subic and Clark bases in the Philippines.²⁵

In terms of trade and as of 2013, the Philippines was China sixth largest trading partner in the Southeast Asian region, with trade between both valued at US\$38.07 billion.²⁶ On the other hand, investments from China into the Philippines remain insignificant, especially when compared with its investments into some other Southeast Asian states. For example, in 2011, Chinese investments in the Philippines were at US\$294 million, which represented a mere 5.4 percent of its investments in Southeast Asia. Similarly, Philippines' investments in China in 2010 were at US\$138.1 million, representing some 2.2 percent of the total investments from the Southeast Asian region in China.²⁷

As one of the claimants to the disputed Spratly islands, the Philippines, like Vietnam, is amongst the two Southeast Asian countries, that have on occasions stood up to the Chinese whenever there are incursions into its economic exclusive zone in the disputed area. Further, in 2012, tensions between the Philippines and China over the Scarborough Shoal surfaced and resulted in a standoff between the navies of both countries. However, when diplomatic efforts provided futile in overcoming the impasse, the Philippines then decided to take the issue to United Nations Arbitral Tribunal in The Hague – albeit China's strong opposition. This decision by the Philippines has since impacted negatively on relations between both and resulted in a downturn in relations.²⁸ Apart from protests in Beijing, Hong Kong and Manila as well as cyber attacks from both sides, China has even imposed stringent restrictions on fruit imports from the Philippines and suspended all tours to the country.²⁹

SINGAPORE

Singapore only established official diplomatic relations with China in 1990 thus making it the second last Southeast Asian country to do so. This was mainly due to a number of reasons. Firstly, Singapore had close relations with Taiwan in the past and still maintains some military training facilities in the latter till today. Secondly, Singapore waited for Indonesia to re-establish its diplomatic relations with China first before it embarked to do so. This was mainly done out of respect of its giant southern neighbor. Lastly, Singapore's population is mainly made of Chinese and on occasions the country has been labelled, rather disparagingly, by Indonesian politicians as the 'little red dot'. Smacked in the middle of a Malay Muslim archipelago, Singapore has also been described as constituting a 'third China'. Therefore, to ensure that its foreign policy was not ethnically-oriented and that it did not in any way represent a 'third China', Singapore made the decision to be amongst the last country in the region to establish relations with China.³⁰

Not only is the current relationship between Singapore and China important in terms of trade and commerce, but it is even significant in the area of investments. In terms of bilateral trade, Singapore is currently China's second largest trading partner in Southeast Asia. In 2013 alone, total bilateral trade between both was valued at US\$75.91 billion, with Singapore's imports from China standing at US\$45.86 billion, while its exports to China amounted to US\$30.5 billion. In addition, Singapore is not only China's most preferred destination for foreign investment in Southeast Asia, in fact, Singapore is also Southeast Asia's biggest investor in China. In 2013 for example, Singapore invested some US\$7.327 billion in China while China invested some US\$2.4 billion in Singapore.³¹ Noteworthy to mention that China is not only Singapore's largest trading partner, but is also China's fifth largest investment destination, with more than 5,200 Chinese companies currently operating in Singapore.³² While Singapore's relations with China are driven by a sense of economic pragmatism aimed at expanding the island state's markets, similarly, China's push into Singapore is also premised on economic rationality such that it has been on occasions been duped as a 'special relationship'.³³

THAILAND

Although Thailand established official diplomatic relations with China in November 1975, however relations between both in the early decades were marked by mutual suspicion. This was mainly due to at least three major factors. The first relates to China's support for leftist parties in Thailand, namely the Communist Party of Thailand. Secondly, was China involvement in the wars in Indo-China, and especially its support for the Khmer Rouge in Cambodia. Last but not least, is related to Thailand's close relations with the United States where it has always been viewed by Beijing as the latter's major ally in mainland Southeast Asia, both during and after the Cold War.

However, in 1979, when Vietnam invaded Cambodia and ousted the Khmer Rouge, Thailand began fostering closer relations with China as means to counter-balance Vietnam. Since the end of the Cold War, relations between both have strengthened in many areas. This has been partly due to Thailand's flexible and multi-aligned foreign policy that emphasizes good relations with both China and the United States. In addition to this, some 20 million or 12 percent of Thailand's population are of Chinese descent and play an active role in the country's economy. In fact, Thailand's growing commercial and trade relations with China are partly due to the influence of these Sino-Thais who view China as a country with immense economic opportunities.³⁴

Present-day relations are extremely cordial especially in the area of trade, commerce and investments. It was reported in 2013 that trade between both countries had increased seven-fold in the last ten years such that in 2012 it reached the value of US\$70 billion, thus making

Thailand China's third largest trading partner in the Southeast Asian region – after Malaysia and Singapore. It was also reported in 2013 that China was Thailand's second largest trading partner while Thailand was China's fifteenth major trading partner. Additionally, China was also reportedly Thailand's second largest foreign investor after Japan.³⁵ Thailand-China bilateral trade in 2013 was valued at US\$71.26 billion with Thailand's imports from China at US\$32.74 billion, while its exports to China stood at US\$38.52 billion, thus creating a trade balance in favor of China. In the area of investment, Thailand was the second largest Southeast Asian investor in China in 2013, with its investments in China amounting to some US\$480 million.³⁶

TIMOR-LESTE

Although China had been maintaining an ambassadorial-level representative office in Timor-Leste since 2001, official relations between both were only established in May 2002 after the latter was officially recognized as an independent state. As such, Timor-Leste is the last country in the region to establish relations with China. China's decision to establish relations with Timor-Leste can be attributed to a number of reasons. The first relates to China's overall expansion into Southeast Asia and as part of its strategy to counter balance the United States' influence in the region. The second relates to the fact that Timor-Leste would most probably be admitted into ASEAN sooner than later and this very much figures in China's engagement strategy with the regional organization as well. The third relates to the fact that Timor-Leste has potentially large oil and natural gas reserves and this figure prominently in China's energy security strategy. Lastly, recognition of Timor-Leste was mainly aimed ensuring that Taiwan does not bring the country into its own camp.³⁷

While trade from both sides is slowly increasing, China is also providing a significant amount of foreign aid to Timor-Leste. One good example is when China footed the bill for the reconstruction of important buildings in Dili, which also included the country's presidential palace. In addition, Timor-Leste has also purchased military equipment from China, namely two Shanghai-class boats and China also provided some US\$9 million for the construction of a new military headquarters in Timor-Leste.³⁸ Further, in April 2014, Timor-Leste's Prime Minister, Xanana Gusmao, visited China where he held meetings with Chinese Premier, Li Keqiang. As a result of this visit, a number of Memorandum of Understandings were signed between both parties, mainly aimed at deepening cooperation and creating an all-round cooperative partnership between the two countries, namely in agriculture and energy.³⁹

VIETNAM

Despite having common socialist inclinations, however, bilateral relations between China and Vietnam have been rather unsteady what more

turbulent both in the past as well as the present. This has been mainly due Vietnam's past historical experience with China where the latter had frequently sought to expand its imperial power and subjugate the former. In modern times, although China assisted North Vietnam during the Vietnam War, relations however took a downturn after the reunification of Vietnam in 1975. In fact, not only did China and Vietnam fight a border war in 1979 but both are also currently embroiled in territorial disputes in the South China Sea, mainly over the Spratly and Paracel islands. In addition, another area that has created uneasiness, at least for China, is the United States attempts to court Vietnam. Since 2003, there have been a number of high-level visits to Vietnam from the United States, especially in the area of defense which has been an irritant to China. For Vietnam, these visits by top American officials are a clear testimony of its attempt to counter-balance China.⁴⁰

Nonetheless, official relations were normalized November 1991, and have to some extent, improved over the years, especially in the area of commerce and trade, although the underlying factors mentioned above continue to affect these relations. Much of the trade is currently via the 1300-kilometershared common border between the two countries which was re-opened in the 1990s. This border trade between both has been increasing at the rate of 20 percent annually. In 2011 alone, trade between Vietnam and China was valued at US\$36 billion while trade between Vietnam and the United States stood at US\$22 billion.⁴¹ A year later, in 2013, it was reported that trade between Vietnam and China had increased and was valued at US\$50.21 billion. Vietnam's exports to China are mainly rice, iron and copper while its imports from China are predominantly manufactured goods and minerals.⁴² It is important to note while there has been an increase in trade between both, the figures are rather minuscule when compared with China's trade with Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand and Indonesia. More so when taking into account that both China and Vietnam share a 1300-kilometer border which has immense potential to harness greater trade between both.

However, despite the increase in trade, relations between both is frequently marred by a series of stand-offs between the navies of both countries in the disputed Paracel and Spratly islands. In fact, it is mainly due to this that Vietnam is currently actively promoting its trade relations with the United States, the European Union and Australia, aimed at diversifying its economic relations and reduce dependency on China should there be a downturn in relations with the latter. Similarly, China which is highly dependent on rice imports from Vietnam has also begun looking at Thailand as a major source of rice imports.⁴³

On another front and related to their maritime dispute over the Spratly and Paracel islands, Vietnam is amongst the two Southeast Asian countries that have on occasions stood-up to China over the latter's incursions into its exclusive economic zone and territorial claims. Tensions have been on the upsurge since Vietnam passed a law, on 21

June 2012, placing these groups of islands under its jurisdiction, a move that was considered by China as illegal and invalid. As a retaliatory move, the status of Nansha (Spratly) and Xisha (Paracel) and its surrounding waters were elevated to a prefectural-level by China.⁴⁴ Since then, there have been a number of incidents involving the navies of both countries in these areas, with a recent one in June 2014. In this latest incident over a disputed oil rig, China mobilized some 71 of its warships into the area with Vietnam sending some 61 warships.⁴⁵ Fortunately enough, the fiasco ended peacefully in July 2014, when China towed away its US\$1 billion oil rig from the area.⁴⁶

CONCLUSION

Taking into account China's relations with the eleven Southeast Asian states discussed above, it can be concluded that while relations between China and some Southeast Asian countries have significantly improved over the years, however, in some areas it remains turbulent – evident in the case of Vietnam and the Philippines. While there may be greater confidence and trust towards China today, the underlying issue of Chinese domination of the region remains of concern for many Southeast Asian countries. What more when this is viewed within the context of Chinese claims in the Paracels and Spratlys – a move that is often viewed by most, if not all, Southeast Asian states as China's attempts to turn the South China Sea into a Chinese lake. The fact that the South China Sea is of immense importance to all Southeast Asian states, any attempt by the Chinese to lay claim on the entire sea would surely have deep ramifications for the region. All the same, for most Southeast Asian countries, China's rapid economic rise as a major economic power has created abundant opportunities for commerce, trade and investments which must be tapped. More so is China's overseas development assistance programs that are much needed by countries like Cambodia, Laos and Timor-Leste. Chinese assistance to these states is considered vital to their respective national development agendas. On the whole, it can be argued that the view of China amongst Southeast Asian states is at best mixed. While some states see China as a strategic partner for development, others remain wary what more suspicious of Chinese interests and ambitions in the region.⁴⁷

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5. China's Venezuela Challenge

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China's peculiar partnership with Venezuela remains firmly intact despite the Latin American nation's deteriorating economy and security situation, and despite wide-ranging efforts in China to limit risk in overseas investment and financing activity. Even amidst violent demonstrations, product shortages, and crushing inflation in Venezuela, President Xi Jinping offered the nation \$4 billion in oil-backed financing during his July 2014 tour of Latin America, adding to the \$50 billion that Beijing has promised since 2005. By means of a Joint Financing Fund and other financing arrangements, China's banks have issued more loans to Venezuela than any other country in the region. In 2013 alone, Caracas received over \$10 billion in Chinese investment.

During that same visit, the Chinese president and Venezuela's Nicolás Maduro also inked a series of smaller agreements for cooperation in a range of economic sectors. The leaders talked about establishing a special economic zone and, in a largely symbolic gesture, upgraded Venezuela's bilateral status from "strategic partnership" to "comprehensive strategic partnership."

China reaffirmed its commitment to Venezuela only days ago, when Maduro, facing serious constraints associated with falling oil prices, sought to restructure the terms of multi-billion dollar China-Venezuela joint financing fund. Declining oil prices require Venezuela to export more oil in order to repay its debt to China, but it has been unable to increase production in the short-term. Indeed, state-owned Petróleos de Venezuela S.A. (PdVSA) has consistently fallen short in the

production of the 800,000 barrels per day (bpd) it promised to China. According to Bloomberg, output at the new Orinoco fields was supposed to reach 195,000 barrels a day by the end of last year. Instead, production is closer to a 6,000 barrel-a-day “trickle” that’s costing PdVSA an estimated \$19 million per day in lost revenue.

Despite the short-term losses associated with restructuring Venezuela’s debt, China nonetheless amended the *China-Venezuela Joint Fund Agreement*, *eliminating the minimum oil export requirement, removing the agreement’s three-year repayment period, and effectively reaffirming its commitment to partnership with Caracas. China continues to accommodate Venezuela, believing perhaps that a foot in the door in the oil rich nation is worth two safely planted in Beijing.*

Risk-Averse China

Over two decades now of experience in international markets have taught China’s firms some valuable lessons. The more than occasional failure of Chinese overseas ventures has also prompted the Chinese institutions responsible for governing overseas economic engagement to devise new policies to improve the experiences of China’s overseas actors. These include provisions to diversify investment, enhance competitiveness, improve social and environmental impact, and push more private firms to invest overseas.

China’s leadership has also clearly articulated a preference for greater risk aversion in overseas investment and lending. As Erica Downs indicates, Chinese CEOs and officials are focused on ensuring that overseas investments do not lose money or damage the Chinese brand. Chinese firms – including state-owned enterprises -- are therefore expected to more carefully vet potential acquisitions and to be responsible for failures abroad. They are also increasingly expected to accept a degree of social responsibility when operating overseas.

As China attempts an overhaul of its economy, Chinese credit will also be distributed more sparingly, with far less financing directed toward state-owned industries, energy-intensive sectors and industries beleaguered by excess capacity. Nor will the country’s SOEs be the primary recipients of financing for overseas investment. China is clearly moving from a system of state bank preferential financing for state-owned enterprises (SOEs) toward a more sophisticated policy scheme. Financing will increasingly be directed toward private industries. Firms are encouraged, moreover,

to engage in mergers and acquisitions (M&A) and other preferred forms of investment in order to minimize risk and to take advantage of the networks and expertise that the acquired firms have to offer.

There is also broad support for more sophisticated assessment of political and economic risk in overseas investment destinations. China's Ministry of Commerce clearly indicates in its 2014 overseas investment regulations that firms should pay attention to risk prevention, including the development of early-warning mechanisms and safety plans. Chinese analysts have also advised against further investment in Venezuela and other "populist" Latin American countries. A 2012 China Development Bank study on risk in Latin America notifies would-be investors of the South American nation's excessive reliance on oil and tradition of military intervention.

Why Venezuela?

How can China's ongoing commitment to Venezuela be understood in the context changing climate in Beijing – from one supporting fairly rapid overseas expansion to one promoting of more measured and responsible overseas engagement?

Beijing's perceived commitment to Venezuela is attributable in part to China's complex plans for energy security, which have involved a retrogressive, government-level focus on supply risk and diversification. The government's interest in diversifying supply was especially evident in the aftermath of the global financial crisis and in response to the political turmoil that has engulfed parts of the Middle East and North Africa since early 2011. As a result, China's oil diplomacy in Venezuela - as well as in other seemingly risky nations - is thought to be part of Beijing's efforts to reduce supply uncertainty.

To the extent that there is money to be made, China's state-owned firms have also been attracted to the prospect of quick deal-making in cash-strapped Venezuela. And from a lending perspective, there is a sense that Chinese banks have reduced risk by means of commodity-backed loans, dollar and Renminbi-based transactions, special account arrangements, and joint lending ventures (the Joint Financing Fund, for example). Venezuela's recent production difficulties challenge that notion, however.

More than anything, however, China's continued support of Venezuela – through new lending and recent debt restructuring – is intended to

prevent Venezuela's collapse, albeit with the expectation of an eventual peaceful transition to a more reliable government. A worst-case scenario for China is extensive unrest in Venezuela, which would lead, presumably, to further delays in oil production and an even greater decline in economic stability. China is by no means devoted to *chavismo*, but instead to protecting its extensive investments in Venezuela's oil sector.

Chinese officials are nonetheless keeping a closer eye on Maduro's ailing Venezuela in a move consistent with their sharpening approach to investment throughout the region. A new agreement in July 2014 to establish a China Development Bank office in Caracas can easily be interpreted as an attempt to more closely monitor Venezuelan expenditures. An office in Caracas might also provide China Development Bank, Venezuela's largest foreign lender, with a greater degree of influence in the event of a political transition.

Venezuela's prospects are undoubtedly a hot topic of discussion within China's foreign affairs apparatus, the country's SOEs, and among experts at state-affiliated think tanks, especially as China engages in sweeping economic reform and a smarter approach to overseas engagement. China nevertheless appears committed to its "comprehensive strategic partnership" with Venezuela, even as Beijing encourages caution, and even as patience with Maduro wanes. China's oil-based commitments to Venezuela will remain intact for the time being, including involvement in the development of the Junín 1, 4, 8, 10, and Boyacá 3 blocks of the Orinoco Belt. For Chinese investors (and some of their international counterparts – Chevron, for example), the potential benefit of continued operation in Venezuela still outweighs the risk.

6. Kazakh - Chinese cooperation in energy sector: geopolitical aspect

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Introduction

In new geopolitical conditions post-Soviet Central Asia have become a part of the emerging vast geopolitical region of Central and Eastern Asia. Central Asia is deeply involved into the energy security issues, because of its relative important hydrocarbon resources. Energy resources of Central Asia represent the special importance for China.

Since 2000, China has been playing an increasingly important role in Central Asia. China attempts to change its status quo in the region (Peyrouse and Laruelle 2009).

The region is experiencing a strong influence of a fast developing China, and in Central Asia it is most noticeable in Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and recently in Tajikistan.

Strengthening of the western and north-western vector of China's national security policy is an important factor in shaping the new geopolitics of the region. China is the fastening rod of a common security space from the Pacific coast to the Caspian Sea.

In the same time Central Asia has an important geo-strategic importance in the regional and global economy, because of the powerful oil, gas and other natural resources, the prospects of building a strong transportation infrastructure.

Allegations that China wants to become a global player in energy field, and its energy interests began to spread throughout the world are considered highly politicized by many Chinese authors. Meanwhile, all Chinese authors are unanimous in their opinion that China is interested in establishing good-neighbor relations with Central Asian countries. Firstly, because of the separatist movement in Xinjiang. Secondly, to avoid military escalation in the region. Thirdly, the region is viewed as potential energy supplier and trading partner. (Zhao Huasheng 2004 and other).

In 2006, China adopted a special state program "Natural resources in exchange for the investment."

More than two-thirds of trade between China and Central Asian region accounts for Kazakhstan. In connection with the development of Turkmen gas and big demand in it in the short term, Turkmenistan appears to become important partner of China too.

Purpose of this paper. The aim of the paper is to analyze the main trends of energy cooperation of Central Asia countries, first of all Kazakhstan, with China. Realization of this goal involves following tasks: identify the major geopolitical consequences of cooperation of Kazakhstan with China in the field of energy.

The China's energy demand. Since 1993, China became a net importer of oil. Oil imports in the Chinese economics were less than 1 million tons in 1980, less than 8 million in 1990, 185 million tons in 2010, and will be close to 583 million tons in 2020 (Medlock 2005)

In 2012, China accounted for 11.7% of global oil consumption (484 mln t), 4.3% of natural gas (143.8 bln m3) and 50.2% of coal (1873.3 mln of oil equivalent).

(<http://nauka.dvfu.ru/ostruktura/news/e607/>).

Ten years later, China became world's second largest consumer of oil after the United States. At the same time, following the American and European practice, China began formation of strategic oil reserves. At the beginning of 2010, the volume of oil reserves was approximately 50 days of consumption (PetroChina 2009)

Since 2010, China became largest primary energy consumer. In 2012, primary energy consumed in China equaled 2.7 bln t of oil equivalent, i.e. 21.9% of global consumption. Year-to-year increase was 7.4% compared to 2011 (BP, June 2013). In 2013, China became largest oil importer, overtaking US, which dominated in oil imports since 1970s (U.S. Energy Information Administration August 9, 2013).

Increase in global activity of the China National Petroleum Company (CNPC), China National Oil Offshore Company (CNOOC), China Petroleum and Chemical Corporation (Sinopec) and, since 2006, of the CITIC state investment fund is a new phenomenon in world oil production.

In 2012, three Chinese energy corporations Sinopec, CNPC and State Grid were placed 5, 6,7 in Global 500. Full List with revenues of \$259,142 mln., \$352,338 mln. и \$375,214 mln accordingly (Fortune Magazine 2013).

The experts of the International Energy Agency suggest that China's natural gas imports will also grow rapidly until 2030 as its own gas production simply won't be enough.

Since 2007, according to long-term contract, China has begun shipments of LNG from Australia to the Guangdong province. More than a dozen of degasification terminals are already under construction or planned to be constructed in China. This will increase capacity of LNG import to 46 - 47 billion cubic meters of gas per year (International Energy Agency 2007. Chapter 10, p. 333).

China is a net exporter of coal. Coal remains the primary fuel for electricity generation. China have to increase the electricity production capacity for more than 1,300 GW. However, most of China's coal reserves are located in the provinces adjacent to the Yellow and East China seas, far away from the main centers of energy consumption.

In China energy problem is partly solved through the exploitation of coal resources of a country, it caused an unprecedented impact on the environment and a sharp increase in greenhouse gas emissions.

Currently, China satisfies most of its demand in energy by internal resources. However, demand for oil is keep growing and have become a key issue in ensuring the security of the country. China has abundant reserves of coal (13% of world reserves) and scarce of oil (2-3%)

and gas (1%). These reserves are not significant in comparison with net demand for these resources in China. Although there are several exploration projects in process, it is unlikely to find large deposits of oil and gas. Oil reserves in China's old oilfields that produce most of the crude oil in the country like Daqing, Shengli and Liaohe have declined sharply. Offshore oil extraction may compensate for the reduction of oil production on the land, though significant progress in regard to this matter unlikely to happen.

Scarcity of local energy resources has led to the adoption of a comprehensive strategy with the following three components:

- Energy sector reform in order to maximize domestic production and attract foreign direct investment;
- Diversification of energy consumption;
- Diversification of international energy sources.

China has also implemented several measures to improve its energy security. First, China has created its own strategic oil reserves. Second, China makes efforts to jointly develop oil fields in the East China and South China seas. Third, China has began to reduce its energy consumption. According to the plan of Chinese government between 2000 and 2020 economy should grow by four times with two-fold increase in energy consumption (Lewis 2007). However, this goal is hard to achieve.

China plans to build more new nuclear power plants. Even so, the share of nuclear energy by 2030 will be insignificant compared to the electricity produced in the country. Certainly, China has paid sufficient attention to the renewable electricity production from sources such as wind power and water power.

Because of threat of naval blockade in case of war with Taiwan, China makes efforts to diversify its oil delivery routes relying more on railway transportation and pipeline. The oil pipeline from Kazakhstan to China is the first one.

Chinese companies have gained an access to the resources of several countries: Angola, Sudan, Russia, Saudi Arabia, and Iran. At the same time, China aims to increase overland oil supplies. Therefore, the importance of an oil pipeline from Kazakhstan is invaluable. According to Chinese estimates, price for oil from Russia will be lower than world prices because of lower transportation costs. In 2007 China entered in gas export agreement with Turkmenistan and it was implemented.

The Russian and Central Asian routes of oil supplies have a strategic meaning for China. China is seriously concerned that Strait of Malacca can be sealed by blockade in the case of conflict with Taiwan.

Russia and Central Asia have direct border with China. However, the length of the pipelines from Russia and Central Asia to consumers are almost the same, and that allows countries of the region to compete with Moscow in the eastern direction.

Competition for energy resources in the region becomes apparent. But it can be avoided.

In 1990s, China promoted the idea of a "pan-Asian continental energy bridge" in order to link the countries of Northeastern Asia with

the Middle East, Central Asia and Iran, via China and under the auspices of Beijing (Christoffersen 2005).

Because of the continental geographical location, China will dominate the northeastern energy markets. Another issue is how this project will relate to the national security of other energy consuming countries in the region.

It is known that in response to the detention of side crew and the captain of Chinese fishing vessel on September 8, 2010, by the Japanese side for "illegal fishing" in the disputed area of two countries called Diaoyu Islands (Senkaku), China has stopped export of rare earth elements used to manufacture electronic products to Japan (Portyakov 2012). Without rare earth elements such as lanthanum and cerium refineries can't produce. The case of Japan suggests that China, enjoy monopoly at the market of rare earth elements, and it can use its advantages as a lever of political pressure.

There are main advantages of CA compared with the Middle East countries.

First, in the OPEC countries in 1973, the nationalization of foreign oil companies was completed and the concession form of relationship was virtually destroyed. Second, in the Middle East China have to deal with a group of countries, while in the CA Beijing builds relationships primarily on a bilateral basis. OPEC's pricing policy has been becoming crucial to China. The Central Asian oil is important for China because the region is not involved with the OPEC and do not depend on them in matters of pricing. It is known that in the first half of 2002, OPEC made an unsuccessful attempt to put pressure on non-member countries, including the Central Asian region, in order to limit oil exports and to maintain high prices on world markets.

Therefore, Chinese companies develop new emerging centers of oil resources throughout the world with low costs and cheap labor, free from influence of the OPEC countries energy policy at the world oil market, such as North and Central Africa, Central Asia and Southeast Asia.

In addition, in the next decade there will be political, economic and social reforms in the Middle East that will affect oil prices.

Chinese companies have begun to strengthen their position in Kazakhstan starting only in the middle of the first decade of this century. Activity of Chinese oil companies in Central Asia was undoubtedly influenced by events in Iraq, the Russian strategy in the oil and gas sector, discovery of the Kashagan field in 2002, Malacca dilemma, and, in recent years, introduction of the ships carbon emission tax that was announced in the EU. China began to build ships for the transportation of heavy crude oil and LNG, hence, the EU innovation can complicate the implementation of this project (Li Bing 2012).

Because of these factors Beijing began to explore energy opportunities in Kazakhstan even more closely.

Kazakhstan's energy sector.

In 1899, oil was discovered for the first time in Kazakhstan in an area called Karashungul in the southeast Caspian depression. 172 oil

and 42 gas fields have been explored, they occupy more than 60% of the territory of Kazakhstan. However, 70% of the hydrocarbon reserves located in the Western region of the country.

On February 20, 2002, on the basis of JSC "NOC Kazakhoil "and JSC "NC Transport of Oil and Gas", National joint-stock Company "KazMunayGas" was founded. The National Company has to improve the competitiveness of the domestic oil and gas industry and to protect the interests of the Republic of Kazakhstan on the market.

Development of the energy sector, which is part of export and includes oil and gas, uranium and coal industries, is of strategic importance for Kazakhstan's economy. At present, companies of more than 45 countries have invested in the production of hydrocarbons in Kazakhstan.

In 2003, Kazakhstan has developed and adopted the State Program on development of Kazakhstan's Caspian shelf until 2015

The volume of oil and gas condensate production

Year	2009	2011	2015	2020
The volume and forecasts of oil and gas condensate	76,5 million tons	80 million tons	95 million tons	163,5 million tons

Source: Ministry of Oil and Gas of the Republic of Kazakhstan
http://mgm.gov.kz/index.php?option=com_content&view=category&layout=blog&id=41&Itemid=63&lang=ru

Oil refining and production of oil products by 2015

Year	2009	2011	2013	2015
The volume and forecasts of oil and petroleum production (million tons)	12,1	13,7	14,2	17,5

Source: Ministry of Oil and Gas of the Republic of Kazakhstan
http://mgm.gov.kz/index.php?option=com_content&view=category&layout=blog&id=41&Itemid=63&lang=ru

The rapid growth of Kazakhstan's oil and gas potential makes pipelines increasingly important.

Western Kazakhstan – China pipeline. In publications of the early 2000s, even the well-known oil and gas industry professionals had little faith in building oil and gas pipelines to China from Central Asia, although they assumed possibility of it. The main obstacle they mentioned was a considerable distance from deposits to the consumers

of raw materials (6500 km) and they believed that cost of oil pumped through this pipeline will be more expensive than oil shipments by sea.

The CNODC, a subsidiary of China National Petroleum Company, and "KazTransOil" undertook the building of an oil pipeline from Western Kazakhstan to China. In late 2005, construction of the first stage of the pipeline was completed. Its capacity is 10 million tons per year, and it is planned to increase its capacity up to 20 million tons. The second stage included the construction of the Kenkiyak – Kumkol pipeline and reconstruction of existing pipelines Kumkol - Karakoin – Atasu and Kenkiyak - Atyrau.

The "Kazakhstan-China pipeline" is owner and operator of the pipeline, this company was created on a parity basis by CNPC and "KazMunayGas".

Geo-economic importance of oil pipeline is that it is the first Kazakh oil pipeline that connects country's oil fields directly with foreign consumers. No less important is the fact that Kazakh oil through it comes to the promising and rapidly growing Chinese market. The pipeline can be used for transit of Russian or Central Asian oil to China as well. In 2009, the transit of Russian oil to China through the pipeline has reached 1.5 million tons.

During the construction of pipelines for export of Kazakh energy resources, Republic is guided by economical and political factors (the strategy of multi-vector transportation system) and environmental benefits of transportation routes.

Thus, in 2011, in terms of volume of Kazakh oil exports leading positions were occupied by CPC's 28,085.709 thousand tons and the Atyrau-Samara's 15427.4 thousand tons. On the Western Kazakhstan - China route oil exports reached 10,694.139 thousand tons.

According to the regional government, oil imports by means of Kazakhstan - China pipeline reached new high of 11.85 mln t in 2013 with 14.09% year-to-year increase. Since 2006 China has imported 63.62 mln t of crude oil through this pipeline mainly for government owned entities in Xinjiang and Beijing (Xinhua: January, 2014).

Gas Industry. Gas fields are also mainly located in the west of Kazakhstan. The main tasks of the gas industry in Kazakhstan are to increase production and rational use of national gas resources, as well as transit facilities of transportation system to meet the needs of the domestic market and further increase the export potential of the Republic.

In 2002, the Concept of Development of Gas Industry was developed. On its basis the Gas Industry Development Program for the period until 2015 was prepared. It was assumed that most of Kazakhstan's gas will be delivered to Russia and the countries of Western Europe. However, even here the Chinese factor has made significant adjustments.

The volume of production of natural and associated gas

Years	2009	2011	2015
The volume and forecasts production of natural and associated gas	36 billion. m3,	39,5 billion m3,	59,3 billion m3,

Source: Ministry of Oil and Gas of the Republic of Kazakhstan
http://mgm.gov.kz/index.php?option=com_content&view=category&layout=blog&id=41&Itemid=63&lang=ru

At the end of 2009, the Turkmenistan - Uzbekistan - Kazakhstan - China gas pipeline started to operate. The capacity of Turkmenistan - China gas pipeline in Kazakhstan will increase up to 40 billion cubic meters, as Kazakhstan not only plans to export its own gas of about 10 billion cubic meters, but also to use the pipeline to supply gas to South Kazakhstan, Zhambyl and Almaty regions.

In Kazakhstan the Turkmenistan - China gas pipeline route starts from the Uzbek-Kazakh border and then to Shymkent-Almaty-Khorgos line. Kazakh branch, Beineu - Bozoy - Kyzylorda - Shymkent, will be connected to the main line. Thus, the gas from the western regions of Kazakhstan will be delivered to the southern regions and to the China.

Central Asia Gas Pipeline system transported about 27 bln cubic meters of gas to China in 2013 and accounted to more than the half of gas imports and one sixth of consumption according to CNPC and Platts Energy News.

The problem of diversification of gas exports as well as oil exports remains relevant. The Turkmenistan - China gas pipeline will increase export of Kazakh gas to the Chinese market and will provide transportation of Central Asian gas to China.

Turkmenistan-Uzbekistan-Kazakhstan-China pipeline will undoubtedly become the driving force for the growth of gas production in the region. Pipelines will significantly change the situation in Central Asia, with its energy resources in geo-economic and, consequently, in the geo-strategic terms. Reduced Gazprom monopoly may reduce political influence of Moscow in the region and improve positions of Beijing.

Import of Central Asian gas is of strategic importance for China as well, as bulk of natural gas currently supplied by pipelines, and about third of imported gas arrives by sea in liquefied form. In addition, Beijing's position in the negotiations with "Gazprom" will be strengthened in matters of Russian gas deliveries from the Far East and the East Siberian oil fields.

Thus, the emergence of China's alternative shook the monopoly of "Gazprom" for the transit and purchase of gas in the region. On the one hand, China by all means encourages competition among post-Soviet gas exporters to gain serious concessions. On the other hand, China is aiming to diversify routes and this point is supported by construction of

new Turkmenistan – China pipeline which will pass Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan and so go round the Kazakhstan.

Many of the issues of cooperation between Central Asia and China in the gas sector are not fully understood. For example, how long the countries of the region will agree on such a low price offered by the Chinese side? Would it cause confusion and complications in energy cooperation between Central Asia and China in the long term?

The positions of the Chinese companies in Kazakhstan.

According to estimates of the famous Kazakhstani sinologist K. Syroezhkin, there are more than 80 Chinese capital companies today in the oil and gas sector of Kazakhstan, 21 of which extract oil at the Kazakh oil fields (Syroezhkin 2012).

By the volume of oil extraction, Chinese companies are inferior to American companies, but they are more than three times superior to the companies from the UK, Russia and Italy.

During the 1997-2010 period, volumes of oil owned by Chinese companies in Kazakhstan increased from 1.6 to 17.7 million tons. Over the years, they have extracted more than one-fifth of all oil produced in Kazakhstan per year. More than half of oil extracted in Kazakhstan by Chinese companies was exported to China (Informatsionno-analiticheskii portal 2011)

The rest of the oil produced by Chinese companies in Kazakhstan, was exported at market prices. Oil prices are being regulated in China.

Kazakhstan topped the list of oil importers to China which included Sudan, Ecuador, Algeria, Indonesia, Syria, Angola, other.

Currently, Kazakhstan has become a successful example of activity of Chinese companies. Both sides are interested in deepening cooperation in the field of mining and oil supplies. It is expected to double the volume of export of Kazakh oil to China by 2020.

The main suppliers of oil to the Chinese market are Saudi Arabia, Angola, Iran, Russia, Oman, Sudan and Kazakhstan. Russia and Kazakhstan have been successfully competing with the Middle Eastern and African countries at the Chinese oil market. China is the fourth largest consumer of Kazakh oil after the Switzerland, Italy and France.

At the CIS countries, Chinese companies have been able to gain a foothold in the oil and gas production projects in Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan.

The Kazakhstan and the Turkmenistan have an important geo-strategic importance as they possess enormous reserves of oil and gas. These countries have become widely known because of giant energy resource fields like oil field Kashagan in the Caspian shelf of Kazakhstan and South Yoloten in Turkmenistan.

CONCLUSION

The Central Asian economies experience high dependence on the state of the energy industry.

With the construction of pipelines from Central Asia to China, reorientation of energy flows from western to eastern direction began, that leads to a shift in the regional balance of power, limitation of Russian monopoly position in terms of transit of Central Asian hydrocarbons.

However, the countries of Central Asia became a stable suppliers of raw materials and recipients of industrial products from East Asia, mainly from China. The policy pursued by China is in the interest of the region.

This was particularly noticeable during the crisis of 2008-2009, when China was buying a large amount of energy resources, supported the economies of exporting countries and ensured stability at oil markets. Price dynamics and structure of the global energy market to a large extent is under the influence of Chinese demand.

One can agree with the statement that energy exporting countries in the region primarily serve the economic interests of Chinese companies in terms of hydrocarbons.

China gets the maximum benefit in the global competition for energy resources of the region. Chinese energy policy in Eurasia provides for elimination of any dependence on both Russian and Central Asian energy resources. Beijing tries to avoid the energy rivalry between the countries of the region for the Chinese market and makes efforts to involve all Central Asian states in the process of cooperation in the field of energy.

The Kazakhstan have benefited from the implementation of energy policy of China as well. Concerns about "Chinese expansion" which existed in the past on the mental level have been gradually receding. According to opinion polls conducted in Kazakhstan, China is regarded as a very worthy alternative to Russia (*Kitai i Rossiya v otsenkakh* 2011).

All Central Asian states make efforts to take advantage of energy competition between the leading players in order to enhance their geopolitical status and maximize economic benefit.

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7. China's Economic Engagement in Central Asia: An Assessment

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China's relations with the Central Asian States (CAS) have gradually evolved since their independence in 1991. At the first step of engagement, China amicably resolved border disputes with the CAS, which were part of Soviet legacy. Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan share border with China. Resolving the border disputes amicably helped China and the CAS in the later years to strengthen their economic ties.

Economic diplomacy has been an integral part of China's engagement with the five countries. Today, China has emerged as an important economic partner of the CAS. Chinese economy is one of the fastest growing economies in the world. Access to reliable sources of supply of energy is an important driver to sustain the present economic growth and also to boost further progress. The growing demand for energy has made it important for China to look for alternate sources of supply. The energy rich Central Asian countries, thus, hold a significant place in China's quest to diversify its sources of energy supply. Developing robust bilateral trade and investing in the region's energy and other infrastructure projects have been important facets of China's economic engagement with the CAS. By increasing its economic engagement with the region, China has been able to get support from the CAS that their territories will not be used to promote the Uighur cause in the Xinjiang province.

The paper attempts to make an assessment of China's economic presence in the region in the past two decades. The paper argues that the growing economic profile of China in the region since 1991 shows that

China would remain an influential economic player in the region. It would discuss the growing China's economic presence in the region by assessing various dimensions of China-CAS economic engagement: energy cooperation, investments in energy and other infrastructure projects and trade. Also, it would highlight the interests of the CAS in developing closer cooperation with China and the geopolitical competition prevailing in the region.

Energy Cooperation

Access to Central Asian hydrocarbon resources has been one of the main Chinese interests in Central Asia. Cooperation in the energy sector constitutes a crucial place in China's economic engagement with Central Asia.

China is the second largest energy consumer in the world and its sources of energy includes mainly coal (primarily domestic production) followed by oil, hydroelectric power and natural gas as indicated in Figure 1. To reduce pollution, China is going for cleaner energy like natural gas. China holds 24.4 billion barrels of proven oil reserves, which is the highest in the Asia-Pacific region.¹ China is the fourth largest oil producer in the world (Table 1). However, its domestic production of oil is unable to meet its growing demand. In 2013, out of 4.5 million barrels per day (bbl/d) of total oil production in China, crude oil production was 4.2 million bbl/d and consumption level of oil was 10.1 million bbl/d (Table 1). China's oil import is expected to rise to 65 percent by 2020.² As pointed in Figure 2, China is the second largest net oil importer in the world. China mainly imports oil from West Asia (Figure 3) through sea routes.

China has the largest reserve of proven natural gas in the Asia-Pacific region, which is about 155 trillion cubic feet (tcf).³ In 2012, natural gas constituted of only 4.9 percent of China's total energy consumption.⁴ Figure 4 indicates that China's demand and production of natural gas have increased substantially in the past decade. In 2012, natural gas production in China was about 3.8 tcf and its consumption was about 5.2 tcf (Figure 4). The government is planning to produce about 5.5 tcf of natural gas by the end of 2015.⁵ It is projected that the demand for gas would rise to 7.8 tcf by 2020 and about 17 tcf by 2040, growing by an annual average rate of above 4 percent.⁶ The share of natural gas in the total energy consumption is expected to constitute about 8 percent by the end of 2015 and 10 percent by 2020.⁷ The growing demand for gas would make China more import dependent and

would thus encourage it to look for alternate supply sources globally. In 2012, about 29 percent of natural gas consumption in China was imported.⁸ China became a net importer of natural gas for the first time in 2007 (Figure 4). Since then, China's natural gas imports have increased substantially (Figure 5). China has also been making huge investments in building pipelines and gas processing infrastructures.

Figure: 1

Total Energy Consumption in China by Type, 2011

Source: EIA (Energy Information Administration), *China*, 4 February 2014, U.S., [Online: Web] Accessed on 19 October 2014, URL: <http://www.eia.gov/countries/cab.cfm?fips=ch>.

Table: 1
Production and Consumption of Petroleum in China
(thousand barrels per day)

	2012				2013*
	China	Asia & Oceania	World	Rank	China
Total Oil Production	4,372.45	9,077	89,755	4	4,459.41
Crude Oil Production	4,085.15	7,731	75,956	4	4,164.12
Consumption	9,874.71	28,976	89,128	2	10,116.64
Estimated Petroleum Net Exports	-	-19,898	—	215	-5,657.23
Refinery Capacity	6,806	24,875	88,097	2	6866
Proven Reserves (billion barrels)	23.72	45	1,646	15	24.38

* = Data of 2013 are projection of the whole year based on available data as on 30 May 2013.

Source: EIA (Energy Information Administration), *China: Country Analysis Brief Overview*, 4 February 2014, U.S., [Online: Web] Accessed on 18 October 2014, URL: <http://www.eia.gov/countries/country-data.cfm?fips=CH#pet>.

Figure: 2

Top Ten Annual Net Oil Importers, 2013
(millions barrels per day)

Note: Estimates of total Production less consumption. Does not account for stock-build.

Source: EIA (Energy Information Administration). *China*. 4 February 2014, U.S., [Online: Web] Accessed on 19 October 2014, URL: <http://www.eia.gov/countries/cab.cfm?fips=ch>.

Figure: 3

China's Crude Oil Imports by Source, 2013

Source: EIA (Energy Information Administration). *China*, 4 February 2014, U.S., [Online: Web] Accessed on 19 October 2014, URL: <http://www.eia.gov/countries/cab.cfm?fips=ch>.

Figure: 4
China's Natural Gas Production and Consumption, 2000-2012
(trillion cubic feet)

Source: EIA (Energy Information Administration). *China*, 4 February 2014, U.S., [Online: Web] Accessed on 19 October 2014, URL: <http://www.eia.gov/countries/cab.cfm?fips=ch>.

Figure: 5
China's Natural Gas Imports by Source, 2006-2013
(trillion cubic feet)

Source: EIA (Energy Information Administration), "Natural Gas Serves a Small, but Growing, Portion of China's Total Energy Demand", *Today in Energy*, 18 August 2014, U.S., [Online: Web] Accessed on 18 October 2014, URL: <http://www.eia.gov/todayinenergy/detail.cfm?id=17591>.

China's hydrocarbon rich Central Asian neighbours have given China another avenue to import oil and gas to meet its increasing demands for energy. China has made huge investments in building energy infrastructures in the region. Central Asian countries are keen on receiving foreign investments to develop their energy sector. The backbone of the economy of the three hydrocarbon rich CAS: Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan is the energy sector. An important area is investment in pipeline projects in the region. Also, Chinese presence in the Central Asian energy sector gave the CAS an alternate to Russian market. The CAS hydrocarbon sector until China's entry was dependent on Russian market and Russian pipeline network. The completion of the Kazakhstan-China oil pipeline and the Turkmenistan-China gas pipeline are important landmarks of China's economic presence in the region. These pipelines also changed the geopolitics of the region by giving the CAS access to new market.

Kazakhstan-China Oil Pipeline

Kazakhstan is the largest producer of oil in the region. In 2013, the production was about 1.79 million barrels per day (bbl/day) or 83.8 million tons annually, out of which about 83.9 percent (70 million tons) was exported.⁹ Kazakhstan has emerged as a significant oil supplier to China. Now, about 96 percent of Kazakhstan's exports to China are energy resources.¹⁰ The completion of the Kazakhstan-China pipeline has been a major development in post-independent Central Asia. This was the first pipeline bypassing Russia, which connected Central Asia with international markets, facilitating Kazakhstan's diversification initiative to reduce its dependence on Russia.

The Kazakhstan-China oil pipeline, a 50: 50 joint venture of China National Petroleum Corporation (CNPC) and the Kazakh oil company *KazMunayGas* was China's first direct pipeline from Central Asia. It transports crude oil from oil fields of western Kazakhstan to the *Dushanzi* refinery located in Xinjiang. The pipeline, one of the longest in the world, is about 2300 km.¹¹

The pipeline was constructed in three segments, which was completed in two phases. The first phase included the 448 km long section, which connects oil fields of *Atyrau* near the Caspian Sea with *Kenkiyak* oilfield, which became operational by the end of 2003. The construction of the first phase of the pipeline was significant for

Kazakhstan as it was the first oil pipeline built in the country after independence. The construction of the *Atasu to Alashankou* and *Kenkiyak to Kumkol* sections constituted the second phase of the pipeline. The construction of the *Atasu to Alashankou* section was started in late September 2004 and completed in December 2005. The 963 km long *Atasu-Alashankou* section begins from the rail link at *Atasu* in the *Karaganda* region (Central Kazakhstan) moving through the border at the *Droujba-Alashankou* rail terminal to *Alashankou* in China's north-western Xinjiang region. This section became operational in July 2006. The pipeline initially carried oil from *Kumkol* field in central Kazakhstan. The *Kumkol* oil field was developed by CNPC, which it acquired in 2005. The initial annual carrying capacity of the *Atasu-Alashankou* pipeline was 10 million tons of oil and its full capacity 20 million tons.¹² The second segment of phase II of the pipeline included the construction of the 794 km *Kenkiyak to Kumkol* section in central Kazakhstan, which was started in December 2007 and became operational in October 2009. The initial transportation capacity of this section was also 10 million tons per year and its full capacity 20 million tons per year.¹³

The *Atasu-Alashankou* oil pipeline has been upgraded to carry its full capacity (20 mt/y) in December 2013. The other sections of the pipeline are being expanded to transport their full capacity. The pipeline is expected to increase its carrying capacity to 50 million tons by 2035.¹⁴ Later, the pipeline might carry oil from Russia's western Siberia¹⁵ and also from the *Kashagan*¹⁶ oil field in the Caspian Sea to China.

Map: 1
Kazakhstan-China Oil Pipeline

Note: Phase 2 and 3 are now completed.

Source: F. William Engdahl, "Washington is Playing a Deeper Game with China", *Global Research*, 11 July 2009, [Online: Web] Accessed 20 October 2014, URL: <http://www.globalresearch.ca/washington-is-playing-a-deeper-game-with-china/14327>.

Central Asia-China Gas Pipeline

Turkmenistan holds the largest gas reserves in Central Asia. With about 17.5 trillion cubic metres (tcm) reserves,¹⁷ Turkmenistan has one of the richest gas reserves in the world. It is the main exporter of gas in the Central Asia region. The Central Asia-China gas pipeline is one of the major projects in post-independent Turkmenistan. It gave the country access to a new market bypassing Russia. Now, this pipeline also supplies gas from Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan.¹⁸ At present, about 52 percent of Chinese natural gas imports come from Turkmenistan.¹⁹

The pipeline starts from *Gedaim* at the Turkmenistan-Uzbekistan border moves through central Uzbekistan and southern Kazakhstan, and then reaches its destination at *Horgos* in the northwest region of Xinjiang. The pipeline, now, has three lines (Line A, B and C) running in parallel and each pipeline is about 1,830 kilometres.²⁰ The construction of Line A and B started in July 2008. Line A started operating in December 2009 and Line B in October 2010. The construction of Line C started in September 2012, which became operational in May 2014.

The decision to build the pipeline goes back to 2007 when CNPC signed a Production Sharing Agreement with Turkmenistan to explore and develop gas fields on the right bank of the Amu Darya River and to build a pipeline through which Turkmenistan would supply 30 billion cubic metres per annum (bcm/a) of natural gas to China for a period of thirty years.²¹ China also signed agreements with Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan as transit countries for sale of gas from Turkmenistan through pipeline A and B and also for gas supply from Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan through pipeline C. Another development was the signing of an additional agreement for 25 bcm/a natural gas sale and purchase between CNPC and *Turkmengaz* (gas company of Turkmenistan) on 3 September 2013, which would be transported through the 4th branch (Line D) of the Central Asia-China gas pipeline. Also, an Engineering, Procurement, Construction (EPC) contract has been inked for building 30 bcm/a gas production capacity on the *Galkynysh* gas field, formerly known as *South Yolotan*.²² In September 2013, China has also signed inter-governmental agreements with Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan for the construction of the Line D project. The construction of the Tajikistan section of the Line D started on 13 September 2014, which

is expected to be completed in 2016. The length of the Line D pipeline would be 1,000 km, of which 840 km would be in Central Asia, starting from Turkmenistan crossing through Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan and finally reaching to China.²³

Line A and B pipelines reached their full delivery capacity of 30 bcm/a by end of 2011.²⁴ Natural gas from Amu Darya Project (13bcm/a), and *Turkmengaz* State Concern (17 bcm/a) feed Line A and B.²⁵ Line C has a capacity of 25 bcm/a, which includes 10 bcm/a from Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan each and 5 bcm/a from Kazakhstan.²⁶ By end of 2015, Line C is expected to achieve its full delivery capacity, taking the total delivery capacity of the three lines to 55 bcm/a. Once the three lines reach their full capacity, natural gas from Central Asia would consist of about 20 percent of China's annual natural gas consumption.²⁷ *Galkynysh* gas field of Turkmenistan would feed Line D of the pipeline, which has a delivery capacity of 30 bcm/a.²⁸ With the completion of Line D, the annual capacity of the Central Asia-China Gas Pipeline will reach to 85 bcm/a, making it the largest gas transmission system in Central Asia. Kyrgyzstan would also benefit after the completion of Line D. It would give Kyrgyzstan access to gas from Turkmenistan at cheaper rate, thereby reducing its dependence on gas from Uzbekistan. Also, Kyrgyzstan will get an opportunity to reduce its reliance on *Gazprom*, Russian gas Company for transportation of gas; the Company has taken over as the service provider in Kyrgyzstan since July 2013.²⁹

Map: 2

Central Asia-China Gas Pipeline

Source: CNPC (China National Petroleum Corporation), "Flow of natural gas from Central Asia", [Online: Web] Accessed on 20 October 2014, URL: <http://www.cnpc.com.cn/en/FlowofnaturalgasfromCentralAsia/FlowofnaturalgasfromCentralAsia2.shtml>.

The pipeline is mutually beneficial. China gets an alternate source of energy supply to meet its demands for energy to sustain its economic growth. China is looking for cleaner energy like natural gas and trying to reduce its dependence on coal consumption. Access to the vast natural gas reserves in Central Asia helps China in its efforts to increase the use of clean energy. China is purchasing Central Asian gas for about one third of the price *Gazprom* receives in the European market.³⁰ An estimate by the International Energy Agency shows that if the current level at which China is spreading its infrastructure network in Central Asian region's energy sector continues, China will be importing half of the region's natural gas by 2020.³¹

The main markets for Turkmen gas, till the Central Asia-China pipeline became operational were Russia and Iran. The Central Asia-Centre gas pipeline built in 1960 was the only pipeline carrying Turkmen gas to international market till Turkmenistan-Iran gas pipeline was constructed. This pipeline carries Turkmen and Uzbek gas to Russia, which is then resold to Europe or used for domestic consumption in Russia.³² The Turkmenistan-Iran gas pipeline built in 1997 gave Turkmenistan an alternate market for its gas. Before the Central Asia-China pipeline was built, about 70 percent of Turkmenistan's gas was exported through pipelines built during Soviet days.³³ The completion of the pipeline to China has changed the situation. Now, Turkmenistan's gas exports to China is more that its exports to Russia.³⁴

Map: 3

Key Oil and Natural Gas Pipelines in China

Source: EIA (Energy Information Administration), *China*, 4 February 2014, U.S., [Online: Web] Accessed on 19 October 2014, URL: <http://www.eia.gov/countries/cab.cfm?fips=ch>.

China has been investing in building gas pipeline infrastructures linking supply areas in the western and northern regions to demand centres along the coast. China would increase imports from the western and northern neighbours to meet its energy demands in the coastal areas (Map 3).

These two pipelines have deep impact on the region's politics. International attention to access the region's hydrocarbon resources have been growing since the independence of the CAS. Also, these states showed willingness to reduce their dependence on Russian pipeline system and to diversify their energy markets. There were many proposals to connect Central Asian oil and gas to international markets, bypassing Russia, like, *Nabucco*, Turkmenistan-Afghanistan-Pakistan-India (TAPI), *Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan* (BTC), etc. However, these pipelines did not make much progress, except BTC. The completion of the pipelines connecting Central Asia and China within the stipulated time helped China to strengthen its presence in the region.

In addition to the Kazakhstan-China oil pipeline and Central Asia-China gas pipeline (discussed above), China has also invested in other energy projects in the region. In 2004, China and Kazakhstan agreed to jointly explore and develop oil and gas resources in the Caspian Sea. CNPC acquired *PetroKazakhstan* in 2005 at US\$ 4.2 billion.³⁵ China's International Trust and Investment Corporation has shares in oil fields in western Kazakhstan worth US\$ 1.9 billion.³⁶ In November 2009, CNPC and *KazMunaiGas* took over Kazakh oil company, *MangistauMunaiGas* at a price of US\$ 2.6 billion.³⁷ China purchased a major stake in *Aktobemunaigaz*, a Kazakh company.

Chinese President Xi Jinping, during his visit to Central Asia in September 2013, signed a number of energy deals with Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan, and promised investments worth billions. During this visit, China and Kazakhstan signed deals worth US\$ 30 billion in energy projects, which among others included a stake in *Kashagan* oil field, a prime discovery in recent times.³⁸ In 2013, CNPC purchased 8.33 percent share of the *Kashagan* field that was earlier owned by *ConocoPhillips*, a US Company.³⁹ India was also trying to purchase *ConocoPhillips'* share in the *Kashagan* field but finally it went to China.⁴⁰ The *Beineu-Bozoi* gas pipeline linking Kazakhstan's southwest and southeast was also inaugurated by the two leaders during

Chinese President's visit to Kazakhstan in September 2013. This pipeline is expected to pump gas to China by 2015.⁴¹ During this visit, other areas of cooperation in the energy sector was also explored like cooperation in the field of commercial nuclear, new and clean energy, etc.⁴²

China, in 2009 gave US\$ 4 billion to develop the *South Yolotan* gas field (now known as *Galkynysh* gas field), which is the largest gas field in Turkmenistan and world's second-biggest gas field.⁴³ Production from this field started in 2013, which was inaugurated by Chinese President during his visit to Turkmenistan in September 2013. Supply of gas from this field will triple Chinese imports from Turkmenistan.⁴⁴ China has invested in building Turkmenistan's east-west gas pipeline, expected to be completed by 2016.⁴⁵

Production of natural gas in Uzbekistan is close to Turkmenistan's production level. However, Uzbekistan's natural gas export is low. In 2013, Uzbekistan exported only 18 percent of its total production, which was 55.2 bcm/a.⁴⁶ Uzbekistan is also trying to attract foreign investments to develop its energy sector. Uzbek-China cooperation in the energy sector is growing. It includes a US\$ 15 billion worth deals in oil, gas and uranium sector signed during Chinese President's visit to Uzbekistan in September 2013.⁴⁷ Earlier in January 2008, *AsiaTransGas*, an Uzbekistan-China joint venture was established.⁴⁸ China acquired the right to refine oil and gas reserves in Uzbekistan and had preferential access to wells after the drilling is completed by an agreement signed between the two countries.⁴⁹ In September 2013, China announced investment worth US\$ 1.4 billion to build the Kyrgyz part of the Central Asia-China gas pipeline (Line D).⁵⁰

China's engagement in the region's energy sector is not limited to hydrocarbon only. There are opportunities for cooperation in harnessing uranium reserves, renewable energy and quartz sand deposits available in the region.⁵¹

Cooperation in Other Areas

Stability of the Xinjiang province is important for China to address the Uyghur issue in the province. China has been careful that the Uyghur cause does not get support from Central Asia, which shares border with the Xinjiang province. As part of its policy to develop its Western region, China has been investing in the Xinjiang province, particularly in infrastructure projects. Greater connectivity between Xinjiang and its western Central Asian neighbours would enhance trade opportunities. To

facilitate connectivity and in the process boost development, China has been investing in roads and railway networks. China has invested in the *Irkeshdam-Osh* road, the *Osh-Uzgen* road and some section of the *Madaniyat-Shamaldyay-Tashkumyr-Razan* road that connects to the *Krupsay* hydroelectric station, etc.⁵²

China will also be constructing a railway line from Uzbekistan to China via Kyrgyzstan. China has now emerged as the largest investor in the transport sector of Uzbekistan.⁵³ China gave loan worth US\$ 10 billion to Kazakhstan in 2009.⁵⁴

Unlike the other three CAS, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan do not have hydrocarbon reserves. China has been developing close ties with these two CAS also. Both these countries share border with China and could serve as transit countries for pipelines coming from other CAS. China has invested in infrastructure projects like electrification and road projects in Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan. In 2009, China agreed to invest US\$ 1 billion in building power plants, electricity grids and roads in Tajikistan.⁵⁵ Also, China has invested more than US\$ 100 million in Tajik mining sector.⁵⁶ China's engagement with Kyrgyzstan is also developing. In January 2010, China and Kyrgyzstan agreed to construct US\$ 342 million in building electric grid link.⁵⁷ China is also investing in electric grid projects that would upgrade domestic electric network in Kyrgyzstan.

During Chinese President's visit to Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan in 2013, China agreed to give loan worth more than 10 billion dollars to these countries.⁵⁸ Chinese President also proposed the idea of "Silk Road Economic Belt", a trans-Eurasian project spreading from the Pacific Ocean to the Baltic Sea.⁵⁹ This initiative aims to boost trade and regional economic cooperation. It was also agreed to enhance cooperation in various other areas like connectivity, agriculture, technology, local currency clearance, etc.⁶⁰ China also has been promoting people-to-people contact with the CAS. In its effort to reach out more to the people of CAS, China has offered scholarship to 30,000 students from member countries of the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) in the next ten years and free study tours for an additional 10,000 students and teachers enrolled at Chinese-government-funded Confucius Institutes in Central Asia.⁶¹ Among the CAS: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan are members of the SCO.

Trade Relations

In recent years, China has emerged as a main trade partner of the CAS.

From the second half of the last decade, China-Central Asia trade has increased significantly. In 2010, China surpassed Russia as the region's largest trade partner.⁶² The total trade volume between China and Central Asian countries increased to US\$ 50 billion in 2013, an increase by 100 times from the 1992 level.⁶³ Table 2 shows that Kazakhstan is the main trade partner of China in the region ever since independence. It is expected that trade volume between two countries will reach US\$ 40 billion in 2015.⁶⁴ Turkmenistan has emerged as the second largest trade partner of China in the region, which was ranked as second lowest immediately after independence. Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan are the main suppliers of oil and gas, respectively, to China.

Table: 2
China-Central Asia Trade Figures, 1992-2003
(Value: million US\$)

Countries	1992 [#]	1993 [#]	1994 [#]	1995 [#]	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003
Kazakhstan	372.8	428.0	218.7	331.7	494.7	488.8	432.7	554.7	824.7	831.7	1336.0	2176.8
Kyrgyzstan	44.3	77.8	66.7	30.4	43.6	64.0	60.0	62.1	81.0	68.0	100.4	101.0
Tajikistan	2.8	10.6	6.2	6.0	7.5	15.3	5.8	5.2	15.3	7.4	9.7	32.4
Turkmenistan [^]	4.5	4.2	4.0	7.7	13	9	12	19	24	65	114	108
Uzbekistan	54.8	57.5	131.3	116.5	177.6	194.9	93.1	41.9	54.3	62.7	139.5	343.0

[^] = Data of Turkmenistan from 1992-95 include only import figures.

Source: Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2014), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

[#] = Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2010), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 14 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

Table: 2 (Continued)
China-Central Asia Trade Figures, 2004-2014
(Value: million US\$)

Countries	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Kazakhstan	2725.5	3675.7	5517.5	9146.9	12241.7	9458.1	14084.1	21312.6	23982.1	28361.5
Kyrgyzstan	119.4	129.5	283.7	417.5	772.6	5794.2	4572.7	5455.0	5660.8	5641.1
Tajikistan	63.1	98.2	158.8	283.6	466.5	671.9	685.2	2262.1	2022.0	2137.5
Turkmenistan	106	116	194	377	909	1043	1524	5131	9163	9341
Uzbekistan	555.8	663.2	961.1	1172.9	1705.5	2033.5	2477.0	2228.3	2954.4	4619.0

Source: Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2014), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

The Tables below (Table 3 to Table 8) highlight the top ten export and import destinations of China, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan.

Table: 3
China: Direction of Trade (million US\$, calendar year)

Exports							Imports					
	1995*	2000	2005	2010	2013		1995*	2000	2005	2010	2013	
	Total	148,965	249,200	761,950	1577,750	2210,019	Total	132,164	220,590	659,950	1396,240	1950,289
Sl. No.	Top 10 Countries®						Top 10 Countries®					
1	Hong Kong	36,004	44,518	124,473	218,302	384,792	Korea	10,288	23,207	76,820	138,349	183,073
2	US	24,744	52,099	162,891	283,287	368,427	Japan	29,007	41,510	100,408	176,736	162,278
3	Japan	28,466	41,654	83,986	121,043	150,275	Taipei	16,180	25,494	74,680	115,739	156,637
4	Korea	6,688	11,292	35,108	68,766	91,176	US	16,123	22,363	48,622	102,099	152,575
5	Germany	5,672	9,278	32,527	68,047	67,348	Australia	2,585	5,024	16,194	61,122	98,818
6	Netherlands	3,233	6,687	25,876	49,704	60,317	Germany	8,035	10,409	30,723	74,261	94,204
7	UK	2,791	6,310	18,976	38,767	50,949	Malaysia	2,065	5,480	20,093	50,447	60,143
8	Russia	1,674	2,233	13,211	29,612	49,595	Brazil	1,228	1,621	9,993	38,125	54,086
9	India	765	1,561	8,934	40,915	48,443	Saudi Arabia	553	1,954	12,246	32,829	53,461
10	Singapore	3,500	5,761	16,632	32,347	45,864	Thailand	1,611	4,381	13,992	33,196	32,738

* = 1996 data.

@ = Ranking of top 10 countries is based on 2013 data.

Source: Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2014), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

¥ = Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2013), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

Table: 4
Kazakhstan: Direction of Trade (million US\$, calendar year)

Exports							Imports					
	1995*	2000	2005	2010	2013		1995*	2000	2005	2010	2013	
	Total	5256.9	9880.0	27858.4	56972.8	64194.4	Total	3807.1	5055.6	17388.1	23660.5	45068.1
Sl. No.	Top 10 Countries®						Top 10 Countries®					
1	China	297.0	673.7	2423.9	10121.6	14567.2	China	34.7	151.0	1251.8	3962.5	13794.3
2	France	17.4	15.8	2665.2	4433.0	6205.9	Russia	1899.7	2439.2	6591.3	5058.1	9218.7
3	Russia	2365.8	1751.4	2927.2	2702.9	5159.4	Ukraine	85.7	81.2	844.7	1360.7	3078.2
4	Germany	171.1	550.9	408.9	1749.7	5040.6	Germany	196.7	335.7	1300.7	1844.5	2810.3
5	Italy	142.5	917.6	4190.5	9579.0	4434.7	US	64.7	277.5	1205.3	1322.2	1205.3
6	Ukraine	121.5	254.2	200.4	666.1	2684.4	Korea	87.8	83.6	256.1	526.3	1182.0
7	Canada	2.4	6.9	528.1	2448.5	2518.4	Turkey	123.5	144.0	399.9	618.7	1113.0
8	Austria	15.7	0.6	1.1	2528.7	1604.7	Italy	30.2	155.9	679.8	1587.4	1022.7
9	Switzerland	203.5	463.2	5509.5	1234.4	1139.1	Uzbekistan	89.3	70.5	254.5	473.4	860.6
10	Netherlands	511.5	226.7	877.8	4159.8	1119.1	Japan	8.4	105.1	598.6	560.3	769.2

* = 1996 data.

@ = Ranking of top 10 countries is based on 2013 data.

Source: Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2014), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

¥ = Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2013), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

Table: 5
Kyrgyzstan: Direction of Trade (million US\$, calendar year)

		Exports					Imports						
		1995 [¥]	2000	2005	2010	2013			1995 [¥]	2000	2005	2010	2013
Total		483.3	501.5	633.8	1042.5	1136.0	Total		391.5	553.0	1111.6	7231.5	10799.3
Sl. No.	Top 10 Countries [@]						Sl. No.	Top 10 Countries [@]					
1	Kazakhstan	112.5	33.4	116.1	150.9	318.8	1	China	27.4	36.9	102.9	4509.5	5584.0
2	Uzbekistan	88.9	89.4	17.1	257.9	317.1	2	Russia	104.8	132.5	379.0	1072.9	2284.6
3	Russia	114.3	65.1	134.4	351.8	126.1	3	Kazakhstan	66.8	57.5	174.4	465.0	840.9
4	UAE	-	1.4	173.1	54.6	78.5	4	Turkey	3.6	26.7	33.4	142.1	427.2
5	Afghanistan	-	4.4	12.4	51.1	62.8	5	Uzbekistan	70.0	75.2	60.1	177.9	218.7
6	China	3.0	44.1	26.6	63.2	57.1	6	Korea	-	6.9	27.8	115.0	180.3
7	Turkey	19.1	7.2	18.2	28.1	33.6	7	Ukraine	8.3	7.0	40.1	82.5	148.2
8	Tajikistan	4.8	7.4	22.9	14.0	17.2	8	Germany	2.3	25.1	37.6	53.4	124.6
9	Iran	6.2 [*]	6.7	3.9	11.3	16.2	9	US	35.7 [*]	53.8	67.2	86.2	116.7
10	Germany	2.8 [*]	144.6	4.1	5.0	14.0	10	Belarus	5.0	3.9	7.1	94.0	108.0

* = 1996 data, - = magnitude equals zero.

@ = Ranking of top 10 countries is based on 2013 data.

Source: Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2014), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

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Table: 6
Tajikistan: Direction of Trade (million US\$, calendar year)

		Exports					Imports						
		1995 [¥]	2000	2005	2010	2013			1995 [¥]	2000	2005	2010	2013
Total		748.6	770.0	908.7	1194.7	953.7	Total		809.9	670.5	1330.1	2656.9	4943.7
Sl. No.	Top 10 Countries [@]						Sl. No.	Top 10 Countries [@]					
1	Turkey	8.1	58.4	143.4	377.0	337.6	1	China	0.4	11.9	92.5	238.2	2056.8
2	Iran	0.7	12.5	36.7	59.6	85.6	2	Russia	136.0	105.1	256.5	856.5	786.2
3	China	5.6	3.4	5.7	447.0	80.7	3	Kazakhstan	26.5	82.4	168.3	292.7	621.4
4	Bangladesh	-	-	-	-	65.9	4	Turkey	3.9	4.0	21.9	60.0	312.0
5	Kazakhstan	7.0	5.7	19.7	19.9	65.3	5	Iran	0.7	7.6	30.9	141.6	197.8
6	Afghanistan	0.3	2.6	12.1	52.2	64.2	6	Turkmenistan	57.4	29.3	53.8	83.5	102.7
7	Russia	95.3	258.8	82.8	101.8	56.1	7	Uzbekistan	251.4	185.6	152.9	71.8	88.3
8	Taipei	-	-	-	-	43.6	8	UAE	-	2.8	24.3	61.0	85.2
9	Italy	2.4	21.4	15.6	17.9	18.1	9	Ukraine	2.2	84.3	82.0	188.7	67.5
10	Uzbekistan	132.0	97.8	66.5	8.6	10.6	10	US	25.3	0.0	11.7	94.9	57.7

- = magnitude equals zero.

@ = Ranking of top 10 countries is based on 2013 data.

Source: Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2014), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

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Table: 7
Turkmenistan: Direction of Trade (million US\$, calendar year)

		Exports					Imports						
		1995 [¥]	2000	2005	2010	2013			1995 [¥]	2000	2005	2010	2013
Total		1880.7	2505	4957	3270	11835	Total	1364.0	1788	2609	5650	9639	
Sl. No.	Top 10 Countries[@]						Top 10 Countries[@]						
1	China	7.1	8	17	950	8085	Turkey	160.4	253	199	1254	2151	
2	Turkey	149.6	186	146	351	594	Russia	95.8	255	246	791	1470	
3	Italy	13.0	-	201	178	441	China	7.7	16	99	574	1256	
4	UK	41 [*]	54	6	94	394	UAE	13.2	147	291	480	652	
5	UAE	16.3	7	145	240	325	Ukraine	416.4	214	206	230	612	
6	Afghanistan	9.1	38	111	215	265	Germany	52.1	53	146	362	580	
7	Iran	11.4	242	139	159	217	Belarus	1 [*]	54	48	96	348	
8	Bermuda	1.6	20	63	123	151	Iran	36.4	91	143	235	319	
9	Russia	34	1029	70	135	135	Italy	7.3	7	28	103	202	
10	Ukraine	460.3	165	2435	29	118	France	16.3	76	97	183	181	

* = 1996 data, - = magnitude equals zero.

@ = Ranking of top 10 countries is based on 2013 data.

Source: Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2014), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

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Table: 8
Uzbekistan: Direction of Trade (million US\$, calendar year)

		Exports					Imports						
		1995 [¥]	2000	2005	2010	2013			1995 [¥]	2000	2005	2010	2013
Total		2717.9	2182.1	3609.8	5548.1	6198.1	Total	3029.9	2071.9	3565.2	9254.2	13966.1	
Sl. No.	Top 10 Countries[@]						Top 10 Countries[@]						
1	China	64.2	10.9	410.0	1181.1	1744.1	China	52.3	43.4	253.2	1295.9	2874.9	
2	Russia	807.9	602.0	820.0	1375.9	1203.3	Russia	906.5	301.9	946.6	1829.9	2799.3	
3	Kazakhstan	245.0	64.1	231.3	430.4	782.4	Korea	269.3	253.5	542.4	1582.5	2164.8	
4	Turkey	14.6	78.0	235.9	783.1	741.3	Kazakhstan	168.4	146.9	266.9	1208.8	1556.6	
5	Bangladesh	-	14.0	163.1	517.7	509.4	Turkey	74.3	90.9	166.2	310.9	618.9	
6	Kyrgyzstan	63.6	68.4	54.6	161.7	198.8	Germany	389.4	233.3	313.4	770.5	607.4	
7	Turkmenistan	25.9	32.1	62.6	121.8	149.8	Ukraine	151.6	125.4	165.7	251.3	387.3	
8	Iran	22.0	45.6	124.3	95.0	136.4	US	69.5	182.7	80.9	111.5	353.1	
9	Japan	99.5	71.4	113.0	157.1	90.9	Kyrgyzstan	97.8	98.3	18.8	283.7	348.8	
10	Ukraine	89.5	161.8	186.7	74.3	83.3	Italy	33.5	52.5	68.2	131.9	129.3	

* = 1996 data, - = magnitude equals zero.

@ = Ranking of top 10 countries is based on 2013 data.

Source: Compiled by the Author from Asian Development Bank (2014), Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific, [Online: Web] Accessed 10 October 2014, URL: <http://www.adb.org/data/statistics>.

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Table 3 shows that the Central Asian countries do not constitute as the top ten trade partners of China. On the other hand, China has emerged as the main trade partner of the CAS in recent years. In the region, Kazakhstan is China's main trade partner ever since independence. China's trade with the five CAS has significantly increased over the years. As shown in Table 4, China is the main export and import destinations of Kazakhstan in 2013. Kazakhstan primarily exports fuel and mining products to China, and imports manufactured products from China.⁶⁵ Table 5 highlights that Kyrgyzstan mainly imports from China. Kyrgyzstan primarily imports manufactured goods from China.⁶⁶ Also, in case of Tajikistan (Table 6), imports from China are more than exports. However, Turkmenistan's trade pattern with China is different from Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan (Table 7). Its exports to China are much higher compared to imports. Natural gas is one of the main items of export to China. In case of Uzbekistan, the trade pattern is similar to Kazakhstan. China is the main trade partner of Uzbekistan as indicated in Table 8. Within a very short time, China has strengthened its trade relations with the five countries of the region.

The vast Central Asian market is yet another attraction for China. In Central Asian markets like *Dordoi* and *Karasuu* in Kyrgyzstan, *Amindzhan*, *Shahrahe Abreshim*, *Bunyad-Shengong* and *Mostafa Artush* in Tajikistan, Chinese manufactured goods are available in large quantities.⁶⁷ Another example is the presence of network of wholesale markets in Kazakhstan selling Chinese goods to other CAS and to Russian regions bordering Central Asia.⁶⁸ Free Economic Zones established in border towns of *Chuguchak* and *Khorgos* by the treaty signed between Kazakhstan-China in 2006 have facilitated trade transactions between the two countries.⁶⁹

Conclusion

China's increasing economic presence in the region has deep implications for the region's geo-politics. Since 1991, accessing the region's rich natural resources has been an area of intense competition among the various countries involved in the region. China's economic profile in the region is growing. The opening of the two pipelines have played a crucial role in strengthening China's economic relations with the

CAS. Cooperation in the energy sector constitutes a significant aspect of China's economic engagement with the CAS. Among other areas, building energy infrastructures like pipelines have been an integral part of enhancing China-Central Asia economic cooperation. The developments in the past decade indicate that China will be a major player in the region's energy sector. Its investments in the energy sector will further consolidate its position in the region as the CAS are keen on foreign investments to develop and modernise their energy sector. In addition to cooperation in the energy sector, economic engagement in other areas is also expanding. Gradually, China has emerged as a leading trade partner of the five CAS. China's trade with the CAS include wide variety of goods. Another factor that has helped China to move closer to the CAS is its silence on issues like human right records, democracy, etc in these countries. Russia, the traditional player in the region also follows this policy. These issues have been major irritants for developing closer ties with the West.

Does the growing economic presence of China challenges Russia's position in the region? Past linkages make Russia a dominant player in the region, a position Russia would not like to lose. Despite competition from China, Russia remains an important player in the region's energy sector. Soviet time pipelines still serve as a significant outlet for the region's hydrocarbon reserves. Post-independence, as part of the CAS' multi-vector foreign policy, these countries are exploring a number of alternate routes and markets. China has emerged as a significant market for the region's hydrocarbon resources. However, the CAS continue to share deep relationship with Russia because of long economic, security and cultural linkages. Russia and China have similar economic interests in Central Asia. Competition between the two countries in Central Asia, especially in the region's energy sector will grow.

Against this background, it is important to see how the creation of Customs Union/ Eurasian Economic Union (EEU) will affect China's economic presence in the region. Russia, Kazakhstan and Belarus are the present members of the Customs Union, established in 2010. Kazakhstan, Russia and Belarus signed the Treaty establishing the EEU, which needs to be ratified by the parliaments of the three countries. It is scheduled to be functional in January 2015. Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan are likely to join the EEU in January 2015. A common tariff rate among the EEU member countries would increase the prices of several Chinese goods entering Kyrgyzstan. Presently, Kyrgyzstan has low import tariff, a position it might lose after joining the EEU. Kyrgyzstan imports cheap goods from China and re-exports these products to other Central Asian

and CIS countries. With Kyrgyzstan entering EEU, this practice would come to an end. Chinese goods entering Central Asia will become costlier after EEU starts functioning. However, there is also need for immediate and sufficient availability of substitute products to replace Chinese goods in Central Asia. It is too early to say that China would lose its economic strength in the region with the establishment of the EEU. However, if EEU emerges as an effective group, it would be a challenge that China has to address.

Despite competition, China and Russia have been cooperating in Central Asia within the framework of the SCO. Also, Russia and China are strengthening their bilateral relationship. Chinese President Xi Jinping's first official visit abroad was to Moscow in March 2013. He attended the G20 summit meeting at St Petersburg. The signing of the agreement to supply natural gas from Russia for 30 years to China in May 2014 was a significant development in the bilateral relationship. It was agreed that Russia would supply 38 bcm of gas annually at US\$ 350 per 1000 cubic metres to China from its eastern Siberian gas fields, which will begin in 2018.⁷⁰ Will this growing closeness between Russia and China also be reflected in Central Asia? Individual economic growth of Russia and China, success of the EEU and the effectiveness of the CAS' multi-vector foreign policy will determine the extent of engagement and influence of these two influential neighbours of Central Asia in the region.

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8. New Silk Road Economic Belt and China's Central Asia Policy

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New Silk Road Economic Belt is regarded as China's latest strategy toward Central Asia by many scholars and observers after it was issued on 2013. Although there are a lot of discussion about this policy, its contents still not very clear until now. And there also are a lot of questions about China's New Silk Road Economic Belt policy, this article tries to interpret some while raising questions.

The New Silk Road Economic Belt policy was raised in Kazakhstan by China's president Xi Jinping on 2013, which is the key state of Central Asia area. The region of Central Asia was considered to be the main area which China's new policy will focus on. Because of the fact that Central Asia had played a very important role in world well-known Silk Road in the history, this kind of opinions is reasonable. But after 2 years, the area which covered by The New Silk Road Economic Belt have gone far beyond Central Asia. Then the role of Central Asia in the New Silk Road Economic Belt has been discovered by many scholars and viewers.

Some of them think highly of Central Asia in the New Silk Road Economic Belt policy, which means China will put Central Asia on a special place in their policy. In other words, the region of Central Asia will be very important to China if China want to carry out its New Silk Road Economic Belt policy. There are three reasons which can make China pursue a particular role in Central Asia. The first reason is about the energy cooperation between Central Asia and China. As we know, Central Asia has become a more and more important energy supplier to China, their cooperation included energy explorations, exploitations and transportations. Both China and Central Asian states, such as Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan hope to keep this kind of energy cooperation as a stable relationship. The second reason is related with China's foreign policy structure. China's new government has made efforts to redesign its foreign policy. In the past several years, the role of

neighbor countries and area has being become more and more important in China's foreign policy. And in the eyes of many analysts and strategists, the region of Central Asia is not only the China's strategic rear, but also the China's experimental area, the success in this region is crucial. On the one hand, China could have more time and resources to deal with challenges come from the east part. On the other hand, some new policy design in Central Asia are good example for China' foreign policy and strategy, for instance, the creation and operation of Shanghai Cooperation Organization. For China, Central Asia is one of the few regions where China could transfer its economic power into foreign policy influence in a relatively easy way. The third reason is about the grassroots of international cooperation. In the past 20 years, especially in the latest decade, the economic cooperation between Central Asian states and China grew fast. For example, China has become the main trade partner of Central Asian states, and the number of China's investment in the region increased a lot. The political and foreign relations between China and Central Asian countries keep in a stable level in the past years. There are no upheaval and tumultuous changes. On the contrary, some of these countries often supported each other when faced with challenges especially when those challenges and critics come from the Western countries. There are some obstacles, however. SCO is a good platform for China and Central Asian states' cooperation. The reasons abovementioned will play a part in the development of China's New Silk Road Economic Belt policy. They are the main support to China's foreign policy design in the area of Central Asia. More specifically, the programs of New Silk Road Economic Belt policy will be proposed based on these main cooperation areas.

Although China's New Silk Road Economic Belt has attracted numerous of attentions of scholars and officials, there are four fundamental questions still not be answered.

The first is local government's role. Many analysis regard the New Silk Road Economic Belt is China's latest strategy toward Central Asia and some other areas, but at the beginning of this policy designing, some local governments played a very important role, especially Chongqing. Because of the well-known international railroad from Chongqing to Germany is crucial to its economy development. Chongqing government tried hard to solve the transport cost problem. It lobbied China's central government to give some help. Its idea got lots of support from Xinjiang,

Gansu and so on. After President Xi stated this policy, these local governments became much more energetic, but according to China's foreign policy design process, there are few rooms left to the local government. If China's Central government wants to put the New Silk Road Economic Belt to the strategic place, local government's flexibility could be narrowed. So how to get a balance between Central government's strategic design and local government's convenience will be a big problem for the progress of New Silk Road Economic Belt policy in the future.

The second is the programs it concluding. However, there are few specific programs have been issued in the structure of New Silk Road Economic Belt. Most of the discussions covered the importance and ideas. Some local governments and scholars have proposed many plan and opinions, but no one have been accepted by the Central government. There is an obvious phenomenon, some local governments and scholars considered the New Silk Road Economic Belt will be an opportunity for their province or China's economic, they seems like it could cover everything. But as we know, the New Silk Road Economic Belt will not be a basket which could contain any kind of policy. Although the idea of New Silk Road Economic Belt is popular, it still on the stage of discussion, there are no specific programs will be a tough nut to crack.

The third is the difference between China's old Central Asia policy and the New Silk Road Economic Belt policy. For Central Asia, the New Silk Road Economic Belt will be the new stage of China's policy toward this area. In the past decades, China pursued its interests though bilateral and multilateral ways in Central Asia, and have been the economic great power in the region. Its economic cooperation has been established in many levels in this region, especially in the energy and trade area. The New Silk Road Economic Belt policy should have some new features. But it will be very difficult if China want to make some progress in the energy or trade field, because there is lack of good opportunity in the foreseeable future. The New Silk Road Economic Belt is China's new policy design, not the common opportunity for each part. As some discussion showed, many analysts consider this policy is one kind of China's expansion, not a opportunity.

The fourth is the border of New Silk Road Economic Belt. This problem includes two levels. In the domestic level, more and more local

governments are interested in the New Silk Road Economic Belt, they think this policy will get central government's financial or policy support, then they issued numbers of ideas in order to board the new policy. In the international level, the New Silk Road Economic Belt policy is not China's Marshall Plan. Seem like the internal level, some countries think this new silk road policy would be China's aiding strategy. Although the policy meaning is not very clear, many countries have expressed their enthusiasm. If we review China's foreign policy in recently years, we can imagine that the neighbor countries will be the focus of China's new Silk Road economic belt policy. This will make some countries feel disappointed. And there is the other key factor which will hold the New Silk Road Economic Belt policy back from "Marshall Plan". China New Silk Road Economic Belt policy is not a pure foreign policy, in my opinion, the domestic development is this policy's main object. When we pay more attention to the local government plan, we can get this conclusion. Their plans are focus on how to develop their own economy, not about foreign affairs.

However, the basic consensus of China's New Silk Road Economic Belt discussion toward Central Asia is energy and infrastructure will be the main field, and they will attract most of the investment. But Central Asia is one of the crucial parts of the New Silk Road Belt policy, its role in the history will be continue, Central Asia will be the transit station of the new great silk road. China should create some regional or international regimes to support its New Silk Road Economic Belt policy. However, many new international organizations such as Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank will play key role in the progress of the New Silk Road Economic Belt policy.

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**9. The impact of the Middle East revolutions
on the Communist party in China**

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Abstract

The 2011 revolutions in the Middle East and Northern Africa (**MENA**) led to considerable hope for some people that China would experience a similar political uprising, as well as considerable anxiety for the ruling regime. The government's immediate response was to downplay the risk of a similar event occurring in China by distinguishing between China and MENA, while at the same time cracking down on activists and other potential sources of instability including attempts to organize popular revolutionary protests in China. Although the government has so far managed to avoid a similar uprising, neither response has been entirely successful. Despite a number of significant differences between China and MENA countries, there are enough commonalities to justify concerns about political instability. Moreover, relying on repression alone is not a long-term solution to the justified demands of Chinese citizens for political reforms and social justice. Whether China will ultimately be able to avoid the fate of authoritarian regimes in MENA countries will turn on its ability to overcome a series of structural challenges while preventing sudden and unpredictable events, like those that gave rise to the Arab revolutions, from spinning out of control.

On the other side, while China's economic and social reforms have gained much attention internationally, the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) regime's efforts at political structural reform initiated by "Deng Xiaoping" have been widely ignored by China scholars so far. Political reforms that do not aim at abolishing one-party rule to the benefit of some form of Western liberal (multi-party) democracy are not taken seriously by most observers of China's modernization process. This article hypothesizes that these reforms do actually affect regime legitimacy in a positive way and should therefore be carefully analyzed in order to explain the "authoritarian resilience" of Communist one-party rule. It is argued that political reform in its limited sense of enhancing cadre efficiency and accountability (instead of empowering the demo's vis-à-vis the state) may, indeed, help to effectively prolong one-party rule in contemporary China

Keywords:

China- North Africa and the Middle East- Chinese Communist Party (**CCP**)- Legitimacy- Revolution- repression- Political Reforms- Arab Spring revolutions.

- Introduction: A legitimacy crisis?

Following the breakdown of autocracies in Tunisia, Egypt, and Libya in early 2011, the international community turned its attention to China, the largest single-party-rule-state in the world. Analysts and commentators have debated the likelihood of a similar round of popular protests and demonstrations in China ¹ At the 48th Munich Conference on Security Policy, U.S. Senator "**John McCain**" warned the Arab Spring would spread to China, and added: "I have said on many occasions and I will say again the Arab Spring is coming to China as well", said McCain ². Will the Arab Spring ignite similar uprisings in China? Could such uprisings shake the foundations of the Communist Party rule in China?

Many analysts and commentators have questioned the long-term viability of China's single-party-rule political system. There will be some changes in the long term; however, the Chinese way of democratization will not follow the western model. The Chinese government has been revising its ruling ideology to allow necessary changes. It slowly directs China to move towards a more democratic society. Other party members and non-party members gradually raise their voices in important national meetings. They participate in more decision-making processes than ever before. Even China's former Premier "**Wen Jiabao**" called for political reform of the leadership system of the Chinese Communist Party and the Chinese government, although he did not precisely state what political reforms he hoped to see³.

Prediction for a long-term change is non-communist party members or non-party members will eventually become part of the decision-making committee. However, this may take years or even decades. Another prediction is this significant change will be made without uprisings or revolutions considering the facts that the "**CCP**" has been trying to adapt

itself to a changing world, and it has been willing to promote China's development in a more democratic way.

It is in this context that this paper examines the Chinese Communist Party's (**CCP**) fears of the Arab Spring, and provides a conclusion on whether such fears are founded and if a similar uprising in China is indeed in the near future.

I- Chinese Communist Party (CCP) and the reforms:

Similar to the factors underlying the Arab Spring, social drivers of popular discontent in China are many: corruption, unemployment, growing socioeconomic inequality, and rising prices, among others. These factors have created accumulated tensions in China, fueling a growing problem of social instability⁴. **The three fundamental questions that emerge are:**

1. What have been the major ideological trends since 1978 and why?
2. How have these ideological trends influenced China's economic reforms and why?
3. What are the conclusions to be arrived at on the role of ideology in economic reforms?

In Chinese Communist vocabulary, "**theoretical work**" can be inferred to be "**ideological work**", and theory is more closely identified with practice than with reality. According to a standard Chinese definition, a theory is a system of concepts and principles, or a systematic rational knowledge, a scientific theory that is established on the basis of social practice and has been proved and verified by social practice, and is a correct reflection of the essence and laws of objective things⁵.

In the Chinese context, a theory is not much different from a doctrine, an ideology or a set of propositions serving as a guiding principle for action. Theories without immediate relevance to policy-making or implementation are considered inconsequential⁶.

China has been experiencing a dynamic process of economic reform, political and social modernization for more than 25 years now. For those who follow the country's transformation as attentively as China scholars do, this process is primarily associated with China's market transformation. The country seems to confirm at least one part of

Fukuyama's "end of history", i.e. the eventual rise of market economies all over the world after the end of the Cold War and the downfall of Soviet socialism⁷. Still, China's economic trajectory since the beginning of the re-form era in the late 1970s, and especially its reform path since the early 1990s, has been profoundly different from developments in Central Europe and in the post-Soviet republics of Central Asia, including Russia. **Three specific features of the Chinese market transformation immediately come to mind as the follow**⁸:

1. The Communist Party survived the critical period after 1989 and has been revitalized since then instead of tumbling into decay. Unlike so many other post-Communist regimes, its elites have not been forced from power, on the contrary, it seems they have been able to consolidate their rule over the last decade⁹.
2. China's market reforms have fared much better than those undertaken in Central Europe and Russia in terms of the absolute economic growth they have unleashed. The abrupt collapse of political institutions and the sudden demise of the entire system of economic regulation and property rights were markers of the development in the former Soviet bloc, causing economic damage from which these countries – especially Russia – would suffer for years to come¹⁰. China, in contrast, engaged in much more gradual economic reform while clinging to its political framework of Communist one-party rule.
3. The privatization of state assets has been much slower and more cautious in China than elsewhere in the post-Communist world, where most of the state assets were transferred to private markets in the first years of the transition. Most strikingly, China's private sector has not risen through the transfer of state assets to private owners, but mainly by way of private entrepreneurship starting out-side the state sector and through foreign investment. Consequently, although being quite large already and contributing to some 55-60 per cent of GDP, China's private sector clearly lags behind most post-Communist economies¹¹.

As a matter of fact, one is tempted to call China's reform path unique. Here is a Communist leadership that is successfully controlling the speed and scope of market reform implementation, with Party elites turning into a new capitalist oligarchy at a much lower rate than elsewhere, a leadership that maintains political supremacy during this process; and a leadership that seems to maintain a critical level of stability and presumably generate sufficient regime legitimacy at the same time, apparently by good economic performance,

nationalistic zeal and a good deal of tolerance with respect to political decentralization and local voice ¹².

For these observers, three scenarios are imaginable for China in the near future. The "**apocalyptic**" variant predicts that the current degrees of social and political instability will lead to intra-Party friction and ultimate regime collapse. The "**optimistic**" variant speculates on a gradual transition to a democratic system along the model set out by South Korea and Taiwan. Some scholars add a third variant often branded "**muddling through**", i.e. the perpetuation of the current way of problem-solving which is reactive in nature and limited to the objective of preserving Communist one-party rule. However, in this scenario the demise of Communist rule is only slowed down; it cannot be rescued from eventual collapse or, in the best case, self-initiated democratic transformation. All in all, system change is regarded as being inevitable in China, be it revolutionary or reformist in nature.³ Even if the current regime may not be considered instable yet, but in a state of "**stable unrest that may continue for some time**"¹³. in the West it certainly counts as deeply delegitimised in the eyes of most of the people it claims to represent. With stability precarious at best, it is assumed, the Communist regime faces a deep-going crisis of legitimacy that will ultimately lead to democratization ¹⁴.

II- Middle East revolutions and the raising of opposition against the legitimacy Chinese Communist Party (CCP):

Chinese authorities including the Communist party (**CCP**) have done what they can to block news of Egyptian people-power from spreading to China. Reports about Egypt in China's state-run media have been brief and vacuous. On February 6, at the height of the protests, the People's Daily informed readers that "the Egyptian government is continuing to carry out its various measures to support restoration of social order". But on the Chinese Internet, which despite vigorous policing is hard to stifle, "**Mubarak**" has received a drubbing: "**autocrat**", "**corrupt thug**", and so on. Thus, while Chinese censors have declared the word Mubarak (along with "**Egypt**" and others) to be "**sensitive**" and have set up filters to delete any message that contains it, Chinese Webusers, in their usual cat-and-mouse game, have invented witty substitutes. These include "**Deng Xiaoping**" and "**Hu Jintao**" which, by playing on the names of China's own autocrats, get around the censors and up the ante at the same time ¹⁵.

The Egyptian uprising is an awkward fact for China's rulers because it undermines one of their favorite arguments. They have long claimed that China has "**special characteristics**" (meaning that its people prefer authoritarianism, at least for now) and that demands in China for democracy and human rights are merely results of the subversive tactics of "anti-China" forces based in Western countries. But if that theory is true, then one needs to explain why millions of Egyptian people were opposing Mubarak, who was a US client. Plainly something deeper was motivating them ¹⁶.

The example of Tunisia raises a related question, equally awkward. For China's rulers, "**Zine El Abidine Ben Ali**", the ousted dictator, would have been seen as following their own approach the so-called "**Chinese model**" of economic growth combined with political repression and having much success with it, or so it was assumed for many years. But the Tunisian people took to the streets to overthrow him. Did the people want something more than the Chinese model? How could that be?

Here, we can indicate some facts about how could the Arab Spring and Middle East revolutions affected on China's domestically, as follow:

(1) In recent years, China's own activists have identified freedom, democracy, human rights and human dignity as "**universal values**". This is one of the core ideas in "**Charter 08**", the reform document the government has tried so hard to suppress. China's rulers have countered by claiming that so-called universal values are merely "**tactics peddled by the West**". This confrontation has spawned a "**universal values debate**" in Chinese intellectual circles, where the government's side, benefiting from its control of the media, has until recently been holding its own. But when young people in Tunisia and Egypt (**of all places!**) speak up for universal values, the claim that these values are parochial and imposed by the US and its western allies are undermined¹⁷).

(2) The uprisings in Tunisia and Egypt could not have happened without "**Facebook**" and "**Twitter**". Young people used these social media to communicate and to organize, and the repressive apparatus of their governments could not keep pace. Facebook has yet to enter China in a major way, but Twitter has already made a huge difference. The direct exchanges that "**Wang Lixiong**" has arranged between the Dalai Lama and thousands of Chinese citizens, for example, have all been done by Twitter, and Twitter is the preferred medium for personal exchanges among people who want to stay one step ahead of the Internet police.

(3) But the deftness of technology is only one reason why "**Liu Xiaobo**", China's Nobel Peace laureate, has called the Internet "**God's gift to China**". Even more important for Chinese wangmin, or "**Web-citizens**", has been the psychological liberation made possible by online anonymity. Throughout the Communist period, Chinese media censorship has been based largely on self-censorship induced by fear. But this mechanism works only when the fear-inducing authority knows who you are. The multifarious and very frank expression that can be found on the Chinese Internet today is done almost entirely under pseudonyms. The authorities have banned the use of pseudonyms, but when 400 million people use them anyway, **what can they do?**

(4) In bearing witness to the popular movements taking hold in Cairo, Tunis, Bahrain, and elsewhere in recent weeks, social media and the Internet have broadened the vision even of Chinese democracy activists themselves, including the drafters of "**Charter 08**". In talks with some of them in recent days, I have learned that they, too, were a bit surprised to see democracy sprouting in North Africa¹⁸.

At first they didn't quite know what to make of it. Until now, they have identified mostly with Eastern European dissidents of the past such as Adam Michnik and Vaclav Havel (**whose Czech Charter 77 provided the inspiration for China's Charter 08**).

They see these Europeans as fighting against similar antagonists to their "**own Communist dictatorships**" and having shared goals as: democracy and human rights of a kind that someone like Havel articulates so well.

In contrast, many Chinese, even to some extent democracy activists, have been taught that Africans are "**backward**", and since the US-led "**war on terror**", activists have sometimes been too ready to give credence to negative American portrayals of the Muslim world. As they think beyond these barriers, however, these activists have begun to embrace the North African democrats as comrades. One of them told me, "Even if they choose something we would not choose" such as an Islamic state "if they do it democratically, we must defend their choice". None of the Chinese activists felt that it would be practical to call for Egypt-type street protests at this point ¹⁹.

(5) The increasing of the protester in Cairo holds a sign written in Chinese, reading "**The Egyptian people demand that President Mubarak step down**", and How Egyptians might feel about China, whether in regard to the government in Beijing or the people who have endorsed "**Charter 08**", is hard to say. But it is certainly interesting that a few of the protesters' signs in Tahrir Square "**Mubarak Go!**" and "The Egyptian People Demand Mubarak Resign" were written in Chinese ²⁰.

Can the authoritarian regimes of the world stop the march of Internet democracy? For five days at the height of the protests, Mubarak's people were able to shut down the Internet and, for a time, cell phone networks as well. This was a tactic Chinese authorities had already tried out in the western region of "**Xinjiang**", after disturbances there in July 2009, it affected a near-total shut down of 312 days. Last year "**Xiao Qiang**", a leading expert on the Chinese Internet, was debating a man of high position in China's power elite about the Internet's "**threat to stability**". As if playing a trump card, the man said at one point, "If we have to, we

can always pull the plug on the whole thing". "Xiao" says this made him feel a sudden chill ²¹.

But could China's authorities really do such a thing? They spend probably tens of billions of Yuan annually to control the Internet, official Chinese sources have revealed that the government spends over 500 billion Yuan (**\$76 billion**) a year on domestic "**stability maintenance**". Yet a complete shut down might still be technically difficult. And even if it were feasible, so many people in China now depend on the Internet not just for political commentary but also for information, commerce, recreation, and communication that "**pulling the plug**" would be truly cataclysmic, and hardly conducive to "**stability**"²².

III- The Stability of (CCP) in China amid Jasmine Revolutions:

Many observers both inside and outside China have come to perceive the country's political system as remarkably resilient. Sustained economic growth, greater political responsiveness, and considerable public satisfaction with the status quo have seemingly created a high degree of political stability. This widely shared assessment of Chinese politics was reflected in comparing the situation in China with the "**jasmine revolutions**" in the Middle East: "**Why It Won't Happen in China?**"

And yet, there is reason to believe that China's own leaders are less confident about their country's stability than these foreign observers. Recent crackdowns on political activists suggest to some a growing nervousness about the future ²³.

The questions rise here, Are Chinese leaders worrying needlessly? Or do they accurately perceive that their country's political system may be subject to increasing strain?

* **First**, Perhaps the most important cause for concern is the increasing level of inflation in China, the result of the flood of foreign capital into the country, China's chronic foreign trade surpluses, growing labor shortages, and rising global prices for food, energy, and raw materials. If not brought under control, inflation has the potential to

create a high degree of popular dissatisfaction. Over the last 20-odd years, China has been beset by numerous public protests over issues ranging from environmental pollution to contaminated food. But almost all of those grievances have been localized and the number of people affected by them has been limited. In contrast, inflation will affect virtually everyone in China, and is already leading to grumbling over rising energy costs and strikes for higher wages²⁴.

* **Second**, China is on the verge of a political succession, with a new generation of leaders to be elected at the Eighteenth Party Congress in 2012. Although the succession procedures are now highly institutionalized and the policy differences within the leadership are far less than they were in the 1980s, there remains considerable uncertainty about the composition of the new leadership and how it will address the country's problems. Moreover, one characteristic pattern of Chinese political life historically has been that dissenters may be emboldened to speak out and act up if they perceive there to be differences among the top leadership.

* **Third**, whatever foreign observers may say, Chinese leaders do appear to be worried about the "**jasmine revolutions**" in the Middle East and the "**color revolutions**" that have occurred elsewhere in the world. Theirs is not simply a generalized fear of contagion, but a more specific perception that the same communication technologies that sparked the protests in the Middle East could have an impact on China as well. Recent reports indicate that Chinese activists working both inside and outside the country have begun to create networks that cross local and provincial boundaries, creating a virtual version, however embryonic, of the independent nationwide political organizations that Chinese leaders have long tried to prevent²⁵.

* **Finally**, there is the widespread perception that political liberalization in China has stalled. Chinese leaders have once again made clear that pluralistic democracy is not on the agenda, and the pace of more limited types of political reform appears to be controversial. This perception can itself become a further cause of grievance and instability²⁶.

All of these developments increasing inflation, apparent differences within the political elite, revolutionary protest in the Middle East, and the continuing revolution in communication technologies – make it easy to

see why Chinese leaders might be concerned about their country's stability, and why they are imposing stricter controls on political expression.

China's political system remains resilient, and there is still considerable popular satisfaction with the country's achievements. But the odds are starting to shift in ways that suggest that the resilience of that system may be increasingly tested²⁷.

IV- The challenges faced Chinese Communist party (CCP) after the

Middle East Revolutions:

Chinese authorities have done what they can to stop news and worse, from their point of view, any influence of Tunisian and Egyptian people power from spreading to China. They have been worrying especially about what social media like "**Twitter**" and "**Facebook**" can do to political power in the Internet age. On the morning of February 19, Chinese President "**Hu Jintao**" delivered a major speech to an audience of provincial governors and central government ministers on maintaining social stability. After a review of the glorious achievements of the Communist Party of China and the immutable correctness of Party ideology, Hu made three main points. He did not directly mention the Middle East or any resonances that the protests there have had in China, but said: one, we need to greatly strengthen control of information on the Internet, two, we need to regulate the "**virtual society**" that it has given rise to, and three, we need to guide public opinion in this new virtual society in "**healthy directions**"²⁸.

As if to make Hu's worst nightmare come true, on that same day, February 19, someone put an anonymous post on the Internet calling for a "**Jasmine Revolution**" in China. The police response was immediate. Within hours, Chinese democracy advocates in several cities, including prominent rights lawyers and signers of the democracy manifesto called Charter 08, were detained, interrogated, or brought to police stations for "**invitations to tea**" of the kind that a person is not allowed to refuse²⁹.

The Jasmine appeal had appeared on a news website called boxun, "**rich information**", that is edited in the US by Chinese exiles and Internet police were quick to shut the site down in China. But the appeal had already got out on the Chinese Internet and spread quickly through Twitter, microblogs, and other social media. Soon activists had planned demonstrations in at least thirteen major cities. Initial gatherings, in Beijing and Shanghai on February 20, were broken up by police, but meetings took place in other cities³⁰.

The anti-authoritarian protests in North Africa, from their beginnings, had received only brief and vacuous reports in the state-run Chinese media. On February 6, at the height of the protests, the People's Daily informed readers that "the Egyptian government is continuing to carry out its various measures to support restoration of social order". But on the Chinese Internet, which despite vigorous policing is hard to stifle, "**Hosni Mubarak**" received a drubbing: "**autocrat**", "**corrupt thug**", and so on. When Chinese censors declared the word "**Mubarak**" (along with "Egypt" and now "Jasmine") to be "**sensitive**" and set up filters to delete any message that contains it, Chinese Web users, in their usual cat-and-mouse game, began inventing witty substitutes. These included "**Mu Xiaoping**" and "**Mu Jintao**" which, by playing on the names of China's own autocrats, get around the censors and up the ante at the same time. They ridiculed Mubarak for claiming³¹.

The Arab Spring, which broke out when a young Tunisian street vendor immolated himself after being harassed by a municipal official, has been shaking the region. It has also marked the end of three dictators while also undermining the authority and legitimacy of various others. The political success of the Tunisian revolution set a dangerous precedent for authoritarian regimes in MENA countries, with Egypt following a similar path.

In the wake of the successful uprisings in Tunisia and Egypt, the risk of the protest becoming contagious became increasingly real. A series of demonstrations took place in Algeria, Bahrain, Iran, Jordan, Syria, and Yemen, while Libya was engulfed in a violent spiral of protests and harsh military repression that left the country with thousands dead and on the brink of civil war. In Syria, residents of a small southern city took to the streets to protest the torture of students who had put up anti-government graffiti. The government responded with heavy-handed force, and demonstrations quickly spread across much of the country. As the crackdown dragged on, thousands of soldiers defected and began launching attacks against the government, bringing the country to civil war³².

Many governments tried to preempt the protests by adopting limited reforms: In Algeria, the authorities promised to lift the state of emergency that has been in place for almost 20 years; in Yemen, President "**Ali Abdallah Salih**" announced that he would not run for a further term in

the next presidential elections in 2013, and in Saudi Arabia, King "Abdallah bin Abd al-Aziz" unveiled a \$37 billion package of pay raises, unemployment benefits, and other social measures. Nevertheless, at the end of 2011, the risk of contagion by civil unrest throughout the "MENA" region was still high.³³

V- The new strategy of the Chinese Communist party (CCP) to (MENA) Revolutions:

The revolutions of the Middle East should now make China think deeply about what strategies can be pushed in a given country to promote reforms without a violent clash or uprising. Also, the jasmine revolutions will leave a lasting legacy in the Middle East. These countries will be in a state of chaos for many years to come. Libya or Syria could be stuck in some form of civil war for a decade. Egypt could lumber on with its dire economic problems and its crippled social and political structures for decades. In this situation, America, dependent on imports of Middle Eastern oil and gas, would once upon a time have been extremely concerned³⁴.

Now, with the prospect of becoming energy independent through shale gas over the next four or five years, the chaos of the Middle East becomes a toxic legacy, left to the Chinese, who are growing more dependent on Middle Eastern energy imports. Moreover, with the arrival of shale gas and oil from America, the price of extracting oil and gas from Russia could become dangerously high relative to exports from the Middle East, putting Russia in a bind. If the situation is peaceful in the Middle East, Russian oil may be too expensive to be extracted and exported. Therefore Moscow has an interest in keeping the situation in the Middle East tense, so overall Middle Eastern extraction costs will be high, thus making oil and gas from Russia competitive.³⁵

This may all be in the interest of America, since it puts Russian and Chinese interests at odds with one another. But curiously, it could also help bring about a convergence of European and Chinese interests. Europe is also dependent on Middle Eastern oil imports, and it has an interest in keeping prices down. Therefore, objectively, there could be a convergence of policies in China and the European Union to make the Middle East more stable, something that could also contain their mutual neighbor - Russia.

In this situation, which could happen by the time America chooses its next president, what will America do? As we have seen, the strategy of

pivoting to Asia is failing, more than a decade of Bush/ Obama policy toward the Middle East is also falling apart, and the discovery of shale oil and gas could push America to more isolationist policies. But it is impossible to think that after eight decades of militant American intervention in the world, Washington will decide simply to withdraw³⁶.

Yet, now more than ever, America should think of what it wants in the world besides being the confused spectator of the Far East's rise. So far, China's cautious approach in its own policies and toward the Middle East, for half a century the battleground of new ideas and foreign policy, has proved more sensible. But this is little consolation for the world, as America is and will be the global leader for many decades to come.

And a confused global leader is extremely dangerous for the leader and everybody else. For China the failure of the leader and the model to follow in development are things that bear little happiness. Without America success, China is lonelier, and is without a model to follow, something very risky for a country still in the middle of time of passage.

Generally, Chinese Communist party (**CCP**) foreign policy in the Middle East after the Arab Spring could be characterized by two main features, **as follow**:

- (1) The first characteristic of China's Middle East policy is that it is pragmatic and realistic.
- (2) The second prominent characteristic of China's Middle East policy is its constancy. Since the end of the Cold War, Chinese foreign policy in the Middle East has been primarily driven by the search for energy security and the desire to increase its overseas markets and investment opportunities. The core of Chinese policy is to maintain a stable international environment to facilitate continued reform and development at home. Consequently, Chinese policy in the "**MENA**" region seeks to advance its economic or energy relations, hence it advocates dealing with conflicts such as the Arab Spring events in a mode of cooperation, negotiation, and conflict management³⁷.

China has maintained its traditional opposition to military intervention and what it sees as U.S. policy in the region in part because of its own history. China does not believe that economic sanctions are an efficacious policy tool, but instead are a blunt instrument that rarely works to achieve the stated objectives. The Chinese clearly have their own reasons for being very sensitive about intervention and sanctions and are a bit reluctant to support their implementation, even when they are aimed at authoritarian regimes in the MENA region³⁸.

Yet the Arab Spring events are making it increasingly difficult for Beijing to maintain this policy. The Middle East has always been a key strategic focus for the United States, Europe, and Russia, while for China, the region is not as important as its neighbors in the Asian Pacific region and other regions. Consequently, China's approach to the Arab Spring is shaped by its relations with the United States, Europe, and Russia. Beijing recognizes that a U.S. presence in the Middle East is considered a strategic interest by Washington, that a U.S. diplomatic and military presence will persist for decades, and that U.S. policy is critical to regional stability³⁹. Thus, it seeks to avoid actions that will place it in direct confrontation with the United States. At the same time, Beijing wants to build and maintain political relationships with both the new and the old regimes in MENA countries, in order to ensure access to resources and markets.

Yet the recent developments in the "**MENA**" region have challenged China's policy, since Beijing's economic interests constitute the most dominant factor in determining its foreign policy toward the region, whose core value is stability in order to ensure uninterrupted access to natural resources. Since the early 2000s, the Chinese have built far closer ties to many of the leading Middle Eastern states, mainly in order to meet China's growing energy needs, but also to achieve Beijing's long-term geopolitical ambitions. China also has begun slowly to insert itself into the politics of the region, whether by appointing its own special envoy to the region or contributing to anti-piracy patrols in the waters between Yemen and Somalia⁴⁰. Nonetheless, Beijing does not yet seem ready to play a larger role in the political turmoil going on in MENA countries. Instead, China has instinctively shied away from intervention throughout the political unrest there.

- Conclusion

China views the revolutions and revolts in "MENA" countries as a threat to stability, but not as new grounds for changing its policy. Furthermore, it has nothing approaching the military capability that the United States can boast to help ensure the security of any regional allies. That is why China's reaction to the revolutions indicates a lack of willingness to shape the political situation by adopting a reactive policy. Beijing's key concerns in the MENA region are still commercial, not political.

From the beginning of the Arab Spring, China has persisted in its tendency to follow a wait-and-see policy. Beijing opts for maintaining a distance from active participation in the reorganization of the Middle East. The reason for such a passive policy could be summed up as an inflexible foreign policy that avoids taking unnecessary risks. China will try to get its share of the Arab markets and continue to pursue economic agreements and business contracts, rather than playing a zero-sum game at the expense of direct confrontation with the United States.

China is not likely on the verge of breaking up due to reasons rooted in Chinese culture and the Chinese government's willingness and efforts to adapt itself to a changing world. The Arab Spring offers a warning to the Chinese authorities. However, for a more sustainable and democratic future, the Chinese government must implement political reforms, making significant efforts to fight corruption, to create more job opportunities, and to reduce socioeconomic inequality and inflation.

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10. Arab States Stances towards the unrest in Xinjiang Province

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Abstract

The prevailing atmosphere of tension regarding the Xinjiang province, which is inhabited by the Uyghurs minority, in light of the events that the region witnessed –such as acts of violence- has raised varied opinions. This paper will study, First: A historical overview of the problem of the Uyghurs, Second: Arab formal Stance and the informal trends towards the problem, Third: The steps that China must follow/undertake to concern the problem of Uyghurs and maintain good Arab-Chinese relations. The study concluded that the official Arab states stances were not affected by that issue, because of its deep economic relations with china and Violence by some Uyghurs.

Key Words: Uyghur Muslim – Xinjiang- Arab-Chinese relations- Terrorism

China is full of contradictions despite the co-existence of Muslims nationalism "Hui" with other nationalities and become high-value partners in the community, but recent years have seen the escalation of tension and unrest in the Xinjiang province of China, which is inhabited by Uighur. The Uyghur is a nationalist from the Centre of Asia speaks a Turkish language and embraces Islam religion mostly in the province of Xinjiang, which was called Eastern Turkestan, and the estimated number of Uyghur roughly estimated 8.5 million¹ people. Uyghur has enriched Chinese cultural heritage in a number of publications books, music, and the arts perhaps most notably acrobatics that excelled in Chinese.

Research problem:

Prevailing atmosphere of tension on the Xinjiang Which is inhabited by minority Uighur, in light of the events region witnessed acts of violence, varied opinions, about the tensions in the province of Xinjiang, where Chinese government considers that Islamic groups in the region promotes the idea of separatism and Contact the foreign elements linked to Al-Qaeda and the Islamic State in the region, while residents complain from restricting religious freedoms , erasing their cultural heritage ,changing demographics of the region by the nationalist "Han" and cite the decision of the Chinese government to prevent young people from prolonging their beards , prevent girls from wearing veils , prevent them from doing fast, and the Arabic reactions varied about this escalation between official Stances , which mostly ignored talking about the issue and popular trends, which denied the Chinese practices in this context, the study seeks to determine the cause of Arab Stances of Muslims in the province Xinjiang and explains it.

The paper seeks to answer the following questions:

What the causes that led to the unrest in Xinjiang province?
What is the size of the human and material losses result from the unrest in the region?
How did the Arab reactions deal with the events?
Is it possible that the Uyghur's problem may have negative effects on Arab-Chinese relations?
What are the motivations of the Arab reactions?
What are the steps that China must follow to avoid criticism about Arab Muslim minority?

Methodology:

The study is based on a secondary analysis of the literature available through the reading and analysis of research studies that address the topic, putting in our consideration the diversity of sources. It entails addressing the following:

First: A historical overview of the problem of the Uyghur
Second: Arab formal Stances and informal trends toward the problem.
Third: The steps that China must follow to concern the problem of Uyghur and keep Arab-Chinese relations. And it is as follows:

First: A historical overview of the problem of Uyghur

The Uyghur are a Turkish Central Asian people, now living primarily in the western Chinese province of the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region (which many people of Uighur prefer to call Eastern Turkestan).²Originally a group of hill tribes from the Altai Mountains, the Uyghurs have their own distinctive culture and a Turkish language. Scientists say that genetically, Uyghurs are an a mixture of Caucasian and East Asian blood. They say this is the reason for many retained light-colored skin and hair. In terms of religion, they are primarily Sunni Muslims.

The relationship between the Uyghurs and the Chinese represents character of the hit-and-run, where they managed to establish the State of Uyghurs from Eastern Turkistan, which has remained steadfast for nearly ten centuries before collapsing in front of the Chinese invasion in 1759 and then in 1876, before a final cause of communism in China in 1950. Over this period, the Uyghurs several revolutions succeeded in some cases in the establishment of an independent state along the lines

of the revolutions of 1933 and 1944 but soon crumbled in front of the Chinese who subjected the region at the end of their control. After a period of independence in the 1940s as Eastern Turkestan, the Uyghur republic's leadership agreed to form a confederation with the new Chinese communist state. But it was not long before Beijing maneuvered the republic into becoming the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region within China³.

The ancient Silk Road trade route cut through what is today the Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region, luring Muslim traders from a far. Descendants of Arab and Persian merchants travelled here in the 7th century and many settled, planting the roots of Islam in the heart of China. About half the country's 20 million Muslims are from the Hui ethnic group. Muslims were persecuted in Ningxia during Mao Zedong's Cultural Revolution in the 1960s and '70s, but today Islam flourishes. More than 400 mosques ornament the region, and Islamic schools have graduated some 7,000 imams - or Islamic clergy known locally as a hongts.

It is ranked 19th in terms of the space between the countries of the world, located Turkestan Central Asia, bordered by Mongolia from the northern-east, China to the east, and Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan to the north and west, Tibet and Kashmir, India and Pakistan from south. Many venerable scientists and scholars who enriched civilization, humanity in the various forms of science and knowledge, and made the golden age of Islamic, like al-Khwarizmi and al-Farabi, al-Tirmidhi and others from Eastern Turkestan.⁴

While descent Muslim Uyghurs of Turkish in the far west face harsh religious restrictions and repression, the Hui have been enjoyed much more political and religious freedom because of their friendly historical relations with the ethnic majority Han, that is the difference. While Hui Muslims enjoy freedom to practice their rituals, Muslim Uyghurs face strict government repression in far-western while the Hui have happily assimilated with the majority Han, the Uyghurs have not.

Eastern Turkestan land contains more than 8 billion tons of oil reserves, and it produces 5 million tons per year. Land reserves of coal Turkestan half of China's reserves of coal and high-calorie too, as well as fertile soil and agricultural land and water possibilities. Extracted from the land of Turkestan about 118 kinds of minerals out of the 148 species produced by the whole of China.⁵

Reasons of the problem:

Part of the problem is language differences. While the Hui and Han both speak Mandarin, the Uyghurs speak their own Turkish dialect and write in Arabic script. The Uyghurs' strong desire for autonomy, demands for separation or autonomy are seen in Beijing as a threat to the continuous viability of the Chinese state."

The government's policy of offering incentives for Han Chinese to migrate west

The government routinely blocks Uyghurs from practicing Islam. Because of perceived national security-related concerns, the PRC government monitors and imposes restrictions upon Uyghur society more stringently than it does most other religious and ethnic groups, focusing on Uyghur religious leaders and practices. Such restrictions include those related to the training and duties of imams, Uyghur and Arabic language, literature, and education, public access to mosques, the celebration of Ramadan,

contacts with foreigners, travel abroad, and the *hajj*. Uyghur children and youth (under 18) are forbidden from entering mosques and government workers are not allowed to practice Islam⁶.

The political reality of southern Xinjiang is that Uyghurs don't see themselves as Chinese.

The spread of militancy and religious thought of the terrorist organizations such as al Qaeda and the Taliban and ISIS.⁷

Forms of unrest in the region

Since the 1950s, separatist organizations have actively worked toward declaring independence for the Uyghur people. The Chinese government has fought back, declaring them outlaws and terrorists. Most Uyghurs support peaceful Uyghur nationalism and independence from China, without participating in violent separatist clashes.⁸ Many Uyghurs complain that they have not benefited from the region's economic development, finding it harder to access benefits such as government grants or bank loans⁹.

In 2008, PRC authorities claimed to have broken up two terrorist cells that allegedly had plotted to bomb hotels during the Beijing Olympics¹⁰. In July 2009 riots erupted in Xinjiang's. The PRC government has often conflated the religious and cultural practices of Uyghurs in Xinjiang with subversive activities or the "three evils of religious extremism, separatism, and terrorism". It claims that the Eastern Turkestan Islamic Movement (ETIM), a Uyghur organization that advocates the creation of an independent Uyghur Islamic state, was responsible for terrorist attacks in China and has ties to Al Qaeda. In 2011, Xinjiang courts tried 414 cases of endangering state security, up 10% over the previous year.

Minors under the age of 18 are forbidden from participating in Islamic practices, and thousands are detained every year for "illegal religious activity". And it is strictly prohibited to celebrate religious holidays and study religious texts at state institutions. Regional government spokeswomen denied that fasting was banned, saying the notices only encouraged people to "eat properly for study and work". There is a much tighter level of control for all Uyghur, and the religious repression has intensified¹¹.

On April 23, 2013, a reported 21 people, including police personnel, members of a community watch patrol, and six Uyghurs alleged to be part of a terrorist group, died in a clash in western Xinjiang near the city of Kashgar. Local officials claimed that the Uyghur group possessed extremist religious literature and bomb-making materials. PRC authorities, who asserted the Uyghur group attacked the community watch officers and a police station after their bomb-making materials were discovered, they arrested 19 Uyghur suspects. Uyghur exile groups questioned the PRC government's version of events, saying that it often uses claims of terrorism to justify excessive security measures. Some Uyghurs at the scene reportedly claimed that the violence occurred after local public security forces fired into a crowd that was protesting ongoing police harassment, killing Uyghur youth¹².

China's Ministry of Foreign Affairs said that Uyghur separatist groups had sent members abroad to work with militants. Chinese militants from the western region of Xinjiang have fled from the country to get "terrorist training" from Islamic State fighters for attacks at home. It is the first

time state-run media had linked militants from Xinjiang, home to ethnic minority Uighur Muslims, to militants of the Islamic State (IS), a radical Sunni Muslim group which has seized large parts of Syria and Iraq.¹³

Second: Arab official Stances and unofficial trends towards the problem:

a- Arab Official Stances:

Some Arab states had individually condemned the terrorist attacks on China, such as Egypt. As Egypt strongly condemned the terrorist attack which took place in the "province of Xinjiang" that targeted a police station on December 30, 2013 resulting many injuries of policemen. Furthermore, Egypt emphasized the full official and popular solidarity with the Government and People of China in combating terrorism and extremism and confront firmly¹⁴. Egypt expressed its sympathy with the injured and the families of the victims who were targeted in this terrorist act and all acts of terrorism that took place in the last period against the governmental Chinese institutions and Chinese civilians by extremist groups. Egypt confirms its full official and popular solidarity with the government and people of China in coping with terrorism and extremism. This is the first time Uyghurs had been blamed for an attack so large and far from their home.¹⁵

As well as Saudi Arabia condemned the terrorist incident, which took place in Kunming in Yunnan Province in southwest China early March 2014, killed 29 people. The Foreign Ministry in Saudi Arabia confirmed that the incident is "a criminal act contrary to all the principles that came out of religions and laws and international legislation."¹⁶ It also the Sudanese government condemned this terrorist attack in the city of Kunming, according to the Sudanese Foreign Ministry it "expresses its deep regret and condemnation of the incident, the terrorist who targeted the station railway in the city of Kunming, capital of Yunnan Province in southwest China, which killed dozens of people and injured hundreds," it is "as condemns this heinous terrorist incident, which seeks to destabilize security and stability in the friend People's Republic of China"¹⁷.

At the collective level, the Arab League, which 22 Arab countries are members¹⁸condemned bloody terrorist attack carried out by a terrorist group in Yunnan Province against the peaceful population, And the Secretary of the Arab League expressed its strong condemnation of this heinous crime, and expressed its solidarity and cooperation with the Chinese people and their leadership and the families of the victims and sympathy with the injured¹⁹.

The Organization of Islamic Cooperation, which includes Arab countries in its membership is concerned by the deteriorating situation in Xinjiang province against the population of Uyghur Muslims, and stressed that the people of Uyghur aspires to maintain the characteristics of cultural, ethnic and Islamic identity, and to enjoy their cultural and economic non-changeable Rights. It explained that security measures alone are not enough.

The silence of Arab countries about the issue of Uyghur may be explained by several factors, including:

- Official systems are busy in the outbreak of revolutions in Egypt, Tunisia, Libya and Yemen, in addition to growing violence and fighting in Syria

- Arab states are keen on maintaining good relations with China as an important trading partner, the Arab states together occupies the eighth position in the world as the largest trading partner with China²⁰.
- Weakness of Media attention to the Chinese affairs, for example, Cairo has 6 media against one Egyptian reporter in China, and there is no Arab channel to China, with the exception of Aljazeera
- Relations of friendship and cooperation linking China with Arab regimes, for example, the Minister of Industry and Commerce of China has visited Egypt to participate in the inauguration ceremony of President Abdel Fattah El-Sisi, it was agreed during the visit on the development of bilateral relations between the two countries in the fields of trade and investment²¹.
- As China supported the proposal of the Council of Foreign Ministers of the Arab League on the establishment of the Forum on Arab- China In 2004, Chinese ex-President Hu Jintao met during his visit to Egypt with the Secretary General of the Arab League, Amr Moussa, and the two sides exchanged mainly of views on Sino-Arab Cooperation Forum Arab-China and Other issues. And Chinese President Hu Jintao's four proposals on the establishment of new China-Arab partnership are:
 - Strengthen political relations based on mutual respect.
 - Increasing commercial exchanges as a common development goal.
 - Expand cultural exchanges and mutual benefit as the content.
 - To strengthen cooperation in international affairs as maintaining the integrity of the world and pay the co-evolutionAmr Moussa Secretary of the Arab League At that time, fully agreed on it, and saw that this important principle to guide the development of China-Arab relations in the future, and in favor of expanding cooperation between the two sides in politics, economy, culture and international affairs and other areas²².In the year 2010, China and Arab countries approved to raise their relations to a strategic level and implement an action plan to deepen cooperation through the China-Arab Cooperation Forum²³.
- Chairman of the Standing Committee of the National People's Congress Bangguo, Met Secretary General of the Organization of the Islamic Cooperation Ekmel Eddin Ihsan Oglu, on June 17, 2010 and the Organization includes in its membership 22 Arab countries: Jordan, Egypt, the United Arab Emirates, Bahrain, Tunisia, Algeria , Djibouti, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Syria, Somalia, Iraq, Oman, Palestine, Qatar, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Mauritania, Yemen, Comoros. Bangguo discussed China's policy for Nationalities and Religious Affairs and China's efforts in accelerating the process of economic and social development in Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region, And the Secretary-General Ekmel Eddin Ihsan Oglu said the Organization rejects terrorism, separatism and extremism in all its forms and the Islamic world is keen on make joint efforts with China to consolidate traditional friendship and enhance communication.²⁴
- The Chinese Foreign Ministry and the Organization of the Islamic Cooperation has been issued a joint statement emphasized that the OIC respects the sovereignty and territorial integrity of China the Chinese side. stressed that the Chinese government is to promote the progress and growth in all areas of economic, political, cultural and social development in the field of environmental protection in the Autonomous Region of Xinjiang with the aim to reach GDP per capita relevant to the national level by the year 2015.both sides confirmed opposition to acts of terrorism, separatism and extremism in all its forms²⁵. Also, it was

agreed between China and the Cooperation Council for the Arab Gulf States announced their intention to develop mechanisms for consultation, coordination and cooperation between the two sides²⁶.

- Looking to the issue of Uyghur as an internal issue and refrain from interfering in the internal affairs of China Following the principle of reciprocity, China has been always on non-interference in the internal affairs of Arab , China was silent about the events of the Arab Spring at the beginning and did not recognize these events as Revolutions , which supported the systems Whatever they are in power and then pull them to support the opposition and compatibility with them when moving the opposition to power, was also due to fear of transferring of these events for China, for example, China has used its veto to stop the Security Council resolution on Syria to stop the use of military force against the Syrian regime, and while the opposition succeeded in Tunisia and Egypt China sought to improve its image and granted Tunisia 40 million yuan, and the Federation of Egyptian Industries, received a Chinese delegation to express their desire for economic cooperation between the two countries²⁷.
- Arab excessive sensitivity towards the issues of separation because the majority of Arab countries suffer from the same problem and have minorities such as the Kurds and the Shiites and the Amazigh, and facing these issues in different ways but refuse to separate from the nation-state.²⁸
- Arab states themselves are struggling with terrorism and suffering from unrest and attacks by Islamic extremists²⁹.

b- Informal Arab trends towards the problem:

The unofficial Arabic trends towards the Uyghur issue are the most obvious, and as shown by the positions of the clergy and throwing light on the Uyghur issue like Dr. Sheikh / Nasser bin Suleiman Al Omary, who stressed that "what happened in this crime requires from Arab and Islamic countries which have huge economic relations with China that to make such transactions a condition to a decent life for Muslims in Turkistan and they must enjoy freedom of faith in accordance with the provisions of Islamic law and the laws of freedom and democracy advocated by all the countries and peoples of the world ³⁰".

The Saudi preacher Sheikh Salman bin Fahd stated that "Arab-Chinese official relations, as well as the business must be employed to raise the pressure, and the injustice of our brothers, and we are in front of the massacre and the issue that the Government of China refuses to Display the case to the Security Council that does not mean never Muslims be silent ", and the Association of Algerian Muslim Scholars, blogs and forums on the Internet, and Mecca statement issued by a number of scientists in the Islamic religion from Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Sudan, the statement stressed that:

- The support of our brothers Muslims of Turkestan, support is duty on the pan-Muslim governments and peoples by various types of political support, media and economic, and that support could be defined to their cause and figuring out what they are exposed to injustice and maltreatment, in global forums and international organizations, and Islamic governments do its best to put pressure on the Chinese government through diplomatic and other means; to raise their injustice and discrimination, and work to give them their rights and save their dignity, and to stop persecution and dissolving their Islamic identity.

- Muslims -in general- and Muslims in Turkistan especially, should know the plans which aim to transform the issue of Turkestan from Islamic issue to the issue of racial, ethnic to Uyghur versus ethnic Han In so similar to the question of Palestine, which began Islamic then turned to Arabic countries to end as Palestinian issue. Also it praised the effort of the OIC, and asked for more effort to reach a solution through the organization to reach an agreement with the Chinese government to give the Muslims of Turkestan all their rights and to initiate the organization to open an office in Turkestan.
- The appeal to the rest of the institutions and organizations, unions and Islamic councils of government and popular; to make every effort through the means available through TV and websites that talk to Uyghur in their own language, and to initiate relief agencies to begin their work of relief and humanitarian sympathy and the establishment of schools and mosques; especially they are going through extremely difficult living conditions and to facilitate the admission of students in the Islamic universities, and appealing to Muslims to devote part of their charity to those Muslims, that it is delivered through the safe channels of Islamic Relief.
- Economic boycott of Chinese goods and products, especially the volume of trade exchange between China and Islamic countries is large, and appeal to Muslim scholars to study issue a fatwa in this regard³¹.

The final Statement issued by the World Muslim League, headed by Sheikh Abdul Aziz bin Abdullah Al-Sheikh Mufti of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and called on OIC countries to exert diplomatic efforts in bilateral and international meetings, with the Government of China to respect the feelings of Muslims, and give them the religious ,social , cultural, and political rights, and stop dumping their land by displaced Chinese also the final Statement recommended OIC Member States, and international organizations interesting Turkestan Muslim people, to save them from practices designed to obliterate the Islamic identity, as well as contacting their patriot leaders ; to know their problems and suffering, and the possibility of mediation between them, and the Government of the PRC, thus alleviating the tension between the two sides and to achieve the demands of the Muslims, and to provide scholarships to the children of the Muslims of East Turkestan in the various disciplines, and facilitate accommodation for them .Facilitate granting Turkstanyen pilgrims coming from china visas from representations of Saudi Arabia in Islamabad, and Alma-Ata, and Tashkent and Dubai, and Istanbul, and Bangkok. Providing support for mosques, schools, and Islamic institutions in china and provision of scholarships, and the appointment of preachers and exchange of visits with associations and Islamic personalities in China.³²

The International Union for Muslim Scholars , which is an informal body comprising a group of clergy from several Muslim and Arab countries such as Egypt, Tunisia, Saudi Arabia, most of them belonging to the banned terrorist organization Muslim Brotherhood.³³ Where the International Union for Muslim Scholars deeply concerned that offered by the media of a fierce attack on unarmed civilians in East Turkistan and others, resulted in casualties, killing and injuring hundreds, and the arrest of thousands of innocent people, and Union condemns this assault on our brothers in Turkestan and calls for the Chinese government to stop immediately these practices, that are harmful to China's historical relationship with the current Muslim world, and demanding granting all the legitimate rights of Muslims in China. On this occasion, the Union

ask the governments of the Muslim world that to support our Muslim brothers in China, in order to put pressure on the Government of China, to stop this carnage and do not recur³⁴.

Readers' comments on the news that newspapers circulated on Muslims Uyghur, By analyzing content of intentional sample of these comments, have been selected on the basis of the subject published on Uyghur and giving space for readers to comment³⁵, we can conclude the following:

-The support of the majority of Comments Uyghur Muslims only because they are Muslims and this requires support in the opinions of readers.

-Neglecting violence and extremism practiced by some of the Uyghur to the National Authority.

-Exaggeration in the numbers of victims of violence and injured from Uyghur including inconsistent with official numbers or traded in the media

-Formation of a mental image that the issue of Uyghur in China is similar to the issue of Muslims in Chechnya.

-Total disregard for the enjoyment of other Muslim minorities in China, such as Hui with their rights and this indicate that the real reasons for cracking down on Uyghur Muslims may be due to economic and political factors, as Xinjiang province represents major economic importance to China.

-supplication to God and call for Uyghur as it's possible.

-The call for a boycott of Chinese goods and products .

-Criticizing the positions of Arab and Islamic countries of failing to support Uyghur,

-Ask Chinese authorities to open formal investigations in the incidents of violence in the region to identify the real criminals and arrest them.

-Asking the European Union to send observers to Xinjiang province to stop the violent repression against Uyghur

- Asking international human rights organizations and the Organization of the Islamic Conference and the Arab League, and the World Federation of Muslim Scholars to intervene.

These unofficial trends are still, despite its condemnation of china's policies do not reflect the Arab public opinion that they are limited to a specific category of users of the Internet, newspaper readers, and belonging to the Muslim Brotherhood and other groups of political Islam.

Third: The steps/ measures that China must follow to contain the problem of Uyghurs and maintain good Arab-Chinese relations:

The Uyghur issue is combination of ethnicity and religion also involves the movement of religious and political ideologies, weapons, and people. There is no single Uyghur agenda. Groups that use violence desire a separate Uyghur state. While some Uyghurs want a separate state, others want to maintain cultural distinction within an autonomous relationship with China and others are integrating into the Chinese system³⁶ Chinese policy offered jobs to Uyghur elsewhere in China outside the Xinjiang region, thus reducing the concentration of this ethnic group. On the other hand, in the last five decades, there has been heavy Han immigration, so that today, Uyghurs barely outnumber the immigrants³⁷.

Several studies suggest that China could become the only competitor to the United States in the horizon of 2025, and a position during the next fifty years that exceed the EU are therefore China keen completely on its

economic resources which a region of Xinjiang represents a large part and China should contain the tensions in the region and prevent the outbreak of social explosions so not to constitute an obstacle to the continued growth of the Chinese economy³⁸ and applying preventive policy against Regional disintegration³⁹. The containment of tensions in the region internally is considered support of the Chinese policy credibility overseas and reduces criticisms from human rights organizations⁴⁰. Pre-President Hu Jintao has stressed that "the primary objective of China's foreign policy is to maintain world peace, and China will continue on the path of peaceful development and raise the banner of peace, development and cooperation."⁴¹ There are fears where the media indicate militants escaped from the Chinese territory of "Xinjiang" in the far west of China from the country to receive training at the hands of a terrorist organization ISIS fighters, to launch attacks in the region after returning.⁴²

Therefore, China must include the following:

- Freedom to practice Islamic rituals .
- Uyghur Investment as capital in economic relationship with Central Asia and the Muslim world,
- Providing jobs for Uyghur Muslims
- Respect the religious traditions of Uyghur , so that should be allowed for all Muslims visit Mecca, and not just those who get government approval to travel for Hajj or Umrah, it can also encourage the Uighur language education, as well as its use in the workplace.
- Adopt policy of reform of the whole society, not only Uyghur, where protests occur every year and characterized by some violence through which citizens express their anger of the poor distribution of income and corruption and severe environmental degradation.⁴³ This is consistent with the comprehensive reform document approved by the eighteenth National Conference of the Central Committee of the CPC which confirmed that the future of China and its stability internally depends on the implementation of a package of reforms such as the balance between urban and rural development, the reform of the financial system and the start of decentralization, strengthening the soft power. ⁴⁴
- Measures such as creating jobs and improving education are seen as fundamental solutions to address the threat of terrorism, Cities such as Kashgar, Korla, Karamay, Hami, Aksu and Yining should be transformed into "major poles of growth"
- Xinjiang must march onto the road of new style urbanization .Urbanization could help to shrink the urban-rural divide, develop the economy and improve the living standard of less developed places,⁴⁵ Urbanization serves as a fundamental solution to tackle poverty, unemployment and inequality in less-developed southern Xinjiang where religious conservatism is prevalent and terrorist attacks occur more frequently
- Good treatment of fair-minded Uighurs, who did not involve yet in terrorism .

Conclusion

The causes of the problem are a complex mixture of history, ethnicity, and religion, fueled by poverty, unemployment, social disparities, and political grievances. The issue then becomes whether China is victimizing the Uyghur minority, using terrorism and separatism as an excuse to violate their human rights, or whether China itself is a victim of separatists and terror networks like Al-Qaeda camps, which trained

Uyghurs in Afghanistan to be involved in activities in Xinjiang. It must be noted that the phenomenon of extremism and terrorism does not impose a serious challenge to the security of the Chinese state and the safety of its citizens, but also impose a serious challenge to the great culture of Uygur and impressive struck roots deep in history, and a distortion for the great importance of the religion of Islam with all the holds of the meanings of love, peace and tolerance. It is the interest of the Arabs and the Chinese to cooperate in the exchange of experiences and information to combat terrorism, the common enemy of humanity.

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Defense Network for the Sunni

<http://www.dd-sunnah.net/>

Islam way

<http://ar.islamway.net>

Story of Islam

<http://islamstory.com/ar>

Brothers Online site

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11. The EU and China trade relations

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Wine, solar panels and rare earths: As bilateral trade relations intensify, a formalised solution for settling trade disputes is becoming increasingly necessary

The EU and China both attach particular importance to their bilateral trade relations. Since China’s accession to the WTO in 2001, bilateral trade has surged. The EU is the largest trading partner of the PRC (15 percent of total trade in 2013), and the PRC is the second largest of the EU (12.5 percent of total trade in 2013). Bilateral trade has increased almost threefold, from €148 billion in 2003 to €428.1 billion in 2013. As technologically advanced Chinese products start to compete for EU market shares with EU businesses, the likelihood of bilateral trade disputes increases.

Graph 1. EU-China Trade-Volume and Trade-Balance

Source:

http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/briefing_note/join/2014/522342/EXPO-INTA_SP%282014%29522342_EN.pdf

Recent EU-China trade data reveal two important trends :

Since the financial crisis in **2008, China has turned into an important strategic export destination for EU manufacturers.** Exports of high-tech consumer goods (especially cars) strengthened European economies during the financial crisis and the European sovereign debt crisis.

With 20 million Chinese households passing the household income threshold of US\$ 13,500 annually – a threshold at which middle class families become able to afford key consumer goods and services – the Chinese market will turn into an even more important strategic export destination for European companies. In 2013, almost 20 percent of EU exports to China were cars and car parts (in 2007 less than ten percent). However, recent Chinese application of the anti-trust law against European carmakers and car part suppliers could prove very effective at putting pressure on the European Union.

Graph 2. Share of Total EU Exports to China

Source: UN COMTRADE

China is exporting more and more technologically advanced products to the EU. The proportion of technologically advanced products (machinery and transport equipment, chemical and related products) in China's exports to the EU is growing, while the share of primary and labour-intensive products (manufactured goods classified chiefly by material) is decreasing.

The share of office machines and automatic data-processing machines and of telecommunications goods in total Chinese exports to the EU has been rising in particular. Portable automatic data-processing machines (SITC 7522) and telephones (SITC 7641) constitute about 17 percent of Chinese exports to the EU. Meanwhile, the importance of toys and sporting goods and other technologically less-advanced products is declining.

Graph 3. Share of Total Chinese Exports to EU

Source: UN COMTRADE

Solving trade disputes via dialogue or WTO panels

The number of trade disputes between the EU and China has been growing in recent years. By the end of July 2014, the EU was enforcing 50 anti-dumping and anti-subsidy measures against Chinese imports.

Between 2008 and 2013, more than a third of all anti-dumping and anti-subsidy investigations initiated by the EU targeted Chinese products. Interestingly, the content of the trade disputes has shifted. While in the late 1990s, EU anti-dumping and anti-subsidy measures focused on primary goods like apparel or textiles, more recently they have targeted technologically advanced and even high-tech products like solar panels.

The anti-dumping and countervailing duty investigation into Chinese solar panels was extraordinary. It was the biggest single product investigation ever opened by the EU, and it affected about seven percent of Chinese exports to the EU (€21 billion) in 2011. Usually, the combined anti-dumping and anti-subsidy measures affect less than two percent of total imports from China.

Solving trade disputes through dialogue is less time consuming than WTO arbitration and strives for amicable solutions. In the run-up to Xi Jinping's visit to Brussels in March 2014, trade disputes regarding Chinese anti-dumping and anti-subsidy investigations (polysilicon, wine) were resolved. In both cases, intense bilateral discussion between Chinese authorities and EU exporters—in the wine case between the European Wine Federation and the Chinese Wine Federation—preceded the dispute settlement.

Graph 4: Anti-Dumping and Anti-Subsidy Investigations Initiated by the EU

Source: DG-Trade Anti-Dumping and Anti-Subsidy Measures List

Although solving trade disputes through dialogue may initially seem preferable, it does, however, create incentives to apply strategic retaliation in order to gain leverage in trade dispute settlement negotiations. For example, the Chinese Ministry of Commerce launched an anti-dumping and anti-subsidy investigation into EU wines one day after the European Commission announced provisional duties on Chinese solar panels (and similar measures against EU solar grade polysilicon the following week).

According to DG Trade officials, the Chinese improved their leverage in the solar panel price agreement negotiations solely by initiating anti-dumping measures against polysilicon and wine, although there were “no indications of breaches against anti-dumping or anti-subsidy regulations by the EU”.

Appealing for arbitration by a WTO panel is another possible way of resolving disputes. Although this is more time consuming, WTO panels can provide just solutions. Currently, the EU and China are involved in six active WTO dispute settlement cases. Four cases were launched by the EU, while two were launched by China.

Outlook for improving dispute settlement

As China continues to improve its manufacturing capabilities, Chinese products are increasingly competing for EU market shares with EU manufacturers. As the solar dispute illustrates, more competition and trade disputes can be expected, including in the high-tech sector.

Although there are more than 50 sectoral dialogues between the EU and China, there is no mechanism on an early-warning system that could effectively express the mutual concerns and control disputes in bilateral trade and economic relations. During the solar panel dispute, Chinese Premier Li Keqiang made a personal call to the president of the European Commission, José Manuel Barroso, in order to solve the dispute. In the long run, this must be regarded as a highly inefficient and arbitrary tool for solving Sino-European trade disputes.

As the complexity of bilateral trade relations and trade disputes increases, a formal Sino-EU dispute settlement mechanism will become necessary. An EU-China bilateral investment treaty or, in the long run, an EU-China free trade agreement could serve as the legal basis for a formalised mechanism for settling disputes.

**12. The 'Re-Emergence' of China
in the Context of East Asian Regionalism**

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With the multiple processes brought about by globalization, more and deeper economic integration in the world is being undertaken. Regionalization, as the mainstream economic trend within these global processes has to be considered as a key aspect in any country's developmental strategy. While the economic and also political maps of Europe, North and South America are being redrawn, the Asia-Pacific region in particular has become the most dynamic and fast growing region. This is often attributed to the so called "Rise" or "Re-emergence" of China (People's Republic of China or PRC), which has changed dramatically the way economic and political relations are conceived around the Pacific Ocean. As trade flows are being redirected to the insatiable Chinese appetite for Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and the other booming economies in this part of the globe, the traditional direction that International Relations had historically taken - namely Trans-Atlantic - has now shifted to what is widely known as the "New Century of the Pacific."

In this environment, where international politics is increasingly determined by economic ties, China's foreign policy signifies a turnover in the regional arena. This is not only substantially transforming the economic relations of the PRC with the outside world, but also implies a great impact on the political economy for the East Asian and trans-Pacific economic integration processes that are underway. Indeed, Beijing's new economic moves towards regional integration are mainly based on Chinese leadership's concern over economic regionalism in the world and also sustained by the fact that China's economy has become significantly intertwined with other regional economies over the past few decades. Therefore, the Chinese are looking for efficient and stabilizing trade mechanisms within the competitive Asia-Pacific market.

Why is China enthusiastically seeking for different levels of economic integration and taking participation in mostly all the regional organizations? Is China taking a leading role in regionalism just because of its growing need to coordinate and cooperate with other economies in order to keep its growth rate, or also because of its desire to enhance and further its traditional sphere of influence as a regional power? To many

observers, it is obvious that China is using its economic might as a means to enhance and expand its traditional sphere of influence in the Asia-Pacific region by achieving different kinds of economic and trade arrangements, especially Free Trade Agreements (FTAs). Certainly, this is a political-power driven strategy as well as an economic-growth driven strategy, and both actually complement each other.

Consequently, China's moves affect greatly regional integration and community-building efforts and the way East Asia is institutionalizing itself. To some extent, China's has come to challenge the regional order that prevailed for most part of the 20th century. East Asian regionalism is therefore evolving in a very unique and particular way. Dajin Peng points out that all the major theories based on the Western experiences, including the economic, realist, and functional theories, are of little use in explaining economic integration in this part of the world. (Peng, 2004: 427).

It is often claimed that what is known as the Flying Geese Pattern (FGP) is the most prominent theoretical model of East Asian economic development to explain the catching-up process led by Japan as the first newly industrializing economies (NIEs). "The form of regional development as postulated by the modern flying geese paradigm presupposes the existence of a hierarchy, with a dominant economy acting as the growth centre and followed by other developing economies" (Kasahara, 2004: 2). But this hierarchy is obviously not permanently fixed and it has obviously changed. China's leapfrogging due to its privileged position as a latecomer, with both its huge economy and growing domestic market, is basically what has altered the original formation. This is why many Japanese authors are alarmingly addressessing the possibility of a "China-centric" regional development pattern that has been encouraged by PRC's central authorities. (Kasahara, 2004) Others, like Munakata, point out how the recent momentum for economic integration in East Asia has largely been driven by China, "with its vast economic potential from which all its neighbors wish to benefit (...) at the same time, China tries to use East Asian cooperation as a vehicle to promote multipolarity in the world" (Munakata, 2002: 19).

The reference to the concept of multipolarity is relevant since it is related to the political implications of Beijing's foreign policy. Zhao highlights that there are three key words, namely, modernization, nationalism and regionalism, which can be used to illuminate the basic trends of Chinese foreign policy in the post-Cold War era. Regionalism in particular emphasizes that "despite its global aspirations, the PRC has

remained a power within Asia. Beijing has confined China's international, political, economic, and military activities primarily to the Asia-Pacific region" (Zhao, 1996: 185). To promote a more institutionalized type of regionalism through economic integration agreements can be considered as a consistent part of Beijing's new international strategy.

As it is well known among scholars and foreign policy-makers in Asia, this last point became a priority after the Asian Financial Crisis (AFC) which marked a turning point on East Asian integration, and contributed to change the way the process had been carried out until 1998 - namely a market-driven integration. As various authors emphasized, particularly Cai and also Munakata, the AFC left an acute sense of interdependence among the region, and convinced not only the affected ASEAN nations but also the Northeast Asian countries that they need a regional mechanism in order to avoid another economic debacle. As a result of the AFC, the configuration of the Asia-Pacific political economy changed dramatically. This allowed China showed itself as a regional power interested in further its ties with its neighbors and strengthen cooperation and integration among the countries in the region. China poured money into the most affected ASEAN economies and helped at large to develop the famous Chiang Mai Initiative to assist countries in financial difficulties.¹

However, China's rise into an economic giant and regional power continue to cause a lot of stress among its neighbors in Asia and beyond. Indeed, over the past two decades China's overwhelming rise has signified a decline on the inward FDI share among other economies in the region. This phenomenon is the main characteristic of the so called the rise of China, and widely discussed by scholars around the world. What many continue to wonder is whether, due to this situation, China is prepared and capable to assume a leading and constructive role in regionalism and economic integration in Asia and a responsible superpower role in the world. Unfortunately, many agree that currently China is increasingly using its unparalleled economic strength to bully its neighbors and challenge particularly the US as the *de facto* super power. This can be understood since all great powers have historically used their strength to promote their regional interests, and China's emergence as an economic powerhouse undoubtedly alters the distribution of power in the Asia-Pacific, in which the US has had a hegemonic position for more than 50 years. Joseph Nye quotes William Pfaff to argue that there is no balance of power in Asia in the classic sense. There is an American military and political predominance that China wishes to break. "China's natural ambition to restore its own

primacy actually tends to create a balance that now is absent (...) in this perspective, it is the United States that increasingly is the destabilizing factor in East Asia" (Nye, 1997/98: 65). That is why Nye signaled long ago that the so called 'Rise of China' is a misnomer, and it was him who proposed that 'Re-emergence' is more accurate, since Mainland China, before as an Empire and now as the People's Republic, has always been a major power in the Asia-Pacific region.

Moreover, the new role of China in promoting regional arrangements has to be understood within the PRC's international and regional strategy. Throughout the 1980s and early 1990s, as China increasingly became incorporated into the Asia-Pacific, Beijing sought a position in the region that was commensurate with China's great power aspirations. During this time, however, China did not devise a "grand strategy" according to authors like Christoffersen. He refers "grand strategy" as a political-military-economic means-ends chain that integrates the military and nonmilitary instruments employed by a state to achieve a broadly defined goal of national security (Christoffersen, 1996: 1067). By 1995 China still had not defined a clear role for itself in the Asia-Pacific and had not yet developed a comprehensive, coordinated strategy towards the region. Steven Levine noted already three decades ago that Chinese leaders did not think in regional terms, leaving China "a regional power with-out a regional policy" (Levine, 1984: 107).

Currently things are much more different. Although there has been constant tension in China's foreign policy-making, the Chinese leadership seems to have understood that taking participation in regional arrangements can indeed help China to ensure its sovereignty while at the same time enhancing its national interests due to the capacity of influencing the regional affairs from within. Certainly, China has been in the process of "learning" to develop a regional policy in the last few decades. This is reflected on the fact that while joining multilateral regimes, China still prefers bilateral interactions, in the understanding that the former option can become an arena to pressure Beijing, whereas within the latter China has more room to maneuver.

For Jean Garrison, China represents a patient power and savvy strategist. This author points out that China's newfound international confidence and surging growth raise important questions about the country's future role in regional and global politics. Regarding this new role, this author notes that "China acknowledges that acceding to international and regional rules-based organizations and agreements has become a sovereignty-enhancing mechanism rather than a limit to its autonomy. In the near future China will primarily follow agreed-upon

international practices, although it is increasingly moving its position to directly shape the system itself" (Garrison, 2005: 25). Beijing activism and even leadership in regional frameworks like ASEAN + 3, or within other groupings like the Shanghai Cooperation Organization and the BRICS are a clear example of this last point. Its demands to reform other global institutions like the IMF or World Bank in order to have more influence in them is also a clear sign of China's aspirations.

In particular, East Asian regionalism represents a good policy option for China, and this explains why China has over the past decade put great emphasis on regional economic integration with ASEAN and also with South Korea and even Japan. Indeed, with the end of the Cold War, where "bloc politics" and ideological differences are less important; instead, national interests, especially economic interests, rise to be preeminent. This aspect has been China's calculus and it is what determines its shift on foreign policy to further seek for economic integration in its region. As mentioned, this so called economic statecraft is by no means only based in pure economic thought and it has certainly other more political implications despite its practical appearance. Vincent Wang explains how China's "new diplomacy", also called "peaceful ascendancy", "peaceful rise" or even "independent foreign policy of peace" is basically a pragmatic approach to international relations. Indeed, "Chinese are more accustomed to analyze international relations from the perspective of practical interests. They are less likely to believe that some spiritual beliefs (values, religions or even ideologies) can be a driving force behind diplomacy" as it occurs in the West (Deng, 1998: 316). The Chinese see international exchanges more in the terms of the motives of interest and the gains-losses thereof.

The timing for China has been ideal over the past decade, since the United States has been busy with other issues and while East Asia is has managed to recover and grow impressively thanks to China's economic engine. the PRC's rise has served as an attractive alternative policy agenda for Southeast Asian nations especially, and since the major instrument used in advancing China's fundamental objectives is its economic power. Wang is exceptionally accurate when he defines China's peaceful ascendancy: "the language is peace and stability, the style is constructive diplomacy, and the substance is economics – at least for now. The key is ascendancy. The theory leaves open the question what happens *after* China has ascended. In other words, is peace an end in China's theory of 'peaceful rise' or simply a means for achieving ascendancy?" (Wang, 2005: 34). The troubles and increased tension over the islands in both the East and South China seas are for many a sign of

the real intentions behind China's allure to entice its neighbors into signing economic integration arrangements over the past decade, especially with the smaller ASEAN nations.

Although up to this moment Beijing has accepted the convenience of the US presence in Asia-Pacific as means to maintain the stability needed for its economic growth and development; for Beijing, to acquire a political leadership through economic integration and trade liberalization as its calculus within Asia-Pacific is relevant for its ambitions as a regional and perhaps global power. This would help understand the PRC's assertive strategy to engage others in FTA talks. Shujiro Urata (2004) explains that many countries opt to form FTAs among "like-minded" nations to pursue trade liberalization. As a result, the creation of blocs with similar not only economic but also political interest is consolidated. China is looking for this kind of like-minded countries among its neighbors in order not just to secure its economic stability and maintain its growth rate, but especially because it wants to enhance its sphere of influence as the leader of an Asia-Pacific regional bloc. The non-economic benefits from all these arrangements are indeed relevant for China's new strategy. Regional security and stability appear to be an emerging challenge that motivates the promotion of a more institutionalized regionalism that East Asia has lacked as compare with other regions. Within this context, geopolitics is apparently what guides Beijing's interests in trade talks. Better regional economic cooperation and integration can also help to solve historical problems, especially among China's Northeast Asian counterparts.

According to Sun Tzu, author of the *Art of War* and legendary figure in Chinese classical literature, "supreme excellence consists in breaking the enemy's resistance without fighting." Today, Sun Tzu's axiom assumes a new meaning as China attempts to become the leader of the Asia-Pacific regional economic integration. China's regional strategy seems to become even clearer in times of crisis: economic integration as means to sustain stability, while restoring confidence, by assuring China's peaceful rise and the possible benefits of it for the whole Asia-Pacific region. More significantly, taking a leadership role in Asia-Pacific economic integration would allow China to craft the economic rules of the region, rather than merely follow them, especially considering the amount of influence that the US has in these regards. Given that international economic rules establish the system of relations between regional neighbors, such rules and the ability to make them are crucial to China's national interests. If China does not assume a position of leadership in Asia-Pacific regionalism, it may be forced to follow

economic rules promulgated by others, possibly rival countries. In other words, should China not initiate formation of a regional arrangement, it would have no other alternative but to accept the existing rules in the future. From the perspective of *realpolitik*, it is understandable that China tries to preempt the right to participate in rule-making by taking the initiative. Thus, the vision of *realpolitik* implied the strategy of China and also its regional competitors is not based on blood and iron but on strategic diplomacy, in which economics acts as the current key bargain element.

Economic integration can be therefore considered as the new method of territorial and ideological expansion in the 21st Century. No conquest by force, but union by enticement. A race that is now being run by regional blocs, each of them trying to become more competitive and trying to attract new aligned partners. American-led Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP), which has been especially designed to counter-balance China's influence and aspirations in the Asia-Pacific landscape is the most clear example of that.

¹. Signed in May, 2000 in the City of Chiang Mai, Thailand, this initiative created a network of bilateral arrangements among China, Japan and the Republic of Korea with the ASEAN countries. This pact provided financing for members which may encounter liquidity problems. In 2009 an agreement was reached to replace the complicated bilateral swap agreements for a comprehensive multilateral arrangement that created a single fund to help with managing regional financial crises which represents the first successful regionalist project of the ASEAN+3 grouping.

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(F) China' s Domestic and Foreign Policies

1. Rebalancing China's Economy

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The remarkable development of China's economy over the past thirty years has transformed the lives of over a billion people and had a global impact. However, China's growth has become increasingly unbalanced and unsustainable. In response, the Chinese government has proposed a series of reforms that would represent the most important transformation of the Chinese economy since the early 1990s. The impact of these changes will be felt internationally both economically and politically.

China has experienced unprecedented growth over the last 35 years pulling more people out of poverty than any nation in history. This has had an impact beyond China's borders, whether it is boosting demand for raw materials from Australia and Brazil or increasing investment in Africa. Many developing countries have been attracted by China's success and have looked for ways to emulate it.

However, over the last few years this model has been showing signs of strain. As early as 2007, Wen Jiabao called China's economic growth "unsteady, imbalanced, uncoordinated and unsustainable" (Lardy, 2011, p. 1). In this paper, I want to outline the imbalances that have formed and the risks they pose to the Chinese economy. I will also summarize current and planned reform efforts and assess the likely domestic and international consequences.

I. Need for Change

Economic Imbalances

GDP can be divided into consumption, investment, government spending and net exports. China only consumes around 35% of its GDP, compared

to 70% for the US and 60% for India (figure 1). Conversely, Chinese investment has risen to almost 50%, compared to less than 20% in the US and around 35% in India. The US and India represent fairly typical numbers for developed and developing countries respectively, while China's investment is higher than almost any other country in history.

Historically, there may have been good reasons for China to focus on investment. In 1980, its infrastructure and capital stock was poor and required a great deal of investment. As long as investment earned high returns, high investment was an engine for growth.

However, as China has developed and its infrastructure improved, the marginal benefit of additional investment has fallen. In order to maintain its growth, China has had to increase its investment and, to fund this increased investment, it has had to borrow more. Standard Chartered (Holliday, 2014), a bank, estimates that China's debt has increased from 147% of GDP in 2008 to 251% in 2014, but over the same period growth has slowed from over 10% per year to around 7.5%. Increasing debt that is used to finance low return investment represents creates the risk of a financial crisis.

FIGURE 1: EXPENDITURE COMPOSITION OF GDP IN CHINA, INDIA AND U.S.
Source: World Bank

The other key plank of China's development model is exports. China exports an extremely large fraction of its GDP for a large country. Ever since opening up, a significant part of China's growth has come from export processing: the importing, assembly and re-export of products. As a result, both China's imports and exports have been high. Figure 2 compares China's exports as a share of GDP to India and the US.

FIGURE 2: CHINA, INDIA & US EXPORTS (% OF GDP)

Source: World Bank

Export-led growth is a viable strategy for a developing country. A low-income country may not have enough domestic demand to develop a manufacturing industry. However, it does have low labor costs and so can sell product to the large developed markets at competitive prices. As growth is not constrained by demand, it can be rapid. However, particularly for a large country like China, there are limits to this strategy. Developed countries typically grow at 2-3% per year, so they cannot increase their imports from developing countries at greater than this rate for ever. At some point, China's export growth has to slow and can no longer provide the same boost to growth. Furthermore, over the last ten years, wages in China have begun to rise rapidly. While this is good news for Chinese workers, it means that China is no longer a low-cost producer.

The reliance on investment and exports is related to another aspect of China's economy: the importance of manufacturing and the lack of services. Figure 3 breaks down China's economy according to primary, manufacturing and service sectors and compares this break down to those of India and the US.

FIGURE 3: SECTORAL COMPOSITION OF GDP IN CHINA, INDIA & US

Source: World Bank

The reliance on manufacturing has made China the world's leading user of most raw materials and energy. As many of these inputs (particularly vital ones like oil) are imported, China is very reliant on the security trading routes which it has historically been unable to secure with its military.

Manufacturing and construction have also left China with some of the world's worst pollution problems. As Chinese incomes rise, citizens become more concerned with pollution. The government has responded by supporting renewable energy projects (particularly hydroelectric

dams, solar panel production, and wind farms). In 2013, China increased its solar power capacity by more than any other country (IEA Photovoltaic Power Systems Programme, 2014). The recent gas deal with Russia represents another initiative to secure China's energy supply (Luhn & Macalister, 2014). Reducing the energy intensity of growth will also help reduce energy demands and pollution problems, and service based growth will help in this respect.

Financial Distortions

In any economy, the financial system has a critical role in the allocation of resources and financial distortions have caused many of China's imbalances. In China under planning, the government decided on the allocation of resources and the financial system was used passively to direct funds in accordance with these policies. Since reform, the financial system has ostensibly functioned independently along commercial lines, but the government influence has remained in a few key ways.

Firstly, interest rates have been kept artificially low. For much of the 2000s, deposit rates were below inflation, and loan rates were also lower than would have been achieved with free markets. Low interest rates transfer funds from savers (mainly households) to borrowers (mainly businesses and government). This explains why the consumption and services are so low (households are the key source of demand for these).

Artificially low interest rates (also known as financial repression) may have been part of a consistent growth policy based on investment and exports. However, it may also have been due to political distortions. Low interest rates create excessive demand for loans. With excess demand, loans are rationed and this gives power to those doing the rationing. In China, the rationers were the state-owned banks and, indirectly, the government. This helps explain why state-owned enterprises received the lion's share of credit, while small and medium-sized enterprises have been squeezed out. It may be part of the reasons that, despite having the world's second largest economy, China has so few world-class companies.

One other important consequence of financial repression has been its effect on the real estate market. Low interest rates have left wealthy Chinese with few investment options. The stock market has been plagued by corporate governance and fraud scandals (for example the SEC barred the Chinese subsidiaries of the big four audit companies for withholding audit documents for firms under investigation for fraud (Eliot, 2014)), and capital account restrictions prevent investment overseas. As a result, most Chinese have invested the bulk of their wealth in the real estate market. This has led to rapid rises in real estate prices and to concerns that China could face a real estate bubble and the risk of a financial crisis.

The second most important distortion has been the exchange rate. The People's Bank of China (China's central bank) has controlled the appreciation of the RMB. This was particularly important during the between 2000 and 2007 and when China ran huge surpluses and accumulated vast foreign exchange reserves. By keeping the exchange rate undervalued, China boosted exports at the expense of domestic consumers of imported goods. More recently, China's surplus has shrunk, suggesting that the RMB may no longer be significantly undervalued.

An additional consequence of the exchange rate policy was the rise in the monetary base caused by the increase in foreign exchange reserves. Given the demand for credit and with no other policy changes, this would have led to rise in the money supply and inflation. Raising interest rates would have been a possible response, but that would have unwound the financial repression discussed above. Instead the People's Bank of China raised the reserve ratio on banks. This was successful in slowing bank loan growth. However, over time, banks found ways to move loans off-balance sheet and so avoid the reserve ratio requirements. This led to the growth of China's shadow banking sector (Tao & Deng, 2013). This has had some positive effects (for example, increasing interest rates for savers, and increasing access to loans for private enterprises), but it has also raised concerns about a financial crisis in China.

II. Reforms

Late in 2013, China announced a series of reforms at the Third Plenum. Though these reforms covered a wide-range of topics, the unifying perspective seemed to be a focus on rebalancing. From this perspective, financial reforms may prove to be the most important, but there will also be some effect from land and hukou reform and strengthened environmental regulations.

Financial Reforms

Announcements following the Third Plenum have indicated that China is keen to allow market forces to play a greater role in setting both interest rates and exchange rates.

As far as interest rates are concerned, loan rates had already been partially liberalized, so the focus now is on deposit rates. The main barrier to liberalizing deposit rates are the banks: artificially low deposit rates boost their profits and give them an incentive to oppose reform. However, the rise of internet-based money market funds like Yu'EBao may have changed these incentives. Over the last year, internet-based funds have attracted significant sums of money by offering higher interest rates than banks can offer on deposits. Yu'EBao attracted over \$90 billion of investments in its first year of operation (Cheng, 2014). Indeed, banks have been forced to offer comparable products of their own to stem the flow. The government has allowed this innovation to flourish

and may see it as a way to force a de facto rise in deposit rates which will smooth adjustment to the official liberalization of deposit rates.

There have also been some moves to liberalize the exchange rate by increasing the band within which the exchange rate can fluctuate (Noble, 2014). It is also not clear that the RMB is significantly undervalued. Over the last ten years, China's real exchange rate has appreciated significantly, mostly due to higher inflation in China than in most developed countries, and its trade surplus has shrunk.

The effect on the exchange rate of liberalizing the capital account (another reform that has been proposed) is also unclear. Though there may be some demand from foreign investors to buy Chinese stocks, much of this demand has already been satisfied by H-shares (shares in domestically-listed firms accessible to foreign investors) and Chinese companies listed in Hong-Kong and the US. On the other hand, there could be significant demand from Chinese investors for shares in international stocks and bonds. If Chinese demand for foreign investment exceeds overseas demand for investments in China, liberalizing the capital account could lead to depreciation of the RMB.

The Third Plenum announcement gave vague indications of the government's desire to see market forces play a stronger role in the economy. One issue where this can be made concrete is in the role of government in guaranteeing private debts. There has been a sense that the government would stand behind private debts. This creates serious moral hazard problems. Risky investments earn higher returns, but have a greater chance of losses. If the government provides an implicit guarantee, the risk of loss is eliminated and there will be a strong incentive to invest heavily in risky investments.

The government has tried to reduce perceptions that it will provide such guarantees. Earlier this year China experienced its first corporate bond default when Chaori Solar missed a coupon payment (Anderlini, 2014). A tougher test came when a large trust fund marketed by ICBC ran into difficulties (Rabinovitch & Noble, 2014). In this case, investors were mostly bailed out, which suggests that the government is still willing to step in (or force others to step in) to avoid panic. However, the government may have to accept some financial and economic distress in order to force investors to adequately account for risk in their investment decisions.

The desire to promote market forces could also lead to reform of the state-owned enterprises. As with the issue of government guarantees, the challenge for the government with SOE reforms is to force them to respond to market forces without forcing too many into bankruptcy.

Other Reforms

China's household registration system (known as the *hukou*) determines what educational, health and social benefits citizens are entitled to. The *hukou* is specific to a particular place (for example a city or county) and entitles holders to health, educational and other benefits and employment opportunities within that place. If the holder moves to another place, they will lose most of the benefits and employment opportunities unless they can acquire a *hukou* of the place to which they have moved. Certain places (e.g. desirable destinations such as Beijing and Shanghai) have high barriers to obtaining a *hukou*. As a result, many migrants in these cities exist as second-class citizens.

The *hukou* system represents a major barrier to urbanization – a key driver of economic development and one of the Chinese government's goals. *Hukou* reform can also be seen as part of China's desire to rebalance its economy. Urban residents generally have higher consumption rates than rural residents because they have more access to shops and services, and because their more generous benefits mean they do not need to save as much to cover health, educational and retirement expenses.

As a result, there have been discussions about reforming the *hukou* system to make it easier for rural residents to obtain urban *hukous* (Branigan, 2014). Current urban residents tend to oppose these proposals as it would force them to share their benefits. The government also wants to control urbanization to avoid overcrowding and overloaded public services – particularly in the popular cities. As a result, it is likely that *hukou* reform will focus on making it easier for rural residents to move to third and fourth tier cities, while maintaining tight restrictions on migration to cities such as Beijing and Shanghai.

Related to *hukou* reform is the issue of rural land reform. While many rural residents have the right to use land, they do not own the land and the rules about selling land are not clear. This leads to three problems. Firstly, it discourages urbanization because rural residents cannot sell their land, and do not want to lose their land use rights by moving. Secondly, as a result, agriculture in China remains dominated by small land owners operating relatively inefficiently. This is a problem as China must feed a large population with relatively little agricultural land. Finally, vague rural land rights encourage abuse by local governments who have forced rural residents off their land for little or no compensation in order to build infrastructure and apartments. Not only has this further reduced the land allocated to agriculture, but it has also led to corruption. Reforms to land use would attempt to address all these issues.

In January 2015, the Chinese government will implement new rules on environmental regulation, which will include punishments for officials

who fail to enforce the rules and for managers of polluting firms (Kaiman, 2014). In addition, the government is looking to introduce market-based pricing for resources such as electricity and water (Rutkowski, 2014). Currently, there are significant subsidies for many of these resources, which have encouraged overuse and waste. These regulations will encourage the economy to rebalance towards cleaner and more efficient industries. It may also encourage the decline of resource-intensive heavy industries towards cleaner hi-tech industries and services.

III. International Impact

China's rebalancing will affect the rest of the world in multiple ways: both economically, but may also have some implications for broader international relations.

Economic

Since 2000, China's growth has been very resource intensive. Between 2000 and 2005, virtually all the growth in demand for steel, nickel and copper came from China (Garnaut & Song, 2007). Between 2011 and 2013, China used more cement than the US used in the entire 20th century (Smil, 2013). Rebalancing will involve the decline of resource-intensive industries and the rise of services. Many of the strongest economies in the world have been commodity suppliers (e.g. Australia and many developing countries). As the nature of China's growth changes, global commodity demand may decline and this may lead to problems in these countries.

Conversely, as China's domestic consumption (particularly for services) grows there will be opportunities for countries that are strong in these areas. For example, countries with strength in financial services (such as the UK and the US) may be able to close their current account deficits with China.

Wages in China have been rising rapidly over the last decade (from about \$1750 per year in 2004 to about \$8300 per year in 2014¹). Wage costs are now significantly higher than in many other developing countries and this has been reflected in the types of industries in which China specializes. It is likely that this transition will continue in the future so that China will increasingly compete with middle-income countries.

To date, China's impact on the global economy has mainly been through the trade channel, but this is likely to change for two reasons. Firstly, Chinese companies are increasingly investing overseas. Chinese outward FDI is growing rapidly reaching \$500bn in 2012 (Economist, The, 2013). While this is still small relative to FDI into China (at about \$2.1tr), it is growing much faster.

China's proposed opening of its capital account for portfolio flows would also be important. Currently, RMB convertibility is limited to trade, FDI and a few other special cases. Full convertibility would allow foreigners to

invest freely in China's capital markets and the Chinese to invest freely overseas. As foreigners have already been able to gain exposure to the Chinese market indirectly via shares of Chinese companies open to international investors, it is the opportunity of the Chinese to invest overseas that is likely to have the biggest effect. Given the limited and often unattractive investment opportunities in China, it is likely that wealthy Chinese would seize the opportunity to invest overseas. This could have effects on international asset prices, but also may cause a downturn in the domestic real estate market.

International relations

Some of the economic issues discussed above may impact other areas of international relations. Already, China's increasing outward FDI flows has created interesting policy problems for other countries. On the one hand, Chinese investment can aid economic development and create jobs; on the other hand, Chinese ownership of key industries or resources may raise questions of sovereignty or security. These issues have already been widely debated regarding China's investments in Africa (Brautigam, 2011) and some other developing countries, but as China moves up the value chain, these issues will increasingly arise for developed countries. As China's largest firms are often state-owned and usually have strong ties to the Chinese government, takeover of firms with key roles in foreign countries or important technologies will be controversial. This might become one of the central issues surrounding China's economic rise.

Another area which spans both economics and security is energy. China's reliance on imported oil has multiple effects on its international relations. On the one hand, it has caused China to develop relations with countries such as Iran and Venezuela that has aggravated relations with the West. In addition, China's increasing military expenditure and assertive attitude over maritime issues may be influenced by its concern about the security of the shipping lanes through which it imports oil. Finally, the recent natural gas deal with Russia will help China reduce reliance both on oil (with its associated security issues) and coal (and its pollution issues).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the next five to ten years are likely to see the most important transition in China's economy since the early 1990s. This transition will have international implications – not only for the global economy, but also for international relations.

¹Source: Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security, China.

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**2.China’s Foreign Currency Reserves
and its Sovereign Wealth Fund**

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The Bank of China (1949), the People’s Republic of China’s Central Bank, is the financial institution tasked with setting and implementing China’s monetary policy and regulating its financial entities. In the early 2000s China’s current account surplus began growing dramatically, and with it the country’s international currency reserves (see figure 1), all of which came within the purview of the bank.

Figure 1

Source: State Administration of Foreign Exchange (SAFE). Available at: <http://www.safe.gov.cn/>

China has traditionally adopted a conservative investment policy, preferring to purchase low-yield U.S. Treasury Bonds (between 2 and 4% interest rate). However, in 2006 foreign currency reserves reached a record \$1 trillion, thanks to a hugely positive trade balance. That year, senior government officials and leading Chinese economists concluded that there was a need to create a financial body to manage and profitably invest these foreign reserves. Moreover, it was apparent that \$800 billion was more than enough to protect the country against possible financial turmoil deriving from unforeseen external shocks, and increased export income made the accumulation of currency reserves above that figure less necessary.

Consequently, in September 2007, after a decade of structural reform of the banking sector, the Chinese government accepted the Ministry of Finance's proposal to establish a new sovereign wealth fund, China Investment Corporation (CIC), to diversify these vast foreign reserve holdings (\$1.4 trillion in September 2007; \$4 trillion as of June 2014) in investments which would potentially yield a much higher income than that guaranteed by U.S. Treasury bonds. Until 2007, China was emulating Middle Eastern oil producers which recycled their "petrodollars" in dollar-based assets and securities, particularly by investing in U.S. Treasury Bills.

CIC is an exception to most of the global family of sovereign wealth funds. Unlike those of other countries, CIC does not have free and direct access to the country's currency reserves. It was created by the Chinese Ministry of Finance through the issuance of \$207 billion of Special Treasury bonds, the sale of which was completed in December 2007. These, rather than the reserves themselves, still form the basis of its capital.

This decision has had important consequences for CIC. In addition to needing to earn high returns on investment, the fund must pay interest on capital (4.5%) to the Ministry of Finance. According to Lou Jiwei, the former head of CIC who is now Minister of Finance, CIC must repay \$9 billion annually (\$300 million every day) to break even, i.e., to cover the interest on the bonds and its operating costs. This means it has to make a yearly return of 10-13% on capital before it can turn a profit.

In 2006, Jiwei proposed to leverage the financial strength of the Central Huijin Investment Corporation (CHIC, 2003), a Chinese investment

company owned by the government of the People's Republic of China dedicated to recapitalising Chinese commercial banks. The Ministry of Finance then proceeded to merge the CHIC with the State Investment Corporation Ltd (SIC) and give it the name of CIC. CHIC was acquired by CIC for roughly \$67 billion.

CIC, which as of August 2013 has \$575.2 billion of assets under management, is now fully owned by the Chinese government and reports directly to the highest executive body: the State Council. Initially, however, there was considerable friction between the Central Bank and the Ministry of Finance over the supervisory and regulatory function of CIC. This debate took place while the State Administration of Foreign Exchange (SAFE), the lead subsidiary of the Central Bank, was tasked with drafting "rules and regulations governing foreign exchange market activities, and managing the state foreign exchange reserves". As China's foreign reserves had burgeoned almost exponentially in recent years, rivalry and competition had set in between state agencies and subsidiaries. Consequently, in September 2007 the Chinese government decided to transfer the control of the newly formed sovereign wealth fund from SAFE to CIC.

The Chinese authorities were inspired to create CIC in the form they did by the example of another sovereign wealth fund: GIC Private Limited, formerly known as the Government of Singapore Investment Corporation, established in 1981. There are differences between the two SWFs, though, one of which is that the GIC investment portfolio is managed by three subsidiaries: GIC Asset Management Pte Ltd (public markets), GIC Real Estate Pte Ltd and GIC Special Investments Pte Ltd (private-equity investments). Traditionally, GIC is a very opaque investor, keeping a low profile in its financial activities. For instance, the quantity of funds it manages and its annual profit and loss are not publicly available, as the management believes that the disclosure of this information would invite speculators to drive the Singapore dollar down and other currencies up during periods of vulnerability. Consequently GIC has a low score (6/10) on the Linaburg-Maduell Transparency Index, a 10-point scale based on ten principles of transparency developed by the Sovereign Wealth Fund Institute located in Las Vegas.

Even so, CIC delegations have several times headed to Singapore to familiarize themselves with the governance and risk management style of GIC, a global firm with one of the highest corporate credit ratings on both the Standard & Poor's (AAA) and Moody's (Aaa) indices and comparably high investment returns. The proceeds of the GIC activities are

reinvested in areas such as education, R&D, health care and infrastructure. In 2013, GIC was the world's fourth largest sovereign wealth fund, with around \$250 billion in assets under management.

But where does CIC invest its money? In May 2007, CHIC – on behalf of the future CIC – took a 10% stake (\$3 billion) in the Blackstone Group, an American multinational private equity corporation and the largest alternative investment firm in the world. However, this group lost more than 50% of its stock value within months, hitting CIC badly. In December of the same year it bought 10% of Morgan Stanley's shares, for a total of \$5 billion. Again, CIC was hit hard when this American multinational financial services corporation suffered huge losses during the last quarter of 2007. In the light of these initial failures, CIC revised its strategy.

CIC has always claimed that its investment objectives are solely the maximization of financial returns in the long term and that no political aims determine, or are factored into, investment decisions. In addition, partly to reassure recipient countries which become concerned when CIC makes equity investments in strategic sectors (such as energy, communications, high-tech, infrastructure, transportation or defense), and partly to diversify its portfolio, CIC has resolved to limit its investments in these “sensitive” sectors and companies by setting a ceiling of 10% of equities.

However, given the stringent conditions of the initial financing of the SWF, CIC is forced to make high-risk investments if it wants to generate acceptable profit margins. An important point is that the size of CIC's investment and yields currently acts as a stabilizer in the dangerously volatile world financial markets. This explains the frequent discussions the Chinese fund has with other similar national funds, international banks, recipient states and other financial institutions, and also why it favours bilateral and multilateral agreements.

CIC Investment activities decreased significantly in 2008 and 2009. In the wake of the “Great Recession”, Beijing made the drastic choice of opting for a \$600 stimulus package in the hope that such a move would support global growth by bolstering demand for imported machinery and raw materials. The plan called for a rise in spending through 2010 on airports, highways and other infrastructure as well as substantial aid to the Chinese poor and farmers and tax cuts for exporters. At the same time CIC restructured its investment strategy and focused on the

diversification of its targeted markets and sectors. Emerging markets were substituted for EU and U.S. markets, which the Chinese considered saturated. Also, energy and commodity products became the top priorities in the new investment policy rather than equities, fixed income bonds, money-market instruments and real estate.

Several factors accounted for this reorientation. Acerbic criticism from SAFE was one. Following the Blackstone and Morgan Stanley fiascos, SAFE began expressing doubts about the performance of CIC, which was considered within the political leadership as the investment fund par excellence. This prompted the sovereign wealth fund to rethink its goals and strengthen its position within the group bodies in charge of foreign investment and foreign exchange reserve management. A second factor that underpinned the new preference for investment in the energy and raw materials sectors was that China forecast an imminent and significant rise of natural resource and energy prices and wanted to take advantage of this.

This strategic shift did in fact prove beneficial, as in September 2010 CIC established CIC International (Hong Kong) Co, a new subsidiary chaired by Lawrence Lau, and in 2011 opened its first foreign office in Toronto, with Felix Chee as its chief representative officer. Both subsidiaries have the mandate to invest and manage overseas assets. Ultimately, the fund was substantially replenished by the Ministry of Finance, to the tune of \$49 billion, as a reward for its good investment performance.

Recent Developments

CIC has recently confirmed its decision to allocate the assets of the fund by following the Endowment Model (or the Yale Model) developed by David Swensen and Dean Takahashi, the Investment Officer at Yale University. This model is premised on the idea that diversification and investment in equities, from which higher returns can be expected, are preferable to concentrating on the low but safe expected returns from fixed income investments (treasury bills or bonds) and commodities. Moreover, the Board of Directors has approved a strategic development plan for the period 2012-2016, i.e., a set of guidelines to stimulate further the growth of foreign investment.

According to the latest annual report, released in June 2013, the Chinese sovereign wealth fund had achieved a 10.6% annual return on investment at the end of 2012 and a growth rate of 5.2% since its inception in 2007.

In January 2012, CIC invested \$276 million in the British company Thames Water and in November another \$450 million in Heathrow Airport Group Holdings Ltd. In the energy sector, CIC spent \$300 million to purchase 10% of EP Energy, an American company, while in April 2012 it agreed to buy 5% (\$425 million) of Polyus Gold International Ltd. (PGIL), a Russian company owned by billionaire Suleiman Kerimov. This confirmed the Chinese wealth fund's expansion into Russia. CIC also bought a 7% (\$386 million) stake in the French company Eutelsat Communications SA and holds a 4.6% (\$187 million) interest in the Moscow Exchange, the largest exchange group in Russia, which runs trading markets in equities, bonds, derivatives and foreign exchange, amongst other activities. Finally, 49% of the fund's assets are composed of U.S. stocks and 28%, consist stocks from advanced economies, while emerging markets take the remaining 23%. The sectors targeted by CIC are those of finance (22%) and IT and computers (12%).

CIC is an active member of the International Forum of Sovereign Wealth Funds (IFSWF) and hosted the third annual meeting of that organization in Beijing in May 2011. Jin Liqun, Chairman of Board of Supervisors of CIC and its subsidiary Central Huijin Investment Ltd. (September 2008 - May 2013), presided over this meeting. CIC is proving to be a major player in the new investment vehicles known as sovereign wealth funds.

3. China's Successful Economic Statecraft: Strategic Motives for Trade Liberalization

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Economic integration and trade agreements have been defined as an increasingly important part of any country's economic statecraft.¹ Nowadays, Free Trade Agreements or FTAs are empirically the most successful tool used by countries in these regards. There is, however, an implicit political underpinning to economic statecraft, and the success of it - in this case economic integration through FTAs - does not depend uniquely on the magnitude of its economic effect. Instead, in order to really succeed it also needs the economic gains it engenders to translate into political opportunities. Economic statecraft, like trade agreements can also motivate key domestic reforms, encouraging growth and development. This is something that the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) has particularly aimed for when engaging in trade talks.

Economic growth specifically has been the main driver of poverty reduction in the developing world. In East Asia, progress in reducing poverty correlates strongly with its impressive growth performance. Countries that have opened themselves up to trade and investment have grown much faster than those which have not. There is today a widespread ideational acceptance that dependence on the capitalist global economy is the best or at least the quickest way of promoting economic growth. The Chinese leadership in Beijing adopted this standpoint long ago, but it was in 2004 when the Chinese government was advised to follow the new trend and to join the "small group" of FTAs after joining the "big group" of the WTO.

Beijing's leaders are indeed relative newcomers to economic integration agreements and only adhered to this within the last decade. In mid-2003, out of a list of 36 Asian FTAs completed or contemplated, China appeared only twice, once regarding the possible China-ASEAN FTA and the other time regarding the even looser ASEAN Plus Three (APT) discussions (Pangestu and Gooptu in Krumm and Kharas, 2003: 83). No bilateral FTA was on China's agenda at that time. However, things have changed dramatically, and in recent years FTAs within the Asia-Pacific have become a vigorous tool used by the People's Republic of China (PRC) towards a comprehensive national power. (Hoadley and Yang, 2007) This big change seems to be associated to a new assertive role in regional integration processes assumed by China.

The strategy shift was clearly noticeable. The PRC has been talking with about 30 countries within and outside the region regarding the establishment of several FTAs. The first Chinese FTAs partners in the Asia-Pacific were Chile, the ten-member ASEAN group and New Zealand. Moreover, it has been the PRC authorities the ones taking a step forward when proposing FTAs with Japan and South Korea more recently through the Northeast Asian framework called the Trilateral Cooperation Meetings among the three most advanced Asian countries. This attitude and proactive approach presented by China illustrates that in Beijing they have understood the kind of benefits an FTA entails.

China's interest in FTA negotiations appears to be consistent with economic and leverage motives. Furthermore, the FTAs across the region also serve China's security and diplomatic interests. "Inasmuch as enhancing the country's 'comprehensive national power' is central to Beijing's long-term strategy, economic initiatives like FTA negotiations are valued in Beijing for their positive political security implications" (Hoadley and Yang, 2007: 328).

From this it can be inferred that China's negotiators developed a realistic understanding of their limited influence in multilateral talks as is the case in APEC for example, which is dominated by the US. China therefore has become increasingly interested in the potential for an East Asian-exclusive regional liberalization, an arena in which it could play a stronger and more effective role. Other reasons are also important when establishing this new economic statecraft based on FTAs. First, they might help alleviate China's energy problem and enhance energy security, a key strategic goal. Closer economic relations with oil producers would help ensure more secure and diverse sources of energy. Second, FTAs might enhance the efficiency and productivity of China's somewhat old-fashioned command enterprises, partly because of the scale effect and partly because of rationalization and modernization would be stimulated by the new competition (Zweig and Bi, 2005: 25-38). Both would make China even more competitive in the changing world economy.

Here it is possible to expose the link between China's economic integration strategy and its necessity of maintaining high rates of economic growth. Indeed, trade helps an economy grow in several ways. It encourages economies to specialize and produce in areas where they have a relative cost advantage over other economies. Over time, this helps economies to employ more of their human, physical and capital resources in sectors where they get the highest returns in open

international markets, boosting productivity and the returns to workers and investors. Even in populous developing economies like China, trading with the world has proven to be the answer to accelerate economic domestic growth and development. China's experience highlights a lesson for all developing countries. All that is at least in theory, but in real life economic ideals often take a back seat to politics.

The central issue for the Chinese case is that in fact in the last 30 years increased openness dramatically increased competition in the domestic market, and that competition has contributed to a substantial transformation of the economy, particularly in the state-owned sector. The so called competitive effect of openness has brought great benefits to the PRC and it helps to understand why economic integration and free trade are being used by Beijing as a way to sustain growth rates. China recorded an unprecedented annual GDP growth rate of 9.8% through the last three decades and it relieved over 300 million people of poverty. It has become the second largest economy and the first largest trading nation of the world.

All this means more than mere numbers for the Chinese central government and the CCP tight grip over it. It has also brought the legitimacy necessary to support further reforms and policy-making regarding trade liberalization for an economy that depends largely on exports. In recent years, China's economic growth has remained respectable amid a difficult global environment, especially given that the PRC's economy is more integrated into the world economy than many other major emerging markets. Consequently, for an economy highly dependent on exports, the access to new markets in a competitive way is thus essential to maintain domestic growth. Economic integration and trade agreements become then an efficient tool used by developed countries and more recently, developing economies like the Chinese. China's most recent economic statecraft could be defined then as a way of assuring economic growth and development through trade liberalization.

China's first big regional initiative, namely the FTA with ASEAN already in action, has potential strategic significance. China's decision to enter into FTA talks with ASEAN was, to a great extent, a politically driven move (Qiu, 2005: 8-13). ASEAN is indeed crucial to the Chinese strategy of promoting multipolarity. An FTA with ASEAN give China a kind of bargaining tool over the smaller and economically dependent countries of Southeast Asia, while counter-balancing and diluting US efforts in the region. More important, ASEAN could become China's ally

in resisting the West's pressure on issues like political liberalization and democratic values, as some authors have pointed out. (Hoadley and Yang, 2007: 335) The allure of China's market for commodity-rich ASEAN countries is undeniable, and locking them into a larger integrated economy with China also plays well into Beijing's strategic and territorial interests over the South China Sea, over which it has several disputes with these same ASEAN nations. Thus, since 2005 the tariffs of more than 7000 items of both sides were eliminated either immediately or gradually. Already in 2007, China and ASEAN became the 4th trade partner to each other.

This progression was a direct outcome of the 1997 Asian Financial Crisis. Because of the vulnerability of their economies after the crisis, ASEAN countries were hoping to see China play a more important role in the regional economy. Consequently, within the ASEAN plus China forum context, the Chinese proposal in 1999 for a FTA was thus immediately accepted by the Southeast countries, and formally signed in November 2004, becoming effective since July 2005. Skeptics worried that an FTA with China could actually undermine the ASEAN Free Trade Area and Economic Community to be consolidated by 2015, but those fears seemed to have faded by now as the economic integration process appears to be on track. Still, many question whether China's real motivation to partner with ASEAN was actually domination, as opposed to integration. The fact that in recent years China has become much more assertive over its claims over the South China Sea waters and islands serves well that argument. Once China consolidated an FTA with ASEAN - thus locking their economies to China's into ever further interdependence - Beijing began to feel in a more confident position to assert its claims, pressuring and even bullying its smaller neighbors to the south.

The fact is that with its economic development, the PRC's allure has been enhanced. In recent years, Chinese leaders have paid visits to many countries in the broader Asia-Pacific region and Latin America, establishing trade and economic cooperation programs. The signal sent to the rest of the Pacific Rim was clear when China began three bilateral FTA negotiations in 2004, first with New Zealand and then with Australia and Chile. But what motivated the Chinese leadership to reach beyond the immediate Asian neighborhood for China's initial bilateral FTA partners?

Of course, not only economic aims but also diplomatic and strategic motives were in play. It is no secret that at a very initial stage of trade liberalization, Chinese leadership wished to avoid intimate dealing with a neighbor which China has been historically suspicious or which would provoke public protest, such as Japan; although China is

currently pushing for a Trilateral FTA with South Korea and Japan, but in reality a bilateral agreement only with South Korea is more likely to occur first. Hence, China chose to look for extra-regional partners as first steps to learn and build capacity on bilateral FTAs deals. The opportunities for expeditious negotiation with developed, experienced and accommodating partners were fulfilled by New Zealand, Australia and Chile. According to many authors, from all of the Asia-Pacific potential partners, these three countries are politically stable and a good investment haven. All three economies are complementary to the Chinese economy. They are also open, liberal and relatively small and therefore non-threatening. China's specific motives in each varied though.

Wellington's early recognition of China as a market economy was the decisive factor in choosing New Zealand as the first partner for FTA talks, agreement that was finally signed in 2008 after a long negotiation process. In Australia, China sees strategic value because this middle power has close relations with some Southeast Asian countries and perhaps can serve as a diplomatic bridge between Beijing and Washington; unfortunately the negotiations became too complex and stagnated, and the two countries have not been able to reach an agreement until today, although they are expected to finalize their talks by end of 2014. For its part, Chile has become crucial to China's economic strategy of penetrating South America and considering this small and stable economy is one of the freest in the world and a very experienced "hub" for economic integration in the Pacific. In fact, PRC's trade leaders made no secret of their intention to use the pact with Chile as a "bridge" and blueprint for later talks with other partners in the Pacific or Latin America, like the Mercosur countries or Mexico. In Beijing's view, Mexico was also an attractive partner, given its market size, oil resources and membership in the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA), therefore, it was no surprise that after Chile, Mexico was China's next transpacific FTA. This network of transpacific FTAs that China has been developing in the past decade is undoubtedly a counter strategy to American-led TPP.

Some striking features in China's FTAs are their diversity both in form and coverage, which appears to reflect pragmatism in recognizing differences across partners. Nevertheless, one can then go further into speculating that China seems to be establishing "clear linkages between seemingly conventional trade interest and China's interests in wider economic, diplomatic and strategic relationships." (Antikiewicz and Whalley, 2004: 14) For instance, given China's large economy and many suitors, bilateralism is not as economically imperative as it is for other trade-dependent Asia-Pacific countries. In addition, many signal China's FTAs as poor quality ones, leaving many items out of the negotiation table and not adhering to "WTO plus commitments."² Alan Oxley pointed out early on that what China is doing with its FTA strategy is an example of bad economics, but such trade policy is enabling it show itself as a regional leader. (Oxley, 2006) Indeed, China's motives might be more than primarily economic and are highly influenced and reinforced by political, diplomatic and strategic considerations.

Within this logic, it is important to pinpoint that China's concept of security has been broadening in parallel with similar re-conceptualization in the West. More attention is being paid to non-military security threats, such as global warming, mass unemployment, drugs and people trafficking, refugee flows, illegal migration, pandemic diseases, terrorism and most recently financial turmoil. This debate has also influenced the understanding of national security in Beijing. Chinese analysts accept that security now means "comprehensive security" (*zonghe anquan*). It no longer simply equals national defense and diplomacy and is no longer limited to the defense of national sovereignty and territorial integrity. In addition to the traditional military dimension of security, national security for the Chinese now includes, among other things, economic, political, societal, environmental, human and technological security (Lin, in Hoadley and Yang, 2007: 345). Most fundamental is the realization that without a strong economy, as most analysts have acknowledged, the grip and legitimacy of the CCP over the Chinese government is put into question. This understanding contributed to China's concept of "comprehensive national power," which now constitutes the foundation of China's foreign and domestic policies.

From another viewpoint, these interests are also consistent with China's desire to be perceived as a major but responsible power. Based on its declared aims of "peaceful rise" and "peaceful development," the PRC is keen to join the world economic system and to demonstrate that the country's growing prominence is an opportunity instead of a threat. In these regards, the leverage motive of using economic integration as a source of soft power comes as an evidence of Chinese attempts of exerting influence internationally. Hoadley and Yang address that China has been using FTA negotiations with many countries, including the ones mentioned above, as leverage because most of those trading partners are relatively small and therefore harmless. That is why it is believed that China chose to begin with countries such as Chile, New Zealand and ASEAN for its FTA strategy, allowing it also to gain FTA negotiation experience and train its bureaucratic cadres in this area.

In sum, despite being a latecomer, China has moved forward briskly in economic integration, whereas multilateral or bilateral agreements, thanks mainly to its new appreciation of utility of these kinds of pacts, especially the second kind to complement the multilateral negotiations that have progressed very slowly under WTO, APEC or ASEAN+3. While economic motives seem to be primary, careful observations of China's FTA initiatives show that it is using economic integration not only to open new markets, avoid exclusion from or discrimination in established markets and leverage reforms in domestic enterprises by exposing them to competition, albeit in a controlled fashion; but also for non-economic strategic implications. China has chosen its initial FTAs partners deliberately, beginning with ASEAN neighbors and moving on to small developed regional states with which Beijing's negotiators can gain experience with minimum risk. In terms of security and leverage motives, trade agreements are designed to strengthen the PRC's economic security. They also aim to consolidate

China's regional influence and ability to engage in strategic competition with other great powers, such as Japan but especially the United States and its TPP project. At the same time, FTAs can also be useful vehicles for China to promote its "peaceful development" theory. All these motives are intertwined, since economic development is so closely related to China's internal stability and external security. Economic integration is allowing the PRC to advance its core interests in foreign policy by validating its conceptualization of a peaceful rise to power.

1. The concept of Economic Statecraft has been widely discussed and developed by many analysts regarding of how countries construct and use economics as part of their international strategies. For a further understanding of the topic the reader can refer to authors like Steil, Benn and Robert E. Litan (2006) *Financial Statecraft-The Role of Financial Markets in American Foreign Policy* (New Heaven: Yale University Press); Blanchard, F.J., E.D. Mansfield and N.M. Ripsman (eds) (2000) *Power and the Purse: Economic Statecraft, Interdependence and National Security* (London: Frank Cass & Co., Ltd).

2. The obligations of a WTO member can be divided into two categories: (a) the general obligation to comply with WTO rules of conduct (the rule obligations); and (b) the individual obligation to reduce trade barriers with respect to specific goods and services (the market access obligations). In addition, some commitments that exceed the requirements of the WTO Multilateral Trade Agreements have been added in areas related to privatization, government procurement, intellectual property, trade in civil aircraft and publications. Such obligations have become known as "WTO-plus" obligations.

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4. GOVERNANCE IN CHINA

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Globalization has made governance an important issue especially in the recent decades as the role of the state has been redefined in significant ways. Globalization has imposed new conditions on the state to make their economies globally competitive on the one hand vis-a-vis manage the socio-economic interests of various groups at the domestic level. These forces working at various levels have made the structural transformation in the nature and formation of the state and the way state interact with global and national forces. The states which were highly authoritarian in nature especially in socialist country like China had underwent a series of transformation at the institutional level which has brought changes in the capacity and the structure of the state. Before the reforms, the economic activities were under the control of the state. State had controlled not only the types of products, but also the quantities, pricing and the distribution which was applied both in rural and industrial sectors. State power was highly centralised and the government, enterprise and institutional structure at the local level were controlled by the centre. There was a sort of social contract between state and society where social organizations had no autonomy and the distribution of human and financial resources was controlled by the state. The reforms have brought out a shift in the way state power was restructured. It led to shift in the two directions mainly : from a centralised to a more decentralised system, where the government at the local provincial, county levels are increasingly playing a more independent role. Second, evolving of system in which a different set of administrative organization have been set-up to perform administrative, economic and social service functions which were integrated into one. Thus, various administrative reforms were introduced from time to time to increase efficiency at the bureaucratic level. These reforms sought to transform the government's organizational structure, address the problem of over-staffing of personnel and increase the efficiency of public action.

There are various studies analysing the new relations between state power and market forces in China. Some have termed Chinese state 'developmental' or 'entrepreneurial' in nature while others have used

'corporatist' state as better suited to current changing situation. However, the key point is that the state has made a shift from authoritarian to one which is performing the role of facilitator of market forces at various levels. One of the important steps in this direction has been a series of institutional reforms introduced in the last few years which have given more autonomy to the local government to manage their economies and make them globally competitive. Blecher and Shue in their study have used the term developmental state to describe the commitment of officials at the county level to use local resources and apply their administrative discretion for the purpose of local economic growth and balanced local economic development.(Blecher, Marc and Vivienne Shue, 1996).In another study of Guanghan County government, they also introduced the idea of the 'entrepreneurial state' to analyse the behaviour of local government.(Blecher, M,1991) Through this, they have discussed the state which is more profit seeking. Rather than focusing on the enabling environment for independent economic enterprises, the entrepreneurial state itself becomes an economic player, engaging in production, creating new enterprises, procuring finance and competing for business. On the other hand, Jean C. Oi used the term 'local corporatist, state as a type of decentralised developmental state.(Oi, Jean, 1995) In this variation, local government officials at village, township and county levels promote local economic development by supporting local collective rural industrial enterprises through the provision of information, access to material and technology, through the redistribution of resources. In this model, local government officials become full- fledged economic actors, intervening in key investment decisions, to promote local political and economic interests. These case studies indicate the diversity in nature and form of the state, the increasing decentralization and growing complexity of local administrative political structures and processes. Given this complexity, it becomes quite clear as to how with the growing pace of global integration, the structural changes at the level of institutions can bought this problem of governance into sharp focus.

Since the 1978, the economic reforms have led to the changes in the way power was delegated to the local level. To boost local economy, the central government have loosened the economic control and regulatory restrictions with a goal of encouraging initiatives at the level of enterprises and localities. This led many scholars to present the 'decentralization' thesis to understand the centre-local relations in China. Decentralization usually implies the transfer of authority and responsibility for the public finances from the central government to the subsidiary and quasi-independent government organization and the

private sector. However, there are various indicators that present a case of China different from the standard model of decentralization. Though the PRC Constitution of 1982 mentioned the setting up of local people's Congresses at the administrative level of province, prefecture, county, township and the villages, the local leadership has to be approved and monitored from the above at the central level. It has not undermined the fundamental relationship between provinces and the centre rather it has increased the complexity. The centre expects provinces to act autonomously in many areas but to do so within the framework of central directives. Moreover, provinces in China are burdened by two conflicting constitutional responsibilities. While the provincial governments are under the leadership of the central government and carry the directives issued by the State Council, at another level, these are formally controlled by and responsible for executing the decisions of the Provincial level people's Congresses. Thus, in a way a province is divided between a responsibility for representing local interests and implementing central directives that sometimes clash with each other.(Chung Jae Ho and Tao-Chiu Lam, 2010). Centre monitors the political process at the local level by stipulating policy targets regarding economic development and this often become the criteria to evaluate cadres' performance. Often it is reported that the local governments are able to retain a greater portion of their revenues. Moreover, at many places, the local authorities are able to mobilize resources through foreign investment, foreign loans, and various administrative fees. The income generated from these sources has been counted outside the state sanctioned budget and thus give them functional autonomy outside the state control. . This is particularly the case in the relatively prosperous cities and provinces such as Guangdong, Shanghai and Tianjin. Provincial economic strategy did not confine to coastal provinces rather western and inland provinces, despite unequal central policies also adopted various approaches to make their economies more efficient in nature. But this freedom at the local level has also made it difficult for the central government to enforce national policy in a coherent manner and to redistribute resources across regions and social groups.(Howell, Jude, 2006) Sometimes, it can also lead to the tension between centrally driven national policies and local initiatives as one can witness the intense rivalry among different local interests.

Provinces also gained new budgetary powers , including the ability to raise their own funds and manage their own budgets. They have also become responsible to raise funds for investment in infrastructure development and other enterprise management and also pay wages and perform social services functions. Each province determines its own ways

of dividing budget responsibilities between itself and its sub-provincial governments and sets broad outlines for the budgets of counties. As a result, in the last few years, provinces have attracted huge foreign investments in infrastructure development. Furthermore, given the increasing value of land, it has become a much contested commodity between various structures of local government. Often, local government has made changes in the use and ownership of land. Local governments in rapidly industrializing regions are keen to invest heavily in infrastructure development from local budgets and establish industrial and commercial development parks offering preferential policies and tax rebate to investors. It has also created a big problem of fastening the process of urbanization and the loss of agricultural land which has been used extensively to generate revenue and economic resources. These kinds of issues can bring forth the problem of huge urban expansion at the cost of agrarian development and large scale social disparities. Under these circumstances, given the complexity of ownership structure, the county and township governments gain more autonomy and thus have a stronger bargaining power. The policies formulated at the central level normally have an adverse impact on the people in the poverty-stricken regions. Since these regions are more dependent on the central state for fiscal transfer and revenue generation, the pressure to meet with policy targets have been watched more closely there than in more developed regions.

Another problem which makes the control of local government difficult is the expansion of local bureaucracy. There has been a practice of overstaffing of the government personnel as jobs are often created for the friends and relatives. However, in many cases, local level bureaucratic expansion is done as a response to tasks and assignment which are considered to be handled by people who have specific skills and expertise. Once new local offices and posts are created to perform certain core functions, it becomes very difficult to eliminate them. Besides, the studies indicate that to generate employment many ad-hoc offices are set up at the local levels which require extra-permanent staff. As the number of township agencies and personnel increase, it leads to the increase in local administrative expenditures and wage bills for government staff. All this increases the burden on township and then transferred to local population. In many cases, local officials and bureaucrats always manage to find ways to evade central regulations when they conflict with local vested interest. These socio-economic disparities and the central-local relations have become a priority area of concern before the central leadership. It was reflected in the Decision

of the CPC on Strengthening the Party's ability to Govern, which was passed by the Fourth Plenum of the 16 Central Committee in 2004.

Given the varied social and political interests, it has increasingly become difficult to establish a uniform state driven developmental project as dictated from the above. It is quite reflected in the number of social protests are taking place in society led by various social groups like women, migrants, unemployed laid-off workers, landless farmers, non-hukou residents, minorities nationalities in various regions. It also indicates the discriminatory policies in favour of some which are creating a group of vulnerable section at the social level. These social and economic interests are making the task of the state difficult to impose a developmental agenda without taking interest of the local people into account. There is an interesting nexus between government officials and economic elites but the outcome is not developmental in nature. These social ties have not essentially led to the cohesion of state power and social forces. More often, entrepreneurs seeking resources and information from government officials develop personalised and clientelistic relations with individual cadres. It goes to the extent that the bribes are given for economic gains like securing contracts and thus developmental priorities become second to the individual gains. State itself became a source of economic rents and bureaucrats compete to purchase promotions and positions. So, corruption within the Party administration is becoming a serious problem to tackle before the regime.

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5. How China's Traditional Harmony Thought Affects Chinese Foreign Policies

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Cultural values shaping the national psychology and identity of a country that have important influence on state leaders to choose their foreign policies.

How to choose the foreign policies of a national leader largely depend on their awareness and views on international issues. For example, if the leader of the big country using "the law of the jungle" to look at the international relationship, they would think that big country should control small countries, if a small country does not obey him even against him, he'll have to use strength to control it or conquer it, superpower is bound to control the world. If the leaders of a large country look at international relationship with a perspective of harmony, peace, cooperation, they would think that big countries should respect small countries, small countries also should respect the big countries, every countries should respect and cooperate with each other, with the development of coexistence, the big powers should not bully a small country, not to interfere in the internal affairs of small countries. If there are conflicts between countries, they should try to consultations and negotiations. Chinese traditional harmonious thought advocates doing so at foreign policy.

Hexie means reasonable and appropriate. Reasonable is to do things according to the law and truth. Appropriate is to make things right, well-proportioned, just right, things achieved coordination by uncoordinated, achieved symmetry by asymmetrical, achieved balance by unbalance. If these ideas be applied to international relations, it will advocate rational approach in dealing with international issues. Under normal circumstances, countries should apply co-ordination, consultation, balancing, cooperation and mutual benefit approaches to the problem as much as possible; should not use the ways of extreme, one-sided dealing with problems. The thoughts of Hexie have been obviously reflected in foreign strategy and policy of China. It is embodied in the Chinese diplomatic principles, behavior and speech of the leader.

1.Harmony and different

The thoughts of Hexie show that there is diversity in universe. Differences does not must mean contradictions, sometimes differences may evolve into conflicts, but sometimes it is a necessary condition for a harmony, there are a number of examples in nature and human society that the different things work in close cooperation. The unity in diversity in universe is the basis for generating of new things. It was the Confucian philosophy to accommodate divergent views. Confucius said that "a gentlemen should have harmony and different", it means that a gentleman has a different point of view without blindly going along with others and be able to live in harmony.

This view has been applied to the Chinese foreign strategy that Chinese Government advocate whether countries big or small shall respect the cultural diversity and all different countries should respect and complement each other, to achieve a "Win-win situation and Coexistence".

Chinese government put forward "The Five Principles of peaceful coexistence" in the 1950s: "Mutual respect for sovereignty and territorial integrity, mutual non-aggression, mutual non-interference in internal affairs, equality and mutual benefit and peaceful coexistence". Since half a century, "The Five Principles of peaceful coexistence" have been accepted by most countries in the world, they became important criteria for regulating international relations.

Former Chinese President Jiang Zemin described the concept of "Harmony and Different" of China's diplomacy in a speech when he visited the United States on 24, December 2002. He said that the Chinese thinker Confucius proposed the ideas that "gentleman should

have harmony and different" two thousand years ago, harmony without uniformity, different without conflict with each other; harmoniously coexistence and growth, be different but complement each other. "Harmony and Different" is an important law of social issues and social development and also is the guideline for people to follow in daily life skills and actions. It is a truth to help coordinate the development of human civilizations. We advocate that different civilizations, social systems and development models should interact and learn from each other and compete with each other peacefully in seeking the common ground and the common development.

Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao delivered a speech at Harvard University in December 2003, he said that reason why China chose a road of peaceful rise that is different from some developed countries. He said because we have our own culture, a kind of long-term culture. The core of this culture is harmony that is very important in our culture. Of course we have the "Harmony and Different". This difference is to complement each other, to learn from each other, rather than a source of conflict.

Recently, the Chinese Foreign Ministry spokesman made a speech on the EU decisions to ban Iran oil exports to their member states and apply sanction to Central Bank of Iran, he said that China has always advocated solving international disputes through dialogue and consultation. China has always opposed unilateral sanctions against Iran, not even in favor of expanding the sanctions. Pressuring and sanctions against Iran are not fundamental solutions to the Iranian issue, but will make the problem more complicated, serious, and is not conducive to regional peace and stability. Under the current circumstances, the relevant parties should strengthen dialogue and cooperation; properly solve the Iranian problem through negotiations.

On Syria, the Chinese Foreign Ministry spokesman said that it is the only way for constructive dialogue and cooperation to promote and protect human rights; it is not conducive to resolve the differences by some countries putting pressure on Syria using certain resolutions.

China's Hexie thought tells us that it is the best way to use negotiation, dialogue to resolve conflicts between countries. When a country's internal affair goes wrong, other countries should not stir up trouble and take the opportunity to confuse its situation, should not interfere in its internal affairs.

2. “Big country should be modest”

Lao Tzu “Daodejing” said that big country should be like living in downstream rivers where hundred streams converge. Being modest to small country, a big country can gain small country’s confidence. Similarly, being modest to big country, a small country can gain big country’s confidence. Whether countries big or small should be modest and respect each other.

Sea can hold thousands of rivers due to its lowest position. Because of this, sea becomes the king of the rivers and no river ever can compete with it. This told us that if you are a big and modest and no others can compete with you. Human society will have future hopes if they can peacefully achieve co-operation, co-existence and co-prosperity instead of competing with each other and killing each other.

This view is applied to the China foreign strategy, China would advocate that big countries should not judge other’s countries by their own values and political systems, and should not contempt, combat or even eliminate those countries that are not up to the big countries own value standards. Different countries should respect and complement each other, to achieve a “Win-Win situation and Coexistence”. China’s foreign policy related to his neighboring countries and the countries of Asian African and Latin American shows this idea.

In dealing with neighboring countries, Chinese government also raises “harmony neighbors, rich neighbors, and good neighbors”. Chinese government initiates the six-party talks on Korean nuclear issue, shelves arguments on South Sea Islands, strengthens cooperation relationship with ASEAN, develops the Shanghai Cooperation Organization , and expands exchanges and cooperation with India and Pakistan.

3. “The highest place is not the safest roost”

The Hexie thought insists that people should look at things dialectically and from all things considered, without going to extremes. “Yijing” said that if a bird flies to a very high place, it will have a disaster. Extreme states cannot be sustained. Lao Tzu “Daodejing” said that the strongest thing is easy to be aging.

Lao Tzu said that “the person who wants to stand tall with a tiptoe cannot stand up; the person who wants to get a big leap end up walk slowly; Self-assertive would fight in isolation; Self-righteous would be

notorious; self-aggrandizement would not success in the end; Conceit would not help to be leaders.”

“Elasticity can maintain integrity; Flexible but can be straight; the low land (Modest) can hold more water; Removing the old and disadvantages can produce new things; Taking less can get more; greed will invite scourge.

These ideas told us when a country goes to its peak; it should understand that “The highest place is not the safest roost”. When a country is growing bigger, It should not go the road of hegemony.

Chinese President Hu Jintao delivered a speech at the United Nations on September 23, 2009, in which he put forward the new security concept of “To hold on the Mutual trust, mutual benefit, equality and coordination.”

Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao said in a meeting with foreign journalists on March 14, 2010 that China's development will not harm any country in the world, we will never seek a superpower position as we are a developing country, not a super power even if China becomes a developed country, and China will never seek hegemony!

Chinese Culture Minister Cai Wu took a speech "Chinese culture and China's peaceful development" at the Woodrow Wilson Center in Washington DC of United States on 21, September 2011. He said that culture is the face of a nation even as well as the soul of a nation. Chinese culture based on human relations, pays attention to self-cultivation, concerns for family, loves of country, cares about the world, and benefits the people. Chinese people not only practice these principles on themselves but also extend far beyond, showing the broad and deep feelings of brotherhood and compassion. Based on this character of national culture, China has chosen the road of peaceful development, internal harmonious society, and an external harmonious world. We hope people all over the world would live under the same sky with freedom, equality, harmony and happiness and share the results of peace and development.

Chinese have a maxim that is "if you don't offend me, I don't bother you; if you attack me, and endanger the safety of my life, I will certainly counterattack."

Hexie (Harmony) is not advocating a neutral, unprincipled compromise, or a peacemaker or an appeasement policy. When

necessary and reasonable, it also advocates taking the just war against an unjust war, opposing violence with just violence. For example, people took self-defense against a war of aggression and the world-wide anti-fascist war of Second World War . Harmony value advocates “curbing violence with reasonable violence, using extreme ways and means properly”. Chinese saying goes: "if you don't offend me, I don't bother you; if you attack me, I will certainly counterattack." This means that we do not infringe on other people, but when others endanger our lives and property, we must resist, in self-defense war.

4. Reasonable Struggle

The value of harmony insists that nonantagonistic conflicts should be handled through consultation, coordination, and balanced means to achieve equilibrium. But in certain cases, such as foreign invasions, one should firmly fight back in self-defense and counter injustice with a just war. As the old Chinese saying goes, “Those who do not offend will not be offended. Those who offend will be offended (ren bu fan wo wo bu fan ren, ren ruo fan wo wo bi fan ren, 人不犯我我不犯人, 人若犯我我必犯人).”

In the face of insults, oppression, and aggression from other countries, people should be brave and succeed in their struggles by leveraging political wisdom and other means. Sun Tzu's *The Art of War* (Sunzi bingfa, 《孙子兵法》) elaborates on using wisdom to fight against the enemy. Thus, traditional Chinese culture includes not only Confucianism, which focuses on the cultivation of virtues and the maintenance of ethics, but also the Art of War for military strategy and tactics.

For instance, in the case of the South China Sea, where the Philippines' provocations threatened China's territorial sovereign right to the islands, the Chinese government tried to solve the issue via diplomatic means and peaceful negotiations. However, to defend the integrity of state sovereignty, territorial waters, islands, and islets, China may engage in struggle if necessary.

5. Building a Harmonious World

The Social ideals of the harmony (Hexie) thought is Universal harmony in the world. Confucian classic "Book of Rites" wrote : “The future world will be public and Universal harmony in the world.”

Chinese President Hu Jintao proposed the concept of “building a harmonious world” at the meeting of the world leaders at the United Nations in May, 2005.

President Hu Jintao said that “building a harmonious world is a long-term foreign strategy of China rather than a blank check.”

"Building a harmonious world" directly reflects the traditional Chinese Hexie thought, this formulation is unprecedented in the international community.

In fact, a state of harmony is not a distant fantasy; it can be realized in real life as long as we try our best. Countless facts in Universe and natural have proved this truth.

Building a harmonious world, is to make every civilization survive well so that every member in the society of different civilization will live vigorously.

In a summary, Chinese harmony foreign strategy are quite different from the power politics and “the law of the jungle”; it provides us a new idea to solve international conflicts. The harmony thought of China and foreign policy of peace will contribute to world peace in a long run.

China was an agricultural country with a long history. The highest requirements of the ancient Chinese farmers was the halcyon days, this also helps to cultivate the spirit of peace and harmony. With no contention, emphasizing coordination and balance, it is this character has created a unique value orientation of Chinese culture. Harmony, tolerance, patience, these spirit have shaped the character of the Chinese people, so Chinese people tend to harmony, peace, cooperation and reasonable struggle Confucianism, Taoism and Buddhism are ubiquitous penetration of pacifism.

6. China's Internal Dynamics and Great Power Compulsions in a Changing World Order

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China celebrated its 65th anniversary as a 'People's Republic' on the first of October this year. Its revolution, over these past decades has been, perhaps the most consequential revamping in the political culture of a major state in the past century. As such, the PRC's founding constitutes one of the modern world's most momentous transformations of an ancient civilizational state into a re-emerging regional superpower. Thus has that country's transformation, under the Communist Party of China (CPC) also reshaped the contours of the global strategic landscape. The internal and external dimensions of the Chinese Revolution are dialectically interrelated.

China's transformative impact on the global strategic landscape

Yet, as momentous as China's transformative re-emergence has been, the bottom-line of its impact in the global realm does not fundamentally alter Samuel Huntington's conception of the power structure of the international system as indelibly 'uni-multipolar.' This is due to US military-strategic global supremacy. America's re-emergence as a hydrocarbon producer reinforces its superpower incumbency. Otherwise, military primacy has long been a depreciating currency in working the will of great powers as American experiences amply show. Thus, overall, one might imagine an over-arching point-counterpoint of 'G2' *co-opertition* between China and the United States as the defining dynamic at the global level.

From Beijing's vantage point, regional rather than global primacy would seem to inform its overriding preoccupation given the global shift in the

world's economic centre of gravity from west to east. Within such changed Asia-centric geoeconomic-political circumstances, regional hegemony seems sufficient in securing China's great power strategic compulsives with global resonance. These stretch from the central Eurasian entry into Europe to the Indian Ocean Rim and Indo-Pacific including the 'seas around China.'

The contiguity of this vast transcontinental region intersects with China's internal dynamics which, in spite of overwhelming Han ethnic supremacy, remains contested terrain along peripheries comprising Tibet, Xinjiang, Hong Kong and Taiwan.¹ These 'national questions' pertaining to resolving the precise nature of a 'One China' identity reflects how China's post-revolutionary transformation remains a 'work in progress.' And the outcome is uncertain as China enters yet another and more complicated era of post-revolutionary transition. It is one resulting from an aging demographic as its economy graduates up the value chain of production while mandating greater priority to consumption rather than export-driven geoeconomic neo-mercantilism.² In terms of China's internal dynamics over the past 65 years, one outcome that seems to have been little understood, is how the 1949 communist victory turned Marxism-Leninism on its ideological head. China's revolution reflects how diverse are the roads to capitalism.

Communist China's capitalist dictatorship: class struggle revisited

Communism, with 'Chinese characteristics' has been the PRC's vehicle for integrating into the world economy – and, in the process, to an authoritarian state capitalism. What started out as the victory of largely rural peasant masses mobilized into the evangelically regimented forces of ideological utopianism by Mao Zedong has, over decades of dialectical class evolution, given us the world's first communist dictatorship of the plutocratic bourgeoisie! In the process, the cost of Maoist mass mobilizational utopianism aimed at avoiding such a scenario was nothing short of catastrophic: the loss of an estimated 30 million lives. Yet, there is a more universal story here in the global expansion of middle class strata and plutocratic elites the world-over (and yes, there are numerous roads to plutocracy, ostensibly liberal democratic and authoritarian alike, with the end result being the same).

China's bourgeois revolution, flowing from Maoist upheavals wrought by communism's victory over Guomindang nationalism, is but a unique variation along a theme that has unfolded the world-over, post-cold war. In reality, as opposed to the idealism of ideology, socio-economic changes

guarantee the permanence of a class-based as opposed to a 'classless society.' This paradoxical contradiction is one of the globally emblematic features of the communist experience.

In the former Warsaw Pact and the Soviet Union, Marxist-Leninist 'vanguards of the masses' became ideological justifications for intellectual elite class dictatorships which midwived many a bureaucratic bourgeoisie in the 'nomenklatura' that emerged throughout the bloc. The nomenklatura organically mutated into the post-communist successor ruling classes in variations along themes of 'crony capitalism.' From this post-communist readjustment in social forces there emerged the plutocratic oligarchs. In spite of the survival of the CPC as China's ruling party, China has not managed to avoid this evolution either given the eventual exhaustion of Maoist versions of 'permanent revolution.'

China's post-Mao elite under 'getting rich is glorious' Deng Xiaoping attempted a transition to that which had occurred in the former Soviet bloc, except (lessons learned?) they ensured the existential survival of the communist party – in form if not in substance. Ironically, it was to prevent the 'top-down,' bureaucratizing ruling class calcification that occurred in the USSR and in eastern Europe that continually motivated The Great Helmsman's permanent revolutions of elite shake-up within the Central Committee and Politburo. Here, Maoism had much in common with Trotskyism. In any event, such sociopathic orchestrated upheavals were no doubt a convenient means of also preserving the neo-patrimonialist personality cult dominance of Mao himself. However, Mao was ultimately in the minority.³

After his disastrous 'Great Proletarian Cultural Revolution,' the party-state coalition of forces whom he had forced onto the defensive amid his youth-mobilizing onslaughts, regained control. The result is the ruling state-capitalist communist party-state that is today's PRC. Together with the USSR-Soviet bloc collapse and diverse experiences unfolding in Cuba and North Korea, the PRC journey is one that calls for a radical reinterpreting of the Marxist scenario wherein working class and middle class are actually one in the same in as much as 'working class' defines all who must work for a living, not a stereotypically lunch-pail carrying factory worker of 'proletarian' vintage. As such, 'working-middle classes' throughout the world represent complexities of socio-economic stratification that defy mechanically ideological partisan political strategies of ascendancy within given polities.

Ethnic imperialism or the cultural pluralism of Minzu Tuanjie?

The challenge for China is whether or not it can retain its authoritarian

state-capitalist model as the guarantor of systemic stability while uncompromisingly resisting some variation along the theme of democratic adjustment – let's call it *participatory governance* for the sake of normative universality! This seems an unrelenting predicament. It occurs amid pressures of aging demographic trends interacting with and propelling socio-economic change heightening contradictions within a system seemingly unable to accommodate socio-cultural safety valves for 'letting off steam' – either within the ethnic 'Han Core' or within its multi-ethnic/national peripheries.

Peripheral instabilities, in turn, condition the dynamics of Beijing's regional international relations with wider Sino-US confrontational possibilities. Here, it is important to factor in the 'devolutionary' trajectory of US foreign policy and national security strategy within the context of US President Barack Obama's rebalancing 'Pivot to Asia' (something of a misnomer since the 'pivot' is more a matter of shifting emphasis within Asia: from the Mideastern Southwest to the East Asia/Indo-Pacific). Predominantly Uygher-Muslim Xinjiang, for example, borders on the essentially unstable Central Asian Turkic borderlands where Beijing is pushing 'soft power' expansionism via its maritime and continental Silk Road geoeconomic diplomacy.

Yet, it pursues a 'one-size-fits-all' internal strategy of top-down, coercive assimilationism. Non-Han minorities must submerge their identities into secular Han majoritarianism. And this is in spite of existing guarantees wherein the *Minzu Tuanjie* notion of 'unity of the various nationalities of China' could be elevated into a non-western indigenous principle of democratic cultural pluralism in the service of China's 'peaceful rise' at home and abroad. Indeed, were Beijing to interpret *Minzu Tuanjie* as the cornerstone of a 'cultural autonomy' approach to 'one country, two systems' applied to the politico-cultural particularisms of Tibet, Xinjiang, Hong Kong and Taiwan as opposed to being rigidly fixated on territorial-based 'regional autonomy,' it might stand a better chance of transcending recurring historical chaos-stability cycles burdening the civilizational history of China.

This historical contingency, in turn, intersects with another possibility locating the PRC future within 'Greater China.' This has to do with the intriguing question of whether or not the rise of the PRC does not, at different level, represent yet another variation along authoritarian paths to modernity that have produced more democratizing Chinese societies in Singapore and on Taiwan – again, questions of political culture-cum-cultural autonomy. Indeed, there is a line of thinking that assumes that China's communist totalitarianism might similarly mutate

into a loosening of the reigns of the party-state in similar fashion as authoritarianism transitioned into something less than one-party hegemony in Singapore and especially on multiparty Taiwan.

Mainland China is but one component(albeit the largest) of a larger *Pax-Sinica* awaiting consolidation into a regional East Asian subsystem. Hence, the importance of how Beijing, in its fixation on consolidating the primacy of 'the Han core' in relation to peripheral minorities, manages future scenarios involving Tibet, Xinjiang, Hong Kong and, ultimately, Taiwan. This, in turn, may have a bearing on China's relations in the wider Asia-Pacific. That is, providing tendencies toward Han ethnic hegemonism, internally, does not propel an expansionist Chinese nationalism that has the effect of mobilizing the rest of the region against it as seems already apparent in East and South China Sea tensions.

If, for example, in the interest of consolidating a joint class dictatorship on the mainland and on Hong Kong, the liberal democratic political *culture* on the island is compromised rather than accommodated, why would Taiwan's political class, including indigenous Taiwanese ethnic nationalists, expect Beijing to respect their autonomous political *culture*? Would it not be naïve in the extreme for them to trust Taiwan's fate to Beijing's tender mercies? But Hong Kong's scenario need not be a harbinger for Taiwan.

Hong Kong's pan-Democrats may ultimately have to come to terms with constraints of The Basic Law offset by 'people power' mobilization. Beijing, on the other hand, will have to accommodate Hong Kong's culture of liberal freedoms where there have been increasing signs of these coming under threat. It has already compromised an integrationist cross-Straits settlement which must ultimately accommodate Taiwan's autonomous political culture, the island's de facto independence and multiparty reality. Local Taiwanese resistance to a cross-Straits traderegime has already become a reality with Beijing-Hong Kong tensions adding fuel to the fire.

Silk Route diplomacy and Asia's evolving balance of power

Yet, within the parameters of global economic interdependence with profoundly federalist systemic implications, the logic of Sino-Taiwanese 'One China' economic integration is unassailable. This, in turn, implicates Beijing's broader regional intentions regarding the possible internationalization of Han cultural imperialism in the economic sphere of the 'seas around China' linked to its more persuasive Silk Route diplomacy. If so, to what extent are prevailing 'Middle Kingdom' cultural

compulsives in the strategic realm suggestive of a manipulative 'carrot and stick'*neo-tributarianism* between China and its neighbors in the greater Asia-Pacific and in Central Asia via its co-leadership with Russia of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO)?

Such a query seems justified as Beijing gears up to launch an Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank to underwrite its continental and maritime Silk Route agenda in greater Asia on the heels of the BRICS launched 'new development bank' at Fortaleza, Brazil. On this score, Moscow resisted Beijing's desire to establish, from scratch, an SCO development bank. China and Russia are fundamentally strategic rivals in Central Asia.⁴ This could complicate Xi Jinping's Silk dreams. An SCO bank under Chinese terms would have been one more instrument in what has to be considered a strategy of internationalizing the yuan through institutionalizing Beijing-controlled or influenced development financing mechanisms.

These are intended as outlets for deploying the humongous currency reserves of Chinese state-capitalism in what can only be interpreted as the external power projection of China's uniquely communist dictatorship of its 'haut bourgeoisie.' Where such power projections generate push-backs is in the strategic sphere of competition for off-shore resources in the South and East China Seas. Here, there is a discernable countervailing containment dynamic taking shape. This is reflected in increasingly close Indo-Japan relations accompanied by the ASEAN consolidating itself into an economic community in 2015.

These developments might also be interpreted in devolutionary terms as a new Asian balance of power system in the making. It will reflect the more burden-sharing motivation behind an evolving US foreign policy tendency (hotly contested by neocons and others within the foreign policy establishment) bent on promoting 'nation-building at home' as America becomes less 'white' and arrogantly imperialist and more demographically minority-majority. This emerging America will not be 'cruising for a bruising' with anyone, least of all China. But it is not likely to abdicate global leadership either. This is why a readjustment in Japan's defense posture as a maritime counterweight to China, without Tokyo revisiting 'greater East Asian co-prosperity sphere' strivings, is in Washington's interest as is a Tokyo-Delhi alignment. Japan's military, after all, is Asia's strongest.

What this means is that in Asian security terms, Washington's preference is for a posture wherein it avoids being in the forefront of an

encircling Sino-containment diplomacy while engaging Beijing more cooperatively on other fronts – also factoring in the realities of Sino-American economic interdependence – the stuff of ‘coopertition.’ The Asian balance of power system that emerges will be more indigenously autonomous while the US plays ‘off-shore balancer’ from the Persian Gulf, including the Indian Ocean to the Pacific Rim.

For both China and the US, with Russia looming in the equation, the real sticking point will be central Eurasia. In whatever way the Ukraine crisis becomes resolved along with the rearranging of the geopolitical map of the Levant emerging out of the Syria-Iraq sectarian civil war and the post-occupation transition in Afghanistan, it is in the national interests of Beijing, Moscow and Washington to arrive at a cooperative security accommodation. And here, there would seem to be a constructive role for India to play within its RIC ministerial with Russia and China linked to the BRICS alignment.

The bottom-line would be the fashioning of a *Eurasian Security Community* based on a NATO-Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO)-SCO burden-sharing partnership. China along with Russia and the US would be its apex guarantors (which begs another question for another time: far-reaching UN, including UNSC, reform). But, among other things, for this to happen, India needs to be upgraded to full membership in the SCO, something China has resisted but which would seem increasingly in its interest as Delhi balances between BRICS-RIC and a Washington-Tokyo axis. China’s internal dynamic impinging on the SCO resides in the stability of Xinjiang where again, a policy of democratic cultural pluralism within the context of Minzu Tuanjie might be considered rather than the current repressive policy of conflating legitimate Uygher concerns with Islamist jihadism in what amounts to reinforcing ‘the pressure cooker’ within the periphery, a scenario that can only lead to an explosion.

Non-interference in ‘internal affairs’: A diplomacy of intimidation?

In the final analysis, do such suggestions amount to ‘interfering’ in China’s internal affairs and, in so doing, threatening its territorial integrity? This is a China policy question for the world over as well as for the Chinese in as much as it interfaces China’s internal dynamics and strategic compulsives as a great power. This is where, in effect, Beijing effectively interferes in the internal policy and political affairs of other countries by imposing its ‘internal affairs’ onto the internal agendas of other states with which it has diplomatic and economic relations.

Whereas there are legitimate state-to-state inter-governmental bilateral reasons of diplomacy for accommodating Beijing's 'One China' hang-ups, it is unacceptable that such considerations should be carried over into the non-governmental and private spheres of civil society in countries with which China interacts with.

When a country like South Africa, for example, feels compelled to toe Beijing's line on the Dalai Lama in regard to private affairs relating to the Nobel Peace Prize, this is not only a serious infringement on South Africa's sovereignty, it subordinates South Africa's strategic autonomy and foreign policy independence to the dictates of an external power, something South Africa would be loath to do in its relations with the US and the west generally. In effect, in the post-cold war era, the rise of China accompanied by its compulsions and concerns that other countries must factor into their calculus, resurfaces questions concerning 'non-alignment' and 'positive neutrality,' especially among countries in the global South that must navigate delicate balancing between relations with China (and Russia in some cases) and the west – especially where BRICS is concerned.

However, these are issues for another time. But they are in need of serious exploration as China's internal cohesion will have a major bearing on its own room for maneuver in advancing its strategic compulsives over time. For, on the mainland home front, today's inheritors of the legacy of Mao are already having their hands full in politically navigating yet another transition as China enters the ranks of an aging demographic with challenging economic implications as the PRC contemplates another 65 years. Thus does Mao's permanent r/evolution live on.

(This article expands on a commentary titled "PRC 65: A Marxist journey along the Capitalist Road," a guest column of the *Studying China-Africa Relations* blog of the Centre for Chinese Studies, Stellenbosch University, 30 September 2014.)

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7. Xinjiang Unrest: Need for a New Look

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Since the time it came to public attention in the 1990s, there have always been differing perceptions about the conflict involving the Uighur in China's Xinjiang province. While Beijing claims Uighurs' fight for a separate Muslim homeland as terrorism, a number of assessments regard this as a result of repression and excessive human rights violations by the state or a ruse by China to crush dissent. Few scholars implicate ethnicity or religion or both as casual factors in the conflict. Some have also discussed identity shaping the grass-root conditions that sustain a "low-level" insurgency and sporadic violence in Xinjiang.¹

In this article, I argue that the roots of the conflict in Xinjiang lie in the perceived or real threat to minority identity of the Uighur which is due to government policies towards national minorities in general in the name of national integration. Second, and following from the above, Xinjiang issue could be transforming itself from a separatist conflict to one which is a contestation for an equitable stake in development and economic prosperity along with a struggle to preserve native identities. This is derived from the nature and the scale of the incidents especially after the 2008 Beijing Olympics and from an assessment of the capability of the Uighur groups including the East Turkistan Islamic Movement (ETIM), also going by the name, the Turkistan Islamic Party (TIP), which China accuses as being responsible for most of the violence in Xinjiang. These incidents reflect anguish and discontent at a local level more than organized acts of terrorism.

ETIM, which exists mostly outside China – mainly in Pakistan, has very limited resources and personnel and scant support in Xinjiang to be a credible threat to China on its own. Groups like the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan (IMU) and Al Qaeda support the cause of ETIM. But these groups have priorities and problems of their own, apart from the Xinjiang issue. There is no indication that any of the other overseas Uighur organizations including the World Uighur Congress (WUC), is inclined or capable to carryout terrorist attacks in China at present.

Culture and Identity

Instead of terrorism per se, the Xinjiang conflict could be explained in terms of identity-dissonance that is sustaining due to state policies which feeds the grievances and the perception of marginalization among the Uighur. In other words, Xinjiang conflict can be explained as being rooted in the perceived or real injustice arising out of unfulfilled minority needs and interests which has resulted in incomplete integration. Failure to address minority group's fundamental needs, to provide space for participation in governance, and to ensure an equitable distribution of resources and benefits² feeds the perception of injustice leading in turn to the identity dissonance which is driving and sustaining the conflict.

Threats to Identity & Conflicts

How is a given individual or society's identity threatened? There is no easy answer as it is difficult to distinguish a "perceived threat" from what can be objectively assessed as really threatening. Often real threats may not be "accurately seen" whereas perceived threats may not be real, but still have real effects.³ A particular society could feel threatened when there is a perception that it's "we" identity is being put in danger or when its ability to sustain its essential character - including its traditional patterns of language, culture, association, religion and national customs among others⁴ - or reproduction of those identities is at risk.

Threats to the reproduction of a society can occur through the sustained application of "repressive measures" against the expression of the identity of the particular society. For instance, if the organizations for reproducing language, religious and culture are forbidden to operate, identity will not be inherited by next generations.⁵ In practice, these threats may occur where there are prohibitions or restrictions on the use of language, names and dress; closure of places for education and worship; and even the killing or deportation of members of the particular society as has been the case with the Uighur in Xinjiang.

Additionally, some policies and commitments to nation-building by the state tend to be seen not only as violations of human rights, but also as threats to identity by the minority community. Under these conditions, minorities do not perceive their current political status as "legitimate," which explains the reason why some minorities demand national self-determination and even resort to terrorist activities under particular circumstances.⁶ In other words, it is the real or perceived threat to identities that generate the discontent of the disadvantaged minorities at the very root level.

Thus, "identity conflicts emerge with intensity when a community, in response to unmet basic need for social and economic security, resolves to strengthen its collective influence and to struggle for political recognition."⁷ Such conflicts are reflections of a more fundamental political and social distrust, borne out of a community's experience of economic inequity, political discrimination and human rights violations.⁸

The distrust which has now led to militancy in Xinjiang could be rooted in the neglect, repression, official insensitivity to local concerns and forcible attempts to impose uniformity of social behaviour on the Uighur. Protests and violence in Xinjiang could be seen as manifestations of a social movement by the Uighur competing against the state and the majority community, which are perceived as threats to the Islamic and Uighur identity, instead of being acts of terrorism.

Islam and Uighur Identity

The People's Republic of China (PRC) comprises 56 officially recognized nationalities (*minzu*) including the Han-Chinese who are in majority, Muslims being among the ten of the fifty-five minority groups. The largest of the ten Muslim groups is the Hui – descendants of Central Asian, Arabian, and Persian Muslim immigrants who intermarried with the Han-Chinese and have largely integrated into the Chinese society. The second largest Muslim group is the majority of the residents of “Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region” (XUAR), comprising the Uighur, Kazak, Dongxiang, Kirgiz, Salar, Tajik, Uzbek, Baoan and Tatar. Unlike the Hui, the majority of whom speak Chinese, scattered throughout China while being deeply influenced by the Chinese culture, the Turkic Muslims are the vastly dissimilar from the Han-Chinese in terms of language, culture, religion and historical experience. These groups have retained their unique dress, customs, language, culture, and most significantly, their faith.⁹ The largest group among them is the Uighur (Uyghurs, or *Weiwuer* in modern Chinese).

Islamic identity among the Muslim minorities in China is far older than the ethnic concepts recognized by the Chinese government. It has evolved historically for over 1,300 years in the course of continuous interaction between Islam and the Chinese culture and society. This interaction has enabled the majority of the Muslims, especially the Hui, to generally integrate into Chinese society and live in apparent harmony with the Han majority. However, this was not the case with the Uighur.

The Uighur had originally been related to Buddhism.¹⁰ The Buddhist Uighur resisted conversion to Islam until the Islamization of the Tarim Basin between the tenth and the sixteenth centuries.¹¹ Due to the displacement of the Buddhist Uighur, the term “Uighur” disappeared from historical records for centuries.¹² The modern “Uighur,” as one ethnic nationality, has actually integrated a number of different Muslim Turkish peoples from the oases where the dispersed population migrated.¹³ However, the Uighur identity has not been all-encompassing, there are number of sub-groups that maintain their primary loyalties not to the collective whole of their ethnic group but to their tribes and oases.¹⁴

Though Islam is now being implicated as an essential aspect of Uighur identity, it has never been the only source of Uighur confrontation with the Chinese state. To some extent, the people recognized as Uighur Muslims emerged out of opposition to other nationalities, especially the Han-Chinese.¹⁵ After 1949, the Islamic identity was reinforced due to government policies which aimed at integration of all nationalities under the dominance of the Han-Chinese. Uighur consider China's nation-building process as an aggressive attempt for total assimilation of their Islamic religion and Turkic-culture. The term "sinicization" is frequently used to refer to China's attempts at integration.

Since 1949, Beijing has been making vigorous attempts to consolidate "the unity and cooperation" among the various nationalities in the country,¹⁶ and in respect of the Uighur, by establishing its political and military control over Xinjiang. During the "Great Leap Forward" period, the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) and the central government emphasized "complete blending of all the nationalities" as an instrument to "continued socialist construction" in minority concentrated areas,¹⁷ especially in respect of the Muslims in China generally and the Uighur particularly. The Chinese Muslim Association was abolished in 1958. The Islamic Institute was closed and the formal study of Islamic literature and law was banned.¹⁸ Islamic and other religious organizations across China were shut down and their publications stopped. The government promoted Chinese in education, while the languages of the minorities were side lined.¹⁹ In 1956, the Cyrillic alphabet was introduced by the government in Xinjiang to replace the Arabic alphabet, which was being used by Uighur for hundreds of years. In 1960, the Cyrillic alphabet was replaced by a modified Latin alphabet.²⁰

Given the sociopolitical oppositions with which the Uighur were confronted, it is not surprising that Islam became an important "cultural marker" of Uighur identity and a rallying point in a battle of contested identities.²¹ As Denise Helly put it Islam played a critical role as a "unifying ideology" of resistance for the Uighur.²² Mosque attendance and Islamic education, for example, became essential ways for the Uighur to strengthen the distinctions in their identities vis-à-vis the Han-Chinese.

State Policies and Uighur Identity

Though during the Deng Xiaoping's "reform and opening" program (*gaigekai fang*), minorities' rights were sought to be restored by providing opportunities "to preserve or reform their own customs and ways,"²³ in Xinjiang, the policies of economic improvement contributed rather to more tensions between the Uighur and the Han-Chinese. One particular reason for the Uighur dissent has been the rapid growth of Han-Chinese migrants in Xinjiang. Most of these Han-Chinese migrants settled down permanently in the main cities in northern Xinjiang,

particularly Urumqi, and state farms all over the region. In 1949, the total population of Xinjiang was 4.33 million, of which 75.9 percent were Uighur and only 6.7 percent were Han-Chinese.²⁴ The 2010 census puts the Han-Chinese population at 8.74 million – 40.1 percent of the total of 21.8 million in Xinjiang. Though the exact number of Uighur in Xinjiang (as per 2010 census) is not available, it is estimated to be about 10.4 million representing 47.7 percent of the total population of the region. Even though the Han-Chinese is still a minority in the region, its population grew from 6.7 percent in 1949 to 40.1 in 2010 whereas the Uighur population shrank from 75.9 percent to 47.7 percent during the same period.²⁵

Though Beijing claims that the migration policy was designed to promote economic development and stability of Xinjiang, there were rather unwelcome consequences. The migration of millions of Han-Chinese into Xinjiang dramatically transformed the demographic structure of the region, which is being considered by indigenous Muslims as a serious threat to their religion and culture as it was to their socio-economic development. From the Uighur perspective, the migration of the Han-Chinese to XUAR has limited the employment of the local Uighur because the majority of the Uighur do not speak Mandarin Chinese and few are as well educated as the Han-Chinese immigrants. Though state-orchestrated Han-Chinese migration to Xinjiang has ceased since 1980s, these migrants continue to receive priority over minorities in employment.²⁶ As a result, the Han-Chinese nearly dominate trade and commerce and usually have good-paying jobs and higher-ranked positions in the government, the party, and the military in XUAR.²⁷ This has led to the sense of injustice and anti-Han-Chinese and anti-government feelings among the Uighur. The incidents of violence historically, and especially since 2009, could be manifestations of such frustration and feelings of marginalization. Moreover, many Uighur believe that the presence of vast numbers of Han-Chinese, who are not Muslims, has posed serious threat to their religious identity. They are worried that their descendants would be drawn away from the traditional way of Islam by the “atheism” and “materialism” of the Han-Chinese migrants.

A Quest for Justice?

Thus, the discontent among the Uighur could be explained as an outcome of an expression of intense bitterness against Beijing’s policies towards its minorities, especially its intolerance of Islam,²⁸ combined with the growing disparity in socio-economic development vis-a-vis the Han-Chinese. The Uighur believe that their freedom of association and expression, particularly involving the religious issues has been limited by Beijing’s policies which are distinctly hostile to minority communities. They are dissatisfied with Beijing’s regulations governing mosque construction, Islamic publications and media, the content of religious education, exit requirements for pilgrimages, and the arrests and

interrogation of Imams and the Ulema deemed “subversive.” Similarly, the industries and infrastructural projects that tap Xinjiang’s enormous gas, oil, and mineral deposits, are seen as instruments of exploitation of the local resources to the detriment of the local population²⁹ due to the dominance of the Han-Chinese in such ventures. As Bovingdon argues, the persistence of inequality between the Han-Chinese and Uighur has fuelled ethnic-based conflicts and separatist movements in the region.³⁰

At the same time, the Chinese response to the unrest in Xinjiang continues to reflect insensitivity and arrogance. The “strike hard” (yanda) campaign against what the official establishment describes the “three evil forces” of “terrorism, separatism and splittism,” is characterized by a huge military insertion, followed by killings, arrests and swift executions. Even though the East Turkistan militants are by number too small, disorganized and dispersed to pose any real threat to the Chinese control over Xinjiang, Beijing’s response has been disproportionately aggressive. This is not discounting the fact that the government has made significant investments to better the economic conditions in the region. But the ruling elite’s aggressive demeanor, overreaction to any form of protests and high sensitivity and low threshold to any criticism of the responses to the unrests in the region have aggravated the situation.

Moreover, according to some analysts, China’s “religious policy is primarily a policy of control.”³¹ This is reinforced by the fact that government’s measures for economic development of the region and national stability are seen to be trampling the identity - cultural, religious and ethnic - of the Uighur as a minority community. For example, plans to relocate residents of “Old Kashgar” to new housing estates were perceived to be a threat to Uighur identity. While the authorities claim that this would improve the quality of life, the Uighur consider this as an attack on their cultural heritage and a well-orchestrated state attempt to break up their communities as the project involves destruction of ancient sites of Islamic architecture.³² The attacks in Kashgar on 31 July 2011 were triggered by the demolition of traditional Uighur houses in the centre of the old city. In the words of Henryk Szadziewski of the Washington-based Uyghur Human Rights Project, “This is the Uighurs’ Jerusalem. By destroying it, you rip the soul out of a people.”³³

Terrorism or Protests?

Of late, the majority of the violent incidents in Xinjiang that Beijing has been characterizing as acts of terrorism do not appear to be carried out by organized entities with high skill sets and transnational support networks in the province itself. For example, in August 2008 attacks, the perpetrators drove a dump truck into a group of People’s Armed Police Force (PAPF) officers during the morning exercise and used knives and a handgun. In August and September 2009 incidents, a group of Uighur stabbed civilians and police officers in Urumqi with hypodermic syringes

which were rumoured to carry HIV or anthrax (subsequently found to be untrue). In July 2011, two Uighur drove a vehicle into a Han-Chinese crowd, following it up with knife attacks. In 2012, attacks were carried out with knives. These attacks do not reflect centralized planning and control and tactical sophistication, which is the hallmark of organized and group-based resistance.

Moreover, as discussed earlier, much of the violence in the region could be stemming from the cleavage between the Han-Chinese and the Uighur communities with the Uighur acting out their anger and frustration against the Han-Chinese and the state. Increasing Han-Chinese migration into Xinjiang, forced relocation of Uighur to other parts of the country and the widening gap between the Han-Chinese and Muslim minorities in terms of socio-economic development have reinforced the sense of marginalization that has produced widespread discontent among the Uighur. The Uighur see Han-Chinese usurping political and economic opportunities in the region. On the contrary, the Han-Chinese see the Uighur as an ungrateful race that despite “pro-minority policies of the government” such as exemption from the one-child policy and heavy economic investment in the region, continue to be rebellious and often violent. Such divergent perceptions have polarized both the communities and led to hostility and violence in recent years. This has been made even more convoluted because Beijing continues to construe particular religious practices and attempts to voice discontent as anti-state actions and terrorism - cracking down on both with militaristic responses.

Conclusion

The threat from organized entities like ETIM or for that matter Al Qaeda for China is of limited consequence, at least at present. Beijing needs to appreciate that extremism and terrorism often take root due to marginalization and repression – perceived or otherwise. This becomes more aggravated where the identity of a particular population is at stake.

Thus it would be a mistake if Beijing continues to put the Uighur discontent as a separatist or terrorist issue and respond with counterproductive measures that could fuel the cycle of distrust and violence between the Uighur and the government. There is a window of opportunity which Beijing can use to bring the majority of the Uighur in Xinjiang to the mainstream while at the same time isolating a miniscule of radical elements therein.

This is possible if Beijing distinguishes local, ethnic or religious grievances from a terrorist motivation. There is a need to be able to recognize protests which are against specific grievances reflecting anguish and discontent at a local scale that can be easily resolved without disproportionate use of force. The situation in Xinjiang has not and does not portend to be of a problem of massive proportions. The way

to establish enduring peace is for the government to empathize with challenges to Uighur identity and address associated concerns.

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2. John Paul Lederach, *Building Peace: Sustainable Reconciliation in Divided Societies*, (Washington DC: United States Institute of Peace Press, 1997), p.8
3. Waever, et al., *Identity, Migration and the New Security Agenda in Europe*, p.43
4. Ibid., p. 273
5. Roe, "The Intrastate Security Dilemma," p. 195
6. Walker Connor, "Nationalism and Political Illegitimacy," in Daniele Conversi, ed., *Ethnonationalism in the Contemporary World* (New York: Routledge, 2002), p. 37
7. Ernie Regehr, "It's not really a matter of hate," *Disarming Conflict*, (9 May 2007), <http://www.igloo.org/disarmingconflict/itsnotre/>
8. Ibid,
9. Ibid.
10. The term Uighur (Uighur) was firstly employed as Turkic nomadic society practicing shamanism and Manichaeism in Mongolia. Later it referred to the name for a sedentary oasis society practicing Buddhism. It was also used as a linguistic designation to distinguish one branch of Old Turkish. Chinese originally use Uighur, and later Hui Hu for all Turkic Muslims. See Wilam Samolin, *East Turkistan to the Twelfth Century: A Brief Political Survey*, (The Hague: Mouton & Co., 1964) p. 73, Gladney, *Dislocating China*, pp. 210 – 214; and Millward and Perdue, "Political and Cultural History through the Late 19th Century," pp. 40 – 43.
11. Gladney, *Dislocating China*, p 210.
12. See Justin Rudelson and William Jankowiak, "Acculturation and Resistance: Xinjiang Identities in Flux," in S. Frederick Starr ed, *Xinjiang*, p. - 299; and Gladney, *Dislocating China*, p.210 – 214
13. Matthew D. Moneyhon, "Taming China's 'Wild West': Ethnic Conflict in Xinjiang," *Peace Conflict, and Development: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 5:5, (2004), p. 6
14. Ibid.
15. Gladney, *Dislocating China*, p. 210
16. See "Zhongguo de ShaosuMinzuZhengcejiqiShijian" (National Minorities Policies and its Practice in China), (Beijing: Information Office of the State Council of PRC, 1999). English translation at <http://english.people.com.cn/whitepaper/1.html>
17. Ibid
18. Richard C. DeAngelis, "Muslims and Chinese Political Culture," *The Muslim World*, 87:2, (1997), p. 161
19. Zhou Minglan , "The Politics of Bilingual Education in the People's Republic of China since 1949," *Bilingual Research Journal*, 25: 1&2 (2001). <http://brj.asu.edu/v2512/articles/art8.html>
20. Ibid.
21. Gladney, *Dislocating China*, p. 218.
22. Denise Helly "The Identity and Nationality Problem in Chinese Central Asia," *Central Asia Survey*, 3: 3 (1985), p. 107.
23. Raphael Israeli, "The Muslim Minority in the People's Republic of China," *Asian Survey*, 21:8 (August, 1981), p. 901

24. *Kuashiji de Zhongguorenkou – Xinjiang fence* (The Population of China Towards the 21st Century: Xinjiang Volume) (Beijing: Zhongguotongjichubanshe, 1994), table 13–7, 418.
25. The statistics for 2010 are compiled from different communiqués of the National Bureau of Statistics of China. Though the population of Han-Chinese is available in official Communiqués, the same for the Uighur is difficult to come by. The number of the minority population in Xinjiang in 2010 is the sum of the same population in 2000 (8.3 Million) and number by which this population has increased (2.9 Million) between 2000 and 2010. See, “Communiqué on Major Data of the Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region in 2010 the sixth national census [1],” *Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region Bureau of Statistics*, 6 May 2011, http://www.stats.gov.cn/tjgb/rkpcgb/dfrkpcgb/t20120228_402804343.htm
26. Ibid., Also see, Minjie Sun and C. Cindy Fan, “China’s Permanent and Temporary Migrants: Differentials and Changes, 1990–2000,” *The Professional Geographer*, 63, 1: 1–21, (2011); Calla Wiemer, “The Economy of Xinjiang,” in S. Frederick Starr, ed., *Xinjiang*: pp. 163–189; and, Clifton W. Pannell and Philipp Schmidt, “Structural Change and Regional Disparities in Xinjiang, China,” *Eurasian Geography and Economics*, 47:3 (2006), pp.329–352
27. Abanti Bhattacharya, “Conceptualising Uighur Separatism in Chinese Nationalism,” *Strategic Analysis*, 27: 3 (Jul-Sep 2003): 369
28. Rahman, “Islam in China,” 53
29. Sean L Yom, “Uighur flex their muscles,” *Asia Times*, (23 January 2003), <http://www.atimes.com/china/DA23Ad01.html>
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**8. “Factionalism and Succession in the CCP:
Power Struggles at the Apex”**

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In Imperial China, the lack of primogeniture often generated uncertainty towards the end of each reign. Historically, China's political system was based on a hierarchical system of hereditary monarchies or dynasties, which became the legitimate form of government of the Chinese civilization since about 2000 BC, all united “Under Heaven” (天下).¹ However, it is widely acknowledged by historians today that it was the Qin Dynasty that first unified China in 221 BC.

As it also occurred in the Western monarchies and empires, the issue of succession to the throne was not always smooth in Imperial China, and it often became problematic in periods of decay from one ruling dynasty to a new one, allowing this way the rise of a new ruling class. Indeed, it was rare for one dynasty to end calmly and give way quickly and smoothly to the next one, especially in the case of the so called "Conquest Dynasties" (e.g. the Yuan and the Qing, well known for being territorially expansionist). More often the new dynasty was put in place long before the overthrow of an existing regime was culminated, and sometimes even continued for a time after they had been defeated. For example, 1644 is widely accepted as the year in which the Manchu Qing dynasty armies occupied Beijing, marking the starting point of Qing rule over China and succeeding the Ming dynasty. However, the Qing dynasty itself was established in 1636 (or even earlier but under a different name following the Manchu Banner system), while the last Ming dynasty pretender was not deposed until 1662.

This change of ruling elites was often a messy and intricate affair that somehow became embedded in Chinese political culture; which is marked not necessarily by meritocracy but more precisely by a Confucian emphasis on hierarchies. The last dynasty, the Qing, ended in the 1911 revolution with the founding of the Republic of China (ROC) by the Kuomintang, the Chinese Nationalist Party. The end of a system that

lasted for a few thousand years certainly brought a huge amount of instability to the new republic. China saw itself immerse into a period of disunity and civil wars that divided the country into two main political camps during the first half of the 20th century – the nationalists and the communists.

After the establishment of the People's Republic of China (PRC) in the wake of the Chinese Civil War that ended in 1949, the stigma of authoritarianism that ruled the Middle Kingdom for almost four millennia did not end, and it was actually prolonged by the accession to power of the Chinese Communist Party (CCP). During the second half of the twentieth century, and especially after the death of Mao Zedong in September 9th, 1976, the cyclical dynamic of leadership succession in the young communist state and its ruling party has proven to be dysfunctional, too. Only in 2002 the CCP witnessed its first smooth power transition, namely the succession from Jiang Zemin to Hu Jintao. The recent turbulent years that have accompanied the current leadership succession to Xi Jinping, China's new president - characterized by the Bo Xilai scandal during 2012 that culminated in his purge and imprisonment in 2013, and that of other high officials - makes the previous case of a smooth succession more likely to be a rare exception. It seems plausible that succession in China's rigid hierarchical political system is - and will remain - a complex power struggle among different groups or factions at the top of the CCP.

Factionalism and Succession: An Intrinsic Relation

The impact that informal groups have within the CCP is enormous, not only on the issue of succession which is the main focus of this analysis, but in many other kinds of political processes, policy and decision-making as well, like the pace or economic reforms and liberalization that has put China where it stands today. Most of the scholars focusing in modern Chinese politics agree that everything in contemporary China is commonly related to the interactions of these informal and personal groups, from its desire to join the WTO, to its policy to develop the western provinces or even the much less emphasized quest for political reforms, not to mention of course the pursue of further economic reforms.

Certainly, there are power struggles at all levels within the CCP, with different lines or tendencies that evolve into the creation of factions especially between the top leadership. This process responds to very diverse interests associated with the PRC's new challenges. When

Dittmer and Wu analyze Chinese politics using a factional approach they assume these groups are the main actors with a set of particularistic interests and goals. (Dittmer and Wu, 1995) This article takes such view into consideration, since it is believed that the ultimate goal for these groupings or factions, as the key players in Chinese politics, is the seizing of power.

When trying to understand Chinese politics, many have focused on factionalism and how it influences the CCP's policy and decision-making on the one hand. On the other hand, however, several scholars have pointed out to the defective leadership transition process at the apex of the party. This article would like to gather these two approaches and their complex interrelation, considered here as co-dependent variables, namely *factionalism* and *succession*. Indeed, faction formation and the succession issue are the most relevant aspects that influence PRC's domestic political landscape.

The curiosity of this paper in these two attributes of China's political system - and the potential bond between them - is due to the fact that power struggles and the radicalization of factions at the CCP's top cadres appear to be especially noticeable in times of transition from an old to a new leadership. During these periods of tension and relative uncertainty the different lines within the CCP see windows of opportunity to have the actual chance to either maintain control, lose it or gain it. In this context, each group tries to push and influence the transition in order to place one of their own members into the party high positions within both the Politburo and its Standing Committee, the apex of power in the PRC.

As a result, it appears that factionalism and the succession issue intertwine in what it could be described as an *intrinsic relation*. Taking this as the hypothesis and point of departure, this article offers at the same time an interesting and innovative view that seems particularly appealing when trying to understand how contemporary Chinese politics function. Hence, the main purpose of this analysis is to explore the influence of faction formation in the CCP regarding its leadership succession and vice versa. Why factionalism seems to arise or become more pronounced especially in times of transition from one generation of leaders to another? Are factions something inherent to Chinese politics or they only become distinguishable during CCP's top cadres renewal?

In order to answer these and other questions that may stem from this analysis, the emphasis will be put first on a historical perspective of

how the processes of power transition have occurred since the founding of the PRC, and particularly in the late Mao and Deng's eras until the most recent and turbulent transition from Hu Jintao to Xi Jinping, paying special attention to the power struggles among diverse informal groups that exist within the CCP, particularly at the top of its hierarchy (e.g. the Politburo and Standing Committee). The revision of secondary sources was the mode selected to carry out the research, by selecting textbooks, articles, papers and other publications regarding Chinese politics in general, as well as factionalism and succession within the CCP in particular, which are also supported by historical facts to illustrate the arguments this article attempts to put forward.

In the following pages, the focus is on how Chinese politics normally function within the CCP by revising the issue of faction formation and informal politics as a way to give a certain framework to better understand the issue. In a subsequent section the analysis is oriented on those special characteristics of Chinese politics and their link to the succession issue within the CCP drawing on the historical facts of past successions. Here the focus is put on how and why faction formation and their struggles has appeared more pronounced during succession periods after the review of some cases. Next, the article also explores the current conditions regarding these two subjects and their relation in contemporary China, including a review of the most recent leadership transition and the events that surrounded it. Finally, some concepts like *intra-party democracy* or *bipartisanship* are embraced and briefly discussed, while the main questions and their answers are addressed, together with a quick glance to future prospects on the topic. A set of conclusions is provided in the last section. Through the review of recent and past events this piece hopes to shed some light on how the intertwined processes of factionalism and succession function within the CCP, thus making a humble contribution in the understanding of China's opaque political system.

Understanding CCP's Factional Formation

To discuss briefly about the definition of factionalism - and how it is manifested in Chinese politics - is pertinent to better outline the topic. Andrew Nathan's defined faction early on as a vertically organized structure composed of face-to-face clientelist ties between leaders and led (Nathan, 1973). In this sense, Chinese politics, marked by a one-party and authoritarian system, has been reckoned to be inherently factional. Thus, it is very hard to delineate Chinese politics given the fact that it highly relies on informal associations, diverse forms of clientelist

loyalties and allegiances. In this matter, Lucian Pye sees “limitations in the construction of any theoretical schema for informal Chinese politics because of the rule of personal relations and the workings of “*guanxi*” or connections,² consisting of subtle nuances.” (in Wang, 2002: 109)

Indeed, since the death of Mao and the power vacuum that it produced, factional politics are at the core of informal relations in Chinese politics, highly determined by different types of kinship like family origins, friendship and other kinds of affiliation. Consequently, factionalism inside the CCP also follows these kinds of leanings. Thus, it is no secret that since the 1960’s the political maneuvers among the top leaders in Chinese politics have been factionalized, and this did not always or necessarily followed ideological lines. Very often factional behavior is strongly based on personal relationships. Other authors, like Tang Tsou, have gone as far as to argue that Chinese informal politics are merely a means to achieve certain goals; but not as an end in themselves. (Tsou, 1995) This certainly becomes a key aspect for this analysis when linked to the issue of succession as we shall see.

The approach put forward by Dittmer and Wu also sheds some light onto this, since they give a broadened definition of factionalism in respect to elite goals. In terms of goals, as these two authors point out, factions may have three sets of ambitions, concerning security, material interests, and ideological and policy commitments. Political security is the top priority, and factional activities are oriented towards a quest to maximize it. (Dittmer and Wu, 1995) Hence, the different factions as the main actors in Chinese politics seek this elemental security in order to prevail and remain in power. It is under transition or succession periods when this kind of struggle takes place in an overt manner. However, while survival remains the highest priority for these groupings, some factional goals can be displaced partially when some personal interests switch or become more relevant. An example of this was Deng Xiaoping’s great tactical flexibility, as history has shown:

“(…) it is the career of the patron rather than the logic of material and ideal group interests per se that may be expected to dictate policy preferences in the crunch. This was most clearly illustrated by the fragmentation of the ‘reform faction’ in 1986-89 over the conflicting personal interests of Deng Xiaoping, Hu Yaobang, and Zhao Ziyang. In a context of partially reformed political economy, it is not surprising that factions have undergone only partial transformation to bureaucratic politics.” (Dittmer and Wu, 1995: 481)

Situations like this one noted above can certainly bring a great deal of instability to the process of power transition, especially considering that - as in many other authoritarian regimes based on a Leninist system - the Chinese did not have an institutionalized and orderly set of procedures for selecting the successor to their paramount leader after the death of Mao. It was Deng and his followers who have continuously tried to implement such institutional framework to safeguard stability and maintain the party in control. Indeed, as Kenneth Lieberthal (2004) clearly puts it, the succession issue is the most complicated task for a dictatorial government or one-party system, since the power is extremely centralized and concentrated usually in one person. Therefore, it becomes difficult to secure a peaceful transition without bringing instability to the political environment.

The bottom line of this lies in the lack of institutionalization. In a government like the Chinese the power is not in the institutions but in the “paramount leader.” Lieberthal explains that this occurs “because power at the top in this system is not institutionalized, when the core leader dies his power dies with him: a successor therefore needed his own base of support to compete successfully for the top position” (Lieberthal, 2005: 149). This became evident after Mao’s death when his appointed successor, Hua Guofeng, was not able to gather the necessary support among the top party members who saw in Deng the best candidate to lead the party, and to somehow bring China out of the stage in which it was left after the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976). Thus, Deng was rehabilitated after its third and last purge.

Going back in history and using facts as precedents, certainly it becomes evident that factionalism has had a dominant role in Chinese politics concerning succession and power transition at all levels in the party, but particularly at the apex. Even before Mao’s death the CCP had to face the challenge of such unstable scenario without much accomplishment, due to confronting interests and the creation of different factions as a consequence. It is a fact that leaders had been divided over succession issues, as occurred in 1969-71, 1973-76, 1978-81 and 1986-89, and most recently 2012-13. Thus, there have been a number of “*unsuccessful successors*” in every new generation of leaders, namely Lin Biao, Hua Guofeng, Hu Yaobang, Zhao Ziyang; and some even argue that such is the fate of Bo Xilai, CCP’s rising star and Xi Jinping’s only possible competitor to the top job in China.

A much earlier example and first precedent to be considered here is what occurred during Liu Shaoqi’s presidency of the PRC (1959-1968)

which was characterized by a constant power struggle between him and Mao Zedong. Fearing that Liu could become the new leader after Mao's death, he was finally removed from all his positions and expelled from party in 1968, under the campaign launched by the Maoist faction at the highest point of the Cultural Revolution. Something similar can be argued in the case of Deng Xiaoping's informal maneuvers that successfully deposed Hua Guofeng in the early 1980's with the assistance of his faction members, especially Chen Yun. These two examples, namely Liu Shaoqi and Hua Guofeng depositions, serve to illustrate the tremendous influence of factionalism, maneuvered strategies of informal politics within the CCP when it comes to select who will rise to the top. The 'behind-the-scenes' rise of Xi Jinping to China's presidency in 2012-13 and his consolidation of power throughout 2014 is said to be full of that kind of old school factional-behavior.

In the following sections a more detailed approach to the several cases and a review of the historical facts is presented in order to depict the relations between factionalism and power struggles for succession in Chinese politics.

Factions and Power Transition in CCP's History

Perhaps not the first but undoubtedly the most acute evidence of factionalism within the CCP solidified as the Cultural Revolution reached a critical point, due to Mao and his close allies' radicalization. The so called "Cultural Revolution" faction emerged in the late 1960's, and its members were mainly a younger generation of very experienced cadres with a bureaucratic career. Most of them were not founders of the party or revolutionary leaders, but they belonged to the "Establishment of the PRC," like Jiang Qing, Zhang Chunqiao, Yao Wenyuan and Wang Hongwen. In this period they emerged to the front line of political arena thanks to Mao's support. In this context, the 9th Party Congress was held in Beijing in 1969, following the failure of Liu and Deng's faction in the strife for power with Mao, which cost Liu's career and his life too. The main objectives of this convention were primarily to settle down the political unrest and enlarge Mao's political influence and domination over the CCP and the whole of China. It was during this time that Lin Biao emerged as the primary military figure and second in ranking behind Mao Zedong in the party. The party constitution was even modified to name Lin as Mao's special successor, while the members of the Cultural Revolution faction ascended to high-rank positions in the Politburo and Central Committee. As it is widely known today, in the 1971 Lin's failed coup and assassination attempt of Mao resulted in his death while trying

to escape from China in a tragic plane crash that many reckon it was not an accident but an assassination. Thus, in the 10th Party Congress held in 1973 the Cultural Revolution faction gradually consolidated its domination. (from MacFarquhar and Schoenhals, 2006)

Following the death of Lin Biao, Mao tried to shape Jiang Qing as his potential successor, and with him also the rest of the Cultural Revolution faction, as the major political leaders in the PRC. However, opposition from the revolutionary leaders, especially Zhou Enlai and Deng Xiaoping, made this attempt not possible. Mao was forced to yield and not pass his power direct down to Jiang. Mao accepted to choose Hua Guofeng as his temporary successor and as a shield to protect Jiang Qing from the attack by the elder revolutionary leaders. Hua, who was once closely linked to the Cultural Revolution faction, was elected to the Politburo in 1973 and started to distance himself from Jiang. He became acting Premier of the PRC following Zhou Enlai's death, in January 1976. Meanwhile, this event did not play in Deng's favor and he was victimized under the power struggle, and he was purged for the third time, since Mao and Jiang still regarded Deng as the greatest threat to their power and positions. When Mao's death came, it was Hua and not Jiang who ascended as the new Chairman of the CCP in September 1976, which indeed produced a power vacuum at the top and particularly a huge shock for Jiang and her followers who felt betrayed. Thus, in the wake of Mao's death, a new faction - so called the "Gang of Four" - emerged. Led by Jiang Qing, they attempted to seize power and take the whole party and country under their control, while at the same time Hua tried desperately to take actions in order to consolidate his power, clashing constantly with Jiang Qing even over the most minor issues. (MacFarquhar and Schoenhals, 2006) Hua launched a coup and arrested Jiang and her three main followers, accusing them of having full responsibility for the excesses witnessed during the Cultural Revolution.

After the arrest of the Gang of Four, the following major political event would be the 11th Central Committee held in 1977 under Hua's regime. Deng Xiaoping was pardoned and rehabilitated to all his previous posts since Hua was not strong enough to withstand the pressure of party veterans and high-ranked People's Liberation Army (PLA) officials who advocated for Deng's return. In the midst of this, new faction was formed around the figure of Deng Xiaoping in the late 1970's, which consisted mainly of party elders who were the victims of the Cultural Revolution, and many of the military leaders to whom Deng had strong relationships. On the other hand, Hua Guofeng's faction was mostly

composed by the leaders who benefited from the Cultural Revolution and some military leaders who resented Deng.

Indeed, even though the hard times of the Cultural Revolution were over, the division it produced within the party remained, and its effect over the succession issue became more evident as Deng became the main challenger to Hua's regime in the post-Mao era due to its wide and well developed personal connections within the party, government and military; which made him a master in tactics of power struggle. This became evident in Deng's skillful maneuver to get rid of Hua in the following years. From the 3rd Plenum of the 10th Central Committee 1977 to the 4th Plenum of the 11th Central Committee in 1979, the power struggles between Deng and Hua were chiefly based on ideology and politics. When trying to grasp support from the elders and in order to create the image as the successor of Mao's ideology, Hua put forward the policy of "Two Whatever's" which basically stressed a policy-making process in conformity with Mao's thought. Hua and his followers then became the "Whatever" faction in opposition to the so called "Pragmatism" faction led by Deng, who proposed the ideology of practice as the only one criterion to test the truth, and were more open to economic reforms.

Ultimately, Deng was able to strengthen his power and faction by returning the purged veteran leaders to politics at the apex of the CCP, which also meant a great deal of popular support for him. Later on, at the 3rd Plenum of the 11th Central committee, Deng made some crucial gains. The most vital one was the designation of Deng's protégé, Hu Yaobang, as the CCP General Secretary to supervise the daily administration of the party affairs in an effort to weaken Chairman Hua's power. Deng's next victory was in the Central Committee when four of his supporters, namely, Chen Yun, Deng Yingchao, Hu Yaobang and Wang Zhen, were elected as additional members of the Politburo. (Lieberthal, 2004: 104) After CCP's 3rd Plenum, Deng took a large step forwards in terms of power consolidation.

In addition, because Deng shared the victim experience with the purged leaders and since he built solid personal friendships with the 'Long March' veteran cadres, he became the leader of a "grand coalition" which finally undermined Hua's power. This grand coalition, which was composed of the aged orthodox hard-liners and the younger pragmatic reformers, allowed a favorable atmosphere for policies and decision-making under Deng's leadership. Hua Guofeng lost his power and control over the party step by step, until he was finally removed from his

positions because his stubborn upholding of the “Two Whatever’s.” Zhao Ziyang, another of Deng’s protégés replaced Hua as Premier to carry out the process of economic opening after the 5th Plenum of 11th Central Committee in 1980. Deng’s victory over Hua was consolidated a year after when Hu Yaobang became the new party Chairman in 1981. (MacFarquhar and Schoenhals, 2006)

The second half of the 1980’s were probably the most turbulent times when it comes to the issue of faction formation in Chinese politics since the Cultural Revolution ended. Deng proved to be a master in factional politics, and that is why he also understood very early how harmful this could be for the system. Consequently, almost immediately when he seized power he tried to set out a predictable and stable succession in a more institutionalized way. Teiwes explains:

“With Deng Xiaoping taking the lead, a serious analysis of past disasters led to the conclusion that the lack of effective institutions and checks on arbitrary authority had helped bring about these disasters, and measures were undertaken to introduce various procedures and limits concerning the exercise of power.” (Teiwes, 2001: 74)

Nevertheless, once Deng’s power was consolidated after getting rid of Hua Guofeng, the process of economic reforms and gradual opening to the world promoted by his faction of reformers brought about a series of tensions within the party that produced greater divisions between the younger and more liberal cadres and the CCP high-ranked elders that always opposed liberalization. Hu Yaobang became the main controversial figure within these struggles.

Hu was a dedicated reformer who tried to rehabilitate the people persecuted during the Cultural Revolution. However, Hu and Deng held different views especially on political liberalization, which became clear during the Anti-Spiritual Pollution Campaign in 1983. Hu’s handling of this campaign raised concern among party elders who did not want to see further liberalization especially in the political and social camps, while younger and liberal Hu advocated for the intellectuals and artists freedom of expression. According to Zhao Ziyang personal account, during this period Hu made the mistake of pushing things too far too fast, and that meant his distancing from Deng. (BaoPu et al, 2009)

Consequently, well before the 13th Party Congress in 1987, Deng had already made up his mind to remove Hu, especially after his lack of prudence when giving an interview to a Hong Kong journalist that

triggered Deng's anger. Zhao explains in his memories that basically Deng lost faith in Hu, and he became problematic for Deng as a possible successor to his position of paramount leader of the CCP. Deng finally had to give up to the pressure of party elders who opposed Hu's tendency towards further and faster liberalization not just of the economy but also the political system. This very conservative hard-line faction was mainly composed by the so called "Ideologues," namely Hu Qiaomu and Deng Liqun, backed by party elders like Chen Yun, Li Xiannian and Wang Zhen. Hu Yaobang was strongly criticized during the 13th Party Congress and forced to write a letter of resignation. Zhao Ziyang, Deng's second man, who until then focused entirely on the economic aspects of reforms as Premier, was appointed as the new General Secretary and had to take up a more political role then.

Zhao assumed his new position facing the challenge of continuing with economic reforms while carrying out campaigns of anti-liberalization and dealing with the party elders who saw him now as their new target. Nevertheless, Zhao proved to be very skillful when making the transition into an arena in which he recognized was not familiar to him at first. (BaoPu et al, 2009) However, the hard-line faction opposed continuously to reforms, in economy, political system or social aspects and now directed all their criticism against Zhao and the younger cadres who were promoting these reforms. Hu Qiamu, Deng Liqun and especially party elder Chen Yun gave Zhao a hard time, particularly in regards to the theoretical foundations to justify reforms and also the way to punish people during the Anti-campaigns of the 1980's. (BaoPu et al, 2009) Thus, Zhao became the new Hu Yaobang, as his fate followed a quite similar path while the Student Movement pushing for more democratic reforms began to gather momentum in the late 1980's. The events that followed are widely known and Zhao's initiatives, along with his conciliatory attitude toward the students protesting in 1989, were not welcomed by the elders and other party hard-liners. Soviet leader Mikhail Gorbachev's visit to Beijing served as the context for Zhao's political downfall. The leadership would not purge Zhao while Gorbachev was still in Beijing, but on the night of 18 May, just after the Soviet leader left, a hastily called Politburo Standing Committee was called to endorse martial law. Zhao's famous visit to the students stationed in Tiananmen Square on May 19th cost him all his positions and political career.

After the demise of Zhao in the wake of the Student Movement of 1989 and the massacre of June 4th, Deng's focus turned toward trying to return stability through CCP's tighter control of the country while trying to continue with economic development. A new faction raised then to

preeminent position in China's political system in this context and during the early 1990's, which will be known as the "Shanghai Gang."

In a sense, the Tiananmen incident reset the agenda for the CCP. The emphasis has since been maintaining stability while promoting economic growth which give the party the legitimacy to govern China. Under this guiding principle, Jiang Zemin was chosen to become the core of the third generation leadership, which was hand-picked by Deng Xiaoping. It is also well known that Deng even further designated Hu Jintao to be Jiang's successor in the following transition to a fourth generation, who Deng deemed a symbol of "transmillennium" leadership stability. (Paltiel, 2001: 117) Hence the Tiananmen tragedy by chance delivered Jiang and Hu their tickets to success. Jiang's top spot was flanked by Li Peng, a conservative who was kept in place to alleviate tension between the reformists and the conservatives, and Zhu Rongji, who was responsible for making sure economic reform continue in a state of macroeconomic stability. While this arrangement and the power structure that signified seemed a miniature of the power dynamics within CCP at the time, Paltiel asserts that the design was meant to consolidate CCP's rule (Paltiel, 2001) and allowed a very smooth couple of decades with stellar economic growth and development.

As the new heir who lacked revolutionary background to claim legitimacy from, Jiang had to find ways to tie himself to the CCP legacy. It was in this context that Jiang fought for recognition, and it proved no easy task since Jiang's background as a technocrat was nothing that could be directly translated into legitimate power. As Joseph Fewsmith points out, technocrats are by training problem solvers, not ideologues; they focus on "problems", not "isms." (Fewsmith, 2001: 84) Hence, in order to lead the CCP, Jiang first had to wait patiently to consolidate his power step by step. It was only after Deng passed away in 1997 and when Jiang successfully ousted Qiao Shi at the 15th Party congress in 1997 that he began to truly live up to his title as the top leader of China. This exemplifies once more the issue of struggle during succession periods at the top of the CCP, especially after the death of the paramount leader - in this case Deng - and the power vacuum that it generates. Accordingly, the 15th Party congress marked the turning point where a more technocratic leadership came to the fore, led by Jiang and his coalition also known as the "Shanghai Gang," most notably represented by Zhu Rongji and Wu Bangguo, who began to dominate the stage of Chinese politics as the turn of the century approached.

The following transition period from Jiang Zemin to Hu Jintao culminated in 2002 without major surprises, scandals or purges. It is reckoned that this succession in particular was accomplished in a very smooth manner thanks largely to the fact that it was carefully scripted by Deng's and his early selection of Hu as successor of Jiang. After revising a historical progression to the topic, in the following sections a more contemporary review is presented in regards to the impact of factionalism over the CCP's apex of power and its more current manifestation in the last decade where new factions and allegiances will be formed. It is worth noting, however, that other relevant aspects and not just the succession issue respond to factional activities, like the development of party guidelines or procedures and policy-making in general. Yet, as history has demonstrated, in China's one-party political system factional conflict becomes more evident in presence of a power vacuum or in periods when a generation of older leaders is to retire and a new cohort of younger leaders has the chance to raise to the Politburo and its Standing Committee, which only happens once every ten years. Oksenberg explains: "in these instances, bureaucrats and the populace quickly detected signs of a divided leadership at the top. In a complicated fashion, factionalism at the top on these previous occasions became linked to and exacerbated societal cleavages." (Oksenberg, 2001: 30) The transition from Hu Jintao to China's current leader Xi Jinping in 2012-13 was indeed less smooth than previously thought. Many scholars and experts predicted a very institutionalized and thus stable power transition based on what was witnessed in 2002. However, the formation of new factions over the last decade - each one pushing for its own interests and with their own set of popular leaders and candidates to the top jobs - meant that some turbulent times and behind-the-scenes power struggle accompanied the transition and consolidation of Xi as the new leader of the CCP and China.

Quest for New Legitimacy: Rise of the Technocrats

For Jing Huang (2000) politics in China are personalistic because of the lack of appropriate institutions to allow other alternatives within the PRC, and this personalism encourages the importance of special relationships. These networks become factions due to the absence of open competition in a one-party system as the Chinese. Huang also proposes that these different groups can effectively take on the functions performed by political organizations under pluralism, achieving what it has been labeled as *intra-party democracy*. (Huang, 2000) Currently in the PRC, the new leadership is indeed seeking to develop this particular concept of intra-party democracy, without overhauling the existing one-

party system. This is a noteworthy asset on the subject of the succession issue in the CCP, since implementation of intra-party democracy could bring to some extent that necessary institutionalization process to the power transmission practices that China currently lack. This would allow establishing the so-called “rules of the game” which normally include laws and jurisprudence, accepted habits, and formal or informal codes of conducts; the latter is especially relevant for the Chinese case. However, setting up these regulations is a slow process:

“It was only after Deng gradually faded from the center stage of Chinese politics in 1994 that Jiang consolidated his authority and closed the gap between formal and informal power. During the Deng era, political succession did not involve a life-or-death struggle among the Party elite, and ideological and policy disputes were much less fierce than those during the Mao era. These preexisting rules of the game established a set of parameters for leadership transition from Jiang Zemin to Hu Jintao, providing both constraints and opportunities for political actors in the new round of the power game.” (Lin, 2004: 257)

As Cheng Li (2005) points out, the new leaders recognize that the survival of the world’s largest political party depends on whether it can revitalize itself to meet the challenges of the day, both domestic and international. The idea of developing more democratic routines within the CCP follows this logic, since Chinese leaders have consistently argued that a Western-style multiparty system is not feasible for China. This aspect is also crucial concerning factionalism and its sway on the struggles for seizing power at the apex.

The concept of intra-CCP democracy is certainly not new. Deng introduced reforms such as term limits and mandatory retirement for the party cadres at various levels in order to solve the succession instability, which were indeed successful and implemented accordingly. At the 14th Party Congress in 1992, an agreement was apparently reached to institutionalize succession procedures. Central to the rules was the notion of term limits, no more than two terms or ten years in office, which is the standard followed until today, although many scholars wondered - among them Oksenberg (2001) - whether the future rulers will adhere to that agreement as their terms in office expire or if they would try hold on to power. In today’s China the first option seems more likely to prevail, especially having the last to succession cases in 2002 and 2012 as a recent historical precedent, when Jiang Zemin and Hu Jintao respectively, stepped down of their posts. China has somehow achieved

timely and relatively peaceful party leadership succession in the last two decades. Experts agree that this kind of smoother transitions may become the norm as the CCP moves from a revolutionary party to a kind of technocratic one. This was certainly the case in the succession of 2002, however new factions, as we shall see, have appeared within the CCP and they are inevitably thirsty for power.

It was during Jiang's rule when for the first time the main concepts of intra-party democracy were articulated within the CCP. This notion has to do with the "governing party" and "governing capacity," terms broadly used by Hu Jintao and Wen Jiabao over the past decade, and now coined by Xi Jinping and Li Keqiang. Indeed, the Chinese leadership has adopted a limited mechanism for electing members of the CCP's Central Committee, which is called the "*election with more candidates than seats*." Moreover, within the decade under Hu's presidency, the new concept of "*bipartisanship*" - a concept usually employed in thriving democracies with at least two different parties - also emerged within the CCP. According to experts, in the case of China bipartisanship refers to the formation of two political factions that compete with each other for power, influence and policy initiatives within the one-party system. "The new leaders may not allow any organized opposition groups to compete for political power, but they are institutionalizing checks and balances between opposing interests." (Li, 2005: 389) Chinese politics in the first decades of the 21st Century, as Li specifies, is characterized by two factions which cannot easily be categorized along ideological lines as liberals and conservatives, like it was the case in the 80's and 90's. "More accurate would be to call the coalition led by former party chief Jiang [Zemin] and his protégé, Vice President Zeng Qinghong, the elitist coalition and the other led by Hu [Jintao] and Wen [Jiabao], the populist coalition. These two factions represent different regional and socioeconomic interests and divergent policy priorities." (Li, 2005: 389)

Certainly, today these two groupings or factions within the CCP are widely recognized, although informal in nature and rather clannish, based on loyalties that do not necessarily follow ideological or political lines. Some refer the grouping led by Hu Jintao, and particularly by former Premier Wen Jiabao, as the "reform wing," which includes current president Xi as one of its main figures and aims to speed up deregulation and privatization of the economy by reducing the often dominant role of uncompetitive and bureaucratic state owned enterprises (SOEs). To be sure, this 'reform wing' does not mean under any circumstances a political kind of reform. This coalition was known as the populist

coalition since their members main common allegiance is to have a more modest background, most of them originally part of the Chinese Communist Youth League, who have risen to high positions in the hierarchy after very successful careers. This more humble background appears as stark opposition to the so called "*princelings*" faction - formerly known as the Shanghai Gang already mentioned above - led by octogenarian former president Jiang Zemin and his protégés. These are leaders who come from well established political families, most of them whose parents were high-ranked officials or revolutionary veterans and with important interests and links to the SOEs that have made them extremely wealthy, thus they oppose some of the reforms pushed by the other faction. Such is the case of disgraced former party boss of Chongqing, Bo Xilai, whose father Bo Yibo served as vice premier and had a long career since the formation of the CCP. Many attribute Bo Xilai's meteoric career, and that of other officials in this faction, to the fact of being a princeling and the patron-client ties to Jiang Zemin. Bo's scandal and downfall is certainly better understood in a context of power transition and factional struggle.

What makes this situation new and dissimilar from prior faction formation within the party, as some experts have explained, is that neither Jiang's elitist coalition nor Hu's populist group is willing or able to defeat the other. (Li, 2005) This is the key to the bipartisanship issue, as factional politics in the PRC has transformed from a zero-sum game in which a winner took all, to today's dynamic process of negotiation and compromise. Observers see Bo Xilai's scandal in these terms, and his ousting not so much as a triumph for the reformist camp of Hu and Wen, but more of a compromise or concession made by Jiang Zemin to let Bo fall - also greatly due to his egotistical and ambitious personality that put him in hot water in the first place - while securing a deal for his own group's seizing of power within the now reduced seats in the Politburo's Standing Committee (PSC) after the 18th National Congress which began on November 8, 2012. Indeed, in the midst of Bo's scandal, the Congress saw the number of PSC seats reduced from nine to seven, electing [Xi Jinping](#) as the new Party General Secretary - who normally also holds the government post of President of the PRC as it was confirmed later on - [Li Keqiang](#), who became the Premier; [Zhang Dejiang](#), [Yu Zhengsheng](#), [Liu Yunshan](#), [Wang Qishan](#) and [Zhang Gaoli](#). Of these high-ranked cadres, at least four have been identified as belonging to the '*Princelings*' faction supported by Jiang, thus confirming Bo's downfall and Xi's rise did not mean a defeat for this group, but more of a compromise, also pointing to the great influence of Jiang in shaping the composition of the new Standing Committee. Certainly, these two factions share now the

purpose of ensuring the CCP's survival at home, hence affecting the way transition is going to be carried out in the coming decades, hopefully in a more balanced manner, but certainly not free of power struggle.

These new arrangement in Chinese politics are by no means coincidental, since the Jiang's Shanghai Gang, with backgrounds in finance, trade, foreign affairs and with strong political family ties from the advance coastal regions represents the interests of wealthy entrepreneurs and cultural elite; while Hu's more populist coalition, with a more humble background working in some of the poorest provinces in China's inland, is mostly bind to local careers on administrative positions as well as to the Youth League. This apparent balance of power between the two factions with opposing interests reflects the desire within the Chinese leaders to perpetuate the CCP's rule in a legitimate way, given that ideology does not provide any credibility by itself anymore. Certainly this so called 'intra-party democracy' and the increasing bipartisanship evolving within the CCP is a new way to add validity and legitimacy for the CCP's control over China, no more as a revolutionary party, but as governing one, which also might bring with it more institutionalized party practices in general, and to the power transition in particular. (Li, 2005) Thus, succession has been gradually improved following an institutionalization and modernization trend within the CCP, but also due to the characteristic of the new leadership. Higher education and professionalism is now required to hold a government and party positions in China. These new cadres are not ideologues anymore; they are mostly technocrats.

Conclusion

When it comes to the complex, uncertain and often unstable issue of succession at the apex of power in the PRC, most authors tend to agree. Chinese expert Gang Lin emphasizes that "leadership transition in China is far from sharply defined – or complete – in the absence of free and competitive election," (Lin, 2004: 255) while Frederick Teiwes (2001) points out that at the moment Chinese political system still based on what might be called a set of "fuzzy principles" contained in what he compares to a black box. "Who has really a say in selecting the successor to the 'core' or the members of the collective leadership?" this author wonders. (Teiwes, 2001: 76) Indeed, factional formation surely has a lot to do in these regards, and will continue to do so for as long as political reforms are not undertaken, which is unlikely to occur under the new leadership of Xi Jinping.

The renown China expert Lowell Dittmer has repeatedly emphasized that factionalism or elite strife "is the Achilles heel of the Chinese political system." (in Wang, 2002: 106) Indeed all the past crisis within the CCP revised in this paper can be attributed to severe elite conflict at the top. (Wang, 2002) This can be understood in accordance to Tang Tsou argument that stresses how the struggle for power in the CCP has, during most of its history, resulted in the ascendancy of one group or coalition over its opposite, (Tsou, 1976) which has determined how the successions processes occurred. However, as noted, this was not the case in the most recent succession, where a more balanced outcome emerged, indicating a power struggle that required compromise in order to ensure the regime's survival. Certainly, power struggle at the apex of the CCP will continue to generate uncertainty and apprehension, which might explain the radicalization of the different factions and why it arises or gets stronger during periods of transition or renewal of party leadership. Ambiguity regarding the who will or will not attain a seat in the Standing Committee until the very last minute inflames factional ambitions.

Several cases revised here over the CCP's history have served as good illustrations of how factional maneuver is so decisive. One good precedent occurred right after Mao's death when Deng's reformer faction finally overthrew the "Two Whatevers" group led by Hua Guofeng. Indeed, Deng proved to be a master in factional politics, and he also understood very early on how harmful this could be for the system. Consequently, almost immediately when he seized power he tried to set out a predictable and stable succession in a more institutionalized way, succeeding to some extent. However, more institutionalization not always guarantees the attenuation of conflicts and the failure of Deng's early succession strategy based on his two protégés - Hu Yaobang and Zhao Ziyang - exemplifies this. Mostly because of the Tiananmen pro-democracy movement in 1989 and how these two more liberal official managed it, Deng's premeditated transition process proved to be damaged, paving the way for the more conservative hard-line faction to finally get rid of reformers like Zhao. Although Deng often spoke about political reforms, as he seemed dissatisfied with the existing system, according to Zhao his idea of political reform was more administrative, against bureaucratization and overconcentration of power, but maintaining always the one-party rule of the CCP. Ultimately, Deng wanted to make the party more efficient, transparent and to provide a better leadership by promoting younger cadres to the top as a source of legitimacy and regime survival. (BaoPu et al, 2009) Indeed, a more technocratic CCP emerged. Therefore, and since the succession issue remained the most threatening aspect to stability, Deng tried once more to anticipate and avoid another possible political

catastrophe by selecting a more consensual set of successors, namely Jiang Zemin and Hu Jintao.

After revising the CCP's faction formation in relation to the succession issue, it becomes evident for this analysis how both issues respond to informal relations and how they remain highly personalistic. Following this analysis, the periods of power transition throughout the last half century have definitely seen a more radical clash between the different lines within the CCP, in which special relationships in Chinese politics are the currency of political change, and where the dominant leaders are those with the biggest networks of special relationships. (Jing Huang, 2000) For similar reasons, when there are significant leadership changes there have to be thorough rectifications in order to eliminate the influence of former leaders and to consolidate the networks of the new leadership. The latest anti-corruption campaign strongly pursued by Xi Jinping and Li Keqiang since 2013 seems to indicate the latter.

Certainly, in such unstable scenarios such as during the succession phase, considering the lack of proper institutionalization to guide the process, factions play a decisive role. This is a key point regarding the bond between factionalism and succession within China's political system. Thus, it can be safely argued that a strong link between factional maneuvering and the succession issue within the CCP does exist. This connection can be considered as *intrinsic* - as argued in the beginning of this analysis - due to the particular characteristics of the PRC political and governmental one-party system. Factionalism and succession mutually influence each other. Factional activities at CCP's apex of power are oriented in order to seize control when a succession takes place. Conversely, the power vacuum created during leadership transitions in Chinese politics influence faction formation and loyalties, as the historical facts have shown.

Although currently there is no good succession mechanism in the PRC, Chinese politics will remain factional since factions are the units of action within the CCP, as Dittmer and Wu pointed out already two decades ago. (Dittmer and Wu, 1995: 493) However, ideology is not what drives this factional formation, as a new set of competing interests in China's political environment has emerged while its society evolves and becomes more diversified. Bureaucratic interest coalitions, economic and trade ambitions, informal ties and personal loyalty, the broader public opinion and other situational groupings are nowadays having increasingly more significance for political outcomes. A common sense of survival and quest for legitimacy

to stay in power remains the common denominator among these factional groups at the top of CCP's hierarchy.

Moreover, even in such non-democratic and authoritarian regime, more pluralistic forces are slowly breaking through the Chinese political framework, which is an encouraging sign. The so called 'intra-party democracy' and the new bipartisanship within the CCP may be revitalizing the party's leadership, but it remains to be seen how much longer it can survive in its current form. As many experts insist, succession and power transition are still colossal flaws in the CCP, and further political reforms are required regarding these aspects. The behind-the-scenes power struggle and turbulent period that surrounded the latest 18th National Congress of the CCP is a testament of that reality.

Notes :

¹ For more on the concept of 天下 (pinyin: Tian Xia) refer to Joseph R. Levenson. 1952. "T'ien-hsia and Kuo, and the 'Transvaluation of Values,'" *The Far Eastern Quarterly*, Vol. 11, No. 4: 447-451.

² Guanxi refers to the pinyin Romanization of the word 關係 (Traditional Chinese) or 关系 (Simplified Chinese) which literally means "relationship" and it is used to describe the basic dynamic in personalized networks of influence as something central to Chinese society.

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Annex. Factionalism and Succession in the CCP: Timeline

9. China's Domestic and Foreign Policies

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"Dr. Parasaran Rangarajan is Editor-in-chief and founder for the International Law Journal of London as well as a scholar from Harvard University.

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Link: <http://www.internationallawjournaloflondon.com/about.html>"

China's Domestic and Foreign Policies

I. Introduction

The People's Republic of China (PRC), split into mainland China and Special Administrative Regions (SAR) or non-mainland China, is an ancient civilisation which has deep rooted systems of governance linked

with the upper classes of its society in the political party of the ruling government; the Communist Party of China (CPC).

The CPC is in full control of the nation by not having a federal structure but by employing citizens who through training at the Central Party School of the CPC and who are deployed to serve positions on state councils formed on administrative boundaries of each province and mass organisations such as trade unions as well as professional unions. The CPC maintains ultimate control in all facets of life in this manner as the national bureaucracy maintains the final say in all matters.

Where the CPC does not rule directly in SAR, there is heavy influence and matters of foreign policy are not implemented without the approval of the CPC. Through this internal system of governance in mainland China, we analyse the rise of PRC both economically and militarily considering the foreign policy it seeks to maintain with the non-traditional threats facing the nation today.

There are many internal dynamics that China faces to accomplish its goals just as any other nation does. Jobs, education, healthcare, etc are all being changed and the overall global vision of the citizens are changing. These factors in turn with security concerns are causing the government and CPC to take a defensive approach in many areas including regional policies and foreign policy. However, while the past teaches us valuable lessons, the future may be approaching too quickly for China.

Our analysis is organised into five topics:

1. China In Search Of A Balance
2. Internal Dynamics Impacting China's Regional Policies
3. China's Geopolitical Environment and Terrorism
4. Non-Traditional Security Threats In China
5. Governance In China

II. China In Search Of A Balance

When we look into Chinese balances of citizen needs or requirements with the growing interdependency of the world, we have to first realise that China is a communist nation through the rise of the CPC after the

civil war with other parties such as the Kuomintang (KMT)¹ ended in 1949, also known as the Chinese National Revolution. The CPC rose through years of hardship in the early 1900's by suppression by the KMT's First United Front which led to the CPC forming of the National Revolution Army to fight for the control of mainland China and one memorable event that is remembered in recent Chinese history is the Shanghai Massacre of 1927². This was when communist forces tried to enter Guomindang and were easily put down by the KMT where over 100 communist forces died.

The PRC is a non-bloc nation unlike the United States (U.S.) for example which is hegemonic in nature just as the Soviet Union was during its rule. The CPC ruling the PRC since 1949 is in a search for international superpower status balanced with its foreign policy of Panchsheel or "Five Principles of Co-Existence" which include non-interference in other countries internal matters³. However, it would like to demonstrate to the world that it is a superpower economically and militarily. To this effect, it already holds a permanent seat on the United Nations (U.N.) Security Council with the power to wield vetoes on important issues which face the world. It is important to observe that the PRC prefers to vote with Russia at the Security Council as it does not like to veto matters alone in the way Russia can stand alone at the U.N. on matters. Thus, the PRC searches for a balance considering its political, economic, and military goals.

Some economists have estimated the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of China at around \$16.2 Trillion USD while nearly all agree that it is over \$10 Trillion USD in which the purchasing price of the Yuen has also gone up with 6 Yuen equivalent to 1 USD⁴. The new BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa) Development Bank with full capital in USD is seen to be as an emerging threat to the USD as a main trading currency in the world with its combined GDP with the Bretton-Woods system was abolished in the 1970's.⁵ This is because it has the capability of dumping and controlling the dollar via its foreign exchange reserves while conducting international trade in local currencies which was recently agreed upon by Russia and India while a similar agreement is being worked out with China⁶. In response to U.S. sanctions, Russia has recently started to dump the dollar to work towards this end⁷.

Just last year in 2013, the PRC was the world's number one exporter with its number one client being the U.S. with \$369.1 Billion USD or 16.7% of all Chinese exports⁸ as electronic equipment, machinery, etc as the world's second richest nation.

There is no doubt that China is an economic superpower although some economists expect India to surpass China by 2025⁹ and certainly by 2050¹⁰. It recently surpassed the U.S. as the world's largest economy¹¹. However, with the BRICS alliance aiming to challenge the

World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) citing lack of their geopolitical interests being represented as demonstrated by voting power statistics in the chart, there is a need for China to strike a balance between remaining an economic superpower while taking up the challenge of the dollar, both which go hand in hand. In addition, there are only 9 or so nations, all western, making benefits from international investments by the IMF¹².

One way this can be done is to increase prices of all products exported to the U.S. while keeping domestic prices intact. This will force the U.S. to either continue to buy products from China and take the heat for inflation and give advantage to China in buying out the dollar by increasing U.S. national debt or have the U.S. face extinction of the dollar as the main trading currency internationally. The BRICS alliance has the capability to do this as there is mutual political support for this initiative which is why the BRICS Development Bank was established in the first place. The balance between showing the economic might of China while keeping its economy functioning can be struck in this way¹³.

Second, China may choose to limit its exports to BRICS nations and keep both exports and imports down. This would not necessarily reduce China's capability as an economic powerhouse because the USD would face heavy inflation as the U.S. will have to find a new trading partner outside BRICS which will likely sell at a much higher price leaving the Yuen-Dollar ration intact. This is in line with a similar policy which India has in that China has the capability to be self-reliant while being interconnected with BRICS. Thus, there are various options for China to undertake to project itself as a higher superpower beyond the U.S. as it holds strategic control on the USD and be interconnected with the rest of the world through the BRICS alliance at the same time.

These same strategies can be implemented by other members of the BRICS alliance such as India as well. The BRICS Development Bank was not developed for China alone although it may have a marginal share in terms of the trillions of dollars which require to be liquidated. It is no secret that Russia and the U.S. continually spar in various areas of the world leading to sanctions on each other. Just recently, the Ukraine and the Crimea issue caused to U.S. putting sanctions on high ranking Russian leaders and vice versa; Russia has put sanctions on American products in trade. Therefore, overriding the IMF and World Bank will counter the American Wolfowitz Doctrine which basically states that the U.S. must exterminate any rivals including Russia and China¹⁴. From the Wolfowitz Doctrine :

“Our first objective is to prevent the re-emergence of a new rival, either on the territory of the former Soviet Union or elsewhere, that poses a threat on the order of that posed formerly by the Soviet Union. This is a dominant consideration underlying the new regional defense strategy and requires that we endeavor to prevent any hostile power from dominating a region whose resources would, under consolidated control, be sufficient to generate global power.”

The BRICS Development Bank will of course be a global power and follow the Russian sanctions as Russia is a member of the bank leaving a strategic option for all members to gain political leverage in the international political economy. South Africa in many ways has acted as an agent of Russia in protesting sanctions¹⁵ against other Non-Aligned Movement (NAM) members and partners of Russia and can be strategic to offer political negotiations towards this end. The BRICS countries represent world’s 43% population, 18% of global trade, and attracts 53% of global financial capital¹⁶. U.S. Commerce Secretary Penny Pritzker, who is a member of the Pritzker family which owns the Hyatt hotel chain commented on the bank with regards to playing a role towards a balanced Asia; *“I see a rebalanced Asia and India has an important role to play there and I think balance is something that is in all*

our interests” but at the same time expressing disappointment with India’s policies at the World Trade Organization (WTO)¹⁷.

There are concerns that by adding the leverage of India to this bank, only China will benefit as it has tried to woo India into the Sino-centric Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) for full membership in return for Indian support¹⁸. In addition, the main contributor to the “Contingency Currency Pool” helping forestall short-term liquidity was China. However, India will have many strategic options with supporting the Chinese market indirectly or directly through BRICS as well as the South Asia Association Regional Cooperation (SAARC) Development Bank¹⁹ such as reviewing “shared sovereignty” models over Tibet (railways between China-India through Tibet have already been started²⁰), equal shares in the global market, serving as a hub for negotiations to keep from the marginalization of not just India but other allies, etc. To offer support towards this end, the BRICS Global Development Bank is headquartered in Shanghai but is headed by an Indian President who is in charge of making the executive decisions of the organisation. A similar strategy of using strength of comparative and absolute advantage where applicable was used by The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the latest Israeli-Gaza conflict by increasing oil export prices by the barrel to force Israel into temporary ceasefire as well as start an international investigation into Israel at the U.N. Human Rights Council and this dates back to 1973 when His Majesty King Faisal of Saudi Arabia refused to lift the oil embargo ban to the U.S. until the Arab-Israeli war was over despite U.S. threats to bomb the oilfields²¹.

Strategically, the PRC is in search of a balance with these new found economic strategies derived from the BRICS Development Bank and the SCO. Traditionally, China has been close to other communist nations such as North Korea but not the Union of Soviet Republics (USSR) as there were differences between the doctrines of Marxism-Maoism and Marxism-Leninism. To this day, China upholds Maoism demanding the need for constant revolution.

Mongolia played a crucial role in this area as it was originally tilted towards the USSR due to its communist policies but with the fall of the Berlin Wall and the rise of democracy in Mongolia, it has been a large destination for Chinese investors²² looking for a trade hub. The rise of the Chinese military in the region has also contributed to seeking a balance between showing the dominance of its growth but keeping good relations with the west for trade purposes. This is especially important to

international relations as the U.S Pentagon has stated it looks to relocate 60% of its Navy to the Pacific by 2020²³.

Thus, the PRC has built up its presence in the East China Sea due to its proximity with North Korea despite opposition from Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan which the PRC sees as a part of China which needs to be re-integrated into the mainland. However, the three mentioned nations are hubs for U.S. military activity with a large amount of arms sales and personnel deployed on the ground there²⁴. In addition, there are disputes in the South China Sea with the Philippines which is

aligned with the U.S. and other nations in the Association For South East Asian Nations (ASEAN) bloc²⁵.

Looking to the west of the nation, it is not particularly positive for the PRC as there are Islamic fundamentalists and militants which claim to represent the ethnic Uyghur population infiltrating the Xinjiang province seeking a separate nation of East Turkestan. Some of the proscribed organisations which have carried out attacks in Xinjiang are the East Turkestan Islamic Movement (ETIM)²⁶, East Turkestan Liberation Organisation(ETLO)²⁷, United Revolutionary Front For East Turkestan (URFET)²⁸, and Uyghur Liberation Organisation (ULO)²⁹. Many of these groups have been trained in nearby nations such as Afghanistan and Pakistan by other militant groups including the Terikh-e-Taliban (TTP)³⁰.

However, Pakistan being an deep ally of China in issues such as nuclear trade and support for issues at the U.N., has launched operations to protect Chinese sovereignty³¹.

China is easily cornered in this way as shown on the map (airplanes represent U.S. Military Bases) as its feuds with other nations can carry over as alliances if a military conflict arises between the nations or with the west. The PRC would be best to try to win friends in nearby nations such as the mentioned South Korea, Japan, and Taiwan to protect its eastern shores of the East Chinese and South Chinese Seas as it has been doing. A balance for the PRC can be struck if it opens doors for cooperation with Russia and India as well. India maintains very close ties to the ASEAN nations as Myanmar, once Burma, used to be part of the British Empire of India. It also holds good relations with other ASEAN nations such as Thailand as well as Vietnam in conducting nuclear and defence trade with India.

The Vietnam War is also of relevance where Chinese communist funded militants were able to defeat U.S. forces in the deep jungles of Vietnam where complex tunnels such as the ones North Korea maintains in the zero-zone with South Korea had and guerilla warfare techniques proved difficulty for the U.S. which withdrew with heavy casualties with

its first post-WWII expedition in Eastern Asia. A scenario unfolding like that is very unlikely due to the new dispute resolve mechanisms the ASEAN nations maintain with the PRC including those of sovereignty. India can play a role if it so chooses.

This is because one must realise the importance of India's geographic position as Lord Curzon of Kedleston, former Viceroy of India during the British Raj stated in his 1909 essay "The Place of India in the Empire"³² that India is the greatest power in Asia with an army of efficiency available in a moment's notice influencing the destinies of Iran and Afghanistan to the west while commanding the Indian Ocean routes to Australia and South Chinese Sea so it may exert pressure on China with regards to Tibet in many ways :

"It is obvious, indeed, that the master of India, must, under modern conditions, be the greatest power in the Asiatic Continent, and therefore, it may be added, in the world. The central position of India, its magnificent resources, its teeming multitude of men, its great trading harbors, its reserve of military strength, supplying an army always in a high state of efficiency and capable of being hurled at a moment's notice upon any given point either of Asia and Africa- all there are assets of precious values. On the west, India must exercise a predominant influence over the destinies of Persia and Afghanistan; on the north, it can veto any rival in Tibet; on the north-east and east, it can exert great pressure upon China, and it is one of the guardians of the autonomous existence of Siam. On the high seas it commands the routes to Australia and the China Sea."

Therefore, it would be in the political and military Chinese interests to align itself with India closer as the U.S. adds pressure. However, China has an edge economically with the alliance that BRICS provides and can prove advantageous for other nations in the alliance as well due to large scale joint investments in Africa. In this way, the PRC is in more search of a balance militarily than anything else which can only be provided as it chooses to cooperate with its immediate neighbors rather than feuding over territory.

III. Internal Dynamics Impacting China's Regional Policies

The Chinese government selects only a handful of citizens to participate in government related affairs and a very marginal amount out of the 1.4+ billion population to attend the national reputed Central Party School of the CPC. Subscribing to the basics of Marxism combined with the Maoist schools of thoughts, China has been able to give a basic medium to its citizens as the poverty rate was only at 7% in

2012³³ compared to the 16% poverty rate the U.S. had in 2012 according to the U.S. Census Bureau³⁴; less than half of the world superpower. Contrary to most democratic or republic nations, Maoism stresses the need for continuous revolution as previously mentioned. Thus, China follows this fundamental principle in relation to regional policies as this may be one of main factors. However there are some other internal factors which affect the regional policies of China such as³⁵

1. Energy demands
2. Ethnic tensions
3. Shifting of power from centre to provinces

Total energy consumption in China by type, 2011

eia Note: Numbers may not add due to rounding. Source: U.S. Energy Information Administration *International Energy Statistics*.

Energy Demands

The PRC is a nuclear nation but is the world’s largest fossil fuel user and cannot meet its energy demands domestically approximately 300 MTCE (Metric Tons Carbon Equivalent) of energy are imported with total usage approximately 2900 MTCE³⁶. Coal accounts for 69% of total energy use in 2011³⁷ and as a result of this, the PRC has become the world’s largest emitter of carbon dioxide (CO₂) with over 8,715 million metric tons. This number may have decreased as the PRC has increased usage of hydro-energy sources and nuclear-energy sources by 10%³⁸

China's crude oil imports by source, 2013

Source: FACTS Global Energy, Global Trade Information Services.

since then but the usage of coal is a major factor influencing regional policy. Being a coal dependent nation, we look at the largest imports of coal since China cannot produce enough energy, coal or otherwise, to supply its demand.

It is important to point out China has large oil fields in the Tarim Basin in Xinjiang Province, Daqing in the northeast Heilongjiang Province, Jilin in the Jilin Province, Liaohe in the Liaoning Province, Shenli in the Jiangsu Province, offshore oil fields, etc. While one might think that Mongolia would be a key exporter of coal due to its availability, friendly ties with China, friendly foreign investor policies allowing 100% foreign direct investment (FDI) into the energy sector, and with many simplified and new incentives derived from the “Mongolian Foreign Investment Law (2013)”, this not the case. However, 89% of all Mongolian exports are to China³⁹ and 20.4% of coal imports⁴⁰ are from Mongolia with the rest of Mongolian exports being minerals and raw materials. The majority of Chinese coal imports to support the energy are from Indonesia, Vietnam, Australia, and Russia⁴¹.

China LNG import sources, 2012

Source: FACTS Global Energy. Others: Oman, Algeria.

Indonesia, 13% from Malaysia, etc. The largest energy corporation in the PRC conducting this business is the China National Petroleum Corporation and its strategy has been to diversify Middle Eastern oil imports with natural gas imports from other nations as well as signing

loan-for-energy deals with many nations. Thus, Chinese regional policies with regards to the energy sector are based on a supply and demand of coal, oil, natural gas, and other natural resources. With Australia being a large exporter of coal, regional policies of importing coal have reduced although Mongolia has expressed to be a larger partner in this area⁴². The large imports of oil from Angola and other commodities such as fertilizers, iron/steel, wood, etc from Africa has also helped the PRC build good relations with African nations such as South Africa and Sudan as beyond its imports, the PRC invests heavily into the development of many African nations as there is even a Chinese-African Fund (CAD) which has invested \$75 Billion USD into Africa⁴³.

The PRC's cooperation with ASEAN through Vietnam and Indonesia in this area has been a factor in keeping trade relations with Southeast Asia in good shape despite political differences. This has been both good and bad for China as it has feuds with the various oil fields in the South Chinese Sea so it will not have to depend on these nations as it holds approximately 900 trillion cubic feet of natural gas⁴⁴ according to the World Bank. There are many occurrences of anti-Chinese protests in Vietnam and Philippines due to Chinese claims over these oil rich zones and this has carried over into the PRC's regional policy when dealing with these nations. Most recently, China has stated it has the right to build whatever it would like in the South China Sea⁴⁵.

Thus, the regional policy of the PRC has been to look beyond traditional neighboring nations in the energy sector and beyond due to the indifferences they have and build relations with non-traditional partners such as nations in Australia, in the Middle East such as Saudi Arabia, or in Africa such as Angola. With the indifferences between China and the ASEAN nations and other neighbors straightened out, China could be a much larger superpower but there is a refusal for many nations to be a Chinese satellite state.

Ethnic Tensions

We must look at ethnic tensions within the PRC to understand the influencing of regional policies. There are over 10 ethno-linguistic groups which maintain their own languages and tradition with the largest being the Han Chinese which represent 91% of the population⁴⁶. The PRC officially recognises 56 ethnic groups with the Zhuang (1.27% of population) and Hui (0.79% of population) after the majority 1.2+ billion Han population⁴⁷.

The longstanding issue of Tibet is well known to the international community as People's Liberation Army (PLA) troops invaded an independent Tibet in 1950⁴⁸ forcing a surrender and where the PRC and Tibetan government signed a 17 point agreement in May of 1951. The 17 point agreement has been at the center of debate between the Tibetans, now represented by the Tibetan government-in-exile and the PRC as duress has been claimed in signing the agreement on the side of Tibet is alleged as there were over 40,000 PLA troops in Tibet, the threat of immediate capture of Lhasa, and the threat of genocide⁴⁹. Under the "1969 Vienna Convention On The Law Of Treaties"⁵⁰, Article 51 and 52 provide that if an treaty was signed by the threat of force, it is invalid considering the principles of international law embodied in the U.N. Charter⁵¹, specifically Article 2 (5) of the U.N. Charter. This coupled with the numerous alleged human rights violations in Tibet⁵² forms the basis for the Tibetan government-in-exile to request their land back and also causes issues for China in regional policy with India as that is where H.H. Dalai Lama and the Tibetan government-in-exile are based out of. India has long requested China to address the situation in Tibet with regards to human rights but has adhered to the "One China Policy". Therefore, the Tibetan situation has affected ties regionally with India and internationally with western nations who have sympathy with H.H. Dalai Lama. PRC policy has also extended to Sri Lanka to counter India in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR) according to former Indian Intelligence Corps Head Col. Hariharan as nearly \$14 Billion USD is aimed to be invested in Sri Lanka and the trilateral relationship between India, the PRC, and Sri Lanka remains fragile unless India and China build better relations⁵³.

As previously mentioned, the Uyghur population in the PRC has caused controversy as many Islamic militant groups are trying to establish a separate state. This has affected China's regional policy as more cooperation with its immediate neighbors have been deepened such as Afghanistan and Pakistan where China invests billions of dollars⁵⁴ that the militants are using as a training ground and launch pad for their operations. The Chinese government has received harsh criticism from the Islamic community for what they have called "repression of Uyghurs"⁵⁵ due to regular curfews, military outposts, attacks on civilian populations, banning beards⁵⁶, and other human rights violations that disturb normal life. On the other hand, other Islamic communities and clerics within the Xinjiang Province of the Uyghurs have supported China's actions against terrorism⁵⁷. Therefore, China is in a balancing acts with its neighbors due to internal ethnic tensions with Islamic militants.

The Han population of China is the majority of the ruling elite and although this has not affected regional policies, it dictates the positions handed out in the CPC. On the other hand, the PRC has disputes with North Korea despite its Korean population as well as its support against western dominance in the region. This is because China has voted against North Korea at the U.N. Security Council in its nuclear tests⁵⁸ which has led to North Korea calling China its “enemy”. Relations with South Korea are much more favourable as it seeks to form alliances against Japan and the west⁵⁹. Regional policies towards Japan are generally hostile because there are no ethnic groups in the PRC which have proximity to the “Ethnic Japanese” which constitute their own ethnicity⁶⁰ as well as to counter western influence as the U.S. has set up bases in Japan.

Shifting Of Power From Centres To Provinces

In recent times, the PRC has had a bitter-sweet relationship with the Republic of China (ROC) or Taiwan due to historical battles between the CPC and KMT which is active in the ROC. China considers the ROC as a part of the PRC which needs to be re-integrated⁶¹ and is ready to use force to do so if the ROC declares independence. In addition, the middle class of the PRC has started the process of shifting power from the central government to the provinces due to the growing economic status of the middle class to challenge the elite⁶² known as the “G2 Generation”. In addition, public trust of the central government of the CPC has gone down due to dissident views on corruption. A good example is how the public viewed CPC leader Bo Xilai as a great crusader against corruption but then now consider him to be the “head of the mafia” in the PRC⁶³. According to the Brookings Institute, public opinion has a big role to play in shaping Chinese policy despite its communist government⁶⁴.

There have also been strong “interest groups” formed by the Chinese public to challenge the elite rulers who are more concerned with economic efficacy and GDP while the populist coalitions stand for social justice and cohesion. The Chinese public has lost trust in its leaders such as the PRC Vice President Xi Jinping and Li Keqiang and public interest groups have directly challenged the government. At the Fourth Plenary Session of the 17th Central Committee of the in 2009, the CPC acknowledged that the directives adopted “explicitly acknowledged that many problems internal to the party are exacerbated by new domestic and international circumstances, “severely weakening the Party’s creativity, unity and effectiveness.” These directives described intra-party

democracy as the “lifeblood of the Party.”⁶⁵ Several Chinese intellectuals have also called for State Armies instead of a Party Army to challenge the CPC rule. As demonstrated, there is an obvious mistrust between the PRC growing middle class with its grassroots interest groups which are considered to be very strong against the ruling elite of the CPC which has been branded as corrupt.

There has been the shift of power from the central government to the provinces despite Wu Bangguo’s 5 “No’s”; 1. No multiple party system, 2. No pluralism in ideology, 3. No checks and balances in power or bicameral parliament, 4. No federal system, 5. No privatisation. Despite these “no’s”, much of them exist today. 90% of Chinese exports come from coastal provinces where multiple strong lobbying and private interest groups have played a larger decision making role than the government. In fact, the PRC had to pass a new law to reduce the number of these “interest groups” and up the standards for auditing. Interests groups show their power through elections, judicial making, and influencing the decision making process so regional which has made the central government weaker. Therefore, the “interest groups” presiding in the coastal provinces that account for 90% of all PRC exports play a major role in regional policy by putting forth their funding and viewpoints to the leaders of the Provincial Councils instead of the central government.

IV. China’s Geopolitical Environment And Terrorism

As previously mentioned, China’s geopolitical environment has much to do with its energy needs as produces less than it requires, thereby requiring imports in the form of petroleum, natural gas, etc. The geopolitics of the PRC also focus on other resources such as gold, minerals, water, etc. All of the mentioned are intrinsically linked with Chinese trade. The trade options of the PRC are linked with international politics, economy, and military positions. The new partnerships the PRC builds with its trading partners are ties which create a seismic shift in the world’s geopolitics due to the enormous size and potential for Chinese growth.

Whenever a nation invests into the PRC or vice-versa, that nation also enjoys the benefit of formulating a regional policy due to China’s close relationships with South Korea, the ROC (Taiwan), Mongolia, etc. An example of this was the recent \$400 Billion USD deal signed between Russia and PRC energy companies CNPC and PetroChina

which are top 10 in the world⁶⁶. By signing this deal, analysts have been quick to point out that Russia is now looking east rather than worrying about western sanctions on supply contracts to European nations or competing with Ukraine. This also is helping establishing an internal architecture within the BRICS nations when one member trades with the other as trades are done in local currency so the use of the dollar as international trade currency also reduces or a new “BRICS Currency” as the Euro was introduced. The PRC’s position in this sense helps nations escape western trade sanctions as the PRC and its partners are trade partners of all nations, regardless of their international political standing.

This has been more relevant with the U.S. Pentagon stating that over 60% of its naval assets will be moved toward the Asia-Pacific region and the U.S. is looking for partners in Asia. Despite U.S. Secretary of Defense Hagel stating that the U.S. is not picking between India and China in all issues, it is clear that the U.S. views India as a partner with greater potential and the U.S. aims to “contain” Chinese growth and expansion. The U.S. currently has

large influence over the second largest exporter in Afghanistan of rare earth metals as the PRC is number one at 97% and by doing so, adopts the position that it is making the world less reliant on the PRC as many countries would rather do business with the U.S.⁶⁷. The U.S. is also seeking to deepen relation with the ASEAN and South-Eastern Asian nations even though there are no U.S. military bases there. The map shows the U.S. influence in the region and most of it is to the west where the U.S. maintains bases in Afghanistan and Tajikistan but where Iran and other nations counter this. Some have argued U.S. relationships with Japan will help counter Chinese-Japanese tensions in the region as well⁶⁸.

To counter U.S. strategy towards the PRC, it has built excellent relationships with African nations with the China-African Development Fund. More importantly, it has also built closer relationships with nations that are proximal due to mutual trade interests. For example, Pakistan is known as an “all weather” friend of the PRC where mutual military exchanges including nuclear technology, occur. The PRC also maintains good relations with Nepal despite its internal changes from a Kingdom or communist nation to a more democratic nation. Then, looking at the ASEAN bloc where China has its fair share of disputes economically but militarily, Chinese ships cruise the trading lanes of the South China Sea before reaching the Indian Ocean where Sri Lanka is a friendly partner and has let the PRC build bases there. Sri Lanka’s deep relationship also came with trade and investment such as Pakistan as well as mutual interests to put a check on Indian influence in the region. For the regional superpower in the Indian Ocean, this has been seen as a threat to some extent as India has tried to outbid Chinese investors in Sri Lanka but it is clear that Sri Lanka has fallen under the PRC’s influence as it is the number one investor in Sri Lanka.

With these improved geopolitical realities comes the negatives as well, namely; terrorism. As previously mentioned, the Islamic Uyghur population in the Xinjiang Province has been at the centre of the spotlight of terrorism in the PRC. The multiple fundamentalist Islamic groups fighting for a separate State of East Turkmenistan receive much training in nearby Afghanistan and Pakistan where terrorism from the Taliban is vast. The PRC has tried to reduce this via cooperation with the government but to no avail as the terror groups are viewing China’s rise as a threat to whatever power they may maintain in the area⁶⁹. Cooperation with western nations has irked them even further. It is also widely regarded that the PLA has

overstepped its boundaries in these Counter-Insurgent Operations (COIN)⁷⁰ by infringing on basic human rights by imposing regular curfews, military outposts, attacks on civilian populations, banning beards, etc. The PRC is signatory to the non-binding Universal Declaration Of Human Rights (UDHR) and legally binding International Covenant On Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) together known as the “International Bill of Human Rights”.

Terrorism in the PRC is limited to the Xinjiang region in western China while only non-traditional security threats such as political activism can be seen in other areas such as Tibet or in the ROC which the PRC considers an integral part of China which needs to be re-integrated into the PRC. However, there was Tibetan militancy against the PRC in the late 1960’s which H.H. Dalai Lama acknowledged that certain Tibetan groups received around \$1.7 Million USD yearly from the U.S. Central Intelligence Agency (CIA)⁷¹. Today’s focus on the several fundamentalist Islamic groups seeking an independent State of East Turkmenistan by separating the Xinjiang Province has found very little political support with regular governments.

Like most fundamental Islamic groups, the ETIM (East Turkmenistan Islamic Movement) has links with the global Islamic terror group of Al Qaeda as well as the Taliban in Afghanistan and receive training in the lawless region between Pakistan and Afghanistan known as the FATA (Federal Administered Tribal Areas)⁷². The *modus operandi* of the ETIM has been bombings in civilian areas in the Xinjiang Province with the most recent attack on a railway station killing 3 civilians and injuring 79 others⁷³. Some of the more notorious and famous ETIM attacks against Chinese nationals was in 2007 when the ETIM opened fire on Chinese civilians travelling in Pakistan’s Baluchistan Province. The ETIM has also tried to terrorise out of its original area as in 2010; the ETIM attempted bombings in Norway but thanks to the swift intelligence services of the European Union, the bombs were defused before killing anyone⁷⁴. Analysts have pointed out *raison d’etre* of these attempted bombings in the west could be linked with providing Al Qaeda support in return for their assistance to the ETIM as well as retaliation against the United States for supporting the “One China Policy”.

The geopolitical situation in the PRC combined with terrorism makes it an easy target from the western borders but as the United States aims to encircle China to contain its growth, it is yet to be

determined how much influence the bases in the ASEAN and in the nations of the North Chinese Sea will assist in this process.

V. Non-Traditional Security Threats In China

Many will argue that non-traditional security threats comes from the domestic policies of the PRC itself as citizens in Tibet self-immolate themselves and protest in other ways to seek equality in regards to practice of religion and other human rights. The PRC maintains a high number of troops in the TAR and Xinjiang Province leading to non-traditional security threats in the form of:

1. Climate change
2. Issues related with the regulation of the internet.
3. The government’s ability to cooperate with the international community.
4. The ability of the government to meet the needs of its citizens.

The policies of the PRC are developed around these main areas of non-traditional threats which make them important to examine individually. Of course, some are mutually shared with other nations such as the issue of climate change or the ability of the government to meet the

needs of its citizens but some are exclusive to the PRC such as internet and media control.

First, we examine the overlooked area of climate change which has been proven time and again by scientists. The PRC has admitted that the government is ill prepared to deal with the effects of climate change within its borders due

to the large population and complex infrastructure⁷⁵. This mainly has to do with the fact that much of the PRC’s natural resources may be used up which puts its policies of self-reliance in question, especially in the agricultural area as nearly 45% of agriculture land in the PRC is irrigated⁷⁶. It is estimated that the PRC is experiencing a decline of rainfall at the rate of 20/60 mm per decade creating large droughts for both residents and farmers. Scientists predict this will continue at the rate of 2% to 3% decrease up to 2020 and 5% to 7% up to 2050. This has practical meanings for the average households in the PRC as adhering to the Ricardian Model, it is estimated that an increase of 1 Degree Celsius creates a downfall of \$10 USD per hectare and an increase of rain by

1mm per year causes a profit of \$15 USD per hectare for the farmer. This has been confirmed by the government of the PRC itself as it has reported that there has and will continue to be increases in temperature⁷⁷. This creates a non-traditional threat and requirement for change in the internal policies of agriculture as the government has concluded that by 2050, farmers will have to rise to higher levels of land to farm due to mitigate climate change. There is also the issue of a “Shirking Shanghai” due to rising seawaters as it is estimated that a sea rise level of 60 cm by 2050 will destroy Shanghai’s economic growth which is so vital for the PRC as it sees foreign investors⁷⁸.

Second, there is a new age threat of “cyber war” and although no such big conflict has taken place, the PRC is a target due to its censoring of the internet as hackers as well as governments alike try to do what cannot be done while gaining information on the other party. The PRC sees overuse of the internet as a health problem and has even set up centres to deal with “internet addiction”⁷⁹. This also poses an internal security threat for the PRC as citizens eager to learn about what is happening in the world beyond their censored view of the world may be potential “cyber terrorists” in hacking government servers. In fact, early last year, the PRC was hit by what it termed “the largest ever hack” as all government domains with a “.cn” extension and 32% internet usage was down for two hours in a nation which has double the internet amount users of the United States⁸⁰. To make things worse between the U.S. and China, both have accused each other of hacking and intelligence snooping with solid evidence. For one, the U.S. claims that PLA Unit 61938 has spied on U.S. servers for the purpose of seeking information on corporate activities in the U.S.⁸¹ On the other hand, the PRC has claimed that the U.S. is hacking its government servers with the motive of stealing secret military information⁸² This non-traditional security threat is very important for the PRC to address as its policy of censorship may be at the centre of all the calamity surrounding the secrecy of the PRC internet world.

The ability of the PRC to create relations with foreign nations has been somewhat limited due to western nations who seek to contain Chinese growth. However, it has excelled in areas such as Africa. This is exhibited as China has yet to forge solid relationships with other permanent superpowers of the United Nations Security Council even on mutually beneficial interests such as solving the political instability in the resource rich Arab world or piracy in the Sea of Aden. Much can be attributed to the reason the PRC remains the last superpower which is communist. The European Union had been seen a large market for China but

nevertheless; it has had its fair share of troubles with the PRC as arms embargoes and trade sanctions imposed in the early 2000's⁸³. The U.S. relationship with the PRC is much relative to the "interest groups" detailed earlier in this article. The Republican Party of the U.S. has criticised the U.S. President's administration on not taking a stronger stand on limiting the growth of these interest groups or take the lead by investing in the interest groups to maintain a stake in the governance of the CPC as the interest groups are very powerful in the government⁸⁴. In addition, the U.S. remains one of the PRC's largest destination for trade and there are tensions on the U.S. relationship or views with Taiwan. For this reason, the U.S. relationship with the PRC has been economic rather than strategic despite the plans. Russia and India have maintained good relations with the PRC but both understand limits to this relationship as the Indo-Russian relationship is the governing power in Asia. The troubled relationships with superpowers has greatly limited its potential for growth as all other world superpowers aim to reduce its expansion.

Last but not least, there is the issue of the PRC meeting the needs of its own citizens which is at risk due various reasons; inability to forge relations with other superpowers for trade, internal political activism, climate change, etc. The goal of self-reliance or (*zi li geng sheng*) has long been a goal for the PRC. Many have argued that after the market reforms of the PRC following the abolishment of the Bretton-Woods economic system by the IMF in the 1970's, self-reliance was achieved. However, issues such as nuclear proliferation along with using technology to combat climate change has affected the rulers of the PRC⁸⁵. Regarding the prior, many nations would like to see the PRC to relinquish or reduce its nuclear arsenal so trade relations, thus placing a burden on internal growth of the nation. Regarding the former, the reliance of obtaining new technology from the west or Russia places the PRC at a disadvantage along with its energy dependency on foreign nations. Due to these reasons, the fact that the PRC is dependent on the international community which it has problems with regards to foreign relations, poses in non-traditional security threat for the stability of the nation.

VI. Governance In China

The government in the PRC is run by the Communist Party of China (CPC) as previously mentioned and the procedure for getting into a government position is highly selective as one must go to the training school of the CPC; the Central Party School of the CPC. With a Maoist-Marxist government in place, there is a Council of Ministers with a rotating chairman selected by the most powerful body in the PRC; the

Central Politburo Standing Committee of the Communist Party of China (PSC). The Chairman or Secretary-General of the PRC is the *de-facto* Head of State of the PRC who has a term of 5 years by virtue of

Article 79 of the PRC Constitution⁸⁶ and the person who holds that position currently is the Hon'ble Mr. Xi Jinping. The government of the PRC holds multiple "National

Councils" for the rest of the bodies such as the legislative branch under the National People's Congress, the executive branch or the State Council, the judicial branch of the Supreme People's Court, and military branch or the Central Military Commission.

As Maoism preaches constant revolution, there is a constant need for revolution and change which according to Ma Licheng, former Senior Editorials Editor at the *People's Daily* poses the biggest threat to China as normal citizens have growing dissident of their current status quo⁸⁷. To this end, the Head of State, Hon'ble Mr. Xi Jinping has tried to keep the people's aspirations in mind by stating "revolution" is occurring in the military sectors of government⁸⁸ via new technology, new departments, new operational management, etc and the PRC has also opened a new division under the Central Military Commission which controls the PLA; the National Security Council (NSC) which coordinates national security policy⁸⁹.

A new shift in the national security policy of the PRC has to engage with neighboring superpower Russia⁹⁰ more often by reviving the arms trade⁹¹ as well as conducting cooperation on joint drills⁹², etc.

In the area of defence, China has become a large arms exporter, number four in the world⁹³, and already has a very large nuclear arsenal built up. The Chairman of the Central Military Commission is also the

Secretary-General of the Central Politburo Standing Committee; Hon'ble Mr. Xi Jinping. The PLA is a "banned organisation" in neighboring India and any member of the PLA can be prosecuted under Prevention of Terrorism (PTA) laws in India. The PLA also makes intrusions into Indian territory or what it considers its own with regards to the Arunachal Pradesh state of India but there have been recent meetings between the armies as well as leaders of the nations to come to an agreement about this issue. The PLA functions under the authority of the Central Military Commission where human rights activists have complained of their violations of human rights in the Tibetan Autonomous Region.⁹⁴ It is important to mention the Chinese intelligence agency of the Ministry of State Security (MSS) which even operates out of the ROC and has succeeded in penetrating the United States Central Intelligence Agencies (CIA) on several occasions. All MSS personnel are trained at the University of International Relations⁹⁵.

Next is the executive council of the PRC which is the Central Politburo Standing Committee of the Communist Party of China or PSC as mentioned previously in this article. The Chairman of the PSC is the Head of State of the PRC. There is also a Vice President and just like the President, he or she may not serve more than two consecutive terms. The State Council serves as the Council of Ministers in the classic communist fashion and drafts bills and laws to be sent to the legislative branch; the National People's Congress (NPC) for approval. The State Council also maintains four Vice Premiers and five State Councilors where one is the State Council's Secretary-General. In addition, the People's Bank of China which is the PRC's Central Bank, is considered part of the State Council where the Council has control over printing notes, etc⁹⁶. The role of the PRC Premier or President is generally tough position due to the

scrutiny of the international community of the PRC with regards to human rights, containing growth and expansion, ability to meet foreign dignitaries, etc but one of immense powers as the PRC is a growing superpower in the world.

The legislative branch of the PRC is what might be the most interesting as it functions similar to a democratic parliament and sometimes has even more power than a western parliament would. The National People's Congress or NPC maintains around 3000 members elected by the representative electoral system where the ROC and special economic zones such as Hong Kong and Macau have their own delegations. Ethnic minorities such as Tibetans are also represented but there is the complaint that they are not given the voice that they need to make effective changes for governance of the TAR. The NPC maintains a Presidium⁹⁷ consisted of 178 members of all parties; both communist and non-communist alike as well members from the All-China Federation of Industry and Commerce. The Presidium has a very important role as it elects the President and Vice President of the PRC, Vice Chairman and Secretary-General of the Standing Committee of the NPC, the Chairman of the Central Military Commission, and the President of the Supreme People's Court; the PRC's judiciary. The NPC has also rejected many bills of the executive branch such as bills on maritime safety, fuel tax bills⁹⁸, and food safety bills⁹⁹. In this way, there is a certain amount of democracy within the NPC.

The judiciary of the PRC is based on the British and Portuguese system of dividing the branches of the judiciary into sections of importance. The most powerful court is known as the Supreme People's Court (SPC); the highest judicial body in the nation which is the court of last resort for the entire nation and deals with matters of public law. The Local People's Courts deal with normal civil and criminal cases and is split into three parts according to the *Organic Law Of The People's Courts*; the Basic People's Courts, the Intermediate People's Courts, and the High People's Courts. According to the *Organic Law Of The People's Courts*, the Basic People's Courts handle civil and criminal cases that are not of importance to make it to trial, the Intermediate Courts handle issues which are prosecuted or where civil litigation is filed, and the High People's Courts handles cases at a provincial level leaving the national cases to the SPC. In this way, the judiciary system of the PRC is very similar to the British legal system of common law and partitioning of the legal system.

The governance of the PRC is a much tedious task as it is one which can be scrutinised by critics. The communist government is responsible for the welfare and allegiance of over 1.4+ billion people to the CPC which is done through various ministries and control over the media as well. At the end of the day, the CPC requires full support from its citizens for it to stay in power.

VII. Conclusion

The internal dynamics of the PRC are very important to understand as it plays a key role in how, what, when, and where actions are taken by the CPC. There is no doubt that the foreign policy of the nation is in the hands of the power elite which are being constantly “revolutionised” by interest groups and in that way; protecting the fundamentalist Maoism philosophy. The PRC has long ways to go in terms of economic self-reliance as its energy dependency may be its shortsightedness in the long run which is why it has competed with neighbors for oil blocs in the nearby sea-lanes, etc. With that said and as mentioned in the beginning; while the past teaches us valuable lessons, the future may be approaching too quickly for China.

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10. Nontraditional Security Threats and China

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Abstract:

Because of ongoing conceptual disagreements, the types of issues considered to be nontraditional security continue to increase. This paper argues that nontraditional security issues of China should be considered as issues of national interests as its starting point. In the Chinese context, nontraditional security issues are divided into three levels: First, nontraditional security issues that are intimately linked with traditional security problems, and which involve key interests such as national sovereignty and territorial integrity; second, issues involving domestic security, which represent an important national interest; and third, issues involving the security of the individual. Different strategies and policies should be prescribed for each of these three levels of nontraditional security issues. This can also help to clarify the importance of different dimensions of nontraditional security problems from the perspective of policy makers, and help them to better appropriate and apply resources, enhancing China's ability to respond to such challenges.

Introduction

Insofar as security is concerned, nontraditional and traditional security belongs to the two integrated security categories which are basic aspects of the comprehensive security concept. Compared with the traditional security, meaning and impact of nontraditional security (NTS) is more diverse and complex.¹ Traditional security refers to some high political

and security issues in the traditional sense, such as national defence, territorial disputes, the issue of sovereignty, military situation between countries. These issues are mainly concern to nationality, country and the survival of the regime, which has always been regarded as the core of security problems. Nontraditional security refers to the traditional security issues other than safety issues.² These questions are usually defined as the so-called low-political-security issues, such as economic security, terrorism, environmental degradation, population explosion, drug trafficking, transnational organized crime, the spread of AIDS.

In addition to the above difference, nontraditional security threats are also different in the characteristics. The source of nontraditional security threats and actors are different from traditional security. Actors in the traditional security issues and sources are relatively clear, generally from interest conflicts and disputes between sovereign states, which is the result of acts of state and government, which is a typical international problem. Actors and the origin of nontraditional security issues are more diverse, and many nontraditional security threats are not directly caused by acts of State, but the results of the various activities of non-state actors. For example, the environment, population, drugs, AIDS, and related security threats such as terrorism, are the result of the behavior of many individuals and community groups.³

After the Cold War era, the theory of nontraditional security and issues become an important topic of research and policy practice. The research and analysis on the NTS concept and characteristics created strong influence on international relations, international security studies and diplomatic studies. In practice, governments paid more attention to NTS issues, dialogue and cooperation. It has created enthusiasm to generalize the phenomenon nontraditional security studies to cover national and international NTS threats. But, how China operationlize NTS theory and issues is the most imperative subject? How Chinese government effectively responding to different types of NTS challenges?

Nontraditional Security Issues and Response

From the perspective of national security, some scholars believe that the current and upcoming times China may face six major nontraditional security challenges: i) financial security, ii) environmental security, iii) information security, iv) epidemiological security, v) demographic security, vi) national separatism.⁴ At the movement China is at crucial stage of deepening financial reforms and rectifies process of financial order. The visibility and the effects of the international financial crisis have made China more conscious. According to some scholars Chinese is well aware and trying to prevent financial risks and avoid the financial crisis. It is also considered that China is still facing challenges in national sovereignty and territorial integrity which is associated with nontraditional security issues.

Moreover, based on the principle of laying equal stress on NTS issues such as, social security, national security, economic security (mainly energy security, financial security, food security), information/cyber security and three other violent issues 'religious extremism, separatism and terrorism' as the major nontraditional security threats to China in recent times. Scholars have suggested that nontraditional security issues are divided into two characteristics: First, non-state actors, which poses threat to national sovereignty and territorial integrity with direct or indirect violence; second, involves people and their security issues which are divided into economic problem, energy problems and social problem like public health, and transnational crime, and environment and ecological problem.

Reviewing overall NTS issues of China, the paper is divided into three levels: the first level is related to the core of national security interests and new threats to the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the country; the second level involves the vital interests of the state, including new threats which affects the normal functioning of society; third level refers to the human security issues with two narrow and broad understanding,

generally refers to the security of all humanity and in narrow sense refers to an individual's security. These different levels of nontraditional security issues have focused on different ways to cope these challenges.⁵ The first level is based on an integrated approach, namely, the use of military means at the same time, emphasize the role of economic, social and cultural fields; The second level is maintained through the markets and economic instruments; third level is continued to upgrade and improve the government's ability to govern and to handle crisis management.

First Level: NTS issues closely associated with traditional security

The first level of nontraditional security issues of China (which involves its core national interests) are the separatists movement in Tibet, Xinjiang and Taiwan, religious extremism, terrorism and other security issues which are threatening the sovereignty and territorial integrity of states. These three forces are remained closer, have seriously threatened national sovereignty and territorial integrity. In General, these problems have following characteristics:

Violent terrorist acts: Separatist activities often occur simultaneously with the terrorists and separatists violence. According to incomplete statistics of 1990 - 2001, the terrorist group namely East Turkestan Islamic Movement (ETIM) conducted more than 200 violent incidents such as assassination, poisoning, arson, assault, rioting and insurrection in Xinjiang province, in which 162 people were killed and more than 440 injured. Since 2008 ETIM and its sister separatist organizations began a new round of sabotage. According to independence and incomplete sources 606 people have been killed and in 31 terrorist incidents which left thousands of injured in between 2008-2014. This not only caused great losses to people's life and property, but also to the serious damage caused by the normal order and social stability.⁶

Strong political overtone: This nontraditional security issue mainly focuses on the secession and interference in normal political, economic and social process to undermining the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the state. ETIM is an example, in early 20th century parts of fanatical Xinjiang separatists and extremist religious forces attempted to establish so-called East Turkistan separatist regimes and tried to disturb the stability of the region with explosions, knife slaughtering, attacking on government property and armed forces to create problems for central government.

External involvement: This transnational nontraditional security issue often associated with drug trafficking and organized transnational crime. These sort of activities usually funded by foreign forces to manipulate and create problem within state, it provides expediency to external forces to interfere internal affairs of China. On the other hand, the interference in internal issues is also a big problem. For example: United States and European states often support Dalai Lama in various ways to manipulate internal matter and the ethnic policies of China on Tibet issue to achieve regional political ends.⁷

This level of nontraditional security issues cannot be separated from the traditional security, problems may be caused by traditional security under certain conditions which may lead to armed conflict or war. It has become more important concern of national security on basis of traditional security. On the other hand, these problems often associated with unbalanced development of politics and economy, require integrated use of military, economic, cultural and other means, in order to safeguard national unity and stability.

In the exceptional cases, nontraditional security issues also require the use of traditional instruments (such as military means) to maintain certain specific problems which are hard to define and make resemblance position with traditional and nontraditional security. China, internally has taken effective steps to deal such issues and regionally it

has actively advocated and promoted the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) to fight with three evils (terrorism, extremism and separatism) and maintain regional stability.⁸ Under the banner of SCO, member states started joint anti-terrorism military exercises to improve the capabilities of military operation at common ground to maintain regional stability and peace. In the non-military means, the ethnic separation of Xinjiang and Tibet is also being settled by economic and cultural means. Economically, special policies, projects, infrastructure and social development projects, such as dedicated funds to support and construction led to the economic development in Tibet.⁹ The decision of establishing special economic zones and reforms in taxation also promote economic development in Xinjiang. In addition, protection of national cultures, customs and religious beliefs is also an important way to safeguard national unity and ethnic solidarity. In fact, through a series of laws, customs and freedom of religious belief in Tibet, Xinjiang has been effectively respected and protected.

Second Level: NTS issues related to social development

Second level focuses on social areas of nontraditional security, various social systems of internal and external security conditions directly impacts on international security environment. Scholars compared social security with internal security, whose main function is to ensure the social system and the provision of adequate public safety which is different from traditional security. The social security threats are probably not occur between states, but more rooted in the social system and assault within the state with profound institutional and structural causes. These issues even if not directly critical for national interests, violent threats and high political implications, but if not properly solved, will lead to social unrest, disorder and chaos.

China is in a phase of rapid economic development, dependence on energy is continue to climb, oil as a strategic resource security is to

maintain social and political stability as well as the foundation of the modern life style of citizens is the social guarantee of sustainable development resources, but also affects economic development. Thus, for China, to ensure adequate and stable supply of energy is not only an economic issue, but a political issue.

The agenda of energy security includes security of supply and environmental security. Security of supply is not only concerned with conflicts between domestic supply and demand, dependence on other countries, but also associated with the country's diplomatic and military influence in resource-rich areas of the world.¹⁰ Threat to security of energy supply included energy sources of political instability, military conflicts between states, terrorist attacks, or other strategic containment and causes of supply disruptions. For example, United States is the oil-consuming country and energy security is its key interest.

On the other hand, environmental security issues that arising the course of energy use is also an important aspect of energy security. With the changing security concepts, pollution control, environmental issues (global warming and nuclear energy) impact on energy security strategy is gradually strengthening the subject. The future of global energy consumption will continue to increase, while the environment security, climate change and other issues are increasingly becoming the main concerns of world.

After 1993, China become a net oil importer and economically fast-growing state, it is now world's second-largest oil consumer and importer state. It has developed an effective energy security policy to ensure future national energy security. Currently, China's oil security mainly faces the following challenges: first, it imports around 60% oil from the Middle East, and the region is recognized as one of the most unstable parts of the world, thus it is not only huge challenge for China but also for world. Second, is facing predicament in energy transport corridor. China's four-fifths oil transport cross through the Strait of Malacca and this channel

has become the focus of some country to establish their status-quo.¹¹ So, whosoever controls the Straits of Malacca, it may curb energy channels of China. China will have to develop new energy security strategy with positive measures to meet new global heights and ensure national energy security. Third, is the adjustment of national energy policy, energy security strategy development, promotion of energy saving and environmental protection technologies.

As a responsible big country, China's energy policy should not only meet the needs of economic development, but also taking environmental factors into account to achieve sustainable economic development and harmonious development between man and nature. It pursues a strategy of peaceful development through the objective of energy security means. In the economic context of globalization and China's rising dependence on foreign oil ensure adequate oil supplies and reasonable prices is an important national interest, requires an integrated approach to maintain.

Third Level: Human security issues

As earlier mentioned, that human security mainly refers to nontraditional security issues of personal safety and health of individual citizens. Such problems normally have the following characteristics: First, sudden or unexpected: the previous two types of nontraditional security issues different and pose a long-term threat to national security, while this type of nontraditional security issues are mostly characterized as unforeseen and unexpected public incidents.¹² It is breaking out tends to respond to such events with less understanding measures within a short time, thereby causing widespread panic and insecurity. Second, uncertainty of the effects: Because of the influence of sudden and wide big losses is difficult to estimate the possible (such as casualties, damage to property, etc) as well as the eventual impact of the event. This state of insecurity could easily cause social panic, greatly affecting the normal functioning of social systems. From the perspective of current domestic studies, these problems mainly include the spread of pandemic diseases

(such as SARS events), natural disaster, food security (tainted). There is need of professionalism of the response such uncertain events. The 2003 SARS pandemic outbreak represents these characteristics. The outbreak of SARS concentrated in Guangdong (is a province of the China), it quickly spread due to insufficient mechanism of warning mechanism, and government information was not timely.¹³ Government completely failed to aware public about the severity of problem, though the number of cases was small but it created panic in the public. SARS is a completely different security issue, it is not only a direct threat to the life individuals but also concern for national economic development, social stability, and international exchanges.

According to occurred process of public emergency, the nature and mechanism is divided into natural disasters (including flood and drought disaster, meteorological disaster, earthquake, geological disaster, marine disaster and forest prairie fire), accident disaster (Enterprise security accident, traffic accident, public facilities and equipment accident, pollution and ecological damage events), and public health event (including outbreak of infectious diseases, food security, other serious effects of public health and life security of events), as well as, the events of social security (including terrorist attacks, economic security and incidents involving foreign elements).

Human security issues involved in most of the unexpected public incidents, but it does not mean that all of sudden public events are the realm of human security. If all the casualties or damage of property caused by unexpected public events considered to human security studies than the list of nontraditional security issues will have to be infinitely stretched. Human security objects should be those that are universal, integration and diffusion effects of security matters. For example, traffic accidents happen due to human error. The events themselves are not holistic and invasive characters, the normal functioning of the state and society will not come in the state of crisis

therefore these human errors should not be regarded as nontraditional security issues. While, the unexpected public events such as the spread of the infectious disease could make society and the world is in danger and likewise cause widespread insecurity, so it can be defined as human security.¹⁴ In the crisis situation states pay more attention human security and improving the ability to deal such public crisis. In Chinese case, it is using the concept of public crisis management to deal with human security issues, and it has become the main measurement of this level of nontraditional security issues.

Conclusion

Based on Chinese hierarchical analysis of nontraditional security issues, anyone can draw the following conclusions: first, the emergence of nontraditional security issues does not change the dominant position of country for maintenance of security, also did not exclude national interests; second, in the context of nontraditional security, national interest or state security are change in essential content of security and the life and property of the individual and society, have become part of national security. The rising China is more concerned about social stratification which refers to the nontraditional security issues with structural problems. In the process of social transformation, particularly, issues that affect the long-term development of the national economy. By contrast, individual security mainly affects the physical and mental health of individuals and the lives and property of emergent safety issues.

With the diversification of sources of security threats and change of security perceptions, sovereign states are facing traditional security issues that have long plagued the national security even with brand new nontraditional security threats. In Chinese case, there is not only a threat to national unity and territorial integrity, nontraditional security issues also need to have effects on various social security and individual human security issues. There is need to enhance the awareness of

strategies from the strategic level to strengthen nontraditional security studies, as well as on a practical level to strengthen national response capability that increase the level of crisis management. For classification of the nontraditional security issues and avoid threats are clearly at different levels of agenda, thus more rational allocation and the use of resources improves China's ability to address such security issues.

Meanwhile, there is a need of nontraditional security tends to maintain a sober understanding of the subject, because in political/security terms once you add unusual meaning this/that would immediately occupy a policy priority and that becomes the focus of public and media attention. Once a problem is defined as the nontraditional security issue, means that departments can be more relevant to the issue of resource allocation and decision-making power. This will encourage relevant departments tend to be controlled by unexpected events included in this area. Therefore, whether it is from search perspective or from the policy practice, it is necessary to clarify all the unexpected public incidents should not need to be regarded as nontraditional security issues. If security trends continue to develop, not only conducive to problem solving but also can be waste of resources and develop low efficiency.

Endnotes

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